

Proceedings of the 32nd North American Conference on Chinese Linguistics

(NACCL-32)

CONFERENCE
ORGANIZER

Chunsheng Yang

PROCEEDINGS
EDITOR

Kaidi Chen

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(NACCL-32)

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CONFERENCE ORGANIZER'S REMARKS
AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The 32nd North American Conference on Chinese Linguistics (NACCL-32) was originally scheduled for April 24th to 26th, 2020. The breakout of the COVID-19 pandemic in the US and the rest of the world in March 2020 has presented many unprecedented challenges and we had to make one after another tough decision regarding the schedule and modality of NACCL-32. After several rounds of online polls among the conference presenters, we decided not to cancel the conference but turn it into a virtual conference on September 18th to 20th, 2020, to ensure the safety and health of all participants. Despite all these complications, the final program included over 100 presentations and more than 300 people from all over the world registered and attended the two-and-a-half- day virtual conference.

NACCL-32 could not have been possible without all the support and assistance that I had received. First, I would like to thank my previous department head, Dr. Gustavo Nanclares, and my current department head, Dr. Jennifer Terni, who both strongly supported the conference and granted me a course release and a half TA position. Second, I would like to acknowledge the generous support from various departments and centers at UConn; they are CLAS Dean's Office, Humanities Institute, The Office of Global Affairs, The Connecticut Institute for the Brain and Cognitive Sciences, Asian and Asian American Studies Institute, Department of Linguistics, and Department of Literatures, Cultures and Languages. Third, I would want to thank my five keynote speakers, Prof. Marjorie K. M. Chan, Prof. James Huang, Prof. Nan Jiang, Professor Ming Xing, and Prof. Yi Xu, for their support of NACCL-32. Last but not the least, I would like to extend my heartfelt thanks and gratitude to my organizing committee at UConn: Prof. Nan Meng, Kaidi Chen, Shengyun Gu, Danwei Li and Juntao Li, as well as all the reviewers of NACCL abstracts. Again, thanks to all for your support and assistance in making NACCL-32 (virtual) possible and a huge success.

I would also like to thank Kaidi Chen for “squeezing” time from his busy schedule of teaching and learning to edit the proceedings of NACCL-32.

Wish everyone safe and healthy in this difficult and challenging time!

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PREFACE

The 32nd North American Conference on Chinese Linguistics (NACCL-32) was held virtually at University of Connecticut on September 18-20, 2020.

After the conference ended, the presenters were invited to submit their revised papers for publication in the Proceedings of the 32nd North American Conference on Chinese Linguistics. Forty-five of the presented papers were submitted and included in the proceedings. The papers have been divided into six parts: Part 1 contains papers on phonetics and phonology; Part 2 pertains to morphology, syntax and semantics; Part 3 is on historical linguistics; Part 4 concerns language processing and learning; Part 5 is on sociolinguistics; Part 6 deals with linguistic studies using corpus data.

The Fate of Rounded Vowels in Cantonese Varieties of the Pearl River Delta **—with a Focus on the Doumen Dialect**

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Not all of the six rounded vowel phonemes in Standard Cantonese (i.e., /u/, /o/, /ɔ/, /ɵ/, /y/, and /œ/) are retained in its dialects in the Pearl River Delta surrounding Guangzhou, China. The dialects spoken in this area also vary in the ways that they realize the rounded vowels of standard Cantonese (Zhan, 2004; Zhan & Zhang, 1987). This paper is part of a study that first seeks to describe the different realizations of the rounded vowels of standard Cantonese in 21 different varieties spoken in the Pearl River Delta, with the aim of adding to our knowledge of Cantonese dialectology. Here we specifically consider the Doumen dialect and offer an analysis of rounded vowel realization within the framework of Optimality Theory. The variation in the rankings of the proposed constraints gives rise to the difference in the realization of rounded vowels across the Pearl River dialects.

1. Introduction

Cantonese is one of the Chinese languages that are spoken in Guangdong and Guangxi provinces, Hongkong and Macau SARs, and overseas Chinese communities in countries such as Singapore and Malaysia, as well as Chinatowns in a lot of countries including the US and UK. In a lot of these communities, it is not uncommon to hear different varieties of Cantonese besides Guangzhou Cantonese (such as Taishai, Enping, and Kaiping). This paper is part of a project that focuses on the 21 Cantonese dialects spoken in Pearl River Delta, with rounded vowels as a specific focus. For the ease of description, Guangzhou Cantonese will be referred to as the “standard” variety, and others as dialects hereafter in this paper.

In Standard Cantonese, there are six rounded vowel phonemes: /u/, /o/, /ɔ/, /ɵ/, /y/, and /œ/. In the Cantonese dialects in the Pearl River Delta surrounding Guangzhou, the capital of Guangdong Province, China, unrounded vowels are in place where they are rounded in standard Cantonese. That is, roundness in the standard variety is usually lost in these dialects. This is especially true for front vowels. For example, the word 书 ‘book’ is pronounced in the Guangzhou dialect as /sy55/ but in Doumen dialect as /si33/. Alternatively, rounded vowels are sometimes substituted by another rounded vowel. For instance, in standard Cantonese, the word 两 ‘two’ is pronounced as /lœŋ13/, but in the

Shajing dialect, Bao'an district of Shenzhen, it is pronounced as /liəŋ13/ instead. By contrast, it is extremely rare for an unrounded vowel to be replaced by a rounded vowel, at least not attested in the dialects in our data. To find out the pattern of how these rounded vowels vary across dialects, this project analyzes with Optimality Theory (Prince & Smolensky, 1993) 21 Cantonese dialects in the Pearl River Delta based on data collected from literature (Qiu, Gan, & Gao, 2016; Shao & Gan, 1999; Zhan, 2004; Zhan & Zhang, 1987), in order to contribute to our knowledge of Cantonese dialectology.

This paper demonstrates our analysis with the rounded vowels in Doumen dialect as an example. It is important to note, however, that there is large variation even within the same region. That is, even the same dialect varies from town to town or from village to village in varying degrees. For example, the Doumen dialect spoken in Hushan, one of the towns of Doumen, is somewhat different from that spoken in Jing'an, another town in the district. While it would be ideal to exhaust all of these variations, given the limits on the collected data, the variety spoken in downtown Doumen represents the dialect in this analysis.

2. Rounded vowels in the Doumen dialect

2.1. Back vowels [u] and [o]

The back high rounded vowel [u] in standard Cantonese is maintained in the Doumen dialect, whether as a monophthong or diphthong, as shown in 1a-c. The back mid tense rounded vowel [o] only exists as part of the diphthong [ou] or followed by a velar consonant in both varieties, as shown in 1d-f. In both varieties, the features of the vowel [u] are [+high], [round], [back], and those of the vowel [o] are [+high], [+low], [round], [back] (the rationale for a mid vowel to have both features [+high] and [+low] will be discussed shortly in the next section). The surfacing of [u] and [o] in the Doumen dialect, then, is the result of the faithfulness constraints.

(1)

		Standard	Doumen	Gloss
a.	超	/ts ^h iu/	/ts ^h iu/	'super'
b.	妹	/mui/	/ ^m bui/	'younger sister'
c.	枯	/fu/	/k ^h u/	'to wither'
d.	草	/t ^h sou/	/t ^h ou/	'grass'
e.	桶	/t ^h oŋ/	/hoŋ/	'bucket'
f.	读	/tok/	/tok/	'to read'

2.2. Back mid lax vowel [ɔ]

The back mid lax rounded vowel [ɔ] as a monophthong in an open syllable in standard Cantonese is realized as a diphthong [uə] in the Doumen dialect, as shown in 2a and 2b. In closed syllables and the diphthong [ɔi], [ɔ] is realized as a high back vowel [u], as in 2c and 2d, except for when it is followed by a velar consonant [k] or [ŋ], as in 2e and 2f, in which [ɔ] remains unchanged.

(2)

		Standard	Doumen	Gloss
a.	多	/tɔ/	/tuə/	‘much’
b.	过	/kwɔ/	/kuə/	‘to pass’
c.	开	/hɔi/	/hui/	‘open’
d.	岸	/ŋɔŋ/	/ ^ŋ gun/	‘riverbank’
e.	凿	/tsɔk/	/tsɔk/	‘to drill’
f.	床	/t ^h sɔŋ/	/t ^h ɔŋ/	‘bed’

That begs the question of why [ɔ] stays the same in the Doumen dialect in some cases but not others. To account for the change from a monophthong [ɔ] to a diphthong [uə], two constraints are suggested in 3 and 4.

(3) RV-velar: A rounded back mid lax vowel must be followed by a velar consonant.

(4) Breaking: A single vowel in the input should correspond to a single vowel in the output.

The constraint in 3, when ranked high, would eliminate any surface form that has the vowel [ɔ] without any velar consonant following it, and the violation of that in 4 would eliminate candidates that realize a monophthong in the input as diphthongs or triphthongs in the output.

With the constraints in 3 and 4, the tableau in 5 shows how the winning candidate [tuə] is selected.

(5) /tɔ/ - [tuə] ‘much’ (2a)

/tɔ/	RV-velar	Breaking
a. [tɔ]	*!	
a b. [tuə]		*

The winning candidate 5b violates Breaking but respects RV-velar. It violates Breaking because the features of [ɔ], namely [round], [back], [+high], and [+low] are realized in a diphthong, or two vowels [u] (containing features [+high], [back], and

[round]) and [ɐ] ([+low] and [-back]). Mid vowels are viewed as having both [+high] and [+low] in this analysis, following the idea proposed in Kostakis (2016). According to this view, physical limitations in articulation would determine that the features in mid vowels must be [-high] and [-low], but perceptually, there is no such limitation, and the features [+high] and [+low] can be coalesced into one mid vowel. That is attested in Old Norse, where the front vowel [e] is realized as [ja] (realizing [+high] in [j] and [+low] in [a]), as well as in the Doumen dialect, where the front vowel [ɛ] is realized as [ia]. The losing candidate [tɔ] respects Breaking but violates RV-velar. It violates RV-velar because it retains a back mid lax rounded vowel without a velar consonant following it.

The tableau in 5 establishes the ranking in 6.

(6) RV-velar >> Breaking

The same strategy of breaking the mid vowel [ɔ] would not work for /tsək/ in 2e, because it violates Breaking and the faithful candidate /tsək/ no longer violates the higher ranked constraint RV-velar, as shown in the tableau in 7.

(7) /tsək/ - [tsək] ‘to drill’ (2e)

/tsək/	RV-velar	Breaking
☞ a. [tsək]		
b. [tsuək]		*!

In the representation of /ŋən/ as [ŋun] in the Doumen dialect, the feature [+low] is lost. For the candidate [ŋun] to be selected, the constraint that prevents the loss of [+low] must be ranked relatively low. This constraint is suggested in 8.

(8) MAX-low: if the feature [+low] is in the input, there should be a corresponding feature [+low] in the output.

Since [ŋun] is selected in the output, the constraint in 8 must be ranked lower than both RV-velar and Breaking, as shown in 9.

(9) /ŋən/ - [ŋun] ‘riverbank’ (2d)

/ŋən/	RV-velar	Breaking	MAX-low
a. [ŋən]	*!		
☞ b. [ŋun]			*
c. [ŋuən]		*!	

In 9, the faithful candidate 9a violates the dominant constraint RV-velar because the back mid lax vowel [ɔ] is not followed by a velar consonant. The other candidate 9c

respects RV-velar but violates another high-ranked constraint Breaking, because [ɔ] is realized as two vowels. The winning candidate 9b gets selected because although it violates MAX-low, it respects the two higher-ranked constraints. The tableau in 9 establishes the ranking in 10. The same ranking explains why /hɔi/ is realized as [hui] in the Doumen dialect.

(10) RV-velar >> Breaking >> MAX-low

The ranking in 10 explains why [ɯgun] is the winning candidate, but it has not explained why another potential candidate [ɯgɛn] is not selected. This candidate maintains the feature [+low] but loses [+high] from the input. For the winning candidate to be selected over this candidate, there must be a constraint that prevents the loss of [+high] and is ranked higher than MAX-low. This constraint is proposed in 11 and the ranking in 12.

(11) MAX-high: if the feature [+high] is in the input, there should be a corresponding feature [+high] in the output.

(12) MAX-high >> MAX-low

With the ranking in 12, the selection of the winning candidate [ɯgun] over [ɯgɛn] is illustrated in 13.

(13) /ŋɔn/ - [ɯgun] ‘riverbank’ (2d)

/ŋɔn/	MAX-high	MAX-low
a. [ɯgun]		*
b. [ɯgɛn]	*!	

The candidate 13b is eliminated because it violates MAX-high. It violates MAX-high in that although it maintains the feature [+low] from the input [ɔ], it loses the feature [+high]. The winning candidate 13a violates MAX-low, but it respects the higher ranked constraint MAX-high. At this point of the analysis, however, it cannot be decided whether MAX-high is ranked higher than the constraints RV-velar and Breaking or not.

2.3. Central Mid Vowel [ə]

The central mid vowel [ə] is considered to consist of features [+high], [+low], [-back], and [round]. In the standard dialect, it never stands alone in the rhyme; rather, it is either followed by the vowel [y] or a coda consonant. In the Doumen dialect, it is either realized as [ui] when combined with [y] or as the unrounded central mid vowel [ɐ], as shown in 14.

(14)

		Standard	Doumen	Gloss
a.	需	/søy/	/sui/	‘need’
b.	栗	/lət/	/lət/	‘chestnut’
c.	津	/tsən/	/tsən/	‘saliva’

The change of [øy] into [ui] needs a high ranked constraint that prevents the surfacing of both [ə] and [y] in the output. Such a constraint would prevent the coexistence of [-back] and [round] in the same vowel but would not prevent these features from being realized in separate vowels. The constraint is suggested in 15

(15) *[round][-back]: a vowel should not be both non-back and rounded.

With this constraint, the analysis of candidates for the input /søy/ is illustrated in 16.

(16) /søy/ - [sui] ‘need’ (14a)

/søy/	*[round][-back]	RV-velar	Breaking	MAX-low
a. [søy]	**!			
b. [sui]			*	

The faithful candidate 16a violates *[round][-back] twice and respects the other constraints. It violates *[round][-back] twice because both [ə] and [y] have [round] and [-back] realized in one single vowel. The winning candidate 16b violates Breaking but respects *[round][-back]. It violates breaking because the features [round] and [-back] from either [ə] or [y] are separated and realized in [u] and [i] respectively. For the winning candidate to be selected, Breaking must be ranked lower than *[round][-back], but it is unknown whether *[round][-back] is ranked higher than RV-velar, and hence the ranking in 17.

(17) *[round][-back], RV-velar >> Breaking >> MAX-low

To account for the realization of /lət/ as [lət] in the output, which drops the feature [round], the constraint that prevents the loss of [round] must be low ranked. This constraint is suggested in 18 and the ranking in 19.

(18) MAX-round: if the feature [+round] is in the input, there should be a corresponding feature [+round] in the output.

(19) *[round][-back], RV-velar >> Breaking >> MAX-low, MAX-round

This ranking would select [lɛt] over two other candidates [lɛt] and [luɛt], as shown in the tableau in (20).

(20) /lɛt/ - [lɛt] ‘chestnut’ (14b)

/lɛt/	*[round][-back]	RV-velar	Breaking	MAX-low	MAX-round
a. [lɛt]	*!				
b. [lɛt]					*
c. [luɛt]			*!		

Candidate 20a is the faithful candidate, which violates *[round][-back], in that both [round] and [-back] surface in the same vowel. Candidate 20c violates Breaking, because the feature [round] is realized in [u] and [-back] is realized in [ɐ], separating features in the same vowel input in two vowels in the output. The winning candidate 20b violates MAX-low in that [round] is lost in the surface form. Since it is ranked lower than both *[round][-back] and Breaking, the analysis arrives at the correct selection.

The ranking in 19 explains why 20b is selected over 20a and 20c, but to account for the elimination of another potential candidate [lut], there needs to be a new constraint and ranking that prefer 20b, which loses the feature [high] and [round] in the input [ɛ] but keeps [-back], over [lut], which loses [-back] but keeps [high] and [round]. A constraint is suggested in 21.

(21) Ident[±back]: if two vowel sounds are in correspondence, then they should have the same ±value for the feature [back].

For the winning candidate to be correctly chosen, the constraint in 21 must be ranked higher than both MAX-high and MAX-round. The ranking that does just that is proposed in 22.

(22) Ident[±back] >> MAX-high >> MAX-low, MAX-round

An analysis with is ranking is illustrated in 23.

(23) /lət/ - [lət] ‘chestnut’ (14b)

/lət/	Ident[±back]	MAX-high	MAX-low	MAX-round
a. [lət]		*		*
b. [lut]	*!			

Candidate 23b violates Ident[±back] because the feature [-back] in the input does not have a corresponding feature in the output. The winning candidate 23a violates MAX-high and MAX-round in that it loses both [high] and [round], but since both constraints are ranked lower than Ident[±back], it is selected.

2.4. Front High Vowel [y]

The features of front high rounded vowel [y] in standard Cantonese are defined as [-back], [high] and [round]. In the Doumen dialect, it is realized as [i], as shown in 24, consisting of features [-back] and [high], in both open and closed syllables.

(24)

		Standard	Doumen	Gloss
a.	鱼	jy	^h gi	‘fish’
b.	羽	jy	ji	‘feather’
c.	月	jyt	^h git	‘the moon’
d.	短	tyn	tin	‘short’
e.	冤	jyn	jin	‘wronged’

The ranking we currently have in 19 can account for this difference between the input and the output, as illustrated in 25.

(25) /jy/ - [ji] ‘feather’ (24b)

/jy/	*[round][-back]	RV-velar	Breaking	MAX-low	MAX-round
a. [jy]	*!				
b. [ji]					*
c. [jui]			*!		

The faithful candidate 25a violates a high-ranked constraint *[round][-back] because the features [round] and [-back] surface in the same vowel [y]. Candidate 25c respects *[round][-back] but violates Breaking, because [round] and [-back] are realized in two separate vowels [u] and [i] respectively. The winning candidate 25b violates MAX-round, but it respects both *[round][-back] and Breaking, which are ranked higher than MAX-round, and that is why it gets selected.

2.5. Front Mid Vowel [œ]

The features in the front mid rounded vowel [œ] in standard Cantonese are [-back], [+high], [+low], and [round]. It is realized as [iə] in open syllables in the Doumen dialect, as shown in 26. In closed syllables, the only two possible consonants to follow [œ] in standard Cantonese are velar consonants [ŋ] and [k] and it is realized as [iɔ] in the Doumen dialect.

(26)

		Standard	Doumen	Gloss
a.	靴	hœ	hiə	‘boot’
b.	约	jœk	jiɔk	‘approximate’
c.	雀	tsœk	tsiɔk	‘bird’
d.	香	hœŋ	hiɔŋ	‘fragrant’

The ranking established back in 19 explains how [iə] is selected as the output for [œ] in open syllables in the Doumen dialect, as illustrated in 27.

(27) /hœ/ - [hiə] ‘boot’(26a)

/hœ/	*[round][-back]	RV-velar	Breaking	MAX-low	MAX-round
a. [hœ]	*!				
b. [hiə]			*		*

Candidate 27a is the faithful candidate, but it violates *[round][-back], as the features [round] and [-back] are realized in a single vowel [œ]. Candidate 27b, the winning candidate, violates two constraints, Breaking and MAX-round. It violates Breaking because the feature [-back] and [+high] from the input surface in the vowel [i] and the feature [+low] in the vowel [ə]. It violates MAX-round because [round] from the input is lost in the output [iə]. However, these two constraints, Breaking and MAX-round, are ranked lower than what candidate 27a violates, *[round][-back], and therefore 27a is eliminated while 27b is selected.

To account for the surface form of [jiɔk] for the input /jœk/ in the Doumen dialect, we need to combine the rankings in 19 and 22. At this point, we know that MAX-high and Ident[±back] are ranked higher than MAX-low and MAX-round, and that

Breaking is also ranked higher than these two constraints, according to 22, but we don't know how Breaking is ranked against MAX-high and Ident[±back] yet. Therefore, there could be several possible rankings, one of which is in 28, where Breaking is placed higher than Ident[±back] and MAX-high.

(28) *[round][-back], RV-velar>>Breaking>>Ident[±back]>>MAX-high >>MAX-low, MAX-round

Following this ranking, an analysis can be illustrated in 29.

(29) /jœk/ - [jiœk] 'approximate' (26b)

/jœk/	*[round][-back]	RV-velar	Breaking	Ident[±back]	MAX-high	MAX-low	MAX-round
a. [jœk]	*!						
(129)b. [jiœk]			*!				
c. [jiak]			*!				*
129 d. [jœk]				*			

In the tableau in 29, the faithful candidate 29a is successfully eliminated for violating the highest-ranked constraint *[round][-back] because the features [round] and [-back] are realized in a single vowel. Candidate 29c is also eliminated, critically because it violates Breaking by realizing features [+high] and [-back] in [i] and [+low] in [a]. Candidate 29b violates Breaking by realizing features [+high], [-back] in [i] and [+low] and [round] in [œ]. Candidate 29d violates Ident[±back], because the feature [round] is lost in the surface form. However, such ranking would falsely choose candidate 29d as the winning candidate, since it violates a lower-ranked constraint, Ident[±back], as opposed to the supposedly winning candidate, 29b, which violates a higher-ranked constraint, Breaking. Since 29b is the true winning candidate, the analysis in the tableau in 29 would not work.

Another possible ranking is shown in 30, where Breaking is ranked lower than both Ident[±back] and MAX-high.

(30) *[round][-back], RV-velar>> Ident[±back]>> MAX-high>>Breaking>>MAX-low, MAX-round

An analysis, accordingly, would be one as illustrated in the tableau in 31.

(31) /jœk/ - [jiøk] ‘approximate’ (26b)

/jœk/	*[round][-back]	RV-velar	Ident[±back]	MAX-high	Breaking	MAX-low	MAX-round
a. [jœk]	*!						
b. [jiøk]					*		
c. [jiak]					*		*!
d. [jøk]			*!				

With the ranking in 30, candidate 31a is, again, correctly eliminated. Candidate 31b, the winning candidate, violates Breaking, and candidate 31d violates Ident[±back], but this time, since Breaking is ranked lower than Ident[±back], candidate 31d is safely eliminated. Both candidates 31b and 31c violate Breaking, but since candidate 31c also violates MAX-round, as the feature [round] is dropped in this surface form, candidate 31b is selected.

The analysis does not end here, however. This ranking in 30 yields analysis that chooses the right candidate, but there is not enough evidence to support the hypothesis that reversing Breaking and MAX-high or *[round][-back] and Ident[±back] would arrive at the wrong candidate, and therefore their relative places in the ranking are not certain yet. Consequently, the ranking should be modified as in 32.

(32) *[round][-back], RV-velar, Ident[±back]>> MAX-high, Breaking>>MAX-low, MAX-round

The modified tableau with the ranking in 32 is shown in 33.

(33) /jœk/ - [jiøk] ‘approximate’ (26b)

/jœk/	*[round][-back]	RV-velar	Ident[±back]	MAX-high	Breaking	MAX-low	MAX-round
[jœk]	*!						
b. [jiøk]					*		
[jiak]					*		*!
[jøk]			*!				

3. Conclusion

The OT analysis in this paper has demonstrated that the ranking of constraints in the Doumen dialect fits into the realizations of its rounded vowels. The high ranking of the constraints *[round][-back], RV-velar, and Ident[±back] is reflected in the phenomenon that the front rounded vowels [y] and [œ] are avoided at all cost. In fact, front rounded vowels /y/ and /œ/ are highly disfavored in many Cantonese dialects. Specifically, /y/ is maintained in only 11 of the 21 dialects in our data and /œ/ in only 7 of

them. One common strategy to retain the features in front rounded vowels from the standard variety and stay faithful to the input is by separating the features and realizing them in different vowels, resorting to the use of diphthongs. The feature [round], for that matter, is disfavored in general, as indicated in the low ranking of the constraint that keeps it, which is consistent with the universal segmental markedness hierarchy put forward by Lin (2002). It is possible that front rounded vowels are typologically more marked because roundness decreases the distinguishing effects of the second formant, which is an acoustic cue that differentiates front from back vowels (Ladefoged & Maddieson, 1996).

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The Moraic Structure of Taiwan Mandarin Contractions

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In natural Mandarin conversations, two syllables are often contracted into a monosyllabic contraction, whose rhyme duration can be longer than that of a lexical monosyllable. Studies of Mandarin contraction focused primarily on segmental loss or tone change. None, to the author's knowledge, has discussed the loss of moras in contraction. Given that the number of moras in a syllable is proportional to rhyme duration, this study probes into the moraic structure of Mandarin contractions through an examination of the rhyme duration of monosyllabic contractions vis-à-vis that of monosyllabic words. The results show that the average rhyme duration of monosyllabic contractions is longer than that of uncontracted monosyllables regardless of speech rate, and that in contracting two syllables, one mora is lost.

1. Introduction

It has been well-established that the rhyme duration of a syllable mirrors the moraic structure. Rhyme duration is proportional to the number of moras in different languages (Broselow, Chen & Huffman, 1997). In Mandarin, all full syllables are bimoraic, so the rhyme duration of every monosyllable is not significantly longer or shorter than one another (Duanmu, 1993; Wu & Kenstowicz, 2015). However, in natural Mandarin conversations, two syllables are often contracted into a monosyllabic contraction, whose rhyme duration can be longer than that of a lexical monosyllable (Chung, 2006). No previous research has been done as to how much longer the rhyme duration of a monosyllabic contraction is than that of a monosyllabic lexical word. The comparison between them is important in revealing what is lost in the process of contraction on the moraic level. The present study measures and compares these two types of rhyme durations to probe into the moraic structure of monosyllabic contractions.

2. Background

Previous studies have shown that different moraic structures can be reflected in the duration of syllable rhyme. Broselow, Chen & Huffman (1997) provide cross-linguistic evidence of this correlation, showing that in Runyambo, Malayalam, and Arabic, rhyme duration is proportional to the number of moras. The correlation between the moraic structure and rhyme duration is illustrated in (1).

(1) Moraic structure and rhyme duration

The duration of a bimoraic rhyme is approximately twice as long as the duration of a mono-moraic rhyme. If the duration of a mono-moraic rhyme is n , the duration of a non-mora-sharing bimoraic rhyme is about $2n$.

In Mandarin, all full syllables are bimoraic, so their rhyme durations are not significantly different (Duanmu, 1993). When two or more syllables are contracted into one in natural conversations, the duration of this kind of monosyllables (hereafter monosyllabic contractions) can be different from that of monosyllabic lexical words. Some examples from Chung (2006, p.18) are given in (2). It is shown that two identical syllables can be contracted into one, with a *considerably lengthened vowel*, which implies that the rhyme duration of monosyllabic contractions are longer than that of monosyllabic lexical words.

(2) Monosyllabic contractions

- a. *xie xie* 'Thanks' → [ɕiɛ:53]
- b. *gang gang* 'just now' → [kɑ:ŋ55]
- c. *tian tian* 'daily, every day' → [tʰjɛ:55]

However, no research has been done to measure the difference. The closest study to this issue is Cheng (2004), who found that the average syllable duration of monosyllabic contractions, like the ones in (2), is shorter than that of lexicalized contracted syllables (e.g. *jiang53* from *zhe53 yang53*). Yet, duration of a whole syllable does not reflect the moraic structure. The duration of the onset should be excluded from the measurement, because the onset is not associated with moras. In fact, little research concerning rhyme durations in contractions has been done. Although Cheng & Xu (2009) found that the average rhyme duration of monosyllabic contractions is shorter than that of uncontracted disyllabic words, they did not compare the rhyme durations of monosyllabic contractions with those of monosyllabic lexical words.

A comparison between the rhyme duration of monosyllabic contractions and that of monosyllabic lexical words can show if monosyllabic contractions differ phonologically from monosyllabic lexical words to the speakers. If all Mandarin full monosyllables are bimoraic, they should have similar rhyme durations. If the rhyme duration of monosyllabic contractions does differ from that of monosyllabic lexical words, their moraic structures must be different. By looking deeper into the moraic structures of

monosyllabic contracted forms, we can be more certain about what is lost during contraction. Hence, this study aims to investigate the following questions:

1. Do monosyllabic contractions differ from monosyllabic lexical words in rhyme duration?
2. What does rhyme duration reveal about the moraic structure of monosyllabic contractions?

3. Methodology

This study used a carrier sentence composed of 3 clauses, as shown in (3), to collect Mandarin monosyllabic lexical words and monosyllabic contractions. The carrier sentence was designed by Cheng (2009) to elicit monosyllabic contractions. A total of 20 disyllabic target words were put in the carrier sentence for the participants to read. There were four participants, 2 females (age 28, 29), and 2 males (age 24, 25). They were shown the carrier sentence with different target words and instructed to say the sentences as naturally as possible at three different speech rates: **slow** as if they were reciting in class, **natural** as if they were having a conversation with a friend, and, finally, as **fast** as possible.

(2) Carrier sentence (Cheng, 2009, p.457)

Character: 「你說的是□□沙拉是吧?我當然不吃□□沙拉那種東西, 因為我最不喜歡他們家出的□□沙拉! 」

Pinyin: “ni shuo de shi □□ shi ba? wo dang ran bu chi □□ sha la na zhong dong xi, yin wen wo zui bu xi huan ta jia chu de □□ sha la.”

English: “You meant □□, didn’t you? Of course I won’t eat □□ salad that kinda stuff, because I dislike □□ salad made by his family the most!”

Every target word comprises two identical syllables. The structures of the syllables are given in (4). There are 20 syllable structures, with three types of onsets (C refers to non-nasal consonants) and six types of rhymes. All main vowels are /a/, because its distribution is the least limited compared to other vowels. Depending on the phonotactics and existing words, the glides are either /j/ or /w/; the nasal segments either /n/ or /m/; and the consonants either /t/ or /k. The tone is primarily the high-level tone (55), but the rising tone (35) is also used when there are no existing words with the high-level tone. The rising tone is used to replace the high-level tone because they do not lead to significantly different rhyme durations compared to the low-rising tone (214) and the falling tone (53) (Wu & Kenstowicz, 2015). It should be noted that the structures **NGVN and NVN are excluded** from the analysis because it is difficult to tell the syllable boundaries in a sequence of two NGVN or two NVN syllables.

(3) Structure of monosyllables

Onset	Rhyme	Combinations
Zero	V, VG, VN, GV, GVG, GVN	V (<i>a</i>), VG (<i>ai</i>), VN (<i>an, ang</i>), GV (<i>wa</i>), GVG (<i>wai</i>), GVN (<i>wan, wang</i>)
C		CV (<i>da</i>), CVG (<i>dai</i>), CVN (<i>dan, dang</i>), CGV (<i>gua</i>), CGVG (<i>guai</i>), CGVN (<i>guan, guang</i>)
N		NV (<i>na</i>), NVG (<i>nao</i>), NGV (<i>nie</i>), NGVG (<i>miao</i>), NGVN , NN

Altogether, 720 tokens were collected (20 words*4 participants*3 clauses*3 speech rates). These tokens were then classified into contracted forms and uncontracted forms based on waveform and formant displays on the spectrogram. If there are interruptions of formants, the disyllabic token is considered uncontracted. If not, the token is classified as contracted.

The uncontracted monosyllabic lexical words and monosyllabic contractions were targeted for measurement of rhyme duration, with an aim to observe how monosyllabic contractions differ from monosyllabic lexical words in rhyme duration. The rhyme durations of these forms were measured and analyzed with *Praat 6.0.53* (Boersma & Weenink, 2019).

4. Results and discussion

The table in (5) shows the number of contracted and uncontracted forms. For each clause in the carrier sentence, the total number of targeted disyllabic tokens is 240 (20 words*4 speakers*3 speech rates). It is shown that **the number of contractions increases and the number of uncontracted forms decreases as the speech rate goes faster**, as expected from Cheng & Xu’s (2009) findings. However, what is different from their findings is that **the number of contractions does not increase as the length of each clause becomes longer**. Originally, it was expected to increase because participants may feel more time pressure when the sentence is longer. The findings in this study suggests that this may be influenced by the varying speech rates in an utterance. When the sentence is long, the participants may slow down a little in order to prevent any speech errors.

(4) Number of contracted and uncontracted forms

	Contracted forms			Uncontracted forms		
	1 st clause	2 nd clause	3 rd clause	1 st clause	2 nd clause	3 rd clause
Slow	3	4	4	77	76	76
Natural	32	29	24	48	51	56
The fastest	55	55	54	25	25	26
Total	90	88	82	150	152	158

The average durations of the monosyllabic contractions and the uncontracted monosyllables in the target words at different speech rates are shown in (6). Both types of durations reduce as the speech rate increases. Interestingly, even the shortest duration of monosyllabic contractions is longer than the longest duration of uncontracted monosyllables (171.7 ms). This indicates that monosyllabic contractions and monosyllabic lexical words differ in rhyme duration, no matter what the speech rate is.

(5) Average duration of monosyllabic contractions and uncontracted monosyllables

	Slow	Natural	The fastest
Monosyllabic contractions	339.2445 ms	215.815133 ms	182.607474 ms
Uncontracted monosyllables	171.681121 ms	119.573905 ms	85.634834 ms

A more perspicuous comparison between the two types of duration is provided in (7). The numbers are the duration of monosyllabic contractions divided by the duration of uncontracted monosyllables. For instance, the rhyme duration of monosyllabic contractions at the slow speech rate (339.2445 ms) divided by that of uncontracted monosyllables at the slow speech rate (171.681121 ms) is about 1.98. The numbers were rounded to the hundredth digit. The numbers indicate how much longer the former duration is than the latter.

(6) Duration of monosyllabic contractions divided by that of uncontracted monosyllables

Uncontracted \ Contracted	Slow	Natural	The fastest
Slow	1.98	2.84	3.96
Natural	1.26	1.80	2.52
The fastest	1.06	1.53	2.13

The table shows that regardless of speech rate, the duration of monosyllabic contractions is always longer than the duration of uncontracted monosyllables because all numbers are more than 1.

The moraic structure of monosyllabic contractions can also be inferred because the difference in rhyme durations reflect the difference in the moraic structures. The problem is which duration of monosyllabic contractions and which duration of uncontracted monosyllables do we compare? It is deemed best that we compare the duration of monosyllabic contraction at the fastest speech rate with the duration of uncontracted monosyllables at the natural speech rate for the following reason.

The most natural context for contractions to occur is the fastest speech rate, and it is also the context where we collected the most tokens of monosyllabic contraction. Thus, the duration of monosyllabic contractions at the fastest speech rate should be closer to reality than the duration at other speech rates. Likewise, the duration of uncontracted monosyllables is indubitably the most natural at the natural speech rate. Only by

comparing these durations can we get a realistic picture of how they differ in rhyme duration and moraic structure in natural speech.

The comparison shows that the duration of monosyllabic contractions is about 1.5 times longer than that of uncontracted monosyllables. Given that an uncontracted monosyllable contains two moras and that rhyme duration is proportional to the number of moras, a monosyllabic contraction should have three moras (2*1.5). This indicates that when two syllables are contracted, one mora is dropped, as illustrated in (8). Nonetheless, it remains uncertain which mora (the former, the latter or part of both moras) is lost during contraction, and how the segments are re-associated with the remaining moras. This requires an investigation of the duration of the vowels and codas and is suggested for future research.

(7) The process of contraction

5. Conclusion

The rhyme duration of a monosyllabic contraction has been suggested to be longer than that of a monosyllabic lexical word in the past literature. Nevertheless, no research regarding the rhyme duration of monosyllabic contraction has been done. Through a comparison between the duration of monosyllabic contractions and monosyllabic words, this study shows that the former duration is longer than the latter by approximately 1.5 times. This also reveals that one mora is lost during the contraction of two syllables. Yet, exactly how the segments are associated with the moras is suggested for future research.

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抚顺话声调的协同发音与连读变调

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连读变调和协同发音都是声调相连时所产生的声学变化，如何结合声学语音学和音系学的证据来厘清两者之间的关系，是值得深入研究和讨论的。本文拟从东北官话抚顺话的声调研究入手，使用声学分析的方法，着眼于对 f_0 变化模式的客观分析，来进一步探索方言连读变调与协同发音的关系。研究发现，虽然抚顺话的单字调调型与北京话非常相似，但其两字组连读变调模式与北京话有明显不同；抚顺话中的协同发音作用既遵循了前人归纳的跨语言的普遍共性，同时也保留了某些方言的特异性。另外从本文的结果来看，连读变调很可能是声调间协同发音作用的固化结果，而固化后的音系层面的连读变调可能又会进一步发生语音层面的协同发音作用，进而导致声调产生更细微的差异，协同发音的作用目标无论是在本调层还是变调层都是一致的。

1. 引言

1.1 抚顺话声调研究概述

抚顺市位于辽宁省东部，东经 123°55'，北纬 41°52'，《中国语言地图集》将抚顺话归入东北官话吉沈片的通溪小片。宋学等（1963）的《辽宁语音说略》根据语音特点将辽宁方言大致分为四区，并将抚顺、沈阳、鞍山等方言归入第三区，他们认为，该区阴平的调值为[44]或[33]，其调型虽跟北京相同，但调值较低；该区阳平的调值为[35]/[24]；该区上声调值都是[213]；该区的去声则都是降调，调值为[53]/[52]/[42]。在这项研究的基础上，贺巍（1986）、张志敏（2005）、石锋、黄彩玉（2007）、杨春宇（2010）、孟祥宇（2011；2012）、王军（2017）、贾珈等（2009）、叶琳（2013）、崔平、王韞佳（2019），Cui & Kuang（2020）等学者也对东北官话声调或其中某一方言小片的声调进行了相关研究，他们都发现东北官话今四个声调的调型与北京话相近，但阴平的调值要比北京话略低，这是东北官

话在听感上区别于北京话的一个标志，根据崔平、王韞佳（2019）的结果，我们将抚顺话单字调情况归纳总结如下：高平调（阴平）[44]、中升调（阳平）[35]、低凹调（上声）[313]、高降调（去声）[52]，具体单字调调型和调值如图 1 所示。

图 1 抚顺话单字调的平均音高曲线及其标准差（崔平、王韞佳（2019））

尽管东北话的单字调模式与北京话相似，但是其连读变调模式却与北京话有很大不同。寇瑾（2009）、赵彩虹等（2014）、崔平、王韞佳（2019）、Cui et al（2020）等学者发现，在东北官话抚顺和鞍山等地的方言中，不仅存在与北京话类似的连上变调规则，上声在后接阴平时也会发生变调，其变调形式与连上变调的前字上声和单字调阳平的形式接近。叶琳（2013）、Cui & Kuang（2020）等还发现在沈阳话和抚顺话中，阴平处于两字组后字位置或大的语调短语结尾（domain-final position）时，不论它的前字声调为何，其都会由原来的高平调变为一个中降调，这既是东北官话不同于北京话的典型表现之一，也是其主要的韵律特征之一。此外，高玉娟（2007）发现胶辽官话的大连话中上声也有类似东北官话抚顺话的变调格式，高使用省力原则来解释上声阴平组合中前上变同阳平的现象。

1.2 声调间的协同发音作用

汉语方言中连读变调的表现相当复杂，既有在语音层面与音步、重音、语调等相联系的语音变调，也有在语义语法层面与特定语义、词类和短语结构相互关联的音义变调，因此长久以来，连读变调问题一直是汉语方言学、音系学和语音学的研究热点之一。

除了连读变调导致的变化之外，声调在连读中还有“微观”层面的变化，即声调连读时相邻声调之间 f_0 的相互调节和影响，其结果是造成邻近声调间音高的同化或异化作用，目前学界把这些非连读变调层面的变化通称为声调的协同发音。

关于协同发音在相邻声调之间的影响范围和作用力大小，不同学者在研究不同语言时，结果不尽相同。Han & Kim（1974）关于越南语的研究以及 Gandour et al（1994）关于泰语的研究都认为，越南语和泰语在整个调高在协同发音中都会受到影响，即整个声调曲线受前后声调的作用而上下移动。而沈晓楠、林茂灿

(1992), 王韞佳(1993), Xu(1997)等人关于汉语普通话的协同发音研究则表明, 普通话中通常只有声调的起点、终点或某些特殊的音高点会受到协同发音的影响, 并且通常顺向作用主要影响后接声调的起点, 逆向作用则对被作用声调的起点和终点都有影响, 另外协同发音的作用范围与相邻声调的调类和具体的音高特征点也有一定关系。

简言之, 前人在跨语言的研究上相对全面地考察了声调间的协同发音作用, 并且已经确定了它的普遍趋势以及某些语言的特定属性。在前人研究基础上, Zhang & Liu(2011)总结了汉语普通话、台湾话、越南语以及泰语中声调间协同发音的四种特性: 1) 声调间协同发音的方向既可以是顺向的也可以是逆向的; 2) 顺向协同发音的影响幅度通常大于逆向协同发音; 3) 顺向协同发音作用以同化为主, 并且这种同化作用具有跨语言的普遍性, 而逆向协同发音作用既可以是同化的也可以是异化的, 通常更具有语言特异性甚至是声调特异性; 4) 高调和低调(不论是目标声调还是触发声调)在协同发音中有不同表现, 具体说来, 低调更有可能对前一个高调产生逆向异化作用, 而高调则通常会导致顺向同化作用。

Chen & Wiltshire(2018)考察了南京话声调的协同发音, 他们发现并不是所有的语言都遵从顺向作用大于逆向作用这一属性, 某些语言在顺向和逆向作用中显示出相似的幅度, 至少南京话中是这样。

1.3 连续变调与协同发音的关系

无论是连续变调还是协同发音, 都会导致声调在连读中发生声学层面的变化。这些变化哪一些是音系层面的连续变调, 哪一些是语音层面的协同发音, 学界对两种变化的界定一直存在争议。

沈晓楠(1992)提出了三个区分标准: 1) 连续变调是由受某种语言特有的形态音位的限制所致, 而协同发音则是由受跟语言无关的生物力学的限制而造成的; 2) 变调和协同发音的语音机制不同, 在变调中, 声调的变化可以由同化或异化造成, 而协同发音主要还是声调同化的结果; 3) 变调与协同发音的区别还在于变调不必保存原来声调本身的特性, 变调作用是音位的, 而声调协同发音作用不是音位的, 其声调的基本曲线相对来说保持不变。王韞佳(1993)则使用声调的宏观和微观变化来进一步区分连续变调和协同发音两种现象, 她认为, 声调的协同发音是指相邻声调间 f_0 的相互调节, 其结果是造成邻近声调间的同化或异化作用, 声调的协同发音不会引起声调调形的改变, 这是它与连续变调的一个重要区别。Chen(2001)则认为连续变调和协同发音之间并没有本质的区别, 只不过连续变调通常可以被耳感知到, 因此更有可能通过田野调查记录下来, 并被整理描述成大规模的音系法则。Zhang & Liu(2011)认为, 从理论上讲, 声调间协同发音与连续变调的不同之处在于, 协同发音是一种渐变的、连续的语音效应, 并且在语速和风格上具有高度可变性, 而连续变调则是范畴性的, 通常会造成两个不同调类的中和现象, 并且在语速和风格上是稳定的。但 Zhang & Liu 也指出, 实际上这些区

别有时难以维持，连读变调在类型特征上也与协同发音作用有许多共同之处，因此，将声调协同发音作为至少是某些连读变调模式的前兆是合理的，这与Przedziecki（2005）提出的元音间的协同发音是元音和谐的前兆非常相似。在此基础上，Zhang & Liu（2011）强调，在声学上研究同一语言中的连读变调和协同发音现象，可以潜在地解决这两种现象之间的差异和联系问题。Li & Chen（2016）则认为在讨论两类声调变化类型的关系时，应当首先基于对 f_0 变化模式的客观观察，如果没有这一点，任何关于这两种声调实现形式的讨论都是没有根据的。在此基础上，他们从 f_0 变化模式的角度出发，总结了两种变化类型之间的一些差异：一般来说，由后接声调引起的语音协同发音作用不会影响声调曲拱的区别性，尽管可能会存在显著的 f_0 偏差；而音系上的连读变调交替通常会引起声调曲拱的显著变化。这一看法实际上与沈晓楠（1992）和王韞佳（1993）关于调形问题的看法是一致的。

相对于连读变调而言，学界对汉语方言中声调协同发音问题的研究较少。当然，连读变调和协同发音之间的界限难以确定，也给研究声调协同发音带来了困难。在更多方言中观察连读变调和协同发音之间的关系，是加深对这一问题理解的最合适的方法。如前文所述，抚顺话在调类上与普通话相同，调值上也与普通话很相似，其连读变调与普通话既有相似点也有不同点，而普通话的连读变调和协同发音问题是学界研究得最为充分的，因此，本文以抚顺话为研究对象来进一步探索方言连读变调与协同发音的关系。本文先用声学分析的方法获得抚顺话两字组连调声学形式，在此基础上界定哪些变化是连读变调层面、哪些变化是协同发音层面的，然后对协同发音现象进行定量的声学分析，本文的重点在于讨论该方言中的连读变调与协同发音的关联，并建立该方言协同发音的模式。

2. 两字组连调的声学分析

2.1 两字组连读变调和协同发音的甄别

2.1.1 方法

发音字表包括 16 种抚顺话两字组声调组合，每种声调组合都有 4 组使用频率较高的词，其中清、浊声母各 2 组，少数声调不能与浊声母搭配，则选用清声母音节替代。语料中每个词呈现两次，共得到 $16*4*2=128$ 个发音项目。所有项目以随机次序排列呈现给 15 名发音人（8 男 7 女），具体发音人情况和音高数据的处理参见崔平、王韞佳（2019）。

2.1.2 结果和分析

图 2 分别显示了阴平、阳平、上声和去声处于两字组前字位置和后字位置时的音高模式。下面分别对四个声调在前后位置上的特点进行分析。

图2 阴平(a)、阳平(b)、上声(c)、去声(d)处于两字组前字位置、后字位置时的音高模式

阴平处于前字位置时，为高平或高-微降调，音系上都可视作高平调；阴平处于后字位置时调型发生改变，变为一个降幅超过1度的降调。阳平在前后字位置都保持中升调型，但无论在前字还是后字位置，其升幅都小于单字调。去声在两字组连字调的前后位置中都保持高降调的调型，不过其下降幅度要比单字调时小 1-2 度。上声的调型在四个声调之前的表现变化较大，后接阴平和上声时，变为一个与阳平相似的中升调，但其上升幅度仅为 1 度，后接阳平时变成一个微降调，后接去

声时仍为低凹调，但其低音点要比单字调时高 1 度；当上声处于后字位置时，调型与单字调时基本一致，不过其高音点和低音点都要比单字调略高。

根据两字组 16 种组合的音高模式，我们将上述会引起声调 f_0 曲拱发生明显变化，改变音高曲线的特征走向，使得其表面 f_0 可能与标准 f_0 曲拱的特征不一致并且不可预测的情况归纳为连读变调，如 T1 位于两字组后字位置时的变化，以及 T3 在 T1 和 T3 前的变化，而其余不改变基频的移动方向，也不改变声调本身的特性，仅在基频高度上引起变化的声调间作用归纳为协同发音。

根据以上结果，抚顺话与北京话连读变调规则最大的不同是阴平和上声的变调：阴平在两字组末字位置变为中降调[43]，上声在阴平和上声前面都变成类似阳平的中升调[34]。具体变调模式如表 1 所列。

表 1 抚顺话两字组连字调的变调模式

声调组合	变调模式
T1+T1	[44]+[44]→[44]+[43]
T2+T1	[35]+[44]→[34]+[43]
T3+T1	[313]+[44]→[34]+[43]
T4+T1	[52]+[44]→[54]+[43]
T3+T3	[313]+[313]→[34]+[423]

关于抚顺话两字组的连读变调现象我们已有专文进行讨论，参见崔平、王韞佳（2019），下文我们主要对抚顺话两字组中的协同发音作用进行进一步的声学分析。

2.2 两字组声调的协同发音分析

本节主要对不改变 f_0 的移动方向，也不改变声调本身的特性，仅在 f_0 高度上引起变化的声调间协同发音作用进行声学分析。鉴于上文已经把“T1+T1，T2+T1，T3+T1，T4+T1，T3+T3”界定为连读变调层面的变化，因此在讨论协同发音的顺、逆向作用时暂时排除这些组合。本节讨论的声调组合为“ T_x+T_2 （ T_x 表任意声调），T1+T3，T2+T3，T4+T3， T_x+T_4 ”。

2.2.1 方法

协同发音部分所有数据均来自前文两字组 16 种声调组合中的音高数据。根据前人研究，在考察声调间潜在的顺向作用时，通常第二个声调保持不变，只改变第一个声调；反之研究声调间逆向作用时，通常第一个声调保持不变，只改变第二个声调。

顺向作用中，我们以所有组合中的前字调类为自变量，然后通过单因素重复测量 ANOVA 检验在前接不同声调时，第二个音节的起点（0%），25%，中间点（50%），75%和终点（100%）的音高值是否存在显著差异。对于某些声调，可能还会考虑前字声调对其某些音高特征点的影响，比如上声的低音点。如果音高值

存在显著差异，我们再进行事后多重比较。相同的步骤做少许修改同样适用于逆向作用。

2.2.2 顺向作用

图 3 分别展示了后字为阳平、上声和去声时，前字声调对它们的顺向作用。由于 T1 处于后字时和“T3+T3”组合属于连读变调层面的变化，故这里暂不包括在内，下文同。

图 3 顺向作用中阳平(a)、上声(b)、去声(c)位于后字位置时的音高曲线图

我们将所有组合中第一个音节的音高终点根据其表层音高实现分为高（H）、中（M）和低（L），如图 3(a、b、c)所示，以 3(a)为例，前字阴平、阳平的音高终点位于 5 度制的 3.5 度以上，我们将其归为高（H）类，前字去声和上声的音高终点位于五度制的 3.5 度-2.5 度以上，我们将其归为中（M）类，依此类推，前字音高终点在 2.5 度以下，我们将其归为低（L）类，下同。

如前文所述，通过单因素重复测量 ANOVA 检验前字不同调类对第二个音节五个音高点的音高值的影响，具体音高点按时间等间距截取，分别为：0%、25%、50%、75%以及 100%。ANOVA 结果总结在表 2 中。表中的 T_x 表示前字为任意声调。

表 2 顺向作用中后字声调五个音高点的 ANOVA 分析结果

声调组合	0%	25%	50%	75%	100%
T_x+T2	F=1.619 $p=0.197$	F=1.513 $p=0.223$	F=1.297 $p=0.292$	F=1.041 $p=0.383$	F=0.189 $p=0.903$
T_x+T3	F=7.863 $p=0.001^{**}$	F=12.130 $p<0.001^{***}$	F=0.434 $p=0.651$	F=0.201 $p=0.818$	F=0.340 $p=0.714$

T_x+T4	F=1.293 $p=0.287$	F=0.251 $p=0.860$	F=0.185 $p=0.906$	F=0.270 $p=0.847$	F=0.323 $p=0.809$
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表中“****”表示 $p < 0.001$ ，“***”表示 $p < 0.01$ ，“**”表示 $p < 0.05$ 。

统计检验结果显示，阳平和去声位于后字位置时，前字声调调类对它们五个音高点上的音高值均没有显著作用，但从音高图中可以看出，阳平位于高终点的声调后时，其音高均值要略高一些。而当上声处于后字位置时，前接声调调类对其起点音高和 25%时间点上的音高值均有显著作用。进一步进行事后两两成对比较，发现低终点的去声位于前字时，上声的起点音高和 25%时间点上的音高值与其他声调位于前字时存在显著差异，音高图中的数据也表明上声的起点音高在 H 调后比在 M 调之后更高。由此可见，在声调间顺向协同发音中，只有上声受到了顺向作用的显著影响，且其主要受到前接声调的同化作用。

关于上声，我们专门对其低音点与前字终点音高的关系进行了统计分析。结果发现，前字声调终点音高对其低音点并没有显著作用 ($F=1.217$, $p=0.308$)。不过前接声调的终点音高会影响上声低音点的出现时间 ($F=6.446$, $p=0.004$)，当前接声调为低终点时，上声的低音点会提前实现，去声后上声的低音点出现在等间距 15 个采样点的第 6 个点上，而当上声位于阴平和阳平后时，其低音点均出现在第 9 个采样点上。

为进一步检验顺向作用的大小，我们参考 Chen & Wiltshire (2018)、东孝拓 (2019) 等人的研究，分别计算了在每个声调组合中第二个音节 (0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 100%) 五个点处提取的音高最大值、最小值、平均值、标准差以及音高变化幅度的结果。根据前人研究，某个音高点的标准差和音高变化幅度越大，相邻声调对它产生的协同发音作用就越强。具体结果如表 3 所示。

表 3 顺向作用中后字五个音高点的相关结果

数值	声调组合	音高位置				
		起点	25%	中间点	75%	终点
最大值	T_x+T2	3.48	3.37	3.60	3.92	3.96
	T_x+T3	3.94	3.34	2.01	2.27	3.04
	T_x+T4	4.69	4.69	4.31	3.56	3.02
最小值	T_x+T2	3.10	3.05	3.37	3.71	3.86
	T_x+T3	3.14	2.22	1.80	2.13	2.76
	T_x+T4	4.51	4.62	4.22	3.39	2.80
标准差	T_x+T2	0.16	0.14	0.10	0.09	0.04
	T_x+T3	0.41	0.62	0.11	0.07	0.15
	T_x+T4	0.08	0.03	0.04	0.08	0.12
平均值	T_x+T2	3.26	3.17	3.49	3.82	3.92

	$T_x + T3$	3.59	2.94	1.89	2.19	2.93
	$T_x + T4$	4.62	4.66	4.27	3.48	2.92
音高变化幅度	$T_x + T2$	0.38	0.32	0.23	0.21	0.10
	$T_x + T3$	0.80	1.12	0.21	0.14	0.28
	$T_x + T4$	0.18	0.07	0.09	0.17	0.22

从标准差和音高变化幅度的结果来看，上声受到的顺向协同发音作用最大。上声的起点和 25%时间点上的音高值的音高变化幅度和标准差较大，这与前面关于前字声调对其音高作用的统计分析结果一致，即前接不同声调时，上声的起点音高和 25%时间点上的音高值存在显著差异。

综上所述，在两字组中，顺向作用只对上声有显著作用，其作用范围也很有限，只有上声的起点音高和 25%时间点上的音高会受到前接声调终点的影响，没有覆盖到 50%的范围，阳平和去声的起点音高均不会受到前接声调的顺向作用。这似乎也从另一个角度说明，抚顺话中后字上声的起点并不重要，因为它可能是受到前接声调顺向作用的影响，而不是上声自身的底层音系特征，相反，没有受到前接声调影响的低音点才是上声真正的底层音系特征。

2.2.3 逆向作用

图 4 分别展示了前字为阴平、阳平、上声和去声时，后字声调对它们的逆向作用。这里同样排除 T1 位于后字时和“T3+ T3”的连读变调组合。

图 4 逆向作用中阴平(a)、阳平(b)、上声(c)、去声(d)位于前字位置时的音高曲线图

对于每个组合，我们同样将第二个音节的起始音高分类为 H、M 或 L，如图 4(a、b、c、d)所示，然后通过单因素重复测量 ANOVA 检验后字不同调类对第一

个音节五个音高点的音高值的影响。ANOVA 结果总结在表 4 中。表中的 T_x 表示前字为任意声调。

表 4 逆向作用中前字声调五个音高点的 ANOVA 分析结果

声调组合	0%	25%	50%	75%	100%
T1+ T_x	F=0.816 $p=0.450$	F=2.741 $p=0.078$	F=7.4 $p=0.002^{**}$	F=9.526 $p<0.001^{***}$	F=9.442 $p=0.001^{**}$
T2+ T_x	F=1.563 $p=0.223$	F=6.337 $p=0.004^{**}$	F=21.122 $p<0.001^{***}$	F=26.356 $p<0.001^{***}$	F=9.831 $p<0.001^{***}$
T3+ T_x	F=0.328 $p=0.572$	F=0.848 $p=0.366$	F=4.026 $p=0.056$	F=2.228 $p=0.149$	F=0.047 $p=0.829$
T4+ T_x	F=10.217 $p=0.001^{**}$	F=9.004 $p=0.001^{**}$	F=3.978 $p=0.027^*$	F=0.345 $p=0.711$	F=0.703 $p=0.502$

表中，“***”表示 $p < 0.001$ ，“**”表示 $p < 0.01$ ，“*”表示 $p < 0.05$ 。

从上述图表中可以看出，前字声调的多数音高点都会受到后字调类的影响。由于前后声调间既有顺向又有逆向作用，为避免循环论证，在讨论逆向作用时，最好以后字较为稳定的后字声调起点值作为自变量。而在顺向作用中我们恰好已经发现上声的起点音高会受到前接声调终点的影响，而阳平和去声的起点音高均不会受到前接声调的顺向作用，因此我们认为在逆向协同发音中，后字阳平和去声的起点音高较为稳定，可以依据它们来讨论后字对前字的逆向作用；后字上声的起点并不是一个可依靠的自变量，因为它的具体音高实现受到了前字音高终点的影响，而没有受到前接声调影响的上声的低音点才是其底层真正的音系特征，因此，我们可以依据上声的低音点来讨论后字对前字的逆向作用。

下面对前字四个声调所受到的逆向作用逐一分析。阴平处于前字位置时，其终点、75%时间点以及中间点上的音高值在不同的后字声调条件下均存在显著差异，25%时间点上的音高值存在边缘显著差异（ $p < 0.1$ 时为边缘显著）。进一步进行事后两两成对比较，发现具有低音目标的上声位于后字时，前字阴平的终点、75%时间点以及中间点上的音高值与其他声调位于后字时存在显著差异。音高曲线图也显示，阴平位于高起点的去声前时，其音高均值较低，而位于具有低音目标的上声前时，其音高均值较高，由此可见，阴平主要受到后接声调的异化作用。比较奇怪的是，阴平处于同样是低起点的阳平前时，音高均值也较低。这个结果可能暗示着逆向作用的关联特征也许并非触发声调的起点，后面将专门对这个问题进行讨论。

阳平处于前字位置时，除起点音高外，其他音高点在不同后接声调之前均存在显著差异。事后两两成对比较结果显示，高起点的去声位于后字时，前字阳平除起点外的音高值与中起点的阳平和上声位于后字时存在显著差异。从音高曲线图来看，阳平主要受到后接声调的异化作用。在高起点的去声前，阳平音高最低，在中

起点的阳平和具有低音目标的上声前，阳平的音高较高。后接声调对于阳平的作用从阳平终点开始覆盖了声调的大部分范围。

在前字为上声时，我们暂时先把阳平和去声前上声的中降和中凹两种变体归到协同发音范畴，而把阴平和上声前上声类似阳平的中升变调归到连续变调范畴。统计结果显示，逆向作用只在上声中间点上存在边缘显著效应，在上声其余音高点上的作用均不显著。

去声处于前字位置时，后接声调对其起点、25%时间点以及中间点上的音高作用均是显著的，对其余两个音高点的作用不显著。事后两两成对比较结果显示，高起点的去声位于后字时，前字去声的起点、25%时间点以及中间点上的音高值与中起点的阳平和上声位于后字时存在显著差异。从音高曲线图来看，去声位于前字时也主要受到后接声调的异化作用，中起点的阳平和具有低音目标的上声前的去声音高较高，高起点前的去声音高均值较低。从作用方向看，去声的结果与阴平和阳平的结果似乎不同，因为后接声调对阳平和阴平的作用似乎是从两个声调的连接处，即前字声调的终点处开始，然后向前覆盖，而去声正好相反，逆向作用对于紧靠触发声调的去声终点音高反而没有显著作用。但是如果从音高特征的角度来分析各声调受到影响的位置，就可以看出，对于具有曲拱特征的阳平和去声来说，未受影响的点，即去声的终点和阳平的起点，均不具有高音特征。这些结果与 Zhang & Liu (2011) 关于天津话的研究结果基本一致，即逆向作用主要影响的是前接声调的非低音点。

在此基础上，为了进一步检验声调间逆向作用的大小，我们同样计算了在每个声调组合中第一个音节（0%，25%，50%，75%，100%）五个点处提取的音高值的最大值、最小值、平均值、标准差以及音高变化幅度的结果。具体结果如表 5 所示。

表 5 逆向作用中后字五个音高点的相关结果

数值	声调组合	音高位置				
		起点	25%	中间点	75%	终点
最大值	T1+T _x	4.25	4.28	4.30	4.32	4.25
	T2+T _x	3.72	3.86	4.19	4.46	4.48
	T3+T _x	3.56	3.29	3.15	3.10	3.15
	T4+T _x	4.90	4.80	4.48	3.93	3.62
最小值	T1+T _x	4.10	4.03	3.89	3.82	3.69
	T2+T _x	3.40	3.37	3.62	3.93	4.12
	T3+T _x	3.43	3.01	2.58	2.79	3.10
	T4+T _x	4.54	4.47	4.20	3.80	3.36
标准差	T1+T _x	0.08	0.13	0.22	0.28	0.29
	T2+T _x	0.16	0.25	0.30	0.29	0.19
	T3+T _x	0.09	0.20	0.40	0.22	0.04

	T4+T _x	0.19	0.18	0.15	0.07	0.13
平均值	T1+T _x	4.20	4.14	4.05	4.00	3.93
	T2+T _x	3.57	3.65	3.96	4.26	4.34
	T3+T _x	3.50	3.15	2.87	2.95	3.13
	T4+T _x	4.76	4.68	4.36	3.86	3.50
音高变化幅度	T1+T _x	0.15	0.25	0.41	0.50	0.56
	T2+T _x	0.32	0.49	0.57	0.53	0.36
	T3+T _x	0.13	0.28	0.57	0.31	0.05
	T4+T _x	0.36	0.33	0.28	0.13	0.26

从标准差和音高变化幅度的结果来看，阴平的终点、去声的起点以及阳平的高音点上的标准差和音高变化幅度值较大，由此可见，高音点更容易受到逆向协同发音作用的影响。

综上所述，在两字组中，声调间逆向协同发音作用大于顺向协同发音作用，逆向作用中前字声调的多数音高点都会受到后字调类的影响，甚至覆盖到前接声调的起点音高，且逆向作用主要影响的是前接声调的非低音点。

2.2.4 小结：抚顺话声调的协同发音特性

根据上文结果总结一下抚顺话两字组声调的协同发音特点。首先，在抚顺话的协同发音中，既存在顺向作用，又存在逆向作用。其次，总体上看，逆向作用大于顺向作用，具体表现为逆向作用的覆盖范围更大，甚至可以越过前字终点而对前字起点音高发生作用，而顺向作用中只有上声的起点音高和 25% 时间点上的音高会受到前接声调终点的影响，没有覆盖到 50% 的范围。第三，抚顺话声调间的顺向协同发音表现为同化作用，而逆向协同发音则表现为异化作用。

关于协同发音中高低调的不对称性，抚顺话的表现较为复杂。在顺向同化作用的触发声调中，统计结果显示除上声起点外后字各音高点的音高值没有显著差异，但从音高图的表现来看，普遍存在高终点后声调音高值较高的情况；关于顺向同化作用的目标，我们发现顺向同化作用主要影响的是上声的起点音高，对于其他音高点均没有显著影响，因此我们认为顺向同化作用的目标对音系层面的高低调并没有明显的偏好。在逆向异化作用的触发声调中，也不存在明显的高低调偏好倾向，不论是音高图还是统计检验结果，均表明高起点前的声调音高值较低，低起点或低音目标前的声调音高值较高；在逆向异化作用的目标中，我们发现后字起点音高主要影响的是前接声调的高音点，这在去声为前字时表现得尤为明显，去声的终点音高值无显著差异，但起点至中间点的音高值却存在显著差异，另外，高音点的音高变化幅度和标准差也比低音点的更大，由此可见，高音点是逆向异化作用中更容易产生变化的音高目标。以上特点可以总结为表 6。

表 6 抚顺话声调协同发音特性

作用方向	顺向作用和逆向作用同时存在
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作用力大小	顺向作用<逆向作用
作用性质	顺向作用：同化；逆向作用：异化
高低调不对称性	顺向同化的触发声调：没有明显偏好
	顺向同化的目标声调：没有明显偏好
	逆向异化的触发声调：没有明显偏好
	逆向异化的目标声调：高>低

3. 连续变调与协同发音的关系

3.1 协同发音对于连续变调的作用

上节考察的是两字组中非连续变调层面的音高变化，本小节拟观察的是，在发生了连续变调之后，声调之间是否还存在协同发音层面的作用。

3.1.1 协同发音对变调阴平的顺向作用

在前文两字组连续变调中我们发现，抚顺话的阴平在两字组末字位置均变为中降调[43]，阴平的变调与前字无关，而是由其自身所在位置决定的，因此这个情况对我们拟研究的问题来说是一个很好的证据。图 5 展示了后字阴平在不同前字声调条件下的音高模式。

图 5 阴平在不同前字声调条件下的音高模式

从平均音高曲线上可以看到，变调之后的阴平在不同的前字声调条件下，音高依然有些微差异，尤其是阴平的起点位置。根据前文两字组声调的协同发音分析，我们同样通过单因素重复测量 ANOVA 检验前字不同调类对后字阴平五个音高点的音高值的影响，并尝试根据表层音高实现对第一个音节的终点音高进行分类。ANOVA 结果总结在表 7 中。表中的 T_x 表示前字为任意声调。

表 7 阴平位于后字位置时五个音高点的 ANOVA 分析结果

声调组合	0%	25%	50%	75%	100%
T_x+T1	F=3.056 $p=0.037^*$	F=1.179 $p=0.328$	F=0.568 $p=0.639$	F=0.497 $p=0.686$	F=0.202 $p=0.894$

表中，“****”表示 $p < 0.001$ ，“***”表示 $p < 0.01$ ，“**”表示 $p < 0.05$ 。

统计检验结果显示，阴平处于后字位置时，前字调类对其起点音高具有显著作用，对其他音高点无显著作用。事后两两成对比较和音高曲线图都显示，低终点的去声后阴平音高较低，而高终点的阳平和上声后阴平音高相对较高，这与前文顺向协同发音的情况基本一致。

由此可见，阴平在后字位置时虽然都变为中降调，但在前接不同声调时具体的音高表现又有细微差异，其中起点音高的差异尤为显著，主要受到前字声调的顺向同化作用。

3.1.2 协同发音对变调上声的逆向作用

在抚顺话两字组连读变调中，上声在阴平和上声前面均变为类似阳平的中升调[34]，我们同样在协同发音层面对上声位于前字时的连读变调现象进行进一步的分析，看看在发生了连读变调之后，声调之间是否还存在协同发音作用。图 6 展示了变调上声在不同后字条件下的音高模式。

图 6 上声在不同后字声调条件下的音高模式

我们同样通过单因素重复测量 ANOVA 检验后字不同调类对前字上声五个音高点的音高值的影响。ANOVA 结果总结在表 8 中。表中的 T_x 表示前字为阴平和上声。

表 8 上声位于前字位置时五个音高点的 ANOVA 分析结果

声调组合	0%	25%	50%	75%	100%
$T3+T_x$	F=0.253	F=1.058	F=4.764	F=8.399	F=8.829
	$p=0.619$	$p=0.314$	$p=0.039^*$	$p=0.008^{**}$	$p=0.007^{**}$

表中，“****”表示 $p < 0.001$ ，“***”表示 $p < 0.01$ ，“**”表示 $p < 0.05$ 。

统计检验结果显示，上声处于前字位置时，后字调类对其中间点、75%时间点以及末点音高均具有显著作用。音高曲线图表明，具有低音目标的上声前的上声，其音高值要比阴平前的上声略高，这与前文逆向协同发音的情况也基本一致，即前字音高主要受到后字声调的逆向异化作用，且作用范围也不仅止于前字声调的

终点音高，可能会向前覆盖至中间点。据此我们认为，在抚顺话连读变调的基础上可能还会进一步发生语音层面的协同发音作用。

3.2 连读变调与协同发音关系探讨

抚顺话与北京话连读变调规则最大的不同是阴平和上声的变调：阴平在两字组末字位置变为中降调[43]，上声位于阴平和上声前时均变成与阳平相似的中升调[34]。崔平、王韞佳（2019）认为，根据共时层面声学分析的结果，上声在阴平和上声前的变调可能是逆向协同发音和减少曲折原则共同作用的结果。另外，上声在阴平前的变化以及阴平自身的变调或许还涉及历时层面的因素，即抚顺话的阴平早期也可能是一个低降调，是它的异化作用导致了前字上声变为升调，由它导致的上声变调在连调格式中保留下来，而它自己的单字调形式却发生了变化，因此阴平在共时分布上的差异，体现的可能正是阴平调的历时演变的方向和路径：低降调>中降调>平调。

在此基础上，本文发现在不考虑连读变调的顺向作用中，只有低调上声的起点音高受到了前字声调的影响；而当我们把变调层面的音高变化也考虑进来，就会发现位于后字位置调型变为降调的阴平，其起点音高也会受到前字声调的顺向作用。另外，在不考虑连读变调的逆向作用中，即只考虑本调层的话，我们发现逆向作用不会对低音点起作用；而当我们把变调层的音高变化也考虑进来，结果显示逆向作用同样不会对变调上声的起点音高起作用，这与对本调层的阳平的效应一致，即逆向作用主要影响的是前接声调的非低音点，不论是在本调层还是变调层。

综上，我们认为抚顺话中的连读变调现象可能是由声调间协同发音作用和减少曲折原则共同触发所致，而固化后的音系层面的连读变调可能又会进一步发生语音层面的协同发音作用，进而导致声调产生更细微的差异。另外，综合所有结果来看，协同发音的作用目标无论是在本调层还是变调层都是一致的，顺向作用主要影响后接声调的起点音高，逆向作用主要影响前接声调的非低音特征点。

4. 结论与讨论

虽然抚顺话的单字调调型与北京话非常相似，但从本文的分析可以看出，其两字组连读变调模式与北京话有明显不同。抚顺话的阴平在两字组末字位置变为中降调[43]，上声位于阴平和上声前时均变成与阳平相似的中升调[34]。

抚顺话中的协同发音作用既遵循了前人归纳的跨语言的普遍共性，同时也有其特异性。与大部分语言一致，其协同发音作用是双向的，顺向协同发音主要表现为同化作用，而逆向协同发音则表现为异化作用。另外，与普通话一致，在具体效应幅度上，抚顺话也表现出了一定的高低调不对称性，高调是逆向作用中更好的目标声调，并且这种效应在本调层和变调层都是一致的。但是，不论是音高图还是统计检验结果，均表明抚顺话中的逆向作用大于顺向作用，这与大部分语言中顺向作

用大于逆向作用不同，如普通话、泰语、越南语等，同时也有别于顺向作用和逆向作用幅度相似的南京话和马来西亚闽南话。

另外，前文提到，作为逆向作用的触发声调，阳平的作用不大好解释，阴平位于高起点的去声前时，其音高均值较低，位于具有低音目标的上声前时，其音高均值较高，且与其他声调存在显著差异，但位于同样是高起点的阳平前时，却没有表现出与上声相同的作用方式，其音高均值仍然较低，这个结果似乎暗示着逆向作用的关联特征也许并非触发声调的起点，而是声调底层的音系特征，上声在底层音系层面是一个低调，且具有低音目标，因此更容易导致前面声调的异化抬高，而阳平起点虽然是非高的，但本质上不是低调，因此在逆向作用中没有表现出与上声相同的作用方式。当然，以上分析只是一种猜测，沈晓楠（1992）、王韞佳（1993）还曾提到一种声调的动力作用，即声调的调形走向、基频的变化趋势可能也会对前后声调的 f_0 高低产生影响，他们发现尽管阴平和阳平终点的音高特征均为高，但阳平 f_0 向上的运动趋势会使其后面声调的音高上升。因此，我们猜想阳平 f_0 向上的运动趋势可能也会异化导致其前接声调在音高上比 f_0 向下运动至低音目标的上声前要低。

总之，我们在文中呈现了一个关于抚顺话声调实现的声学研究，特别关注由相邻声调语境引起的声学变化——连读变调和协同发音，这也是一种基于声调变化范畴类型的传统分类。从理论上来看，协同发音和连读变调并不相同，由相邻声调引起的语音协同发音作用不会影响声调曲拱的区别性，尽管可能会存在显著的 f_0 偏差，但声调实现的 f_0 曲拱仍如预期一样类似于声调的典型实现，符合其标准的声调形状；而音系上的连读变调交替通常会引起声调曲拱的显著变化，它们要么改变 f_0 轨迹，要么大大提高整个 f_0 调阶，从而使得其表面 f_0 可能与标准 f_0 曲拱的特征不一致并且从声学层面不可预测。但在具体方言的研究中我们发现，两种声调变化类型之间的界限并非理论上认为的那样简单明晰，连读变调在类型特征上与协同发音也有许多共同之处。从本文的结果来看，一方面，协同发音和连读变调并不相同，协同发音作用并不改变基频的移动方向，而连读变调往往会改变音高曲线的特征走向，使其与标准 f_0 曲拱显著不同；另一方面，二者之间又有着紧密的联系，连读变调很可能是声调间协同发音作用的固化结果，上声位于前字位置时的变调模式可能是由声调间协同发音作用和减少曲折原则共同触发所致；而固化后的音系层面的连读变调可能又会进一步发生语音层面的协同发音作用，阴平位于后字位置的变调和上声位于前字位置的变调，均会受其相邻声调影响而产生更细微的差异，即协同发音的作用目标无论是在本调层还是变调层都是一致的。

本文目前仅关注了抚顺话两字组中声调间的协同发音与连读变调现象，在三字组乃至语调中这两种声调实现形式又会有怎样不同的表现？另外，要想更好区分界定连读变调和协同发音的关系，可能还要进一步结合听辨实验。由于篇幅所限，本文未能对以上问题加以研究讨论，我们将在未来对这些问题进行更深入和专门的研究。

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Formation of Reduplicative Polysyllabic Onomatopoeia in Mandarin

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The article applied OT to reanalyze polysyllabic reduplicative onomatopoeia in Mandarin. The structure of different patterns of reduplication depends on different choices of alignment constraints, which rank high for all the patterns. We defined two markedness constraints to explain the segment variation in prepositive and postpositive reduplicant. The sonority contour of the reduplicant is analogous to the base but narrows in amplitude. For patterns without segment changes, markedness constraints rank lower than the correspondence constraint of Ident-BR. A hierarchy of restriction on different patterns proposed at the end corresponds to the frequency of occurrence and perception by native speakers.

1. Introduction

In contemporary Mandarin, most words consist of two syllables forming a typical metrical foot. Giving the general “character - syllable - morpheme correspondence”, a disyllabic compound word made up of two morphemes is the most common word-formation. Onomatopoeia, however, is a kind of single-morpheme word where one or more syllables represent one meaning. Different from other single-morpheme Mandarin words such as transliterated words, polysyllabic onomatopoeia always derive from monosyllabic or disyllabic ones by reduplication. According to Kager (1999), some cross-linguistic principles regulate the derivation of words by reduplication. Therefore, the analysis of the derivation of Mandarin polysyllabic onomatopoeia could shed new light on reduplication constraints of Optimality Theory and also provide a way to investigate the interaction between prosody and morphology.

Former researches on Mandarin have explored the segment variation of derivative onomatopoeia and revealed some general tendencies. Zhu (1982) was the first to study the formation of Mandarin onomatopoeia by reduplication, proposing that quadrisyllabic onomatopoeia derived from monosyllabic ones by reduplicating twice, changing onset at the first time and rhyme at the second. Based on that, Wang (1996) summarized six kinds of Mandarin onomatopoeic metrical structure and put forward the iambic form in disyllabic onomatopoeia. Namely, the former syllable tends to be “dark”, whereas the latter is comparatively “bright”. Shi (1995) claims that segments in quadrisyllabic onomatopoeia obey the sonority sequence principle that the nuclei in the second foot are more sonorant than the first, while in the same foot, the onset in the second syllable is more sonorant than the first syllable. Ran (2009), however, made use of “brightness”

(depending on the gap between first and second formant frequency) instead of sonority to account for the formation of onomatopoeia with different rhymes and demonstrated with perceptual evidence. In general, sonority and brightness explained the similar tendency of the segment variation of derived onomatopoeia in different aspects. Though their hypothesis can interpret most phenomena, there exist quadrisyllabic onomatopoeias that seem to violate the rules such as [xua li xua la] and [tə^{hi} ts^{hi} k^{ha} tɕ^{ha}]. Whether they derived in the same way as others and how to account for them remain to be explored.

Yeh (2011) employed alignment and adjacency to analyze ABAB and AABB Mandarin quadrisyllabic onomatopoeia. However, there are some problems in the analysis of the AABB form. In the paper, the second and third syllables in AABB were taken as the base, which seems to disobey cross-linguistic generalizations. Moreover, the paper didn't explain the asymmetry of the two patterns, specifically, why some disyllable can only undergo ABAB reduplication instead of the other. Furthermore, there is a lack of accounts for onomatopoeia with segment variations.

The purpose of this paper is to apply Optimality Theory to reanalyze polysyllabic Mandarin onomatopoeia, especially those going through segment variations, and try to formalize a unified set of constraints for different patterns. The paper is organized as follows. The second part gives a brief description of different patterns of Mandarin onomatopoeia. The third part proposes a series of markedness, correspondence, and alignment constraints to account for different types of reduplications. The last part discusses on restriction hierarchy of various patterns and relevant semantic association.

2. Patterns of Mandarin Onomatopoeia

Shao (1981) generalized two groups of patterns of Mandarin onomatopoeia listed below according to the way of formation. Tones are not included since onomatopoeia always share the same tone.

2.1 Monosyllable and Its Reduplicative Pattern

Table 1. Monosyllable and Its Reduplicative Pattern

Pattern	Example	IPA
A	哗 (sound of water flow)	[xua]
AA	汪汪 (barking)	[uaŋ uaŋ]
AAA	蹬蹬蹬 (sound of going upstairs)	[təŋ təŋ təŋ]
AAAA	砰砰砰砰 (knock at door)	[p ^h əŋ p ^h əŋ p ^h əŋ p ^h əŋ]

Polysyllabic onomatopoeia can derive from monosyllable by reduplicating several times. Theoretically, monosyllable can be reduplicated infinite times, while practically, onomatopoeia longer than 4 syllables are rare to see.

2.2 Disyllable and Its Reduplicative Pattern

Table 2. Disyllable and Its Reduplicative Pattern

Pattern	Example	IPA
AB	哗啦; 滴答; 咕嘟; 噼啪	[xua la]; [ti ta]; [ku tu]; [p ^h i p ^h a]
AABB	滴滴答答 (sound of rain drops)	[ti ti ta ta]
ABAB	咕嘟咕嘟 (sound of drinking water)	[ku tu ku tu]
ABB	哗啦啦 (sound of water flow)	[xua la la]
AAB	滴滴答 (sound of rain drops)	[ti ti ta]
CDAB	稀里哗啦 (broken sound of glassware)	[ɕi li xua la]
ACBD	劈里啪啦 (sound of firecrackers)	[p ^h i li p ^h a la]

As is shown in Table 2, trisyllable and quadrisyllabic onomatopoeia can also derive from disyllable by partial or total reduplication. Some interesting phenomena can be found from the conditions of polysyllabic patterns.

AB stands for the base in quadrisyllabic and trisyllabic patterns. The examples show that apart from sharing the same tone, two syllables in the AB pattern can also share the same onset, such as [ti^h tu^h], or the same rhyme, such as [ku tu] and [xua la]. Words like these are always derived from a single morpheme and one of the two syllables can be regarded as a base. For example, in [xua la], [la] is a variation of monosyllable [xua] by reduplication. Syllables in AB without derivative relationship are combined to represent a single morpheme, such as [ku tɕi].

When disyllable evolves to trisyllable by partial reduplication, whether ABB or AAB pattern is chosen depends on the shared segment of the base AB. ABB pattern can only derive from disyllable with the same rhyme. Conversely, the AAB pattern can only originate from disyllabic words with the same onset. Examples are shown below.

Table 3. Conditions of AAB and ABB

AB	ABB	AAB
[xua la]	[<u>xua</u> la la]	*[xua <u>xua</u> la]
[ti ta]	*[<u>ti</u> ta ta]	[<u>ti</u> ti ta]

II: FORMATION OF REDUPLICATIVE

Quadrisyllabic onomatopoeia stemmed from disyllable counterparts by total reduplication. It is noteworthy that there exists asymmetry between AABB and ABAB patterns. ABAB reduplication is allowed for all the disyllabic words. AABB pattern, on the contrary, can only accept some disyllabic onomatopoeia, as the following examples illustrate.

Table 4. Asymmetry of AABB and ABAB

AB	ABAB	AABB
[p ^h u t ^h ong] (sound of jumping into water)	[p ^h u t ^h ong p ^h u t ^h ong]	*[p ^h u p ^h u t ^h ong t ^h ong]
[ku tu]	[ku tu ku tu]	*[ku ku tu tu]
[ti ta]	[ti ta ti ta]	[ti ti ta ta]
[xua la]	[xua la xua la]	[xua xua la la]

A way to account for the asymmetry is to compare other word categories with the same pattern of reduplication. Onomatopoeia imitates the sound of some kind of movement and their function in sentences is similar to verb or adjective. In Mandarin, ABAB is also the form of verbal reduplication to show a short and tentative action. For example, [ɛiou ɛi](to take a rest) can be reduplicated as [ɛiou ɛi ɛiou ɛi]. AABB, however, is the pattern of adjective reduplication to increase the degree of a certain quality. For instance, the degree of happiness in [kau kau ɛing ɛing] is higher than [kau ɛing] (happy) due to reduplication. Consequently, reduplication in onomatopoeic patterns is influenced by the continuity of the movement imitated. For the onomatopoeia simulating momentary movement, the only acceptable pattern is ABAB. Therefore, [p^hu t^hong] which means the sound of jumping into the water can only go through ABAB reduplication. For continuous movement, both ABAB and AABB are acceptable.

In terms of quadrisyllabic onomatopoeia that have gone through segment changes, the distinct conditions of ACBD and CDAB patterns are similar to those of trisyllable patterns. The reduplicative pattern of the disyllabic base with the same onset is ACBD, while for the disyllabic base with the same rhyme it is CDAB, which is shown in the following table.

Table 5. Conditions of ACBD and CDAB

AB	CDAB	ACBD
[xua la]	[ɛi li xua la]	—
[ku lu] (unclear voice)	[tei li ku lu]	—
[ti ta]	—	[ti li ta la]
[p ^h i p ^h a]	—	[p ^h i li p ^h a la]

3 Constraints of OT for Reduplication

As we can see from the examples above, AABB and ABAB seem to be special cases of ACBD and CDAB respectively when CD equals to AB, which implies that there might be some general constraints applied to all of the patterns.

In CDAB, the CD is a prepositive reduplicant. Take [ei li xua la] and [tei li ku lu] as an example. Comparing with the base, we can find that the nucleus in the reduplicant [i] has the feature of [+high][-back], while the nucleus feature in the base syllables is the complement [-high] or [+back]. The consonant in C become palatalized because of place assimilation. In ACBD, however, C and D are postpositive reduplicants. The rhyme in reduplicant remains the same as the base whereas the onset changes to a liquid [l], the most sonorant consonant in Mandarin.

The question then turns to how to describe the constraints for the segment variation properly. Two hypotheses can be proposed from the observation.

Hypothesis 1: Nuclei in prefix reduplicant must be [i] and onset in suffix reduplicant must be [l].

Hypothesis 2: Nuclei in prepositive reduplicant are less sonorant than the base while onset in postpositive reduplicant is more sonorant than the base.

Though they sound reasonable, there are problems in both of the hypotheses. If Hypothesis 1 is true, we should suppose [p^{hi} p^{ha}] and [ti ta] become [p^{hi} p^{hi} p^{hi} p^{ha}] and [ti ti ti ta] by CDAB pattern respectively. However, both changes are not acceptable. It can be inferred that there exists some relationship between nuclei in reduplicant and base and Hypothesis 1 doesn't reflect it. Hypothesis 2 reveals the relation by sonority hierarchy theory. Since there is no difference in sonority between the first and third syllable in [ti ti ti ta], the CDAB pattern cannot be applied. But there remain problems as Hypothesis 2 fails to explain why the nuclei of reduplicant become [i] rather than other less-sonorant vowels. For example, both [i] and [u] are less sonorant than [a] because of [+high] feature, but [ti li ta la] is acceptable while [tu lu ta la] is not.

Considering the sonority hierarchy of the whole phonetic inventory, it is obvious that in Mandarin, [i] is the least sonorant vowel, and [l] is the most sonorant consonant. Since vowels are more sonorant than consonants, it turns out that the changes aim to narrow the sonority distance between vowels and consonants in the reduplicant while keeping the shape of sonority contour of the base. As the typical Mandarin syllable structure is a CV, which is a rising sonority contour, we narrow the sonority distance in the postpositive reduplicant by increasing the starting point as much as possible while decreasing the ending point in the prepositive reduplicant. This could explain why [ti ta] cannot become CDAB since the vowel in [ti] is already the least sonorant vowel that cannot be decreased in sonority. [tu lu ta la] is not acceptable since the sonority distance in [tu] has not been narrowed to the utmost. The constraints can also explain why CDAB requires AB to share the same rhyme. Since the rhyme becomes [i] in the reduplicant, the base rhyme should be the same to maintain the shape of the sonority contour between reduplicant and base. The markedness constraints can be described below.

3.1 Markedness Constraints

Differ-BR-N: Decrease the sonority of the nucleus to the utmost in the prepositional reduplicant. Assign one violation mark for every nucleus in the prepositional reduplicant that isn't lowered in sonority to the utmost compared with the base.

Differ-BR-O: Increase the sonority of onset to the utmost in postpositional reduplicant. Assign one violation mark for every onset in the postpositional reduplicant that isn't elevated in sonority to the utmost compared with the base.

These markedness constraints show that in the abstract, the sonority contour of prepositive and postpositive reduplicant is similar to the asymmetry of onset and coda of a syllable. It is a universal tendency that the sonority of onset is comparatively lower while the coda consonant is higher. The lower start and higher-end in syllables are reflected in replicant as the prepositive sonority contour is narrowed down to the bottom while the postpositive one is narrowed upward to the peak.

Contrary to markedness constraints, the correspondence constraints indicate faithfulness. There are three relative constraints defined as follows.

3.2 Correspondence Constraints

Ident-IO: The stem in input and output should be the same.

Ident-BR: The correspondent segment in base and reduplicant should be the same. Assign one violation mark for every segment in reduplicant that is not the same as the correspondent segment in the base.

Contiguity: Adjacent segments in the input should be adjacent in the output.

While the markedness and correspondence constraints regulate the segment variations, alignment constraints determine the structure of the reduplicative pattern.

3.2 Alignment Constraints

Align-R(PW, M): For every prosodic word there is a morpheme in the stem such that the right edge of the prosodic word aligns with the right edge of the morpheme.

Align-L(foot, M): For every foot, there is a morpheme in the stem such that the left edge of the foot aligns with the left edge of the morpheme.

Align-R(foot, RED): For every foot, there is a reduplicant such that the right edge of the foot aligns with the right edge of the reduplicant.

Align-R(PW, RED): For every prosodic word there is a reduplicant such that the right edge of the prosodic word aligns with the right edge of the reduplicant.

The following tableaux show the ranking of constraints for different patterns. Ident-IO ranks high in all the patterns since the base in output remains the same as the input. Alignment constraints also rank high since they determine the order of reduplicant and base. The difference among patterns lies in the rank of contiguity, Ident-BR, and markedness constraints.

JI: FORMATION OF REDUPLICATIVE

Tableau 1. CDAB pattern (base is underlined in candidates):

/RED + pa ta/	Align-R(PW, M)	Contiguity	Ident-IO	Differ-BR-N	Differ-BR-O	Ident-BR
a.[pi ti <u>pa ta</u>]						**
b.[pa ta <u>pa ta</u>]				**!		
c.[pi li <u>pa ta</u>]						***!
d.[<u>pa li ta</u> la]	*!	*				***
e.[pi <u>pa ti ta</u>]		*!			*	**
f.[pi li <u>pa la</u>]			*!			**

Tableau 2. ACBD pattern

/RED + p ^{hi} p ^{ha} /	Align-L (foot, M)	Ident-IO	Differ-BR-N	Differ-BR-O	Contiguity	Ident-BR
a.[p ^{hi} li p ^{ha} la]					*	**
b.[p ^{hi} p ^{ha} li la]	*!					**
c.[p ^{hi} la p ^{ha} la]			*!		*	***
d.[p ^{hi} p ^{hi} p ^{ha} p ^{ha}]				**!	*	
e.[p ^{ha} li p ^{ha} la]		*!			*	***

Tableau 3. ACAB pattern

/RED + xua xua/	Align-L (foot, M)	Ident-IO	Differ-BR-N	Differ-BR-O	Contiguity	Ident-BR
a.[<u>xua li xua</u> la]					*	***
b.[<u>xua la xua</u> la]			*!		*	**
c.[<u>xua xua</u> la la]	*!					**
d.[<u>xua ei xua</u> ei]				**!	*	
e.[<u>ei li xua</u> la]		**!			*	**
f.[<u>xua li xua</u> li]					*	****!

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As is illustrated in the tableaux above, Ident-BR ranks low in CDAB, ACBD, and ACAB pattern because segments in reduplicant are different from base. In contrast, markedness constraints rank high. The order of constraints of ACAB and ACBD is the same since ACAB is a special case for ACBD. CDAB and ACBD differ from each other in a distinct choice of alignment and also in the rank of contiguity. According to the order, [ti ta] can only go through ACBD change to [ti li ta la] but not CDAB pattern [ti ti ti ta] because it violates the Differ-BR-N. Conversely, [k^ha tɕ^ha] can form CDAB as [tɕ^hi tɕ^hi k^ha tɕ^ha] but cannot become [k^ha li tɕ^ha la] because [k^ha] and [tɕ^ha] cannot be regarded as a morpheme individually, which violate alignment constraint.

Tableau 4. AABB pattern

/RED + ti ta/	Align-R (foot, RED)	Ident-BR	Ident-IO	Differ-BR-O	Differ-BR-N	Contiguity
a. [t̥i t̥i t̥a t̥a] ^{ㄟㄟ}				**		*
b. [t̥i t̥a t̥i t̥a]	*!			**		
c. [t̥i li t̥a la]		**!				*
d. [t̥i t̥i la la]			*!	*		*

Tableau 5. ABAB pattern

/RED + ku tu/	Align-R (PW, RED)	Ident-BR	Contiguity	Ident-IO	Differ-BR-O	Differ-BR-N
a. [k̥u t̥u k̥u t̥u] ^{ㄟㄟ}					**	
b. [k̥u k̥u t̥u t̥u]			*!		**	*
c. [t̥ei li k̥u t̥u]	*!	***				
d. [k̥u t̥u lu lu]		**!				
e. [k̥u lu k̥u lu]				*!	*	

In the AABB and ABAB pattern, Ident-BR ranks high while markedness constraints rank low. The difference consists in the choice of alignment and ranking of contiguity. As has been mentioned in the previous part, all the disyllable onomatopoeia can go through ABAB reduplication but not AABB due to semantic restrictions.

The tableaux above illustrate the constraints ranking for quadrisyllabic patterns, which could be applied to account for trisyllable ones. As is mentioned in the second part, trisyllable patterns can only derive from AB sharing the same onset or rhyme. Providing the derivative relationship of A and B, it is assumed that trisyllabic onomatopoeia is formed by twice of reduplication. AAB is formed by pattern CDAB and

AABB. For example, [ti ti ta] derives from [ta] to [ti ta] and then to [ti ti ta] by partial reduplication. Similarly, ABB is formed by the combination of ACBD and ABAB. As an example, [xua la la] originates from [xua] to [xua la] by total reduplication followed by partial reduplication to [xua la la].

3. Conclusion and Discussions

The paper applied OT to reanalyze reduplication in Mandarin polysyllabic onomatopoeia. The structure of different patterns of reduplication relies on different choices of alignment constraints, which rank high for all the patterns. As there is an insufficient account for segment variation in CDAB and ACBD patterns in previous research, we come up with two markedness constraints to explain the variation of sonority contour in prepositive and postpositive reduplicant, which reveals the abstract similarity of sonority structure between syllable and prosodic word. For patterns without segment changes, markedness constraints rank lower than the correspondence constraint of Ident-BR. It is also suggested that trisyllabic patterns derive from monosyllable by the combination of different reduplicative patterns.

Comparing the degree of restriction, quadrisyllabic patterns form a hierarchy from the least restricted to the most restricted ones, which is “ABAB < AABB < CDAB < ACBD < ACAB”.

Table 6. Restriction Hierarchy of Quadrisyllabic Patterns

Pattern	Scope of Restriction	Restriction on Base
ABAB		none
AABB	AB	continuous movement
CDAB	AB	same rhyme; nucleus ≠ [i]
<u>B</u> BA	A	same onset; A = morpheme
<u>A</u> BB	A	same rhyme; A = morpheme
ACBD		same onset; onset ≠ [l]; each syllable = morpheme
ACAB		same onset and rhyme; onset ≠ [l]; each syllable = morpheme

The restriction of different patterns is connected with their distribution and frequency in Mandarin. Quadrisyllabic onomatopoeia with [li] as the second syllable and [la] as the last syllable is the most common form of onomatopoeia since it is allowed by all the patterns. The mirrored shape of sonority contour between the first and second foot in ACBD and CDAB, like a small wave followed by a big wave, is the typical form of quadrisyllabic onomatopoeia. It also conforms to perceptual principle as people are more sensitive to the sound of high frequency. By contrast, words like [pa tɛi] and [ka tɕi] are

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rare to see because they are the opposite of a small wave preceding a big wave. Semantically, these words are always used to describe the negative meaning, as [pa tɕi] indicates the sound of goods broken by falling, and [ka tɕi] represents the sound of broken twigs. The association with negative meaning even spread to other word categories, such as the quadrisyllabic state word in Mandarin, where only the first syllable has meaning, followed by three meaningless syllables as the suffix. For example, in adjective [ʂa lə pa tɕi] and [k^hu pə la tɕi], which describe “stupid” and “bitter” respectively, the first syllable is a meaningful morpheme. The second syllable with a schwa serves as a transition. The last two syllables with downward shrinking sonority contour indicating the negative meaning. The relation between rare sound patterns and negative meaning might result from the psychological effect of disharmonious sound raising some discomfort in people’s minds, which need to be examined by further research.

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Restrictions on Consonant + Glide (CG) Sequences in Chinese Varieties

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Restrictions on CG onsets involve both OCP and anti-OCP constraints: dissimilation of major articulator features for distinctiveness of phonetic cues, and agreement of dependent features like backness for ease of articulation. In some languages (Mandarin and Shangfu) the feature [back] plays a key role, while Putian ranks CG backness agreement relatively low.

1. Introduction

Some languages, like Korean, allow any consonant + glide (CG) combinations, while other languages, like Kirundi, avoid all CG sequences. Many languages have restrictions on CG onsets: for example, some varieties of Italian disallow palatals preceding [j] and [w], and some varieties of American English disallow coronals followed by the glide [j]. In Chinese varieties, consonant + glide (CG) combinations are allowed, but with a relatively complex system of restrictions. We examine restrictions on CG clusters in Mandarin Chinese, Shangfu Chinese, and Putian Chinese, and investigate the features that play a role in restricting CG onsets. We argue that both OCP (in particular, No Lab + Lab) and CG [back] agreement constraints are needed to explain onset grammaticality in Chinese varieties.

According to Liu & Repetti (2019), in Mandarin, no fricatives or affricates can precede [j, ɥ], except the palatals [tʃ, tʃʰ, ʃ]. In contrast, all fricatives and affricates can precede [w], except the palatals. Furthermore, Mandarin velars are disallowed before [j, ɥ], yet can occur before the velar glide [w], and labials cannot combine with labial glide [ɥ, w] as onsets. [tɥ] and [tʰɥ] are also banned, but all other CG sequences are legal. Overall, two principles are needed to explain Mandarin CG onset restrictions: *LabLab (1)¹ and various [back] agreement constraints (2-4). The three backness agreement constraints require the two segments of certain consonant + glide sequences to be both

¹ Duanmu's (2000: 32) *Articulator Dissimilation Principle* ("Identical articulators cannot occur in succession") can account for some but not all of the restrictions on Mandarin CG onsets.

[+ba] or both [-ba]. If the word-initial consonant is [0ba], then the relevant Agree[back] constraint is violated.²

- (1) *LabLab – A labial consonant cannot occur with a labial glide [ɥ]/[w]
- (2) Agree[back]: C_[-son, +cont] j – A [-son, +cont] consonant (affricate or fricative) and the following glide [j] must have the same backness value: [-back]
- (3) Agree[back]: C_[-son] ɥ – An obstruent and the following glide [ɥ] must have the same backness value: [-back]
- (4) Agree[back]: DorG – A dorsal consonant (palatal or velar) and any following glide ([j ɥ w]) must have the same backness value

This study analyzes CG patterns in two other varieties of Chinese: one that is similar to Mandarin (Shangfu Chinese) and one that is quite different (Putian Chinese). Shangfu, as part of Central Plains varieties, is geographically closer to and differs minimally from Standard Chinese (Mandarin). Spoken in southern Henan and northern Anhui in eastern China, Shangfu’s consonant inventory is similar to Mandarin Chinese, except that Shangfu has the voiced fricative [z]. The first author is a native speaker of this variety. In contrast, Putian, spoken in the central area of Fujian Province, differs maximally from Mandarin. It belongs to the coastal Min language group with approximately 5 million native speakers. Without palatals [tɕ, tɕ^h, ɕ] or retroflexes [tʂ, tʂ^h, ʂ, ʐ], its consonant inventory includes the lateral fricative [ɬ] and velar nasal [ŋ] which Mandarin and Shangfu lack. The Shangfu data in the following discussion come from Compilation Commission of Chorography of Putian (1964, 2001). We analyze Cj (§2), Cɥ (§3), and Cw (§4) sequences in Shangfu, Mandarin, and Putian, and conclude (§5) that Shangfu imposes even stricter backness agreement requirements on CG sequences than Mandarin does, while Putian is less restrictive.

2. C+j in Shangfu, Mandarin, and Putian

In (5), we see that Putian allows all Cj sequences, whereas Shangfu and Mandarin behave similarly to each other regarding Cj sequences.³

² The backness feature specification of [j] and [ɥ] is [-back], while [w] is [+back]. Furthermore, we analyze the labial consonants and non-palatal coronals as [0 back], the palatal consonants as [-back], and the velars as [+back] (Riggle 2011, Kenstowicz 1994, Hayes 2011, etc.).

³ The “—” symbol is used when a consonant is not present in the inventory. Labiodental [f], palatals [tɕ, tɕ^h, ɕ] and retroflexes [tʂ, tʂ^h, ʂ, ʐ] are not in Putian’s consonant inventory, nor are [s] and [z]. The lateral fricative [ɬ] and velar nasal [ŋ] are absent in Mandarin and Shangfu, and [z] is not found in Mandarin.

(5) Cj in Shangfu, Mandarin, and Putian

	Cj	Shangfu	Mandarin	Putian
labial	p	√	√	√
	p ^h	√	√	√
	m	√	√	√
	f	*	*	—
non-palatal coronal	t	√	√	√
	t ^h	√	√	√
	n	√	√	√
	l	√	√	√
	ts	*	*	√
	ts ^h	*	*	√
	s	*	*	—
	ʃ	—	—	√
	ʒ	*	—	—
	tʂ	*	*	—
	tʂ ^h	*	*	—
	ʂ	*	*	—
palatal	tɕ	√	√	—
	tɕ ^h	√	√	—
	ɕ	√	√	—
velar	k	*	*	√
	k ^h	*	*	√
	x	*	*	√
	ŋ	—	—	√

The Shangfu and Mandarin data can be accounted for with the constraints in (2) and (4): fricatives and affricates, as well as palatals and velars, must have the same backness value as the following glide [j]: [-back]. However, Putian allows fricatives and affricates, as well as velars to precede [j]. An interesting effect of Putian's tolerance for Cj sequences can be found in its consonant inventory. Duanmu (2000: 31) claims that Mandarin combinations [tsj, ts^hj, sj] could be palatalized and became [tɕ, tɕ^h, ɕ]. The present study argues that this sound change can be interpreted as an effect of the backness agreement constraint in (2). Since Putian does not require backness agreement of these sequences, they were not palatalized, and palatal consonants are not present in the Putian consonant inventory.

3. C+ɥ in Shangfu, Mandarin, and Putian

In (6), we see that only labial + [ɥ] groups are penalized in Putian. Shangfu and Mandarin are more restrictive and behave similarly to each other.

(6) Cɥ in Shangfu, Mandarin, and Putian

	Cɥ	Shangfu	Mandarin	Putian
labial	p	*	*	*
	p ^h	*	*	*
	m	*	*	*
	f	*	*	—
non-palatal coronal	t	*	*	√
	t ^h	*	*	√
	n	√	√	√
	l	√	√	√
	ts	*	*	√
	ts ^h	*	*	√
	s	*	*	—
	ʃ	—	—	√
	z	*	—	—
	tʂ	*	*	—
	tʂ ^h	*	*	—
	ʂ	*	*	—
	ʐ	*	*	—
palatal	tɕ	√	√	—
	tɕ ^h	√	√	—
	ɕ	√	√	—
velar	k	*	*	√
	k ^h	*	*	√
	x	*	*	√
	ŋ	—	—	√

The Shangfu and Mandarin facts are accounted for with the constraints in (1) and (3): the labial consonants are banned before [ɥ] because of (1), and the non-palatal obstruents + [ɥ] are penalized by (3).⁴ In Putian, on the other hand, only the labial + [ɥ] clusters are penalized; all other sequences of non-labials (coronals or velars) plus [ɥ] are permitted: 强[kɥaŋ] ‘strong’, 却[k^hɥau] ‘but’, 仰[ŋɥaŋ] ‘look up’, 靴[xɥau] ‘boot’. The only relevant constraint for Putian is defined in (7).

⁴ The constraint in (4) can also account for the ban on dorsal consonant + [ɥ] sequences, but since all dorsal consonants in Mandarin and Shangfu are obstruents, the constraint in (3) is sufficient.

(7) Putian constraint: *C_q-LabLab - A labial consonant cannot occur with [ɥ]

4. C+w in Shangfu, Mandarin, and Putian

In (8), we see that Putian allows any consonant to precede [w], while Mandarin is more restrictive, and Shangfu even more so.

(8) Cw in Shangfu, Mandarin, and Putian

	Cw	Shangfu	Mandarin	Putian
labial	p	*	*	√
	p ^h	*	*	√
	m	*	*	√
	f	*	*	—
non-palatal coronal	t	√	√	√
	t ^h	√	√	√
	n	√	√	√
	l	√	√	√
	ts	*	√	√
	ts ^h	*	√	√
	s	*	√	—
	ʃ	—	—	√
	z	*	—	—
	tʂ	*	√	—
	tʂ ^h	*	√	—
	ʂ	*	√	—
	ʐ	*	√	—
palatal	tɕ	*	*	—
	tɕ ^h	*	*	—
	ɕ	*	*	—
velar	k	√	√	√
	k ^h	√	√	√
	x	√	√	√
	ŋ	—	—	√

In Putian, the labial velar glide [w] can co-occur with all consonants, including a labial consonant [p, p^h, m], as in 杯[pwai] ‘cup’, 泼[p^hwa] ‘splash’ and 满[mwan] ‘full’. The adjacent labial features in onset are not banned here, while they are before the glide [ɥ] (§3), highlighting the restricted nature of [ɥ] as compared to [j, w]. The Shangfu and Mandarin patterns are accounted for by constraints (1) and (4): a labial consonant cannot precede the labial glide [w] (1), and a dorsal consonant can precede [w] because they

share the [+back] feature specification (4). The differences between Shangfu and Mandarin can be found among non-palatal coronal fricatives and affricates, which Shangfu bars before [w], whereas Mandarin does not. Thus, sequences like [tsw, ts^{hw}, sw, zw, tʂ^{hw}, tʂw, ʂw, zʂw] are missing in Shangfu, which indicates that Shangfu requires backness agreement not only with C[-son,+cont]+j and C[-son,+cont]+ɥ sequences, but also C[-son,+cont]+w sequences. We can account for this restriction with the constraint in (9) requiring affricates and fricatives to agree in backness with any following glide, not only [j, ɥ], but also [w].

(9) Shangfu constraint: Agree[back]: C[-son,+cont]G – A [-son, +cont] consonant (affricate or fricative) and any following glide ([j ɥ w]) must have the same backness value

5 Summary

We have seen that Putian is very tolerant of CG sequences, banning only labial consonants before [ɥ]. Mandarin and Shangfu are more restrictive, banning labial consonants + [ɥ] or [w]. Furthermore, unlike Putian, Mandarin and Shangfu also require backness agreement between fricatives/affricates and [j], obstruents and [ɥ], and dorsal consonants and any glide. Shangfu is even more concerned with backness agreement than Mandarin, requiring all fricatives and affricates to have the same backness value as any following glide. In conclusion, phonotactic constraints on CG sequences differ in these three varieties of Chinese with Putian being the most permissive and Shangfu the least, but all impose some restrictions that can be characterized as both OCP and anti-OCP constraints.

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Masked Phonological Contrast Maintained in Phonetics –Vowel Feature Remnant in Rugao Contracted Syllables

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In full syllable contraction, where only one vowel survives while the other vowel deletes, phonological distinction between a fully contracted disyllabic word and a monosyllabic lexical word seems to be lost. However, experimental evidence from Rugao syllable contraction suggests that the seemingly fully deleted vowel in full syllable contraction can leave feature remnant on the surviving vowel in the contracted syllable, altering the vowel quality of the latter without changing its category. The masked phonological contrast between the contracted vowel and a lexical vowel, as well as the lexical contrast between the two words, can thus be preserved in the phonetics.

1. Introduction

Syllable contraction in the context of Chinese means multiple syllables, usually two, merge into one syllable that has segments from both/all (Tseng 2005, Lin 2007). Rugao, a dialect of Mandarin spoken in Rugao, Jiangsu Province, China, is one of the many language/dialects of Chinese with abundant cases of syllable contraction. For example, the disyllabic word [ma²¹.sæn³³] ('right away') can be contracted into a single syllable [mæn²¹³] in *full contraction*. As opposed to *partial contraction*, in which the contracted output has more than one syllable, the process of full syllable contraction only leaves one syllable in the contracted output, possibly with the process of resyllabification. A fully contracted syllable may sound like a lexical syllable, i.e., a monosyllabic lexical word, with seemingly same segments and sometimes even same tone, making full syllable contraction seem like a neutralization process (Kuo 2010). The vowel in this extremely reduced form is thus comparable to a lexical vowel. The following pairs of Rugao data in (1)-(2), (3)-(4) and (5)-(6) are examples of fully contracted syllable resembling a lexical word in both segments and tone. For example, [sar²¹], the contracted form of [səʔ¹⁵. ar²¹] ('twelve'), sounds very similar to the monosyllabic word [sar²¹] ('spoon') to the ear of the speakers.

- (1) [mæn²¹³] 'right away', contraction of [ma²¹.sæn³³]
- (2) [mæn²¹³] 'aggressive'
- (3) [sar²¹] 'twelve', contraction of [səʔ¹⁵. ar²¹]
- (4) [sar²¹] 'spoon'
- (5) [tɛin²¹] 'experience', contraction of [tɛəŋ²¹. in²¹]

(6) [tɛin²¹] ‘pointy’

The two vowels in the word pairs above can be similar enough to belong to the same vowel category, and there are no other choices of phonetic symbols to represent the contracted form. However, this similarity does not guarantee the exact resemblance between the contracted vowel and a lexical vowel. This means that although a fully contracted syllable seems to have lost its distinction to a monosyllabic lexical word, the underlying lexical contrast can still be maintained in the phonetics. Compared to the partially contracted syllables, the fully contracted syllables are more consistent and predictable as to what segment survives and in what form. Despite the relative consistency and predictability, however, data of production and perception experiments indicate that a fully contracted syllable is distinguishable from a corresponding lexical syllable, and that listeners are ready to pick up subtle differences and differentiate the two syllables (Kuo 2010, Wong 2006).

It is likely that a cluster of cues are maintained in the contracted form, so that listeners can use them to make distinctions. Tone differences are proven to help both speakers and listeners maintain the contrast between a contracted and a lexical syllable in Mandarin and Cantonese (Kuo 2010, Wong 2006). Syllable length and vowel length are also helpful, according to Kuo (2010). With regards to the vowel quality, Kuo (2010) found inconsistent patterns between male and female participants. Only male speakers used a wider vowel space and higher vowels [i, u] in contracted syllables, but no difference was observed for female speakers. However, as the experiment did not control the deleting vowels, it is possible that the deleting vowel either does not change the surviving vowel because it is the same vowel, or that it ‘pulls’ the remaining vowels to different directions in the vowel space, which neutralizes the differences. A different picture may be seen if the deleting vowel is controlled.

In summary, there needs to be more in-depth studies on the phonetic properties of the segments in the contracted syllables. This study is dedicated to analyzing the phonetic properties of contracted syllables, starting with vowels in the fully contracted syllables in isolation (i.e., not in sentences or phrases). Compared to the relatively good predictability of consonants, vowels may undergo more complicated changes in this process, such as deletion, lenition, length change, and quality change. Vowels thus provide first-step information for us to look closer at contracted syllables and the process of syllable contraction. If the vowel deletion of syllable contraction is incomplete, the contracted form and the corresponding lexical form are not completely neutralized. Moreover, if the vowels are also proven to have changed in the process of syllable contraction, this study will connect syllable contraction with other cases of incomplete neutralization in the literature for the fact that what seems to be ‘complete to the ear’ may be in fact incomplete (Port & O’Dell, 1985, Port & Leary 2005). The vast literature on *incompleteness* of phonological changes (McCollum, 2019; Port & Leary, 2005; Warner, Jongman, Sereno, & Kemps, 2004) suggests that even if there *is* some neutralization in

the phonological process, the neutralization can be incomplete; the final output and the comparing unit are discretely different in aspects that are not easily captured by human ears. Such incompleteness makes the fully contracted syllables similar enough to a lexical word, but fine phonetic differences, such as duration and quality distinctions, are retained in order to maintain the underlying lexical contrasts.

To find out about the phonetics of vowels in the syllable contraction process, a production experiment was run. The major goal of the experiment and the following measurements was to elicit and compare comparable word tokens which are then used to compare the quality of the surviving vowel in the fully contracted word and the corresponding lexical vowel. This general goal can be divided into two questions. First, is the fully contracted syllable structurally similar to a single syllable, a one-and-half syllable, or two syllables? Second, is the vowel in the contracted syllable the same quality as a corresponding lexical vowel, including height (F1) and backness (F2)?

2. Methodology

Based on the vowel inventory of Rugao, 8 vowels well distributed along the vowel space are chosen for the experiment, including two low vowels (front and central), four mid vowels (front and back) and two high vowels (front and back): [a, æ, ε, e, ɔ, o, i, u]. All vowels are their surface forms. Test items were attested contractible multi-syllabic words and corresponding monosyllabic lexical words. The contractible part in the multisyllabic test items has [ə] in the first syllable and one of the eight target vowels [a, æ, ε, e, ɔ, o, i, u] in the second syllable in order to ensure consistency of the deleted vowel and promote syllable contraction. First, the analyses can be focused solely on the 8 target vowels when the deleting vowel is controlled and does not change. All test items are summarized in Table 1 below, including 16 contractible words, including 14 disyllabic words and 2 trisyllabic words, and 16 corresponding monosyllabic lexical words with the target vowels [a, æ, ε, e, ɔ, o, i, u] and similar neighboring consonants as the comparable contracted forms. As a control group, a completely matching (consonants, vowel and tone) word to the contracted syllable is given whenever possible. When there is no matching lexical word for a contraction form, the closest lexical word is given.

Vowels	Disyllabic Word	Meaning	Expected Contraction	Comparing Lexical Word	Meaning
[ə, a]	[səʔ ¹⁵ + aɪ ²¹]	‘twelve’	[saɪ ²¹]	[saɪ ²¹]	‘spoon’
	[ɪən ¹⁵ + kɑ ²¹]	‘other people’	[ɪɑɑ ³⁵]	[ɪɑ ²¹³]	‘annoy’
[ə, æ]	[pjən ²¹ + ɛjæn ²¹]	‘fridge’	[pjæn ²¹]	[ɛjæn ²¹]	‘aromatic’
	[jəʔ ⁵ + jæn ⁵⁵]	‘same’	[jæn ⁵⁵]	[jæn ¹⁵]	‘Yang’
[ə, ε]	[pəʔ ⁵ + ηɛ ²¹]	‘no problem’	[pɛɛ ⁵¹]	[pɛ ⁵⁵]	‘greet’
	[pən ²¹³ + lɛ ¹⁵]	‘originally’	[pɛɛ ²¹³]	[pɛ ²¹³]	‘put’

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[ə, e]	[tɛjəŋ ²¹ + xej ²¹]	‘thereafter’	[tɛjej ²¹]	[xej ²¹]	‘thick’
	[ɛjəŋ ²¹ + nej ²¹]	‘in mind’	[ɛej ²¹]	[sej ²¹]	‘search’
[ə, ɔ]	[ɛjə ⁵⁵ + jɔŋ ⁵⁵ + k ^h a ²¹³]	‘credit card’	[ɛjɔŋ ⁵⁵ + k ^h a ²¹³]	[ɛjɔŋ ²¹]	‘competent’
	[tsəʔ ⁵ + jɔ ⁵⁵]	‘only if’	[tsjɔ ⁵⁵]	[p ^h jɔ ⁵⁵]	‘ticket’
[ə, o]	[tsəʔ ⁵ + jow ²¹³]	‘only’	[tsjow ⁵¹²]	[te ^h jow ²¹³]	‘prank’
	[p ^h ən ¹⁵ + jow ²¹³]	‘friend’	[p ^h jow ¹⁵]	[te ^h jow ²¹³]	‘prank’
[ə, i]	[jən ¹⁵ + iʔ ⁵ + p ^h u ²¹]	‘Business Dep.’	[jiʔ ⁵ + p ^h u ²¹]	[jiʔ ⁵]	‘leaf’
	[teəŋ ²¹ + in ²¹]	‘experience’	[tein ²¹]	[tein ²¹]	‘pointy’
[ə, u]	[pəʔ ⁵ + xuj ²¹]	‘cannot’	[puj ⁵¹]	[t ^h uj ⁵⁵]	‘return’
	[tsən ²¹ + juʔ ²¹]	‘Lunar January’	[tsjuʔ ²¹]	[te ^h juʔ ⁵]	‘short of’

Table 1. Contractible disyllabic words and comparing monosyllabic words

26 female speakers of Rugao participated in the experiment (mean age = 31 years, range = 26—36 years). Only female speakers were recruited, as women are more likely to be contraction users (Xu & Mao, 2017). All participants grew up and lived in downtown Rugao for most of their life except the three to four years in college. They also speak the Rugao dialect exclusively at work and at home or use a mixture of Mandarin and Rugao.

The experiment consists of two tasks: a self-paced word contraction task and a wordlist reading task. The participants first listened to an introduction to the concept of syllable contraction and the task of this block. In each task, participants saw the randomly presented wordlist, one word each time on the screen in standard *hanzi*. They were instructed to say the contraction form of each word. There was no time limit for each word, and participants had the option to record multiple tokens.

The elicited tokens were then measured in vowel duration, word duration, F1 values and F2 values at the midpoint of the vowel. All measurements were made on Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2018). If there were repeated tokens for the same word, only one fully contracted token was measured. All monosyllabic lexical words were measured, but only the fully contracted contractible tokens were measured. Particularly, a token must pass three criteria to be considered ‘fully contracted’. First, there is no audible [ə] in the audio file to the ear of the author. Second, there is no visible [ə] on the Praat spectrogram. Third, the intensity line is a smooth curve, or at least does not have a visible dip where the boundary between the two syllables is expected, as non-full contraction can be spotted as a “dip” in intensity. For less perfect cases where the intensity line is not as smooth, i.e., showing a slight dip or plateau or trough-depth not equal to 0, the author referred the first two criteria that combine audial and visual examination. As expected, not every participant contracted every word. A total of 226 contracted tokens, 606 non-contracted disyllabic tokens, and 641 monosyllabic tokens were measured and compared.

3. Results

3.1 Vowel/Word ratio

As the speech rate for the two tasks are not comparable, it is unmeaningful to compare the length directly. The vowel/word ratio is calculated by dividing vowel duration from the word duration. The results are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Vowel/Word ratio [No.con.mono = non-contracted monosyllabic, no.con.disy = non-contracted disyllabic. Asterisks indicate significant levels.]

As seen in Figure 1 (red box vs. blue box), the vowel ratios in the non-contracted disyllabic words were smaller than those in either contracted or monosyllabic lexical words for all the words except for those that contain [ɔ]. And this dramatic difference is most likely due to the syllable count difference (2 vs. 1). Recall that the comparing contracted and non-contracted tokens are the same word underlyingly, for example, [tsju?] ('first Lunar month') vs. [tsən.ju] ('first Lunar month').

Generally, the vowel proportion of a fully contracted word is not different from that in a monosyllabic lexical word (red box vs. green box, Figure 1). This pattern holds true for [a, æ, e, o, ɔ, u]. Paired Welsh tests were run, and the results are as follows. [a]: $t(22^1) = -1.37$, $p = .18$, [æ]: $t(16) = 1.89$, $p = .08$, [e]: $t(7^2) = .38$, $p = .78$, [o]: $t(9) = .23$, $p = .82$, [ɔ]: $t(21) = -1.64$, $p = .11$, [u]: $t(18) = -.43$, $p = .67$. However, [ɛ] and [i] are two exceptions, with [ɛ] having a larger proportion of vowel in the contracted syllable ([ɛ]: $t(9) = -3.85$, $p < .01$), and [i] having a smaller proportion of vowel in the contracted syllable ([i]: $t(22) = 2.39$, $p < .05$).

Results presented above indicate that the fully contracted disyllabic word is no longer a disyllabic word, but patterns with some other type of word, the corresponding monosyllabic word. Contrary to the belief in the former literature that the contracted syllable is somewhere between its corresponding di-syllabic form and a monosyllabic word, the contracted word/syllable has the syllable structure of a monosyllabic word.

3.2 F1

The F1 value is known to be positively related to the height of the vowel. The F1 results are shown in Figure 1. I will report the results for the contracted vs. monosyllabic lexical words and contracted vs. disyllabic words respectively below.

Contracted vs. monosyllabic lexical

Generally, the F1 values in the fully contracted syllables are different from that in the monosyllabic lexical words for non-mid vowels. As shown in Figure 2 (red bar vs. green bar), for vowels [a, æ, u] ([a]: $t(22) = -4.66$, $p < .001$, [æ]: $t(16) = -2.15$, $p < .05$, [u]: $t(18) = -3.54$, $p < .01$), the F1 in the contracted word is lower than that in the monosyllabic lexical word, suggesting raising. For all mid vowels [e, ɛ, o, ɔ] and high vowel [i], no statistically significant difference was observed ([e]: $t(7) = -1.0$, $p = .35$, [ɛ]: $t(9) = 1.88$, $p = .09$, [o]: $t(9) = -1.77$, $p = .11$, [ɔ]: $t(21) = -0.12$, $p = .09$, [i]: $t(22) = -0.48$, $p = .64$).

Contracted vs. disyllabic lexical

1 Note that these df values vary because participants that did not contract the words for a certain vowel were excluded.
2 Only a few participants contracted words with [e], [ɛ] and [o], making their df 's relatively small. Word frequency may be a cause for the low contraction incidences. This is expected, however, considering the forced contraction task is by nature a more difficult environment for syllable contraction.

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As shown in the red bar vs. blue bar in Figure 2, three vowels, [a, o, u], show a lower F1 in contracted syllables than in disyllabic lexical syllables ([a]: $t(22) = -4.01, p < .001$, [o]: $t(9) = -2.51, p < .05$, [u]: $t(18) = -3.51, p < .01$). For the rest of the vowels [e, ε, ə, i, æ], no difference was observed ([æ]: $t(16) = -1.62, p = .12$, [e]: $t(7) = -1.24, p = .25$, [ε]: $t(9) = -0.74, p = .48$, [ə]: $t(21) = 1.5, p = .09$, [i]: $t(22) = -0.47, p = .64$). This suggests that [a, u, o] are higher in the contracted form than in their corresponding non-contracted disyllabic forms, but there is no difference between the contracted and the non-contracted disyllabic lexical words with regards to the height for [æ, e, ε, ə, i].

Figure 2. F1 (Hz) at midpoint [No.con.mono = non-contracted monosyllabic, no.con.disy = non-contracted disyllabic. Asterisks indicate significant levels.]

3.3 F2

The F2 value is an indicator of the front/backness of the vowel, with a higher F2 corresponding to a fronter vowel, and a lower F2 corresponding to a backer vowel. The F2 results are summarized in Figure 3. I will report the results for the contracted vs. monosyllabic lexical words and contracted vs. disyllabic words respectively below.

Figure 3. F2 values (Hz) at midpoint [No.con.mono = non-contracted monosyllabic, no.con.disy = non-contracted disyllabic. Asterisks indicate significant levels.]

Contracted vs. monosyllabic lexical

The F2 values for [e, o, ə, u] are different in the contracted form than in the monosyllabic lexical form, as shown in Figure 3 (red bar vs. green bar). More specifically, for vowels [o, ə, u], the F2 in the contracted word is higher than that in the monosyllabic lexical word, suggesting fronting ([o]: $t(9) = 2.29$, $p < .05$, [ə]: $t(21) = 2.57$, $p < .05$, [u]: $t(18) = 3.5$, $p < .01$). For [e], the F2 value is lower in the contracted words than in the monosyllabic words ($t(7) = -2.55$, $p < .05$), suggesting backing in the contracted form. No difference was observed for [a, æ, ε, i] ([a]: $t(22) = 1.6$, $p = .12$, [æ]: $t(16) = 1.59$, $p = .13$, [ε]: $t(9) = 0.7$, $p = .65$, [i]: $t(22) = -1.3$, $p = .31$).

Contracted vs. disyllabic lexical

As shown in Figure 3 (red bar vs. blue bar), three vowels, [e, ə, u], exhibit differences between fully contracted and disyllabic words. For [ə] and [u], the F2 values in the contracted word are higher than those in the disyllabic lexical words, suggesting fronting ([ə]: $t(21) = 2.31$, $p < .05$, [u]: $t(18) = 5.8$, $p < .0001$). Mid-front vowel [e] has a lower F2 value in the contracted form compared to the disyllabic form, suggesting it is more back in the contracted forms ([e]: $t(7) = -2.98$, $p < .05$). F2 values are not different for vowels [a, æ, ε, o, i] ([a]: $t(22) = 0.3$, $p = .98$, [æ]: $t(16) = 0.6$, $p = .95$, [ε]: $t(9) = 0.99$, $p = .35$, [o]: $t(9) = 0.69$, $p = 0.51$, [i]: $t(22) = -0.2$, $p = .84$).

4. Discussion

The above results show that 1) the vowel ratio in fully contracted words patterns better with that of a monosyllabic lexical word than a disyllabic word, and that 2) the vowel quality in the fully contracted words is phonetically different from that of lexical vowels in the monosyllabic words with regards to vowel height and/or backness.

Past research is more inclined to say that a contracted syllable is a one-and-half syllable, with a longer vowel, a bigger vowel ratio, and the tonal contour of the underlying disyllabic form (Cheng & Xu, 2009; Kuo, 2010; Wong, 2006). However, this study suggests that, although the vowels in the contracted syllable are usually longer than a lexical vowel, the vowel ratio of the contracted syllable is more consistent with that of a single syllable word than a disyllabic lexical word. Based on the results of the experiments presented above and the narrow definition of a fully contracted syllable, I would like to propose that, structurally, a true, fully contracted syllable resembles a single syllable. The partially contracted syllable may fall between one syllable and two syllables, supposedly with longer total vowel lengths and bigger vowel ratios than a single syllable, but not to the extent that it is a two-syllable word.

Despite the structural resemblance of a fully contracted syllable and a monosyllabic lexical word, the vowel qualities in fully contracted syllables are different from those in lexical words in at least one dimension. At the same time, there is much less or no difference between the lexical forms, whether in the non-contracted disyllabic

form or the monosyllabic forms, the two of which show great consistency in the vowel qualities. This further suggests that the vowel quality differences are generally between contrasting contracted forms and lexical forms, no matter how many syllables the lexical form has.

More specifically, the vowel quality difference manifests mostly in one dimension along the vowel space, in either height or backness, and both height and backness in only a few cases. Height-wise, as indicated by the F1 differences, the low vowels are higher in the contracted forms than the lexical forms, whether the lexical is monosyllabic or disyllabic. But critically, mid vowels are more stable with regards to height. Even when there is a height difference for some mid vowels, the difference is much smaller than seen in the cases of low vowels. Mid vowels mainly exhibit backness differences between the contracted form and the lexical form. Mid-back vowels are more front and mid-front vowels are more backed in contracted forms than in lexical forms, all pointing to the center of the vowel space. Crucially, great consistency in the direction of difference is observed, even for differences that do not have statistical strength. If difference exists, the low vowels are always higher, and sometimes more back. Mid-front vowels are always more back, while mid-back are vowels always more front, if difference exists. This consistency verifies that the vowels are not randomly different, but different because of something consistently there, the ‘deleted’ [ə] in the first syllable. Only the seemingly deleted mid-central vowel can make such a consistent change to the surviving peripheral vowels. The vowel quality differences further suggest that the deletion of [ə] is *incomplete* even in the fully contracted syllables, shown by a changed height and/or backness of the surviving vowel. The incomplete deletion then links the syllable contraction process, at least for the fully contracted syllables, to the widely discussed issue of incompleteness in the phonological changes (McCollum, 2019; Port & Leary, 2005; Warner et al., 2004).

According to the definition of a fully contracted syllable in this paper, the seemingly deleted [ə] vowel is not only auditorily absent but also invisible on the spectrogram. But it still leaves its quality remanence on the remaining vowel and centralizes these non-schwa vowels. This means that vowel coalescence must have been involved in some ways in this process, a phonological process that changes the quality of vowels by merging the features, as commonly seen in Bantu languages. For example, $a + i \rightarrow e$; $a + u \rightarrow o$, in Shona (Harford, 1997). The type of coalescence in syllable contraction is different from the canonical cases of vowel coalescence in that it only slightly alters quality of the surviving vowel, instead of merging and producing “another” vowel. The category of the vowel does not change, but the vowel bears the remanences of the deleted vowel and gets “pulled” to the direction of the deleted vowel.

Finally, with the altered vowel quality of the contracted syllables, it seems a clear conclusion that the vowel space that, under this specific experimental setting, i.e., with a vowel [ə] consistently in the first syllable, the contracted vowels take a smaller vowel space than lexical vowels do. Since the deletion of [ə] is incomplete, the remanences of

the seemingly deleted mid-central vowel pull the surviving peripheral vowels to the center of the vowel space, resulting in a smaller vowel space. However, it is too early to take this to any further conclusion about the general vowel space of the contracted vowels. Kuo (2010) concluded that the contracted syllables use a wider vowel space to mark the contraction, but this was based on the conclusion that only [i, u] are higher in the contracted words than in the lexical words. It is a fair prediction based on the findings of this study that when the competing vowels are all peripheral vowels, the actual vowel space may not change drastically. Put in short, whether the vowel space becomes bigger or smaller depends on the deleting vowel and the surviving vowel, and no clear general prediction can be made based on the available evidence yet.

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Quantity-Sensitive Foot Formation in Suzhou: Evidence from Light-Initial Tone Sandhi

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Based on a first-time acoustic analysis of the checked-tone sandhi patterns in Suzhou (Northern Wu; author's fieldwork), I argue that the tone sandhi patterns in Suzhou can best be accounted for using two types of trochaic feet, syllabic and moraic trochees (based on Kager 1993). The choice of which type of foot to use is made by mediating the quantity relationship between foot heads and dependents (cf. Head-Dependent Asymmetry; Dresher and van der Hulst 1998). Furthermore, unfooted and toneless prosodic constituents (i.e. syllables/moras) are interpreted as "default L" in phrase-final positions (cf. Chen 2000). This paper addresses a key debate in prosodic typology, viz. the interaction of tone, syllable quantity, and metrical structure (Kehrein et al. 2018 for overview).

1. Introduction

The relationship between metrical structure and tonal alignment has been used to account for many phonological alternations that appear to be purely tonal/paradigmatic otherwise (Duanmu 1995; 1999; de Lacy 2002; Köhnlein 2011; Iosad 2016; Köhnlein and Zhu 2019; Morrison 2019). The current paper contributes to this line of research by investigating tone sandhi in Suzhou, which shows evidence of foot structure despite not showing any *phonetic* correlates of prominence (stress). That is, the *phonological* properties of metrical structure may manifest as systematic tonal distributions on the surface *without* bearing any traditional phonetic correlates of stress (i.e. duration, intensity, pitch) – or, as Duanmu (1995) puts it, "metrical systems may exist in ... languages in which phonetic stress is not obvious" (see also Köhnlein et al. 2019 for similar arguments)

I term the specific tone sandhi patterns that is central to this paper "light-initial sandhi" – disyllabic prosodic words where the first syllable carries what is traditionally referred to as *rusheng* or "checked" tone and the second syllable carries a *shusheng* or "smooth/unchecked" tone. In addition to recent analyses that treat "checked" tones as monomoraic (e.g. Chen 2000), I also present synchronic acoustic data of Suzhou that supports the monomoraic status of checked-toned syllables. A direct result of treating "checked" tones as monomoraic is that it creates light-heavy disyllables as part of the syllabic inventory of Suzhou. The light-initial sandhi pattern has been overlooked in recent systematic documentation (Wang 2011) and theoretical analyses (Ling 2011; Shi

and Jiang 2013). Furthermore, it deviates from straightforward metrical-foot-based accounts of tone sandhi, which have been immensely successful in other representative dialects of Northern Wu (see Duanmu 1993; 1995). My main claims and crucial points of departure are two-fold:

(1). Main analytical claims

a. Footed and unfooted material (cf. de Lacy 2002) plays an active role in Suzhou tone sandhi – tones can only be realized inside the domain of the foot. This is reminiscent of, but not entirely identical to, the traditional *left/right-prominent* analysis of various Chinese dialects (e.g. Duanmu 1995; Chen 2000; Zhang 2007; Shi and Jiang 2013).

b. Suzhou Chinese demonstrates two types of foot structures: syllabic trochees (built on syllables) and moraic trochees (built directly on moras, following Kager's 1993 foot inventory). The choice of the foot is regulated by the quantity relationship between the foot head and the foot dependent – the moraic trochee is chosen only when the dependent would be heavier than the head in a syllabic trochee parse (Dresher and van der Hulst 1998; Iosad 2013).

This study contributes to various ongoing debates in the literature on theoretically-informed prosodic typology in general, and the phonology of Chinese languages in particular. The approach adopted here has empirical support from other typologically diverse language families (e.g. Köhnlein 2011; 2016 for Franconian, Morén-Duolljá 2013 for Swedish, Iosad 2016 for Danish, Morrison 2019 for Scottish Gaelic, Köhnlein and Zhu 2019 for Uspanteko), but has not been proposed for any Chinese language. Moreover, the foot-based analysis explores two less well-established generalizations in phonological theory: Head-Dependent Asymmetry (despite having many empirical examples; Dresher and van der Hulst 1998) and Violable Syllable Integrity (cf. Martínez-Paricio and Kager 2016; Kager and Martínez-Paricio 2018; Breteler 2018).

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. §2 offers some further background information on metrical prominence and tone sandhi in Chinese dialects generally. In §3 I report the empirical data on both the synchronic phonetic status of "checked tone"/light syllables and the pitch patterns of light-initial tone sandhi. A metrical analysis accounting for all light-heavy tonal combinations is given in §4. §5 concludes the paper

2. Background

2.1. Left-dominant tone sandhi

Tone sandhi broadly refers to phonological tone changes between adjacent toned morphemes/syllables (see Chen 2000; Zhang 2016 for overview). First noted by Yue-Hashimoto (1987) and Chan and Ren (1989), most varieties of Chinese languages demonstrate certain "dominance" effects in their tone sandhi patterns. The current study

discusses empirical data that demonstrate *left-dominance*, similar to numerous neighboring Northern Wu dialects do. In a left-dominant or left-prominent sandhi process, the leftmost/initial syllable in a prosodic constituent (typically a prosodic word; see Zhang 2016) preserves its tonal material while the remaining non-initial syllables undergo either tonal neutralization or "pattern extension" (term coined by Chan and Ren 1989) – the displacement or redistribution of initial syllable tones to subsequent syllables. Left-dominant sandhi can be seen as a left-to-right phonological process, where the leftmost lexical tone determines the surface tonal/pitch pattern. A concise example from Suzhou Chinese is given in (2).

(2). /LH/ + /HL/ + /HLH/ → [L.H.L] e.g. [zo:.gø:.di:] "tea shop"

A trisyllabic word in Suzhou preserves all tonal material of the initial /LH/ syllable by redistributing the contour tone evenly across the first two syllables. The third syllable, on the other hand, undergoes tonal deletion and realizes as a phonetic L on the surface (see Chen 2000 on the status of "default L"). Noticeably, the underlying tones of the second and third syllables play no role in determining the sandhi output.

Despite the criticism that phonetic *stress* per se in Chinese languages is notoriously elusive, if not non-existent (see Chen 2000 for review), various phonological analyses rooted in autosegmental tonal representation (Leben 1973; Goldsmith 1976) and metrical stress theory (Hayes 1995) essentially argue that *phonological prominence*, a structural property, can stand independent to the presence or absence of *phonetic stress*, an acoustic property. Left-dominant sandhi patterns among Northern Wu dialects such as Shanghai (Duanmu 1993; 1995), Wuxi (Chan and Ren 1989), Danyang (Chan 1995) and Nantong (Ao 1993) have all been analyzed in ways that connect tonal behaviors to left-headed stress feet. In the context of Suzhou, previous studies such as Shi and Jiang (2013) have also provided a convincing analysis: assuming that a disyllabic trochaic foot is formed at the left edge of every prosodic word, the surface tonal pattern in (2) can be captured in three steps: (i). the initial /LH/ retains all tones by virtue of its metrically strong position; (ii). all non-initial syllable tones are deleted; (iii). the initial /LH/ contour is evenly distributed within the disyllabic foot, but does not extend to the third syllable, which is hypothesized to be toneless and phonetically L on the surface. (3) shows the autosegmental diagram of such process.

(3). A foot-based analysis of tone sandhi in Suzhou, based on Shi & Jiang (2013)

In (3), a left-aligned syllabic trochee dominates the first two syllables, retaining all tones under the metrical head (σ^+) and evenly redistribute the contour with the dependent (σ^-). The leftover third syllable is unparsed by a foot and directly dominated by the Prosodic Word (PrWd), and surfaces without any phonological tone (\emptyset). In essence, such an approach illustrates a three-way distinction of tonal behaviors in three types of syllables:

- (4). Three types of syllables under a foot-based analysis
- a. Foot head (σ^+): retains all lexical tones; redistributes/reassociates¹ tones to the foot dependent
 - b. Foot dependent (σ^-): deletes all lexical tones; accepts redistribution from the head
 - c. Unfooted/unstressed syllable (σ): deletes all lexical tones; surfaces as default L

A crucial extension of (4) is that *only* the foot head (initial syllable) can determine the tonal output of polysyllabic words in Suzhou. In the next subsection I present some preliminary data in Suzhou that contradicts with predictions listed above. These counterexamples are the primary motivation for my fieldwork and the focus of the analysis section as well.

2.2. Exceptional tone sandhi patterns in Suzhou Chinese

Suzhou has seven lexical tones, two of which are traditionally referred to as "checked" tones (Qian 1992; Ye 1993; Wang 2011). The two "checked" tones have rather short syllable nucleus duration and often end in a glottal stop in citation form (i.e. isolation). Below in Table 1 I provide minimal or near-minimal pairs² containing the seven lexical tones.

Table 1. Lexical tones in Suzhou

Representation	Tone letter	Example	Gloss
/HH/	44	[ti:]	low
/LH/	13	[di:]	carry

¹ The process where leftmost syllable "shares" tones with foot dependents are often referred to as "tonal spreading" in the tone sandhi literature (Chan 1991; Duanmu 1999; Chen 2000b). Here I use the terms "redistribution" or "reassociation" to differentiate the process in discussion from canonical examples of tonal spreading – a single tone spans over a few Tone Bearing Units (e.g. unbounded H spreading in Chinlungu: /kú-/ + /saakul/ + /-à/ → [kú-sáákúl- à], cf. Bickmore 1996).

² Onset voicing contrasts are partially predictable from tonal registers (Yip 2002). Therefore, for some tonal contrasts only near-minimal pairs differing in both onset voicing and lexical tone are available.

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/HL/	52	[ti:]	bottom
/HLH/	412	[ti:]	emperor
/LHL/	231	[di:]	ground
/H/	5	[tɿʔ]	trickle
/LH/	23	[dɿʔ]	flute

The last two lexical tones will be the focus of this paper. They have a (C)Vʔ syllable structure in citation form and are traditionally referred to as "checked" tones (Qian 1992; Ye 1993; Wang 2011). I refer to them as *light/monomoraic* tones here, following Chen (2000). Note that there are two lexical tones with the same /LH/ underlying representation in Table 1 – [di:] "carry" and [dɿʔ] "flute". Consequently, the phonological contrast between these two morphemes is not about tones *per se*, but about syllable structure: the morpheme "carry" is represented as a *bimoraic* open syllable with a /LH/ rising tone, and the morpheme "flute" a *monomoraic* open CV syllable with a /LH/ rising tone. Importantly, despite the fact that the last two light tones are realized with a coda glottal stop *in isolation*³, I will argue that the glottal stop, even if present, does not contribute to any moraic status in contemporary Suzhou (unlike other varieties of Chinese; see Duanmu 1999; 2007) and the "checked" vs. "unchecked" contrast has shifted from a difference of coda /ʔ/ to a difference of syllable weight – monomoraic vs. bimoraic (see §3.2).

The crucial data that provide counterevidence to the claims in (4) are concerned with lexical items with an initial checked-tone, which I will refer to as *light-initial sandhi*. Two relevant generalizations are given in (5).

(5). Exceptional sandhi patterns in Suzhou

a. Second syllable tone is able to influence tone sandhi, but *only* when the initial syllable is a light tone.

/H/ + /LH/ → [H.L]

e.g. [hə.dæ:] "spade"

/H/ + /HL/ → [H.HL]

e.g. [hə.tsi:] "black paper"

Compare this with:

/HH/ + /LH/ → [H.H]

e.g. [foŋ.lǎ:] "cold"

/HH/ + /HL/ → [H.H]

e.g. [foŋ.su:] "fengshui"

b. The falling contour tone /HL/ does not redistribute in initial position. Additionally, it does not undergo deletion in second position, when preceded by initial /H/ (/T/: any lexical tone).

/HL/ + /T/ → [HL.L]/*[H.L]

e.g. [si:.nm] "dead people"

³ This could potentially be due to a word minimality constraint, which regulates that a minimal word in Suzhou must be bimoraic. See Lin (1993) and Duanmu (1999) for discussion on word minimality in Chinese languages.

/H/ + /HL/ → [H.HL]/*[H.L] e.g. [hə.pɛ:] "blackboard"

(5a) contradicts with the prediction that only initial tones determine the sandhi output directly: in light-initial sandhi, different underlying tones of the second syllable may contribute to different sandhi output. A consequence is that one initial syllable tone may not correspond to only one sandhi pattern anymore – in fact, light /H/-initial sandhi has *three* distinct pitch patterns instead of one: [H.L], [H.H] and [H.HL] (see §3.3). (5b) contradicts with the observation that contour tones always redistribute in initial positions, and as an effect also contributes to the alternative tonal patterns in light-initial sandhi. As I would argue later, this is due to the special tonal structure of the contour tone /HL/, but not to the exceptional behaviors of light-initial sandhi only (also see Zhu 2020). Based on the data in (5), there are two research questions I aim to address in this study:

(6). Research questions

- a. What are the synchronic phonetic characteristics of syllables with “checked”/light tones? What tone sandhi patterns do light tones demonstrate?
- b. Can a foot-based analysis account for all tone sandhi patterns in Suzhou? What are the relevant stress/sandhi domains?

In the next section I provide two pieces of acoustic data coming from my fieldwork in Suzhou – checked-tone/light syllables embedded in carrier sentences (§3.2), and F0 patterns of light-initial sandhi (§3.3).

3. The data

3.1. Methods

The focus of the present study is tone sandhi patterns of disyllabic prosodic words in Suzhou Chinese. I used a word reading task to elicit disyllabic lexical items. To avoid various domain-final phonetic effects (e.g. domain-final lengthening, L tone insertion), all disyllabic stimuli are embedded in a carrier phrase "講__撥我聽"("Say __ for me") in Chinese. The elicitation word list contains 203 common disyllabic nouns in the language with various tonal combinations. Since light-initial sandhi patterns are my main focus, 168 of the words include an initial light tone – /H/_μ[5] or /LH/_μ[23], while the remaining 35 start with an initial heavy tone and partially serve as distractor items. Since there are two light tones in contemporary Suzhou and seven lexical tones in total, all light-initial disyllabic forms can be divided into 2*7 = 14 binary tonal combinations. In Table 2 I provide one example for each cell of combination.

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Table 2. All light-initial disyllabic combinations⁴. Columns: initial light tone. Rows: second tone. /T/μμ: bimoraic/heavy tones; /T/μ: monomoraic/light tones.

	/H/μ	/LH/μ
/HH/μμ	[po.foŋ] "north wind"	[ba.tɛm] "platinum"
/LH/μμ	[hə.dæ:] "spade"	[ba.dã:] "white sugar"
/HL/μμ	[hə.tsi:] "black paper"	[ba.pɛ:] "whiteboard"
/HLH/μμ	[fo.tɛ ^h i:] "fortune"	[ba.ts ^h ɛ:] "bok choy"
/LHL/μμ	[s ^h ə.di:] "snowfield"	[ba.mi:] "white rice"
/H/μ	[ts ^h a.tɛ ^h ɔ] "barefoot"	[la.pjə] "crayon"
/LH/μ	[s ^h ə.bo] "tinfoil"	[zə.lo] "sixteen"

The main acoustic data come from two male speakers who were 25 and 27 years old at the time of the recording. There are therefore 406 * 2 = 812 word tokens in carrier sentences in the data I report here. Each speaker signed an informed consent form before participating in the elicitation.

The elicitation had two parts: a sociolinguistic interview and a pseudorandomized wordlist of disyllabic items. The target disyllabic words were presented in Chinese characters in a slideshow, with one word per page. Each participant was digitally recorded in a quiet room at a sampling rate of 44100Hz using a Shure SM10A-CN head-worn microphone and a Zoom H4N PRO digital recorder. After collecting the recording data, the wave files were then submitted to Praat (Boersma and Weenink 2019) for further acoustic analysis. Each target disyllabic word was marked and segmented using Praat's textgrid function. Three tiers were used: one tier for the word token (in both Chinese and English), one for segmentation, and one for a search index. An example of textgrid segmentation is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. A target word in textgrid. 'phj' = shorthand for a palatalized aspirated stop: [p^hj]

⁴ Note that almost all disyllabic words are bimorphemic compounds, as monomorphemic disyllabic words in Chinese are extremely rare. See (Chen 2000: 39; Lin 2007) for discussion.

Pitch-related information was also extracted from Praat using the "Draw visible pitch contour" function. Pitch duration was normalized by using the same length of Praat Picture window for each pitch contour. The pitch range for extraction was adjusted to 60-220Hz to accommodate the male pitch range. Moreover, detailed pitch settings (e.g. "voicing threshold", "silence threshold") were hand-adjusted for each word token to ensure that the entirety of the voicing period was recognized by Praat's pitch tracking function. An example of the normalized pitch data is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Time-normalized pitch tracking data. The middle section without pitch tracking information is due to oral closure of coda/onset stops. The example word in the figure will be transcribed as [L_μμ.H_μ], with a bimoraic L-toned syllable followed by a monomoraic H-toned syllable (see also §3.3)

3.2. Segmental characteristics of light/"checked" tones

In this subsection I report some segmental data that lead to my characterization of "checked" tone syllables as light/monomoraic syllables. Crucially, the so-called "checked" tones in contemporary Suzhou have *extremely short vowel duration* and *no discernable coda closure* in an embedded context. They are better characterized as lexical tones with *light/monomoraic* syllable structure. The mean rhyme durations of "checked" and "unchecked" syllables are summarized in Table 3, accompanied by a bar graph in Figure 3.

Table 3. Means and standard deviations(in parentheses) of "checked" and "unchecked" syllable rhymes.

	Mean
Checked	0.1566 (0.0472)
Unchecked	0.0789 (0.0304)

Figure 3. Bar graph for mean syllable rhyme durations (in seconds) of "checked" and "unchecked" tones. Error bars represent standard error.

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Both the summary table and the bar graph show that "checked" syllables in Suzhou are only have half the rhyme duration ($\approx 75\text{ms}$) of "unchecked" syllables ($\approx 150\text{ms}$). A potential interpretation of the durational data is that "checked" tone syllables are realized with a short/monomoraic vowel [V] in Suzhou, while "unchecked" tone syllables are either open syllables with long/bimoraic vowels [V:] or closed syllables with a short vowel and a nasal coda [VN]. However, due to the fact that checked-tone syllables in Suzhou are still realized with a coda glottal stop in isolation, it is unclear if the glottal stops is associated with a mora, making the checked syllable still bimoraic. Now, consider the acoustic data in Figure 4 showing an initial checked syllable followed by another unchecked syllable in running speech.

Figure 4. Waveform and spectrogram for "cough". Visible creaky vowel production in the second syllable is due to a falling HL tone.

Clearly, there is no stop closure whatsoever between the first syllable [k^hə] and the second syllable [sɛɪ]. The initial "checked" syllable is better transcribed as a *monomoraic/light open syllable*: [k^hə] instead of [k^həʔ]. Combining this with the extremely short vowel duration, we have ample evidence to claim that the crucial contrast between checked and unchecked syllables in contemporary Suzhou is in syllable weight: checked syllables are light, while unchecked ones are heavy. From this point on, I will refer to the contrast as light vs. heavy and use corresponding moraic transcriptions T_μ vs. T_{μμ} when applicable.

3.3. F0 patterns of light-initial sandhi

Below I present all majority pitch patterns of light-initial tone sandhi: when the light /H/ tone is initial, there are three distinct pitch forms: [H_μ.L_{μμ}] (Figure 5), [H_μ.H_μL_μ] (Figure 6) and [H_μ.H_μ] (Figure 7); when the light /LH/ tone is initial, we see two pitch patterns instead: [L_μ.H_μL_μ] (Figure 8) and [L_μ.H_μ] (Figure 9). All possible light-initial sandhi pitch patterns and their corresponding underlying tone combinations are summarized in Table 4, followed by respective figures.

Table 4. Light-initial sandhi patterns. Columns: initial light tone. Rows: second tone. Forms in slashes are underlying representation of different lexical tones, while those in square brackets are surface pitch patterns.

	/H/ _μ	/LH/ _μ
/HH/ _{μμ}	[H _μ .L _{μμ}]	[L _μ .H _μ L _μ]
/LH/ _{μμ}		
/LHL/ _{μμ}		
/HL/ _{μμ}	[H _μ .H _μ L _μ]	
/HLH/ _{μμ}		
/H/ _μ	[H _μ .H _μ]	[L _μ .H _μ]
/LH/ _μ		

Figure 5. [H_μ.L_{μμ}]: H monomoraic tone followed by a L bimoraic tone. Three tonal combinations result in this pattern: /H/_μ + /HH/_{μμ}, /H/_μ + /LH/_{μμ}, /H/_μ + /LHL/_{μμ}.

Figure 6. $[H_{\mu}.H_{\mu}L_{\mu}]$: H monomoraic tone followed by a HL falling bimoraic tone. Two tonal combinations result in this pattern: $/H/_{\mu} + /HL/_{\mu\mu}$, $/H/_{\mu} + /HLH/_{\mu\mu}$.

Figure 7. $[H_{\mu}.H_{\mu}]$: H monomoraic tone followed by a H monomoraic tone. Two tonal combinations result in this pattern: $/H/_{\mu} + /H/_{\mu}$, $/H/_{\mu} + /LH/_{\mu}$.

Figure 8. $[L_{\mu}.H_{\mu}L_{\mu}]$: L monomoraic tone followed by a HL falling bimoraic tone. Five tonal combinations result in this pattern: $/LH/_{\mu} + /HH/_{\mu\mu}$, $/LH/_{\mu} + /LH/_{\mu\mu}$, $/LH/_{\mu} + /HL/_{\mu\mu}$, $/LH/_{\mu} + /HLH/_{\mu\mu}$, $/LH/_{\mu} + /LHL/_{\mu\mu}$.

Figure 9. [L_μ.H_μ]: L monomoraic tone followed by a H monomoraic tone. Two tonal combinations result in this pattern: /LH/_μ + /H/_μ, /LH/_μ + /LH/_μ.

For exposition reasons, this paper focuses on the $2*5=10$ disyllabic patterns of the shape light-heavy, as: (i). Alternative sandhi patterns conditioned by the second syllable tone are most robustly attested here; (ii). light-light disyllables can be easily analyzed as a "cut-off" version of corresponding light-heavy pitch forms (i.e. [H_μ.H_μ] and [H_μ.H_μL_μ] only contrast in mora count, but not in tonal composition).

Three crucial observations can be drawn from the summary data in Table 4. First, all tones of the initial syllable in the input *is always preserved* – when light /H/_μ is initial, output forms always begin with [H_μ]; when light is /LH/_μ initial, the L and H tones appear in different syllables [L_μ.H_μ...] in the output but are nevertheless preserved. Second, the second syllable plays a role in determining the sandhi output only when light /H/_μ is the initial syllable. The last observation is concerned with unattested (and by inference ungrammatical) forms in light initial sandhi: whenever the disyllabic word takes the shape of light-heavy [μ.μμ], the third mora never has a H tone. That is, pitch patterns such as [H_μ.H_μμ] (from /H_μ/ + /HH/μμ) or [H_μ.L_μH_μ] (from /H_μ/ + /LH/μμ) are unattested. Importantly, this restriction on the third mora (or, the second mora of the second syllable) is unique to light-initial sandhi: [L_μμ.H_μμ] is grammatical as a heavy-initial tonal pattern but *[L_μ.H_μμ] is not. The three generalizations are summarized below.

(7). Generalizations of light-initial tone sandhi

- a. Initial syllable tones are always preserved.
- b. Only /H/_μ-initial forms are conditioned on the second syllable tone.
- c. In "light + heavy" disyllables, the third mora is never H / always L.

4. A metrical analysis of light-initial sandhi

In this section I offer a concise analysis of the light-initial sandhi patterns couched in metrical stress theory (for a full OT analysis, see Zhu in preparation). Crucially, I argue that the exceptional behavior of light-initial sandhi is rooted in the quantity contrast between initial light vs. heavy syllables: Suzhou Chinese disallows an "unbalanced"

trochaic foot with a light head and a heavy dependent, and avoids such structure by opting for a bimoraic trochee.

4.1. Tonal representation

Before we proceed to the analysis, a few notes on the overall tonal structure and representation of Suzhou. First, consider the exceptional behavior of the falling tone /HL/ in (5b), repeated here for convenience:

(8). The falling contour tone /HL/_{μμ} does not redistribute in initial position. Additionally, it does not undergo deletion in second position, when preceded by initial /H/_μ (/T/: any lexical tone).

/HL/_{μμ} + /T/ → [HL.L]/*[H.L] e.g. [si:.nm] "dead people"
 /H/_μ + /HL/_{μμ} → [H.HL]/*[H.L] e.g. [hə.pɛ:] "blackboard"

Simply put, there is a certain "stability" with the /HL/_{μμ} tone that prevents any modification on it, regardless of its position in the disyllable. Compare this with the low rising tone /LH/_{μμ}:

(9). The rising contour tone /LH/_{μμ} both redistributes in initial position and deletes in second position when preceded by initial /H/_μ

/LH/_{μμ} + /T/ → [L.H]/*[LH.L] e.g. [hoŋ.dæ] "heart" (playing card suit)
 /H/_μ + /LH/_{μμ} → [H.L]/*[H.LH] e.g. [hə.dæ] "spade" (playing card suit)

As shown, the exceptional light-initial sandhi patterns are partially due to the unique structure property of the /HL/_{μμ} tone (and for that matter, /HLH/_{μμ} tone as well; see below). Disregarding the light-initial patterns, any adequate phonological analysis still has to account for the independent fact that /HL/_{μμ} does not demonstrate the prototypical "deletion-redistribution" processes other Northern Wu dialects would. To account for this fact, I argue that Suzhou makes use of *associated vs. floating* underlying tones (see similar approaches in Chan 1985; Milliken 1989; Chen 2000; also see further discussion in Zhu 2020). A general dispreference against delinking autosegmental association lines accounts for the non-redistribution/non-deletion of /HL/_{μμ}. I show the representational contrast of /LH/_{μμ} and /HL/_{μμ} and below.

(10). Underlying representations of /<LH>/_{μμ} and /HL/_{μμ}

LH	HL
μ μ	μ μ

Linearly, I choose to represent floating underlying tones with angle brackets, following Chen (2000). Note that the representation assumes that moras are the TBUs in

Suzhou (cf. Duanmu 1995). This easily accounts for the observation that no contour tones (i.e. tones consisting of two tonemes) are observed in light/monomoraic syllables after tone sandhi, and no complex contours (i.e. tones with three tonemes) are observed in heavy/bimoraic syllables: many-to-one tonal association is generally prohibited in Suzhou.

4.2. Quantity-sensitive foot formation

Now we tackle the intriguing patterns of light-initial tone sandhi. Recall the three observations in (7): only /H/_μ-initial sandhi shows alternation conditioned on second syllable tone, while the /LH/_μ-initial sandhi output is uniformly [L_μ.H_μL_μ]. More specifically, the only lexical tone demonstrating alternative sandhi patterns is at the same time the only lexical tone consisting of one toneme – all other lexical tones in Suzhou contain at least two tonemes (see Table 1). Suzhou Chinese seems to allow preservation of second syllable tone only when the initial morpheme does not provide "enough" tonal material. In addition, when the initial tone is a complex contour such as /HLH/_{μμ}, only *two* of the three tonemes are preserved in sandhi: /HLH/_{μμ} + T → [H.H]/*[H.LH],*[HL.H]. This echoes with the observation succinctly put by Kenstowicz (1994: 597): "linguistic rules do not count beyond two". In the context of Suzhou, the optimal amount of phonological tones after sandhi seems to be *two*, reflecting the binary nature of metrical footing.

Once we have accepted that post-sandhi forms carry at most two phonological tones, we still need to explain why light-initial forms such as [L_μ.H_μL_μ] and [H_μ.H_μL_μ] seem to be tri-tonal. Interestingly, in the ten possible light-heavy tonal combinations, the second mora of the second heavy syllable is always L (observation 7c). Forms such as [H_μ.L_μH_μ] or [L_μ.H_{μμ}] in phrase final positions⁵ are considered ungrammatical and rejected by native speakers. The exceptionless distribution of phonetic L pitch on the third mora in light-heavy disyllables resembles phonetic Ls in third *syllables* in heavy-initial trisyllabic tone sandhi. Recall the form in (2):

$$(11). /LH/ + /HL/ + /HLH/ \rightarrow [L.H.\emptyset] \quad \text{e.g. [zo:.g\emptyset:.di:] "tea shop"}$$

It is usually assumed that trisyllabic lexical items only have one left-aligned syllabic trochee, leaving the third mora unparsed and *toneless* on the surface. Toneless syllables are assigned a "default L" in phrase final positions (cf. Chen 2000). Could the third mora in light-heavy disyllables also be toneless and interpretable as phonetic default Ls [L_μ.H_μ∅_μ]/[H_μ.H_μ∅_μ]?

A possible binary foot that is able to exclude the third (and later) mora is the *bimoraic trochee* (Kager 1993b; Martínez-Paricio and Kager 2016; Kager and Martínez-

⁵ A third [H] mora in phonetic pitch is indeed observed in phrase-non-final positions when followed by another phonological H tone. See Zhu (2021).

Paricio 2018). That is, disyllabic trochees are the relevant foot structure in heavy-initial sandhi, while bimoraic trochees are formed when a disyllabic word starts with a light/monomoraic "checked" syllable. I show this crucial contrast between a trisyllabic heavy-initial word and a trimoraic light-initial word in (12).

- (12). Comparison between a disyllabic trochee and a bimoraic trochee
 a. Disyllabic trochee (heavy-initial) b. Bimoraic trochee (light-initial)

(12a) shows a trisyllabic heavy-initial lexical item (such as [zo:.gø:.di:] "tea shop"), with an unparsed and toneless third syllable. (12b), on the other hand, shows a trimoraic light-heavy disyllable, with a trochaic foot directly dominating the first two moras. The third mora (second mora of the second syllable) for the same reason is unparsed and toneless on the surface. Importantly, such a quantity-sensitive foot alternation is not only empirically adequate, but also preferred under purely structural grounds. Motivation for this comes from a cross-linguistic observation that "dependents cannot be more complex than heads" in quantity-sensitive systems (Dresher and van der Hulst 1998: 341). That is, heavy-heavy or heavy-light disyllables are compatible with a disyllabic trochaic foot, since the leftmost foot head is always heavier than or as heavy as the foot dependent on the right. If we were to use the same disyllabic foot to parse the light-heavy sequence, however, we end up with a light foot head with a heavy dependent. Such dispreference for lighter metrical heads is referred to as "Head-Dependent Asymmetry" (HDA) by Dresher and van der Hulst. Suzhou Chinese in this case chooses to repair HDA-violating metrical structures by positing an alternative bimoraic trochee.

Once we have established that bimoraic trochees are the relevant metrical structure for the light-heavy disyllables, the alternative sandhi output follows directly from the underlying representation of heavy lexical tones and the hard requirement for the third mora to be toneless. Crucially, /<HH>/_{μμ}, /<LH>/_{μμ} and /<LHL>/_{μμ} are all lexical tones with fully floating tonemes, allowing them to redistribute freely in initial position, and delete completely when following /H/_μ, yielding [H_μ.Ø_{μμ}] (phonetically [H_μ.L_{μμ}]). On the other hand, /HL/_{μμ} has both tonemes associated, while /H<LH>/_{μμ} has at least the first toneme anchored, blocking them from deletion or redistribution.

5. Conclusion

To summarize, the exceptional light-initial sandhi with second syllable conditioning is caused by two facts. First, Suzhou preserves at most two phonological tones within a tone sandhi domain, directly echoing general phonological principles such

as foot binarity; Second, /H/μ being the only single-toneme lexical tone in Suzhou allows extra input from the second syllable, but only when the tonemes are underlyingly associated. These two claims connect well with the general properties of heavy-initial sandhi, the majority patterns in Suzhou. In addition, the exceptionless third mora L tone in light-heavy disyllables resembles toneless syllables unparsed by the metrical foot. This in turn leads to a quantity-sensitive footing alternation depending on the initial syllable quantity: a disyllabic trochee in heavy-initial sandhi, but a bimoraic trochee in light-initial sandhi. This footing alternation has both empirical coverage and theoretical grounding: Head-Dependent Asymmetry (Dresher and van der Hulst 1998) captures the fact that foot heads lighter in quantity are cross-linguistically dispreferred, which corresponds precisely to the condition of the syllabic-moraic footing switch – light-heavy disyllables. As a side note, the case of alternating moraic trochees in Suzhou also contributes the more recent investigation of "Violable Syllable Integrity", the fact that moraic trochees may intervene within a syllable (Martínez-Paricio and Kager 2016; Kager and Martínez-Paricio 2018; Breteler 2018)

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(In)definiteness in a Language without Articles: A Study in Mandarin Chinese

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This paper presents a detailed analysis of the interpretation of the noun phrases of the form Yi(one) + Classifier + Noun in different positions in a sentence – the subject position and the object of *bǎ*. In Mandarin Chinese, ‘Yi ‘one’ + CL + N’ is the lexical form mainly used for indefinite referents. And it is said that there is a strong tendency in Mandarin that the subject of a sentence or the object of *bǎ* has a definite reference. However, we found out that the indefinite NPs can occur in the subject position and the *ba*-NP position in Chinese sentences. Indefinite NPs can take the subject role with or without an existential syntactic marker, as for the indefinite *ba*-NPs, they are actually indefinite reference NPs, which includes indefinite specific and, contrary to expectation, indefinite non-specific NPs, but they can also be definite in some cases.

0. Introduction

It is well known that the Chinese is a language which is claimed to have no functional equivalents of the definite and indefinite article in western languages, by which the concept of definiteness has been biased. However it should be noted that definiteness is conveyed in every language, also including articleless languages like Chinese, though in diverse ways. For Chinese noun phrases, the complexity in the definite or indefinite interpretation and their position in sentence has been a controversial topic for a long time. It is said that the subject of a sentence or the object of a pretransitive has a definite reference [Chao, 1968, p343]. With our counting up corpus of spoken and written Chinese, literature, news and scientific style, we want to examine whether the NPs of the form Yi(one) + Cl + N – a lexical form mainly used for indefinite referents – could appear in these positions, and furthermore, to analyze their interpretation.

1. Definition of definite and indefinite

The reason why we start by examining the notion of reference, is that only noun phrases that are referential can be definite or indefinite. In other words, the question of definiteness does not arise for nonreferential noun phrases [Li and Thompson, 1989, p.129]. We will present this relation by the following simple diagram:

In accordance with our general view of verbal interaction, referring will here be interpreted as a pragmatic, cooperative action of a Speaker in a pattern of communication between Speaker and Addressee. A referent may be presumed to be available to A on four bases: (a) long-term pragmatic information, (b) short-term (contextual) information, (c) perceptual information, (d) inferences drawn on the basis of information from (a)-(d).

When the orientational parameter only concerns the question whether or not the intended referent is presumed to be already available in addressee's pragmatic information, we speak of definite vs indefinite term operators [Dik, 1997, p.184]. Definite and indefinite in this article are taken as a pragmatic notion relating to the assumptions made by the speaker on the cognitive status of a referent in the mind of the addressee in the context of utterance [Chen Ping, 2004, p.1129]. For us, definite expressions and indefinite expressions are considered as the instruction given by the speaker to his interlocutor. Thus:

(1) a. By means of a definite term Speaker invites Addressee to identify a referent which Speaker presumes available to Addressee.

b. By means of an indefinite term Speaker invites Addressee to construe a referent conforming to the properties specified in the term. [Dik, 1989, p.114; 1997, p.184]

From these characterizations, it follows that indefinite terms are usually used to introduce referents into the discourse, whereas definite terms are typically used to refer back to a referent that has already been established in the discourse. On the basis of this distinction, the vast majority of uses of definite and indefinite terms can be understood. Consider such examples as:

(2) a. Yesterday I met an old friend of mine (construe referent x_i). He (identify x_i , which is now available through contextual information) did not even recognize me!

b. I was greatly impressed by the Eiffel Tower.
(referent presumed to be available through long-term information).

c. Do you see the man with the green hat?
(referent presumed to be available through perceptual information).

d. I like the car but I do not like the color.
(referent presumed to be available through inference).

2. (In)definiteness in Chinese: lexical strategies

As the category of definiteness is universal, there are many means in Chinese, including lexical, morphological, and position in sentence, to indicate whether the

nominal expressions should be interpreted as being of definite or indefinite reference.

We should point out that the expression of definiteness in Mandarin does not bring into play a distinct morphological unit that correspond to the French articles *le* (the in English) and *un* (a in English), but it is possible to give some general rules to determine whether a noun phrase will be interpreted as definite or indefinite. From a lexical point of view, according to some linguists [Chao, 1968; Rygaloff, 1973; Li et Thompson, 1989; Chen Ping, 2004], of the major determiners in Chinese, the demonstratives is beginning to function as ‘the’ if it is not stressed, and *yi* ‘one’ + classifier, if it is not stressed, on the other hand, is beginning to function as ‘a’¹. For example:

(3) 你认识不认识那个人?

nǐ	rènshi	bú	rènshi	nèi	gè	rén?
you	know	NEG	know	that	CL	person

‘Stressed: Do you know that person?’

Not stressed: Do you know the person?’

(Li et Thompson, 1989, p.132)

(4) 他买了一顶帽子

tā	mǎi	le	yì	dǐng	màozi.
3sg	buy	PFV	one	CL	hat

‘Stressed: He bought one hat.

Not stressed: He bought a hat.’

(ibidem)

But it should be known that the definiteness in Chinese, could be characterized by the absence of any determiners, including the demonstrative, or the absence of any quantitative or qualitative determination. That’s what makes Chinese further different from languages like English. In Mandarin, bare NPs and numeral NPs by themselves are neutral in respect of the interpretation of definiteness. At least in this case, a double problem of interpretation cannot fail to arise, if only for the translation into French, because of the two choices which are simultaneously imposed on us, due to the existence and the game of articles: definite / indefinite and singular / plural. For example, the bare noun 书 “book”, itself can be translated into French in four different ways, « le livre » (the book), « les livres »(the books), « un livre »(a book), « des livres »(books). Thus, in this case, we need more strategies to indicate the definite and indefinite in Mandarin.

3. (In)definiteness in Chinese: position in sentences

1 It should be noted that morphologically and in some cases also functionally they have not yet been fully grammaticalized. See Chen Ping [2004].

Most linguists [Mullie, 1932; Chao, 1968; Teng, 1975; Coyaud et Paris, 1976; Ding, 1979; Li et Thompson, 1989; Zhu, 2010] agree in recognizing that the position of the noun phrase in sentences is closely correlated with the definite reference and indefinite reference in Mandarin Chinese. More specifically, a number of linguists argue that the verb, in Mandarin Chinese, establishes by its position in a sentence the privileged position for the interpretation of the noun phrases as definite or indefinite. It is therefore possible to posit as a general rule that a bare noun is definite and indefinite according to whether it precedes the verb or follows it [Rygaloff, 1973, p87]. Consider the following classic example:

(5) a. 客人来了。

kèrén	lái	le.
guest	come	PFV
‘The guest(s) arrived.’		

b. 来客人了。

lái	kèrén	le.
come	guest	PFV
‘A guest/some guests arrived.’		

(Givon, 2001, p409)

The NP 客人 kèrén ‘guest’ in the classic example (5a), can be interpreted as definite when it precedes the verb, but as indefinite when it follows it in (5b).

It is also said that the subject of a sentence or the object of a pretransitive has a definite reference [Chao, 1968, p343]. To gain a better understanding of the interpretation of NPs in Mandarin, we will examine this rule in detail in the following sections.

4. Subject

The first linguists who took this phenomenon into account in Chinese, Mullie [1932, pp.160-168, 178-185] and Chao [1968, pp.76-78, 343-344] argue that the subject sets the topic of the talk and the predicate gives the information by adding something new, the subject is likely to represent the known while the predicate introduces something unknown. Thus we obtained a classic rule accepted for several decades by all linguists: ‘there is a very strong tendency for the subject to have a definite reference and the object to have an indefinite reference’[Chao, 1968, p.76].

Most Chinese linguists agree that indefinite NPs cannot occur in the subject position in Chinese sentences, unless they are licensed with an existential syntactic marker [Coyaud and Paris, 1976, p137; Zhu, 2010], as illustrated in the following sentences:

(6) a. *一个人来看你

yí	gè	rén	lái	kàn	nǐ
one	CL	person	come	see	you

b. 有一个人来看你。

yǒu	yí	gè	rén	lái	kàn	nǐ
have	one	CL	person	come	see	you

‘Someone comes to see you / ‘There is a person who comes to see you.’

The majority of linguists have accepted this rule for a long time, and try to convince us that cases where an indefinite NP appears in subject position are exceptions in Chinese. However, it is indeed difficult to understand why this type of sentence is rarely allowed in Chinese, while it does not encounter any difficulties in other languages, such as French and English:

- (7) a. Une voiture passe dans la rue.
 b. Un enfant jouait dans la cour.
 c. A car came.
 d. A man from New Zealand does a backflip.

After our counting up corpus of spoken and written Chinese, literature, news and scientific style, we found out that the yi(one)+classifier NPs can take the subject role with or without an existential syntactic marker in Chinese sentences. It is not an exceptional and rare case in Mandarin but with certain constraints. In fact, we noticed here three types of situations:

- a. It is necessary to have the existential syntactic marker 有yǒu ‘have’ before the yi(one)+classifier NPs:

(8) a. 有一个女青年笑了。

yǒu	yí	gè	nǚ	qīngnián	xiào	le.
have	one	CL	female	youth	laugh	PFV

‘A young woman laughed. / There is a young woman laughed.’

b. *一个女青年笑了。

yí	gè	nǚ	qīngnián	xiào	le.
one	CL	female	youth	laugh	PFV

We noticed that an intransitive verb cannot assume by itself (even with a sentence-final particle) the predicate function when an indefinite NP is in the subject position. The predicate of sentence needs to have a complex form:

- (9) 一个女青年笑得直不起腰来。

yí gè nǚ qīngnián xiào de zhí bù qǐ yāo lái.
 one CL female youth laugh DE straighten NEG rise up waist LAI
 ‘A young woman does not straighten her back with laughter.’ (being bent with laughter)

We have also noted that the complexity of the NP also determines its ability to be inserted at the beginning of a sentence, i.e., the more specific the SN is, the more it can function as the subject of a sentence, as the following examples show:

- (10) a. ??一个人来了。

yí gè rén lái le.
 one CL person come PFV
 ‘A man came.’

- b. ?一个中年人来了。

yí gè zhōngnián rén lái le.
 one CL middle-aged man come PFV
 ‘A middle-aged man came.’

- c. 一个抱小孩的中年人来了。

yí gè bào xiǎohái de zhōngnián rén lái le.
 one CL hold baby DE middle-aged man come PFV
 ‘A middle-aged man carrying a baby in his arms came in.’

b. the existential syntactic marker 有yǒu ‘have’ is optional. Following are some examples:

- (11) a. 刚要出去瞅瞅，一个人冒冒失失跑来了。

gāng yào chūqù chǒuchǒu, yí gè rén màomàoshīshī pǎo lái le.
 just want go out to see one CL man reckless run LAI PFV
 ‘(He) was just about to go out and take a look, a person came running recklessly.’

- b. ...有一个人冒冒失失跑来了。

...yǒu yí gè rén màomàoshīshī pǎo lái le.
 have one CL man reckless run LAI PFV

‘...there was a person came running recklessly.’

We can accept both constructions here. From a semantic point of view, we can hardly notice the difference between these two constructions. Just with the auxiliary mark 有yǒu ‘have’, we insist on the existence of the entity, without 有yǒu ‘have’, we rather insist on the event.

c. it is not appropriate to have the 有yǒu ‘have’ for some sentences. Consider the following sentences:

(12) 敌人的一个卫兵在打盹, 一个战士上去, 一匕首结果了他。

dírén de yí gè wèibīng zài dǎdǔn, yí gè zhànshi shàng qù
 enemy DE one CL guard PROG nap one CL soldier up QU
 yí bīshǒu jiéguǒ le tā.
 one dagger kill PFV he

‘One of the enemy guards was napping, and a soldier went up and killed him with a dagger.’

In the example above, we cannot add the existential syntactic marker 有yǒu ‘have’ before the second indefinite NP 一个战士 *yí gè zhànshi* ‘a soldier’, while for the first indefinite NP, where another modifier precedes the structure YI+CL+N, 有yǒu ‘have’ cannot present without changing the word order, let's compare the following sentences:

(13) a. *有敌人的一个卫兵在打盹...

yǒu dírén de yí gè wèibīng zài dǎdǔn...
 have enemy DE one CL guard PROG nap

b. 有一个敌人的卫兵在打盹...

yǒu yí gè dírén de wèibīng zài dǎdǔn...
 have one CL enemy DE guard PROG nap

‘One of the enemy guards was napping...’

After comparing these two structures, we can emphasize again that the indefinite NP in subject position is not an exceptional case, but a necessary structure in some cases.

5. The BA construction

According to several linguists[Chao, 1968, p343; Ding, 1979, p95; Hashimoto, 1971, p66; Lü, 1979, pp173- 175; Tan, 1983; Zhu, 1982, p187], the use of the *ba* sentence is linked to a definite reference. The case when the *ba* NP is indefinite is considered as exceptions to Chinese, as exemplified in the following sentences[Zhu, 1982, p.187]:

(14) a. 请来了一位大夫。

qǐng	lái	le	yí	wèi	dàifu.
invite	come	PFV	one	CL	doctor

‘We invited a doctor to come.’

b. *把一位大夫请来了

bǎ	yí	wèi	dàifu	qǐng	lái	le
BA	one	CL	doctor	invite	come	PFV

According to Zhu Dexi(ibid.), the reason that (14b) is an ungrammatical sentence, is that the NP of *bǎ* 一位大夫 *yí wèi dàifu* ‘a doctor’ is indefinite and an indefinite NP can not occur in the *bǎ* construction. The sentence will become grammatical if we use a definite NP:

(15) 把那位大夫请来了。

bǎ	nà	wèi	dàifu	qǐng	lái	le.
BA	DEM	CL	doctor	invite	come	PFV

‘We invited that doctor to come.’

The *ba* NP should be definite is considered as a general rule recognized by the vast majority of linguists and often cited in textbooks. The ‘definite/indefinite’ opposition is established in the pupil’s mind in relation to the articles of the same name in French, the French pupils even pass through the French translation to check whether they can use BA. However these concepts are quite vague and need further specification. Our data in the table below shows that for the ‘*ba*’ sentences, *yi*(one)+classifier NPs can occur in the *ba*-NP position.

Table 1:

Year of publication	Titles	Word count	BA sentences	BA + YI + CL + N
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2005-2012	Three novels of Chun Sue ²	25000	352	10
2004-2009	Two novels of de Sun Rui ³	25000	495	4
2008-2013	Two CCTV programs	four million	5591	78
2017-2018	People's Daily	forty million	30281	249

Based on our findings, we found seven possible uses of the sequence [BA + YI (un) + CL + Noun], as illustrated by the following examples:

a) a certain number of people, animals, things or ideas: one.

(16) 都乐 (Dole) 食品靠什么可以把一根香蕉卖到6块钱 ?

dōulè shípǐn kào shénme kěyǐ bǎ yì gēn xiāngjiāo
 Dole food depend on what can BA one CL banana
 mài dào liù kuài qián?
 sell arrive six yuan money

« Why can Dole Food sell one banana for 6 yuan? » (sohu news : www.sohu.com)

b) the whole.

(17) 老塘趴在一个长沙发上,

lǎotáng pā zài yí gè cháng shāfā shàng,
 PN lie prone Prep one CL long couch on

把一个沙发都占严了, ...

bǎ yí gè shāfā dōu zhàn yán le...
 BA one CL couch all occupy tight PFV

« Laotang lies prone on a long couch, (he) occupies the (whole) sofa. . »
 (Sugimura, 2002, p.21)

c) a specific object that is part of a given set.

2 Chun Sue, born June 28, 1983 in Beijing, is a Chinese novelist, publisher and poet. The three novels concerned are: “2条命 Liang Tiao Ming”(2005), “长达半天的欢乐 Changda Bantian De Huanle” (2004), “光年至美国梦 Guangnian Zhi Meiguo Meng”(2010).

3 Sun Rui, born in 1980 in Beijing, is a Chinese writer, director and publisher. We used his two books: “草样年华 Caoyang Nianhua” et “朝三暮四 Zhao San Mu Si”.

- (18) 我走到他跟前，他把一只手放在我肩上。

wǒ zǒu dào tā gēnqián, tā bǎ yì zhī shǒu
 1sg walk arrive 3sg nearby 3sg BA one CL hand
 fàng zài wǒ jiān shàng.
 put Prep 1sg shoulder one

« I approached him, he put a hand on my shoulders. »

(Zhao, *Le Livre-cœur*, 2012)

d) any referent.

- (19) 我想把一本中文小说译成英文，但还没决定译哪一本，你说译哪本好？

wǒ xiǎng bǎ yì běn zhōngwén xiǎoshuō yìchéng yīngwén,
 1sg want BA one CL Chinese roman translate English
 dàn hái méi juéding yì nǎ yì běn
 but yet NEG decide translate which one CL
 nǐ shuō yì nǎi běn hǎo?
 2sg say translate which CL good

« I intend to translate a Chinese novel into English, but (I) have not yet decided which one to translate. Tell me which one should be translated? »

(Song, 1981, p.42)

e) a number of: 一些

- (20) 我把一些事情处理好马上走！

wǒ bǎ yì xiē shìqíng chùlǐ hǎo mǎshàng zǒu!
 1sg BA one CL affair dispose good right away go

« I will go right away after the processing of some cases. »

(Wang Huo, *Zhanzheng He Ren*, 1993)

f) indefinite

- (21) 老叫花...把一个油布包塞给年少的廖学兵。

lǎo jiàohuā... bǎ yì gè yóubù bāo sāi gěi niánshào de liàoxuébīng
 old beggar BA one CL tarpaulin bag fill give young DE PN

« The old beggar slipped a tarpaulin bag to the young Liao Xuebing. »

(Zhang Junbao, *Chaoji Jiaoshi*, 2009)

g) a unique referent

(22) 吕洞宾的青蛇、酒气、纵笑, 把一个洞庭湖搅得神神乎乎。

lǚdòngbī	de	qīngshé	jiǔ	qì	zòngxiào,	bǎ	yì	gè
PN	DE	Green snake	wine	breath	laughter	BA	one	CL
dòngtíng hú	jiǎo	dé	shénshénhūhū.					
PN	disturb	DE	mysterious					

« Dongting Lake was disturbed by the green snake, the smell of alcohol and the laughter of Lu Dongbin. »

(Yu Qiuyu, *Cultural Perplexity in Agonized Travel*, 1992)

In these examples, ba NP could be interpreted differently, including definite interpretation (examples (17) and (22)), indefinite specific interpretation (examples (18) (20) and (21)) and indefinite non-specific interpretation (examples (19)). The category d must be mentioned. That contrary to expectation, the ba NP has not only an indefinite interpretation, but also an indefinite non-specific interpretation. In examples (17) and (22), in spite of the form Yi(one) + Cl + N, which is called ‘indefinite form’ by some linguists, the ba NP should be interpreted as definite, because they refer back to a referent that has already been established in the discourse.

6. Conclusion

It should be noted that for English, French, also for Chinese, the category of definite indefinite does not concern simply a morpheme but the interpretation. For the formal expression of the operators definite and indefinite there is a frequent, but not a necessary correspondence with definite and indefinite articles or affixes. This correspondence is far from complete even in English or French. To understand the essence of definiteness, it is necessary to investigate the notion beyond the article systems of specific languages.

For Chinese, the structure of the noun phrase is not the only factor related to the distinction between definite reference and indefinite reference. The syntax of the whole sentence, as well as the broader context, plays an important role in a language without article like Chinese. Multiple factors interact, mutually reinforce and mutually condition each other, this forms a complex system of interpretations of noun phrases as definite, indefinite, specific and generic in Chinese.

Based our findings in this paper, I would like to make a further point of more general interest. The previous work of several linguists on *bǎ* construction, and the analysis of our corpus led us to find the existence of examples like the one in (22), where the noun 洞庭湖 *dòngtíng hú* ‘Dongting Lake’, being a proper name, can only refer,

semantically, to a unique referent. Yet we see the co-occurrence of the form Yi(one) + CI used with an expression of definite reference. So what is the function of the form Yi(one) + CI here?

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CHEN: (IN)DEFINITENESS IN A LANGUAGE WITHOUT ARTICLES

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How Sub-Event Verbal Classifiers and Numerals are Related to Telicity in Taiwan Mandarin: From a Constructionist Perspective

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This study discusses sub-event verbal classifiers and numerals in Taiwan Mandarin as well as the roles they play in event structure. Using the Exo-Skeletal Model (Borer 2005a) as a framework, I propose that when an event is divided into countable sub-events by a verbal classifier, a classifier phrase projects, and its empty head is given semantic content by the classifier in the specifier position. The classifier phrase then merges with a functional head called Asp_Q , which projects into Asp_QP with a numeral in its specifier position. I will show that the numeral is responsible for giving semantic content to the empty head of Asp_QP , thereby giving rise to a telic reading of the whole event.

1. Introduction

This study explores the relationship between three things: sub-event verbal classifiers, numerals, and telicity. It will focus on the following construction, which I will term “the divided-event construction.”

- (1) Ta qie le dangao liang xia / dao.
 3rd cut PFV cake two CL-time / CL-knife
 “S/he cut the cake twice.”

In example (1), a verb and its object are followed by a numeral, which in turn is followed by what I call a sub-event verbal classifier (*sub-event classifier* for short henceforth)¹.

¹ From the perspective of this study, sub-event classifiers form a paradigm in the sense that they serve the same syntactic function; namely, they all assign range (to be defined in section 2.2.1) to the same functional head. From a semantic point of view, however, there are different types of sub-event classifiers. First, instrument sub-event classifiers specify what instrument is involved in the event. “Dao (knife)” in sentence (1) is a typical example, indicating a knife was used in the cutting event. Second, body-part sub-event classifiers specify what body part is used by the agent that carries out the action denoted by the verb. Third, emission sub-event classifiers such as “sheng (sound)” denote the production and discharge of something as a result of an action. Finally, there is the default sub-event classifier “xia (time),” as seen in sentence (1).

The numeral-sub-event classifier combination has often been thought of as a frequency phrase in the literature (e.g., Del Gobbo 2014). More specifically, the classifier in this combination has been treated as denoting sub-events or “slices of events” (Jeong 2002:5, Zhang 2017). In this work, I will maintain the view that sub-event classifiers divide an event into countable sub-events, which in turn can be counted with a numeral.

The relationship between telicity and sub-event classifier has also been discussed in the literature. For instance, in their discussion on the semantic functions of sub-event classifiers in Cantonese and Thai, Matthews and Leung (2001) suggest that constructions like that in (1) assign boundary to an event, thereby rendering the event telic. In line of this view, I will propose that the divided-event construction is telic because quantity has been assigned by a numeral. (The notion of quantity will be defined in section 3.1.)

The present study, however, differs from previous ones in three major aspects. First, although right about the connection between the divided-event construction and telicity, Matthews and Leung (2001) did not formalize that connection. Their proposed structure of a divided event, which has a VP dominating a Classifier Phrase, also differs considerably from the one I will propose in this work. Second, although Zhang (2017) has formalized the relation between Classifier Phrase and VP and demonstrated how different surface word orders can be derived, telicity is still not included in her formalization. Third, to the best of my knowledge, most analyses of the divided-event construction in the literature are lexicalist, whereas the one to be presented here is generative-constructionist in nature (largely based on Borer’s (2005a, b, 2013) Exo-Skeletal Model). As we will see, a generative-constructionist approach has a certain theoretical advantage over a lexicalist one.

The remaining sections are organized as follows. Section 2 will introduce an overall syntactic structure of the divided-event construction and lay out my central theses. I will also provide a brief introduction on the theoretical framework to be used. In section 3, I will focus on the connection between the divided-event construction and telicity. Evidence will be provided to show such a connection does exist. Section 4 will address issues related to movement and derivation of surface word order. I will also highlight one advantage of my approach to these issues. Section 5 will conclude this study.

2. Hypothesis

2.1. Structure of a Divided Event

Using sentence (2) as an example, I propose a syntactic structure of the divided-event construction in (3):

- (2) Ta qie le (dangao) liang xia.
 3rd cut PFV (cake) two CL-time
 “S/he cut (the cake) twice.”

(3) Syntactic structure of the divided-event construction

In line with Zhang (2017), I propose that the sub-event classifier divides an event into countable sub-events, and that there is a functional projection within which the classifier resides. I assume this projection, which will be called CLvP from now on, is part of the extended projection in the event-structure domain, and that whatever lexical phrase merges with the head of a CLvP will become a VP².

² Recall that the model adopted here is a generative-constructionist model. A lexical word is, by assumption, devoid of categorial information and only obtains a category by merging with a functional head. For example, the word “walk” becomes an N when it merges with a D (e.g., “the walk”) but becomes a V with an Asp (e.g., “walked”). “Walk” by itself is merely a root with no category specified in its entry. For more details, see Borer (2005a, b, and especially 2013).

Careful readers may notice that in (3) the sub-event classifier “xia (time)” is in the specifier position and assigns range from there (more on range assignment in section 2.2.1). This is different from many previous accounts that analyze the sub-event classifier as the head of a classifier phrase.

Building upon CLvP, which has divided an event into countable sub-events, I propose that there is a functional projection that turns an event into a quantity (telic) one. (See section 3.1 for the definition of quantity.) Following Borer’s (2005b) terminology, this projection will be referred to as Asp_QP. A numeral assigns range to the empty Asp_Q head from the specifier of Asp_QP. Note that according to Borer’s (2005b) account, Asp_Q may introduce an internal argument and assign accusative case if needed. However, as will be clear in later sections, internal arguments are not introduced in the divided-event construction this way.

Should there be an internal argument in a divided-event construction, it will be introduced and assigned partitive case by a semantically vacuous functional projection. Again, following Borer’s (2013) terminology, I will call this partitive-case-assigning projection F^{SHLP} from now on.

The three pieces of structure—CLvP, Asp_QP, and F^{SHLP}—will be the primary focus of this work. There may be, of course, more structure above them. For example, a vP must project to introduce an external argument; an AspP (not to be confused with Asp_QP) is needed if outer aspect is to be specified; a TP projects for tense reasons and, by common assumption, for the assignment of nominative case.

In the next two sections, I will lay out some fundamental assumptions on which the Exo-Skeletal Model (Borer, 2005a, b, 2013) is built. As this work is largely based on this particular model, it is essential to have an adequate understanding of its workings.

2.2.1. The XS Model: The Basics

The present analysis is largely based on the Exo-Skeletal (XS) Model developed in Borer (2005a, b, 2013). Being a generative-constructionist model, the XS Model posits that functional projections have radically empty heads (denoted by <e> henceforth). Because they are empty, they need to be assigned semantic content (*range* in the XS Model terminology) so that the functional projections can properly return an interpretation. Range assigners are typically functional words, but they can be abstract features with no phonological content (e.g., <past> for past tense). Diagram (4) is an example where the determiner “the” assigns range to [D<e>] by being in the head position. A range assigner can also occupy the specifier (or adjunct) position of a functional projection and assign range to the empty head through specifier-head agreement. Diagram (5) is an example of a numeral assigning range to the head of a Quantity Phrase:

(4)

(5)

Aside from the two modes of range assignment above, it is also possible to assign range to an empty head from outside of the projection. Regardless of the mode, however, once an empty head is assigned range, it cannot be assigned range again by another functional element. Thus, cases like (6), where two determiners compete to assign range to the same empty head [D<e>], are ruled out:

(6) *my the cat

Crucially, a functional projection, if it is to return any interpretation at all, must have its empty head assigned range properly one way or another. If no range is assigned, the semantic component cannot compute the intended meaning, and ungrammaticality will ensue. The model in Borer (2005b, 2013), however, does allow certain functional projections to have no interpretations at all; that is, these projections only assign case, introduce an argument, and/or categorize a lexical constituent, but they play no role in computing meaning and therefore do not require range assignment. I will continue to assume in this work that such semantically vacuous functional projections exist.

2.2.2. The XS Model: Movement

What triggers movement? In this model, movement can occur for phonological reasons when range is assigned by an abstract, phonologically null feature. Consider the following example in English (CL stands for Classifier):

(7)

The head of the functional projection CLP is assigned range by an abstract feature <div> (division, i.e., turning a mass into countable units), and due to the feature’s lack of phonological content, it needs support from the lexical domain to be properly spelled out. The lexical head “woman” thus undergoes head movement to provide phonological content for <div>. The head pair [<div>, woman] will spell out as “women.”

I have laid out the basic assumptions behind the XS Model and proposed a structure of the divided-event construction. In summary, I am proposing the following:

- (8) There is a functional projection called CLvP, which is responsible for dividing an event into countable sub-events. The CLvP is projected from an empty head, which is assigned range through specifier-head agreement by a sub-event classifier in the specifier position of CLvP. (See (11).)
- (9) The divided-event construction denotes a quantity (telic) event, and thus AspQP, which is a functional projection for quantity event structure, must project. The empty head of AspQP is assigned range through specifier-head agreement by a numeral in the specifier position of AspQP. (See (12).)
- (10) Should there be an internal argument in a divided event, it will be introduced by a semantically vacuous functional projection called F^{SHLP}, whose head needs no range assignment. (See (13).)

(11)

(12)

(13)

- (14) The linear word order of the divided-event construction is the result of head movement. Specifically, a lexical head moves up to a functional head above AspQP (and F^{SHLP}, if there is one) to provide phonological content for some abstract feature.

3. Telicity (Quantity)

In this section, evidence for the claims in (9) and (10) will be presented. I will first provide a definition of telicity and then argue that numerals, rather than the presence of a quantity internal argument, are responsible for telicity in the divided-event construction.

3.1. Telicity Defined

Following Borer (2005b), a telic event is defined as an event that is quantity, which is in turn defined informally as below:

(15) X is quantity if X is non-cumulative or non-divisive.

It follows from (15) that sentences such as (16) cannot denote a quantity event, for (16) is both divisive and cumulative. It is divisive in that the event of the bird flying can be divided into multiple sub-events, all of which are instances of flying and can be properly denoted by sentence (16). It is also cumulative in the sense that if (16) is only a sub-event of a larger event E, and if the other sub-event or sub-events of E can also be properly denoted by (16), then E can be properly denoted by (16), i.e., “The bird flew.”

(16) The bird flew (for two minutes / *in two minutes).

In contrast, (17) is a quantity—hence telic—event, for it is obviously non-divisive. One cannot divide the event denoted by (17) into multiple sub-events and claim in any sensible way that all the sub-events are instances of (17). The first half of the event, for example, is clearly not “flying to the top of the tree,” but an instance of “flying toward the top of the tree.” Note that in this case, the non-divisiveness of (17) alone satisfies the condition for quantity and telicity, regardless of whether it can be established that (17) is cumulative or not.

(17) The bird flew to the top of the tree (*for two minutes / in two minutes).

Having defined telicity, we can now substantiate the claim that the divided-event construction denotes a quantity/telic event. Compare the following:

(18) Ta (zai san miao nei) qiao le liang xia.
 3rd (be-at three second inside) knock LE two CL-time
 “S/he knocked twice (in three seconds).”

(19) Ta (*zai san miao nei) qiao le.
 3rd (be-at three second inside) knock LE
 “S/he knocked (*in three seconds).”

It is clear that (18) denotes a telic event because it is non-divisive. There is no way to break up the event and properly denote any of the sub-events by sentence (18). One cannot, for example, use (18) to refer to the sub-event that spans from the beginning to the point where the first knock is completed, for that sub-event should be an event of “knocking once.” It is equally clear that (18) cannot be cumulative, either. If (18) is only

one sub-event of E, and if E has another sub-event that can also be properly denoted by (18)—that is, there is another sub-event of knocking twice—, then one cannot sensibly refer to E as an event of “knocking twice” instead of “knocking four times.” In contrast, (19) is both divisive and cumulative. Under the most natural interpretation³, a sub-event of knocking can still be properly referred to as “knocking.” Similarly, if there is a bigger event E that comprises (19) and other sub-events which can also be properly denoted by (19), then E will be an event of knocking, too.

In sum, the divided-event construction denotes telic/quantity events and does not need a quantity internal argument to yield telic interpretation, as evidenced by sentence (18). Instead, numeral phrases like “liang xia (twice)” are responsible for telicity. We now turn to motion predicates for further evidence that bolsters this conclusion.

3.2. Evidence from Motion Predicates

I have argued elsewhere (Chen 2018, Chen et al. 2019) that telicity in motion predicates stems from the presence of an “arriving verb” or preposition with a similar meaning, and that this is true not only in English (cf. (17)) but also in multiple unrelated languages such as Tati, Ghanaian Student Pidgin, and Mandarin:

- (20) Xiao niao zai san miao nei fei **(dao* shu shang).
 little bird be at three second inside fly **(arrive* tree top)
 “The birdie flew **(to* the top of the tree) in three seconds.”

Recall that a telic syntactic structure has the functional projection Asp_QP , whose head needs to be assigned range. And since telicity in motion predicates hinges on the arriving verb, it must be the one that assigns range to $[Asp_Q<e>]$. (For details, see Chen (2018).)

With that in mind, note that we concluded in the last section that numeral phrases like “si xia (four times)” give rise to telicity; put in technical terms, they force the projection of Asp_QP . The question now is whether they assign range to the empty head of Asp_Q , as claimed in (9). If a numeral phrase in the divided-event construction assigns range to $[Asp_Q<e>]$, we should predict that it cannot co-occur with an arriving verb, for they would compete for the same empty head. This prediction is born out:

³ By that I mean a semelfactive (i.e., durative, indefinitely iterative (Ramchand 2008, p. 80)) reading of (19). One might argue that is not the only possible reading, and that “qiao” may sometimes denote an event of achievement (i.e., an event of knocking one time and one time only). However, that is beside the point, for what I am trying to demonstrate here is how (18), even under a semelfactive reading, can still obtain telicity. Thus, sentences (18) and (19) should be treated as a minimal pair, both being semelfactive. Readers who are interested in the relation between telicity and achievement verbs can refer to Chapter 10 of Borer (2005b).

- (21) Mu-zhuang bei qiao dao fang-kuai li.
 wood-peg BEI hammer arrive cube inside
 “The wooden peg is hammered into the cube.”
- (22) Mu-zhuang bei qiao si xia.
 wood-peg BEI hammer four CL-time
 “The wooden peg is hammered four times (in a row).”
- (23) *Mu-zhuang bei qiao si xia dao fang-kuai li.
 wood-peg BEI hammer four CL-time arrive cube inside
 “The wooden peg is hammered four times (in a row) into the cube.”

Incidentally, notice that even though sentence (24) below is possible in English, it can only denote an event in which the peg went into the cube each time it was hammered, not one in which the peg went into the cube as a result of being hammered three times in a row. In other words, “thrice” is the number of times the event of “the peg being hammered into the cube” repeats, rather than the number of sub-events it can be divided into. Sentence (24) is therefore not a divided-event construction.

(24) He hammered the peg thrice into the cube.

In sum, the numeral phrase in a divided-event construction not only causes the projection of Asp_QP but also functions as a range assigner to [Asp_Q<e>].

3.3. Numeral vs. Classifier: Which Assigns Range?

I have argued that numeral phrases in the divided-event construction, e.g., “si xia (four times)” in (22), give rise to telicity. However, careful readers may notice the claim in (9) is more specific. According to (9), range is assigned to [Asp_Q<e>] by “a numeral,” not a numeral phrase. This means a sub-event classifier such as “xia (time)” by itself does not assign range to [Asp_Q<e>], as it is not a numeral. I will provide evidence to support the claim.

Ideally, one would have to demonstrate that a divided-event construction with a sub-event classifier but without a numeral does not obtain telicity. To the best of my knowledge, however, no example of such a divided-event construction can be found in Mandarin. We thus have to turn to idioms consisting of reduplications of sub-event classifiers. Below is one example:

- (25) quan quan dao rou
 CL-fist CL-fist arrive flesh
 “beat someone with forceful punches”

- (26) Wo *quan quan dao rou* de da ta.
 1st *CL-fist CL-fist arrive flesh* DE beat 3rd
 “I beat him/her with forceful punches.”

Note that “quan (fist)” in this idiom is a sub-event classifier as opposed to a nominal classifier. The reduplication of “quan” does not mean that multiple fists are involved in the beating event. Rather, it means there are multiple sub-events of beating. Sentence (26) is still acceptable even if I hit my victim multiple times with only one hand.

Now, suppose this idiomatic adverbial phrase in (26) can assign range to the empty head of CLv (see (28)). Suppose further that sub-event classifiers by themselves cannot assign range to [AspQ<e>]. Without any numeral, (26) should have a semelfactive, atelic reading, and this appears to be true:

- (27) Wo *quan quan dao rou* de da ta *wu fen-zhong*
 1st *CL-fist CL-fist arrive flesh* DE beat 3rd *five minute*
 “I beat him/her with forceful punches for five minutes.”

(28)

When the “for x time” phrase is replaced with “in x time,” acceptability deteriorates:

- (29) ?Wo *zai wu fen-zhong nei quan quan* dao rou de da ta.
 1st *be at five minute inside CL-fist CL-fist arrive flesh* DE beat 3rd
 “I beat him/her with forceful punches in five minutes.”

While the contrast between (27) and (29) is not sharp, the fact that the former is perfectly acceptable is in favor of the claim that numerals, rather than sub-event classifiers, are the ones assigning range to [AspQ<e>].

3.4. Internal Arguments

It should be clear by now that in the divided-event construction, [Asp_Q<e>] is assigned range by a numeral, the presence of which is licensed by a sub-event classifier. It follows that the construction cannot allow range assignment to [Asp_Q<e>] by an internal argument that is quantity in the sense of (15) (repeated below as (30)). Verkuyl's Generalization (Verkuyl, 1972), which states that telicity arises in the presence of a quantity internal argument⁴, does not apply here.

(30) X is quantity if X is non-cumulative or non-divisive.

How exactly does a quantity internal argument fit in this picture, then? Note that the internal argument of a divided-event construction *can* be quantity. Sentence (31) is an example. The internal argument “na zhuo-zi (that table)” is clearly non-divisive, for no subparts of the table can be sensibly referred to as “that table.”

(31) Ta qiao na zhuo-zi liang xia.
 3rd knock that table two CL-time
 “S/he knocked that table twice.”

An answer has been put forward in (10), which states that internal arguments must be introduced by a semantically vacuous functional projection (F^{SHLP}) instead of an Asp_QP. The following sections will justify this answer.

3.4.1. Finnish

Recall that in the XS Model, telic and atelic events syntactically correspond to the presence and absence of Asp_QP, respectively. Should there be a quantity internal argument in the specifier of Asp_QP, it will receive accusative case and assign range to [Asp_Q<e>] through specifier-head agreement, giving rise to telicity in the way captured by Verkuyl's Generalization. On the other hand, if there is a quantity internal argument but no telicity, Asp_QP must not project, and the argument has to be introduced by F^{SHLP} and receive partitive case from it. In Finnish, accusative and partitive case markings are phonologically distinct:

(32) Anne rakensi taloa.
 Anne built house-PRT
 “Anne was building a/the house.”

(33) Anne rakensi talon.
 Anne built house-ACC
 “Anne built a/the house.”

⁴ To illustrate Verkuyl's Generalization, consider the following pair:

- (i) Mary ate apples (for five minutes / *in five minutes).
- (ii) Mary ate two apples (*for five minutes / in five minutes).

If the internal argument in a divided-event construction is not introduced by Asp_QP, we should predict that in Finnish, the internal argument in a divided event will take partitive rather than accusative case. This prediction is correct:

- (34) Koputin ovea /*oven kahdesti.⁵
 knocked.1st.SG door-PRT/*door-ACC twice
 “I knocked the door twice.”

- (35) Simplified tree diagram⁶ of sentence (34)

Sentence (34) lends very strong support to our analysis. Accusative and partitive case marking in Finnish is generally thought of as reflecting the difference between telicity and atelicity, respectively. In (34), however, the internal argument takes on partitive case despite the telic reading of the event. The reason is that [Asp_Q<e>] is already assigned range by “kahdesti (twice);” the internal argument is therefore “forced” to be in a structural position other than Spec Asp_QP, otherwise it would assign range to [Asp_Q<e>], causing double range assignment as illustrated below.

⁵ I thank Dr. Angela Bartens for providing the Finnish sentence and Kwaku Osei-Tutu for consulting her on my behalf.

⁶ VP, CLvP, and vP are omitted for simplicity. Judging from the tense marking, “koputin (knocked)” presumably moves from V to T through head movement.

(36) Ungrammatical structure due to double range assignment

3.4.2. Unaccusative vs. Unergative

As is well known, unaccusative and unergative constructions have different structural configurations and interpretations, though they both involve only one argument. The sole argument of an unaccusative verb is introduced by Asp_QP. The argument of an unergative verb, on the other hand, is introduced by vP. Consider a typical unaccusative example in Mandarin in (37) and its structure in (38). Putting aside tense, aspect, and verb movement for a moment, note that the sole argument in (38) is an internal one, base-generated in Spec Asp_QP. The argument, being quantity, assigns range to the empty head of Asp_Q and subsequently moves to Spec TP for case. Needless to say, the event is a telic one.

(37) Hua-ping po le.
flower-vase break LE
“The vase broke.”

(38)

Now, what happens when sentence (37) is in a divided-event construction? In other words, what happens when the internal argument “hua-ping (the vase)” has to compete with a numeral for [AspQ<e>]? As predicted, such a sentence is unacceptable:

- (39) *Hua-ping po le liang xia.
 flower-vase break PFV two CL-time
 “The vase broke twice (in a row).” (unaccusative/non-agentive reading)

Interestingly, if one wishes to coerce a grammatical reading out of (39), it can only be done if “hua-ping” is introduced by a different functional projection to prevent double range assignment. What functional projection can serve such a purpose? The most obvious candidate is *v*P, which, as mentioned earlier, is the functional projection that introduces the sole argument in the unergative construction.

- (40) Structure of sentence (41), with a coerced reading

- (41) #Hua-ping po le liang xia.
 flower-vase break PFV two CL-time
 “The vase broke twice (in a row).” (unergative/agentive reading)

Again, putting aside tense, aspect, verb movement, and range assignment that is not relevant to this case⁷, the unergative structure in (40) is now a licit one, for the internal argument is no longer competing with the numeral for [Asp_Q<e>]. The *v*P here is, as it were, an escape hatch for what would otherwise be an ungrammatical structure. The interpretation, of course, is a coerced and comical one because of the conflict between grammar and world knowledge, but a little imagination can fix it: Suppose the vase has free will and a superpower to break itself up and pull its pieces back together in a matter of seconds. In such a scenario, sentence (41) will become acceptable.

Careful readers may object that the unaccusative construction is compatible with the divided-event construction as long as the classifier is “*ci*” instead of “*xia*.” However, Zhang (2017) argues that “*ci*” is in fact an *event* classifier whereas “*xia*” is a *sub-event* classifier, a difference that can be captured by the following pair:

(42) Hua-ping po le liang ci, qu-nian yi ci, jin-nian yi ci.
 vase break PFV two CL-time last-year one CL-time this-year one CL-time
 “The vase broke twice, once last year, once this year.”
 (unaccusative/non-agentive reading)

(43) *Ta qiao zhuo-zi liang xia, qu-nian yi xia, jin-nian yi xia.
 3rd knock table two CL-time last-year one CL-time this-year one CL-time
 “S/he knocked the table twice, once last year, once this year.”

Because “*ci*” is *not* an event divider and is thus outside the scope of Asp_QP, the numeral “*liang*” does not compete with “*hua-ping*” for [Asp_Q<e>] in (42), and therefore the sentence does not have to be coerced in order for grammaticality to be maintained. “*Xia*,” per contra, *is* a bona fide sub-event classifier and is thus incompatible with a context like (43), where events rather than sub-events are counted. Furthermore, the fact that structure—or the Aktionsart of a verb—has to be coerced by the presence of “*xia*” in cases like (41) to be grammatical, but not in cases like (42), suggests that sub-event classifiers are indeed related to inner aspect rather than outer aspect, hence within the scope of Asp_QP.

4. Word Order

In this section, I will show that the surface word order “V + (Object) + Numeral + Classifier” in the divided-event construction can be derived straightforwardly if we assume the verb moves to some functional head above Asp_QP and F^{SHLP} (if there is one).

4.1. Movement—From Lexical to Functional

Recall that in the XS Model, movement is triggered when a phonologically null feature needs to be spelled out. The surface word order of the divided-event construction

⁷ But see section 4.1 regarding the feature <init> in the head of *v*P.

is derived from the verb undergoing head movement to the little v that introduces an external argument. Arad (1999) has argued that there are different types of v with different interpretations. If true, then a vP cannot be a semantically vacuous projection, and its empty head must be assigned range. If one assumes that $[v<e>]$ is assigned range by an abstract feature in Mandarin, perhaps $<init>$ (standing for *initiation of an event*, in the sense of Ramchand (2008)), a lexical head will need to move to v and provide the feature with phonological content. We thus have the derivation in (45). The circled portion spells out as “qiao.”

(44) Ta qiao liang xia.
 3rd knock two CL-time
 “S/he knocked twice.”

Note that the movement illustrated above is not a unique theoretical proposal, for V-to- v movement has been proposed to take place in Mandarin (e.g., Huang et al., 2009). Therefore, even though the XS Model may have a different set of assumptions about what triggers movement than previous proposals, the movement itself is nothing new.

Once the verb has landed in v , it may move further up if there is another abstract feature in need of phonological support. By common assumption, the external argument “ta (s/he)” moves up to Spec TP for nominative case. To illustrate, the derivation of (46) will look like (47):

(46) Ta qiao le (zhuo-zi) liang xia.
 3rd knock PFV (table) two CL-time
 “S/he knocked (the table) twice.”

(47)

4.2. The XS Model vs. Lexicalist Alternative

The straightforwardness of the derivation in (47) is one advantage of the XS Model, which allows the existence of radically empty functional heads (Borer 2005a, b, 2013). This is different from a certain type of lexicalist treatment of the divided-event construction (e.g., Zhang 2017), which assumes CLvP is projected from a classifier rather than an empty head:

(48) [_{VP}... [_{CLvP} Numeral [_{CLv'} Sub-Event Classifier [_{VP} V ([_{DP} Object])]]]]]

One problem with (48) is that it is not clear how V-to-*v* movement can be maintained without violating the Head Movement Constraint since the sub-event classifier, being in a head position between *v* and V, blocks the movement. It appears that if (48) is to be maintained, one must either abandon V-to-*v* movement or posit more steps in order to derive the surface word order.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, I have argued that telicity, sub-event verbal classifiers, and numerals are interconnected. A sub-event classifier functions as an event divider, breaking an event into countable sub-events and thereby licensing the presence of a numeral, which in turn gives the whole event a quantity/telic reading by specifying how many sub-events there are. I have also shown that the XS Model has a clear advantage over a certain type of lexicalist account that treats the sub-event classifier as the head of a classifier phrase. This is mostly because the XS Model employs functional projections with empty heads. Without a classifier standing in the way, the surface word order can be easily derived by simply moving the verb from V to *v* without violating the Head Movement Constraint.

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An Experimental Investigation of Reconstruction Effects of the Head Quantifier Phrase in Chinese Relative Clauses

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Aoun and Li (2003) argued that whether the head of Chinese relative clauses can reconstruct is determined by the phrasal category of the head. When the head is a noun phrase, it can reconstruct into the relative clause whereas when it is a quantifier phrase, it cannot. This paper used a controlled truth value judgment experiment to investigate whether it is true that the head quantifier phrase cannot reconstruct in Chinese relative clauses. The results strongly suggested that a universal quantifier phrase in the embedded subject position can actually have scope over the head quantifier phrase, which argues against Aoun and Li's (1993, 2003) claim. It indicates that the head quantifier phrase can actually reconstruct into the Chinese relative clause, the same as the head noun phrase.

0. Introduction

Aoun and Li (2003) argued that the head reconstruction in Chinese relative clauses (RCs) is determined by the phrasal category of the head. When the head is a noun phrase, it can reconstruct into its base position inside the RC, supported by the evidence of anaphor binding. In contrast, when the head is a quantifier phrase (QP), it cannot reconstruct into the RC, which is evidenced by scope interaction: if there is a universal QP in the RC subject position, it cannot take scope over the head QP. Thus, Aoun and Li proposed a NP/QP distinction concerning the head reconstruction in Chinese RCs: an NP can reconstruct but a QP cannot. Moreover, the head QP's constraint is complicated by the presence of *dou* 'all' inside the RC. Aoun and Li (1993, 2003) observed that the universal QP in the RC subject position cannot have scope over the head QP only when there is *dou* 'all' in the RC. When there is no *dou*, the universal QP in the RC subject position can take scope over the head QP. In order to account for this contrast, Aoun and Li made the following proposal about the reconstruction of the head QP in Chinese RCs: i) a head QP simply cannot reconstruct into the RC; ii) when there is no *dou* inside the RC, a QP in the RC subject position can be raised out of the RC at LF and have scope over the head QP of RC; but when there is *dou* inside the RC, the raising of the embedded subject QP would be impossible because *dou* has a domain requirement with its related QP.

With a controlled truth value judgment experiment (Crain & Thornton, 1998), this paper investigated whether it is true that the head QP cannot reconstruct in Chinese RCs

with *dou*. The experimental results suggest that the universal QP in the RC subject position can always take wider scope over the head QP, regardless of the presence of *dou*, which argues against Aoun and Li's (1993, 2003) claim. Thus, the head QP of Chinese RCs should be able to reconstruct into the RC in the same way as the head NP and Aoun and Li's (2003) NP/QP distinction regarding the head reconstruction in Chinese RCs is not necessary. We can then conclude the head of Chinese RCs can always reconstruct into its base position at Logical Form (LF), regardless of its phrasal category.

1. Issue

Aoun and Li (2003) argued that the evidence for the head derivation in Chinese RCs is conflicting. On the one hand, when an anaphor *ziji* 'self' or a bound pronoun *ta* 'him/her' occurs within the head, it can be bound by an antecedent within the RC, as in (1a) and (1b) (Aoun & Li, 2003; Huang, Li & Li, 2009).

- (1a) [[wo jiao Zhangsan quan mei-ge-ren_i kai t_j lai de] [ziji_i-de chezi]_j]
 I ask Zhangsan persuade every-CL-person drive come DE self-GEN car
 'self's car that I asked Zhangsan to persuade everyone to drive over.'
 (Aoun & Li, 2003, p. 132)

- (1b) ni hui kandao [[wo xiwang mei-ge xuesheng_i dou neng dai t_j lai de] [wo
 you will see I hope every-CL student all can bring come DE I
 gei ta_i de shu]_j
 give he DE book
 'You will see the book that I gave to him_i that I hope every student_i will bring.'
 (Aoun & Li, 2003, p. 133)

The possible co-indexation between the anaphor *ziji* 'self' and the embedded subject *meige-ren* 'everyone' in (1a) and that between the bound pronoun *ta* 'him/her' and the embedded subject *meige-xuesheng* 'every student' in (1b) imply that the head can reconstruct into the RC and be bound by the RC subject at LF. Under the assumption that reconstruction occurs only when syntactic movement is involved (Chomsky, 1993), the head must be raised from within the RC in Chinese.

On the other hand, Aoun and Li (1993, 2003) observed that such reconstruction is not always available when it comes to scope interaction, as in (2):

- (2) wo xiang zhengli [mei-ge-ren dou hui kan t_i de] [san-ben shu]_i.
 I want arrange every-CL-person all will read DE three-CL book
 'I will put the three books that everyone will read in order.' (same three books)
 (Aoun & Li, 2003, p. 133)

Aoun and Li claimed that in (2), the ‘three books’ must be the same three books that everyone will read, which means the head of the RC always have scope over the RC subject *meige-ren* ‘everyone.’ In contrast, when *dou* ‘all’ disappears,¹ as in (3), the RC subject may have scope over the head of the RC:

- (3) wo xiang zhengli [mei-ge-ren hui kan ti de] [san-ben shu].
 I want arrange every-CL-person will read DE three-CL book
 ‘I will put the three books that everyone will read in order.’ (same/different 3
 books) (Aoun & Li, 2003, p. 134)

In (3), the ‘three books’ can be either the same or different three books that everyone will read. Thus, there is a clear contrast between (2) and (3): in (2) where there is a *dou* ‘all’ inside the RC, the only available interpretation is ‘three books > everyone’ whereas in (3), where *dou* does not exist, there are two possible interpretations: ‘three books’ > ‘everyone’ and ‘everyone’ > ‘three books.’ Aoun and Li (2003) further noted that this contrast cannot be found in nonrelative sentences:

- (4) mei-ge-ren dou hui kan san-ben shu.
 every-CL-person all will read three-CL book
 ‘Everyone will read three books.’ (same 3 books) (Aoun & Li, 2003, p. 134)
- (5) mei-ge-ren hui kan san-ben shu.
 every-CL-person will read three-CL book
 ‘Everyone will read three books.’ (same/different 3 books) (Aoun & Li, 2003, p. 134)

In both (4) and (5), the interpretation ‘everyone’ > ‘three books’ is available. Thus, in order to account for the contrast between (2) and (3), Aoun and Li argued that if the head of the Chinese RC is a QP having the form [Q+Cl+N], it cannot reconstruct into the RC at LF. Thus, if there is a universal QP in the RC subject position, it cannot have scope over the head QP.

Then why can *meige-ren* ‘everyone’ have scope over *sanben-shu* ‘three books’ in (3)? Aoun and Li (1993, 2003) stated that the RC subject *meige-ren* ‘everyone’ can be raised out of the RC and c-command the head QP *sanben-shu* ‘three books’ if there is no *dou* ‘all’ inside the RC. However, if there is a *dou* ‘all’, the RC subject cannot be raised due to the domain requirement between *dou* and the related QP. That is, the QP must be within the government domain of *dou*.

¹ *Dou* ‘all’ is a distributor (e.g., Lee, 1986; Liu, 1990) and it generally co-occurs with a *wh*-word, a QP or a plural NP (Aoun & Li, 1993).

In short, according to Aoun and Li (2003), if the head of a Chinese RC is a QP, it cannot reconstruct into the RC at LF. In contrast, such reconstruction is possible if the head is an NP.

Nevertheless, Aoun and Li's proposal cannot explain why the anaphor *ziji* 'self' and the bound pronoun *ta* 'him' inside the head QP of the following sentences can be co-indexed with the RC subject:

(6) [mei-ge-xuesheng_i xi t_i de] [san-tiao ziji_j-de kuzi_j] zai nali.
 every-CL-student wash DE three-CL self-GEN pants at there
 'The three pants of themselves that every student washed are there.'

(7) [mei-ge-xuesheng_i du t_i de] [san-ben wo gei ta_j de shu_j] zai nali.
 every-CL-student read DE three-CL I give him DE book at there
 'The three books I gave him that every student read are there.'

In (6) and (7), the anaphor *ziji* 'self' and the bound pronoun *ta* 'him' inside the head QP can be co-indexed with the RC subject *mei-ge-xuesheng* 'every student,' respectively, which suggests that the head QP can reconstruct into its base position inside the RC at LF.

By using a controlled truth value judgment experiment, this paper explored the following question: when *dou* 'all' occurs inside a Chinese RC with a head QP as well as a universal QP in the subject position, can the universal QP have scope over the head QP? The experimental results showed that the contrast between the RC with *dou* (2) and that without *dou* (3) claimed by Aoun and Li (2003) can only be accounted for by preference. Particularly, the analysis of individual data suggested that the head QP in both types of sentences can reconstruct into the RC and the universal QP in the RC subject position can have scope over the head QP, regardless of the presence of *dou*. That is, in both (2) and (3), the interpretation of 'everyone' > 'three books' is possible, although such interpretation is more plausible in (3). Therefore, we do not have to stipulate that in Chinese RCs, a head QP taking the form [Q+CI+N] cannot reconstruct into the RC while a head NP can. The claimed NP/QP distinction regarding the reconstruction of the RC head does not exist and the head should always reconstruct into the RC at LF, no matter whether it is an NP or QP.

3. Experiment

3.1 Participants

A total of 30 adult native speakers of Chinese participated in this experiment. They were all university students in China, whose age ranges from 18 to 23. Based on the background information survey results, they were all born and raised in China and none of them had ever lived outside China when the experiments were conducted. They were paid for their participation.

3.2 Design and materials

A picture-matching truth value judgment task was created to investigate the following research question: when a *dou* occurs inside the Chinese RC, can the universal QP in the RC subject position have scope over the head QP?

Seven characters from *Journey to the West* were used in this task, which include four students, *Monkey* (8a), *Xuanzang* (8b), *Pigsy* (8c), and *Sandy* (8d), and their teachers, *Sakyamuni* (8e), *Maitreya* (8f) and *Bodhisattva* (8g). These characters are shown below:

Each experimental item begins with a story. Here is an example: one day, the four students, Monkey, Xuanzang, Pigsy and Sandy, made their own wines and they put their face photos on the wine barrels to declare their possessions, as illustrated in (9):

Then the story continues as follows: the three teachers tasted different students' wines: Sakyamuni tasted Monkey's and Xuanzang's wines, Maitreya tasted Monkey's and Pigsy's wines and Bodhisattva tasted Monkey's and Sandy's wines. Then a wolf comes out, as in (10), and says either (11) or (12):

(11) zai-zheli de shi [mei-ge laoshi chang-le ti de [liang-hu jiu];
 at-here DE is every-CL teacher taste-PST DE two-CL wine
 ‘Here are the two wines that every teacher tasted.’

(12) zai-zheli de shi [mei-ge laoshi dou chang-le ti de [liang-hu jiu];
 at-here DE is every-CL teacher all taste-PST DE two-CL wine
 ‘Here are the two wines that every teacher tasted.’

(10) has a context of *universal-wide* (U-wide) reading (e.g., Feiman & Snedeker, 2016; Raffray & Pickering, 2010). In other words, in order for (11) and (12) to match (10), the universal QP *mei-ge laoshi* ‘every teacher’ in the RC subject position must have wider scope over the head QP *liang-hu jiu* ‘two wines.’ For each experimental item, there were two conditions: a condition without *dou* ‘all,’ as in (11), and a condition with *dou* ‘all,’ as in (12). Participants were asked to judge whether the wolf’s sentence is correct or not under the U-wide reading context.

There were 20 items of different lexicalizations. Since there were two conditions for each item, 40 tokens were created, which were further distributed into two lists so that each list contained only one condition from the same lexicalization. Thus, there were a total of 20 critical stimuli in each list and each condition had 10 stimuli.

Moreover, the same 40 fillers were included in each list. There were 4 types, each of which had 10 items. (13) and (14) include the 4 different fillers for the sample context above, also shown in (15).

(13) quanti laoshi (dou) chang-le liang-hu jiu.
 all teacher all taste-PST two-CL wine
 ‘all teachers tasted two wines.’

(14) quanti laoshi (dou) chang-le si-hu jiu.
 all teacher all taste-PST four-CL wine
 ‘all teachers tasted four wines.’

(15)

(13) without *dou* ‘all’ is a Type 1 filler and that with *dou* is a Type 2 filler, for which participants were expected to select ‘Mismatch’ and ‘Match,’ respectively.² Meanwhile, (14) without *dou* is a Type 3 filler and that with *dou* is a Type 4 filler, for which participants should select ‘Match’ and ‘Mismatch,’ respectively. All fillers were used to monitor whether our participants paid enough attention to the presence of *dou* in experimental sentences. Each story included a critical item and two fillers of different types. All four types of fillers were evenly distributed and the order of all experimental items was pseudo-randomized.

3.3 Procedure

All participants completed this experiment in a computer lab. The total time for them to finish the task was about 15 minutes. At the beginning of the experiment, each participant was asked to fill out a background information survey, which included: (i) name; (ii) hometown; (iii) native language; (iv) experience of living abroad. In the instruction section, each participant was asked to say aloud the names of the seven characters used in the experiment, as in (8). This procedure was to confirm that our participants had no problem identifying the characters in the experiment. Moreover, two examples were presented to show how to do the experiment. After that, the participants continued to practice four more trials before starting to read the actual experimental items. All participants’ data were analyzed by pairwise comparison tests, performed on both participant (F_1 and t_1) and item (F_2 and t_2). Also, individual participants’ data were also examined to understand whether individuals made a distinction between RCs with *dou* and those without *dou* in the U-wide reading context.

4. Findings

Recall that all four types of fillers were used to confirm that our participants paid enough attention to the presence of *dou* ‘all’ within the experimental sentences. Since there were 10 items for each type, based on the binominal distribution, we would be more than 95% confident that they read sentences carefully as long as they accept eight or more Type 2 and 3 fillers and reject eight or more Type 1 and 4 fillers. The data showed that a total of six participants failed to do so: two did not reject eight or more Type 1 fillers and four did not accept eight or more Type 3 fillers. Thus, their data were excluded and the remaining 24 participants’ data were further analyzed.

The mean frequencies of accepting the items in the ‘RCs without *dou*’ condition and the ‘RCs with *dou*’ condition were 0.63 and 0.4, respectively.

² *Quanti* ‘all’ in (13) with *dou* has a universal quantification interpretation, which is ‘each teacher tasted two wines.’ This also applies to (14) with *dou*.

The participants' mean frequencies of accepting the items in the 'RCs without *dou*' condition and the 'RCs with *dou*' condition, along with their standard deviation (SD) and standard error (SE), were calculated and summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Participants' judgments in Experiment I

Condition	Mean (SD)	SE
RCs without <i>dou</i>	0.63 (0.44)	0.09
RCs with <i>dou</i>	0.4 (0.41)	0.08

Pairwise comparisons showed that the difference between the two conditions is significant in the participant analysis ($t_1(23) = 3.19, p < .01$) and is also significant in the item analysis ($t_2(19) = 9.82, p < .01$). It suggests that RCs without *dou* is significantly preferred to those with *dou* in the U-wide reading context, where the embedded universal QP must have scope over the head QP.

The individual data showed the following: eight participants (33.3%) accepted eight or more items in both conditions, which means they consistently accepted both RCs with *dou* and those without *dou* under the U-wide reading context. In contrast, there were eight participants (33.3%) who rejected eight or more items in both conditions, which indicates that they did not allow either type of RCs under the U-wide reading context. Moreover, four participants (16.7%) consistently accepted RCs without *dou* and consistently rejected RCs with *dou*. Further, there were four participants (16.7%) making inconsistent judgment in one or both conditions, whose data is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Number of 'Match' answers of the 4 participants making inconsistent judgment

Condition	Participant I	Participant II	Participant III	Participant IV
RCs without <i>dou</i>	10	7	4	10
RCs with <i>dou</i>	7	5	2	4

Recall Aoun and Li (2003) stated that the universal QP *mei-ge-ren* 'everyone' in the RC subject position can have wider scope over the head QP only when there is no *dou* inside the RC. When there is *dou*, the head QP must always have wider scope over the RC subject QP. Based on their claim, we predict that all participants should consistently accept RCs without *dou* and consistently reject RCs with *dou*. Nevertheless, only four participants behaved like that and we have to account for the data of the remaining 20 participants.

As for the eight participants who consistently rejected the items, we can infer that the only interpretation available to them in RCs with/without *dou* is the surface reading ($2 > \forall$): the head QP always has wider scope over the universal QP in the embedded subject position. This is unpredicted because, according to Aoun and Li (2003), the U-wide reading should be available in RCs without *dou*. Then what prevented the eight

participants from accessing the U-wide reading? Note that the U-wide reading ($\forall > 2$) involves one more derivational step than the surface reading: to reconstruct the head QP into its base position within the RC.³ In fact, the dominance of the surface interpretation in the eight participants' mind is well predicted by Anderson's (2004) principle of Processing Scope Economy:

- (16) Processing Scope Economy (Anderson, 2004, p. 48)
 The human sentence processing mechanism prefers to compute a scope configuration with the simplest syntactic representation (or derivation).
 Computing a more complex configuration is possible but incurs a processing cost.

Since the U-wide reading involves more complex syntactic derivation and costs more effort, it is not unexpected if we find that some participants stick to the preferred surface interpretation and reject the less preferred U-wide reading.

The strongest counterevidence against Aoun and Li's (2003) claim is from the eight participants who consistently accepted both RCs with *dou* and those without *dou*. It strongly indicates that the U-wide reading is available in RCs with *dou*. That is, the embedded universal QP can have wider scope over the head QP even if there is a *dou*, which further suggests that the head QP of Chinese RCs can always reconstruct into the RC at LF, regardless of the presence of *dou*.

Meanwhile, the data from the four participants who consistently accepted RCs without *dou* and rejected RCs with *dou* seem to support Aoun and Li's (2003) claim. However, this can be explained in an alternative way: the U-wide reading is more likely to be accessed in RCs without *dou* than those with *dou*. In other words, RCs without *dou* are preferred over those with *dou* in the U-wide reading context. The four participants might be committed to the preferred RCs and rejected the ones that are more difficult to derive. Such preference can also be seen in the data of the four participants who made inconsistent judgment, as in Table 2: each participant accepted more items of the RC-without-*dou* condition than those of the RC-with-*dou* condition. Further, this preference is also well reflected in the statistical analysis of the group data: the RC with *dou* is significantly less preferred than the RC without *dou*.

5. Discussion

The experimental findings showed that in Chinese RCs with *dou*, the universal QP in the RC subject position can have wider scope over the head QP, contrary to Aoun and Li's (2003) claim that only the surface reading is possible in Chinese RCs with *dou*.

³ Aoun and Li (1993, 2003) stated that the U-wide reading is derived by raising the RC subject out of the RC. However, no matter what the derivational mechanism is, one additional step from the surface structure is necessary for the U-wide reading.

Since the universal QP in the subject position can always take scope over the head QP in the RC, regardless of the presence of *dou*, we can infer that the head QP can always reconstruct into the RC at LF. This has an important implication for the availability of head reconstruction in Chinese RCs. Based on their judgment that the universal QP in the RC subject position cannot have wider scope over the head QP in Chinese RCs with *dou*, Aoun and Li (2003) stated that the head reconstruction is inconsistent in Chinese RCs:

(17) Reconstruction is possible for binding relations involving anaphors, bound pronouns, and so on, in the Head.

Reconstruction is not possible for structures involving a Head QP interacting with another QP inside a relative clause for scope interpretations.

(Aoun & Li, 2003, p. 139)

Following (17), Aoun and Li further argued that it is the NP/QP distinction that leads to the conflicting reconstruction effects: only NP heads can reconstruct. However, our experimental results indicated that we do not need such a stipulation: reconstruction is always possible for all NP and QP heads of Chinese RCs.

Moreover, according to Aoun and Li (1993, 2003), since the head QP cannot reconstruct, the U-wide reading in RCs without *dou*, such as (18), can be accounted for by subject raising. That is, the RC subject can be raised out of the RC and take scope over the head QP at LF. In contrast, when there is a *dou*, such as (19), the RC subject cannot be raised out of the RC due to the domain requirement between *dou* and the universal QP in the RC subject position.

(18) wo xiang zhengli [mei-ge-ren hui kan ti de][san-ben shu]i.
I want arrange every-CL-person will read DE three-CL book
'I will put the three books that everyone will read in order.' (same/different 3 books)

(Aoun & Li, 2003, p. 134)

(19) wo xiang zhengli [mei-ge-ren dou hui kan ti de] [san-ben shu]i.
I want arrange every-CL-person all will read DE three-CL book
'I will put the three books that everyone will read in order.' (same 3 books)

(Aoun & Li, 2003, p. 133)

Aoun and Li (2003) further provided a piece of evidence arguing for the raising of the subject: if the embedded universal QP fails to be raised out of the RC, it cannot have scope over the head QP, as in (20):

(20) wo hui zhengli [ta xiwang mei-ge-ren hui kan ti de] [san-ben shu]i
I will arrange he hope every-CL-person will read DE three-CL book

‘I will put the three books that he hopes that everyone will read in order.’ (same 3 books) (Aoun & Li, 2003, p. 137)

In (20), the universal QP *mei-ge-ren* ‘everyone’ is located in a doubly-embedded RC subject position. According to Aoun and Li, it cannot be raised out of the RC to take scope over the head QP at LF so the U-wide reading is unavailable. Nevertheless, whether the U-wide reading is really unavailable in sentences like (20) may still need a further experimental investigation.⁴

6. Conclusion

Previous studies claimed that the head QP of Chinese RCs cannot reconstruct into the RC, with the evidence that the universal QP in the RC subject position cannot have wider scope over the head QP when *dou* ‘all’ occurs inside the RC. With a controlled truth value judgment experiment, this paper argued that the head QP can indeed reconstruct into its base position within the RC, with the evidence that the universal QP can take scope over the head QP, regardless of the presence of *dou*. Therefore, we do not need to stipulate that there is an NP/QP distinction that leads to the conflicting reconstruction effects of the head in Chinese RCs. Rather, all heads in Chinese RCs can reconstruct into the RC and Aoun and Li’s (1993, 2003) proposal that the universal QP in the RC subject position can be raised out of the RC at LF might not be necessary.

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⁴ Based on my consultation with several native speakers of Chinese, the U-wide reading is available. That is, the three books can be different ones for each individual, which is different from what Aoun and Li’s (2003) claimed. This issue is left open for future studies.

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Rethinking the Sentence-Final Particle (SFP) system in Mandarin: The Status of *Le**

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This paper argues (i) that the traditionally analyzed Class 1 Sentence Final particle (SFP1 hereafter) *le* should not be treated equally with other Class 1 members *laizhe*, *ne* and *eryi* in syntactic structure, (ii) that *le* is closer to VP than the other three members of Class 1, and (iii) that *le* should be treated as a separate class and the SFP system should have four classes instead of three.

1. SFP system in Mandarin Chinese

First observed by Chao (1965), it is noticed by many scholars that there is a kind of particles in Mandarin that always appear at the sentence-final position. Summarized by Erlewine (2017), these particles can be categorized into three classes due to their distribution (they are called SFP1, SFP2 and SFP3 respectively as references):

(1) Three classes of Mandarin Chinese SFPs:

a. SFP1: low SFP

- i. *le* “currently relevant state” marker (Li & Thompson, 1981)
- ii. *laizhe* recent past (Paul, 2015: 258–260)
- iii. *ne* durative aspect (Constant, 2011)
- iv. *eryi* exclusive ‘only’ (Erlewine, 2010)

b. SFP2: clause-type

- i. *ma* polar question
- ii. *ba* imperative
- iii. *ne* contrastive topic (Constant, 2014) or follow-up and constituent questions (Cheng, 1997)

* I would like to thank Alan Munn, Yan Cong and NACCL-32 participants for their comments.

c. SFP3: speaker/addressee attitude

- i. *ou* impatience
- ii. *a* softening
- iii. *ei* gentle reminder

2. Problem with this system

There are two predictions made by this system. The first is that inside a SFP class, members are in complementary distribution. The second is that across classes, particles are always compatible. To prove the first prediction, some combination are shown to be impossible by Paul (2015):

(2) Complementary distribution of two SFP1 (Paul, 2015: 253–254):

- | | |
|----------------------------|---------------------------------------|
| a. wo chi fan {le, laizhe} | b. *wo chi fan {le laizhe, laizhe le} |
| I eat dinner {LE, LAIZHE} | I eat dinner {LE LAIZHE, LAIZHE LE} |
| ‘I (just) ate dinner.’ | |

But this prediction cannot hold if we explore all the possibilities of this system. For example, inside SFP1, *le* is compatible with all other three particles. I consulted the CCL Corpus developed by the Department of Chinese at Peking University. For the combination of *le* and *laizhe*, there is 1 example as shown below:

- (3) jintian jihao le laizhe?
 today what date LE LAIZHE
 ‘What date is it today?’

And for the combination of *le* and *ne*, there are 3,747 examples (since *ne* can also be put in SFP2, I examined a small portion of them, none of them are in SFP2), so I am confident that this combination can hold in Mandarin at the sentence-final position. An example can be:

- (4) zuo shenme qu le ne?
 do what go LE NE
 ‘‘What is someone going to do?’’

For the combination of *le* and *eryi*, there are 51 examples. An example is shown as below:

- (5) xing le eryi
wake up LE ERYI

“Someone just does the action of waking up (there is not a big deal).”

Then let’s explore the second prediction, for SFP1 *le*, it is compatible with all three particles. For the combination of *le* and *ma*, there are 11,821 results in CCL corpus, so this combination is definitely in the grammar, an example can be:

- (6) tian qing le ma?
weather sunny LE MA

“Has the weather become sunny now?”

For the combination of *le* and *ba*, there are 7,460 results. An example can be:

- (7) kan jian le ba
see see(indicate has seen) LE BA

“Have (you) seen (this)?”

For the combination of *le* and *ne*, there are 3,747 results. An example can be:

- (8) bing le ne
silk LE NE

“what about when you are sick (What are you going to do?)”

Similar test can be run on *laizhe*, *eryi* and *ne*.

For *laizhe*, there are 7 examples of the combination of *laizhe* and *ma*, an example can be:

- (9) ta zhen dazhang laizhe ma?
he real fight LAIZHE MA

“Has he really fought(with other people)?”

And 12 examples of the combination of *laizhe* and *ne*, an example can be:

- (10) laohu hai gen wo woshou laizhe ne
tiger even with me shake hands LAIZHE NE

“The tiger has even shaken hands with me.”

But there are no example of the combination of *laizhe* and *ba*.

For *eryi*, there are 11 examples of the combination of *eryi* and *ma*, an example can be:

- (11) zhi you zhe yidian eryl ma
 Only have this a little bit ERYI MA
 “Do you only have this little bit?”

There are 11 examples of the combination of *eryl* and *ne*, an example can be:

- (12) shifou jin ci eryl ne
 Yes or no only this ERYI NE
 “If this is it?”

There are 11 examples of the combination of *eryl* and *ba*, an example can be:

- (13) shuoshuo eryl ba
 say say ERYI BA
 “Just want to make a comment.”

For *ne*, there are 40 examples of the combination of *ne* and *ma*, an example can be:

- (14) da ne ma?
 Hit NE MA
 “Is it the case someone is hitting right now?”

For *ne*, there are 30 examples of the combination of *ne* and *ba*, an example can be:

- (15) chi ne ba?
 eat NE BA
 “Is it the case someone is eating right now?”

There are no example of the combination of SFP1 *ne* and SFP2 *ne*.

So we can see the caveats here, there are two combinations missing, namely SFP1 *ne* plus SFP2 *ne* and *laizhe* plus *ba*. It is more clear to show this on a chart:

(16)

		SFP1 Particles			
		<i>le</i>	<i>laizhe</i>	<i>ne</i>	<i>eryl</i>
SFP2 Particles	<i>ma</i>				
	<i>ne</i>			*	
	<i>ba</i>		*		

“*” indicates unattested combinations

I will try to solve the two problems in the following sections. The two problems are summarized as follows:

(17) Two problems

Problem 1: There are possible combinations within the same class.

Problem 2: There are unattested combinations across classes.

3. Solution for Problem 1

If it is true, as shown in the tree depicted by Erlewine (2017) in (18), that *eryi*, *laizhe* and *ne* are specifiers of SFP1P, and there is only one slot at the SFP1 specifier position, then it is impossible for members of SFP1 class to combine with each other.

(18)

Proposed structure:

It is worth noting that the only “trouble-maker” here is the *le*, which is a “currently relevant state” marker according to Li and Thompson (1981). It is easy to show that the ability of *le* combining with VP is different from other SFP1 participles combining with *le*.

The first piece of evidence comes from conjunction. There is a conjunction in Mandarin that is used to combine verb phrases, which is *ye*. *Le* can be combined with *ye* but not other three SFP1 particles.

So it is possible to say:

- (19) wo chi fan le ye shuijiao le
 I eat dish LE YE sleep LE
 “I have eaten dishes and also slept.”

But it is impossible to say:

- (20) a. wo chi fan laizhe ye shuijiao laizhe
 I eat dish LAIZHE YE sleep LAIZHE
 “I have eaten dishes and also slept.”
- b. wo chi fan ne ye shuijiao ne
 I eat dish NE YE sleep NE
 “I have been eating dishes and also sleeping.”
- c. wo chi fan eryl ye shuijiao eryl
 I eat dish ERYI YE sleep ERYI
 “I have been eating dishes and also sleeping.”

It is even grammatical to combine *le* and other SFP1 particles in this structure where *le* is combined closely to verb phrases while other SFP1 particles are relatively far away:

- (21) a. wo chi fan le ye shuijiao le laizhe
 I eat dish LE YE slept LE LAIZHE
 “I have eaten dishes and also slept.”
- b. wo chi fan le ye shuijiao le ne
 I eat dish LE YE sleep LE NE
 “I have been eating dishes and also sleeping.”
- c. wo chi fan le ye shuijiao le eryl
 I eat dish LE YE sleep LE ERYI
 “I have been eating dishes and also sleeping.”

So it is clear that in terms of structure, *le* should be closer to verb phrase compared to other three SFP1 particles. Then the question arises where exactly are the position of *le* and other SFP1 particles?

According to Erlewine, there are several possible check that can decide the position of SFP1 particles, including negation, modal, subjects and disjunctions. But unfortunately, Erlewine only use these tests to show the case of *le*, after testing all SFP1 particles, it turns out only *le* can pass the test to show that it is really inside the TP but not the other three.

Let's talk about the negation test first. The test for *le* is shown as follow:

(22) SFP1 *le* takes scope above *bu* but below *bushi* (Soh & Gao, 2006):

a. *bu...le*: LE > NEG, *NEG > LE
 wo bu xiang jia le
 I NEG miss home LE

Asserts: ‘I do not miss home now.’
Presupposes: ‘I did miss home before.’

b. *bushi...le*: *LE > NEG, NEG > LE
 wo bushi xiang jia le
 I NEG miss home LE

Asserts: ‘I do not miss home now.’
Presupposes: ‘I did not miss home before.’

Since ‘*bushi*’ is considered to take scope over the TP in Mandarin, *le* should be inside TP. For the case of *laizhe*, the two sentences that should be evaluated:

(23) a. wo bu xiang jia laizhe
 I NEG miss home LAIZHE
 b. wo bushi xiang jia laizhe
 I NEG miss home LAIZHE

From my point of view, these two sentences have exactly the same meaning, which is “in the recent past, I did not miss home.” Then *laizhe* should take scope over both *bu* and *bushi*, which means that *laizhe* has higher position than *le* in terms of syntactic structure.

To test other members of the SFP1 particles, for *ne*, the sentences should be:

(24) a. wo bu xiang jia ne
 I NEG miss home NE
 b. wo bushi xiang jia ne
 I NEG miss home NE

Again, I can only get the meaning that ‘I do not miss home (durative aspect)’, which means *ne* should also take scope over both *bu* and *bushi*.

Finally for the case of *eryi*, the sentences should be:

(25) a. wo bu xiang jia eryi
 I NEG miss home ERYI

b. wo bushi xiang jia eryi
 I NEG miss home ERYI

Again, I can only get the meaning that ‘I only do not miss home’, which means *ne* should also take scope over both *bu* and *bushi*.

To summarize, it is reasonable for *le* to be put inside TP to be higher than VP but lower than T according to Elrewine. But the other SFP1 particles should be higher than *le* but lower than SFP2, since the other SFP1 particles take scope over the tense but not the subject, I would like to propose that *laizhe*, *ne* and *eryi* should be head of a SFP there is higher than T but lower than the subject of TP.

(26) Elrewine’s structure.

Proposed structure:

Since *le* behaves so different from other SFP1 particles and it is closely attached to VP. I would propose that *le* is really a pseudo sentence final particles and I will name it as SFP0. So the new system of Mandarin SFP should be:

(27)

a. SFP0 pseudo SFP

- i. *le* change of state

b. SFP1: low SFP

- i. *laizhe* recent past
- ii. *ne* durative aspect
- iii. *eryi* exclusive 'only'

c. SFP2: clause-type

- i. *ma* polar question
- ii. *ba* imperative
- iii. *ne* contrastive topic

d. SFP3: speaker/addressee attitude

- i. *ou* impatience
- ii. *a* softening
- iii. *ei* gentle reminder

And their positions at the syntactic tree should be:

(28)

4. Solution for Problem 2

To refresh, Problem 2 is stated as follows:

(29) Problem 2: There are unattested combinations across classes.

And to consult the combination chart between SFP1 particles (also contains the SFP0 *le*) and SFP2 particles, there are two combinations that are unattested in the corpus, namely *laizhe* plus *ba* and *ne* plus *ne*.

(30)

		SFP1 Particles			
		<i>le</i>	<i>laizhe</i>	<i>ne</i>	<i>eryi</i>
SFP2 Particles	<i>ma</i>				
	<i>ne</i>			*	
	<i>ba</i>		*		

“*” indicates unattested combinations

These two unattested and probably ungrammatical combination is not according to syntax since system largely can hold with only these two caveats. I would like to propose that the combination of *laizhe* and *ba* being bad is according to semantics.

laizhe means recent past while *ba* means imperative. It makes sense a person instructs another person to do something at present. Your mom orders you to go to the grocery store to get an onion saying ‘Go to the grocery store to get me an onion.’ And you may reluctantly get out of the bed to get your job done. But it makes no sense your mom says ‘Went to the grocery store to get me an onion.’ Since time cannot go back, it is really meaningless to order people to do something at a time point in the past.

The reason why SFP1 *ne* cannot combine with SFP2 *ne* may due to the effect of merge. If I say a sentence like:

- (31) wo chi fan ne, ta shuijiao ne
 I eat dinner SFP1 NE ta sleep SFP1 NE &SFP2 NE

For the second *ne*, it makes sense to me that it contains both the SFP1 meaning (durative aspect) and SFP2 meaning (contrastive topic). And the motivation of the merge may be a similar one with the Obligatory Contour Principle (OCP) effect in phonology, which prevents identical segments or features sequence.

5. Conclusion

In Mandarin, since *le* is syntactically lower than SFP1 particles and therefore forms a class of its own, there are four classes of Sentence-Final Particle.

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The Weak Hand in Verb Agreement and Argument Marking: A Study of Verbs with Weak Hand Classifier in Chinese Sign Language

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In this study I investigate the role of the weak hand at the lexical level through the lens of a set of verbs in Chinese Sign Language (CSL) which is characterized by use of a remnant classifier handshape ‘A’ (2) or ‘Y’ (f) handshape on the weak hand. I show that these verbs are exclusively transitive and exhibit a division of labor between the two hands in the marking of arguments: the weak hand identifies a patient whereas the strong hand identifies an agent. Moreover, a typology of agreement realizations of these verbs is laid out based on combinations of three agreement devices: movement direction, facing, and localization. I show that the behavior of the weak hand in various morphophonological forms of agreement is predictable and conforms to the restrictions on a lexical sign. At last, allomorphs of 1st person object agreement are observed with respect to the deletion of the weak hand. I argue that this is a result of the obliteration rule. A morphological markedness hierarchy regarding argument referentiality (body > weak hand classifier > locus) is proposed as the motivation for deriving such allomorphs.

1. Introduction

Since the work of Stokoe (1960), a sign is decomposable into handshape, location, movement (Stokoe 1960), and orientation (Battison 1978, Crasborn et al. 2000, Sandler & Lillo-Martin 2006). Moreover, each sign language studied to date involves one-handed signs and two-handed signs (van der Kooij 2002). The hand that appears in a two-handed sign is called the strong hand whereas the hand that is not always active is called the weak hand. These elements, including handshape, location, movement, orientation, and weak hand, are arguably the building blocks of a sign. Figure 1 and Figure 2 illustrate CHEAP and FEW from Chinese Sign Language¹. The two signs involve the same handshape (i.e., M), the same movement (i.e., straight downward movement), the same location (i.e., neutral space in front of the signer’s chest), and the same orientation (i.e., palm up). The two signs form a minimal pair by merely differing in handedness, i.e., involving the weak hand or not.

¹ The notation for sign languages is that near-equivalent English translations with all letters in upper case are given for individual signs, such as CHEAP. If a single sign corresponds to more than one word in English, a hyphen is used to connect the English words as in LOOK-AFTER.

Figure 1 CHEAP

Figure 2 FEW

Figure 3 ENCOURAGE

Figure 4 LOOK-AFTER

A monomorphemic sign such as CHEAP and FEW involves meaningless sub-lexical units. This is not the whole story about a sign though. Apart from a simple sign, morphologically complex signs are abundant in sign languages. In this study, I investigate a set of verbs in Chinese Sign Language (CSL) that are characterized by use of a classifier handshape ‘Y’ (f) (Figure 3: ENCOURAGE) or ‘A’ (2) (Figure 4: LOOK-AFTER) on the weak hand. From a crosslinguistic perspective, similar verbs are attested in other Eastern Asian sign languages such as Taiwan Sign Language (TSL: Smith 1989), Japanese Sign Language (JSL: Mathur 2000), and Hong Kong Sign Language (HKSL: Tang 2007). Despite sporadic descriptions of these verbs, few studies have systematically analyzed the linguistics properties of these verbs. I will develop a fine-grained analysis and show through the lens of CSL that these weak hand classifier verbs are polymorphemic by involving a morphemic weak hand, being eligible for agreement processes, and involving an allomorph with respect to the obliteration of the weak hand.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2 introduces the basic terms of weak hand classifier verbs and agreement, which comprise the key topics in this study. Section 3 is on participants and methodology of this study. Section 4 reports the findings. I will make a generalization of the weak hand with respect to its role in argument marking. Moreover, a typology of verb agreement realizations is given and the role of the weak hand in the agreement processes is examined. At last, a type of one-handed allomorphs in 1st person object agreement is discussed. Section 5 concludes.

2. Terms

2.1. Weak hand classifier verbs

Classifiers are arguably attested in almost all sign languages. Classifiers are morphemes with a non-specific meaning and expressed by particular configurations of the hand (Zwitserslood 2012). In CSL, classifier handshape ‘A’ (thumb extended) or ‘Y’ (thumb and pinkie finger extended) denote an animate entity. In a classifier construction, orientation and movement of the hand can be manipulated to express iconic meaning. The group of two-handed signs I investigate in this study involves such animate entity classifier on the weak hand. They are characterized by the following properties in phonological form: The weak hand is static while the strong hand executes some motion onto the weak hand. Although the weak hand in these verbs is a classifier, it is a kind of remnant, in that the

form of the weak hand is highly restricted and cannot undergo modifications in orientation or movement, contra its behavior in a classifier construction. That is, the weak hand cannot be modified in its orientation or movement to signify the physical position or moving trajectory of the animate entity being represented, while in regular classifier constructions such manipulation is productively used. For instance, in the verb LOOK-AFTER (Figure 4 above), the weak hand classifier cannot undergo orientation change to thumb downward or inward, which would denote the animate entity being represented in an upside-down or lying position respectively, as it could in a classifier construction. In sentence (1) below, [MOM LOOK-AFTER SICK LIE-DOWN OLD MOM OLD] ‘Mom looks after the granny who is sick and lying (in bed)’, the weak hand in LOOK-AFTER stands for the patient ‘granny’. Despite being a classifier, the weak hand is not observed to undergo orientation modification to signify the ‘lying-down’ position. See the contrast in orientation of the classifier between LOOK-AFTER and LIE-DOWN in Figure 5b and Figure 5d. The signers I consulted also immediately reject a modified form of LOOK-AFTER with the weak hand oriented in the same direction as the strong hand of LIE-DOWN. Moreover, the weak hand classifier is unmovable due to the dominance condition (Battison 1978). This condition mandates the passive status of the weak hand so that the weak hand functions as the static base for the strong hand and cannot move by itself. Given that the verbs in this group are lexicalized, the weak hand classifier is frozen in form and its palm orientation and movement cannot be manipulated to encode further meaning.

(1) MOM LOOK-AFTER SICK LIE-DOWN OLD MOM OLD
 ‘Mom looks after the granny who is sick and lying (in bed).’

Figure 5 [MOM LOOK-AFTER SICK LIE-DOWN OLD MOM OLD] (‘Mom looks after the granny who is sick and lying (in bed).’)

2.2. Agreement

2.2.1. Pronominal system

Before diving into verb agreement, it is necessary to introduce the pronominal system in sign languages, which pertains to the arguments that control the person feature expression on verbs. In sign languages, the referents in the discourse can be associated to referential loci (R-loci) in the signing space. The locus is expressed by a pointing sign which targets at a certain location (Friedman 1976, Klima & Bellugi 1979). The loci can be either actual locations of the present referents in the immediate physical context or arbitrary locations that are related to the non-present referents. Padden (1983) made a three-way distinction among the loci which are assigned to first person, second person, and third person pronouns. For 1st person pronouns, the indexical sign points towards (usually in contact with) the signer's body. For 2nd person pronouns, the indexical sign points at the addressee in the discourse. For 3rd person pronouns, the finger points to a locus in the space in front of the signer's body which has been assigned to a present or non-present referent. Different 3rd persons can be differentiated by different loci in the signing space, as illustrated by locus 3a and locus 3b in Figure 6 below. Usually no more than four or five different 3rd person loci are used at one time in the conversation (Padden 1983).

Figure 6 The loci associated with different referents (from Pfau et al. 2018)

A grammatical distinction between 2nd and 3rd person pronouns, however, is not needed due to fact that 2nd person and 3rd person are both expressed as loci in the signing space and the implementation of 2nd person is thus realized in an unlimited number of ways, depending on the location of the addressee and the location of the addressee's variable (Liddell 2000). The referential difference is fulfilled by discourse or pragmatics and only a two-way distinction between 1st person and non-1st person is required in the sign language pronominal systems (Meier 1990, Hou & Meier 2018).

The pronominal system in CSL is like this: The assignment of a locus to a referent is done through an index finger pointing to the signer's body or to a locus in space, as shown by Figure 7a and Figure 8, with the former for 1st person (i.e., IX1) and the latter for non-1st person (i.e., IX2/3). Figure 7b and 7c illustrate two variants of the 1st person pronoun, with 7b involving a palm open handshape and 7c involving a location on the nose. In the following discussion, 2nd person agreement will not be singled out as distinct from

3rd person agreement, though the subscript index 2 or 3 will be used in the context for specific discourse interpretation. I contend that the grammatical system only distinguishes two persons in this language, i.e., 1st person and non-1st person.

Figure 7a IX1

Figure 7b IX1

Figure 7c IX1

Figure 8 IX2/3

2.2.2. Devices for person agreement

I now turn to verb agreement, particularly person agreement as the focus of this study. It is well documented across sign languages that a set of verbs can inflect in person features of their arguments. These verbs can undergo a modulation in movement and/or facing of the hand to mark verb agreement (see Mathur & Rathmann 2010 for an overview). Recently work proposes localization as a device to mark verb agreement as well (Lourenço & Wilbur 2018). I introduce each of these three agreement realization devices below.

2.2.2.1. Movement direction

Modification of movement direction refers to changes in the starting and ending points of the path movement of a sign to mark the arguments the verb agrees with. For instance, in the CSL sentence in (2), $IX_{3a} IX_{2b} {}_{2b}LOOK-AFTER_{3a}$ ‘You look-after him/her’, IX_3 and IX_2 refers to a 3rd person pronoun and a 2nd person pronoun respectively. A 2nd or 3rd person pronoun is produced by pointing towards a locus in the signing space. The subscripts a and b denote the loci the pronouns are pointed towards. The two arguments IX_{3a} and IX_{2b} are thus associated with the two loci 3a and 2b respectively. The citation form of the verb $LOOK-AFTER$, i.e., the form with no person features, is produced in front of the signer with the strong hand (in this case, the right hand) moving from a position proximal to the signer’s body straightly towards the weak hand in neutral space that is distal to the body, as illustrated in Figure 4. In sentence (2), the verb ${}_{2b}LOOK-AFTER_{3a}$ undergoes a movement from locus 3a to locus 2b, which are associated with the locations of the argument IX_{3a} and the argument IX_{2b} respectively, as shown in Figure 9. The modification of the starting and ending points of the movement thus realizes 2nd person subject and 3rd person object agreement.

(2) $IX_{3a} IX_{2b} {}_{2b}LOOK-AFTER_{3a}$ (OSV)
 ‘You look after him/her.’

Figure 9 IX_{3a} IX_{2b} _{2b}LOOK-AFTER_{3a} ('You look after him/her')

Figure 10 SUPPORT (citation form)

By the same token, the citation form of the verb SUPPORT is articulated with a straight path movement towards the weak hand, which is positioned in neutral space, as shown in Figure 10. In sentence (3), IX₃ ₃SUPPORT₁ IX₁ ('He/she supports me'), IX₁ refers to the 1st person pronoun and is articulated on the center of the chest, in contrast to the 2nd/3rd person pronouns which can be assigned an arbitrary locus in the signing space. In sentence (3) where the 3rd person argument and the 1st person argument function as subject and object respectively, the verb ₃SUPPORT₁ (Figure 11) is executed by undergoing the trajectory from the locus 3a that is associated with the subject IX₃ to the chest which marks the object IX₁.

(3) IX₃ ₃SUPPORT₁ IX₁ (SVO)
 'He/she supports me.'

Figure 11 IX₃ ₃SUPPORT₁ IX₁ ('He/she supports me')

2.2.2.2. Facing

Facing refers to the agreement device in which the orientation of the palm and/or fingertips of the verb is adjusted towards the locus of an argument. Facing invariably marks object agreement. As illustrated by ${}_{2b}$ LOOK-AFTER ${}_{3a}$ and ${}_{3}$ SUPPORT ${}_{1}$ in Figure 9c and Figure 11b, the palm and fingertips of the strong hand are oriented towards locus 3a in ${}_{2b}$ LOOK-AFTER ${}_{3a}$ and towards the chest, i.e., the 1st person, in ${}_{3}$ SUPPORT ${}_{1}$.

2.2.2.3. Localization

Movement direction and facing are regarded as two canonical devices for person agreement in sign languages. However, not all verbs can be modifiable in their movement direction and facing for agreement. The blocking of these two devices on certain verbs is due to having a certain type of lexically specified movement other than the path movement along the horizontal plane (Mathur 2000). Similarly, facing is unavailable as a device if changes in facing violates a ‘naturalness constraint’ which is usually physiologically driven.

The view of agreement was challenged in Lourenço and Wilbur (2018), who brought back the notion of localization and argued that each verb exhibits agreement except for a few cases where the verbs are body-anchored (having movement in contact with the body). As a concept that goes back to Fischer and Gough (1978), localization refers to the scenario where the verb is produced *at the location* that is associated with a certain argument. To some extent, the notion of localization can be subsumed under movement direction since the starting and ending points of movement are loci of the arguments and thus the loci guide the localization of the verb. However, in contrast to movement direction, localization shows agreement with only one argument. In intransitive verbs, localization marks subjects, and in transitive verbs it marks agreement with objects (Meir 1998, Costello 2015). The citation form of KIDNAP in Figure 12, for instance, involves a circular movement and the palm is facing down towards the ground. The sign is not modifiable in either movement direction or facing due to its phonological shape. It can nonetheless be displaced in neutral space to align with the locus of the 3rd person argument in sentence (8) $IX_1 IX_3 KIDNAP_3$ (‘I kidnap him’), as shown in Figure 13 below:

Figure 12 KIDNAP (citation form)

(4) $IX_1 IX_3 KIDNAP_3$ (SOV)
 ‘I kidnap him.’

Figure 13 IX₁ IX₃ KIDNAP₃ ('I kidnap him.')

3. The present study

This section introduces participants and methodology of this study. Five deaf participants in Shanghai were recruited. Four of them were born into deaf families and acquired CSL from birth. One was born into a hearing family. This participant lost hearing at the age of 2 and was exposed to CSL in the local deaf school at age 8. The self-reported background information in the year 2019 of the five signers is given in Table 1:

Table 1 Self-reported background information of the signers

Pseudonym	Age	Gender	Deaf family members
A	49	Female	Parents, brother
B	36	Female	Parents
C	36	Male	Parents
D	37	Female	Parents
E	52	Male	None

The methodologies consist of elicited production and grammaticality judgement tasks. The author and a deaf assistant were present throughout the data consultation. The author gave the instructions in CSL to the participants. The deaf assistant clarified the tasks and recorded the video. Each of the five participants met individually with the author and the deaf assistant to avoid interference from other participants' judgments. In the elicited production task, each signer was asked to watch a vignette or a picture prompt and then describe the scenario. The elicited sentences were expected to contain the target verb and to involve 3rd person arguments since the signer perceived the event from a viewer's perspective. All participants responded to 41 vignette/picture prompts the author prepared by producing the target verbs and complete sentences. Two other verbs with weak hand classifier were brought up by one participant on the spot. After the elimination of one sign BALD² and the addition of the two verbs, I obtained a total of 42 weak hand classifier

² I excluded BALD from the analysis of weak hand classifier verbs by the reason that BALD can appear pre-nominally within an extended NP, which functions as the subject in a sentence. BALD is arguably an adjective rather than a verb, which falls beyond the scope of this study.

verbs in elicited production. For the grammaticality judgments, each signer was asked about the acceptability of the following agreement forms-- 1st person subject and non-1st person object form (${}_1V_{2/3}$), non-1st person subject and 1st person object form (${}_{2/3}V_1$) as well as non-1st person subject and non-1st person object form (${}_{3a}V_{3b}$). The accepted forms of the verbs were then produced by each signer in a complete sentence.

4. Results

4.1. Argument marking

In this study, the 42 weak hand classifier verbs investigated are found to be transitive. The classifier on the weak hand is grammaticalized as a morpheme that marks the patient argument in the verb subcategorization, which usually is mapped onto the object in the grammatical relation. I contend that by having the classifier on the weak hand, the division of labor between the strong hand and the weak hand is elucidated. The two hands in these verbs identify different NPs. Precisely, the strong hand invariably identifies the agent and the weak hand invariably identifies the patient. With respect to the grammatical roles, the strong hand usually maps onto the subject NP and the weak hand the object NP.

Such encoding of syntactic roles between the two hands at the word level has not been proposed before. This echoes findings from syntactic studies on classifiers in Italian Sign Language (Geraci 2014, Branchini 2020), which illuminate a parallel pattern at the sentence level. Branchini (2020) reported that hand selection contributes to specifying the NP syntactic role in Italian Sign Language. Hand selection in the production of classifiers, according to Branchini, is driven by the syntactic role of the NP represented by the classifier: the strong hand for subjects and the weak hand for non-subject arguments. My study on weak hand classifier verbs in CSL shows that the same behavior is attested at the word level. This verb-internal property indicates that both the strong hand and weak hand are morphemic in weak hand classifier verbs.

4.2. Agreement patterns

Combinations of the three agreement devices, movement direction, facing, and localization, yield four types of agreement realizations. Table 2 lists the typology of agreement device combinations and their morphophonological realizations. Among the 42 CSL verbs with weak hand classifier, 29 signs were observed with type (a) combination: movement direction and facing. Type (a) is also the most common way to realize agreement on weak hand classifier verbs. Eight signs were found to employ type (b) combination: facing alone. Two signs go to type (c) combination: movement direction alone. And three other signs are of type (d): localization alone. Among the four types of agreement realizations, those that occur on the strong hand are considered primary processes and those that bear on the weak hand are predictable and thus regarded as secondary processes. The grey cells indicate blockings of certain agreement devices. The following subsections elaborate each type with respect to their agreement realizations.

Table 2 Morphophonological realizations of agreement in weak hand classifier verbs

Verb types	Primary agreement processes			Secondary agreement processes		CSL examples
	Strong hand			Hand relation	Weak hand	
Type (a) (29 verbs)	movement direction	facing	n.a.	hand order	palm orientation	SCOLD, SUPPORT
Type(b) (8 verbs)		facing	n.a.	hand order	palm orientation	SLAP-FACE, ENCOURAGE
Type (c) (2 verbs)	movement direction		n.a.	hand order	palm orientation	EXPEL
Type (d) (3 verbs)			localization	n.a.	palm orientation	KIDNAP, REMOVE

4.2.1. Type (a): movement direction and facing

Type (a) employ the modulation of both movement direction and facing for agreement realization. The agreement conjugations include both subject and object agreement, including 1st person subject, non-1st person object agreement ($1V_{non-1}$), non-1st person subject and object agreement ($_{non-1-a}V_{non-1-b}$), and non-1st person subject agreement, 1st person object agreement ($_{non-1}V_1$). I instantiate the morphophonological realizations of each agreement form with the verb SCOLD. Figure 14a shows the citation form of SCOLD. It is produced by moving the strong hand towards the weak hand in neutral space, with the palm and fingertips orientated towards the weak hand. The citation form of SCOLD does not exhibit any person agreement. The underlying path movement and palm/fingertips orientation are modifiable in accordance with the loci of the arguments that SCOLD subcategorizes. For the agreement conjugations on person features, I provide the illustrations for ${}_1SCOLD_3$, ${}_{3a}SCOLD_{3b}$, and ${}_3SCOLD_1$ in Figure 14b, c, d respectively.

Figure 14a SCOLD Figure 14b ${}_1SCOLD_3$ Figure 14c ${}_{3a}SCOLD_{3b}$ Figure 14d ${}_3SCOLD_1$

In the 1st person subject, 3rd person object agreement of SCOLD in Figure 14b, the verbal complex is formed by moving the strong hand from near the signer’s chest to the position distal to the signer. In this example in Figure 14b, the right side of the signer is the position for the object referent. Given this, the weak hand which stands for the object is displaced to that position. Meanwhile, the palm and fingertips are modified to face

outward the right side of neutral space. By the same mechanism, the 3rd person subject and object agreement of SCOLD, as shown in Figure 14c, is realized. The movement initiates from the right area of the signer, which identifies the subject referent, and terminates at the left area of her, which is associated with the object referent. The facing of the palm and fingertips likewise is modulated towards the area that stands for the object.

In the 3rd person subject, 1st person object agreement of SCOLD in Figure 14d, the verbal complex undergoes modulation in the following respects: First, the strong hand moves from an area distant in neutral space that is established for the 3rd subject referent towards the signer's body which represents the 1st object referent. Second, the palm and fingertips are modified to face inwards towards the body. Third, the weak hand, which stands for the object, is accordingly positioned closer to the body than the strong hand, resulting in a reverse in the hand order. Such a change in the order of hands is predictable from the modulation either in the movement direction or facing since the weak hand co-occurs at the position of the ending point of movement. Lastly, a closer inspection of the weak hand reveals its slight adjustment in orientation. Compared with other agreement forms which do not involve a 1st person object, the weak hand which represents the 1st person object tends to orient its palm towards the body, as shown in Figure 14d. This alignment of the forearm and hand in parallel with the body falls naturally from physiological constraints when the weak hand is in proximity to the body. Otherwise, the joints that connect the forearm and the hand must be contracted to form a flexion. Besides the modulation of movement direction and facing on the strong hand, the latter two aspects of modulations pertain to the weak hand only and are exclusively attested on the 1st person object agreement form in a verb that involves a static weak hand. Provided that change in hand order is redundant and predictable from movement direction or facing, and weak hand orientation adjustment is more physiologically triggered, I contend that such modulation on the weak hand is secondary and results from phonetics, a stage which occurs after the grammatical operation. Only the strong hand is therefore considered for morphophonology of agreement. This is also in line with other agreement verbs that do not involve the weak hand and satisfies a unified analysis of agreement.

4.2.2. Type (b): facing alone

The type (b) makes use of facing alone. These verbs cannot employ modulations on movement direction because there is no underlying path movement or there is specialized movement other than the forward linear motion. Since facing invariably marks an object referent (Meir 1998), only object agreement is seen in agreement conjugations of these verbs, namely, non-1st person object agreement ($V_{\text{non-1}}$) and 1st person object agreement (V_1). I use the verb SLAP-FACE for illustrations.

In Figure 15a, the citation form of SLAP-FACE involves placing the strong hand fingertips towards the weak hand. There is no path movement in SLAP-FACE. The strong hand executes a hand-internal movement by flexing all fingers in repetitive motion. Since movement direction modulation requires a path movement on the horizontal plane as a

prerequisite, this device is unavailable for agreement realizations on verbs such as SLAP-FACE. However, facing is used for object agreement, as shown by the 3rd person object agreement in SCOLD₃ in Figure 15b and the 1st person object agreement in SCOLD₁ in Figure 15c. SCOLD₃ is produced by orientating the fingertips of the strong hand towards the locus for the object referent on the left side. And in SCOLD₁, the signer lets the fingertips of the strong hand orient towards the signer's body. Following the modulation of the strong hand facing, the weak hand is placed closer to the signer's body than the strong hand, leading to a change in the hand order.

Figure 15a SLAP-FACE

Figure 15b SLAP-FACE₃

Figure 15c SLAP-FACE₁

4.2.3. Type (c): movement direction alone

Type (c) employs movement direction only for agreement realizations due to fact that the underlying palm or fingertip orientation is not eligible for modulation. Through modulation of the movement direction, these verbs are attested with agreement conjugations of both subject and object agreement, including 1st person subject, non-1st person object agreement ($1V_{\text{non-1}}$), non-1st person subject and object agreement ($_{\text{non-1-a}}V_{\text{non-1-b}}$), and non-1st person subject, 1st person object agreement ($_{\text{non-1}}V_1$). Two verbs, namely EXPEL and LEARN-FROM, fall into this group. I illustrate EXPEL, including its citation form and its agreement forms, in Figure 16.

Figure 16a EXPEL

Figure 16b ₁EXPEL₃

Figure 16c _{3a}EXPEL_{3b}

Figure 16d ₃EXPEL₁

The citation form of EXPEL in Figure 16a contains an outward movement of the strong hand towards the weak hand in neutral space, which affords modulation of the directionality of movement for agreement. Neither the palm nor the fingertips face in the direction of the weak hand. This means that no regular modulation on facing is available for verbs like EXPEL. Among the agreement forms of ₁EXPEL₃, _{3a}EXPEL_{3b}, and ₃EXPEL₁, the palm is invariably directed inward toward the body regardless of the agreement

conjugations. Movement direction is modulated among the three agreement forms by varying the starting and ending points of the movement according to the locations of the subject and object referents. Movement direction also implies a hand order reversal in the 1st person object agreement form of 3EXPEL₁ in Figure 16d.

4.2.4. Type (d): localization alone

The last type employs localization alone. It is solely applied when neither movement direction nor facing are modifiable for agreement. In other words, localization comes into play when there is inherent lexical movement and facing that block the agreement modulations. Localization shows agreement with subject in an intransitive verb and agreement with object in a transitive verb (Meir 1998, Costello 2015). The verbs I investigate are transitive and thus show object agreement via localization. According to the five deaf participants, localization only marks non-1st person agreement by stretching the arm towards the location that is associated with the 2nd or 3rd person object referent. The inflection for the 1st person object referent by localization alone is not acceptable. For all signers, placing the hands in proximity to the body does not lead to 1st person object agreement and rather is more appropriately recognized as a citation form. The agreement conjugations of type (d) verbs are impoverished compared with the other types. Only non-1st person can be inflected for object referents, i.e., V_{non-1}. I provide the citation form and the localized agreement form of the verb KIDNAP in Figure 17a and Figure 17b below.

Figure 17a KIDNAP

Figure 17b KIDNAP₃

4.3. One-handed allomorph

In production of agreement conjugations, one type of allomorphs regarding the weak hand deletion was observed in the 1st person object agreement forms of some weak hand classifier verbs. Not all weak hand classifier verbs allow such one-handed allomorphs. Omission of the weak hand is ill-formed if it results in semantic ambiguity with another underlying one-handed sign. For instance, LOOK-AFTER does not allow a one-handed allomorph since the strong hand part of LOOK-AFTER is identical to another one-handed verb LOOK-AT in CSL. Six weak hand classifier verbs (i.e., RESTRICT, SCOLD, KISS, KILL, SLAP-FACE, LEARM-FROM, KIDNAP) were found to have one-handed allomorphs and they span across the four types of morphophonological realizations in Table 2. These allomorphs are characterized by two properties: (1) The weak hand is dropped; (2) The strong hand has idiosyncratic landing locations on the body. The

reference to specific body parts in the one-handed 1st person object agreement form involves mouth, neck, cheek, and forehead. Below I provide illustrations of 1st person object agreement and one-handed allomorph of SCOLD (Figure 18), KISS (Figure 19), SLAP-FACE (Figure 20), and KILL (Figure 21).

Figure 18a SCOLD₁ (chest)

Figure 18b SCOLD_{1-mouth} (1 hand)

Figure 19a KISS₁

Figure 19b KISS_{1-heck} (1 hand)

Figure 19c KISS_{1-mouth} (1 hand)

SCOLD and KISS make use of movement direction and facing for agreement. As illustrated in Figure 18b, SCOLD₁ involves one-handed allomorph that is directed towards the mouth area rather than the canonical chest level in Figure 18a. KISS₁ involves two variants of one-handed allomorphs. In contrast to the canonical agreement form KISS₁ in Figure 19a, the two variants of one-handed KISS₁ lands on the ipsilateral cheek (Figure 19b) and the mouth (Figure 19c) respectively.

Figure 20a SLAP-FACE₁

Figure 20b SLAP-FACE_{1-heck} (1 hand)

Figure 21a KILL₁

Figure 21b KILL_{1-neck-ipsi} (1 hand)

Figure 21c KILL_{1-neck-contra} (1 hand)

SLAP-FACE and KILL solely employ facing for agreement. For SLAP-FACE₁ in Figure 20, its one-handed allomorph SLAP-FACE_{1-cheek} involves an execution on the ipsilateral cheek, as shown in Figure 20b. KILL₁ has two variants of one-handed allomorphs: KILL_{1-neck-ipsi} in Figure 21b involves the hand contacting the ipsilateral side of the neck with palm down whereas KILL_{1-neck-contra} in Figure 21c involves the hand contacting the contralateral side of the neck with palm up.

I propose that the one-handed allomorph is the output of an obliteration rule (Arregi & Nevins 2007) which prunes the entire morpheme, i.e., the weak hand, in weak hand classifier verbs. Given that the weak hand identifies the patient argument, omission of the weak hand deletes an entire morpheme. As for the referentiality to a specific part of the body, these idiosyncratic body locations are unpredictable and can occur independently from weak hand obliteration. Evidence comes from another type of allomorph which involves a specific reference to the body while the weak hand is preserved, as shown in SCOLD_{1-mouth} and RESTRICT_{1-neck} in Figure 22 and Figure 23. Such reference to different body areas is iconically motivated given that SCOLD involves an action related to the mouth and that RESTRICT has an immediate effect on the trachea. These idiosyncratic locations on the body thereby needs lexical specification as diacritic indexes on the verb.

Figure 22 SCOLD_{1-mouth}

Figure 23 RESTRICT_{1-neck}

As for the motivation for the obliteration of the weak hand, I argue that the omission of the weak hand is a repair rule triggered by morphological markedness (Calabrese 2005, 2011). The one-handed allomorph is mostly attested in the 1st person object form by the reason that the 1st person object has dual spell-outs, with one by the body and the other by the weak hand. The role of the body varies depending on the verb types and when it comes to the agreeing verbs, the body identifies the object while the strong hand identifies the subject (Meir et al. 2007). I have shown that the weak hand classifier invariably stands for the patient, which mostly maps onto the object. Since the body and the weak hand are both encoded as the object referent, deleting one element removes the redundancy and fulfills the ease of articulation. Given that the body is physically undeletable, obliteration of the weak hand becomes the only option.

Moreover, retaining the body is also triggered by an asymmetry in markedness. In sign languages, an argument can be realized by assigning a locus in neutral space, as has been discussed in the pronominal system and agreement realizations. The locus that is close to or in contact with the body naturally stands for 1st person in the context. The locus

assigned with reference to the other participants in the discourse invariably stands for non-1st person. In contrast to the consistent mapping of the signer's body onto 1st person and the present referent's body onto the non-1st person, the weak hand classifier identifies either 1st person or non-1st person. Displacement of the weak hand is required for disambiguation in person agreement. Based on the person referentiality, I propose that the body is more unmarked than the weak hand classifier. The obliteration is thus triggered as to reduce markedness. The body of the signer and the physically present participants explicitly represent arguments involved in a verb event. By contrast, the weak hand classifier encodes the argument in an abstract way though the presence of the weak hand classifier is iconic and makes the animate argument explicit. In CSL, the weak hand classifier in the agreeing verbs exclusively identifies an object. For most other agreeing verbs without weak hand classifier, the only way to mark an animate argument is an abstract referential locus in neutral space if no physical referents are present. Based on the animate argument explicitness and person referentiality, I propose the following hierarchy with increasing morphological markedness in (5):

(5) Morphological markedness hierarchy:

The body (of the signer or present participants) > the weak hand classifier > the locus associated with the non-present participant

5. Conclusion

In this study, I develop an analysis of verbs with weak hand classifier based on empirical data from a natural sign language used by the deaf community in China. I show that the weak hand is morphemic, and it matters in the argument marking: the strong hand identifies the agent whereas the weak hand identifies the patient of the verb predicate. Such division of labor between the two hands in weak hand classifier verbs of CSL echoes the findings on hand selection at the sentence level in other sign languages. This adds evidence to the argument marking function of the weak hand in morphosyntax. Moreover, I find that the weak hand classifier participates in person agreement realizations though the behavior of the weak hand is largely predictable and arguably secondary to the strong hand. This corroborates that these verbs are lexicalized and thereby conform to the dominance condition, which mandates that the weak hand is static and acts as the base for the strong hand. The agreement forms of weak hand classifier verbs are no exceptions. Finally, the weak hand can be obliterated in the 1st person object agreement in some weak hand classifier verbs. I propose a morphological markedness hierarchy on referentiality (body > weak hand classifier > abstract locus) and argue that the disappearance of the morphemic weak hand is accounted by a reduction in markedness when the body arises as the sole unmarked representation for the object referent in the 1st person object agreement.

This study of verbs with weak hand classifier in CSL sheds light on the role of the weak hand in sign language morphology. Despite the surface difference in phonetic forms of a word between signed and spoken languages, the notions of agreement, argument

marking, and markedness are nonetheless a-modal, i.e., not specific to the channel a language is conveyed or perceived. Like spoken languages, sign languages employ grammatical devices for complex verbal morphology.

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When NONFUT Tense Meets Perfective Aspect

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This paper examines the proper analysis for perfective aspect in a non-future tense framework for Mandarin. I focus on root clauses with only one predicate and one aspectual element. After demonstrating the possible implementations and potential problems of Sun's (2014) assumptions for perfective aspect in a non-future framework, I offer a solution to avoid the problems by assuming that temporal adverbials denote a set of intervals and the time argument of the perfective aspect encodes the 'past' interpretation in its presupposition.

0. Introduction

The temporal reference of Mandarin declarative root clauses with only one predicate involves two properties: the past reading of eventive predicates marked by the perfective aspect marker *le*₁ and the non-future constraint of temporal adverbials for bare predicates without overt aspect markers. It has been noticed that a root clause with only one predicate marked with perfective aspect *le*₁ reports a past event.¹ For example, the

¹ This paper focuses only on declarative root clauses with one predicate and one aspectual marker to understand the basic facts of the two functional categories under discussion: tense and aspect. Root clauses with two or more predicates or with more than one aspectual element show different patterns from the simplest cases. For example, with the aspectual adverb, *le*₁ can also be used in future contexts, as shown in (i). In (ii), when talking about the plan of a series of events, the non-final predicate can also be marked by *le*₁. In these cases, *le*₁ reports a relative past reading. Namely, the evaluation point for past is a future time (some time tomorrow in (i) and the initial time of going to your place tomorrow in (ii)). In principle, these phenomena are also compatible with the current analysis proposed in this paper, as long as we have a principled constraint on the evaluation point for the perfective aspect. Due to limit of length, we will leave these details for future research.

- (i) Lisi mingtian yijing likai-**le** Nanjing.
Lisi tomorrow already leave-PFV Nanjing
'Lisi will have left Nanjing by tomorrow.'
- (ii) Lisi mingtian zuowan-**le** zuoye zai dao ni
Lisi tomorrow finish-PFV homework again arrive 2SG
jia.
home
'Tomorrow Lisi will go to your place after having finished his homework.'

sentence in (1a) marked with *lei* is natural with a past time adverb but is odd if we replace the past time adverb with a future or a present time adverb.

- (1) a. Lisi **zuotian** likai-le Nanjing.²
 Lisi yesterday leave-PFV Nanjing
 ‘Lisi left Nanjing yesterday.’
 b. #Lisi **mingtian** likai-le Nanjing.
 Lisi tomorrow leave-PFV Nanjing
 c. ?Lisi **xianzai** likai-le Nanjing.
 Lisi now leave-PFV Nanjing

The non-future constraint on time adverbs (frame setting temporal adverbs) refers to the fact that bare predicates, including statives and bare eventive predicates denoting generic readings, are able to freely combine with present or past time. However, the combination with future time adverbs is not free (Sun 2014, Chen 2017). For example, the examples in (2) contain a stative stage-level predicate *jusang* ‘be frustrated’. The sentences in (2a-2b) are natural to combine with present time and past time adverbs. When combined with a future time adverb *mingtian* ‘tomorrow’, the sentence is odd without an overt future morpheme *hui*. Similarly, the sentences in (3) contain a bare predicate *henshao shuqiu* ‘rarely loose’ denoting generic readings, present time and past time adverbs can be used flexibly. But future time adverbs cannot.

- (2) a. Lulu **xianzai** hen jusang.
 Lulu now very frustrated
 ‘Lulu is very frustrated now.’
 b. Lulu **gangcai** hen jusang.
 Lulu just.now very frustrated
 ‘Lulu was very frustrated just now.’
 c. **Mingtian** Lulu *(hui) hen jusang.
 tomorrow Lulu MOD very frustrated
 ‘Tomorrow, Lulu will be very frustrated.’

(Adapted from Sun 2014: 163-165)

- (3) a. **Zhei-ji-nian** zhongguo dui hen-shao shu-qiu.
 this-several-year China team very-few lose-ball
 ‘The Chinese team rarely loses these years.’
 b. **Yiqian** zhongguo dui hen-shao shu-qiu.
 In-the-past China team very-few lose-ball

² Abbreviations adopted in this paper are summarized as follows:
 PFV: perfective, nonfut: non-future tense

‘The Chinese team rarely lost in the past.’

- c. *Mingnian* zhongguo dui *(jiang) hen-shao shu-qiu.
 next.year China team MOD very-few lose-ball

‘The Chinese team will rarely lose next year.’

To account for the non-future constraint on time adverbs with bare predicates in root clauses, Sun (2014) extends the non-future tense analysis in St’átimchets (Matthewson 2006) to Mandarin. Following a pronominal approach for tense (Partee 1973, Kratzer 1998), the denotation for NONFUT in (4) from Sun (2014) says that the tense operator takes in a time argument and returns the same argument if this time satisfies the presupposition: it precedes a context salient time t_c or includes t_c . t_c is a context supplied evaluation time. In root clauses and matrix clauses, the evaluation time t_c is the utterance time (s^* henceforth). The first component of the disjunction in the presupposition corresponds to a past tense reading and the second component of the disjunction corresponds to a present tense reading. The non-future tense makes a distinction between future and non-future. But it is unspecified between past and present. This constrains the time adverbs in a stative sentence to be in the past or present, but not future.

$$(4) \llbracket \text{NONFUT} \rrbracket^{g,c} = \lambda t: t < t_c \text{ or } t \supseteq t_c. t \quad (\text{Sun 2014: 192})$$

Note that Sun’s definition for NONFUT is a looser version of Matthewson’s proposal for St’átimchets. The fact that the reference time that satisfies ‘ $t \supseteq t_c$ ’ in principle allows the time offered by the tense operator to stretch into the future, while Matthewson’s definition in (5) does not allow such an option. In the following discussion, I will adhere to Mathewson’s proposal³ and revise it as in (6). The tense operator carries an index i , which picks out an interval from the context via the assignment function g . The interval offered by NONFUT meets the presupposition that no part of it is after the evaluation time t_c . Though the semantic types in (4) and (6) for the tense operator are different, the key ingredients are coherent so that the different types of tense do not make a difference in the composition.

$$(5) \llbracket \text{NONFUT}_i \rrbracket^{g,c} \text{ is only defined if no part of } g(i) \text{ is after } t_c. \text{ If defined,} \\ \llbracket \text{NONFUT}_i \rrbracket^{g,c} = g(i) \quad (\text{Matthewson 2006: 680})$$

$$(6) \llbracket \text{NONFUT}_i \rrbracket^{g,c} = g(i), \text{ iff } g(i) \leq t_c.$$

The non-future proposal focuses on temporal interpretations of bare predicates in root clauses. However, how NONFUT interacts with other aspectual elements is not well-explored in Sun (2014). Specifically, how to obtain the ‘past reading’ associated with the

³ In Matthewson (2006), NONFUT_i is notated as TENSE_i .

perfective aspect in a non-future framework is not investigated. This paper aims to start filling this gap and explore the theoretical possibilities. I will take into account the interaction between perfective aspect marker le_1 , time adverbs and NONFUT, offering the details of the solution to capture the ‘past’ reading of perfective root clauses in a non-future framework with necessary modifications of Sun’s assumptions. In Section 1, I will demonstrate the assumptions for time adverbs and perfective aspect in Sun (2014) and point out the problems with these assumptions. Section 2 spells out my modifications to the assumptions and offers an analysis for a perfective root clause with a covert NONFUT tense. Section 3 concludes.

This research is conducted within a formal semantics framework. I follow the neo-Davidsonian framework for eventualities, assuming that a predicate carries an eventuality argument. The variable representing the eventuality is e , with the semantic type of $\langle v \rangle$. Time arguments are represented by the variable t . Its semantic type is $\langle i \rangle$.

1. The assumptions and problems in Sun (2014)

1.1 The assumption of time adverbs and perfective aspect

Though not explicitly spelt-out, Sun (2014) makes three assumptions about the semantic type, the syntactic position of a time adverb and the connection with the interval supplied by NONFUT. From Sun’s derivation of clauses with time adverbs and NONFUT tense, as well as clauses with time adverbs and perfective aspect marker le_1 , we can tell that Sun (2014) assumes the following:

- (7) a. In a root clause, NONFUT returns an interval that either refers to the utterance time or a time that co-indexes with the time adverb.
- b. Time adverbs modify the perfective aspectual phrase if the event time of the vP is within the time denoted by the time adverb.
- c. A time adverb (*1987 nian* ‘1987’, *jintian* ‘today’ etc.) denotes an interval, with a semantic type of $\langle i \rangle$ (Lin 2003).

Moreover, Sun (2014) assumes that the perfective aspect marker le_1 possesses the denotation in (8). The denotation in (8) is a modification of Lin’s (2006) proposal for perfective aspect.⁴ In (9), Lin treats Mandarin perfective as a tense-aspect operator, i.e. a morphological bundle of past tense and perfective aspect. In a standard view of perfective aspect in (10), the perfective aspect takes in a property of eventuality P and a time t , returns true if the runtime of the eventuality ($\tau(e)$) that holds for P is located in the time

⁴ Lin (2006) does not adopt a neo-Davidsonian approach for his analysis. The original denotation is demonstrated in (i).

(i) $\|PFV\| = \lambda P_{\langle i, t \rangle}. \lambda t_{\text{Top}}. \lambda t_0. \exists t[t_{\text{Top}} \subseteq t \wedge P(t) \wedge t_{\text{Top}} < t_0]$ (Lin 2006: 6)

of t . Compared to (10), the denotation in (9) proposes a different semantic type for perfective. In (9), the perfective aspect in Mandarin takes a property of eventuality P and two intervals, t and t' . The temporal inclusion relation between the runtime of the event and the interval t' remains the same as a normal perfective aspect marker. However, the perfective also poses another constraint on the two intervals. Namely, the interval that includes the runtime of the event must precede a time t in the context. In a root clause, t' corresponds to the reference time and t corresponds to the utterance time. Therefore, ' $t' < t$ ' is in fact a semantic past tense bundled with perfective. This succeeds in capturing the fact that a root clause with perfective *le* reports a past event.

- (8) $\|le\| = \lambda P. \lambda t'. \lambda t. \exists e[P(e)=1 \ \& \ t' \supseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ \tau(e) < t]$ (Sun 2014: 75)
 (9) $\|PFV\| = \lambda P. \lambda t'. \lambda t. \exists e[P(e) \wedge t' \supseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ t' < t]$
 (10) $\|PFV\| = \lambda P. \lambda t. \exists e[P(e) \wedge t \supseteq \tau(e)]$

Compared to Lin's account in (9), Sun (2014) makes a modification for perfective. According to Sun (2014), the two time arguments are no longer linked to each other directly, but are connected indirectly by the runtime of the event. On the one hand, the core component of the temporal inclusion relation between the time argument t' and the event time still holds. On the other hand, the event also needs to precede another time argument t . The structure in (11) incorporates the assumption about perfective and the assumptions in (7). Each node specifies the semantic type of the outcome.

I will repeat an example from Sun (2014) in (12a) to illustrate how Sun's assumptions work. The syntactic structure of (12a) is demonstrated in (12b). The time adverb supplies the first time argument for the perfective phrase and the tense operator supplies the second time argument. Through the step-by-step derivation, the denotation of the sentence in (12a) is shown in (12i), which says, there is an eventuality of publishing, the agent is Moyan, the theme is the Red Sorghum Clan. The event occurred in 1987 and it preceded the utterance time.

- (12) a. 1987 nian, Moyan fabiao le Hong Gaoliang Jiazhu.
 1987 year Moyan publish PFV Red Sorghum Clan
 ‘In 1987, Moyan published Red Sorghum Clan.’
 (Sun 2014: 72)

b.

- c. $\|le\| = \lambda P. \lambda t'. \lambda t. \exists e[P(e)=1 \wedge t' \supseteq \tau(e) \wedge \tau(e) < t]$
 d. $\|vP\| = \lambda e.[publish(e) \wedge Agent(e) = m \wedge Theme(e) = h]$
 e. $\|PfvP\| = \lambda t'. \lambda t. \exists e[publish(e) \wedge Agent(e) = m \wedge Theme(e) = h \wedge t' \supseteq \tau(e) \wedge \tau(e) < t]$
 f. $\|Adv\| = \text{the year of 1987}$
 g. $\|AdvP\| = \lambda t. \exists e[publish(e) \wedge Agent(e) = m \wedge Theme(e) = h \wedge \text{the year of 1987} \supseteq \tau(e) \wedge \tau(e) < t]$
 h. $\|NONFUT\| = g(i), g(i) = s^*$
 i. $\|12a\| = \exists e[publish(e) \wedge Agent(e) = m \wedge Theme(e) = h \wedge \text{the year of 1987} \supseteq \tau(e) \wedge \tau(e) < s^*]$

1.2 Problems with the assumptions in Sun (2014)

At the first sight, Sun’s assumptions and modification to le_1 seem to succeed in capturing the ‘past reading’. However, this analysis has three problems.

The first problem concerns the semantics for le_1 . Sun’s modification for perfective aspect faces two disadvantages. Firstly, the semantics of le_1 as a perfective marker is so irregular that it is hard to connect it to other known temporal/aspectual elements. Secondly, indirectly linking the two intervals in principle allows the reference time to

- b. $\exists e[\text{publish}(e) \wedge \text{Agent}(e)=m \wedge \text{Theme}(e)=h \wedge \text{the year including } s^* \supseteq \tau(e) \wedge \text{the year including } s^* < s^*]$

The problem suggested by Sun (2014) about perfective is based on the treating *jinnia* ‘this year’ as it is in (14). However, this assumption calls for further scrutiny. For time adverbs denoting an interval that overlaps with the utterance time (*jinnian* ‘this year’ *jintian* ‘today’), they may refer to an interval that precedes the utterance time or an interval after the utterance, depending on the context. For example, the sentences in (16) both contain the time adverb *jintian* ‘today’. However, ‘today’ in (16a) refers to the time within ‘today’ but precedes the utterance time while in (16b) it refers to the time within ‘today’ but after the utterance time. If we simply treat *jintian* ‘today’ as a single interval of the day including the utterance time, it is difficult to capture the context-sensitivity of this type of time adverbs. In fact, in Section 2, I will show that if we change our assumption about time adverbs, the problem suggested by Sun (2014) for Lin’s account no longer exists.

- (16) a. Zhangsan jintian jian-le Lisi.
Zhangsan today meet-PFV Lisi
‘Zhangsan met Lisi today.’
b. Zhangsan jintian yao jian Lisi.
Zhangsan today MOD meet Lisi
‘Zhangsan is going to meet Lisi today.’

The third problem concerns the ‘general template’ with two time arguments of perfective aspect marker. If we maintain Sun’s assumptions for time adverbs (also the assumption in Lin 2003) and Lin’s proposal for perfective aspect in a non-future framework, the composition order must be constrained in order to obtain the right reading. That is, to secure a ‘past’ reading, the utterance time must be supplied by the non-future tense and serves as the second time argument for perfective, as the structure in (11) shows. If a root clause does not contain a time adverb, NONFUT cannot directly pick out a context-salient past time as the reference time for the perfective phrase. We need to stipulate that under this circumstance, the first time argument of the perfective phrase must be existentially closed to secure a past reading (Lin 2003, 2006). For example, the sentence in (17a) possesses a structure in (17b). After existentially closing the first time argument of the perfective phrase, we correctly predict that the sentence in (17a) means that Moyan published *Red Sorghum Clan* in a time that preceded the utterance time, as (17g) illustrates.

- (17) a. Moyan fabiao-le Hong Gaoliang Jiazu.
Moyan publish-PFV Red Sorghum Clan
‘Moyan published Red Sorghum Clan.’

- c. $\|PFV\| = \lambda P. \lambda t'. \lambda t. \exists e[P(e) \wedge t' \supseteq \tau(e) \wedge t' < t]$
 d. $\|PfvP\| = \lambda t'. \lambda t. \exists e[\text{publish}(e) \wedge \text{Agent}(e) = m \wedge \text{Theme}(e) = h \wedge t' \supseteq \tau(e) \wedge t' < t]$
 e. $\|\alpha\| = \lambda t. \exists t' \exists e[\text{publish}(e) \wedge \text{Agent}(e) = m \wedge \text{Theme}(e) = h \wedge t' \supseteq \tau(e) \wedge t' < t]$
 f. $\|\text{NONFUT}_i\|^{g,c} = g(i), g(i) = s^*$
 g. $\|TP\| = \exists t' \exists e[\text{publish}(e) \wedge \text{Agent}(e) = m \wedge \text{Theme}(e) = h \wedge t' \supseteq \tau(e) \wedge t' < s^*]$

The stipulation of composition order and the rule of existential closure for sentences without time adverbs are acceptable. However, both Lin (2006) and Sun (2014) assume a standard analysis for imperfective marker (i.e. progressive marker *zai*) as in (18), which requires the reference time to be in the runtime of the eventuality.

$$(18) \quad \|\text{IPFV}\| = \lambda P. \lambda t. \exists e[P(e) \wedge t \subseteq \tau(e)]$$

The difference between perfective and imperfective in Mandarin is obvious: the imperfective aspect requires one time argument while the perfective requires two. The difference in semantic types leads to one consequence: elements that can take both perfective and imperfective phrases in its complement (e.g. attitude predicates that take propositional complements) need extra stipulations to handle different semantic types. We have two options. The first option is to assume different lexical entries for these elements so that they can handle aspectual phrases of different types. The second option is to stipulate the existential closure rule (Lin 2006) for perfective phrases so that all aspectual phrases will turn out to be of the same semantic type to serve as inputs for these

elements. Both options add extra complexity to the computation, which is not theoretically ideal.

To summarize, Sun’s irregular analysis for the perfective aspect marker will license improper readings that allow the reference time to stretch into the future. Treating perfective aspect as fundamentally different from imperfective in taking two time arguments also adds unnecessary complexity to the composition. Moreover, treating time adverbs as directly denoting a designate interval fails to capture the context-sensitivity of indexical time adverbs.

2. Modifications and solutions

To avoid the problems discussed in Section 1, I will propose my modifications to the assumptions and offer a solution to capture the ‘past reading’ associated with the perfective root clauses in a non-future framework. Firstly, following Heim (1997), von Stechow (2009), Alxatib & Sharvit (2017) etc., I assume that time adverbs denote a set of intervals rather than an interval. The semantics of *jinnian* ‘this year’, *1987 nian* ‘1987’ are illustrated in (19). Here ‘this year’ no longer means the full year that includes the utterance time, but means a set of intervals that is included in ‘this year’. Similarly, *1987* does not mean the full year of 1987, it can be any interval within 1987, which can be the full year of 1987 or a part of it.

- (19) a. $\|jinnian\|^c = \lambda t.[t \subseteq \text{the year that includes } s^*]$
 b. $\|1987\ nian\| = \lambda t.[t \subseteq \text{the year of 1987}]$

Secondly, following Bochnak et al. (2019) for Samoan, I revise the perfective aspect as in (20). The ‘past’ reading is no longer encoded in the assertion of the perfective. It is set to be a presupposition of the time argument taken by the perfective. We can easily see the connection between Mandarin perfective and a standard view for perfective: the Mandarin perfective presupposes the time in which the event time is located to precede the context-supplied evaluation time. Moreover, the perfective aspect shares the same semantic type with imperfective. Therefore, we do not need extra stipulations in composition to handle different semantic types.

- (20) $\|PFV\|^c = \lambda P.\lambda t: t < t_c. \exists e[P(e) \wedge t \supseteq \tau(e)]$

Based on the modification, we are able to provide a unified structure to Mandarin root clauses with tense and aspect as follows. Both perfective phrases and imperfective phrases offer a property of time $\langle i, t \rangle$, i.e. a proposition that needs to saturate a time argument. The temporal adverbial phrases modify the aspectual phrase via predicate modification.

The current proposal is also able to handle the context-sensitivity of time adverbs such as *jinnian* ‘this year’. Let’s take the sentence in (22a) as an example to illustrate the proposal.

- (22) a. *Jinian, Moyan fabiao le Hong Gaoliang Jiazu.*
 this-year Moyan publish PFV Red Sorghum Clan
 ‘This year, Moyan published Red Sorghum Clan.’
 b.

- (23) a. $\|jinnian\| c = \lambda t. [t \subseteq \text{the year that includes } s^*]$
 b. $\|le\|^c = \lambda P. \lambda t: t < tc. \exists e [P(e) \wedge t \supseteq \tau(e)]$
 c. $\|Asp_1P\| = \lambda t: t < tc. \exists e [\text{publish}(e) \wedge \text{Agent}(e) = m \wedge \text{Theme}(e) = h \wedge t \supseteq \tau(e)]$,
 d. $\|Asp_2P\| = \lambda t: t < tc. \exists e [\text{publish}(e) \wedge \text{Agent}(e) = m \wedge \text{Theme}(e) = h \wedge t \supseteq \tau(e) \wedge t \subseteq \text{the year that includes } s^*]$
 e. $\|NONFUT_i\|^{g,c} = g(i)$, iff $g(i) \leq tc$

- f. TP is defined iff $g(i) < t_c$
 g. $\|TP\|^{g,c} = \exists e[\text{publish}(e) \wedge \text{Agent}(e)=m \wedge \text{Theme}(e)=h \wedge g(i) \supseteq \tau(e) \wedge t_c \subseteq \text{the year that includes } s^*]$, iff $g(i) < t_c$

Given the structure in (22b) and the derivation shown in (23), the denotation of (22a) in (23g) means that (22a) is only defined when the context salient reference time $g(i)$ is a time preceding the utterance time and it is an interval within the year that includes the utterance time. Within this time, there is an event of Moyan publishing the *Red Sorghum Clan*. The presupposition of le_1 limits the reference time supplied by the NONFUT to be in the past, capturing the ‘past’ property of perfective root clauses. If there is no temporal adverbs in the structure, the right reading can also be derived without assuming the existential closure rule as Lin (2006) and Sun (2014) need. For example, the NONFUT tense can directly supply a non-future interval for the perfective phrase for the sentence in (24a). Due to the presupposition of the perfective aspect, this time interval is further restricted to be in the past, a correct prediction.

- (24) a. Moyan fabiao le Hong Gaoliang Jiazu.
 Moyan publish PFV Red Sorghum Clan
 ‘Moyan published Red Sorghum Clan.’
 b.

- c. $\|TP\|^{g,c} = \exists e[\text{publish}(e) \wedge \text{Agent}(e)=m \wedge \text{Theme}(e)=h \wedge g(i) \supseteq \tau(e)]$, iff $g(i) < s^*$

3. Conclusions and future research

In this paper, I demonstrate the problems of the assumptions in Sun (2014) and the challenges of deriving the past reading of the perfective root clauses within a non-future tense framework. I made two revisions based on Lin (2006) and Sun (2014): (i) time adverbs denote a set of intervals; (ii) a past tense is encoded in the presupposition of the perfective aspect marker. The modifications succeed in capturing the past reading of a

perfective root clause with unified assumptions about aspect and less stipulations in composition.

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Finiteness as Anchoring: Evidence from Cantonese

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Whether there is a finite/nonfinite distinction in Chinese has been the subject of much debate. In this paper, I offer novel observations on the distribution and syntactic properties of a set of linguistic elements, including temporal and modal sentence final particles (SFP), negators, and speaker-oriented and subject-oriented adverbs in Cantonese. I argue that these properties show that a finite-nonfinite distinction is clearly attested in the language, following Bianchi's 2003 finiteness as logophoric anchoring approach. I further argue that Bianchi's approach cannot be equated with a speaker anchoring approach, based on a well-observed syntactic phenomenon called the *Incompleteness effect*, which suggests that the role of temporal anchoring in licensing finite clauses. Lastly, I propose an analysis of finiteness realized at FinP as a category that specifies the modality or mechanism by which propositions are evaluated, which can be overtly realized by different sets of C in Cantonese.

0. Introduction

Whether Chinese exhibits a finite/nonfinite distinction is a controversial issue in the syntactic literature. Due to the lack of overt morphology, some widely-used diagnostics for identifying finite and nonfinite clauses haven't been shown not to be entirely reliable (see Hu, Pan, Xu's 2001 critique to earlier accounts (C.-T. Huang, 1982; Li, 1990; C.-C. Tang, 1990, 2000) that argue for a finite/nonfinite distinction in Chinese). There have been more analyses recently that argue for a finiteness distinction in Chinese based on the distribution of overt subjects (Zhang, 2016), sentence final aspect particles (Zhang, 2019), the scopal relation between sentence final aspect particles and modals (T.-H. J. Lin, 2011, 2012, but see Grano 2017 for a recent critique), and properties of the clausal complements (N. Huang, 2018).

In this paper, I offer new observations from the distribution and syntactic properties of some seemingly unrelated elements, such as sentence final particles (SFP *lei* and *sin*), negation markers *mai*, and speaker-oriented and subject-oriented adverbs that support the analysis of Cantonese as a language with a finiteness distinction. Mandarin examples will be used when necessary. Adopting Bianchi's (2003) proposal of finiteness as logophoric anchoring, I present evidence that finite and nonfinite clauses are attested in Cantonese, and that some finite clauses can anchor to the external center of deixis, while some nonfinite clauses can only anchor to the internal center of deixis. I will further argue that

Bianchi’s proposal can identify some finite and nonfinite clauses in Cantonese, but cannot be equated with a speaker anchoring approach. Temporal anchoring plays an important role in licensing finite clauses, based on a phenomenon called *incompleteness effect*, which contributes to the discussion of the relation between finiteness, tense, and aspect.

Section 1 starts with a review of Bianchi’s proposal for finiteness, and some recent analyses based on Bianchi’s proposal (Landau, 2015; Zagana, 2013). The distributional evidence in favor of a finite/non-finite distinction in the sense of Bianchi’s notion of finiteness based on data from Cantonese is presented in Section 2. I then in Section 3 show that speaker anchoring itself is not sufficient for capturing different finite and nonfinite clauses, and temporal anchoring is crucially required. A proposal for deriving finite and nonfinite clauses of Cantonese is presented in Section 4. Section 5 discusses issues involving aspectual verbs and their relation to finiteness, and section 6 concludes the paper.

1. Finiteness as anchoring

The notion of finiteness has been investigated from at least two perspectives, one is a ‘morphological’ approach, and the other is a ‘functional-semantics’ approach (Sybesma, 2017). Bianchi (2003) is one of the representative analyses that argues that finiteness encodes the logophoric anchoring. This paper revisits Bianchi’s proposal and examine to what extent her proposal can help identify finite and nonfinite clauses.

Bianchi proposes that finiteness encodes the logophoric anchoring of the clause, and every clause is anchored to a Logophoric Center, with its own participants and temporal coordinates, which constitutes the center of deixis (Bianchi 2003: 3). Based on the role of person features in signaling finiteness (that person features consistently occur in finite contexts only), Bianchi further argues that: a finite [+Fin] clause encodes an external Logophoric Center (eLC), which can be construed as the (external) speech event with the presence of Speech Time (S) that can license person agreement, which eventually licenses a [+R] lexical subject. By contrast, a nonfinite [-Fin] clause encodes an internal Logophoric Center (iLC), the lack of S in the iLC locally licenses a [-R] person feature, which takes as its only possible values the participants of the iLC of the clause (from the matrix verb essentially). The former context includes main clauses and complements introduced by verbs of communication (1a), whereas the latter is exemplified by control verbs, such as ‘ask’, see the Italian example in (1b). The matrix verb acts as the iLC with their participants (i.e., speaker(i) and hearer(j)) as the participants of the embedded clause).

(1) a. Finite clause

i. Main clause: [CP..[FinP +Fin [TP eLC DP [+R] [+T]]]]

ii. Embedded finite clause: V [CP..[FinP+Fin [TP eLC DP[+R] [+T]]]]

b. Nonfinite clause: Gianni_i. Chiese₁ a Maria_j [TP iLC₁ DP_j [-R]_idi preparare. La cena].

G. asked M. [-Fin] to cook the dinner

‘Gianni asked Maria to cook the dinner.’ (Bianchi 2003: 13)

In Bianchi’s analysis, which in turn is based on Landau’s work on control, Partial Control (e.g. verbs like ‘ask’ in (1b)) and Exhaustive Control (e.g. aspectual verbs) receive

completely different treatments, based on the difference in their temporal properties (tensed for the former while tenseless for the latter, as shown in (2)) and semantic properties (mainly attitudinal for the former but non-attitudinal for the latter). Partial Control selected by attitude verbs encode the Internal Logophoric Center while Exhaustive Control does not encode any Logophoric Center.

- (2) a. Yesterday, John hoped to solve the problem tomorrow. (Partial Control)
 b. *Yesterday, John began to solve the problem tomorrow (Exhaustive Control)

A final implication of Bianchi’s proposal is that finite clauses at least come in two subtypes (1-ai) and (1-aii). Main clauses (1-ai) and communicative events in (1-aii) are finite and can encode the relation to S (eLC), while embedded clauses (e.g., those selected by verbs such as ‘believe’) may be finite (e.g., with [+R] person feature) although they anchor to the matrix event. For the latter, Bianchi (2001) argues that languages can vary in whether the time is anaphoric to the matrix event or not.

Recent work on clausal structure and functional projections have pushed Bianchi’s anchoring approach further and proposed several revisions. Landau (2015) places Bianchi’s logophoric center at a higher position in the left periphery, rather than being located at FinP. Zagona (2013) specifically encodes Bianchi’s notion of logophoric center (internal or external) in a functional projection called Deixis Phrase with the interpretable deixis feature [iperson:] [itime:] that is in an Agree relation with the higher ForceP (with the uninterpretable counterparts [uperson:] [utime:], in addition to the speech act feature) (3). For a main declarative clause such as *John read a book*, ForceP is a predicated of the external speaker and values the deixis feature (4), first person and the speech time.

- (3) [_{ForceP} Force [_{iACT:decl}] [_{uPERSON}] [_{uTIME:}] [_{DeixisP} Deixis [_{iperson:}] [_{itime:}] [_{FinP} Fin [_{MOOD}] [_{TP}]]]]
 (Zagona 2013:760)

- (4) John read a book.

[_{ForceP} Force [_{iACT:decl}] [_{uPERSON}] [_{uTIME:}] [_{DeixisP} Deixis [_{iperson:1}] [_{itime:1}] [_{FinP} Fin [_{iMOOD:ordering}] [_{TP}]]]]

By incorporating mood features into the analysis of tense, the Tense category is assumed to be a reflection of indicative mood, as opposed to non-indicative mood such as subjunctive (which is left unclear in Bianchi’s original proposal). Thus, in this proposal, FinP is assumed to be a category with a [mood] feature that conveys that there is an external situation with respect to which the proposition is judged, and specifies the mechanism or modality of the evaluation, either temporally as a reflection of indicative mood (5a) for declarative sentences like (4), or in some other way (as a reflection of non-indicative mood, as shown in (5b) (Zagona, 2013).

- (5) a. [_{FinP} Fin [_{iMOOD:ordering}] TP]] (Indicative)
 b. [_{FinP} Fin [_{uMOOD}] ModP]] (Non-indicative)

Cantonese, like other Chinese languages, lacks overt morphology for either person or tense, which makes a direct application of this line of investigation to Cantonese impossible. However, there is a set of syntactic facts in Cantonese that presents direct evidence for the finiteness distinction in Cantonese, following the spirit of Bianchi's original anchoring approach, and Zagona's syntactic implementations, in particularly the different realizations of the category of Finiteness.

2. Distributional patterns of SFPs, negators, adverbs, in Cantonese

2.1 SFPs in different clausal complements

Sentence final particles (SFP) in Chinese languages provide a good testing ground to see the syntactic properties of the complement clauses because it has been observed that the environments where temporal SFPs can occur are not random. For instance, the temporal SFPs (e.g. *le* or *laizhe*, which indicates perfect and recent past, respectively) in Mandarin cannot occur in complements introduced by verbs such as *jiào* 'ask' or *quàn* persuade (6), but can appear in complements introduced by verbs such as *shuō* 'say' or *yǐwéi* 'believe' (7) (Zhang, 2019). This distributional pattern suggests a finite-nonfinite contrast, Zhang (2019) argues that these SFPs as finite [+Fin] markers, which are allowed only in finite but not non-finite contexts. The Cantonese counterparts (e.g. *laa* and *lei*) show a similar pattern in (8) and (9).

- (6) *Zhāngsān jiào/quàn Lǐsì [míngtiān qù xuéxiào le/laizhe].
 ZS. ask/persuade Lisi tomorrow go school SFP
- (7) Zhāngsān shuō/yǐwéi [Lǐsì jīntiān qù xuéxiào le/laizhe].
 ZS. say/believe Lisi today go school SFP
 'Zhangsan believed/said Lisi had gone/just went to school.'
 [Mandarin]
- (8) *A ma giu/hyun. A Fai [tingjat zoudi heicong laa/lei].
 mom ask/persuade AF. [tomorrow early get.up. SFP
- (9) Wong lousi waa/yiwai [A Fai heoi-zo gwo-dou laa/lei].
 Wong teacher say/believe AF. go-PERF there SFP
 'Teacher Wong said/believe that A fat had gone there/just went there.'
 [Cantonese]

Thanks to the rich inventory of the SFPs in Cantonese, in addition to [+Fin] markers, SFPs that show complementary distribution with the established [+Fin] markers can be identified. This section highlights two of them from Cantonese, *sin* and *lei*, respectively.

Both SFPs *sin* and *lei* have multiple functions, as shown in (10) and (11), according to (Tang, 2012, 2015, 2016). The SFP *sin* has two related functions, one is to indicate the precedence of an event meaning 'first' (10a), *sin1*, while the other expresses a sort of

‘imperative’ reading, *sin2*, which is glossed as ‘for the time being’, (10b). The SFP *lei* has at least two functions, one is a temporal reading roughly equivalent to ‘recent past’ as shown in (4), repeated in (11a); the second reading is of an ‘imperative’ reading (11b).

- (10) a. Keoi hang sin.
 he walk SIN1
 ‘He walks first.’ (Eventive *sin* = *sin1*)
- b. Nei co-hou di sin.
 you sit-good some SIN2
 ‘You sit properly for the time being.’ (Imperative *sin* = *sin2*)
- (11) a. Keoi maai syu lei.
 He buy book LEI1
 ‘He just bought books.’ (Temporal-*lei* = *lei1*)
- b. Co hou lei
 sit good LEI2
 ‘Sit properly!’ (Imperative-*lei* = *lei2*)

The two functions of *sin* are closely related, which cannot be easily distinguished in many contexts. Tang (2012) suggests a diagnostic to tease the two apart by using the adverb *gansau* ‘subsequently’, which is semantically at odds with the eventive *sin* (*sin1*) because an event cannot happen ‘first’ and simultaneously happen subsequent to other events. The following examples use *gansau* ‘subsequently’ to make sure the two meanings of *sin* are distinguished.

While *sin1* and *lei1*, both being eventive or temporal markers, can occur in main clauses (matrix *sin1* and *lei1*) and complement clauses introduced by *waa* ‘say’ and *jiwai* ‘believe’ (embedded *sin1* and *lei1*), *sin2* and *lei2*, both being markers indicating ‘imperative’, can occur in neither of these contexts (12a) and (12b).

- (12) a. [A.Fai waa/jiwai [Leisei se zo go bun syu (LEI1)/(*LEI2)](LEI1)/(*LEI2)]
 AF. say/believe LS. writePERF that-CL book (LEI1/2)](LEI1/2)
 ‘AF said/thought that LS. wrote that book.’ (embedded LEI1)
 ‘AF just said/thought that LS. wrote that book.’ (matrix LEI1)
- b. [A.Fai waa/jiwai [Leisei gansau japheoi *SIN1/*SIN2] SIN1/*SIN2]
 AF say/believe LS. subsequently enter SIN1/2
 ‘AF firstly said/thought Leisei entered first.’
 (Note that *gansau* in (12b) is to force the *sin2* reading.)

Instead, *sin2* and *lei3* can occur only in very restricted contexts, such as, the complements introduced by *giu* ‘ask’ or *hyun* ‘persuade’, which is usually where the ‘imperative’ reading is derived (13). These are exactly the contexts where the temporal

SFPs *leil* and *sin1* are disallowed, as shown by the contrast between the two markers occurring in the matrix and embedded clauses.

- (13) a. [A.Fai giu [Leisei se hou (di) (*LEI1)/(LEI2)](LEI1)/(*LEI2)]
 AF. ask LS. write well (some) LEI
 ‘A Fai asked Leisei to write (more) properly!’(embedded LEI2)
 ‘A Fai just asked Leisei to write (more) properly. (matrix LEI1)
- b. A.Fai giu Leisei gansau japheoi *SIN1/SIN2]SIN1/??SIN2]
 AF. ask LS. subsequently enter SIN
 ‘AF. asked Leisei to enter subsequently for the time being!’
 ‘A Fai firstly asked Leisei to enter subsequently.’

Lastly, neither temporal SFPs nor imperative SFPs are allowed in the complements introduced by aspectual verbs such as *hoici* ‘begin’ (14) (Only the matrix clause can allow temporal SFPs).

- (14) [A Fai hoici [se go bun syu (*LEI1)/(*LEI2)/(*SIN2)] (LEI1)/(*LEI2)]
 AF. start write that-CL book LEI
 ‘A Fai just started to write that book.’ (matrix LEI1)

To summarize, *waa* ‘say’/*yiwai* ‘believe’ type of complements allow temporal SFPs, but not imperative SFPs; while *giu* ‘ask’/*hyun* ‘persuade’ type of complement shows the opposite pattern in disallowing temporal SFPs while allowing imperative SFPs. Crucially, the imperative SFPs can only occur in the latter type of complements. *hoici* ‘begin’ type complements permit neither type of SFPs. The availability of SFPs distinguishes three subtypes of clausal complements, parallel to Bianchi’s three-way distinction. The distribution of different negators shows a similar effect in identifying the three subtypes of complements clauses. Section 3.2 focuses on this issue.

2.2 Negators *mhou/mai* in different complements

In addition to the aspectual negator *mau*, which negates the existence of an event (15a), there is a pair of negators *mhou* and *mai* (15b) that prescriptively can serve to introduce negative commands (Matthews & Yip, 2002) in Cantonese. Tang (2012:11) observes that *mai/mhou* can optionally co-occur with imperative SFPs such as *sin2* (15c).

- (15) a. Nei mau faanhok.
 you NEG go.school
 ‘you didn’t go to school.’
- b. Nei mai/mhou faanhok.

- you NEG go.school
 ‘You don’t go to school!’
 c. (Nei) mai/mhou tungzi keoi sin¹.
 you NEG remind him SIN2
 ‘(You) don’t remind him/her for the time being.’

Crucially, the negators *mhou/mai* exhibit a distribution similar to *sin2*, which can occur in *giu* ‘ask’/*hyun* ‘persuade’ type of complements but not *waa* ‘say’/*yiwai* ‘believe’ type of complements, as shown in (16). The only acceptable negator in the former context is the regular aspectual negation, not the imperative negation. By contrast, the latter context only allows the imperative negation, but not the aspectual negation. Tang (2012) suggests that *mou/mai* and *sin2* all express deontic modality². (see Yip 2016’s discussion of *bié* as a marker of deontic modality³, the Mandarin counterpart of *mhou/mai*). *Hoici* ‘begin’ type complements disallow both types of negation (16c).

- (16) a. A.Fai waa/jiwai [Leisei kamjat mau/*mai/*mhou faanhok]
 AF. say/believe LS. yesterday NEG go.school
 ‘A Fai said/believed that Leisei *didn't* go to school yesterday.’
 b. Zoengsaam giu Leisei mai/mhou/*mau faanhok.
 ZS. ask LS. NEG go.school
 ‘Zoengsaam asked Leisei *not to* go to school.
 c. *Zoengsaam hoici mai/mhou/mau hok Yingman.
 ZS. start neg study English

The preceding distribution of negators serves to identify three subtypes of clausal complements, parallel to those shown by the distribution of SFPs. The three-way distinction is again consistent with Bianchi’s anchoring approach to finiteness. Recall that Bianchi proposes that a finite clause encodes an external logophoric center that events can be related to an external speech event (including its participant (i.e., speakers or addressees)

¹ As shown in the previous examples for *sin*, this sentence can be ambiguous between a reading with *sin* construed as *sin1* or *sin2*. (16) focuses on its *sin2* reading.

² The ‘imperative’ function traditionally attributed to these elements is a subtype of the deontic modality, which is shown in (i) by its occurrence in a non-imperative context with a 3rd person subject (see Yip’s 2016 discussion of the similar properties of the Mandarin *bié*):

- (i) Keoidei geigo (mai)ganzyu japheoi sin.
 they several subsequently enter SIN2
 ‘They *should* enter subsequently for the time being.’

³ Liao & Wang (2020) in a recent manuscript present a detailed discussion of Mandarin *bié* in different clausal complements such as those introduced by ‘persuade’ and ‘believe’ in Mandarin. This paper provides similar data from Cantonese and agrees with some of their assumption but differs in several crucial aspects, as will be shown in section 4.

and speech time, whereas a nonfinite clause encodes an internal logophoric center that events can be related to an internal speech event (matrix event, including the participants and temporal coordinates of the matrix clause).

Deontic SFPs and negators in Cantonese can occur only in those contexts that are related to the internal speakers (the matrix subjects), not the external speakers. For instance, the negators *mai/mhou* does not express the deontic modality of the external speaker, but the matrix subject (17). The conflicting continuation in (17) does not trigger unacceptability, which suggests that the deontic modality is evaluated by the internal speaker, but not the external one.

- (17) A Fai giu Leisi mai/mhou faanhok, danhai ngo gokdak keoi jinggoi faan.
 AF. ask LS. NEG go.school but I feel he should go
 ‘A Fai asked Leisi not to go to school, but I feel he should go.’

Combining the behavior of SFPs shown in Section 2.1 and that of negators in Section 2.2, it can be argued that the deontic SFPs (*sin2* and *lei2*) and their optional co-occurring negators can receive a unified analysis, that is, they both point to a [-Fin] clause in the sense of Bianchi (that anchors to the internal logophoric center). Zhang (2019) proposes that temporal SFPs (e.g., Mandarin *le*, *laizhe* and the Cantonese counterparts *laa* and *lei1*) heading a [+Fin] clause (the derivation of which will be discussed in Section 2.3). However, the deontic SFPs in Cantonese suggest a Fin head with the opposite feature [-Fin]. Interestingly this fills the gap in the inventory of potential complementizers realized at the Fin head, as summarized in (18).

- (18) a.

In this subsection, I have shown that deontic SFPs heading non-finite CPs in the sense of Bianchi (anchoring to internal speakers), but the relation of temporal SFPs as [+Fin] by Zhang and Bianchi’s anchoring approach has not yet been established. Due to the controversial status of Tense in Chinese (J. Lin, 2010; Sybesma, 2007), one recent line of investigation proposes a finiteness approach in which clauses that allow temporal SFPs are finite clauses that can anchor to the speaker, without making reference to Tense, departing from Bianchi’s original approach in which temporal anchoring is one important component of her notion of logophoric center (e.g. Zhang, 2019). Some of these discussions are based on the distribution of speaker-oriented adverbs (SpOA). Section 2.3 focuses on this issue, where it will be shown that Bianchi’s proposal clearly distinguishes some finite clauses as those anchoring to the speaker, while some other finite clauses do not anchor to speakers but nevertheless allow temporal SFPs.

2.3 Adverbs in different complements

It has been argued in the literature that clauses that allow temporal SFPs also allow speaker-oriented adverbs (SpOA) and there is a correlation between finiteness and SpOAs (Zhang, 2019). Some of the Mandarin examples are reproduced in (19)-(20). Examples of clauses that disallow temporal SFPs as well as SpOAs, are shown in (21)-(22). Cantonese exhibit similar patterns. Due to space restriction, only Mandarin examples are provided.

- (19) Wǒ zhīdào [Ajie xìngkuī/háihǎo mǎi-le bǎoxiǎn le].
 I know Ajie fortunately buy-PERF insurance SFP
 ‘I know that Ajie has fortunately bought insurance.’
- (20) [Yīnwèi Ajie xìngkuī/háihǎo mǎile bǎoxiǎn le],
 because Ajie fortunately buy-PERF insurance SFP
 suǒyǐ. wǒ bù dānxīn.
 therefore I not worry
 ‘Because Ajie has fortunately bought insurance, therefore, I’m not worried.’
- (21) Ajie dǎsuàn [míngtiān zhōngwǔ (*xìngkuī/háihǎo) zài jiā děng nǐ (*le)].
 Ajie plan tomorrow-noon. fortunately. at home wait you SFP
 Ajie plans to wait for you at home tomorrow noon.’
 (Mandarin Example adapted based on Zhang 2019: 991-992)
- (22) Zhangsan jiào Lisi [(*)xìngkuī/háihǎo) duō kànshū (*le)].
 ZS. ask LS. fortunately more read.book SFP
 ‘Zhangsan ask Lisi to read more books.’

That (20) and (21) disallow SpOA is in line with the fact that these complements, as shown in section 3.1 and 3.2, can only anchor to the internal speakers, not the external speakers, which cannot support SpOAs. The licensing of SpOAs, such as those in (20) and (21), on the other hand, is in fact not as clear-cut as it seems on the surface, which could potentially challenge the correlation drawn between SpOAs and finiteness.

Specifically, while the environments where temporal SFPs are allowed to occur often overlap with those where SpOA can appear, there are many environments where SFPs are possible but SpOA are banned. In (19), for example, it is true that *xìngkuī/háihǎo* ‘fortunately’ are allowed to occur in the cited *yīnwèi* ‘because’ adverbial clause, but they are not allowed in a context similarly introduced by *yīnwèi* ‘because’ in (23a)

- (23) Yīnwèi Zhāngsān (*xìngkuī) chīyào le, tā jīntiān kěyǐ cānjiā.
 Because ZS. fortunately take.pill SFP, he today can join
 ‘Because Zhangsan took some medicine, he can participate today.’
 [Mandarin]

The crucial difference between (20) and (23a) is that the former *yīnwèi* ‘because’ adverbial clause ‘provides the speaker’s evidence’ for making the claim that ‘I am not worried’ while the latter *yīnwèi* because adverbial clause provides ‘the subject’s reason for

not be able to run’, which ‘expresses a cause for the state of affairs expressed in the matrix clause’ (Haegeman: 2012:161-162). The former context instantiates the so-called ‘peripheral adverbial clause’ while the latter exemplifies the ‘central adverbial clause’ proposed by (Haegeman, 2012). It turns out that only peripheral adverbial clauses allow SpOAs. Another similar context is the *zicung* ‘since’ adverbial clauses (see Haegeman 2012 for detailed discussions of different types of adverbial clauses), the insertion of the SpOAs in *zicung* ‘since’ adverbial clauses renders the entire sentence unacceptable (24). Note that the temporal SFPs are nevertheless properly licensed.

- (24) [Zicung A Fai (*houcoi) songzo jap jyun laa], ngodei sin fongsam.
 since AF. fortunately send.PERF enter hospital SFP, we first in.relief
 ‘Since A Fai was sent to hospital, we finally felt in relief. [Cantonese]

These facts then suggest that the correlation between temporal SFPs and SpOA cannot be maintained. There are many contexts in which SpOAs cannot occur but which do allow temporal SFPs, which then leads one to rethink the correlation between SpOAs with finiteness. Moreover, while complement clauses like (19) seem to allow SpOA *xìngkuī* ‘fortunately’, crucially a change of the matrix subject from the first person *wǒ* to a third person such as *Zhangsan* renders the sentence unacceptable (25). This again casts doubt on whether SpOAs can reliably serve to identify finite clauses.

- (25) Zhangsan zhīdào [Ajie (*xìngkuī/háihǎo) mǎi-le bǎoxiǎn le].
 I know Ajie fortunately buy-PERF insurance SFP
 ‘I know that Ajie has fortunately bought insurance.’ [Mandarin]

Put differently, anchoring to the speaker is not a necessary requirement for licensing finite clauses. There are two pieces of evidence. First, as shown above, SpOAs like *xìngkuī/háihǎo* ‘fortunately’ which anchor to the external speakers, do not always occur in clauses that allow temporal SFPs. The second comes from the seemingly availability of some subtypes of SpOAs in complement clauses (excluding *xìngkuī/háihǎo* ‘fortunately’), such as *bùxìng* ‘unfortunately’, *yěxǔ* ‘perhaps’, *quèshì* ‘actually’, as shown in (26).

- (26) Zhangsan zhīdào [Lisi bùxìng/ yěxǔ/ quèshì de le zhège bing].
 ZS know LS unfortunately/perhaps/actually get-PERF this-CL disease
 ‘Zhangsan knows that Lisi unfortunately/perhaps/actually got this disease.’

From this, it can be seen that these contexts allow some subtypes of SpOAs, but not SpOAs like *xìngkuī/háihǎo* ‘fortunately’. This contrast in itself shows a distinction in SpOAs between strong SpOAs (e.g., strong evaluative SpOAs) and weak SpOAs (e.g., weak evaluative/modals and evidential SpOAs) proposed by (Ernst, 2009), in which strong SpOAs are argued to be subjective and ‘must be true for the speaker’s entire belief set’,

which means ‘the speakers brook no possibility of the proposition being false’ (Ernst 2009: 516). By contrast, weak SpOAs, are not necessarily subjective, and can be objective and ‘in principle may be at odds with the speaker’s belief set’ (Ernst 2009: 516).

I argue that the general incompatibility between strong SpOAs and complement clauses suggests that these clauses cannot anchor to the external speakers. The fact that some complement clauses can contain SpOAs is in fact an instantiation of weak SpOAs that are not indexed by the external speakers. Ernst argues that the SpOA ‘unfortunately’ in (27) is related not to the external speaker but to the speaker of the matrix clause (Jenny).

- (27) Jenny said that Amanda had unfortunately been rained out of her camping trip. (Ernst: 2009:525)

In the same spirit, the SpOAs in (27) in Chinese are all weak SpOAs that do not point to the external speaker but to the subject of the matrix clause, as shown by the acceptable continuation in (29) where the evaluation of the external speaker is denied.

- (28) Zhangsan zhīdào [Lisi búxìng/ dàgài/yěxǔ/quèshì de le zhège bìng].
 ZS know LS unfortunately/perhaps/actually getPERF this-CL disease
 Dàn wǒ juéde bùshí.
 But. I think not
 ‘Zhangsan knows that Lisi unfortunately/perhaps/actually got this disease, but I (the speaker) don’t think so.’

Moreover, if the SpOAs can be indexed by the external speakers in complement clauses, there should exist contexts where the evaluation made by the external speakers is true but false for the internal speakers. Take *búxìng* ‘unfortunately’ in (26) again, in a context where the (absolute) external speaker makes the evaluation of *búxìng* ‘unfortunately’ with regard to the following proposition while the matrix (internal) speaker Zhangsan holds the opposite evaluation (who evaluates the following proposition as fortunate), (27) is predicted to have an acceptable interpretation, if the complement clauses can contain the external speakers. However, this interpretation is not obtained for (27), which suggests that the SpOAs do not anchor to the external speaker, at least in the complements introduced by verbs such as *zhīdào* ‘know’. The same pattern holds for verbs like *yǐwéi/xiāngxìn* ‘believe’. Thus, if one wants to test whether a clause can contain an SpOA that can point to the external speaker, the strong SpOAs are better candidates.

As far as my data indicate, only complements of verbs of saying like *shuō* seems to be able to contain strong SpOAs that can anchor directly to the (absolute) external speakers (29), in addition to the internal speakers (however the judgments exhibit variations among native speakers).

- (29) Zhāngsān shuō [Lǐsì háihǎo qù yīyuàn le].
 ZS. say LS. fortunately go hospital SFP
 ‘Zhangsan said that Lisi fortunately went to the hospital.’

The distinction between verbs of saying and other verbs in whether external speakers are available in their complements is evidenced by the location of the SpOAs. Notice that all the SpOAs shown so far occur in post-subject position in the embedded clause. If anchoring to the external speaker licenses a finite clause, there is nothing that can prevent strong SpOAs from occurring in positions that are otherwise possible for these adverbs, such as sentence-initial position in main clauses (30).

- (30) Xìngkuī/háihǎo Lǐsì qù yīyuàn. le.
 fortunately Lisi go hospital SFP
 ‘Fortunately, Lisi went to the hospital.’

However, robust judgments show that these sentence-initial adverbs render the entire complex sentences unacceptable if the complement is introduced by verbs like *xiāngxìn* ‘believe’ (31a), as opposed to complements introduced by verbs of saying such as *shuō* ‘say’ or *xuānbù* ‘announce’ where sentence-initial adverbs are allowed (31b).

- (31) a. Zhangsan xiāngxìn/yǐwéi [*xìngkuī/háihǎo Lisi qù yīyuàn. le].
 ZS. believe/think. fortunately Lisi go hospital SFP
 ‘Zhangsan believes/thinks (*unfortunately) Lisi went to the hospital.’
 b. Lǎobǎn shuō/xuānbù [xìngkuī/háihǎo gōngsī jīnnián méi cáiyuán].
 Boss. say/announce fortunately company this.year not lay.off
 ‘The boss said/announced that fortunately the company didn’t have any lay-off this year.’

Combining (28)/(29) and (31), it can be seen that not all clauses that allow temporal SFPs, which are argued to be finite clauses, can contain SpOAs. Only those clauses introduced by verbs of saying can contain genuine SpOAs anchoring to external speakers. The SpOAs that are seemingly allowed in some complements are in fact those weak SpOAs anchoring to the internal speakers.

The distribution of SpOAs in complement clauses shows that only main clauses and complements introduced by verbs of communication can contain external speaker. The availability of SpOAs then can distinguish the ‘most’ finite clauses versus the non-finite clauses. This is line with Bianchi’s proposal of finiteness, in which she argues that a nonfinite form cannot encode any relation to the speech event while a finite form can encode the relation to the speech event *at least in the main clauses*. This italicized restriction made by Bianchi for main clauses (including communicative events) of finite forms is consistent with the distribution of SpOAs.

Summarizing the distributions of SFPs, negators, and adverbs, it can be shown that Bianchi's anchoring approach to finiteness clearly provides evidence for a finite/nonfinite distinction in Chinese. A nonfinite clause can only anchor to the internal speakers (exemplified by verbs such as *giu* 'ask'/*hyun* 'persuade'), while the most finite clauses (e.g., main clauses and communicative complements *shuō*) anchor to the external speakers. In addition to the existence of [+Fin] C in the latter contexts, SFPs in Cantonese provide evidence of [-Fin] C in the former contexts, exemplified by the deontic modal sentence particles *lei2* and *sin2*, as well as their (optional) co-occurrence with the deontic negators *mai* and *mhou*. However, it is also shown that Bianchi's approach cannot necessarily be equated with a speaker anchoring approach, on the basis of the fact that many contexts allow temporal SFPs ([+Fin] C) but do not anchor to the external speakers directly (e.g., *xiāngxìn* 'believe' contexts, cf. Zhang 2019), as shown by the distribution of SpOAs. The immediate question then is what is the crucial element that licenses a finite clause, if anchoring to speaker is not sufficient? In Section 3, I will propose an account based on the well-observed incompleteness phenomenon to complete the story of anchoring in Chinese via temporal anchoring, as argued in Bianchi's original analysis.

3. Speaker-anchoring?

In Section 2, it was shown that a finite/nonfinite distinction is clearly attested in Cantonese, in the sense of Bianchi's anchoring approach in which main/root clauses and complements introduced by verbs of communication are clearly distinctive from clauses introduced by predicates such as *giu* 'ask'. The former are clearly finite while the latter are nonfinite. It was also shown that anchoring to speakers is not necessary for licensing finite clauses, as the appearance of SpOAs cannot identify finite clauses as an encoding of external speakers. Facts from a well-observed phenomenon called the *incompleteness effect* (32a) in Chinese languages (Gù, 2007; Tsai, 2008) can similarly show that a purely speaker anchoring approach is not sufficient. If anchoring to speaker were how a finite clause is licensed, then it will be predicted that a sentence with elements clearly indicating the involvement of the speaker (e.g., the evaluation with strong SpOAs by the speaker) is grammatical ('complete'). However, an insertion of these elements still fails to remedy the incompleteness (32b), which suggests that speaker-oriented elements (which anchor to speakers) cannot license a finite clause. Moreover, the incompleteness cannot be remedied even when these clauses are embedded, which could potentially provide anchoring for the incomplete embedded clause (32c). The incompleteness can be remedied only when either temporal (e.g., verbal *-le* or sentence final *le*) or modal elements (e.g., modal auxiliaries) are inserted (33) (see Tsai 2008 for more details). These two major types of remedies for the incompleteness effect exactly match with the two sets of SFPs (e.g., temporal or deontic) that occur in finite and nonfinite contexts. Those temporal SFP ([+Fin]) markers are exactly those that can remedy the incompleteness. I argue that these SFPs instantiate the category of Finiteness whose main role is to identify the

mechanism for how a proposition is evaluated with regard to the deixis center (Zagona, 2013: 756), either temporally or via modality. Only if either of the [+Fin] or [-Fin] is specified, can a sentence become anchored, either temporally to the external or internal center of deixis, or via modality to the internal center of deixis.

- (32) a. ??Zhangsan kàn yìběn shū.
 ZS. read one-CL book
 Intended: ‘Zhangsan read a book.’
- b. ?? Zhangsan xìngkuī kàn yìběn shū.
 ZS. fortunately read one-CL book
 Intended: ‘Zhangsan fortunately read a book.’
- c. ??Lisi yǐwéi [Zhangsan kàn yì-běn shū].
 LS. believe ZS. read one-CL book
 Intended: ‘Lisi believes that Zhang read a book.’
- (33) a. Zhangsan xiě (le) yìběn shū le.
 ZS. read PERF one-CL book SFP
 ‘Zhangsan has read/read a book.’
- b. Zhangsan yīnggāi kàn yìběn shū
 ZS. should read one-CL book
 ‘Zhangsan should read a book.’
- c. A Fai tai jat-bun syu sin.
 A Fai read one-CL book SIN2
 A Fai (should) read a book for the time being! (Cantonese)

4. Proposal

In Section 2, it was shown that Cantonese, and more broadly speaking, Chinese clearly exhibits a finite/nonfinite distinction. SFPs (temporal or modal, and the co-occurring modal negators) serve to identify the distinction between complements introduced by *waa* ‘say’/*jiwai* ‘believe’ as opposed to those by *giu* ‘ask’/*hyun* ‘persuade’. SpOAs make a further distinction between main clauses (including those introduced by verbs of communications) and other complement clauses. Bianchi’s analysis of finiteness, based on logophoric anchoring, can clearly distinguish the main clauses and *giu* ‘ask’/*hyun* ‘persuade’ type of nonfinite clauses. *Hoici* ‘start’ type of complement is yet distinctively different from the other two, which is argued to not encode any logophoric anchoring. In other words, there is a four-way distinction in complement clauses based on the distributions of different SFPs and SpOAs, as summarized in (34). The temporal SFPs identify finite clauses, while the modal SFPs identify nonfinite contexts. SpOAs makes a further distinction among the finite contexts, main clauses (including the complements of verbs of communications) and other embedded contexts introduced by attitude verbs such as *jiwai* ‘believe’.

(34) Diagnostics used in identifying different complement clauses

	Temporal SFPs [+Fin]	Modal SFPs (and deontic negators) [-Fin]	SpOAs
Main Clauses & Verbs of communication	✓	✗	✓
<i>jiwai</i> ‘believe’	✓	✗	✗
<i>giu</i> ‘ask’/ <i>hyun</i> ‘persuade’	✗	✓	✗
<i>hoici</i> ‘begin’	✗	✗	✗
<i>Incompleteness</i> remedies	✓	✓	✗

In Section 3, I show that anchoring to speaker is not sufficient for licensing finite clauses, based on the well-observed incompleteness phenomenon. The unique role of [+Fin] C overtly realized by temporal SFPs (together with aspectual *-le*) and [-Fin] C overtly realized by modal SFPs in salvaging the incompleteness suggests a unified approach for deriving finite and nonfinite clauses, which is reminiscent of the proposal (Platzack, 1995) made with regard to the category of Finiteness in which he argues that finiteness consists of tense and mood. Specifically, I adopt Zagona’s (2013) analysis of FinP (headed by Fin) whose syntactic function is to identify the mechanism for how a proposition is evaluated with regard to the deixis center (see Section 2). In Chinese, I argue that temporal anchoring, which is overtly realized by temporal SFPs and verbal aspect, which in turn constitutes one of the major remedies to the incompleteness effect, is an instantiation of indicative mood with a temporal-ordering value, which values the mood feature at Fin. Alternatively, the mood feature can also be valued by modality, which specifies the proposition is evaluated in a non-indicative mood. I assume that the deontic modal SFPs *sin2* and *lei2* (together with the co-occurring modal negation element *mai* and *mhou*) are some of the overt realizations of the non-indicative mood [-Fin] (35).

- (35) a. Finite [imood: ordering +Fin *lei1 laa3*]
 b. Finite [umood: -Fin *lei2, sin2*]

Therefore, based on the properties shown in (34), the three-way distinction between *shuō/waa* ‘say’, *rènwéi/jingwai* ‘believe’, and *jiào/giu* ‘ask’ can be summarized in the following (36) (the fourth subtype *hoici* ‘start’ will be discussed in Section 5). Main clauses and complements of verbs of communication (36a) are the ‘most’ finite context (or root contexts) in which temporal SFP *lei1* and *laa3* can occur. These two SFPs serve to specify the mechanism by which the proposition is temporally evaluated and is anchored to the external speaker as encoded in the interpretable deixis feature (e.g. the speaker and speech time, as indexed by 1). Complements introduced by *rènwéi/yǐwéi* ‘believe’/‘think’ (36b) are finite and allow temporal SFPs, which similarly specify that the embedded proposition is temporally evaluated. The difference between (36a) and (36b)

lies in the deixis feature specification. For the latter, there is no deixis feature specified; the uninterpretable counterpart at the Force head is instead valued by the matrix verb. This is an instance of Bianchi’s internal logophoric center. Finally, for *hyun* ‘persuade’/*giu* ‘ask’ type complements, similar to (36b), the deixis feature is not valued, which leaves their uninterpretable counterpart to be valued via Agree with the matrix verb. The difference between (36b) and (36c) is the way in which the proposition is evaluated, one temporally as an instantiation of indicative mood (36b), and the other non-indicatively via deontic modals (36c).

(36)

a. Main clauses and verbs of communication clauses⁴

[ForceP Force_{[uperson][utime:]} [DeixisP Deixis_{[iperson:1][itime:1]} [FinP Fin_[imood:ordering] *lei1/laa3*]]]

b. ‘believe’/‘think’ clauses:

V [ForceP Force_{[uperson][utime:]} [DeixisP Deixis [FinP Fin_[imood:ordering] *lei1/laa3*]]]

c. ‘ask’/persuade clauses:

V [ForceP Force_{[uperson][utime:]} [DeixisP Deixis [FinP Fin_[umood:] *lei2/sin2*]]]

5. Some issues relating to the relation between Aspectual verbs/Exhaustive Control and finiteness

It has been shown in Section 2 that complements of verbs like *hoici* ‘start’ consistently behave differently from the other two embedded contexts (*yiwai* ‘believe’ and *giu/hyun* ‘ask’/ ‘persuade’) and also main clauses. Interestingly, Bianchi’s anchoring approach similarly treats Exhaustive Control, which subsumes aspectual verbs like *hoici* ‘start’, as distinctive from finite contexts and nonfinite contexts such as *giu/hyun* ‘ask’/‘persuade’. She argues that Exhaustive Control does not encode any logophoric center. I argue that the facts shown in (36) support this distinction. Complements introduced by this kind of verb are neither finite nor non-finite, but just simply parts of the main clauses. I will follow Fukuda’s (2012) proposal that analyzes aspectual verbs as functional heads, specifically, the Higher or Outer Aspect (Travis, 2010), which is essentially a monoclausal structure. Being a monoclausal structure, the incompatibility of

⁴ This three-way distinction is largely in line with a proposal recently made by Grano (2017), reproduced in (i)

- (i) a. Main clauses: project up to Attitude P
 b. Complements to predicates *rènwéi*: project up to TopicP/Illocutionary Force P
 c. Complements to predicates like *jiào*: project up to vP

The current analysis presents evidence for the split between (ia) and (ib) as well as the distinction between (ib) and (ic) based on the distributions of SpOAs and the distribution of different SFPs, respectively. Moreover, this paper presents evidence that *jiào* type of complements can project not only up to vP, but a CP, realized by the modal SFPs. Instead, the complements that can project to vP only in this analysis are those introduced by aspectual verbs, which is a distinction that is not clearly made in the proposal in (i).

all the SFPs (temporal and modal), and adverbs (speaker and subject-oriented adverbs) falls out naturally. These elements can occur only in the matrix left periphery (37).

- (37) a.[Zoengsaam hoici [se gobunsyu (*LEI1)/(LEI2)/(SIN1)(SIN2)]
 (LEI1)/(LEI2) (SIN1)(SIN2)]
 ZS. start [wirte that-CL book LEI1/LEI2 SIN1/SIN2]
 (LEI1)/(LEI2) (SIN1)(SIN2)
 ‘Zoengsaam *just* started to write that book.’ (matrix LEI1)
 b.[Zoengsaam soksing/sat [hoici *soksing/*sat hok Faatman].
 ZS. directly/definitely begin directly/definitely study French
 ‘Zoengsaam might as well/definitely started to learn French.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, I made several observations about the distribution of a set of sentence final particles, negators, and speaker-oriented and subject-oriented adverbs. These seemingly unrelated items support the existence of a finite/nonfinite distinction in Cantonese, or Chinese more broadly, following Bianchi’s finiteness as logophoric anchoring approach. I further presented evidence that temporal anchoring is required in Cantonese such that Bianchi’s approach cannot be reduced to a speaker anchoring approach (cf. Zhang, 2019). Adopting Zagona’s (2013) framework of functional categories, I developed an account of Cantonese as a language in which the functional category of Finiteness Phrase specifies the modality or mechanism for the evaluation of the introduced proposition, either by the external speaker or the matrix subject.

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“Wanting” the Future: The Case of Future *Yao*

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This paper addresses questions about the status of future *yao* “will, going to, about to” in Mandarin Chinese. Using evidence from future *yao*’s synchronic distribution and interpretation, we argue that it has the syntax and semantics typical of a root modal or aspect marker, rather than those of an epistemic modal. Our proposal bears on a recent debate over how future *yao* should be analyzed (Ren 2008, Wu & Kuo 2010, T.-H. J. Lin 2012, Santana Labarge 2016, etc.) as well as on questions about grammaticalization, since *yao* is said to have developed from either a desire verb (“want”) or deontic / teleological modal (“must, need to”). We suggest that these properties of future *yao* reflect an initial formal alignment between its desire or deontic/teleological precursors and root modals (or aspect markers).

0. Introduction¹

Although Chinese does not have tense morphology, it has various overt markers for indicating future events and states, for example, *jiang*, *hui*, and *yao*. This paper focuses on *yao* “will, be going to, be about to” (1), which many have claimed is an epistemic modal (e.g. Ren 2008, Wu & Kuo 2010, Santana Labarge 2016). We evaluate this claim from a distributional angle. We present novel evidence that *yao* behaves syntactically more like a root modal or an aspect marker (building on the aspectual analysis in T.-H. J. Lin 2012) and argue that it is likely to have both modal and aspect semantics.

- (1) Lisi yao shuǐjiào (le).
 Lisi YAO sleep LE
 Future *yao*: ‘Lisi is going/about to sleep.’²

Our analysis and diagnostics add to a recent literature concerned with the expression of temporal relations in Mandarin Chinese (e.g. Smith & Erbaugh 2005, J.-W.

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² Abbreviations used in glosses: CL: classifier; LE: change-of-state particle *le*; PFV: perfective; PROG: progressive; PRT: particle

Lin 2006, Ren 2008, Wu & Kuo 2010, Sun 2014, Huang 2015, Chen & Husband 2018, among others). It also contributes to work on the range of ways in which the future is expressed across languages (see Bochnak 2019 for an overview).

Beyond questions about tense, modality, and aspect, our conclusions about *yao* also have implications for diachronic change. *Yao* has several uses in modern Mandarin: in addition to being a future marker, it marks desire (“want”) and deontic or teleological modality (“must, need”). As many have observed, these uses are diachronically related (Ota 1987, Wang 1989, Lu 1997, Santana Labarge 2016, among others). *Yao* began as a verb with request or demand-like semantics and acquired a deontic or teleological reading (“must, need to VP”) by around 200 C.E. *Yao* as a desire verb (“want to VP,” “want NP”) appears later, by the Tang period (600-900 C.E.). Clear evidence of a non-deontic/teleological, non-desire future use appears even later, although it is unclear whether the future use developed directly from the desire use (Lu 1997) or directly from the deontic/teleological use (Santana LaBarge 2016). By studying what properties *yao* currently has as a future marker, we are better placed to address questions about how it might have changed diachronically, and how the case of *yao* informs general theories about the grammaticalization of desire or obligation verbs into future markers (Bybee et al. 1994, Harris & Campbell 1995, etc.).

The paper is organized as follows. Section 1 provides background on cross-linguistic variation in how the future is expressed grammatically and how *yao* bears on this issue. Section 2 lays out some arguments that the future *yao* and the other uses of *yao* constitute a case of ambiguity, rather than semantic generality. Section 3 provides distributional evidence for a root modal or aspect analysis of *yao*. Section 4 discusses aspects of the semantics of future *yao*, pointing out that it has properties characteristic of modals. Section 5 offers speculations on why *yao* might have developed into a root modal or aspect marker, but not into an epistemic modal. Finally, Section 6 concludes.

1. Desire, future, and modality

There is substantial variation in the analysis of items expressing a future-like meaning (Bochnak 2019). Take for instance English *will*. Is *will* a tense marker, in that it shifts the time of evaluation of the sentence forward with respect to the utterance time (Kissine 2008)? Some have instead argued that *will* is not the exact mirror image of the past tense (Palmer 1987, Klecha 2014, among others): The future, in contrast to the past, is unknown, and a way to incorporate this notion of uncertainty is to assume a modal analysis for *will*, in which it is treated as a quantifier over possible worlds.

A further factor in the debate is that future markers within the same language have different meanings: In English, *will* has been argued to be different from *going to*, which Copley (2001, 2009) claims is a combination of a modal and an aspect (a progressive). Cross-linguistically, finally, future markers show variable behavior, with some markers behaving parallel to tenses, while others behave more parallel to modals (see Bochnak

2019). More specifically, some proponents of a modal analysis of future markers claim that the modal flavor is epistemic (Giannakidou & Mari 2014), in that it deals with our knowledge about future events. An interesting piece of support for this analysis is that *will* in English can be used both as a future marker and an epistemic modal (2).

- (2) a. I will go home now. (Future)
 b. That will be the postman. (Epistemic: “Given our knowledge, ...”)
 (from Palmer 1987)

Ren (2008), Wu & Kuo (2010), and Santana Labarge (2016), among others, also propose that *yao* is an epistemic modal. In this paper, we argue against this proposal. We claim that *yao* is a root modal that deals with future *circumstances*, or an aspect (as claimed by T.-H. J. Lin 2012), or a combination thereof. We use root modality as a term that covers all non-epistemic modalities, i.e., deontic, teleological, ability, and other modalities (3). It has long been known that epistemic and non-epistemic modalities differ quite radically in the syntactic and semantic environments they occur in (Ross 1969, Brennan 1993, Hacquard 2006, 2010, Kratzer 2013, among others). An example is that non-epistemic modals are generally future-oriented (they combine with an event in their preadjacent that lies in the future of the evaluation time of the modal), while epistemic modals are not (e.g. Condoravdi 2002, Klecha 2016, though see Thomas 2014 for some modifications). We will discuss ways in which epistemic and non-epistemic modals differ in Mandarin, and argue that *yao* patterns with the non-epistemics.

- (3) Root modal (English *have to*)
 a. I have to pay taxes. (Deontic: “According to the law, ...”)
 b. I have to drink a glass of water. (Teleological: “To stay hydrated, ...”)

Our analysis of *yao* is also predicated on the assumption that future *yao* is grammatically distinct from the other uses associated with *yao*. That is, there isn’t just a single *yao* that is semantically general enough to accommodate the various uses. Arguments against semantic generality and for ambiguity can be found in Li & Thompson (1981), who showed clearly that desire and future *yao*s have different distributions. In the next section, we briefly present two arguments to establish the point.

2. *Yao*: a case of ambiguity

Here, we compare future *yao* with desire *yao* “want” and deontic/teleological *yao* “must, need to,” from which future *yao* has been claimed to descend (Lu 1997, Santana LaBarge 2016).

Li & Thompson (1981:175-176) describe a simple test to distinguish between desire and future *yao*: desire *yao* can be negated with *bu*, but future *yao* cannot be (4). We note here that deontic/teleological *yao* cannot be negated either.

- (4) Tamen bu yao he kafei.
 they NEG YAO drink coffee
 i. Desire *yao*: ‘They don’t want to drink coffee.’ (‘They want to not drink coffee.’)
 ii. #Future *yao*: ‘They are not going to drink coffee.’
 iii. #Deontic *yao*: ‘They are required to not drink coffee’/ ‘They are not required to drink coffee.’

Distinguishing between deontic/teleological and future *yao* is a little more complex. We use a standard test of semantic generality and ambiguity (Zwicky & Sadock 1973). Take for example English *teacher* (or Mandarin *laoshi* / *jiaoshi* “teacher”), which is semantically general in that it is compatible with any subject of instruction. When a semantically general predicate like *teacher* takes two conjoined NPs as its argument, the resulting sentence is compatible with what we call a uniform or a mixed reading (5a).

To the extent that *yao* is semantically general between deontic / teleological and future uses, mixed readings should also be available. This is not the case, however: mixed readings are decidedly infelicitous (5b). From this, we conclude that *yao* is not only ambiguous between desire and future, but that distinction between future *yao* and deontic/teleological *yao* is an instance of another ambiguity.

- (5) a. Mary and John are teachers.
 i. Uniform reading: ‘Mary is a math teacher. John is also a math teacher.’
 ii. Mixed reading: ‘Mary is a math teacher. John is a physics teacher.’
 b. Lisi he Zhangsan mingtian yao qu Chengdu le.
 Lisi and Zhangsan tomorrow YAO go Chengdu LE
 i. Uniform deontic/teleological reading: ‘It is now the case that Lisi and Zhangsan must go to Chengdu tomorrow.’ (Scenario: This morning, Lisi and Zhangsan were ordered by their boss to go to Chengdu tomorrow.)
 ii. Uniform future reading: ‘Lisi and Zhangsan are going to go to Chengdu tomorrow.’ (Scenario: Lisi and Zhangsan made plans a long time ago to go to Chengdu tomorrow.)
 iii. #Mixed reading: ‘It is now the case that Lisi must go to Chengdu tomorrow, and Zhangsan is going to Chengdu tomorrow.’ (Scenario: This morning, Lisi was ordered to go to Chengdu tomorrow, while Zhangsan had made plans a long time ago to Chengdu tomorrow.)

3. Future *yao* as a root modal or aspect marker

In this section, we critically examine recent claims that future *yao* is an epistemic modal. We make use of the fact that in Mandarin, epistemic modals, like *keneng* “maybe, might,” *kending* “must,” and *yinggai* “should, probably,” have a different distribution from root modals (e.g. deontic, teleological, bouletic, circumstantial modals) and aspect markers. The relevance of this distributional difference has generally gone underappreciated in previous work on *yao*. Here, we use it to provide independent evidence that *yao* behaves more like a root modal or an aspect marker.

Ideally, we would like to be more specific about whether *yao* patterns with root modals or with aspect markers. However, modality and aspect can be closely intertwined, for instance, in the case of the progressive and prospective aspects (Dowty 1977, Portner 1998, Copley 2001, 2009, among others). Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, there is no definitive morphosyntactic diagnostic for differentiating between these two categories, whether for Mandarin or for other languages. For these reasons, we will primarily be concerned with how root modals and aspect markers as a whole are different from epistemic modals.

First, epistemic modals can freely take a complement with the copula *shi* “be” (6a). In contrast, there are restrictions on root modals co-occurring with the copula (6b-c),³ and aspect markers in general cannot occur with the copula at all (6d).

- (6) a. Lisi keneng / kending / yinggai shi gongmin.
 Lisi might must should be citizen
 ‘Lisi might / must / should be a citizen.’ (Scenario: We know that Lisi’s children are citizens and citizenship is inherited from one’s parents.)
- b. * Lisi keyi / nenggou shi gongmin.
 Lisi can can be citizen
 Intended: ‘Lisi is allowed to be(come) a citizen.’ (Scenario: Lisi has met the requirements for naturalization.)
- c. ??Lisi xuyao / bixu shi gongmin.
 Lisi need need be citizen
 Intended: ‘Lisi needs to be(come) a citizen.’ (Scenario: Lisi is a non-citizen but wishes to run for election.)
- d. * Lisi zai shi gongmin.
 Lisi PROG be citizen
 Intended: ‘Lisi is currently a citizen.’

³ The restriction against root modals and *shi* is lifted when the subject is generic (i), although we do not have an account for why there is such an exception.

- (i) Houxuanren bixu shi sanshi-wu-sui yishang de gongmin.
 candidate must be thirty-five-years.old above MOD citizen
 ‘Candidates must be citizens above the age of 35.’

(7) shows that future *yao* also cannot take a complement with the copula.

- (7) * Lisi yao shi gongmin (le).
 Lisi YAO be citizen LE
 Intended: ‘Lisi going to be(come) a citizen.’ (Scenario: Lisi is just about to take the oath of allegiance.)

To be clear, this argument can be seen as a narrower version of T.-H. J. Lin’s (2012) claim that epistemic modals can have “stative” complements and future *yao* cannot. We avoid appealing to stativity because it might cover too broad a class of predicates: some arguably stative predicates, like *you* “have, to exist,” can appear with *yao* (8).

- (8) Kanlai zhe bu dianying yao you xuji (le).
 looks.like this CL movie YAO have sequel LE
 ‘It looks like this movie is going to have a sequel.’

Our second argument involves the change-of-state particle *le*, which can be translated along the lines of “It is now the case, when it was not before, that...” For the sake of argument, we adopt the generalization that epistemic modals scope above *le* (9a), while root modals and aspect markers scope under it (9b-c) (Santana LaBarge 2016, also see more discussion in T.-H. J. Lin 2012).

- (9) a. Zhangsan keneng/ kending / yinggai qu Taipei le.
 Zhangsan might must should go Taipei LE
 Epistemic > *le*: ‘It is possible / necessary / probable that it is now the case that Zhangsan went to Taipei.’ (#‘It is now the case that Zhangsan might / must / should go to Taipei.’)
- b. Zhangsan neng qu Taipei le.
 Zhangsan able go Taipei LE
Le > root: ‘It is now the case that Zhangsan is able to go to Taipei.’
- c. Zhangsan qu-le Taipei le.
 Zhangsan go-PFV Taipei LE
Le > aspect: ‘It is now the case that Zhangsan has now gone to Taipei.’

Santana LaBarge (2016:413) claims that *yao* scopes above *le* like an epistemic modal, pointing to the interpretations given in (10a-b) as evidence. The intuition is that if Zhangsan had always had plans to go to Chengdu tomorrow, then the *le* > *yao* reading (10a) should be pragmatically odd, since this reading implies that Zhangsan had no plans to go to Chengdu until much more recently.

- (10) Zhangsan mingtian yao qu Chengdu le.
 Zhangsan tomorrow YAO go Chengdu LE
 Scenario: Zhangsan made plans a long time ago to go to Chengdu tomorrow.
 a. #*Le* > *yao*: ‘It is now the case that tomorrow, Zhangsan will go to Chengdu.’
 b. *Yao* > *le*: ‘Tomorrow, it will be the case that Zhangsan goes to Chengdu.’
 (adapted from Santana LaBarge 2016:413 ex. 33)

We have no issues with the form of Santana LaBarge’s claim, as presented in (9) and (10). However, we would like to argue that there is actually a viable *le* > *yao* reading available for (10). For this alternative analysis to work, one needs to assume, following Li & Thompson (1981:175), that *yao* marks an immediate future, i.e., *yao* is semantically more like English *about to* than *will*. (11) provides support for this assumption: the occurrence of *mingnian* “next year” instead of *mashang* “right away” with *yao* reduces acceptability.

- (11) Mashang / #Mingnian yao rishi le.
 right.away next.year YAO solar.eclipse LE
 Intended: ‘There will be a solar eclipse right now / next year.’

On the assumption that *yao* expresses an immediate future, (10) can receive a paraphrase where *le* scopes over *yao*, along the lines of “It is now the case (= *le*) that there is an immediate future (= *yao*) event tomorrow of Zhangsan going to Chengdu.” More specifically, previously, Zhangsan’s trip was deemed to be too far in the future, so describing it with *yao* would have been inappropriate. However, enough time has since passed, so there has been a change of state at the time of speech: the trip is now only a day away, so it can be described as imminent. *Yao* is therefore licensed.

Time adverbs provide a third argument. Mandarin modals – epistemic or root – can appear in modal-time adverb-verb word order (12); (12c) shows that this is the case for the various root readings of *yao*. Time adverbs can also precede modals, although this fact is irrelevant for our purposes.

- (12) a. Zongtong keneng mingtian jiejian dashi.
 president might tomorrow meet ambassador
 Epistemic *keneng*: ‘The president might meet the ambassador tomorrow.’
 (Scenario: there are rumors of a meeting.)
 b. Zongtong keyi mingtian jiejian dashi.
 president able tomorrow meet ambassador
 Root (circumstantial) *keyi*: ‘The president is able to meet the ambassador tomorrow.’ (Scenario: the president just had a meeting cancelled, and so can meet the ambassador.)

- c. Zongtong yao mingtian zhiqian jiejian dashi.
 president YAO tomorrow before meet ambassador
 Root *yao* (desire *yao* “want” or deontic *yao* “must”): ‘The president wants/has to meet the ambassador before tomorrow.’

In contrast, for the progressive aspect *zai*, the word order is time adverb-*zai*-verb (13). (The other aspect markers are irrelevant for this discussion because they are all verbal suffixes. It is not possible at all for them to precede a time adverb.)

- (13) a. * Zongtong zai {xianzai / nashi} jiejian dashi.
 president PROG now that.time meet ambassador
 Intended: ‘The president is meeting the ambassador now / was meeting the ambassador at that time.’
 b. Zongtong {xianzai / nashi} zai jiejian dashi.

Future *yao* patterns more like *zai*: as (14) shows, time adverbs as a rule precede *yao*, with only two exceptions: *mashang* “right away” (Yuhan Zhang, p.c.) and *suishi* “at any moment.” This parallel with *zai* is suggestive that *yao* is aspectual (as claimed by T.-H. J. Lin 2012), although the exceptions mean that we should be careful about interpreting it as clear evidence that *yao* is an aspect marker. (This word order difference between future *yao* and desire and deontic/teleological *yao* also provides additional evidence in favor of an ambiguity analysis.)

- (14) a. * Zongtong yao {guohou / wu fenzhong hou} jiejian dashi (le).
 president YAO later five minute after meet ambassador LE
 Intended: ‘The president is going to meet the ambassador later / in five minutes.’
 b. Zongtong {guohou / wu fenzhong hou} yao jiejian dashi le.

To summarize, we have pointed out several ways in which epistemic modals like *keneng* “maybe,” *kending* “must,” and *yinggai* “should” differ systematically from root modals and aspect markers in Mandarin. To the extent that future *yao* is an epistemic modal, we predict that its distribution should pattern with *keneng*, *kending*, or *yinggai*. However, this prediction is not borne out, *contra* Ren 2008, Wu & Kuo 2010, and Santana LaBarge 2016. Instead, the evidence is compatible with *yao* being a root modal or an aspect marker, along the lines of T.-H. J. Lin 2012.

4. Remarks on future *yao*'s semantics

Our conclusion about the syntax of future *yao*, namely, it has the distribution of a root modal or aspect marker, and not that of an epistemic modal, raises an important question about *yao*'s semantics: does it have root modal or aspect semantics?

This is admittedly a difficult question to answer, for two reasons. First, as far as we know, there is no widely-accepted test for positively identifying aspect semantics. Second, the question presupposes that a lexical item can have either aspect or root modal semantics, but not both. However, this assumption might be too strong: the progressive aspect marker *be going to* in English has been argued to exhibit both aspectual and modal semantics (Dowty 1977, Portner 1998, Copley 2001, 2009, among others).

Given these claims about English *be going to*, it is not implausible that *yao* also has both aspectual and modal semantics. We tentatively suggest that *yao* encodes prospective aspect, locating the event denoted by the VP in the future of a reference time (Reichenbach 1947) or topic time (Klein 1994).

We can show with more certainty that *yao* passes two diagnostics of modal semantics. The first diagnostic, proposed by Klecha (2014), is that a lexical item with modal semantics should support a counterfactual, nonveridical reading. This property follows easily from a classical analysis of modal operators as quantifiers over possible worlds (e.g. Kratzer 1991). (15a) illustrates this point for the modal *yinggai* "should," while (15b) makes the same point for *yao*.

- (15) a. Kafei benlai yinggai he-wan de.
 coffee originally should drink-finish PRT
 'The coffee should have been finished.' (There is still some coffee left.)
- b. Kafei benlai yao he-wan de.
 coffee originally YAO drink-finish PRT
 'The coffee was going to be finished.' (There is still some coffee left.)

The second diagnostic is polysemy. Cross-linguistically, a modal can be associated with several modal flavors. For instance, English *must* can have epistemic (necessarily true given one's knowledge), deontic (necessary given certain rules), or teleological flavors (necessary given one's goals). Mandarin *neng* and *hui* are also polysemous: *neng* has deontic and ability flavors (16a), while *hui* has ability and future readings (16b). The same is true for *yao*, as mentioned previously. In addition to the future use, *yao* is also associated with bouletic (desire), deontic, teleological, and circumstantial readings (17).

- (16) a. Lisi neng kai che.
 Lisi can drive car
 Deontic modal: 'Lisi is allowed to drive a car.'
 Ability modal: 'Lisi is able to drive a car.'

- b. Lisi hui tan gangqin.
Lisi can play piano
Ability modal: ‘Lisi is able to play the piano.’
Future modal: ‘Lisi will play the piano.’
- (17) a. Qiangxie yao cunfang hao.
firearm YAO store good
Deontic / teleological modal: ‘Firearms must be stored well.’ (if one wishes to avoid accidents, to comply with laws, etc.)
- b. Dongtian guoqu, xueren zongshi yao ronghua de.
winter pass snowman always YAO melt PRT
Circumstantial modal: ‘When winter ends, snowmen always melt.’

5. Why is future *yao* a root modal or aspect marker?

Given that future *yao* is a root modal or aspect that developed out of a desire or deontic/teleological use, we consider why it should have grammaticalized in this way. This question is relevant because there are other directions that *yao* could have taken. For instance, consider English *will*, which developed from a desire verb in Old English. As mentioned earlier, *will* has arguably epistemic properties (18a). *Yao* could have developed into an analogue of *will*, but it did not. Besides the distributional arguments presented above, we can show that (18b), the equivalent of (18a) with *yao*, is unacceptable.

- (18) a. Oil will float on water. (Given our knowledge about how oil and water behave.)
b. *You yao fu zai shui-mian shang (de / le).
oil YAO float at water-surface above PRT LE
Intended: ‘Oil will float on water.’

Obviously, it is difficult to give a definitive answer to why *yao* developed the way it did. What we will do here instead is to offer a formal perspective on the problem, integrating formal approaches to grammaticalization (e.g. Lightfoot 1979, Roberts & Roussou 2003, Hacquard & Cournane 2016; see also Santana LaBarge 2016 for a different framework) with observations about *yao*’s development (e.g. Ota 1987, Wang 1990, Lu 1997, Santana LaBarge 2016). Although it is unclear whether the future use developed directly from the desire use (Lu 1997) or directly from the deontic/teleological use (Santana LaBarge 2016), we suggest that either development trajectory helped ensure that future *yao* has root modal or aspect properties.

More specifically, if future *yao* had developed from a deontic/teleological modal (“must, need to”), which is itself a type of root modal, then it would of course be unsurprising for it to retain root modal properties. But we would also like to suggest that even if future *yao* had developed directly from a verb with desire semantics (“want”), it

would also be quite natural for future *yao* to have root modal or aspect marker properties, because of formal similarities between verbs and root modals / aspect markers.

At a high level, the fact that the desire verb *yao*, which can take complement clauses, should develop into a functional head over time is unsurprising. For instance, Roberts & Roussou (2003) point out that biclausal (control) constructions are often susceptible to reanalysis as a monoclausal construction, especially if there is no clear morphosyntactic evidence that the complement of the control predicate is a clause. In the context of *yao*, this means that a string like (19) can be plausibly analyzed in two ways. The first is a biclausal analysis where *yao* is a control predicate and *shuijiao* its complement clause (19a). The second is a monoclausal analysis, where *shuijiao* is the main verb of the sentence, and *yao* a functional head in the clausal spine (19b).⁴

- (19) Lisi *yao* *shuijiao*.
 Lisi want sleep
- a. *Yao* + complement clause: [Lisi [VP *yao* [s PRO *shuijiao*]]
- b. *Yao* + VP: [Lisi [FP *yao* [VP *shuijiao*]]

However, this reanalysis proposal alone is not specific enough to explain why desire *yao* acquired root modal or aspect marker properties. We suggest that this development might follow because of the following cross-linguistic generalization: verbs scope under tense, as do aspect and root modals. Epistemic modals, on the other hand, scope over tense (Groenendijk & Stokhof 1975, Iatridou 1990, among others, but see Rullmann & Matthewson 2018 for a claim that root modals can scope over tense). This initial alignment between verbs and root modals / aspect might have helped ensure that future *yao* has root modal or aspectual properties.

Here, we abstract away from the contentious issue of how tense is represented in Chinese (see J.-W. Lin 2006, 2010, Sybesma 2007, T.-H. J. Lin 2012, Sun 2014, Huang 2015, Chen & Husband 2018, etc. for recent discussion) and whether to cash out this generalization about modality and tense in structural terms (cf. Cinque 2006, Hacquard 2006, Grano 2015). What is more relevant here is the cross-linguistic robustness of this generalization, illustrated in (20) and (21) for English and Mandarin: it suggests strongly that the same scope generalizations should hold in earlier varieties of Chinese, even though we obviously cannot access native speaker intuitions for these varieties.

- (20) a. John had to be at home last night.
- b. Yuehan zuowan yinggai zai jia.
 John last.night should be home

⁴ A similar intuition that control predicates can be instantiated as functional heads and/or take VP-like complements can be found in the literature on restructuring (e.g. Wurmbrand 2001, Cinque 2006, Grano 2015, Huang 2018).

- (i) Epistemic modal > past: ‘(Given what we now know,) it is now necessary/probable that last night, John was at home.’
 (ii) Past > root modal: ‘Given the circumstances last night, there was a requirement then that John be at home.’ (e.g. it was John’s wife’s birthday.)
- (21) a. Last night, Zhangsan wanted to go home.
 b. Zuowan Zhangsan yao hui jia.
 last.night Zhangsan want return home
 (i) #*Want/Yao* > past: ‘It is now desirable that Zhangsan was home last night.’
 (ii) Past > *want/yao*: ‘Given the circumstances last night, it was then desirable for Zhangsan to be at home.’

More tentatively, we note that there are two other formal properties that modern Mandarin desire *yao* “want” shares with root modals but not epistemic modals. To the extent that these properties of desire *yao* and modals predate the development of future *yao*, they provide additional reasons for why future *yao* came to behave more like a root modal than an epistemic modal.

First, desire *yao* cannot have a complement with the copula *shi* (22). This fact parallels the copula facts shown earlier: root modal and aspect markers impose restrictions on whether the complement can have the copula, but epistemic modals do not.

- (22) * Lisi yao shi gongmin.
 Lisi want be citizen
 Intended: ‘Lisi wants to be(come) a citizen.’

Second, in terms of interpretation, desire *yao* is incompatible with a present temporal orientation: the time of the event in *yao*’s complement cannot be simultaneous with the time of the desire (23). Likewise, root modals in Mandarin are generally incompatible with a present temporal orientation: the time of the event expressed by the main verb cannot be simultaneous with the time of the modal (24).⁵

- (23) ??Lisi yao xianzai zai jia.
 Lisi want now be home
 Intended: ‘Lisi wants / needs to be at home now.’
- (24) ??Lisi bixu / keyi xianzai zai jia.
 Lisi need can now be home

⁵ Like the restriction on root modals and the copula *shi* (footnote 3), this restriction on root modals and temporal orientation is lifted when the subject is generic (i).

- (i) Shenqingzhe bixu xianzai zai Meiguo.
 applicant must now be United.States
 ‘Applicants must now be in the United States.’

Intended: ‘Lisi needs / is allowed to be at home now.’

Unlike desire *yao* or root modals, epistemic modals can have a nonfuture temporal orientation, as (25) illustrates.

- (25) Lisi {keneng / kending / yinggai} xianzai zai jia.
 Lisi might need should now be home
 ‘Lisi might / must / should be at home now.’

As further support for our analysis, in other work (van Dooren et al. 2019), we note that desire verbs in at least two other languages – Brazilian Portuguese and Dutch – have independently undergone a very similar grammaticalization process, acquiring root modal uses. Notably, the desire verbs also pattern like root modals in these two languages.

Our emphasis on formal properties contrasts with meaning-based or functionalist approaches regarding how desire verbs grammaticalize into future markers. These approaches tend to highlight the conceptual overlap between a desired or intended action and the action happening in the future (Bybee et al. 1994, also Sweetser 1987, 1990, Traugott 1989, Hengeveld 2011). To the extent that these accounts discuss finer-grained distinctions in the development of future markers, they are often framed in terms of general “paths” or “stages” of diachronic change (e.g. Bybee et al. 1994, Hengeveld 2011, among others). In such a framework, the fact that future *yao* has root modal or aspect properties simply reflects a tendency for verbs to proceed through such a stage before acquiring an epistemic use. While insightful from a descriptive and typological perspective, we argue that such frameworks have a more limited explanatory value, in that their claims only cover semantic change. It leaves unexplained why future *yao* is also syntactically different from desire *yao*, for instance, as we observed with the negation facts in Section 1 and the temporal adverb facts in Section 2. In contrast, the account we sketched above – which explicitly assumes a categorical change from verb to functional head, based on formal similarities and differences – offers a way to understand how such distinctions might arise.

6. Conclusion

We showed in the sections above that future *yao* and the other uses of *yao* (e.g. “want”, “must, need to”) are a case of ambiguity, rather than semantic generality. Building on T.-H. J. Lin 2012, we provided evidence from the distribution and interpretation of future *yao* to show that *yao* behaves syntactically like an aspect marker or a root modal, and not an epistemic modal, as claimed by Ren (2008), Wu & Kuo (2010), Santana LaBarge (2016), among others. We also argued that *yao* might have both aspectual and modal semantics.

Beyond addressing a debate about the status of future *yao*, our study of its synchronic properties bears on the grammaticalization of desire verbs or

deontic/teleological modals into future markers, a process that is well-attested across languages (e.g. Bybee et al. 1994). In principle, the future can be expressed through a variety of ways: tense, epistemic modals, root modals, aspect, and so on. The fact that *yao* has not developed into an epistemic modal calls for a principled explanation. Our contribution here has been to point out that there are syntactic and semantic properties that desire *yao* shares with root modals, but not with epistemic modals. This alignment, we suggest, makes it less likely that desire *yao* grammaticalizes into an epistemic modal.

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Bare (Double) and Prepositional Objects in Cantonese Applicatives*

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This paper provides a new analysis, in the Minimalist framework (Chomsky 2000), of four Cantonese applicative constructions, concentrating on the availability of internal arguments for A'-movement in relativization and adversativization ("long passive"). The theme direct object (DO) is always bare and has structural case. The affectee originates in the specifier of an applicative phrase ApplP, as an indirect object (IO) that is either bare (without a preposition at LF) or prepositional (with a preposition at LF, potentially deleted at PF). Both kinds of IO nominals have inherent case. Whereas inherent case prevents A'-movement of bare nominals, both PP islands and inherent case do so for prepositional nominals. Consequently, only DO nominals can be relativized by gapping; IO nominals require resumption. In contrast, the null adversative operator Op^P replacing a nominal is caseless. Although Op^P still cannot escape from PP islands, it can undergo A'-movement if it is bare. Bare affectees thus permit adversativization by Op^P-gapping, as do themes in general, while prepositional affectees trigger Op^P-resumption.

1. Introduction

Cantonese has four constructions in which a ditransitive verb subcategorizes for the following theta roles and syntactic positions: the AGENT encoded as SUBJECT (S); the THEME as DIRECT OBJECT (DO); and the AFFECTEE as INDIRECT OBJECT (IO) either with or without a preposition (P). The constructions are designated neutrally here as Con A to Con D, but are also accompanied by their old names in the literature (Tang 1998) and their new names under my applicative analysis.

***Acknowledgments:** I would like to thank my consultants for their grammaticality judgments, and John Bowers, Miloje Despić, John Whitman, and participants at NACCL-32 for their comments. Any errors are my own. **Abbreviations:** 1SG first person singular; 3SG third person singular; ACC accusative; Adv adverb; Appl applicative; Asp aspect; C complementizer; Cl classifier; COMPL complete; D determiner; DAT dative; Dem demonstrative; DO direct object; EPP Extended Projection Principle; IO indirect object; LF Logical Form; LK linker; NOM nominative; Op^P adversative operator; Op^R relative operator; P preposition; PF Phonological Form; PFV perfective; Poss possessor; S subject; T tense; V verb; Voi voice. **Romanization:** Cantonese examples are Romanized in Jyutping.

(1) Con A

Old: PREPOSITIONAL DATIVE S V DO P_{bei} IO
 New: OVERT-BEI APPLICATIVE S V DO P_{bei} IO

我 畀/賣/寄/掉/買/作/ 咗 本 書 畀 個 學生
 ngo⁵ bei²/maai⁶/gei³/diu⁶/maai⁵/zok³/zo² bun² syu¹ bei² go³ hok⁶saang¹
 1SG give/sell/send/throw/buy/write/ PFV CL book DAT CL student
 ‘I gave/sold/sent/threw/a book to the student.’
 ‘I bought/wrote/a book for the student.’

(2) Con B

Old: INVERSE DOUBLE OBJECT CONSTRUCTION S V DO IO
 New: COVERT-BEI APPLICATIVE S V DO P_{bei} IO

我 畀/*賣/*寄/*掉/*買/*作/ 咗 本 書 畀 個 學生
 ngo⁵ bei²/*maai⁶/*gei³/*diu⁶/*maai⁵/*zok³/zo² bun² syu¹ bei² go³ hok⁶saang¹
 1SG give/*sell/*send/*throw/*buy/*write/ PFV CL book DAT CL student
 ‘I gave a book to the student’

In Cons A and B, the agent causes the affectee to possess the theme. Affectees can be classified according to the method of causing possession expressed by the verb: inherent caused possession (e.g., GIVE, SELL: **POSSESSIVE-AFFECTEE**); caused possession through caused motion of the theme (e.g., SEND, THROW: **GOAL-AFFECTEE**); or caused possession through the agent’s obtainment or creation of the theme (e.g., BUY, WRITE: **BENEFACTIVE-AFFECTEE**) (cf. Bowers 2010:87ff., Rappaport Hovav & Levin 2008). Con A supports any of these verbs, but Con B accepts only *bei*² ‘give’.

The theme DO precedes the affectee IO in both constructions. Under traditional analyses summarized in Tang 1998 and Lam 2014, Con A is a PREPOSITIONAL DATIVE (or alternatively, a serial verb construction) in which the affectee is introduced by the dative preposition (or coverb) *bei*², while Con B is a typologically rare INVERSE DOUBLE OBJECT CONSTRUCTION in which the IO is bare (cf. Haddican 2010 on Manchester English). In contrast, I adopt Tang’s treatment of both constructions as underlyingly prepositional.

In Narrow Syntax and after Spellout at LF, the preposition *bei*² always exists. At PF, it is pronounced in Con A (hence the new name OVERT-BEI APPLICATIVE), but deleted

in Con B under haplology with the verb *bei*² ‘give’ (hence the new name COVERT-BEI APPLICATIVE).¹ Non-haplogical verbs disallow Con B.

(4) Con C

Old: REGULAR DOUBLE OBJECT CONSTRUCTION S V IO DO
 New: NON-PRIVATIVE BARE APPLICATIVE S V IO DO

我 教/問/考/ 咗 個 學生 啲 好 難 嘅 題目
 ngo⁵ gaau³/ man⁶/ haau²/ zo² go³ hok⁶saang¹ di¹ hou² naan⁴ ge³ tai⁴muk⁶
 1SG teach/ ask/ test/ PFV CL student CL very hard LK question
 ‘I taught/ asked/ the student some very hard questions.’
 ‘I tested the student on some very hard questions.’

(5) Con D

Old: REGULAR DOUBLE OBJECT CONSTRUCTION S V IO DO
 New: PRIVATIVE BARE APPLICATIVE S V IO_j PRO_j.POSS-DO

我 偷/搶/攞/ 咗 [個 學生] 本 書
 ngo⁵ tau¹/ coeng²/ lo²/ zo² [go³ hok⁶saang¹]_j PRO_j bun² syu¹
 1SG steal/ snatch/ take/ PFV [CL student] CL book
 ‘I stole/ snatched/ took/ a book from the student.’

Con D is limited to privative verbs (e.g., STEAL), where the agent dispossesses the SOURCE-AFFECTEE of the theme (hence the new name PRIVATIVE BARE APPLICATIVE). In contrast, Con C is selected by communicative verbs (e.g., TEACH, ASK), where the GOAL-AFFECTEE receives the theme, typically some information or demand, set metaphorically into motion by the agent (hence the new name NON-PRIVATIVE BARE APPLICATIVE).

Previous studies (Tang 1998, Lam 2014) observe the semantic distinction between Cons C and D, but assimilate them syntactically to the same REGULAR DOUBLE OBJECT CONSTRUCTION, in which the bare IO precedes the DO. I argue, however, that they differ in the internal structure of the DO (cf. Huang, Li, & Li 2009, Kuo 2014 on

¹ Prepositional deletion is preferred as linear distance between verbal and prepositional *bei*² decreases, for example, with a phonologically light DO (Tang 1998).

- a. 我 畀 本 書 ^{(?)A}畀/^B畀 個 學生
 ngo⁵ bei² bun² syu¹ ^{(?)A}bei²/^Bbei² go³ hok⁶saang¹
 1SG give CL book DAT CL student
 ‘I give a book to the student.’
- b. 我 畀 [我 尋日 搵 到 嗰 本 書] ^A畀/^B畀 個 學生
 ngo⁵ bei² [ngo⁵ cam⁴jat⁶ wan²dou² go² bun² syu¹] ^Abei²/^Bbei² go³ hok⁶saang¹
 1SG give 1SG yesterday find COMPL DEM CL book DAT CL student
 ‘I give the book that I found yesterday to the student.’

Mandarin). In Con D, the DO must be a possessive nominal PossP whose internal *PRO* possessor is controlled by the IO. In Con C, the DO need not even be a PossP.

2. Root clauses

I now discuss the derivation of each construction in root clauses.

(6) Cons A and B: structure for (1, 2)

In Cons A and B, the arguments are merged in three positions: the theme DO in [Spec,VP]; the affectee IO as the complement of the preposition *bei*² in a PP inside [Spec,AppIP]; and the agent S in [Spec,vP].² Whereas the preposition assigns inherent dative case to the IO, the DO and S are phi-goals whose structural case is valued by Agree with the nearest c-commanding phi-probes in Voi and T, respectively. Cons A and B have a REGULAR Voi hosting both a probe to license accusative case to the DO, and an EPP feature that attracts the DO (as the nearest nominal without inherent case) to [Spec,VoiP].³ Likewise, T licenses nominative case to the S, which then satisfies the EPP of T by raising to [Spec,TP]. The EPP-driven movements of the DO and S combine with the cyclic raising of V to Appl, Voi, v, and Asp, to produce the word order S V DO P IO

² I assume that Cantonese has only one AppIP, per Marantz 1993, and does not distinguish between high and low applicatives, contra Pylkkänen 2008.

³ PARTIALLY DEFECTIVE Voi, found in Cons C and D, has a case probe but no EPP. A nominal-substitute without inherent case, such as the caseless adversative operator (§5), can also satisfy EPP.

(cf. Bowers 2010:22 on the English *to*-dative). After Spellout, the preposition remains at LF in both constructions; at PF, it is pronounced in Con A, but deleted in Con B.

(7) Con C: structure for (4)

(8) Con D: structure for (5)

Cons C and D introduce the arguments in the same specifiers as Cons A and B, but display three differences from the latter. Firstly, both the IO and DO are bare.

Secondly, the IO has already been assigned inherent dative case by the verb. Thirdly, Voi is PARTIALLY DEFECTIVE. It lacks EPP but can still value the structural accusative case of the DO, which remains in [Spec,VP] after Agree, resulting in the word order S V IO DO.

The DO in Con D, unlike in Con C, must be a PossP whose *PRO* possessor is controlled by the bare IO as the nearest c-commanding nominal. An alternative analysis, in which the IO is the complement of a null preposition at LF, is excluded, since the IO could not c-command the DO from inside a PP. (In §5, adversatives provide further evidence for the bare IO in both Cons C and D, since the adversative operator substituting for the IO can be gapped only if bare.)

3. Relativization

In Cantonese, the choice of relativization strategy for a nominal in a root clause obeys the Noun Phrase Accessibility Hierarchy (Keenan & Comrie 1979):

- (9) SUBJECT >> DIRECT OBJECT >> INDIRECT OBJECT >> OBLIQUE >> GENITIVE >> OBJECT OF COMPARISON

The S and DO can be relativized by GAPPING, but any lower-ranked constituent requires RESUMPTION.⁴ Resumption is obligatory for the IO, whether bare or prepositional, because its inherent case is otherwise irrecoverable, unlike the structural case of the S and DO (cf. Broihier 1995, Pesetsky 1998 on Slavic relatives). The head of a Cantonese relative clause is a classifier phrase, which is preceded by the demonstrative *go*² 嗰 (distinct from the classifier *go*³ 個), preceded in turn by the relative clause itself.⁵ I now illustrate and derive the relativization strategies for each construction.

- (10) Con A: relative data

a. DO

[我 畀/寄/ 咗 畀 個 學生] 嗰 [本 書]
 [ngo⁵ bei²/gei³/ zo² ej bei² go³ hok⁶saang¹] go² [bun² syu¹]
 1SG give/send/ PFV DAT CL student DEM CL book
 ‘the book that I gave/sent/ to the student’ gapping

b. IO

[我 畀/寄/ 咗 本 書 畀 *(佢)] 嗰 [個 學生]
 [ngo⁵ bei²/gei³/ zo² bun² syu¹ bei² *(keoi⁵)] go² [go³ hok⁶saang¹]
 1SG give/send/ PFV CL book DAT 3SG DEM CL student
 ‘the student that I gave/sent/ the book to’ resumption

⁴ Resumption is also available for the DO, but gapping is preferred.

⁵ Besides classifier relatives, Cantonese also has *ge*-relatives, in which the head is a NP preceded by the linker *ge*³ 嘅 instead of a demonstrative and classifier (Matthews & Yip 2011). They are not examined here since they pattern with gapping and resumption like classifier relatives.

(11) Con B: relative data

a. DO

[我 畀 咗 畀 個 學生] 嗰 [本 書]
 [ngo⁵ bei² zo² e_j bei² go³ hok⁶saang¹] go² [bun² syu¹]
 1SG give PFV DAT CL student DEM CL book
 ‘the book that I gave to the student’

gapping

b. IO

[我 畀 咗 本 書 畀 *(佢)] 嗰 [個 學生]
 [ngo⁵ bei² zo² bun² syu¹ bei² *(keoi⁵)] go² [go³ hok⁶saang¹]
 1SG give PFV CL book DAT 3SG DEM CL student
 ‘the student that I gave the book to’

resumption

(12) Cons A and B: relative structures

a. DO (10a, 11a)

b. IO (10b, 11b)

In both strategies, the CIP relative head ultimately occupies a [Spec,CP]. The TP relative clause originates as the complement of C, while the CP itself is the complement of Dem. With regard to the head, the relative clause is initially postnominal, but subsequently raises to [Spec, DemP] to become prenominal, perhaps because Dem has an EPP feature that attracts the nearest TP. I have adapted here Yu’s (2006) structure for Cantonese DO relatives (based on Kayne 1994) to IO relatives.

The two strategies derive the head differently (Aoun & Li 2003). In gapping, represented by the DO relative (12a), the head originates by A'-movement of the bare DO

with structural case out of the TP into the sole [Spec,CP]. The IO (12b), however, cannot undergo A'-movement, because of its PP island (banning preposition stranding) and inherent case. Resumption acts as a repair strategy. The resumptive pronoun is base-generated in place of the IO inside the PP. The relative operator Op^R is then introduced in an inner [Spec,CP] and coindexed with the pronoun. Finally, the head is base-generated in an outer [Spec,CP] to bind Op^R , forming a chain that extends to the pronoun.

(13) Con C: relative data

a. DO

[我 問 咗 個 學生] 嗰 [啲 好 難 嘅 題目]
 [ngo⁵ man⁶ zo² go³ hok⁶saang¹ e_j] go² [di¹ hou² naan⁴ ge³ tai⁴muk⁶]
 1SG ask PFV CL student DEM CL very hard LK question
 ‘the very hard questions that I asked the student’ gapping

b. IO

[我 問 咗 *(佢) 啲 好 難 嘅 題目] 嗰 [個 學生]
 [ngo⁵ man⁶ zo² *(keoi⁵_j) di¹ hou² naan⁴ ge³ tai⁴muk⁶] go² [go³ hok⁶saang¹]
 1SG ask PFV 3SG CL very hard LK question DEM CL student
 ‘the student that I asked some very hard questions’ resumption

(14) Con C: relative structures

a. DO (13a)

b. IO (13b)

For Con C, DO and IO relatives are formed as for Cons A and B. Even though the IO is bare and not confined to a PP island, its inherent case still blocks A'-movement.

(15) Con D: relative data

a. DO

(?) [我 偷 咗 [個 學生]] 嗰 [本 書]
 [ngo⁵ tau¹ zo² [go³ hok⁶saang¹]_j PRO_j e_k] go² [bun² syu¹]_k
 1SG steal PFV CL student DEM CL book

‘the book that I stole from the student’

gapping

b. IO

[我 偷 咗 *(佢) 本 書] 嗰 [個 學生]
 [ngo⁵ tau¹ zo² *(keoi⁵_j) PRO_j bun² syu¹] go² [go³ hok⁶saang¹]_j
 1SG steal PFV 3SG CL book DEM CL student

‘the student that I stole a book from’

resumption

(16) Con D: relative structures

a. (?) DO (15a)

b. IO (15b)

For Con D, relativization proceeds as for Con C. The DO relative, however, may be marginal, because the DO CIP, after A'-movement to [Spec,CP], is separated from its *PRO* possessor (cf. Kuo 2014:52n14 for Mandarin). But the IO relative is fully acceptable, since *PRO* and the DO CIP always belong to the same PossP inside the TP.

4. Monotransitive-ditransitive ambitransitivity

With the notable exception of *bei*² ‘give’, almost all verb roots that subcategorize as ditransitives can also serve as monotransitives with the word order S V DO. The DO must be a theme or patient, not an affectee.

(17) Con A root as monotransitive: cf. (1)

我 賣/寄/ 咗 本 書
ngo⁵ maai⁶/ gei³/ zo² bun² syu¹
1SG sell/ send/ PFV CL book
‘I sold/ sent/ a book.’ theme DO

(18) Con C root as monotransitive: cf. (4)

a. 我 頭先 教/問/ 咗 啲 好 難 嘅 題目
ngo⁵ tau⁴sin¹ gaau³/ man⁶/ zo² di¹ hou² naan⁴ ge³ tai⁴muk⁶
1SG just teach/ ask/ PFV CL very hard LK question
‘I just taught/ asked/ some very hard questions.’ theme DO

b. 我 頭先 教/問/ 咗 啲 好 叻 嘅 學生
ngo⁵ tau⁴sin¹ gaau³/ man⁶/ zo² di¹ hou² lek¹ ge³ hok⁶saang¹
1SG just teach/ ask/ PFV CL very clever LK student
‘I just taught/ asked/ some very clever students.’ patient DO

(19) Con D root as monotransitive: cf. (5)

我 偷/擱/ 咗 本 書
ngo⁵ tau¹/ lo²/ zo² bun² syu¹
1SG steal/ take/ PFV CL book
‘I stole/ took/ a book.’ theme DO

The ditransitive theme in Cons A, C, and D corresponds to the monotransitive theme, but the ditransitive affectee in Con C corresponds to the monotransitive patient. Since the monotransitive DO can always be relativized by gapping, it must not have inherent case:

(20) Con C root as monotransitive: relative data

a. Theme DO
[我 頭先 問 咗] 嗰 [啲 好 難 嘅 題目]
[ngo⁵ tau⁴sin¹ man⁶ zo² e_j] go² [di¹ hou² naan⁴ ge³ tai⁴muk⁶]
1SG just ask PFV DEM CL very hard LK question
‘the very hard questions that I just asked’ gapping

b. Patient DO

[我 頭先 問 咗] 嗰 [啲 好 叻 嘅 學生]
 [ngo⁵ tau⁴sin¹ man⁶ zo² e_j] go² [di¹ hou² lek¹ ge³ hok⁶saang¹]
 1SG just ask PFV DEM CL very clever LK student
 ‘the very clever students that I just asked’

gapping

The monotransitive DO merged in [Spec,VP] must be licensed with structural accusative case by Voi. A given root projects the same Voi in monotransitives and transitives. In monotransitives of SELL-type roots, Voi is regular with a case probe and EPP, as in Con A. But in monotransitives of TEACH-type roots (and STEAL-type roots), Voi is partially defective with a case probe but no EPP, as in Con C (and Con D):

(21) Con A root as monotransitive: structure for (17)

(22) Con C root as monotransitive: structure for (18)

5. Adversativization

The Cantonese “long passive” is an adversative construction, in which the matrix verb *bei*² (translated here as ‘get’) selects an experiencer S and a TP with its own agent S (Huang, Li, & Li 2009, Tang 2001).⁶ The matrix S is coindexed, via a null ADVERSATIVE OPERATOR Op^P in the embedded clause’s outer [Spec,TP], with the embedded theme or affectee.⁷ Op^P has two possible origins. Firstly, it can directly replace the embedded argument and undergo A’-movement to outer [Spec,TP] (Op^P-gapping). Secondly, it can be base-generated in outer [Spec,TP] and coindex an embedded resumptive pronoun argument (Op^P-resumption). In Cons A and B, only the theme can be adversativized by Op^P-gapping, while the affectee requires Op^P-resumption. In Con C, both the theme and affectee support Op^P-gapping. In Con D, the affectee permits Op^P-gapping, while the theme completely prohibits adversativization for reasons of binding.

(23) Con A: adversative data

a. Theme

[啲 假 貨] 畀 我 畀/ 寄/ 咗 畀 個 學生]
 [di¹ gaa² fo³]_j bei² Op^P_j ngo⁵ bei²/ gei³/ zo² e_j bei² go³ hok⁶saang¹ e_j]
 CL fake goods get 1SG give/ send/ PFV DAT CL student
 ‘The fake goods got given/ sent/ by me to the student.’ gapping

b. Affectee

[個 學生] 畀 我 畀/ 寄/ 咗 啲 假 貨 畀 *(佢)]
 [go³ hok⁶saang¹]_j bei² Op^P_j ngo⁵ bei²/ gei³/ zo² di¹ gaa² fo³ bei² *(keoi⁵_j)]
 CL student get 1SG give/ send/ PFV CL fake goods DAT 3SG
 ‘The student got given/ sent/ fake goods by me.’ resumption

(24) Con B: adversative data

a. Theme

[啲 假 貨] 畀 我 畀 咗 畀 個 學生]
 [di¹ gaa² fo³]_j bei² Op^P_j ngo⁵ bei² zo² e_j bei² go³ hok⁶saang¹ e_j]
 CL fake goods get 1SG give PFV DAT CL student
 ‘The fake goods got given by me to the student.’ gapping

⁶ The adversative verb *bei*² 畀 is homophonous with and historically derived from *bei*² ‘give’. It is distinct from the etymologically unrelated adversative verb *bei*⁶ 被 (Mandarin *bèi*), which occurs rarely in colloquial Cantonese, and selects either an agentive TP (“long passive”) or an agentless VP complement (“short passive”).

⁷ Adversatives derived from applicatives may be semantically anomalous (marked #), because the themes in particular (e.g., 27a), and sometimes the affectees as well, are not considered to ‘suffer’ sufficiently from the event. (23b, 24b) would sound less natural without the adjective ‘fake’.

b. Affectee

[個 學生] 畀 我 畀 咗 啲 假 貨 畀 *(佢)]
 [go³ hok⁶saang¹]_j bei² Op^P_j ngo⁵ bei² zo² di¹ gaa² fo³ bei² *(keoi⁵_j)]
 CL student get 1SG give PFV CL fake goods DAT 3SG
 ‘The student got given fake goods by me.’ resumption

(25) Cons A and B: structure for theme adversative (23a, 24a)

In the theme adversative, the caseless Op^P replaces the bare DO in embedded [Spec,VP]. Although Voi has a phi-probe, it does not Agree at all, in the absence of any active phi-goal with unvalued structural case. Since Agree is a fallible operation, the derivation continues unproblematically (Preminger 2014:97). The EPP of Voi is satisfied by raising Op^P (as the nearest nominal-substitute without inherent case) to [Spec,VoiP]. Op^P then undergoes A'-movement to outer [Spec,TP], where it is bound by the base-generated S of matrix *bei²*. The matrix S thus coindexes the embedded DO via Op^P.

(26) Cons A and B: structure for affectee adversative (23b, 24b)

The affectee cannot be adversativized by Op^P-gapping, for two reasons. Firstly, Op^P cannot replace the prepositional IO, since prepositions require overt complements in Cantonese. Secondly, even with replacement, A'-movement of Op^P would illicitly strand the preposition. PPs are islands for both nominals and Op^P. Resumption, however, saves the derivation. A resumptive pronoun is base-generated in the IO's position, and coindexed with the Op^P base-generated in outer [Spec,TP]. The base generation of Op^P in affectee adversatives parallels the base generation of the head in IO relatives (12b).

(27) Con C: adversative data

a. Theme

(#) [啲好 難 嘅 題目] 畀 我 問 咗 個 學生]
 [di¹ hou² naan⁴ ge³ tai⁴muk⁶]_j bei² Op^P_j ngo⁵ man⁶ zo² go³ hok⁶saang¹ e_j]
 CL very hard LK question get 1SG ask PFV CL student
 'The very hard questions got asked by me to the student.' gapping

b. Affectee

[個 學生] 畀 我 問 咗 啲好 難 嘅 題目]
 [go³ hok⁶saang¹]_j bei² Op^P_j ngo⁵ man⁶ zo² e_j di¹ hou² naan⁴ ge³ tai⁴muk⁶]
 CL student get 1SG ask PFV CL very hard LK question
 'The student got asked some very hard questions by me.' gapping

(28) Con C: structure for theme adversative (27a)

(29) Con C: structure for affectee adversative (27b)

For Con C, either the theme or affectee can be adversativized by gapping, since, firstly, both arguments are bare, and, secondly, the Op^P replacing them is caseless and thus eligible for A'-movement.⁸ As in root clauses, the embedded Voi is partly defective (with a case probe but no EPP). In the theme adversative (28), when Op^P replaces the DO nominal, Voi does not Agree at all. In the affectee adversative (29), when Op^P replaces the IO nominal, Voi licenses accusative case to the DO nominal.

(30) Con D: adversative data

a. Theme

* [本書] 畀 我 偷 咗 [個 學生]
 [PRO_j bun² syu¹]_k bei² Op^P_k ngo⁵ tau¹ zo² [go³ hok⁶saang¹]_j ek
 CL book get 1SG steal PFV CL student
 Intended: 'The book got stolen by me from the student.' gapping

b. Affectee

[個 學生] 畀 我 偷 咗 本書
 [go³ hok⁶saang¹]_j bei² Op^P_j ngo⁵ tau¹ zo² e_j PRO_j bun² syu¹
 CL student get 1SG steal PFV CL book
 'The student got a book stolen by me.' gapping

(31) Con D: * structure for theme adversative (30a)

⁸ Op^P does not activate the verb's ability to assign inherent case, so it remains caseless.

(32) Con D: structure for affectee adversative (30b)

For Con D, the theme cannot be adversativized. Although Op^P can replace the entire PossP DO and be gapped, the derivation fails because the *PRO* possessor of the matrix PossP S has no licit controller. The affectee, however, is adversativizable by Op^P-gapping as in Con C. In outer [Spec,TP], Op^P still binds the *PRO* in the embedded DO.

6. Conclusion

This paper has offered a new formal analysis of A'-dependencies in four Cantonese applicative constructions. Affectee nominals may be either prepositional (Cons A and B) or bare (Cons C and D), but always have inherent case. Theme nominals are always bare with structural case. PP is an island that prohibits A'-movement for nominals and the adversative operator Op^P. Inherent case also blocks A'-movement for bare nominals, while no such restriction applies to the caseless Op^P. As a result, affectee nominals can be relativized only by resumption, while theme nominals permit gapping. Bare affectees can be adversativized by Op^P-gapping, as can themes in general, while prepositional affectees require Op^P-resumption.

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The AABB-Like Reduplication of Disyllabic Adjectives and the Related Commendatory/Derogatory Senses

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There are many forms of reduplication in Chinese disyllabic words, with AABB being one of the patterns. Shen (1999: 315) proposed the synchronic form-meaning correspondence is not one-to-one, which Chao(1968: 9) defined as skewed relations. In this paper, we purport there underlies a corresponding assessment on AABB-reduplication of adjectives and their related commendatory/derogatory senses. Combined with the view of introspection and instinct, through which most of the previous researchers made their judgments, we adopt perception tests and data analysis to make a further verification in the hope of filling the statistical gap.

0. Introduction

There are many forms of reduplication in Chinese adjectives, with AABB being one of the patterns. Some adjectives can be flexibly stretched into a reduplicated form, like AABB pattern, e.g. “高高兴兴(happy)”, while there are also some adjectives that have no flexibility, such as “可怕(scary)” and “邪恶(evil)”. The criterion of reduplication is controversial, which contains various debates in previous researches.

Among them, some focus on the subjective evaluation (Zhu 1956, Li and Lu 2016), some on the sentimental color (Zhu 1956, Hua 2002a, Li and Lu 2016), some on the positive and negative meaning (Liu 1995), some on the willingness (Hua 2002b, 2003), subjective emotion (Hua 2002b, 2003), pragmatic mentality (Hua 2002b, 2003) and some on the commendatory and derogatory assessment (Hua 2002b, 2003). Some researchers hold that commendatory words are much easier to be reduplicated in AABB pattern compared to the derogatory ones (Cao 2006).

We agree with this point of view, however, there are some methods to be improved in previous studies: a) the examples (Zhu 1956, Liu 1995, Hua 2002a, Hua 2002b, Hua 2003, Li and Lu 2016) were enumerated in favor of the arguments, yet not exhausted and it is hard to generalize a rule based on the insufficient examples; b) the conclusion was drawn through introspective reflection, in other words, the previous researchers made judgments based solely on their own language instinct and experience without statistical support. We thus embark our research addressing the problem with multi-facet viewpoints. Firstly, we set up an assessment on commendatory/derogatory

senses (§2), then provide a perception test (§3), a corpus description (§4), a statistical analysis (§5), and offer our conclusion at the end (§6).

1. On the assessment of commendatory/derogatory senses

Previous scholars held different opinions on the assessment of commendatory/derogatory senses. Tan (1991) disagreed that emotional colors could be divided into two opposite types, and further explained that the connotation of commendatory/derogatory sense was obviously different from the commendatory/derogatory sense itself. Zhang (2000) believed that though the emotional colors were numerous and complicated, they could be concluded into two assessments of commendatory and derogatory, and two attitudes of likes and dislikes. It can be seen that Tan and Zhang both hold the view that commendatory/derogatory senses are terms which exclude the connotation of the words (or speakers' attitudes).

Based on this, Liu (2009) investigated the divisions of the words with commendatory/derogatory senses in previous literature and found out many ambiguities in traditional views. Liu separated connotations from the basic meanings of words and proposed the “five-level” classification, that is, words can be divided into five categories: commendatory words, words with commendatory senses, neutral words, words with derogatory senses and derogatory words. Hua (2002b, 2003) made a similar classification that derogatory sense of adjectives should be divided into “strong derogatory” and “weak derogatory”. It can be seen that these two methods are interlinked to some extent. For example, a word with derogatory sense (J[0b]+P[-b]) is usually a weak derogatory word. That is because the word itself has no derogatory sense, yet practical uses of the word gives it the derogatory connotation at the utterance level rather than linguistic level.

In addition, Lv (2002) proposed the “seven-level” classification, that is, strong commendatory, light commendatory, weak commendatory, neutral, weak derogatory, light derogatory and strong derogatory. However, Lv (2002) himself also realized that it could be tricky to draw a clear line between the seven levels. A too detailed classification method would result in a difficulty of its practical use.

2. Perception tests

Language instinct test (Xue and Duanmu 2018) and emotional assessment test are both perception tests, with the former measuring how flexible a word is to be stretched into the AABB-reduplication form, and the latter assessing how commendatory or derogatory a word is.

The dependent variable Y should have been designed as dichotomy, that is, in language instinct test, 1 stands for flexible and 0 stands for inflexible. In emotional assessment test, 1 stands for commendatory and 0 for derogatory. The statistical result of Y is {0,1}. However, in view of the differences in language instinct and emotional cognition between people, this is not a zero-and-pole question to define the AABB-reduplication flexibility of words and no clear line between commendatory and derogatory senses. Therefore, a five-point scale is designed to evaluate the AABB-

reduplication flexibility of words and the degree of commendatory/derogatory senses, with the purpose of using an interval to represent the concepts that were thought to be dichotomous.

Scoring criteria for language instinct test:

5 points: High reading smoothness and listening smoothness; 100% sure can be reduplicated.

4 points: Relatively high reading smoothness and listening smoothness; 75% sure can be reduplicated.

3 points: Medium reading smoothness and listening smoothness; 50% sure can be reduplicated.

2 points: Relatively low reading smoothness and listening smoothness; 25% sure can be reduplicated.

1 point: Low reading smoothness and listening smoothness; 100% sure cannot be reduplicated.

Scoring criteria for emotional assessment test:

5 points: A commendatory word/ strong commendatory

4 points: A word with commendatory sense/ weak commendatory

3 points: A neutral word

2 points: A word with derogatory sense/ weak derogatory

1 point: A derogatory word/ strong derogatory

3. Corpus description

After screening all the AABB-like adjectives in *The Dictionary of Adjective Usage* (Zheng and Meng 1991) and *The Dictionary of Modern Chinese* (7th edition 2016), we extracted and tested 183 words as lexical samples. 95 Chinese-native speakers were asked to take language instinct test, while 62 were asked to take emotional assessment test. People's language instincts differ. The abundance of data provides a guarantee for the accuracy of the conclusion, which is also consistent with the original intention of our study. By comparison, in the emotional assessment test, the subjects need to decide whether the given words are commendatory or not after reading the related literature, which made data collection relatively difficult. Besides, people's assessments on the commendatory/derogatory senses of words are always consistent. For example, we all agree that “漂漂亮亮(beautiful)” is a commendatory word, while may just disagree on how commendatory it is.

The average score was got from all the data. There were two averages for each word, with one being language instinct score which is used to measure the AABB-reduplication flexibility, and the other being emotional score which is used to measure the degree of commendatory/derogatory senses. Then to link the two scores, CCL (Center for Chinese Linguistics of Peking University) corpus, which provides the entry number of each AABB-like adjective was introduced as a mediator.

First, it should be clarified that there is a correlation between reduplication flexibility and the entry number in CCL Corpus. Figure 1 shows that when a word has a high entry number in the corpus, its language instinct score is relatively high. That is, the word has strong flexibility in AABB-reduplication.

Figure 1. Correlation between the language instinct score and the entry number in CCL Corpus

Then the correlation between the entry number in CCL Corpus and commendatory/derogatory senses could be proved. Table 1 shows the top 30 words with highest entry number in CCL corpus which are arranged in a descending order. Of the 30 emotional scores, 26 are more than or equal to 3 points, with only four less than 3 points. It suggests that, when a word has a high entry number in the corpus, it is more likely to be a commendatory word, a word with commendatory sense or a neutral word.

Table 1. The top 30 words with highest entry number in CCL corpus

<i>AABB</i>	<i>emotional score</i>	<i>entry number in CCL corpus</i>
实实在在	3.951612903	3599
扎扎实实	4.290322581	3199
方方面面	3.048387097	2018
清清楚楚	4.064516129	1921
形形色色	3	1569
干干净净	4.483870968	1387
老老实实	3.693548387	1378
轰轰烈烈	3.596774194	1332
家家户户	3.177419355	1178
风风雨雨	3.016129032	1107
兢兢业业	4.580645161	1101
断断续续	2.403225806	1053

高高兴兴	4.258064516	1026
浩浩荡荡	3.661290323	979
密密麻麻	3	964
普普通通	3.048387097	914
辛辛苦苦	3.629032258	898
沸沸扬扬	2.838709677	895
熙熙攘攘	3.064516129	872
明明白白	3.838709677	850
整整齐齐	4.14516129	782
祖祖辈辈	3.161290323	727
郁郁葱葱	3.887096774	686
匆匆忙忙	2.774193548	676
地地道道	4.532258065	650
认认真真	4.693548387	618
痛痛快快	3.903225806	594
战战兢兢	2.532258065	573
热热闹闹	4.112903226	572

In conclusion, when a word has a high entry number in CCL Corpus, it has strong flexibility in AABB-reduplication, and it is unlikely to be a derogatory word or a word with derogatory sense. The corpus bridges strong reduplication flexibility and non-derogatory sense.

4. Statistical analysis

In this part, we used the same perception tests as in §4, but expanded the vocabulary size. After screening all the disyllabic adjectives in *Modern Chinese Dictionary* (5th edition 2005), we extracted and stretched 2,892 words into AABB-form and tested as lexical samples. Similarly, there were two average scores for each word, one being language instinct score which is used to measure the AABB-reduplication flexibility, the other being emotional score which is used to measure the degree of commendatory/derogatory senses.

4.1 Words with opposite senses

An observation indicated that many adjectives with corresponding commendatory and derogatory senses had a large score gap in the language instinct test, namely a large difference in the flexibility of reduplication. For example, the average scores of “安分 (rule-biding)”, “安静(quiet)” and “安全(safe)” were all 5 points, which referred to “high reading smoothness and listening smoothness; 100% sure can be reduplicated”. By contrast, the average scores of their corresponding derogatory words “淘气(naughty)”, “

吵闹(noisy)” and “危险(dangerous)” were 2.57, 4 and 1. Similarly, for “漂亮(beautiful)” and “丑陋(ugly)”, the former scored 4.33, while the latter scored 2.5. This initial finding was very encouraging, which suggested that the flexibility of an adjective in performing AABB-reduplication is related to its commendatory/derogatory senses and may be more significant than previous anticipation.

Then several pairs of words with opposite (commendatory and derogatory) senses were further selected, such as “大-小(big - small)”, “高大-矮小(tall - small)”, “大方-小气(generous - stingy)”, “宽大-窄小(wide - narrow)” and “浩大-渺小(vast - tiny)”. A series of adjectives derived from “大(big)” and a series of adjectives derived from “小(small)” corresponded one by one, respectively with commendatory sense and derogatory sense. Excel was used to draw a scatter diagram with smooth lines, where the X-axis was the number of adjective pairs with opposite senses; the Y-axis was the average score in language instinct test. One line stood for commendatory words while the other stood for derogatory words, as shown below.

Figure 2. Scatter diagram (with smooth line) of the adjective pairs of “大-小(big - small)”

In a radar graph drawn by the same data, two closed polygons could be obtained with one circle inside and the other outside. The Y-axis is the radius, that is, the closer the scatter to the center, the lower the adjective's language instinct score is; the closer the scatter to the edge, the higher the adjective's language instinct score is. The smaller the area enclosed by the closed polygon, the weaker the reduplication of the series of words is, and vice versa. The two polygons do not intersect, which means the inner polygon is completely surrounded by the outer polygon. It shows that the AABB-reduplication flexibility of each word in commendatory series is stronger than that of the corresponding word in derogatory series.

Figure 3. Radar graph of the adjective pairs of “大-小(big - small)”

In addition to “大-小(big - small)”, similar relationships can also be found in adjective pairs such as “富-贫(rich - poor)”, “雅-俗(elegant - vulgar)”, “明-暗/晦(bright - dark/dim)”, “清-浊/混/污(clean - turbid/mixed/dirty)”, “白-黑(white - black)”, “长-短(long - short)” and “轻-重(light - heavy)”. In “轻-重” series, “轻” can be either commendatory or derogatory, depending on the context. So is “重”. Thus two sets of scatter diagrams and radar graphs can be obtained. Figures are as follows:

Figure 4. Scatter diagram and radar graph of “富-贫(rich - poor)” series

Figure 5. Scatter diagram and radar graph of “雅-俗(elegant - vulgar)” series

Figure 6. Scatter diagram and radar graph of “明-暗/晦(bright - dark/dim)” series

Figure 7. Scatter diagram and radar graph of “清-浊/混/污(clear - turbid/mixed/dirty)” series

Figure 8. Scatter diagram and radar graph of “白-黑(white - black)” series

Figure 9. Scatter diagram and radar graph of “长-短(long - short)” series

Figure 10. Scatter diagram and radar graph of “轻-重(light - heavy)” series

Figure 11. Scatter diagram and radar graph of “重-轻(heavy - light)” series

With the high and low, outer and inner lines, scatter diagrams and radar graphs enable us to “see” the correlation between the AABB-reduplication of adjectives and the related commendatory/derogatory senses, which is, commendatory words are much easier to be reduplicated in AABB-pattern compared with the derogatory ones.

4.2 Regression analysis

In order to exhaustively take all 2,892 adjectives into account, and achieve the quantitative change from enumeration to exhaustion, in this part, function models are introduced to further explore the correlation between AABB-reduplication and commendatory/derogatory senses.

First, the whole range of the score [1,5] was divided into eight intervals: [1,1.5), [1.5,2), [2,2.5), [2.5,3), [3,3.5), [3.5,4), [4,4.5) and [4.5,5]. We use the average of two endpoints of each interval to represent the language instinct score of the interval. Then, whether or not the AABB-like adjectives in each interval were commendatory was evaluated to calculate the proportion of commendatory words, thus eight percentages were obtained (two decimal places are remained). The language instinct score was taken as the independent variable, while the proportion of commendatory words was taken as the dependent variable.

Firstly, the independent and dependent variables were tested in SPSS to see whether they obeyed the normal distribution. Table 2&3 show that variables are normally distributed.

Table 2. Tests of Normality (independent variables)

<i>Tests of Normality (independent variables)</i>						
Point(s)	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
	.105	8	.200*	.975	8	.933

Table 3. Tests of Normality (dependent variables)

<i>Tests of Normality (dependent variables)</i>						
Proportion	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
	.185	8	.200*	.897	8	.269

Then curve estimation was used to find the best fit. Table 4 lists the 4 models with the highest fitting degree, each of which is significant ($P < 0.05$). Figure 12 shows the scatter diagram and the fitting curves.

Table 4. Model Summary and Parameter Estimates

Equation	Model Summary			Parameter Estimates			
	R Square	F	Sig.	Constant	b1	b2	b3
Linear	.851	34.138	.001	.496	.039		
Quadratic	.920	28.603	.002	.583	-.028	.011	
Cubic	.969	41.885	.002	.380	.221	-.080	.010
Exponential	.878	43.173	.001	.507	.063		

Figure 12. SPSS scatter diagram and fitting curves

Although the cubic model fits best, it is not available due to multicollinearity (VIF>10), so is the quadratic model. Only the linear model and the exponential model are valid with all the parameters passing the significance tests.

Table 5. Collinearity Statistics (cubic model)

<i>Collinearity Statistics (cubic model)</i>				
Model	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	4.437	.011		
Point(s)	2.192	.093	.001	726.504
Point(s) ²	-2.209	.092	.000	3427.545
Point(s) ³	2.534	.064	.001	1064.686

Table 6. Collinearity Statistics (quadratic model)

<i>Collinearity Statistics (quadratic model)</i>				
Model	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	12.947	.000		
Point(s)	-.849	.434	.027	37.000
Point(s) ²	2.073	.093	.027	37.000

Table 7. Coefficients (linear model)

<i>Coefficients (linear model)</i>			
	Unstandardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B		
Point(s)	.039	5.843	.001
(Constant)	.496	22.994	.000

Table 8. Coefficients (exponential model)

<i>Coefficients (exponential model)</i>			
	Unstandardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B		
Point(s)	.063	6.571	.001
(Constant)	.507	32.640	.000

With the coefficients above, the linear regression equation is given as (1), while the exponential regression equation given as (2).

$$\hat{Y}_l = 0.496 + 0.039X \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{Y}_e = 0.507e^{0.063X} \quad (2)$$

According to (1), the dependent variable increases by 3.9% for every additional unit of the independent variable. The two equations indicate that, the proportion of commendatory words in adjectives increases with higher reduplication flexibility; the more flexible the reduplication is, the more likely the word is to be commendatory.

4.3 Reverse analysis

The regression analysis model above took language instinct score (reduplication flexibility) as the independent variable, the proportion of commendatory words as the dependent variable. Then, how about swapping the two parameters, that is, taking the proportion of commendatory words as the independent variable while taking language instinct score as the dependent variable. In this part, 2,892 adjectives were divided into two major categories: commendatory and derogatory. The score distribution of each category was analyzed to realize the reverse verification.

First, the whole range of the score [1,5] was still divided into eight intervals: [1,1.5), [1.5, 2), [2, 2.5), [2.5, 3), [3, 3.5), [3.5,4), [4, 4.5), [4.5, 5]. Excel helped us count the number of commendatory/derogatory words in each interval and the total number of commendatory/derogatory words, and then calculate the ratio of the former to the latter. As shown below, we can see from Figure 13 that the proportions of commendatory words and derogatory words in different intervals differ. Figure 14 reflects that, in the interval where language instinct score is high, there are more commendatory words than derogatory words; in the interval where language instinct score is low, there are more derogatory words than commendatory words. Commendatory words are more likely to be in the intervals of high scores, that is, the more commendatory the word is, the more flexible the reduplication is.

Figure 13. Score distribution of commendatory/derogatory words

Figure 14. Score distribution of commendatory/derogatory words

4.4 The boundary of reduplication

If the adjectives with a language instinct score of more than 3 points (that is, the score is in (3, 5]) are evaluated as words with strong AABB-reduplication flexibility, then adjectives that can be reduplicated in AABB pattern account for 17.25% (499/2892) of the total number of adjectives, which is similar to the result (17.3%, 300/1738) of Li (1984) and the result (15.9%, 169/1066) of Zheng and Meng (1991). The statistical result of our study coincides with the results of previous studies.

5. Conclusion

Shen(1999: 315) proposed the synchronic form-meaning correspondence is not one-to-one, which Chao(1968: 9) defined as skewed relations. Lakoff(1980: 128) pointed out that:

- Reduplication applied to noun turns singular to plural or collective.
- Reduplication applied to verb indicates continuation or completion.
- Reduplication applied to adjective indicates intensification or increase.
- Reduplication applied to a word for something small indicates diminution.

When viewed in conjunction with the Pollyanna effect, it is easy to understand why commendatory words are much easier to be reduplicated in AABB pattern compared with the derogatory ones: people are psychologically inclined to favor positive emotions while avoiding negative ones. This preference on a subconscious level is an instinctive human self-preservation.

So far, both from the perspective of introspective deduction (preliminary studies) and the perspective of perception tests and statistical analysis (this study), we can conclude that commendatory words are much easier to be reduplicated in AABB pattern compared with the derogatory ones.

Although we cannot say that all the adjectives with commendatory senses can be reduplicated in AABB form while derogatory ones cannot, we surely have found people's psychological tendency to reduplicate adjectives in AABB form, which makes it possible to predict the trend of language development and change. Besides, the strong derogatory adjectives, which were considered by previous scholars to be never ever can be reduplicated, may also reduplicate themselves in a certain context. Similarly, those commendatory words that can be reduplicated in AABB form, may, over time, evolve into weak derogatory or even strong derogatory adjectives.

Since language is constantly developing and changing, perception test, a dynamic experimental mode, will bring its advantages into full play gradually. Synchronically, the more participants involve, the more data we can acquire. Diachronically, tracking tests can be used to record language changes.

We hold the opinion that in addition to AABB, other forms of reduplication, such as AA, AAB, ABB, A li AB and ABAB, are more or less related to the commendatory/derogatory senses of the words as well, and the relevant conclusions remain to be further investigated.

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Factive Island is not an Island in Mandarin

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This study examines factive island effect in Mandarin. In order to test whether a factive island effect exists at LF, we conducted an acceptability judgment test for a matrix scope interpretation of an embedded *wh*-phrases. Our experimental results show that factive verbs do not create an island in Mandarin. However, the similar effect was not observed in another weak island, *whether* island.

1. Introduction

Since Ross (1967) introduced the phenomenon that *wh*-extraction out of certain syntactic structures is restricted, which is called *island* effects, it has been a main topic of debates among theoretical syntacticians and psycholinguists for many years. One example of islands is that *wh*-extraction out of a sentential complement introduced by factive verbs (1a) is less acceptable than *wh*-extraction from a clause introduced by non-factive verbs (1b).

- (1) a. * Who did Peter whisper that Mary likes ___?
b. Who did Peter think that Mary likes ___?

(Sabel 2002)

This restriction (factive island effect) has been cross-linguistically reported as a type of weak islands. In the previous literature including Haegeman and Ürögdi (2010) and Basse (2008), the ungrammaticality of the extraction has been explained in terms of blocking effect of the intermediate event operator in a Relativized Minimality fashion.

This study challenges to that analysis by showing that matrix interpretation of *wh*-phrases embedded in factive complements is possible in Mandarin Chinese. We argue that the intermediate event operator does not block the extraction at LF and a factive island, therefore, is not an island in Mandarin comparing the empirical data of another weak island (i.e. a *wh*-island).

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. We will overview the relevant grammatical properties in section 2. The details of an experiment examining the effect of factive island will be discussed in section 3. The results will be presented in section 4. Section 5 concludes this paper.

2. Factive islands

Factive predicates (2a) are distinguished from non-factive predicates (2b) in terms of semantic and syntactic distinct properties.

- (2) a. Factive predicate: regret, hate, remember, notice ...
 b. Non-factive predicate: think, say, reckon...

First, the factive predicates presuppose the truth of their complement clause while the non-factive predicates do not. This difference is visible in the case of contradiction. As shown in (3a), the clausal complement of the predicates *she skipped class* is required to be true. Thus, contradiction of the complement clause in (3b) is unsuccessful because the speaker contradicts a proposition which is presupposed to be true.

- (3) a. Mary regrets that she skipped class.
 b. # Mary regrets that she skipped class but she didn't.

(Basse 2008)

This semantic requirement, however, is not required for the non-factive predicates since the truth of the entire sentence is independent from that of the complement clause (Melvold 1991). As in (4b), the speaker can felicitously state that the complement clause *she skipped class* is false.

- (4) a. Mary says that she skipped class.
 b. Mary says that she skipped class but she didn't.

(Basse 2008)

Since the requirement on the factive predicate complement is arguably semantic, one would expect to find the similar in Mandarin Chinese as in (5).

- (5) # *Lisi hen yiban ta buneng chuli Zhe-jian shi,*
 Lisi very regret he cannot handle this-CL matter,

danshi ta neng Chuli.
 but he can handle
 'Lisi regrets that he cannot handle this matter, but he can.'

Adapted from (Tsai 1994)

In addition to the semantic requirement, factive predicates are also distinguished from non-factive predicates by a syntactic behavior, which is *wh*-extraction. As in (1) repeated in (6), the clausal complement of the factive predicate disallows *wh*-extraction while there is no such restriction in the non-factive case. This restriction is called factive island effect.

- (6) a. * Who did Peter whisper that Mary likes ___?
 b. Who did Peter think that Mary likes ___?

(Sabel 2002)

The ungrammaticality of (6a) has been explained in terms of the blocking effect of the event operator. Based on the observation in (7), Haegeman and Ürögdi (2010) argues that factive clause are referential CPs.

- (7) a. I regret [_{DP} the incident].
 b. * I think [_{DP} the incident].

(Basse 2008)

According to them, the referential CPs are derived by event operator movement as in (8). The event operator blocks *wh*-extraction in English, which is called a factive island effect.

- (8) [_{CP} Op_i [_{FunctionalP} t_i [_{TP} V...]]]

- (9) * John regrets that [this book]_i Mary read t_i.

This factive island effect is reported to be weakened or erased when the *wh*-phrase is D-linked (Maling and Zaenen, 1982; Cinque, 1990; Rizzi, 1990; de Swart, 1992; Kiss, 1993; Chung, 1994). It is because the blocker is weak and does not prevent *wh*-extraction of featurally rich category based on Relativized Minimality fashion as in (11).

- (10) a. ?? what did you notice that Mary had fixed ___ ?
 b. Which car did you notice that Mary had fixed ___ ?

(Haegeman and Ürögdi 2010)

- | | | | | |
|------|-----------|--------------|---------|---------------------|
| (11) | Category: | operator | factive | D-linked- <i>wh</i> |
| | Feature: | Q + δ | Q | Q + δ |

Chinese is syntactically different from English. In Chinese, to form of a *wh*-question, an overt *wh*-extraction is not required but it happens covertly (Haung 1982). Then, the following question arises. Will we be able to observe the similar syntactic factive island effect in Mandarin? If the event operator also blocks covert *wh*-extraction, the matrix scope interpretation should be ungrammatical in Mandarin. In order to examine whether there exists the factive island effect at LF, we conducted an experiment.

3. Experiments

3.1 Participants

Thirty-two native speakers of Mandarin participated in the study. Twenty-one participants were female and eleven participants were male. The average age was 32 years.

3.1 Materials

In stimuli, we used two sentence final particles *-ma* (YNQ) and *-ne* (WHQ) which lead to a specific scope reading as in (12). If the event operator blocks a *wh*-movement at LF, the ungrammaticality of (12b) is expected.

- (12) a. *Zhengzhi zhidao Lisi chunban-guo ne-ben-kehuanxiaoshuo ma?*
 know Lisi publish-ASP which-CL-science Q
 Zhengzhi fiction
 ‘Did Zhengzhi know Lisi has published which book?’
 (embedded scope reading of *wh*)
- b. *Zhengzhi zhidao Lisi chunban-guo ne-ben-kehuanxiaoshuo ne?*
 know Lisi publish-ASP which-CL-science Q
 Zhengzhi fiction
 ‘Which science fiction did Zhengzhi know Lisi has published?’
 (matrix scope reading of *wh*)

Due to the lexical ambiguity of *wh*-phrases in Mandarin such as *shui* ‘someone’ or ‘who’, we used D-linked *wh*-phrases that are interpreted as *wh*-phrases in most cases.¹ *Wh*-phrases always occurred at object positions in the embedded clause.

In our experiment, five different matrix verbs as in (13) were tested. In the verb list, we included the verbs creating whether island (13d) and (13e), in order to investigate whether the island effect in Mandarin would happen consistently over weak islands.

- | | | | | |
|---------|-----------------|---------------|-------------|--------------------------|
| (13) a. | <i>yishidao</i> | ‘realize’ | Factive | (factive island) |
| b. | <i>zhidao</i> | ‘know’ | Factive | (factive island) |
| c. | <i>xiangxin</i> | ‘believe’ | Non-factive | |
| d. | <i>wen</i> | ‘ask’ | Non-factive | (<i>whether</i> island) |
| e. | <i>diaocha</i> | ‘investigate’ | Non-factive | (<i>whether</i> island) |

factive verbs from Tsai (1994), Xinliang and Yulin (2017), Pan (2000)

Total 40 target sentences (= 4 sets x 5 verbs x 2 markers) were created.

¹ According to Lee et al. (2018), in Mandarin, *wh*-types (regular *wh*-phrases vs D-linked *wh*-phrases) do not affect *wh*-extraction at LF.

3.2 Procedure

Four lists were created using a Latin square design. In addition to the 40 experimental sentences, there were 126 filler sentences of similar length and complexity. The experiment was run individually for each participant, using online survey platform Qualtrics. Participants were asked to judge the acceptability of the given sentences with a seven-point scale (0: least acceptable, 6 most acceptable) as in Figure 1.

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3. 李木子意识到钱倩倩采访过哪位史学大师呢?

请重新阅读上述问句, 并根据语感对上述问句的接受度作出判断。
0表示完全不接受, 6表示完全接受, 0到6接受程度逐渐提高。

0 完全不接受 1 2 3 4 5 6 完全接受

>>

Survey Powered By Qualtrics

Figure 1. The example screenshot of the experiment.

The experiment took about 20 minutes.

3.3 Analysis and Results

The results are summarized in Figure 2. The results in (3) show that three different types of verbs behave differently. When the matrix verb is a factive verb (*yishidao* ‘realize’ and *zhidao* ‘know’), the *wh*-extraction at LF for the matrix scope reading is permissible. In fact, the matrix scope reading is preferred to an embedded scope reading.

Figure 2. The results of the acceptability judgment task

In addition, the scores of acceptability of matrix scope reading are significantly higher in the factive island verb sentences than in the other island verb sentences (Logistic regression: $p < .001$). The average acceptability score of matrix scope reading of *whether* islands is 3.37 but the average acceptability of matrix reading of factive islands is 4.50. These results suggest that LF movement is not subject to factive islands.

5. Conclusion

In English, factive complements are weak islands for *wh*-extraction, similar to *whether* island as in (14) and (15).

- (14) a. ?? what did you **notice** that Mary had fixed ___ ?
 b. Which car did you **notice** that Mary had fixed ___ ?
 (Haegeman and Ürögdi 2010)
- (15) a. ??/* What do you wonder **whether** John bought ___ ?
 (Miyagawa 2004)
- b. Which problem do you wonder **whether** John will solve ___ ?
 (Haegeman and Ürögdi 2010)

However, we couldn't observe such similarities in Mandarin. Factive islands do not pattern with *whether* islands in Mandarin; D-linked *wh*-extraction is easier in factive islands than in *whether* islands. Thus, blocking effect proposed for English weak islands does not apply to Mandarin phenomena.

(16) [CP Op_i [FunctionalP t_i [TP V...]]]

Our experimental results suggest two possible scenarios. One is that the syntactic event operator blocking *wh*-extraction does not exist in Mandarin. The other is that the syntactic event operator is null at LF. We remain the proof of these scenarios for future studies. In addition, whether LF movement causes different weak island phenomena in other *wh*-in-situ languages needs to be studied.

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Strength in Deontic Modals as Acceptability and Optimality*

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This paper investigates the empirical landscape of deontic modals with particular reference to their strength. I discuss the semantic properties of the expression *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ in Mandarin Chinese, which is often excluded from the discussions on modality. Following recent work by Beddor (2017, “Justification as faultlessness” *Philos. Stud.*, 174:901-926), I argue that *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ illustrates a logical possibility that falls out from the two dimensions on deontic modals: the quantificational force and the relative strength. On one hand, I show that *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ is a possibility modal, contrasting with necessity modals like *bixu* ‘must’; on the other hand, it is distinguished from *keyi* ‘may’ by encoding what is taken to be *optimal* (not just *acceptable*). I suggest that *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ should be recognized as a *strong possibility modal*, mirroring what has been more commonly identified in the discussion of necessity modals: the *weak necessity modal* (e.g. *should/ought to* in English).

1. Introduction

This paper investigates the empirical landscape of deontic modals. In addition to the quantificational force and modal flavor, the notion of modal strength has attracted much attention in both philosophical and linguistic literature (for the former, see Sloman 1970, Wedgwood 2006, Swanson 2008, Yalcin 2016, Beddor 2017, Silk 2019; for the latter, see Kratzer 1991, von Stechow and Iatridou 2008, Lassiter, 2011, 2017, Rubinstein 2012, 2014, 2017, Vander Klok and Hohaus 2020, among many others). With an aim to contributing to the discussion on modal strength, I discuss the semantic properties of the expression *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ in Mandarin Chinese, which is often excluded from the discussions on modality. An example is given below in (1):

- (1) Zhangsan **you-liyou** qu Meiguo.
Zhangsan have-reason go US
‘Zhangsan has reason to go to US.’

* Earlier versions of this work have been presented at NASSLLI (2018, CMU) and IACL 27 (2019, Kobe City University of Foreign Studies). I thank the audience at the above occasions and at NACCL 32 (UConn). Thanks also go to Deniz Rudin for helpful discussions. All remaining errors are mine.

Following recent work by Beddor (2017) and his notion of “faultlessness”, I show that *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ illustrates a logical possibility that falls out from the two dimensions on deontic modals: the quantificational force and their relative strength. In particular, I show that, on one hand, *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ is a possibility modal, contrasting with necessity modals like *bixu* ‘must’; on the other hand, it is distinguished from *keyi* ‘may’ by encoding what is taken to be *optimal* (not just *acceptable*). I suggest that *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ should be recognized as a *strong possibility modal*, a subtype of possibility modal with a different strength, mirroring what has been more commonly identified in the discussion of necessity modals: the *weak necessity modal* (e.g. *should/ought to* in English).

The rest of the paper consists of four sections, organized as follows: §2 overviews the two parameters of modal expressions and points out a missing logical possibility; §3 argues that *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ is a *strong possibility modal* by showing that it is logically independent from other deontic modals and that it displays properties of possibility modal but comes with an additional strength. §4 touches on the distributional properties of *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ and the morphological make-up of modal expression in Mandarin. §5 concludes with remarks.

A few notes are in order. First, I will focus on deontic or teleological readings (or more generally the “prioritizing” reading in Portner’s (2009) terms); other modal flavors will be ignored in the discussion. I leave the extension to epistemic modals to future work. Second, this paper does not aim at a unified account on or a precise formalization on modal strength. For recent works on this topic, see Rubinstein (2012, 2014), Lassiter (2017) Silk (2019) and Vander Klok and Hohaus (2020), among others.

2. Two parameters of modal verbs

A well-received dichotomy of modal expressions concerns their quantificational force: necessity modals involve universal quantification while possibility modals existential quantification. Two properties follow from this dichotomy. First, necessity modals and possibility modals stand in *dual* relations, illustrated in (2) with English *must* and *may*. The Mandarin counterpart is given in (3). The symbol \Leftrightarrow indicates symmetric entailment relations.

(2) You **must** go. \Leftrightarrow It is not the case that you **may** [not go]. $(\forall \Leftrightarrow \neg \exists \neg)$

(3) ni **bixu** qu \Leftrightarrow binfei ni **keyi** bu qu $(\forall \Leftrightarrow \neg \exists \neg)$
 You must go not you may not go
 ‘You must go’ \Leftrightarrow ‘(It is) not that you may not go.’

Second, possibility modals, but not necessity modals, are compatible with conjunction of mutually exclusive propositions. The English examples are taken from von Stechow and Iatridou (2011:31).

- (4) a. You **must** stay, and/but also, you **must** leave. (leave = not stay). [contradictory]
 b. You **may** stay, but also, you **may** leave. [consistent]
- (5) a. ni **bixu** liuxia, ni ye **bixu** likai [contradictory]
 you must stay you also must leave
 ‘You must stay; also, you must leave.’
 b. ni **keyi** liuxia, ni ye **keyi** likai [consistent]
 you may stay, you also may leave.
 ‘You may stay; also, you may leave.’

Another dimension concerns modal strength. Among necessity modals, *must/have to* is regarded as the strong necessity modals, since it asymmetrically entails the weak necessity modals *should/ought to* (examples modified from von Stechow and Iatridou 2008:117). The same contrast is also observed with Mandarin *bixu* ‘must’ and *yinggai* ‘should/ought’. Both (6) and (7) show that the weak modals are compatible with the negation of the strong modals, but not vice versa.

- (6) a. You **ought to** do the dishes but you don’t **have to**.
 b. #You **must** do the dishes but it is not the case that you **ought to**.
- (7) a. ni **yinggai** qu, danshi binfei ni **bixu** qu
 you should go but not you must go
 ‘You should go, but it is not the case that you must go.’
 b. #ni **bixu** qu, danshi binfei ni **yinggai** qu
 you must go but not you should go
 ‘You must go, but it is not the case that you should.’

Additionally, it follows from the asymmetrical entailment relation that the weak necessity modal can be reinforced/strengthened by a follow-up strong necessity modal, but not vice versa (English examples from von Stechow and Iatridou 2008:117).

- (8) a. You **ought to** wash your hands—in fact, you **have to**.
 b. ??You **have to** wash your hands—in fact, you **ought to**.
- (9) a. ni **yinggai** xishou, qishi, ni **bixu**
 you should wash.hand in.fact you must
 ‘You should wash (your) hands. In fact, you must.’
 b. ??ni **bixu** xishou, qishi, ni **yinggai**
 you must wash.hand in.fact you should

‘You must wash (your) hands. In fact, you should.’

Against these backgrounds, Beddor (2017) critically observes that the two parameters (i.e. the force and the strength) entails a logical possibility with regard to possibility modals (depicted in Figure 1). Particularly, it seems legitimate to ask whether there is a possibility modal that displays a different from strength from MAY, i.e. English *may* and Mandarin *keyi*.

Figure 1: A taxonomy of modal expressions (Beddor 2017)

Beddor (2017) proposes that there *is* such modal expression in natural languages and he argues that the English expression *be justified in* is what qualifies as the strong version of possibility modals, mirroring the split in necessity modals. He suggests that this modal expression captures the notion of “faultlessness” which is in contrast to permission and obligation. For the details of this notion in the deontic ontology, I refer interested readers to the original paper. In what follows, I suggest that the Mandarin expression *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ also fit comfortably into this missing box, lending further support to Beddor’s proposal.

3. A strong possibility modal

I suggest that *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ is the strong possibility modal in the sense that it represents a stronger version of possibility modal (i.e. it is logically stronger than *keyi* ‘may’). In §3.1, I first discuss the logical independence of this expression with regard to its “relatives”, especially its relevance to *yinggai* ‘should’ and *keyi* ‘may’. In §3.2, I adopt the diagnostic tests discussed in §2 to show that *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ stands in dual relation with *yinggai* ‘should’ and it displays asymmetrical entailment relation to *keyi* ‘may’.

3.1. Logical independence

To illustrate the truth-conditional differences between *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ and the other three (namely, *bixu* ‘must’, *yinggai* ‘should’, *keyi* ‘may’), let us fix on a discourse context where the interlocuters are discussing transportation means to get to

Paris (i.e. a teleological conversational background). Consider the following schematized sentence in (10), where the blank is supposed to be occupied by one of the four modal expressions. I show that the use of *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ depicts a particular context that is distinct from the rest of the modals.

(10) A schematized sentence

ruguo ni qu Bali, ni _____ zou huoche.
 If you go Paris you _____ take train
 ‘If you go to Paris, you _____ take a train.’

Let us start with the *bixu* ‘must’ and *keyi* ‘may’. For (11) and (12), the corresponding contexts are given in (a), and the target sentences in (b). The context specifies what the speaker knows about the transportation means to Paris.

(11) a. Context: *the speaker knows that trains are the only possible way to go to Paris.*

b. ruguo ni qu Bali, ni **bixu** zou huoche.
 If you go Paris you must take train
 ‘If you go to Paris, you must take a train.’

(12) a. Context: *the speaker knows that trains are one possible way to go to Paris, but there are other options, e.g. planes and ferries.*

b. ruguo ni qu Bali, ni **keyi** zou huoche.
 If you go Paris you may take train
 ‘If you go to Paris, you may take a train.’

In both examples, taking trains is a possible way to achieve the goal of “getting to Paris”, the use of the two modals differs in terms of available options: *bixu* requires trains to be the *unique* means, whereas *keyi* requires trains to be the *non-unique* means.

Let us then turn to the other two modals. While *yinggai* ‘should’ also involves universal quantification like *bixu* ‘must’, but the felicitous use of *yinggai* does *not* require trains to be the only means to go to Paris (i.e. the context in (11a) favors *bixu* over *yinggai*). In this regard, *yinggai* is similar to *keyi* ‘may’. Crucially, what is particular to *yinggai* is that the speaker is adding some implicit assumption/ consideration (i.e. unknown/ not shared by the hearer) to the option of taking trains to Paris (*cf.* von Stechow and Iatridou 2008, Rubinstein 2012 and Silk 2012). For example, the speaker may assume that the hearer wants to go to Paris in a *comfortable* way (or the speaker wants the hearer to do so). In such a case, while taking trains is not the only option to Paris, but it is the only option to go to Paris *in a comfortable way* (at least from the perspective of the speaker). The context in (13a) is so constructed to illustrate this intuition, and (13b) with *yinggai* can be felicitously uttered. The additional (implicit) considerations in (13aii)

and (13aiii) distinguish *yinggai* from *keyi*. Note that it is also because of these considerations that make *yinggai* a necessity modal, as it points to a unique option. But it also sounds less forceful than *bixu* ‘must’, since the additional considerations seem to be more *negotiable* in the discourse (see also Rubinstein 2012).

(13) a. Context:

(i) *the speaker knows that trains are one possible way to go to Paris, but there are other options, e.g. planes and ferries.*

(ii) *the speaker wants the hearer to take a comfortable means to go to Paris.*

(iii) *the speaker also knows that only trains are comfortable, among other options.*

b. ruguo ni qu Bali, ni **yinggai** zou huoche.

If you go Paris you should take train

‘If you go to Paris, you should take a train.’

Lastly, for *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’, it patterns with *keyi* and *yinggai* in terms of having the non-unique options (i.e. it does not require taking trains to be the only way to Paris). I suggest that it also involves some additional assumption/ consideration on a par with *yinggai*, which gives rise to the impression that *you-liyou* sounds somewhat subjective in the discourse. Crucially, *you-liyou* differs from *yinggai* in the sense that with the additional assumptions, there are still non-unique options. Consider now a context minimally different from (13a) in (14a). (14aiii) specifies that there are more than one option to go to Paris in a comfortable way, i.e. trains and planes, hence *you-liyou* sounds weaker than *yinggai*. Note that with the use of *you-liyou*, the speaker sounds more forceful or involved than *keyi*, as it concerns multiple options to a more “specified” goal.

(14) a. Context:

(i) *the speaker knows that trains are one possible way to go to Paris, but there are other options, e.g. planes and ferries.*

(ii) *the speaker wants the hearer to take a comfortable means to go to Paris.*

(iii) *the speaker also knows that trains and planes are both (equally) comfortable, but not, e.g., ferries.*

b. ruguo ni qu Bali, ni **you-liyou** zou huoche.

If you go Paris you have-reason take train

‘If you go to Paris, you have reason to take a train.’

Here, I suggest that the above observations can be re-described with the notions of “acceptability” and “optimality”, following Fintel and Iatridou (2008) and Beddor (2017). Concerning “acceptability”, the dual of *bixu* ‘must’ and *keyi* ‘may’ represents the simpler cases, where they specify contexts where only acceptability is taken into consideration (from the speaker’s perspective). In other words, the proposition associated with the

modal expressions concerns whether the proposition is within the (accessible) worlds that are acceptable. In our cases above, we have assumed a teleological conversational background which is explicitly expressed in the conditional clause (i.e. ‘if you go to Paris...’). Any proposition that fails to achieve this goal is not acceptable. If taking trains to Paris is the only option, then all acceptable worlds are train-taking worlds, giving (11). If taking trains is one of the options, then (at least) some acceptable worlds are train-taking worlds, giving (12).

As for “optimality”, I suggest that both *yinggai* ‘should’ and *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ concern worlds that are not just *acceptable*, but also *optimal* (where the optimal worlds must be acceptable worlds, but not vice versa). The proposition associated with them is thus evaluated according to whether the proposition is within the (accessible) worlds that are optimal. These worlds are not only acceptable (i.e. going to Paris), but are optimal at least from the speaker’s perspective (see also the “best-of-the-best worlds” in von Stechow and Iatridou 2008 or the “Optimality Interpretation” in Beddor 2017). In our examples (13) and (14), those worlds are worlds where one goes to Paris in a comfortable way. As such, *yinggai* and *you-liyou* differ only in whether there is more than one option to achieve this optimality: if no, then one ‘should’ take trains to Paris; if yes, then one ‘has reason’ to do so. Note that this is consistent with the observation that both of them do not require taking trains to be the only option to go to Paris.

The above discussion can be summarized in (15) in terms of accessible worlds, where the four modal expressions are distinguished from each other with regard to quantificational force and strength (i.e. acceptability and optimality). The idea is also visualized in Figure 2, following Beddor (2017). Note that by definition, an optimal world is always an acceptable world, and that the set of all acceptable worlds always include all optimal worlds (roughly represented by the size of circles in Figure 2).

- (15) a. *bixu* p is true iff *all acceptable* worlds in the modal base are p-worlds.
 b. *keyi* p is true iff *some acceptable* worlds in the modal base are p-worlds.
 c. *yinggai* p is true iff *all optimal* worlds in the modal base are p-worlds.
 d. *you-liyou* p is true iff *some optimal* worlds in the modal base are p-worlds.

Figure 2: Logical impendence of the four modal expressions (cf. Beddor 2017)

3.2. Diagnosing the modal force and strength

In this subsection, I apply diagnostic tests for the quantificational force and the relative strength to *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’, the results of which is entirely consistent with the discussion in §3.1. Concerning the quantificational force, first, we see that *you-liyou* stands in dual relation to *yinggai* ‘should’, as illustrated in (16). Note that both sentences can be felicitously uttered in the context in (13a).

- (16) *ni yinggai zuo huoche* \Leftrightarrow *ni mei-you-liyou bu-zuo huoche* ($\forall \Leftrightarrow \neg \exists \neg$)
 you should take train you not-have-reason not-take train
 ‘You should take a train’ \Leftrightarrow ‘You have no reason not to take a train.’

Additionally, *you-liyou* in (17a), but not *yinggai* (17b), is compatible with conjunction of mutually exclusive propositions (assuming that one can take either trains or planes), suggesting its force being existential, instead of universal. Note that (17b) may sound less degraded if the speaker is shifting the contexts for the two conjuncts, rendering a train is a unique option (with respect to some consideration) in the first conjunct and a plane is also a unique option (with respect to some other consideration) in the second conjunct; but no such context shifting is required for (17a).

- (17) a. *ni you-liyou zuo huoche, ni (ye) you-liyou zuo feiji*
 you have-reason take train, you (also) have-reason take plane
 ‘You have reason to take a train. You also have reason to take a plane.’
 b. #*ni yinggai zuo huoche, ni (ye) yinggai zuo feiji*

you should take train, you (also) should take plane
 ‘You should take a train. You should also take a plane.’

As for the relative strength of *you-liyou*, it asymmetrically entails *keyi* ‘may’, hence expressing a (logically) stronger possibility. (18) illustrates this property. In (18a), *keyi* is compatible with the negated form of *you-liyou*; however, in (18b), *you-liyou* is not compatible with the negated form of *keyi*. This follows from the suggestion that *you-liyou* is the stronger form, so negating the weaker form entails the negation of the stronger form, hence infelicity. Note that (18a) is felicitous in the context in (14a), where taking ferries is possible, but it is not “optimal” (for not being comfortable, from the perspective of the speaker).

- (18) a. ni (shi) **keyi** zuo chuan, dan ni mei-**you-liyou** zuo chuan
 you FOC may take ferry, but you not-have-reason take ferry
 ‘You may take a ferry, but you don’t have reason to take a ferry.’
 b. #ni (shi) **you-liyou** zuo huoche, dan ni bu-**keyi** zuo huoche
 you FOC have-reason take train but you not-may take train
 ‘You have reason to take a train, but you may not take a train.’

Lastly, *you-liyou* can be used to reinforce/strength *keyi* with the aid of *shenzhi* ‘if not’. The reverse pattern does not go through, resulting in a sense of inconsistency.

- (19) a. ni **keyi**, shenzhi **you-liyou**, zuo huoche
 you may, if.not have-reason take train
 ‘You may, if not have reason, to take a train.’
 b. #ni **you-liyou**, shenzhi **keyi**, zuo huoche
 you have-reason, if.not may take train
 ‘You have reason, if not may, take a train.’

The results of these tests are consistent with the observations in §3.1. I therefore conclude that the modal expression *you-liyou* is best recognized as *a strong possibility modal*. It mirrors the split in the necessity modals and fills the missing gap entailed by the two parameters (i.e. the force and strength) discussed in §2.

4. A note on the external and internal syntax of *you-liyou*

Before I conclude this paper, I briefly discuss the external and internal syntax of *you-liyou*. As is obvious, the morphological makeup of *you-liyou* is substantially different its relatives: it consists of the possession verbs you ‘have’ and an (abstract) noun *liyou* ‘reason’. In spite of this, two aspects on *you-liyou* suggests that it deserves a modal analysis on its own instead of the one derived from possession verbs.

First, *you-liyou* is distributionally similar to other modal expressions in the sense that it does not impose a selectional requirement on the surface subject (unlike the possession verbs *you*). It thus syntactically functions as a raising predicate, on a par with other modal expressions (independently argued for in Lin and Tang 1995; Huang, Li and Li 2009). (20) gives an example where the surface subject is inanimate and is thematically selected by the embedded predicate instead of *you-liyou*.

- (20) zhe-xie shouji **you-liyou** ran ni tao yaobao
 these cell.phone have-reason let you take.out fanny.pack
 ‘These cell phones have reason to let you pay (for them).’

accessed on Dec 27, 2020: <https://www.cnmo.com/guide/539996.html>

Additionally, it is not uncommon for a synthetic modal expression to have an analytical counterpart. This is at least the case for *bixu* ‘must’ and *keneng* ‘be.possible’ (an epistemic possibility modal), giving *you-xuyao* ‘have-necessity’ and *you-keneng* ‘have-possibility’, respectively. Incidentally, *keyi* and *yinggai* happen to lack an analytical counterpart. In this regard, *you-liyou* is only “special” in the sense that it lacks a synthetic form, but the availability of the synthetic/analytic form for different modal expressions seems to be largely idiosyncratic in Mandarin.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, I have discussed the semantic properties of the expression *you-liyou* ‘have-reason’ and argues that it is best regarded as a *strong possibility modal*, suggesting a split within possibility modals that mirrors the one in the more discussed necessity modals. Following the core idea in Beddor (2017), the empirical landscape for (at least) deontic modals can be represented in Figure 3, where *you-liyou* is filling the missing bottom-right concern.

Figure 3: A taxonomy of modal expressions

Many issues deserve further investigation. For example, existing theories on modal strength build particularly on the distinction between strong and weak necessity

(e.g. von Fintel and Iatridou 2008, Rubinstein 2012, Silk 2019, i.a.). The identification of a strong possibility modal requires that a theory on modal strength should be general enough to apply to modals with varying quantificational force. Also, the precise nature of a strong possibility modal under an epistemic construal remains to be seen. Its relevance to epistemic possibility seems particularly interesting in the growing literature on graded modality (Lassiter 2017, i.a.).

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Focus but not Focus Movement: The Syntax of the Mandarin *Lian...Dou* Construction

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This paper provides a new analysis of the syntax of the Mandarin *lian...dou* construction. Following Fanselow and Lenertová (2011), it is proposed that the movement in the *lian...dou* construction is due to an unselective edge feature in the CP or TP area. This movement is subject to the locality constraint of accentuation that bans the movement of a constituent with structural accent across another constituent with the same type of accent. The advantage of this analysis is that it can explain not only *lian...dou* sentences with DP-focus, but also those with VP- or IP-focus.

1. Mandarin *lian...dou* and its properties

The mandarin *lian...dou* construction is known as the equivalent of the English *even*-construction. The construction uses two words, *lian* and *dou* to express the focus meaning. (1) and (2) are two typical examples with subject-focus and object-focus respectively. *Dou* must precede the verb; the *lian*-marked phrase, which is usually the focus of the sentence, must precede *dou*. This is why (3) is ungrammatical.

(1) Subject-focus

Lian **Yuehan**¹ dou xihuan yuyanxue.
LIAN John DOU like linguistics.
'Even [**John**]_F likes linguistics.'

(2) Object-focus

Lian **yuyanxue** Yuehan dou xihuan².

¹ Boldface indicates that the phrase after *lian* may carry a stress.

² When the focus is on the object, the *lian*-phrase may occur sentence-initially and this paper treats this type of *lian...dou* as the default. The *lian*-phrase may also occur sentence-internally after the subject, but before *dou* as shown in 1.

1. Yuehan lian **yuyanxue** dou xihuan.
John lian linguistics dou like
'John even likes [**linguistics**]_F.'

LIAN linguistics John DOU like
 ‘John even likes [**linguistics**]_F.’

- (3) *John DOU like LIAN **linguistics**.
 **dou* > *lian*-phrase
 Intended meaning: ‘John even likes [**linguistics**]_F.’

In addition to the DP, the *lian...dou* construction can also be used to focus the VP or IP. (4) is an example with VP-focus.

- (4) VP-focus
 (In order to make the girl marry him, he painted a portrait of her, cooked a meal and....)
 Lian **jiezhi** ta dou mai-LE.
 LIAN **ring** he DOU buy-PERF
 ‘He even [**bought the ring**]_F.’

A valid scenario of the utterance of (4) is like this: *In order to make the girl marry him, he painted a portrait of her, cooked a meal and even bought the ring*. In this scenario, the verbal phrase *mai jiezhi* ‘buy the ring’ is the focus. But unlike (1) and (2) where the entire focused DP moves to the front, only a partial element of the focused part, *jiezhi*, gets moved to the front.

The *lian...dou* construction can also focus the entire IP as shown in (5).

- (5) IP-focus
 (The spring is coming. People began to wear light coat. Birds are migrating back to the north...)
 Lian **shu** dou zhang-LE xin ya.
 Lian **tree** DOU grow-PERF new twig
 ‘Even [**The trees grew new twigs**]_F.’

A scenario for this utterance to occur is like this: *The spring is coming. People began to wear light coat; birds migrated back to the north; and even the trees grew new twigs*. Here, the entire IP *shu zhangle xin ya* ‘the trees grew new twigs’ is the focus. But again, only a subpart of the semantic focus, *shu* ‘trees’, is moved to the front.

2. Previous analyses of the syntax of Mandarin *lian...dou*

In previous analyses of the syntax of *lian...dou*, *dou* is treated as a functional head. Shyu (1995) argues that this functional head has a focus feature while Badan and Del Gobo (2015) argue that it is a maximality feature. In both analyses, *lian* forms a constituent with the focused phrase. The combined phrase is attracted by the relevant

feature of *dou* and is moved to the specifier position of the *dou*-phrase. The syntactic diagram of these analyses can be represented in (6)

(6)

The analyses and the proposals of previous studies have been based on data that represent typical *lian...dou* sentences where the focus is on the DP. As a result, these analyses will meet some challenges when data like (4) and (5) with VP and IP as the focus is taken into consideration. The movement of partial focus in these “overlooked” cases is contradictory to the traditional view that in feature-driven movement the entire phrase that bears the relevant feature, in these cases the focus or maximality feature, gets moved.

3. Proposal

In this section, a new analysis of the syntax of *lian...dou* is proposed. This analysis can explain the movement in all types of *lian...dou* sentences, including the type with VP-focus and IP-focus. Specifically, the following questions will be discussed: 1) what triggers the movement in the *lian...dou* construction? 2) What is the landing site of the moved element? 3) Why does movement happen from the perspective of semantics? and 4) What are the functions of *lian* and *dou*?

3.1. Fanselow and Lenertová (2011): Subpart Focus Fronting (SFF)

Fanselow and Lenertová (2011) discuss the Subpart Focus Fronting (SFF) in German and Czech. SFF refers to the phenomenon that a small part of the focus can move to the front. But there is a constraint on this movement: only the left-most accented phrase can be fronted. Let's look at an example in German. In (7) the question “what did he do” evokes an answer with VP-focus. The answer is “he has thrown the gun into the

3.2. Apply Fanselow and Lenertová's (2011) analysis of SFF to Mandarin *lian...dou*

3.2.1. Modifications to Fanselow and Lenertová's architecture of the grammar and SFF

Following Fanselow and Lenertová (2011), I propose that the movement in *lian...dou* is also triggered by an unselective edge feature. However, in their analysis, phrases that carry new information should have structural stress, including phrases that are both [+new] and [+contrastive]. If this were true, then there would be a problem when their analysis is applied to Mandarin *lian...dou*. I will explain this problem shortly. In order to make their analysis work in Mandarin *lian...dou*, we must clarify the notion of focus, separating information focus from contrastive focus as have been suggested by many scholars (Vallduví & Vilkuna 1998, É. Kiss 1998, Neeleman & Vermeulen 2012, Chen & Braun 2006, Greif 2010, among others). This clarification leads to the following assumptions. Information focus receives structural stress and must undergo immediate linearization. Contrastive focus receives contrastive stress and doesn't need to undergo immediate linearization. Since the nature of the focus in the *lian...dou* construction is contrastive and it is a fact that the *lian*-phrase may carry a noticeably higher stress than normal information focus in Chinese, I assume that the stress that manifests in the *lian...dou* construction is contrastive stress and it should be distinguished from the structural stress for the purpose of linearization.

3.2.2. Movement in Mandarin *lian...dou*

Now let's see how this works with *lian...dou* sentences that show contrastive focus on different part of the clause. Keep in mind that the movement all the following cases is due to the unselective edge feature. First, consider cases where the contrastive focus is on the DP as in (10).

(10) Contrastive focus on DP

a. What does he eat?

Lian **Xiangjiaopi** ta dou chi.

LIAN **banana skin** he DOU eat

'He even eats [**banana skins**]_F.'

b. You know what?

Lian **pingguo** Zhangsan dou bu chi.

LIAN **apples** Zhangsan DOU not eat

'Zhangsan doesn't even eat [**apples**]_F

In (10a), since *xiangjiaopi* "Banana skin" carries a contrastive stress, it doesn't need to be linearized immediately at merge. Therefore, it can move cross the subject. In

(10b), the context question makes the subject Zhangsan the new information and it receives structural accent. Therefore, it is linearized immediately. The object *pingguo* “apple” is also new, but since it is contrastive focus, it receives contrastive stress. This means that it doesn’t need to be linearized immediately and can cross the subject. (10b) is actually the case that will have a problem if we follow Fanselow and Lenertová’s (2011) original idea. According to them, both the subject and the object in this case will receive structural stress because they are both discourse-new. This means that moving the object across the subject is not allowed, which is contradictory to the fact.

Now let’s examine the case where the contrastive focus is on the VP as shown in (11), repeated from (4).

(11) Contrastive focus on VP

Lian **jiezhi** ta dou mai-le.
 LIAN **ring** he DOU buy-PERF
 ‘He even [**bought the ring**]_F.’

In (11), the VP is the contrastive focus. The contrastive stress will fall on the rightmost constituent, which is the object. Therefore, the object doesn’t need to undergo immediate linearization and can move across the subject later.

Finally, let’s look at the case with IP-focus as shown in (12), repeated from (5).

(12) Contrastive focus on IP

Lian **shu** dou zhang-LE xin ya.
 LIAN **trees** DOU grow-PERF new twig
 ‘Even [**The trees grew new twigs**]_F.’

In (12), we can see that only the subject is possible to move. This suggests that both the subject and the object are getting structural accents. As a result, moving the object across the subject will destroy the ordering statement established at an earlier stage. Normally, if the whole sentence is the focus evoked by *lian...dou*, the object will receive contrastive stress and then would have been expected to move to the front. Since this doesn’t happen, it must be that focusing the whole IP (focusing everything) is not really focusing anything at all. In fact, this interpretation of “broad focus” constructions that the “broad focus” is not a focus at all has been argued for by many scholars (Bianchi et al. 2013, Katz & Selkirk 2011, Selkirk 2008).

3.3. The movement in Mandarin *lian...dou* from the perspective of semantics

I have shown that the movement in *lian...dou* is due to an unselective feature. Since this feature is unspecified, we still don’t know why movement needs to take place from the perspective of semantics. In the following I will argue that this movement has something to do with mirativity. Mirativity is a grammatical category to express new or

surprising information (Aikhenvald 2004, 2012, DeLancey, 1997, 2001, 2012, among others). I propose that *dou* in the *lian...dou* construction is a mirative marker in Mandarin. To illustrate this, consider example (13).

- (13) Lian **Yuehan** dou zuochu-le zhe-dao shuxueti.
 LIAN **John** DOU solve-PERF this-CL math problem.
 ‘Even [**John**]_F solved this math problem.’

In (13), the mirative meaning is that John solving the problem is less likely than him not solving the problem. In this sentence, the focus is John and the alternative set generated includes {John, Mary, Bill,...}. These alternatives form a scale in terms of their ability to solve math problems. In order for *dou* to give rise to the mirative meaning, John must be positioned toward the lower end of the scale. Only when this is true, can we expect that John solving the problem is less likely. By deriving this mirative meaning, we get the scalar meaning of *lian...dou*. In this case, the scalar meaning is that John is the least likely person in the alternative set to solve this math problem. As for the function of *lian*, it takes scope over the focused constituent so the alternatives are interpretable in semantics. For this reason, *lian* in some way also contributes to the mirative meaning.

Let’s come back to the question: why is movement needed from the perspective of semantics? In other languages, such as French, mirativity is reflected by syntactic movement. This is illustrated in (14).

- (14) Partial focus fronting (object moving in VP-focus)
 Le candidat du patron, ils ont refusé!
 The candidate of-the boss they have.2PL refused
 (You know what happened?) ‘They **refused the boss’s candidate!**’
 (Abeillé et al. 2008: (19a))

In (14), to express a surprise meaning, the speaker moves the object, which is part of the VP-focus, to the front. This is known as mirative fronting. Bianchi and colleagues (2015) have proposed that such movement is actually triggered by a mirativity feature as shown in (15).

- (15) Movement is driven by [mir] (Bianchi et. 2016) :
 [ForceP Force ... [FaiP FAI⁰_[mir] [FocP YPi_[+foc] Foc⁰_[+foc]... [TP ... <YPi > ...]]]]

I propose that in the Mandarin *lian...dou* construction, the movement is not driven by the mirativity feature, but the reason it takes place is to indicate that the sentence carries a mirative meaning.

3.4. The syntax of Mandarin *lian...dou*

The proposed syntactic structure of the *lian...dou* construction is shown in (16). *Dou* is an adverb and also a mirativity marker; it adjoins to *vP*. *Lian* selects an *EdgeP* and it marks the scope of the focused constituent and therefore also contributes to the mirative meaning. The *Edge⁰* head has an unselective edge feature and requires its specifier position to be filled. Moving the focused phrase or part of the focused phrase can satisfy this requirement. Movement takes place to indicate a mirative meaning.

(16)

As for the sentence-internal *lian...dou*, I propose that in addition to the possibility of having an *EdgeP* selected by *lian* in the higher clausal area above *TP*, it is possible to have an *EdgeP* under *TP*, selected by *lian*. The sentence-internal *lian...dou* has a syntactic structure shown in (17).

(17)

4. Conclusion

Previous analyses of the movement of the Mandarin *lian...dou* construction are feature-driven (Shyu 1995, Badan & Del Gobbo 2015). All these studies have focused on common *lian...dou* sentences where the focus is on the DP. These analyses meet challenges when *lian...dou* sentences demonstrate VP- or IP-focus. In this paper, a new analysis of the syntax of the Mandarin *lian...dou* construction is proposed that can accommodate data with DP-, VP-, and IP-focus. Following Fanselow and Lenertová (2011), it is proposed that an unselective edge feature on a functional head either in the CP area or TP area may pick anything within the focus and move it to its specifier position as long as one element with structural stress doesn't cross another element also with structural stress. This requirement on movement is the result of linearization. It is also proposed that *dou* in the *lian...dou* construction is a mirativity marker and it gives rise to a relative surprising meaning. *Lian* marks the scope of the focus and in some way also contributes to the mirative meaning. From the perspective of semantics, it is also shown that Mandarin *lian...dou* syntactically expresses the mirative meaning by moving something within focus to a higher position of the clause.

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The Ergative Marker Revisited in Tangut

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Tangut is SOV language and assumedly used in Western Xia in 11-16 centuries in China. Its logographic writing system in historical literature is the only way allowing us to observe linguistic phenomena. This language has long been considered a nominative-accusative language, while ergative analysis was also raised by Kepping (1979), Guillaume (2014). In this paper, I discuss its case-marking system in this language to clarify this question.

1. Canonical case-markers

The most common way in Tangut to mark both the subject of intransitive and transitive verbs is zero-marking, as shown in (1) ‘Chang Gang’ and (2) ‘king’, and (3) ‘owners’ and (4) ‘West King’.

- (1) □ □-∅ □ □ □
 tsjow¹ ko¹-∅ tjij¹ mji¹ sjj¹
 Chang Gang (NAME) only NEG go
 ‘Only Chang Gang was not going’ (*Leilin* 166-2~3)
- (2) □-∅ □ □
 dzjwi¹-∅ ja tshja¹
 king PREF angry
 ‘The king was angry’ (*Leilin* 324-4)
- (3) □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □-∅ □-∅ □
 jij¹ mjii¹ wji² rjiir² nji¹ dzjwi¹ o¹ nji²-∅ wa¹-∅ sjii¹
 Self home east home neighbor owner.PL pig kill
 ‘A neighbor on the east of my house killed a pig’ (*Leilin* 151-3)
- (4) □ □ □ □-∅ □ □ □ □-∅ □ □
 lji² rjiir² njij² tsəj¹-∅ tja¹ jij¹ gji² tshji¹-∅ wji² dzji¹
 West King TOP self son flesh PREF eat
 ‘West King ate his son’s flesh’ (*Leilin* 178-5)

The object of transitive verbs is sometimes marked by an accusative marker ‘jij¹’ as shown in (5) and (6) or unmarked as shown in (3) ‘pig’ and (4) ‘flesh’.

- (5) □-∅ □-□ □ □
 jwar¹-∅ yu¹-jij¹ dja² ljii²

Yue Wu-ACC PREF attack
 ‘Yue conquered Wu’ (*Leilin* 190-7)

- (6) □-∅ □ □-□ □ □
 ju¹-∅ thu¹ sji²-·jij¹ kjɿ¹ źier¹
 Ghost Tu Xin (NAME)-ACC PREF scold
 ‘Ghost scolded Tu Xin’ (*Leilin* 310-7)¹

Based on the above fact that subject of intransitive verbs and intransitive verbs manifest the same marker, contrasted those on direct objects, Tangut should be considered a nominative-accusative language.

Grammatical relation	case form for nouns
Subject of transitive verb	∅
Subject of intransitive verb	∅
Direct Object	∅ or ‘·jij ¹ ’

2. An ergative marker?

The question centers on an optional ergative marker ‘dźji wji¹’, which often appears in an active transitive sentence. An ergative analysis regards the subject of transitive verbs as marked by ‘dźji wji¹’ (shown in (7) ‘people’ and in (8) ‘king’), and the subject of intransitive verbs and the object of transitive verbs as unmarked or marked by an absolutive marker ‘·jij¹’.

- (7) □ □ □ □ □ □-□ □ □
 kju¹ we² dzjwo² dźji wji¹ tśiow¹ tśhji²-·jij¹ dja² sja¹
 Ju (NAME) city people ERG? Zhao Chi (NAME)-ABS PREF kill
 ‘People in Ju city killed Zhao Chi’ (*Leilin* 237-4)
- (8) □ □ □ □ □ □
 dzjwi¹ dźji wji¹ swē¹ xū¹-·jij¹ rjɿr² śio¹
 king ERG? Song Hong-ABS PREF lead
 ‘The king led Song Hong’ (*Leilin* 326-3)

Grammatical relation	case form for nouns
Subject of transitive verb	dźji wji ¹
Subject of intransitive verb	∅ or ‘·jij ¹ ’
Direct Object	∅ or ‘·jij ¹ ’

¹ We also have other examples that the accusative marker ‘·jij¹’ marks inanimate nominals.

Importantly, this marker does not mark all the transitive sentences. We also notice that this marker can only mark agents of certain verbs, such as ‘to kill’, ‘to lead’, ‘to conquer’, ‘to advise’, ‘to give’. Van Vain & LaPolla (1997) suggests that causative verbs can be distinguished from the non-causative ones by the existence of a causative paraphrase such as ‘cause... to...’, which includes resulting-states. It should be noted that the paraphrased sentence should have the same number of NPs as the original sentence and therefore intransitive verbs with only one argument, are ruled out. The verbs mentioned above can all be paraphrased and entails results. For instance, ‘to kill’ is ‘to cause...to die’, and ‘to give’ is ‘to cause...to have’, ‘to lead’ is ‘to cause...to be in a place’.

In addition, only the causer in a causative sentence (10) and the agent of a theme-fronting sentence (theme-agent-verb)² (9) can be marked by ‘dźji wji¹’.

(9) □ □ □-∅ □ □ □ □ □ □
 :jj¹ wə¹ gji²-∅ lju² tshjiw¹ dźji wji¹ dja² sja¹
 REFL husband Lu Chao(NAME) ? PREF kill
 ‘(Her) husband was killed by Lu Chao’ (*Leilin* 388-2)

(10) □ □ □ □ □-□ □ □ □
 dzjwɪ¹ dźji wji¹ ljow¹ kji¹-’jj¹ dja² sja¹ phji¹
 king ? Liang Ji(NAME)-ACC PREF kill CAUS
 ‘The king asked (someone) to kill Liang Ji’ (*Leilin* 166-6)

The syntactic properties of the theme-fronting construction remain unclear with regard to its relationship to the passive sentence, but it seems that Tangut has relatively fixed word order. This fact allows us to suspect that the subject should always precede the object so as not to create confusion when both of them are with zero-case marking. In this case, if an ergative marker is to be added, it is the subject (a theme) in a theme-fronting sentence that should be marked by ‘dźji wji¹’, which is not true here. Besides, we also found that the agent in theme-fronting sentences are all with causative verbs listed above, which demonstrates that ‘dźji wji¹’ is likely to be a causer marker³.

In addition, no example shows the subject of unergative verbs (often an agent) is marked by this marker, nor does this marker mark an experiencer, the subject of ‘to see’, ‘to hear’. The subject of unaccusative, hence a theme, can never be followed by this marker, such as in the verb ‘to die’. These facts suggest that ‘dźji wji¹’ is neither an agent marker nor a nominative marker.

² The theme-fronting sentence is usually used to stress affectedness of themes, and often translated as passive sentences in the Chinese translation.

³ If the verb is not a causative verb, other strategies to stress the affectedness of themes i.e. to form the passives are used. For instance, adding an experience verb ‘encounter’ or use the active form.

Moreover, once the verb includes no obvious causative meaning but ‘dźji wji¹’ appears (e.g. with intransitive verbs, activity verbs), a causative verb ‘phji¹’ or ‘wji¹’ will follow the verb, as shown in (11) and (12). This is another piece of evidence that the marker could be a causer marker.

(11) □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □
 dzjij¹ dzjwo² dźji wji¹ kiow² ljow² bji¹ wji² jar¹ phji¹
 time people ? river .side tablet PREF stand CAUS
 ‘People at that time established a tablet on the river side. (*Leilin* 415-4)

(12) □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □
 swē¹ khjow² dźji wji¹ dji² lhjwi¹ wji¹
 Song-Kang (NAME) ? PREF take CAUS/APPL
 ‘(Hang-Ping’s wife) was taken away by Song-Kang’ (*Leilin* 323-4)

Because causation requires two events with causal relationship, ‘dźji wji¹’ also appears in sentences with instrumental marker ‘ηwu²’ as shown in (13).

(13) □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □
 wja¹ mja¹ dźji wji¹ lhji² ηwu² tśjow¹ ljaa² ljjj² ji¹
 father mother ? fear-INSTR Zhang Liao (NAME) come say
 ‘(His) Father and mother threatened him by saying Zhang Liao came’ (*Leilin* 528-3)

A resultative complement such as ‘ηa²’ (good) can also follow the verb to add a resulting state in order to cooccur with ‘dźji wji¹’ in (14).

(14) □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □
 tshew¹ šji¹ dźji wji¹ gjjj² kji¹ ŷjir¹ zji² kha¹ ηa² lji¹
 Cao-zhi(NAME) ? poem PREF do most good COP
 ‘Cao-zhi was the best at writing poems’ (*Leilin* 306-1~2)

A supporting evidence is that ‘dźji wji¹’ marks either inanimate force or causing events. The below examples show an inanimate ‘the smelly thing’ in (15) and a causing event ‘the fire’ in (16) precede ‘dźji wji¹’. If this marker is an agent marker, inanimate nouns cannot be marked.

(15) □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □
 thji² tja¹ war² sjjj² dźji wji¹ nioow¹ lji¹
 This TOP thing smelly ? because COP
 ‘This is what this smelly thing did/ This is due to this smelly thing.’ (*Leilin* 339-1)

(16) □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □

məə¹ dʒji wji¹ ŋa² wə¹ kji¹ pju² ŋwu² dja² sji²
 fire ? I husband PREF burn INSTR PREF die
 ‘My husband was burned by the fire and died’ (*Leilin* 243-5)
 Lit. ‘Fire burned my husband to death’

When an affectee appears on the subject position, it can never be marked by ‘dʒji wji¹’ as shown in (17). This further confirms our proposal that ‘dʒji wji¹’ is to mark a causer.

- (17) □ □ □ □-∅ □ □ □
 mji¹ ji¹ wə¹ gji²-∅ dja² ljwij¹ wji¹
 newly husband PREF die CAUS/APPL
 ‘(Wenjun) was affected by his husband’s death’ (*Leilin* 467-4~5)

3. Examples from Kepping (1985) and Guillaume (2014)

Previous researchers have raised several intransitive examples to show that ‘jij¹’ can be seen as an absolutive marker, in favor of ergative analysis. However, as we will examine below, this marker can simply be regarded as other markers.

- (18) □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □
 nji² jij¹ sow¹ sji¹ sju¹ khju¹ dʒjiij¹ tji¹ ja tsjwu¹ wji² thji¹ phji¹ ŋa² ji¹
 you-POSS mulberry under live one-bottle PREF-drink CAUS-I COMP
 “You can let me stay under your mulberry tree and have a meal” (*Leilin* 318-4)

- (19) □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □
 məə¹ lha¹ nioow¹ tej¹ tshew¹ jij¹ dja² sji² ji¹ kjj² wji² tshiew¹ wji¹
 fire-stop-after Dai-Jiu-ACC PREF-die-say room-PREF-destroy-CAUS
 ‘After the fire stopped, (someone) said Dai-Jiu was dead and destroy the room (to look at it)’ (*Leilin* 267-6)

In (18), ‘jij¹’ can simply be a possessive marker and means ‘your mulberry tree’. If this ‘jij¹’ were an absolutive marker and to marker the subject of intransitive verb ‘to live’, this would be an anomaly in *Leilin*--most examples in *Leilin* with this verb ‘dʒjiij¹’ do not mark the subject with ‘jij¹’. In (19), the ‘jij¹’ is argued to mark the subject of the intransitive verb ‘to die’. In addition to the rareness of marking the subject of ‘to die’ with ‘jij¹’, another reason for rejecting this proposal is that the verb ‘to say, to regard’ appears in the clause. This probably suggests a covert subject ‘someone’ is there and that person regards *Daijiu* as dead and then destroys the room to confirm. If *Daijiu* were the subject of this sentence, *Daijiu* has to be the subject to destroy the room, since the subject in the following sentence should follow the previous clause. This does not make any sense. Therefore, the sentences raised in previous literature has raised do not support the ergative analysis and even yield unreasonable interpretation with the ergative analysis.

4. Conclusion

To conclude, Tangut still should be seen as a nominative-accusative language, with the same zero-marking on subjects of transitive verbs and intransitive verbs. The object of transitive verbs is unmarked or followed by an accusative marker ‘‘jjj’’. A non-canonical marker ‘‘đzji wji’’ should be regarded as a causer marker due to its identifying function, rather than an ergative marker suggested in previous literature.

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Unaccusative and Unergative Verbs in Child Mandarin Chinese

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The provocative claim made by the A-Chain Deficit Hypothesis (Borer & Wexler, 1992) is that children should have difficulty with unaccusative verbs, since they involve A-movement of the internal argument to subject position, suggesting unaccusative and unergative verbs are treated the same by children. We test whether Mandarin Chinese children distinguish unaccusative and unergative verbs, using two diagnostics for unaccusativity: subject-placement and aspect. Our results reveal both diagnostics show evidence for children treating these verb classes as distinct.

Babyonyshev et al. (1998; 2001) famously claimed that Russian children struggle with unaccusative (but not unergative) verbs, although the evidence for children exhibiting unaccusativity is increasing (Becker et al. 2013 etc.). In Mandarin Chinese, Liu & Ning (2009) showed that A-movement within the VP layer is acquired earlier than other A-movements, but they did not examine whether children are able to distinguish unaccusative and unergative verbs.

We use two tests for unaccusativity in Mandarin (Huang 1991, Pan, 1996, a.o.):

- (1) Displacement: unaccusative verbs allow subjects to occur postverbally (as well as preverbally), while unergative verbs only allow preverbal subjects.
- (2) Aspect: Both unaccusative and unergative verbs allow the perfective marker, but the former does not allow the durative aspect marker, while the latter does.

Method. We tested 40 children aged 3yrs-7yrs (along with adult native controls) using a forced-choice selection task, where participants saw a series of pictures depicting an action and then heard two sentences from puppets to describe the scene. Their task was to choose the puppet who said it the best. We crossed verb type (unaccusative/unergative) with the position of subject (preverbal/postverbal) and aspect (durative/perfective) such that children heard a pair of sentences with the same verb, but they differed either by position of the subject or aspect.

Results. There exists an overall preference for preverbal subjects for both verb types (table 1), and a statistically significant difference between verb classes (Chi-square=4.9351, $p=0.026316$). For aspect, with statistically significant difference, (Chi-square=11.3377, $p=0.000759$), unergative verbs allowed both aspect markers freely, while unaccusative verbs strongly patterned with perfective aspect. The result suggests that, like adults, children can distinguish two types of intransitive verbs using these tests.

We further breakdown the result by age groups. In all the age groups, children show statistically significant difference for the aspect marker test between, while for the displacement test, the statistically significant difference does not occur until age 6-7 (p -value for the three groups= 0.2607, 1, 0.009522<0.05, respectively), although core accusative verbs, following to Sorace (2000)'s subcategorization ('to come' and 'to drop'), reach this difference in as early as in age 3-5. We interpret these results to indicate that the telicity of intransitive verbs is acquired early

in child development, but the A-movement of non-core unaccusative verbs is delayed.

Table 1	perfective	durative		pre-verbal	post-verbal
Unergative	74	67	Unergative	113	31
Unaccusative	104	38	Unaccusative	94	47

The Peripheral Applicative *Gei* in Mandarin Chinese*

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This paper proposes the existence of a peripheral applicative *gei* in Mandarin Chinese. In addition to the high and low applicative in Pykkänen's (2002, 2008) applicative framework, Tsai (2012, 2015b, and 2017) proposes that there is another kind of speaker-oriented applicative projection which is located in the CP domain. However, after examining Tsai's data carefully, I suggest that there is yet another peripheral applicative projection around vP , a proposal supported by the unique properties of the applicative projection itself and its co-occurrence with other applicative projections. This further delineation of applicative projections across syntactic domains in Mandarin Chinese can enrich our wider understanding of applicatives.

1. Introduction

In Pykkänen (2002, 2008), there are two main applicative projections which can introduce extra arguments: the high applicative projection and the low applicative projection. The high applicative projection is proposed to be located right above VP, and denotes a relationship between the high applied NP and the whole VP, as shown in (1). A typical example is shown in (2). In this example, the old woman is an addition NP relative to the VP and is interpreted as an affectee/benefactive.

(1) High Applicative Projection [ApplHP]

[vP [_{ApplHP} NP_{BENEFACTIVE} [_{ApplH'} ApplH [vP V NP_{THEME}]]]]

(2) Venda

Nd-o-tandulela **tshimu** ya mukegulu.

1SG-PAST-survey old.woman the field

'I surveyed the field for the old woman.'

(Pykkänen 2008: 19)

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In contrast, the low applicative in (3) is proposed to be in the complement position of the main verb and denotes a possessor-possessee relationship with the object, as shown in (4). In this example, it is Taro who writes a letter, and Hanako is interpreted as a recipient of the letter.

(3) Low Applicative Projection [ApplLP]
 [VP V [ApplLP NP_{SOURCE/RECIPIENT} [ApplL' ApplL NP_{THEME}]]]

(4) Japanese
 Taro-ga **Hanako-ni** tegami-o kaita.
 Taro-NOM Hanako-DAT letter-ACC wrote
 'Taro wrote Hanako a letter.'

In this paper, I would like to examine other potential applicative projections in Mandarin Chinese. In Section 2, I first review an applicative projection in the CP domain in Mandarin Chinese proposed by Tsai (2009, 2012, 2015b, and 2017). In Section 3, I present some further examples from Tsai that seem to require an additional new applicative projection distinct from his CP applicative projection. In Section 4, I propose a peripheral applicative projection around *v*P and discusses its relevant structure. I conclude the paper in the last section.

2. A very high applicative

In Mandarin Chinese, the applicative proposal of Pylkkänen (2002, 2008) has been applied to several constructions as well (i.e. Huang 2007, 2008; Paul and Whitman 2010; Tsai 2012, 2015b, 2017, among others). For example, Huang (2007, 2008) examines the following sentence in (5), also known as pseudo-double object construction, and proposes that Lisi is a high applied NP.

(5) Zhangsan he-le Lisi san-ping jiu.
 Zhangsan drink-ASP Lisi three-CL wine
 'Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on Lisi.'

In sentence (5), it is Zhangsan who drinks the wine, but Lisi is interpreted as the affectee of the wine-drinking event.

Later, Tsai (2009, 2012, 2015b, and 2017) observes another construction that also involves an applied NP, as shown in (6).

(6) Zhangsan juran [gei wo] he-le san-ping jiu!
 Zhangsan unexpectedly GEI me drink-ASP three-CL wine
 'Unexpectedly, Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on me!'

In sentence (6), as in (5), Zhangsan drinks the wine, and someone else is affected by the drinking event – in this case, the speaker.

Although there are superficial similarities between sentences (5) and (6), Tsai points out that the applied NPs in the respective sentences differ in a few ways. First, in sentence (5), the applied NP cannot be introduced by the applicative marker GEI, as shown in (7); whereas, in (6), it must be, as shown in (8).

- (7) Zhangsan he-le (*gei) Lisi san-ping jiu.
 Zhangsan drink-ASP GEI Lisi three-CL wine
 ‘Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on Lisi.’

- (8) Zhangsan juran *(gei) wo he-le san-ping jiu!
 Zhangsan unexpectedly GEI me drink-ASP three-CL wine
 ‘Unexpectedly, Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on me!’

Second, there is a possession difference between the two sentences. In sentence (6), the bottles of wine Zhangsan drinks can belong to anyone; whereas, in sentence (5), the wine has to belong to Lisi.

Finally, the applied NP in sentence (5) can be replaced by any personal pronoun, and it can be singular or plural, as shown in (9); whereas there is a person restriction in sentence (6), and the applied NP has to be a first-person singular, as shown in (10).

- (9) a. Zhangsan he-le wo/women san-ping jiu.
 Zhangsan drink-ASP me/us three-CL wine
 ‘Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on me/us.’
 b. Zhangsan he-le ni/nimen san-ping jiu.
 Zhangsan drink-ASP you/you(pl.) three-CL wine
 ‘Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on you.’
 c. Zhangsan he-le ta/tamen san-ping jiu.
 Zhangsan drink-ASP him/them three-CL wine
 ‘Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on him/them.’

- (10) a. *Zhangsan juran [gei women] he-le san-ping jiu!
 Zhangsan unexpectedly GEI us drink-ASP three-CL wine
 ‘Unexpectedly, Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on us!’
 b. *Zhangsan juran [gei ni/nimen] he-le san-ping jiu!
 Zhangsan unexpectedly GEI you/you(pl.) drink-ASP three-CL wine
 ‘Unexpectedly, Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on you!’
 c. *Zhangsan juran [gei ta/tamen] he-le san-ping jiu!
 Zhangsan unexpectedly GEI him/them drink-ASP three-CL wine
 ‘Unexpectedly, Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on him/them!’

Based on these contrasts, Tsai concludes that the two applied NPs in sentences (5) and (6) are distinct and should be located in different positions. Tsai (2007, 2008, 2011) (cf. Huang 2007, 2008) has proposed that the pseudo-double object construction in sentence (5) should involve a high applicative projection. The sentence and its structure are shown in (11).

In structure (11), following Pylkkänen (2002, 2008), there is a high applicative projection right above VP, and the applied NP *Lisi* is base-generated at Spec, ApplHP. The main verb undergoes head movement from V to *v*, following Chomsky (1995) and Huang et al. (2009).

As for sentence (6), Tsai notes the following two observations to support the argument that there should be a very high applicative projection located in the CP domain that hosts the applied NP. First, it has been observed that the applied NP in sentence (6) has to be licensed by a special kind of illocutionary force – hence, the presence of the evaluative adverb *juran* ‘unexpectedly’ is required, as shown in (12). However, this evaluative adverb is simply optional for sentence (5), as shown in (13).

- (12)
- | | | | | | |
|----|---|--------------|-----------|-----------|---------------|
| a. | Zhangsan | juran | [gei wo] | he-le | san-ping jiu! |
| | Zhangsan | unexpectedly | GEI me | drink-ASP | three-CLwine |
| | ‘Unexpectedly, Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on me!’ | | | | |
| b. | *Zhangsan | [gei wo] | he-le | san-ping | jiu. |
| | Zhangsan | GEI me | drink-ASP | three-CL | wine |
| | ‘Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on me!’ | | | | |

- (13) a. Zhangsan juran he-le Lisi san-ping jiu!
 Zhangsan unexpectedly drink-ASP Lisi three-CL wine
 ‘Unexpectedly, Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on Lisi.’
 b. Zhangsan he-le Lisi san-ping jiu.
 Zhangsan drink-ASP Lisi three-CL wine
 ‘Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on Lisi.’

Second, the fact that only a first-person singular pronoun is allowed in sentence (6), as shown previously in the contrast between (9) and (10), indicates that the applied NP is strictly speaker-oriented. Putting these two observations together and adopting a split-CP approach by Rizzi (1997) and Cinque (1999), Tsai proposes the structure in (14).

In this structure, the very high applicative projection is proposed to be right above TP, and the obligatory GEI is the applicative head. The applied NP is base-generated at the Spec, ApplP position. To derive the correct word order, the applicative head *gei* has to undergo head movement to the head position of the EvaP, and the subject NP has to undergo topicalization to Spec, TopP.

To summarize, in this section, we have presented Tsai's rationale and structure for a very high applicative projection in the CP domain that can be distinguished from the high applicative projection in the pseudo-double object construction first observed by Huang (2007, 2008).

3. Another *gei wo* phrase

In this section, analysis of additional applicative examples from Tsai (2012) suggest that another relatively high applicative projection may need to be posited distinct from his very high applicative projection in the CP domain.

Recall that the very high applicative projection in the CP domain is speaker-oriented and needs to be licensed by an evaluative adverb. Tsai (2012) notes, however, that it is also possible for reversal adverbs like *que* ('however') in (15) and *wh*-adverbs like *zenme* ('how.come') in (16) to serve as licensers.

- (15) Wo jiao ta mai jiu,
 I ask him buy wine
 ta que [gei wo] mai-le yan!
 he however GEI me buy-ASP cigarette
 'I asked him to buy wine. He, however, bought cigarettes on me!'

- (16) Wo jiao ta mai jiu,
 I ask him buy wine
 ta zenme [gei wo] mai-le yan?!
 he how.come GEI me buy-ASP cigarette
 'I asked him to buy wine. How come he bought cigarettes on me?!'

Further, he proposes that an imperative or negative mood can also license the very high affective construals, as shown in (17) and (18), respectively.

- (17) Ni [gei wo] gui-xia!
 you GEI me kneel-down
 'Kneel down for my sake!'
- (18) Zhangsan cong mei [gei wo] diu-guo lian!
 Zhangsan ever not GEI me lose-ASP face
 'Zhangsan has never lost face on me!'

Although the combination of GEI and *wo* ('me') appears in sentences (15) through (18), I would suggest that the *gei wo* phrase in (17) is different from the others and requires further scrutiny.

The *gei wo* phrase in (17) appears at first glance to exhibit similar behavior to the *gei wo* phrase in (6). It is also speaker-oriented and can only be first-person singular, as shown in (19).

- (19) a. *Ni [gei women] gui-xia!
 you GEI us kneel-down
 ‘Kneel down for our sake!’
 b. *Ni [gei ni/nimen] gui-xia!
 you GEI you kneel-down
 ‘Kneel down for your sake!’
 c. *Ni [gei ta/tamen] gui-xia!
 you GEI him/them kneel-down
 ‘Kneel down for his/their sake!’

However, sentence (17) in fact exhibits at least three differences from the other *gei-wo* sentences. First, the *gei wo* phrase in (17) is translated differently than the *gei wo* phrases in (6), (15), (16) and (18). To be more specific, in (17) it is interpreted as a beneficiary; whereas, in the other sentences, it is interpreted as a malificiary.

Second, there is a telicity difference in the event expressed by (17) and the other sentences. Specifically, the event in sentence (17) has not yet been realized and is therefore interpreted as an atelic situation; whereas, the events in the other sentences have been carried out and are interpreted as telic situations.

Finally, if the evaluative adverb *juran* ‘expectedly’ is inserted in sentence (17), the sentence becomes ungrammatical, as shown in (20). In contrast, in sentence (6), repeated here as (21), *juran* is required.

- (20) *Ni **juran** [gei wo] gui-xia!
 you unexpectedly GEI me kneel-down
 ‘Unexpectedly, kneel down for my sake!’
 (21) Zhangsan **juran** [gei wo] he-le san-ping jiu!
 Zhangsan unexpectedly GEI me drink-ASP three-CLwine
 ‘Unexpectedly, Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on me!’

Importantly, insertion of this evaluative adverb is also grammatical in sentences (15), (16) and (18), as shown in (22) through (24), respectively.

- (22) Wo jiao ta mai jiu,
 I ask him buy wine
 ta que **juran** [gei wo] mai-le yan!
 he however unexpectedly GEI me buy-ASP cigarette

‘I asked him to buy wine. Unexpectedly, he, however, bought cigarettes on me!’

- (23) Wo jiao ta mai jiu,
 I ask him buy wine
 ta zenme **juran** [gei wo] mai-le yan?!
 he how.come unexpectedly GEI me buy-ASP cigarette
 ‘I asked him to buy wine. Unexpectedly, how come he bought cigarettes on me?!’

- (24) Zhangsan **juran** cong mei [gei wo] diu-guo lian!
 Zhangsan unexpectedly ever not GEI me lose-ASP face
 ‘Unexpectedly, Zhangsan has never lost face on me!’

From the above comparisons, we can conclude that the *gei wo* phrase in (17) should be differentiated from the one proposed by Tsai (2012, 2015b and 2017) and that an additional applicative projection may be required to account for the data.

4. The periphery GEI

In this section, I would like to further explore the *gei wo* phrase in sentence (17) and propose a possible structure.

There is evidence that suggests the subject *ni* (‘you’) in sentence (17) is indeed in the standard subject position of Spec, TP. For example, Lin & Tang (1995) propose that a true subject in Chinese can move to the matrix subject position with the raising modal *yinggai* (‘should’), as illustrated in (25).

- (25) Ni yinggai gei wo gui-xia!
 you should GEI me kneel-down
 ‘You should kneel-down for my sake!’

In addition, Li (1990) has argued that the Chinese ECM verb *yao* (‘want’) takes a TP as its complement. As shown in (26), sentence (17) can become the complement taken by the ECM verb *yao* (‘want’), indicating that the subject *ni* (‘you’) is in the Spec, TP position.

- (26) Wo yao ni gei wo gui-xia!
 I want you GEI me kneel-down
 ‘I want you to kneel-down for my sake!’

Based on the above, it can be inferred that the *gei wo* phrase in (17) should be lower than Spec, TP, and evidence from the *Ba* construction in example (27) shows that it should be higher than Spec, *vP*.

- (27) Ni *gei wo* *ba* *fan* *chi-wan!*
 you GEI me BA rice eat-finish
 ‘Finish eating the rice for my sake!’

In the literature, the projection which hosts *ba* has been proposed to be located right above *vP* (i.e. Li 2006), indicating that the *gei wo* phrase in (27) has to be located in the TP domain.

Following Kim (2011, 2012), who proposes a peripheral applicative projection right above *vP*, I propose a structure for the *gei wo* phrase in (17), as illustrated in (28).

In this structure, there is a peripheral applicative projection right above *vP*, and the applied NP *wo* is base-generated at Spec, Peripheral Applicative Projection. The applicative head *gei* undergoes head movement to a higher deontic modal projection (i.e. Tsai 2015a), which would explain the imperative mood of the *gei wo* phrase in (17), since the deontic modal is associated with a command or request mood.

If the *gei wo* phrase in (17) is indeed in the TP domain, one might wonder if it can co-occur with another *gei wo* phrase in the CP domain or in the *vP* domain. Its co-

occurrence with a *gei wo* phrase in the CP domain does not seem possible, as shown in (29).

- (29) *Zhangsan juran [gei wo] [gei wo]
 Zhangsan unexpectedly GEI me GEI me
 he-le san-ping jiu!
 drink-ASP three-CL wine
 ‘Unexpectedly, Zhangsan drank three bottles of wine on me/for my sake!’

This ungrammaticality may be due to their mood incompatibility and situation-type differences, as pointed out previously. However, if we try to put a *gei wo* phrase in the TP domain and another applied NP in the ν P domain, this co-occurrence seems possible, as shown in (30).

- (30) Ni quai [gei wo] he-le Lisi san-ping jiu!
 you quicklyGEI me drink-ASP Lisi three-CL wine
 ‘Drink three bottles of wine on Lisi for my sake!’

In example (30), there are two applicative projections. The one in the TP domain hosts the applied NP *wo*, while the one in the ν P domain hosts the applied NP *Lisi*. The co-occurrence of the TP applied NP and the ν P applied NP therefore further strengthens the proposal of a new TP peripheral applicative projection in Mandarin Chinese.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we have seen that, in addition to Pylkkänen’s (2002, 2008) high applicative projection, a very high applicative projection has been proposed by Tsai (2009, 2012, 2015b, 2017) in Mandarin Chinese. After examining the relevant data further, I propose that there is also a peripheral applicative projection available around the ν P periphery. This proposal is supported by the distinct properties of the peripheral applicative projection itself and its co-occurrence with other applicative projections in Mandarin Chinese. The current findings therefore provide a further cross-linguistic verification of possible applicative projections in natural languages.

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On the So-Called Gapless Relative Clauses in Chinese*

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The syntactic status of gapless relative clauses in Chinese has been extremely controversial among the linguistic literature. In recent years, most studies treat them not as relative clauses but complements that are selected by the head nominal. Refusing to take on this position, this study argues that gapless relative clauses should be analyzed as adjunct relative clauses, both of which involve an operator movement. We propose a notion of "adjunctivizer," which selects the covert operator as its complement and ultimately functions to turn the head nominal into an adjunct in the modifying clause in gapless relative clauses and adjunct relative clauses. The notion of adjunct is thus extended in our analysis.

0. Introduction

Chinese has different types of clausal modifiers of nominal heads. The most familiar type is (1), in which the NPs contain gapped relative clauses (RCs). Following the tradition from Aoun and Li (2003) and Huang, Li and Li (2009), I will refer to the clauses in (1a) and (1b) as "argument relative clauses" and "adjunct relative clauses." In these relative clause constructions, the head nominals correspond to a gap inside the modifying clause, which can be an argument, i.e., *shouji* 'cell phone' or an adjunct *difang* 'place.'¹²

(1) Gapped relative clauses

- a. *Argument relative clauses (RCs with an argument gap)*
- | | | | | | | |
|-----|--------------------|----------|-----|------------------|------|----------------------------------|
| [NP | [_{ArgRC} | Zhangsan | mai | [e] _i | de] | shouji] |
| | | Zhangsan | buy | | DE | cell phone |
| | | | | | | 'the cell phone Zhangsan bought' |

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¹ The abbreviations used in the Chinese data are as follows: DE = nominal modifier creating particle *de*; PERF = perfective aspect marker; SFP = sentence final particles. The abbreviations used in the Japanese data are as follows: NOM = nominative case marker.

² Notice that these labels are given not because the whole relative clause can be an argument or adjunct of the nominal head but because the gap therein is interpreted as an argument or an adjunct.

b. *Adjunct relative clauses (RCs with an adjunct gap)*

[NP [A_{ject}RC Zhangsan [e]_i xiu che de] difang_i]
 Zhangsan fix car DE place
 'the place where Zhangsan fixed the car'

In addition, another type of prenominal clause is what people usually call "complement clause" since the modifying clause is considered to be the complement of a nominal predicate. One example is shown in (2).

(2) *Complement clauses*

[NP [CompCL Zhangsan lihun de] shengming]
 Zhangsan divorce DE claim
 'the claim that Zhangsan is divorced'

Particularly, this paper is focused on a special type of Chinese relative clauses as in (3), which is usually referred to as a "gapless relative clause" since the head nominal cannot be identified as any gap inside the modifying clause.³ (Japanese and Korean are also known to have a similar construction.)

(3) *Gapless relative clauses*

- a. [NP [GaplessCL Zhangsan tan gangqin de] shengyin] (CL = clause)
 Zhangsan play piano DE sound
 Lit: '(the) sound [Zhangsan plays the piano]'
 'the sound that arises/arose from Zhangsan's playing the piano'
- b. [NP [GaplessCL Zhangsan tiaowu de] yangzi]
 Zhangsan dance DE appearance
 Lit: '(the) appearance [Zhangsan dances]'
 'the way that Zhangsan looks when he dances'
- c. [NP [GaplessCL Zhangsan chuli shiqing de] xiaolü]
 Zhangsan deal.with things DE efficiency
 Lit: '(the) efficiency [Zhangsan deals with things]'
 'the efficiency with which Zhangsan deals with things'

In (3), the head nominals *shengyin* 'sound', *yangzi* 'appearance', and *xiaolü* 'efficiency' do not seem to relate to any position inside the modifying clause.

The name "gapless relative clause," however, is rather controversial and misleading since previous literature has not agreed on whether they are truly relative clauses or gapless. On the one hand, Cheng and Sybesma (2005), Ning (1993), and Tsai (1997) treat them as one type of relative clause. On the other hand, Aoun and Li (2003), Huang et. al (2000, 2009), Huang (2016), and Tsai (2008) argue that they are not relative clauses but complement clauses selected by predicative nominal heads similar to the complement clauses in (2). For example, Huang et. al (2009: 234) claim that the gapless clause "is more

³ The earliest examples of gapless relative clauses are shown in Tang (1979).

like a Head noun with a preposition and XP (a PP) in English, such as [*the price [for him killing the boy]*], [*the sound [of his singing]*]...rather than being a counterpart of the English [Head + Relative clause]." Pursuing an analysis similar to Huang et. al's approach, Zhang (2008) claims that gapless clauses should be at Spec, NP, which act as subjects predicated by the nominal heads as predicates.

Moreover, some previous studies argue that gapless relative clauses are not truly gapless. Postulating a gap within the prenominal clause, Ning (1993) argues that there is an adjunct gap in the modifying clause created by the movement of a relative operator. In addition, Tsai (1997), and Cheng and Sybesma (2005) argue that there is an implicit event argument in the clause bound by a base-generated operator. On the other hand, Aoun and Li (2003), Huang et al. (2000, 2009), Huang (2016), Zhang (2008) and others argue that there is indeed no gap inside the clause.

Given these controversies over gapless relative clauses, I will refrain from using the term "gapless relative clauses" to avoid potential ambiguity and confusion. Instead, I will just appeal to the observational characteristic of this construction and use the neutral label "gapless clauses (gaplessCL)" to refer to it. Following Ning (1993), we will argue that the so-called "gapless clauses" have an adjunct gap similar to adjunct relative clauses. However, this study is crucially different from Ning in postulating what I call an "adjunctivizer," an archi-category in syntax which subsumes prepositions (and postpositions). The adjunctivizer introduces some specific types of adjunct phrases into gapless clauses whose semantico-pragmatic functions may go beyond the standardly recognized adjunct expressions. I will elaborate on this concept in later sections.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 1 will first introduce our assumptions about the syntactic behaviors of argument and adjunct relative clauses. Section 2 will discuss Huang (2016) and Ning (1993) that have a contrast viewpoint in analyzing gapless clauses and are most relevant to the current study. We will then introduce our syntactic and semantic analyses of gapless clauses in Section 3, and rebut some arguments of Huang (2016) in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper.

1. Syntactic behaviors of argument and adjunct relative clauses

Among the analyses of Chinese relative clauses, we will adopt the gist of the analyses offered by Aoun and Li (2003) and Huang et. al (2009), who argue for a promotion analysis for argument relative clauses and an operator movement approach for adjunct relative clauses. We will develop and refine the syntactic analysis of adjunct relative clauses in later sections.

Under the so-called promotion analysis, the head nominal of the argument relative clause construction is claimed to be raised directly out of the modifying clause. The proposed structure of the NP in (4a), for example, is shown in (4b).

- (4) a. [NP wo xihuan de shu] mai-wan le
 I like DE book sell-over SFP
 'The book that I like is sold out.'

- b. [NP [ArgRC wo xihuan t_i de] [NP **shu**]_i]
 I like DE book
 'the book that I like'

In (4b), the head NP *shu* 'book' is moved from the direct object position in the relative clause, as indicated by the trace t_i . Aoun and Li (2003) and Huang et. al (2009) provide several syntactic arguments for this derivation, among which I will discuss the island effect and the reconstruction effect in the following. First, argument relative clauses obey the Complex NP island constraint in (5), where the head *nühai* 'girl' cannot move out of the complex NP headed by *ren* 'people'. This is a piece of evidence for movement.

- (5)
 *[[NP2 [ArgRC2 [NP1 [ArgRC1 wo renshi t_i henduo xihuan t_k de] **ren**]_i] de] [NP **nühai**]_k]
 I know many like DE people DE girl
 Intended: 'the girl_k that I know many people_i who_i t_i like t_k '
 (Huang et. al 2009: 219, modified)

Secondly, the reconstruction effect can be observed in argument relative clauses. To begin with, let us confirm that *ziji* 'self' generally must be c-commanded by the quantified antecedent in order to be interpreted as its variable, as the contrast between (6a) and (6b) shows.

- (6) a. wo jiao Zhangsan quan **meigeren**_i kai **ziji**_i de chezi guolai
 I ask Zhangsan persuade everyone drive self DE car come
 'I asked Zhangsan to persuade everyone to drive (her/him)self's car over.'
 (Huang et. al 2009: 220)

- b. wo jiao Zhangsan quan [NP **meigeren**_k dasuan dailai t_i de **tongbani**]_i]
 I let Zhangsan persuade everyone plan bring DE partner
 kai **ziji**_{*k} de chezi guolai
 drive self DE car come
 'I asked Zhangsan to persuade the partner_i that everyone_k plans to bring t_i to drive (her/him)self*_k's car over.'

In (6a), *meigeren* 'everyone' properly c-commands and binds the reflexive *ziji* 'self' within the object in the subordinate clause. However, in (6b), similar binding is prohibited since *ziji* 'self' is not c-commanded by the quantifier *meigeren*, which is located within the relative clause embedded in the subject NP. Now, examine the argument relative clause construction (7).

- (7)
 [[ArgRC wo jiao Zhangsan quan **meigeren**_k kai t_i guolai de] [NP **ziji**_k de chezi]_i]
 I ask Zhangsan persuade everyone drive come DE self DE car
 '(her/him)self's car that I asked Zhangsan to persuade everyone to drive over'
 (Huang et. al 2009: 220, modified)

Here, *ziji* 'self' is contained in the head NP and hence obviously fails to be c-commanded by any element within the relative clause at surface. It, however, can still be bound by *meigeren* 'everyone' in the relative clause. This puzzling phenomenon can be accounted for if it is assumed that the head NP originates from the position c-commanded by *meigeren* within the relative clause and moves to its surface position. That is, if the so-called promotion analysis is adopted, the reconstruction effect can be explained.

Unlike the argument relative clause construction, the adjunct relative clause construction has been claimed to involve an operator that is generated within the relative clause and moves to its periphery (Ning 1993; Aoun and Li 2003; Huang et al. 2009). This operator links to the base-generated head nominal, thereby establishing a correlation between the clause-internal trace and the head nominal. This matching process eventually allows the entire relative clause to function as a modifier of the head nominal.

The operator movement hypothesis is argued to be supported by the island effect, the reconstruction effect, and the intervention effect. I will discuss the island effect and reconstruction effect in this paper.⁴

First, adjunct relative clauses are subject to island constraints such as the adjunct island condition, as shown in (8).

- (8)
- | | | | | | | | | | | |
|-----|------------|-----------------------|-----------------|----------|--------------|-----------|----------------------|------------------|----|------|
| *wo | tingdao-le | [[A _{jet} RC | Op _i | [Adjunct | <i>ruguo</i> | <i>ta</i> | <i>t_i</i> | <i>shengqi</i>] | wo | hui |
| I | hear-PERF | | | | <i>if</i> | he | | angry | I | will |
| bu | gaoxing | de] | yuanyini] | | | | | | | |
| not | happy | DE | reason | | | | | | | |
- *‘I heard the **reason**_i I will not be happy [if he gets angry **t_i**].’⁵
(Huang et al. 2009: 222 modified)

In this sentence, the head *yuanyin* "reason" of the adjunct relative clause cannot be properly associated with a variable within the adjunct island. This is a piece of evidence for movement.

In addition, adjunct relative clauses make a striking contrast to argument relative clauses, which have been claimed to involve the "promotion" of the head nominal from within the relative clause.

Recall that the head nominal of the argument relative clause construction induces a reconstruction effect on the variable binding of *ziji* 'self' in (7). On the other hand, in the adjunct relative clause construction, no such reconstruction effect can be induced by the head nominal, as shown in (9).

⁴ As for the intervention effect, I raised concerns about the legitimacy of this test in Patterson (2020), which ultimately leads us not to adopt this test in this study.

⁵ Notice that the head 'reason' needs to be interpreted as the reason for *his* being angry, not the reason for *my* being not happy. With the latter reading, the sentence is acceptable.

(9) Adjunct relative clauses

*wo xiang kan [[A_{ject}RC Op_i ni shuo *meigeren*_k ti xiu che de] [*ziji*_k de didian]
 I want see you say everyone fix car DE self DE place
 *'I want to see (him/her)self's place in which you said that everyone fixed the car.'

In (9), *ziji* 'self' contained in the head nominal cannot be bound by *meigeren* 'everyone' in the modifying clause. This suggests that the head nominal in the adjunct relative clause construction is base-generated in its surface position instead of originating in the clause. Instead, what moves is the operator from within the island to the peripheral position, as supported by the island effect earlier.

2. Previous analyses of gapless clauses

In this section, two previous analyses will be introduced, which are directly relevant to this study. In the first one, Huang (2016) argues that gapless clause are complements of a head nominal, which is a nominal predicate. We will call this the complement approach. The other one is Ning (1993), who claims that gapless clauses have a similar derivation to adjunct relative clauses, both of which involve movement of an empty operator that binds a variable. We will call this the adjunct operator approach.

2.1 Huang's complement approach

On the one hand, Huang (2016) argues that Chinese gapless clauses have a similar derivation to complement clauses as complements of the head N°. Both of them are contrary to argument relative clauses, which he analyzes as adjuncts to N-bar. He discusses a few tests to show the differences between the two kinds of clauses. Due to the space limitation, we will only show one test in this section, which we will ultimately rebut in later sections.

Huang (2016: 448-449) claims that argument relative clauses can be iterated, meaning that the head can be modified by multiple argument relative clauses as in (10), while gapless clauses cannot be iterated, as indicated in (11).

- (10) [[ArgRC ta fa-chulai de] [ArgRC ling ren haipa de] shengyin]
 he produce DE cause person afraid DE sound
 'the sound that terrified others that he produced' (Huang 2016: 448, modified)
- (11) *[[GaplessCL ta tan gangqin de] [GaplessCL wo la xiaotiqin de] shengyin]
 he play piano DE I play violin DE sound
 Intended: 'the sound that arises/arose from me playing the violin and his playing the piano' (Huang 2016: 448, modified)

According to Huang, this asymmetry arises because a nominal head can be syntactically modified by multiple adjuncts but cannot take multiple complements and hence not multiple gapless clauses, either. Such an idea was also expressed in Zhang (2008). In addition, Huang argues that adjuncts can be iterated because they can successively create

subset denotations from the supersets defined by the head nominal, while complements can only fill argument positions.

2.2 Ning's adjunct operator approach

Different from the complement approach, Ning (1993) analyzes gapless clauses on a par with adjunct relative clauses. On the one hand, he claims that Chinese adjunct relative clauses contain covert operators as counterparts of the single relative operators in English adjunct relative clauses, i.e., *where*, *when*, *how*, and *why*. Ning argues that both the covert and overt adjunct relative operators can be decomposed into the following structure in (12).

(12) The LF Decomposition Rule (for Single-word Adjunct Operators):

An adjunct operator (overt or covert) is decomposed into a PP containing an unspecified preposition and an NP operator with a restriction in:

where α is a collection of restrictions. (Ning 1993: 28, modified)

In (12), the top operator (Ajct-Op₁) corresponds to a single-word adjunct relative operator, which is overt in English and covert in Chinese. This operator can be lexically decomposed into a covert preposition [P E] and a covert NP operator (NP-Op₂), which is restricted by its domain R< α > (R means restriction) such as PLACE, TIME, MANNER etc. The space limitation prevents us from going into the technical details of Ning's analyses. I refer the readers to Patterson (2020) for detailed discussion. Simplifying the derivation, Ning's syntactic structure of adjunct relative clauses should look like (13).

In (13), the nominal operator inside the entire adjunct operator moves to the periphery of the modifying clause. The restraining domain of the operator is a set of places. Ning argues that the covert preposition is not specified because the location of the meeting is not specified, i.e., the people could meet *in* the place, *on* the place, or *outside* the place. This adjunct operator associates the modifying clause with the head nominal. In terms of gapless clauses, Ning argues that they should have a structure similar to adjunct relative clauses. However, he proposes that gapless clauses should contain a *resultative* VP adjunct rather than a PP adjunct, due to some technical details we will omit here. Instead

naturally include notions such as place, time, instrument, and manner. We will argue, however, that what I have called gapless clauses crucially involve some adjunct notions that go beyond such standard types of adjuncts.

Moreover, recall that Ning assumes a complex adjunct operator that serves as the link between the head nominal and the modifying clause. However, we argue that the operator should be nominal and is selected by an empty adjunctivizer in the Adjunctivizer Phrase (AjctvP). In Patterson (2020), I discuss in detail the evidence for the nominal status of adjunct operators from English free relative clauses in (Caponigro 2004, Caponigro and Pearl 2008, 2009), English *wh*-questions in (Huang, 1982), and "non-*wh*" adjunct nominal expressions in Larson (1985). Additionally, I also found certain evidence from Chinese *wh*-questions. For example, in English *wh*-questions with the adjunct operator *where* and Chinese counterpart with *nali* 'where', the preposition can be overt in syntax such as (16) and (17). This is a piece of evidence that the operator *where* is an NP rather than a PP.

(16) Where did we just run [PP [P **past**] [NP t]]?

Caponigro and Pearl (2008: 13, modified)

(17) Zhangsan yiban ??(**zai**) nali xiu che?
 Zhangsan normally **at** where fix car
 'Where does Zhangsan normally fix the car?'

Huang (1982) argues that the PP gap from which the operator moves contains a silent preposition. Such a preposition can be overt such as *past* in (16). In the Chinese example in (17), the sentence actually sounds degraded without the overt preposition *zai* 'at'.

In later sections, we will also argue that the analysis in (15) appealing to an adjunctivizer can be further extended to adjunct relative clauses.

3.1 Syntactic arguments for operator movement

In this section, we will provide syntactic arguments that support our analysis, which Ning (1993) fails to provide. Similar to adjunct relative clauses, gapless clauses obey island constraints as in the adjunct island in (18) but lack the reconstruction effect as in (19).

(18) $\overbrace{\text{Op}^j \text{ [Adjunct ruguo [CP ta } t_i \text{ tan gangqin]]}}^{\times}$
 *wo tingdao-le [NP [GaplessCL **Op**^j [Adjunct ruguo [CP ta *t*_i tan gangqin]]]
 I hear-PERF if he play piano
 wo hui gaoxing de] shengyin^j]
 I will happy DE sound
 Intended: 'I heard the sound I will be happy [if he plays the piano] and arises.'

(19) $\overbrace{\text{Op}^j \text{ meigeren}_k \text{ zhoumo } t_i \text{ mai shu de } [ziji_k \text{ de qian}^j]]}^{\times}$
 *wo kandao-le [NP [GaplessCL **Op**^j *meigeren*_k zhoumo *t*_i mai shu de] [ziji_k de qian^j]]
 I see-PERF everyone weekend sell book DE self DE money
 Intended: 'I saw (him/her)self's money that was earned by everyone selling (the) books on the weekend.'

In (18), the operator cannot move outside of the adjunct island. In (19), *ziji* 'self' cannot be bound by *meigeren* 'everyone' in the prenominal clause. If the gapless clauses do not involve the "promotion" of the head NP but rather is base-generated, so that the head NP comes to be associated with an empty operator moved to the periphery of the clause, we can explain why no reconstruction effect is observed while island effects are observed.

Now a word is in order for the long-distance reading of gapless clauses. Huang et. al (2009) and Huang (2016) argue that gapless clauses cannot have a long-distance reading such as (20), because there is no variable-binding relation between the variable and the head nominal.

(20) *zhe jiushi [NP [GaplessCL wo xiangxiang [Zhangsan tan gangqin]
 this is I imagine Zhangsan play piano
 de] shengyin]
 DE sound

Intended: 'This is the sound which I imagined (pretended/fantasized/visualized) had arisen from his playing the piano.'

However, in Patterson (2020), I argue that such a reading is in fact possible. To begin with, there should be three ways of the potential association between the operator and the variable in these sentences, as illustrated in (21).

- (21) a. [**OP_i** I *imagine* **t_i** [...]] sound
 b. [**OP_i** I *imagine* [.. **t_i** ..]] sound
 c. [I *imagine* [**OP_i** ... **t_i**]] sound

It is assumed that the trace of the operator indicates which eventuality is to be interpreted as the cause of the sound regarded as its effect. In (21a), the trace is in the higher clause. Its entire sentence is shown in (22).

(22) zhe jiushi [NP [GaplessCL **OP_i** wo **t_i** xiangxiang [Zhangsan tan gangqin]
 this is I imagine Zhangsan play piano
 de] shengyin^j]
 DE sound

'This is the (imaginary) sound that arose/arises from my imagining (fantasizing) that he played/will play the piano.'

In (22), the head nominal is the effect of the event denoted by the matrix clause, i.e., the sound is the effect of me fantasizing the event of someone playing the piano. Huang et. al (2009) and Huang (2016) argue that such a reading is possible, although they explain this based on the complement status of the gapless clause instead of the variable binding relationship. On the other hand, in (21b), the trace is in the subordinated clause as shown in (23).

- (23) zhe jiushi [NP [GaplessCL **Opⁱ** wo xiangxiang [Zhangsan *t_i* tan gangqin]
 this is I imagine Zhangsan play piano
 de] shengyin^j]
 DE sound
 'This is the (imaginary) sound that arose/arises from my imagining (fantasizing) that
 he played/will play the piano.'

Although Huang et. al (2009) and Huang (2016) argue that this long-distance reading is not possible, we argue that it is possible but requires some specific context. Imagine a context where Zhangsan is a very promising budding pianist, and his piano teacher is playing a recording of some famous pianist's performance. The speaker knows that Zhangsan is not performing in that recording, but he confidently tells the hearer that he can imagine that Zhangsan will produce a piano sound of equally high quality after two more years of training under him with the sentence:

- (24) zhe jiushi [NP [GaplessCL **Opⁱ** wo xiangxiang [Zhangsan liang nian
 this is I imagine Zhangsan two year
 hou *t_i* tan gangqin] de] shengyin^j]
 after play piano DE sound
 'This is the sound which I imagined (pretended/fantasized/visualized) had arisen
 from his playing the piano two years from now.'

Therefore, I claim that a long-distance reading in gapless clauses is possible, but when there is an island, the long-distance reading is not allowed because the operator movement is blocked by the island.

Finally, I claim that (21c) is not possible. Consider (25).

- (25) *zhe jiushi [[GaplessCL wo xiangxiang [**Opⁱ** ta *t_i* tan gangqin] de]
 this is I imagine he play piano DE
shengyin^j]
 sound
 Intended: 'This is the sound such that I imagine a **property** of arising from
 Zhangsan's playing the piano.'

The interpretation in (25) is not possible due to both syntactic and semantic reasons. Syntactically, the operator should be in a local position of the head nominal, i.e., the Spec, CP of the matrix clause, so that the gapless clause can be locally predicated of the head nominal (Chomsky 1986) or that they can enter into an agreement chain (Browning 1987). Semantically, the verb *xiangxiang* "imagine" needs to select a complement denoting a proposition (type <t>); however, the movement of the operator to the lower clause turns the embedded clause into type <e,t>, which denotes a property. Thus, it creates a type mismatch. Consequently, the locality condition imposed on the association between the operator and the head nominal in syntax may be reducible to a semantic anomaly.

3.2 Semantic composition of gapless clauses

In this section, I will offer formal analyses of the semantic composition of gapless clauses. Consider the syntax-semantics mapping of the sentence (26a) in (26b).

- (26) a. [NP [GaplessCL **Op**_i^j Zhangsan *t*_i tan gangqin de] shengyin_i^j]
 Zhangsan play piano DE sound
 'the sound that arises from Zhangsan's playing the piano'

In (26b), the verb *play* is of type $\langle e, \langle e, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle \rangle$ and takes two individual arguments and one covert event argument. Following Davidson (1967), I assume that verbs take a covert event argument. It selects the theme *piano* (type $\langle e \rangle$) and the agent *Zhangsan* (type $\langle e \rangle$) via Functional Application and returns a VP of type $\langle e, t \rangle$ denoting eventuality description. The lower VP denotes the set of playing events whose agent is *Zhangsan* and whose theme is *piano*, respectively. Crucially, an Adjunctivizer Phrase (AjctvP) is joined to VP, which will ultimately associate the head nominal as the effect of the event of *Zhangsan* playing the piano. The Adjunctivizer holds the function *EFFECT*, which takes an individual and an eventuality, and identifies the individual as the effect of the eventuality. The individual variable in Adjunctivizer Phrase is represented as a trace from the operator movement, which is indexed with the assignment value 1. The adjunctivizer,

which is of type $\langle e, \langle \epsilon, t \rangle \rangle$, takes a trace of type $\langle e \rangle$ and returns an Adjunctivizer Phrase of type $\langle \epsilon, t \rangle$. The covert Adjunctivizer Phrase has scope below the existential closure since the head nominal of the gapless clause construction is related to the eventuality of the modifying clause. The Adjunctivizer Phrase and VP are combined via Predicate Modification and return a VP of the same type $\langle \epsilon, t \rangle$. This higher VP denotes the set of events of Zhangsan playing the piano whose effect is the individual $g(1)$. The VP then undergoes existential closure and returns a truth value of type $\langle t \rangle$. This highest VP is true iff there is an event of Zhangsan playing the piano whose effect is individual $g(1)$. Since my analysis does not deal with tense, aspect, or modality, we will ignore the semantic contribution of T and treat it as semantically vacuous and let it inherit the value of VP. Moving on to CP, we also treat the modifier-creating particle *de* as the semantically vacuous head of CP, so the C' will inherit the value of TP. When the operator is moved to [Spec, CP], it triggers Predicate Abstraction and returns a CP of type $\langle e, t \rangle$. The CP denotes the set of individuals that are the effects of an event of Zhangsan playing the piano. The CP then combines with the head *sound*. Since *sound* is a predicate NP of type $\langle e, t \rangle$, it is predicated of an individual sound and denotes the set of sounds. The CP and the NP then combine via Predicate Modification and return another NP of the same type $\langle e, t \rangle$. As a result, the modified NP denotes the set of individuals such that they are sounds and the effect of an event of Zhangsan playing the piano.

We also argue that this derivation can be applied to adjunct relative clauses, in which the functions would contain PLACE, TIME, MANNER, INSTRUMENT, and REASON, as demonstrated in (27).

- (27) a. [[_{AjctRC} Opⁱ ta [_{AjctvP} Ø_{AJCTVZER=PLACE} [_{NP} t_i]] jiamian de] didian]
 he meet DE place
 'the place where they met'
- b. [[_{AjctRC} Opⁱ ta [_{AjctvP} Ø_{AJCTVZER=MANNER} [_{NP} t_i]] jiamian de] fangfa]
 he meet DE way
 'the way they met'

Finally, in Patterson (2020), I observe different kinds of gapless clauses with different relations between the eventuality denoted by the modifying clause and the head nominal. I argue that the adjunctivizer includes different functions such as CAUSE, COMPONENT, ATTRIBUTE as illustrated by the Japanese data and Chinese data in (28).⁹

⁹ For reasons that are too complicated to go into details here, we will not discuss why the CAUSE relation is not possible in Chinese. In a word, I argue that empty adjunctivizers can be blocked by the overt ones, which is what the situation is in here. I also pinpoint other situations where an over adjunctivizer is required in Patterson (2020).

(28) a. *Japanese data*

[[GaplessCL Opⁱ atama-ga [A_{ctvP} Ø_{AJCTVZER=CAUSE} [NP t_i]] yokunaru] hon]
 brain-NOM gets better book
 'the book **which makes** one's brain gets better (= becomes smarter)'
 (Matsumoto (1997: 48), modified)

b. *Chinese data*

[[GaplessCL Opⁱ Zhangsan [A_{ctvP} Ø_{AJCTVZER=COMPONENT} [NP t_i]] tiaowu de] lunkuo^j]
 Zhangsan dance DE silhouette
 'the silhouette of Zhangsan's dancing'

c. *Chinese data*

[[GaplessCL Opⁱ Zhangsan [A_{ctvP} Ø_{AJCTVZER=ATTRIBUTE} [NP t_i]] zuo shi de] wanmei]
 Zhangsan deal.with thing DE perfection
 'the perfection **with which** Zhangsan deals with things'

In (28a), the head *hon* 'book' can be seen as the cause of the eventuality of one's brain getting better. In (28b), the head *lunkuo* 'silhouette' can be treated as a component for the dancing event. Finally, in (28c), the head *wanmei* 'perfection' represents some attribute of the eventuality denoted by the clause, i.e., Zhangsan's dealing with things was realized in a perfect way. These adjunctivizers will function to turn the head nominal into a certain adjunct in the gapless clause. We thus extend the notion of adjuncts from traditional ones such as time, place, manner, instrument, and reason in adjunct relative clauses to unconventional ones such as cause, effect, component, and attribute in gapless clauses.

Although both the current study and Ning's "adjunct approach" analyze gapless clauses on a par with adjunct relative clauses. They are different in some crucial respects. To begin with, the two studies have a different treatment of the operator. On the one hand, Ning postulates a complex composition of an adjunct operator, which consists of an empty proposition/verb and a nominal operator. On the other hand, in our system, the operator is nominal adopting the argument of the nominal status of operator in previous works such as (Caponigro 2004, Caponigro and Pearl 2008, 2009). This also follows the semantic composition we discussed in this section. In addition, another important aspect is our proposal of an "adjunctivizer," an archi-category in syntax which subsumes prepositions (and postpositions). It introduces some specific types of adjunct phrases into gapless clauses whose semantico-pragmatic functions may go beyond the standardly recognized adjunct expressions. An adjunctivizer head is analyzed as selecting an empty nominal operator as its complement ([A_{ctvP} Adjunctivizer [NP OP]]). The operator undergoes movement and binds a trace as its variable inside the modifying clause, and is linked to the head nominal. As a result, the head nominal functions as an adjunct in the eventuality denoted by the prenominal clause. Furthermore, Ning proposes that gapless clauses have a covert resultative VP adjunct headed by an empty verb having a meaning of "obtain." However, in Patterson (2020), I observe other kinds of gapless clauses. The relationship between the head nominal and the eventuality that the modifying clauses denote are beyond the kind observed in Ning, as shown in the above examples in (28). Moreover, I also

provide some evidence in Patterson (2020) that shows that the covert VP that Ning postulates is likely not an adjunct VP. Finally, Ning does not provide syntactic arguments for his syntactic claims, which we did in this study. Finally, we also offer the formal semantic composition for gapless clauses, which can be further extended to adjunct relative clauses. The semantics makes the contribution of the empty operator and the adjunctivizer much clearer in the interpretation of these kinds of relative clauses.

4. Problem with Huang's (2016) complement approach

Remember in Section 2.1, we report the observation of Huang (2016) and Zhang (2008), who report their observation that argument relative clauses can be iterated, but gapless clauses cannot. They claim that this contrast supports their analysis that argument relative clauses are adjuncts, but gapless clauses and complement clauses are complements of the head nominal.

However, in Patterson (2020), I report some contrast data suggested by Yoshihisa Kitagawa, which argue against this claim. Consider the two examples in (29). They are structurally similar to (11) but are pragmatic felicitous.

- (29) a. [GaplessCL2 wo yong gangqin banzou de] [GaplessCL1 ta yong xiaotiqin
I use piano accompany DE he use violin
la zhu xuanlü de] qudiao
play main melody DE tune
'the tune that was performed with his playing the main melody on the
violin and my playing the accompaniment on the piano'
- b. [GaplessCL2 wo chang di shengbu de] [GaplessCL1 ta chang gao
I sing low part DE he sing high
shengbu de] [meimiao de hesheng]
part DE beautiful DE harmony
'the beautiful harmony which arose from her singing the higher
melody and his singing the lower melody'

One possibility is that the unacceptability of (11) is caused by some semantic incongruence of the modification achieved by the two gapless clauses, which does not arise in (29). In the hierarchy of noun modification, the gapless clause closer to the head first combines with the head and thus restricts the meaning of the head. In (11), for example, the sound is produced by my playing the violin (GaplessCL1). Later, the second gapless clause, i.e., GaplessCL2, combines with the head nominal whose meaning is already restricted by the modification by GaplessCL1. However, it would be contradictory to combine the sound produced by my playing the violin with his playing the piano, thus causing the anomaly. Such a contradiction does not exist in (29) since the tune is produced both by the violin which plays the main melody and the piano which accompanies the violin, and the harmony is produced both by me singing the lower melody and him singing the higher melody. Thus, it is pragmatically felicitous for both

gapless clauses to modify the same head in this case. In the same vein, we can also construct other gapless clauses such as (30).

- (30) [GaplessCL2 xihongshi dang zhucai de] [GaplessCL1 suanmiao
 tomato serve.as main.ingredient DE garlic.bulb
 dang peicai de] weidao
 serve.as side.ingredient DE taste
 'the taste that arises/arose from using the garlic bulbs as the side in
 ingredient and tomato as the main ingredient'

In the Chinese stir-fry, some vegetables may be considered as the main ingredients while others as the side ingredients. Thus, (30) can be uttered felicitously to describe the taste of a dish in which tomatoes are used as the main ingredient and garlic bulbs as the side ingredient. No contradiction between the two gapless clauses will arise. More examples of iterated gapless clauses are shown in (31).

- (31) a. [GaplessCL2 tai zhuiqiu zhenli de] [GaplessCL1 pro_i bu pa quanguai
 he pursue truth DE no afraid authority
 de] jingshen
 DE spirit
 'the spirit because of which he is not afraid of the authority and can
 pursue the truth'
- b. [GaplessCL2 tai qipian yuangong de] [GaplessCL1 pro_i tanwu
 he cheat staff DE embezzle
 gongkuan de] houguo
 public funds DE consequence
 'the consequences that came from his embezzling public funds and
 cheating the staff'
- c. [GaplessCL2 tai xisheng ziji de] [GaplessCL1 pro_i yingyong jiu ren
 he sacrifice self DE brave save people
 de] huibao
 DE reward
 'the reward that came from his bravely saving people and sacrificing
 himself'

In (31), the gapless clauses modifying the same head are closely related to each other in a relevant event(s). In (31a), his not being afraid of the authority occurs in the course of his pursuing the truth, which is driven by a particular spirit. In (31b), his cheating the staff may be a necessary step for embezzling public funds. In (31c), his sacrificing himself is manifested in his bravely saving people. Since the gapless clauses in each case denote closely related event(s), which can be associated with the head nominal altogether, no contradiction will arise. This is in contrast to the allegedly ungrammatical cases in (11), where the gapless clauses are difficult to relate in the absence of any context, and therefore would result in a contradictory interpretation when they modify the same head.

For lack of space, please refer to Patterson (2020) for the counter arguments for the other tests provided in Huang (2016).

5. Summary

This study provides a syntactic and a semantic account for the quite mysterious gapless clauses that exist in East Asian Languages such as Chinese. Different from what we call the "complement approach" in the previous literature, which argues that gapless clauses are complements of the head nominal, we argue that gapless clauses should be analyzed on a par with adjunct relative clauses by revising and extending the previous "adjunct approach." The paper first establishes its assumptions about argument and adjunct relative clauses in Section 1 by adopting the gist of the analyses from Aoun and Li (2003) and Huang et. al (2009). We then introduce the complement approach and the adjunct approach about gapless clauses in the literature based on Huang (2016) and Ning (1993), the two most relevant studies of the current one. In Section 3, we introduce our syntactic analysis about gapless clauses and provide the syntactic arguments for such an analysis. We also provide the formal semantic composition for gapless clauses, which can also be extended to adjunct relative clauses. Finally, we rebut the complement approach by offering counter arguments to the tests in Huang (2016). The notion of adjunctivizer that we propose selects a nominal operator and turns the head nominal into an adjunct that serves a certain function in the modifying clause. We also extend the notion of adjuncts from the traditional ones such as time, place, manner, instrument, and reason in adjunct relative clauses to unconventional ones such as cause, effect, attribute, and component in gapless clauses, the latter of which have not been recognized as adjuncts to date.

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The Role of Polarity in Measure Phrase Constructions: Evidence from Mandarin, German, Dutch and English

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This paper presents new data from Mandarin and German showing that some negative adjectives can license measure phrases (*0.4 mm bao* '0.4 mm thin') regardless of surface positions. This observation challenges existing work on measure phrase constructions such as Schwarzschild (2005) and Breakstone (2012), which argue that measure phrases cannot directly modify negative adjectives. This paper offers a novel analysis of measure phrase constructions. I propose (i) measure phrases are inherently downward monotonic, and this polarity is sensitive to contextual and lexical information; (ii) measure phrases denote the maximum value of the set of degrees. This analysis explains the markedness of negative adjective in measure phrase constructions crosslinguistically, along with the variation of grammatical judgement in some languages and contexts, and among different speakers.

0. Introduction

It has been observed that measure phrases (MPs) such as '5 feet' in (1) generally do not modify negative antonyms (among others Bierwisch 1989, Schwarzschild 2005, Kennedy 2001), as shown below:

- (1) a. The boy is 5 feet tall.
b. *The boy is 5 feet short.

Although it is grammatical to say *the boy is 5 feet tall* (1a), the sentence becomes unacceptable when the positive antonym is replaced by its negative counterpart (1b). This contrast between antonyms pairs is argued to be systematic (Kennedy 2001, Winter 2005 and others), as in (2).

- (2) ten meters wide/*narrow/deep/*shallow
five years old/*young/long/*short

(Winter 2005)

Bierwisch (1967, 1989), Schwarzschild (2005), Winter (2001, 2005) and others attribute this contrast to the boundedness of the scale related to negative antonyms like

short. Kennedy (2001) (see also Cresswell 1976, von Stechow 1984) proposes that both positive antonyms and MPs denote positive degrees, while negative antonyms denote negative degrees. Most accounts, as I will illustrate later, stipulate a finite interval for MPs to be licensed (see also Morzycki 2008 for discussion), which predicts that negative adjectives should never allow direct MP modification.

However, other languages provide counterexamples to such prediction. In Dutch, as Doetjes (2012) pointed out, MP constructions with negative adjectives are sometimes judged grammatical in prenominal positions (*het 20 cm ondiepe water* ‘The 20 cm shallow water’). Similar constructions are in Mandarin and German. Interestingly, unlike Dutch, some negative adjectives in Mandarin are compatible with MPs regardless of their surface positions (3).¹

(3) *Mandarin*

- a. zhe zhang **0.4 mm bao** de zhi
 this CL 0.4 mm thin de paper
 ‘this 0.4 mm thin paper’
- b. zhe zhang zhi **0.4 mm bao**.
 this CL paper 0.4 mm thin
 ‘The paper (is) 0.4 mm thin.’

Furthermore, unlike positive antonyms (4a), negative antonyms in MP constructions are interpreted with regard to a contextual standard (4b). (4b) is judged ungrammatical if most other papers are thinner than 3mm, and grammatical if other papers are mostly thicker than 3mm. (4a), on the other hand, is grammatical in both cases. This is in parallel with the well-known paradigm in (5).

(4) *Mandarin*

- a. zhe zhi **3 mm hou**, (hen bao).
 this paper 3 mm thick very thin
 ‘This paper (is) 3 mm thick, (it’s) very thin.’
- b. zhe zhi **3 mm bao**, (*hen hou).
 this paper 3 mm thin very thick
 ‘This paper (is) 3 mm thin, (it’s) very thick.’

- (5) a. The (*short) boy is tall.
 b. The (short) boy is 3 feet tall.

¹ It should be noticed that the judgement is not strictly agreed among all native speakers, this variation of judgement will be addressed in detail in section 3.

Notice the construction *the short boy is tall* (5a) becomes acceptable when the gradable adjective is modified by the MP *5 feet* (5b). The adjective *tall* in (5a) is sensitive to contextual standard. For *the boy is tall* to be judged true, the boy must be taller than the contextual standard of tallness. Likewise, for *the short boy* to be judged true, the boy must be shorter than the relevant contextual standard, which makes *the short boy is tall* ungrammatical. However, once modified by the MP *5 feet*, the adjective *tall* no longer requires the boy to be taller than the contextual standard. It then becomes perfectly acceptable to say that *the short boy is 5 feet tall*. Following Neeleman et al. (2004) and Rett (2015, 2017), I call this interpretation of adjective in (5a) as *evaluative*, and the one in (5b) as *unevaluative*.

The aim of this paper is to present evidence that shows negative antonyms can license MPs regardless of their surface positions and to present an amended version of Schwarzschild's (2005) interval analysis of MPs. The paper is organized as follows. Section 1 is a review of Kennedy's (2001) and Schwarzschild's (2005)'s interval accounts of MPs followed by a discussion of data found in Dutch, German and Mandarin in Section 2. Section 3 examines the role of polarity in light of the data provided in Section 2. In Section 4, I present the amended interval analysis of measure phrases, and show how this new account of MPs and Rett's (2015) analysis of evaluativity can explain the problematic data. Section 5 is the conclusion, and some questions are brought up for future studies.

1. Interval analysis of MP

1.1 Kennedy's (2001) analysis of MPs

Kennedy (2001) distinguishes degrees denoted by positive and negative antonyms, as motivated by sentences like (6). He argues that the anomaly of (6a) can be explained by the fact that positive antonyms only denote positive degrees, while negative antonyms denote negative degrees. This means that the antonym pairs denote two disjoint sets, thus no comparative relation is defined for these sets, which makes (6a) ungrammatical.

- (6) a. *John is taller than Amy is short.
 b. John is taller than the robe is long

Kennedy refers to the unacceptability of (7a) as cross-polar anomaly (CPA). The ungrammaticality of MP-negative antonym constructions as shown in (7b) is another form of CPA. He proposes that MPs, like positive antonyms, only denote positive degrees. He argues that (7a-b) has the semantic representation of (7c-d). For (7d), the ordering relation between *short* (*J*) which is a negative degree and positive degree denoted by *5 feet* is undefined. (7b) is thus ungrammatical.

- (7) a. John is 5 feet tall. c. tall (J) \geq 5 feet
 b. *John is 5 feet short. d. short (J) \geq 5 feet

As for the acceptability of comparative sentence such as *John is 5 feet shorter*, he proposed a function ZERO to map differential degrees imposed by comparative expressions to degrees with a minimal value of zero point (8). Under this analysis, differential degrees are like positive degrees, and therefore can appear in comparatives with negative antonyms.

- (8) [ZERO]] = {<d₁, d₂>|
 (i) $\forall p_1, p_2 \in d_1[p_1 < p_2 \rightarrow \exists p'_1, p'_2 \in d_2[p'_1 < p'_2]] \wedge$
 (ii) $\forall p'_1, p'_2 \in d_2[p'_1 < p'_2 \rightarrow \exists p_1, p_2 \in d_1[p_1 < p_2]] \wedge$
 (iii) MIN(d₂) = MIN(S) (Kennedy 2001:61)

1.2 Schwarzschild (2005)'s analysis of MPs

Schwarzschild (2005) also addresses the contrast between comparatives and MP constructions. He argues that the number of positive antonyms that can appear in MP constructions is limited, and their distributions seem lexically idiosyncratic (*5 feet tall*, **4 kg heavy*). That is to say MP constructions (i.e. direct measure phrase) are the more marked expressions relative to comparatives (i.e. indirect measure phrase) (9).

- (9) (Schwarzschild 2005: 212) If a language has direct measure phrases, it will have indirect measure phrases, but not vice versa.

Following McConnell-Ginet (1973: 135), Schwarzschild argues that MPs are predicates aiming to describe a gap and cannot occupy the degree argument position of gradable adjectives. In order to allow MP-adjective constructions, he postulates the Homonym Rule which produces homonyms of predicates that can have intervals as arguments rather than degrees, as given in (10).

- (10) a. Homonym Rule: from degrees to intervals.
 (if A has meaning A' that relates individuals to degrees then A has a secondary meaning relating individuals to sets of degrees (intervals).
 The secondary meaning is given by: $\lambda I. \lambda x. I = \{d: A'(x, d)\}$
 b. Homonym Rule applies to tall, wide, deep, thick, old, long, high.
 (Schwarzschild 2005: 216)

He also pointed out that this Homonym Rule only applies to positive adjectives. This is achieved by his analysis of MPs as gap predicates that measures the size of the gap. Schwarzschild argues that the incompatibility of MP and negative antonyms is due to the upper and lower bounds of relative adjectives. That is, when an individual is

associated with a degree by a gradable predicate, the exceeding relation gives the set of degrees with an upper bound. For instance, for the sentence *the robe is long*, the robe's length is the upper bound of the set of degrees. Thus, the upper bound is provided by the context, while the lower bound is inherent in the scale itself. And for positive antonyms, both lower bound and upper bound can define a closed set of degrees. However, for negative antonyms, there is no inherent lower bound on the scale. Under this analysis, the positive antonyms denote a closed set of degrees, from which an interval modified by the MP by partitioning it into subsets of degrees, but the negative antonyms denote a set with only upper bound and no lower bound, so it is impossible for the MP to divide the interval into finite unites of subsets.

The two aforementioned approaches, namely Kennedy (2001) and Schwarzschild (2005), both stipulate a finite interval for MPs to be licensed. For Kennedy (2001), positive degrees are 'finite, closed intervals', while negative ones are 'infinite, open intervals'. Since MPs denotes positive degrees, it has to denote finite and closed intervals with a minimum value of zero point. This coincides with Schwarzschild's (2005) analysis. For Schwarzschild, the gap-predicate MP *n*-units is held true if only the gap can be partitioned into finite unites of subsets, which means the gap needs a lower bound or zero point. In a nutshell, for both accounts, MPs are licensed when the gradable adjective can denote a closed set.

2. MP construction with negative adjective

As discussed in the previous section, both Kennedy's (2001) and Schwarzschild's (2005) accounts require the gradable adjective to denote a closed set to license MPs, which put a strong restriction against MP-negative antonym constructions. In this section, I present data that is not predicted by their approach, specifically, negative antonyms are found in MP constructions in Mandarin, German and Dutch.

2.1 MP distribution

Kennedy (2001), Schwarzschild (2005) and others predict that negatives antonyms cannot be modified by MPs in MP constructions, as illustrated in the English example (11). However, as Doetjes (2012) pointed out, such constructions are judged acceptable by some speakers in prenominal position in Dutch, as in (12).

(11) *John is 5 feet short.

(12) a. *Het water is 20 centimeter ondiep.

The water is 20 centimetres shallow. (Kloodter, 1972, cited from Doetjes 2012)

b. % het 20 cm ondiepe water

The 20 cm shallow water

(Doetjes 2012)

This observation challenges most existing analyses. It should be noted that there is an ambiguity of constituency in the structure (12) as in (13)², which might weaken the argument.

- (13) a. [het [20 cm [ondiepe water]] ‘the 20cm shallow water’
 b. [het [[20 cm ondiepe] water]] ‘the 20cm shallow water’

Nevertheless, MP constructions with negative antonyms are also attested in Mandarin and German, as in (14-15).

(14) *Mandarin*

- a. % 5 mi zhai / duan / bao/ jin ‘5m narrow/ short/ thin/ near’
 b. % -5 du leng ‘-5°C cold’

(15) *German*

- a. 3 Meter schmal / kurz / flach / niedrig / nah ‘5m narrow/ short/ shallow/ low/ near’
 b. £20 billig ‘£20 cheap’
 c. 20 kg leicht ‘20 kg light’
 d. 10 Jahre jung ‘10 years young’
 e. 3 Zoll klein ‘5 inches small’
 f. -5 ° kalt ‘-5°C cold’

Unlike Dutch, negative antonyms in Mandarin are compatible with MPs regardless of their surface positions, as in (16).

(16) *Mandarin*

- a. zhe zhang **0.4 mm bao** de zhi
 this CL 0.4 mm thin GEN paper
 ‘this 0.4 mm thin paper’
 b. zhe zhang zhi **0.4 mm bao**.
 this CL paper 0.4 mm thin
 ‘The paper (is) 0.4 mm thin.’

However, as noted by Doetjes (2012), there is a contrast of evaluativity between antonym pairs when they are used with MPs, as negative antonyms additionally express evaluativity as in (17). A plausible explanation for this is Rett’s (2015) implicature account of evaluativity, which correctly predicts the contrast of meaning in (17). However, as she noted (also see Doetjes 2012), to allow MP constructions in (12-16), the current approach of MPs has to be revised.

² I owe Sudo, Yasutada here for suggesting this idea.

(17) *Mandarin*

- a. zhe zhi **3 mm hou**, (hen bao).
 this paper 3 mm thick very thin
 ‘This paper (is) 3 mm thick, (it’s) very thin.’
- b. zhe zhi **3 mm bao**, (*hen hou).
 this paper 3 mm thin very thick
 ‘This paper (is) 3 mm thin, (it’s) very thick.’

2.2 Other potential problems

Apart from that some negative antonyms do license MP modification in German and Mandarin, MP constructions such as -5° *kalt* ‘ -5° c cold’ in German are also potentially problematic for previous analyses. As presented in Section 2, both Kennedy (2001) and Schwarzschild (2005) discussed gradable adjectives associated with scales with an absolute zero point and cannot extend their analyses naturally to scales without an upper or lower limit (e.g. the scale of coldness). For Kennedy (2001), the MP -5° in -5° *kalt* ‘ -5° c cold’ should denote positive degrees which are finite and closed, while -5° denotes degrees that have no lower bound. Schwarzschild (2005), on the other hand, would predict -5° *kalt* ‘ -5° c cold’ to be unacceptable, since MP should measure the size of an interval, and no interval can be measured as -5 .

Another problem for both analyses is that they include zero point in the scale associated with gradable adjectives. For instance, in *John is 5 feet tall*, Schwarzschild (2005) argues that *5 feet* measures the interval to which John is tall and the interval includes zero point as its minimal value. However, it should be argued whether John is tall is true for the zero point, since the degree of tallness is undefined at zero – the minimum value on the scale denotes a point rather than a line and it is questionable to say a point has a dimension or length. Such worry also applies for Kennedy (2001).

In summary, I showed that negative antonyms do appear in MP constructions in languages such as German and Mandarin, which calls for an amendment of existing accounts.

3. Inherent polarity

As Schwarzschild (2005) noted, MP constructions are more marked than comparatives cross-linguistically and adjectives that appear in MP constructions are idiosyncratic. This view is strongly supported by new data, as in (18), *chang* and *jiu* both denotes the scale of length in Mandarin, yet only *chang* can appear in MP constructions (18a-b). Similarly, German and Dutch also have adjectives that share a similar scale but differ in their ability to license MP modification (18c-f).

(18) *Mandarin*

- a. 30 fenzhong **chang** ‘30 minutes long’

b. *30 fenzhong **jiu** '30 minutes long'

Dutch

c. 250 mph **snel** '250 mph fast' (as in the speed of car)

d. *250 mph **sterk** '250 mph strong' (as in the speed of wind)

German

e. £200 **teuer** '£200 expensive'

f. *£200 **reich** '£200 rich'

Moreover, the new data show that negative antonyms are more marked than their positive counterparts in MP constructions. This markedness is indeed observed cross-linguistically – if a negative antonym allows direct MP modification, its positive counterpart will allow direct MP modification, but not vice versa, which is shown in (19).

(19) *Mandarin*

a. 2 m gao/ *ai/ chang/ %duan/ kuan/ %zhai
'2 m tall/ *short/ long/ %short/ wide/ %narrow'

German

b. 20 Dezibel laut/ *leise

'20 decibel loud/ *soft'

c. 25 Meilen pro Stunde schnell/ *langsam

'25 mph fast/ *slow'

In a nutshell, new data show that adjectives in MP constructions are lexically idiosyncratic, which is in line with the Homonym Rule (Schwarzschild 2005). It is also shown that negative antonyms are less likely to appear in MP construction, which suggests a weaker restriction of MP modification than previously predicted.

Instead of stressing the correlation between finite intervals and MPs (Kennedy 2001, Schwarzschild 2005 a.o.), I propose that the markedness of negative antonyms in MP constructions can be explained by the inherent polarity of MPs. In other words, MPs are inherently downward monotonic – in sentences where MPs serve as predicates (20a-b), if $d+1$ ($d>0$) is included in the set of degrees, then d is also included, as in (20c-d).

(20) *Mandarin*

a. Yuehan **25 sui** ***da**.

John 25 years old

John (is) 25 years old.

b. zhe jian chenshan **100 yuan** ***gui**

this CL shirt 100 yuan expensive

This shirt (is) 100 yuan.

c. { d : John is d -years} = {1, 2, ..., 25} = (0, 25]

d. { d : shirt is d -yuan} = {1, 2, ..., 100} = (0, 100]

- (21) a. John is 4 feet (tall). → John is at least 3 feet (tall)./ John is taller than 3 feet.
 b. *John is 4 feet short. → #John is at least 3 feet short./ #John is shorter than 3 feet.

This inherent polarity of MPs leads to a contrast of polarity in MP constructions with negative antonyms, since negative antonyms are upward monotonic (Bartsch and Vennemann 1972, Rett 2015 etc.). Therefore, the polarity contrast makes it more difficult for negative antonyms to license direct MP modification, as shown in (21).

This analysis of MP polarity correctly predicts the contrast of grammaticality between **John is 4 feet short* and *John is 4 feet shorter*. In the MP construction, the MP *4 feet* is associated with a scale of shortness that is upward monotonic (21b), while in the comparative, the MP is related to a scale that is downward monotonic (22). Thus, to modify negative antonyms in MP constructions, the MP must have its polarity reversed, as in (23). The following sections will show that this polarity can indeed be reversed by a lexical morpheme [POLAR] and is sometimes sensitive to different contexts.

- (22) John is 4 feet shorter (than Mary). → John is at least 3 feet shorter (than Mary)./ The gap of height between John and Mary is more than 3 feet.

- (23) a. {d: John is d-feet shorter} = {1, 2, ..., 4} = (0, 4]
 b. {d: John is d-feet short} = {4, 5, 6, ...} = [4, +∞)

3.1 POLAR application

As shown above, the ability of gradable adjectives to license direct MP modification is a lexical idiosyncrasy (Schwarzschild 2005). I revise the Homonym Rule to allow its application to negative antonyms, which is shown in (24), and propose a [POLAR] application rule which applies to certain adjectives, as shown in (25).

- (24) a. Homonym Rule: from degrees to intervals.
 (if A has meaning A' that relates individuals to degrees then A has a secondary meaning relating individuals to sets of degrees (intervals).

The secondary meaning is given by: $\lambda I. \lambda x. I = \{d: A'(x, d)\}$

- b. Homonym Rule applies to tall/ short, wide/ narrow, deep/ shallow, thick/ thin, old/ young, long/ short, high/ low and others.

(revised from Schwarzschild 2005: 216)

- (25) a. [POLAR] application: if the adjective relates individuals to scales that are upward monotonic/ downward monotonic, then it can license MPs and command them to be upward monotonic/ downward monotonic.

b. [POLAR] applies to *hou/ bao* 'thick/ thin', *kuan/ zhai* 'wide/ narrow' and others in Mandarin, *lang/ kurz* 'long/ short', *breit/ schmal* 'wide/ narrow' and others in German.

To explain, for *heavy* in English, the Homonym Rule does not apply (Schwarzschild 2005), which makes it unable to license MP modification (e.g. *5 kg *heavy*). For *tall* and *short*, both can relate individuals to intervals, however, since [POLAR] does not apply to either of them, the polarity of *short* contradicts with the that of MPs, which contributes to the contrast between *5 feet tall* and **5 feet short*. On the other hand, for adjectives like *lang* ‘long’ and *kurz* ‘short’ in German, the [POLAR] morpheme scopes over the MP and determines the its polarity. For *lang* ‘long’, the inherent polarity of MP coincides with that of *lang* ‘long’, so the [POLAR] is vacant, while for *kurz* ‘short’, the polarity of MP is reversed and thus allow it to modify the negative antonym, as in (26).

- (26) a. for 3 Meter, {d: d-mm} = (0, 3]
 b. for [POLAR[3 Meter [kurz]]], {d: d-mm} = [3, +oo)

Another observation that supports this approach is that in Mandarin, ungrammatical MP constructions can be made acceptable once the adjective is combined with the morpheme *name* (27). I argue that *name* is an overt [POLAR] morpheme in Mandarin. Native speakers find (27a) unacceptable and they cannot access the intended entailment counterpart ‘the tree is at least 4m’ or ‘the tree is at least 6m’. In contrast, after *name* is attached to the adjective *ai* ‘short’, the entailment ‘the tree is at least 6m *name-short*’ is granted and the new MP construction *5 mi name ai* ‘5m *name-short*’ is judged grammatical, as in (27b). Also, since the MP *5 mi* ‘5m’ in *5 mi name ai* ‘5m *name-short*’ is upward monotonic, as is the negative adjective *ai* ‘short’. The prediction of the polarity approach is indeed borne out.

- (27) a. *zhe ke shu **5 mi ai**. → #zhe ke shu zhishao 4 mi/ 6 mi (ai).
 this CL tree 5m short this CL tree at least 4m/ 6m short
 ‘this tree is 5m short’ ‘this tree is at least 4m/ 6m (short)’
 b. zhe ke shu **5 mi name ai**. → zhe ke shu zhishao #4 mi/ 6 mi name ai.
 This CL tree 5m name short this CL tree at least #4m/ 6m name short
 ‘this tree is 5m *name-short*’ ‘this tree is at least #4m/ 6m *name-short*.’

3.2 Contextual standard

Apart from the effect of [POLAR] application, empirical evidence also supports that the inherent polarity of MPs is sensitive to contexts, for example, (28a) is judged to be better than (28b) in Mandarin. It is further observed that, given (28a), some native speakers would judge the statement ‘the tree is at least shorter than 2m’ to be true. By contrast, when provided with (28b), native speakers find it difficult, if not impossible, to tell whether ‘the tree is at least shorter than 2m’ is true or not. This difference between (28a) and (28b) is in parallel with that between (27a) and (27b).

- (28) a. ?senlin li shu dou hen gao, zhiyou zhe ke shu **1m ai**.
 forest in tree all very tall, only this CL tree 1m short
 The trees in forest (are) all very tall, only this tree (is) 1m short.
- b. *shu **1m ai**.
 tree 1m short
 The tree is 1m short.

A plausible factor that contributes to this difference in (28a-b) is the exhaust (EXH) operator *zhiyou* ‘only’. *zhiyou* ‘only’ negates all alternatives in context, namely any tree other than this tree is 1m short. This entails that all trees other than this tree are tall and are not 1m short, which gives rise to the implicature that all trees that are taller than 1m, and thus taller than this tree. This implicature could lead listeners to access the statement that ‘this tree is at least shorter than other trees whose height are above 1m’, which is contrary to the inherent polarity of the MP *1m*. The inherent polarity of MPs is thus weakened and makes the MP construction (28a) more grammatical than (28b). The sensitivity to context might also lead to the variation of judgement among different native speakers when given a context-free sentence (28b). This variation is indeed the case with negative antonyms in Mandarin (as already shown in Section 3).

Although it could be argued that *ai* ‘short’ in *1m ai* ‘1m short’ is evaluative (i.e. shorter than the contextual standard of shortness) and the context (28a) provides a contextual standard that makes it more acceptable to use the marked antonym *ai* ‘short’, similar effects of *zhiyou* ‘only’ are attested with sentences without a contextual standard in Mandarin, as shown in (29). In (29b-c), contextual standard of shortness or lightness is not entailed. For instance, it is acceptable to say that *Mary and Tom are very heavy, only John is 40kg, which is just about the average weight*. Therefore, it is more ostensible to separate the negative antonym’s ability to license MPs and its evaluative interpretation in MP constructions, which is consistent with Rett (2015, 2017)’s implicature analysis of evaluativity.

- (29) a. *1m duan ‘1m short’
 *40 kg qing ‘40kg light’
- b. ?hong shengzi he lv shengzi hen chang, **zhiyou** huang shengzi **1m duan**.
 red rope and green rope very long, only yellow robe 1m short
 The red and the green rope (are) very long, only the yellow robe (is) 1m short.
- c. ?mali he tangmu hen zhong, **zhiyou** yuehan **40kg qing**.
 Mary and Tom very heavy only John 40kg light
 Mary and Tom (are) very heavy, only John (is) 40kg light.

4. MP as half-open interval

To account for the markedness of negative antonyms in MP constructions, in Section 3, I propose a polarity analysis of MPs which argue that the inherent polarity of

MPs contradicts with the polarity of negative antonyms. This section aims to explain how MPs license antonym pairs and the current analysis is consistent with Rett (2015)'s approach of evaluativity to explain why negative antonyms in MP constructions are evaluative.

As already discussed in section 1 and 2, new data present challenges to existing analysis (e.g., Kennedy 2001, Schwarzschild 2005, Breakstone2012) which argues that MPs are only defined over fully bounded intervals and prohibits negative antonyms from licensing MPs. I propose a modified interval analysis of MPs based on Schwarzschild (2005)'s approach. I argue that MPs are defined over intervals that are bounded by a maximum value and MPs denote the maximum value of the set. This analysis would still require the adjective to relate individuals to intervals, which is compatible with the Homonym Rule (Schwarzschild 2005 and the revised the version in Section 3). Yet, it would allow negative antonyms to license direct MP modification as long as the polarity of MPs agrees with that of the adjective. To be specific, for *0.4 mm bao* '0.4mm thin' in Mandarin, after the application of [POLAR], the interval over which the MP is defined has the maximum value of thinness (i.e. 0.4 mm). The sentence *zhi 0.4 mm bao* 'the paper is 0.4mm thin' is thus read as the interval of degrees to which the paper is thin has the maximal value of thinness of 0.4 mm.

The current analysis also eliminates potential problems discussed in Section 2.2, namely it is more compatible with antonym pairs associated with scales that do not have a minimum value or zero point. First of all, the current analysis argues that MPs are defined over intervals bounded with a maximal value instead of fully bounded intervals. Thus, for scales that start with zero point, whether the zero point is included in the scale or not does not interfere with the grammaticality of the MP construction. Furthermore, my analysis can also be extended to adjectives associated with scales that have no zero points. For *-5°c kalt* '-5°c cold' in German, since both Homonym Rule and [POLAR] morpheme can be applied to *kalt* 'cold', the adjective *kalt* 'cold' can denote an interval partially bounded by its maximum value of coldness (i.e. -5°c) though with infinitely many degrees.

A further observation suggests it is the inherent polarity of MP rather than the boundedness of intervals that affects the grammaticality of MP-negative antonym constructions. The data are provided in (30-31). (30b) provides a fully bounded scale related to narrow. In other words, because the width of the table is no longer the its length, the interval to which the table is narrow is a closed set [1, 3]. For Kennedy (2001), the MP *Im* denotes positive degrees and thus cannot modify the negative antonym *zhai* 'narrow', which fails to predict that some native speakers judge (30b) to be grammatical. For Schwarzschild (2005), unlike (30a), the MP in (30b) measures the size a closed set. It would then be predicted that (30b) is more grammatical than (30a). However, native speakers find (30b) no better than (30a). Also, imagine that the strength value of a certain person is defined over a closed set [0, 500], the interval analysis predicts (31a) and (31b) to be equally good, given that both [0,300] and [300, 500] are

fully bounded intervals. However, (31b) is still judged as unacceptable by native speakers. This contrast is predicted under the polarity approach, since [POLAR] is not in the lexicon of *di* ‘low’ in Mandarin, as in (14) and (25), there would still be contradiction of polarity between MP and *di* ‘low’.

- (30) a. %zhe zhang zhuozi 1 mi zhai
 this CL table 1m narrow
 ‘This table (is) 1m narrow’.
- b. %zhe zhang 3 mi chang de zhuozi 1 mi zhai
 this CL 3m long GEN table 1m narrow
 ‘This 3m long table (is) 1m narrow’
- (31) a. %**300 dian gao** de nengli zhi.
 300 points high GEN strength value
 ‘(the) 300 points high strength value’
- b. ***300 dian di** de nengli zhi.
 300 points low GEN strength value
 ‘(the) 300 points low strength value’

A remaining problem is the contrast of evaluativity. As presented in Section 2, negative antonyms, unlike their positive counterparts, are evaluative in MP constructions (32). This contrast is problematic for previous generalisations such as Bierwisch (1989) and accounts such as Breakstone (2012) who argue that only non-evaluative adjectives can license MPs. I argue that the present analysis of MPs, along with Rett (2015)’s account for evaluativity can better account for this contrast. Rett (2015, 2017) argues that antonym sensitive evaluativity in expressions like equatives and degree questions is a Manner implicature. The Manner implicature is conveyed by the marked construction among M-alternatives. And since negative antonyms are more marked compared to positive ones (among others Lehrer 1985; Heim 2007), they become evaluative. However, Rett also adopted Schwarzschild (2005)’s MP analysis, and observed that, to account for MP constructions with negative antonyms in Dutch (Doetjes 2012), this analysis might need further amendment.

(32) *Mandarin*

- a. zhe zhi **3 mm hou**, (hen bao).
 this paper 3 mm thick very thin
 ‘This paper (is) 3 mm thick, (it’s) very thin.’
- b. zhe zhi **3 mm bao**, (*hen hou).
 this paper 3 mm thin very thick
 ‘This paper (is) 3 mm thin, (it’s) very thick.’

As discussed above, the current analysis proposes that MPs are defined over intervals bounded with a maximal value instead of fully bounded intervals, which eliminates the strong restriction against MP-negative antonyms combinations in Schwarzschild (2005)'s account. The current MP approach also suggests a contrast of polarity leads to the markedness of MP-negative antonyms constructions (see Section 4 for detailed analysis). In other words, the polarity of negative antonyms is in contrast with the inherent polarity of MPs, which make negative antonyms more marked in MP constructions. This is in line with Rett's account. To clarify, without evaluativity, the two MP constructions in (32) would be synonymous. These two constructions are thus M-alternatives. However, since the MP construction with the negative antonym *bao* 'thin' is the marked construction, as in (32b), it then conveys a Manner implicature. The adjective *bao* 'thin' in *3 mm bao* '3 mm thin' is then evaluative (32b).

5. Conclusion and further questions

The paper presents cross-linguistic data that show negative antonyms can license direct MP modifications, which contrasts the prediction of most existing accounts. By examining the role of polarity in MP constructions, I argue that there is a general markedness of negative antonyms in MP constructions and this markedness is the result of the contrast of polarity between MPs and negative antonyms. I then extend Schwarzschild (2005)'s analysis of MP constructions by proposing a [POLAR] morpheme which is only applied to certain gradable adjectives and suggesting that MPs are defined over intervals bounded by a maximal value. This approach would allow a limited set of negative antonyms with [POLAR] morpheme to license direct MP modification and would predict these negative antonyms to be evaluative in such constructions. This is compatible with the observation that the ability of antonym pairs to license MP modification is a lexical idiosyncrasy, and that negative antonyms are more marked in MP constructions.

The paper also shows that the grammaticality of MP constructions is sometimes sensitive to certain contexts. I suggested a polarity-based approach to account for this sensitivity. It is also argued that due to the variation of lexicon of negative antonyms, it is easier for native speakers of languages that allow MP-negative antonyms combinations to access entailments of MP constructions that are upward monotonic. Furthermore, I presented *name* as an overt [POLAR] morpheme in Mandarin, though further examination is needed to examine its role. Further cross-linguistic investigations are also required to examine the range of negative antonyms allowed to co-occur with MP, as well as the variation of native speakers' ability to access entailments of upward monotonic MP constructions.

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A Prosodic Analysis of Mandarin Classifiers

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This paper discusses the distribution of Mandarin classifiers and proposes the Verb Proximity Condition (VPC), which requires NP-initial classifiers in Mandarin to stay within the same intonational phrase as the verb. That is why Mandarin CI-N phrases are restricted in terms of their distribution. Finally, the VPC can explain why CI-N phrases are banned from the subject/topic positions in Mandarin. Mandarin subject/topic positions generally disallow non-specific expressions, so that non-specific CI-N phrases cannot appear in these positions (cf. Chao 1968; Huang et al. 2009; Li & Thompson 1981). Additionally, elements in subject/topic positions generally form separate I-phrases by themselves, so that in these positions, a CI-N phrase with a NP-initial classifier cannot stay within the same I-phrase with the verb, violating the VPC. This also explains why CI-N phrases as subjects are even worse than numeral expressions with overt numerals other than *yi* 'one'. The former involves a double violation (the specificity requirement on subjects and the VPC), while the latter only violates one requirement (the specificity requirement on subjects).

1. Introduction

Numerals phrases in Mandarin usually refer to Numeral (Num)-Classifier (CI)-Noun (N) expressions. A classifier in Mandarin usually requires the presence of a numeral, as shown in (1). However, there are some exceptions. When the numeral is *yi* 'one', it may be covert, resulting in CI-N phrases (e.g., Lü 1944; Chao 1968; Li & Thompson 1981; Cheng & Sybesma 1999; Li & Bisang 2012; Jiang 2012). As in (2), a classifier sometimes can appear at the initial position of a noun phrase (NP), without any numerals.

(1). *(san)-ben shu
three-CI book
'three books'

(2). Wo mai-le ben shu.
I buy-ASP CI book
'I bought a/one book.'

Since CI-N phrases are interpreted as singular, some works argue that they contain a deleted numeral *yi* 'one'. In other words, CI-N phrases are derived from *yi*-CI-N phrases by deleting the numeral (e.g., Lü 1944; Wang 1989; Yang 2001; Zhu 1982). However, interpretational and distributional differences between *yi*-CI-N phrases and CI-

N phrases have been observed and thus some works have argued against the deletion analysis (e.g., Cheng & Sybesma 1999; Li & Bisang 2012; Wang 2019; Zhang 2013, 2019). For example, CI-N phrases are prohibited from the sentence-initial position. As in (3), a *yi*-CI-N phrase can occur in the sentence-initial position, while CI-N cannot.¹ This paper will present some new observations of the distribution of Mandarin classifiers and propose that Mandarin classifiers are prosodically deficient in the sense that the classifiers in NP-initial positions have to be parsed within the same intonational phrase (I-phrase) as the verb.

- (3). *(Yi)-ge xuesheng jinlai-le.
 a-CI student enter-ASP
 ‘A student came in.’

The outline of this paper is as follows. Section 2 will summarize some previous analyses and discuss the remaining questions. Section 3 will propose a new analysis. Section 4 will conclude the paper.

2. Previous analyses

Regarding the distributional restrictions of CI-N phrases in Mandarin, some works have argued for a lexical government condition (Cheng & Sybesma 1999; Li & Bisang 2012; Li & Feng 2015). According to the government condition, CI-N phrases must be c-commanded by a head element without any intervening clausal or nominal node (see Li & Feng 2015). For example, the CI-N phrase in (4a) is c-commanded by the verb *song* ‘give’, and the CI-N phrase in (4b) is c-commanded by the focus phrase head *lian* ‘even’.

- (4). a. Wo hui song tamen ge liwu. (Li & Feng 2015)
 I will give they CI gift
 ‘I will give them a gift.’
 b. Ta lian zhang zhi dou bu gei xuesheng. (Li & Feng 2015)
 he even CI paper even not give students
 ‘He did not give the students even a piece of paper.’

¹ Note that Individual-denoting numeral expressions in Mandarin are generally considered to be indefinite non-specific expressions (e.g., Huang et al. 2009). They usually do not appear in subject or topic positions, since these positions in Mandarin do not allow non-specific readings (e.g., Chao 1968; Li & Thompson 1981; Lee 1986; Li 1996). However, *yi* ‘one’-CI-N phrases are different in this respect. They can be either specific or non-specific. Thus, Tsai (1996) noted that numeral expressions with *yi* ‘one’, but not other numerals like ‘two’ or ‘three’, can be specific (see also Huang 1987). As a result, *yi*-CI-N phrases, unlike other numeral expressions, can occur in subject positions, as in (3). More discussion will be given below.

On the contrary, the CI-N phrase in (3), as the subject, is not c-commanded by any element, violating the government condition. Hence it is prohibited in Mandarin. The CI-N phrase in (5) does have a c-commanding head element (i.e., *ruguo* ‘if’), but there is a clausal node intervening between the c-commanding head and CI-N phrase. Therefore, it is again prohibited in Mandarin.

- (5). *Ruguo* [_{IP} [**(yi)* *ge* *xuesheng*] *bing-le*] (Zhang 2019)
 if one CI student ill-ASP
 ‘If a student gets ill’

However, as noted by Zhang (2019), the government condition cannot explain the whole picture (see also Li & Feng 2015). As in (6), the CI-N phrase is c-commanded by the post-modifier element *de*, but it is still unacceptable.

- (6). *Houhou de *(yi)-ben shu* (Zhang 2019)
 Thick DE one-CI book
 ‘a thick book’

Zhang (2019) argues that in addition to the lexical government condition, the c-commanding head and the CI-N phrase have to be able to form an interpretable semantic complex. The examples in (4) are compatible with this semantic requirement. In (4a), the head *song* ‘give’ and the CI-N phrase *ge liwu* ‘a gift’ form a meaningful complex ‘send a gift’, and in (4b), the focus phrase *lian zhang zhi* ‘even a piece of paper’ is interpretable. In contrast, *de ben shu* in (6) does not form a semantic complex and is not interpretable (Zhang 2019). Thus, it violates the semantic requirement and is disallowed in Mandarin.

Another analysis is proposed by Yang (2001). Yang (2001) proposes that a classifier in Mandarin is either a lexical suffix directly attached to a numeral forming the Num+CI complex or an enclitic cliticizing onto the preceding host word in the absence of a numeral.² Yang (2001) suggests that in the absence of a numeral, demonstratives, quantifiers, and verbs can be the host for a classifier. Thus, a classifier is still licit without a numeral in the examples of (7). But the sentence in (8) shows that adjectives do not qualify as a host for a classifier.

- (7). a. *Na (yi)-ben shu hen gui.* (Yang 2001)
 that one-CI book very expensive
 ‘That book is very expensive.’

² Yang (2001) proposes that a numeral and a classifier together form a morphological complex which is a D head. As shown in (i), Num+CI is a single head for Yang, rather than two separate syntactic heads.

i. [_{DP} every [_D Num-CI [_{NP} book]]]

- b. Mei (yi)-ben shu dou yao san-kuai qian. (Yang 2001)
 every one-Cl book all cost three-dollar money
 ‘Every book costs three dollars.’
- c. Yuehan mai-le (yi)-ben shu. (Yang 2001)
 John buy-PAST one-Cl book
 ‘John bought a book.’
- (8). Na houhou-de *(yi)-ben shu hen gui. (Yang 2001)
 that thick-DE one-Cl book very expensive
 ‘That very thick book is expensive.’

Nevertheless, there are both conceptual and empirical issues with Yang’s analysis (2001). The conceptual question is that clitics usually either are very picky about their hosts, or allow anything to be their hosts. Compare here the common distinctions between verbal clitics, whose host must be a verb (as in e.g. Romance languages) and ‘second position’ clitics as in Serbo-Croatian, whose host can be anything. From this perspective, it is unclear why Mandarin classifiers, as clitics, can cliticize onto verbs, demonstratives, and quantifiers, but not adjectives, relative clauses, possessives, or other elements. Verbs, demonstratives, and quantifiers do not form a natural class. This is a strange situation which is otherwise not found with clitics.

Furthermore, a clitic and its host cannot be separated by any non-clitic elements. Therefore, the only way (9) can be grammatical is if the pronominal indirect object (i.e., *tamen* ‘them’) is also a clitic which has already cliticized onto the verb. Only this way can the classifier *ben* in the direct object be able to cliticize onto the verb. However, there is evidence that a pronominal indirect object is not a clitic in Mandarin. Consider (10), which contains a proper name as the indirect object. The element intervening between the verb and the *yi*-Cl-N phrase is clearly not a clitic, but *yi* ‘one’ can still be covert here.

- (9). Yuehan song-le tamen ?(yi)-ben shu.
 John give-PAST them one-Cl book
 ‘John gave them a book.’
- (10). Yuehan song-le Zhangsan (yi)-ben shu.
 John give-PAST Zhangsan one-Cl book
 ‘John gave Zhangsan a/one book.’

In addition, the example in (11) shows that the intervening element can be quite long. With a relative clause between the verb and the *yi*-Cl-N phrase, *yi* still can be covert. These facts are not expected under Yang’s (2001) clitic analysis.

- (11). Yuehan song-le biaoxian zuihao de xuesheng (yi)-ben shu.
 John give-PAST perform best DE student one-Cl book
 ‘John gave the student who performed the best a/one book.’

More interestingly, if the relative clause in (11) is replaced with an appositive, *yi* ‘one’ cannot be covert, as shown by (12). Apparently, the acceptability difference between (10), (11), and (12) cannot be explained by the clitic analysis proposed by Yang (2001) or the semantic analysis by Zhang (2019).

- (12). Yuehan song-le Zhangsan, biao-xian zui-hao de xue-sheng, *(yi)-ben shu.
 John give-PAST Zhangsan perform bes DE student one-CI book
 ‘John gave Zhangsan, the student who performed the best, a/one book.’

3. A New Analysis: Verb Proximity Condition

There is an obvious prosodic difference between a relative clause and an appositive which distinguishes (11) and (12). Appositives form separate intonational phrase (I-phrases). This means that a distinct I-phrases intervenes between the verb and *(yi)-ben shu* in (12), but not in (11). Nespor and Vogel (1986), Selkirk (1986), and Hayes (1989), among many others, have proposed a hierarchical structure for the prosody of utterances, which is partially determined by the syntactic structure of the sentences. This prosodic hierarchy includes: syllable, foot, prosodic word (ω), phonological phrase (φ), and intonational phrase (ι) (Selkirk 1986). In this paper, following standard assumptions, I assume that each clause corresponds to a single intonational phrases (I-phrase), unless the clause is interrupted by elements that form separate I-phrases.³ Such elements include appositives and heavy fronted elements. They form separate I-phrases and are usually followed by pauses (Bošković 2001).

Capitalizing on this, I propose that classifiers are prosodically deficient in the sense that when they occur in NP-initial positions, they have to be parsed within the same intonational phrase as the verb. I will refer to this constraint as the Verb Proximity Condition (VPC), as in (13).⁴

(13). *Verb Proximity Condition (VPC)*

In Mandarin, when a classifier occurs in the initial position of a traditional nominal phrase, it has to be parsed within the same I-phrase as the verb.

According to the VPC, elements that form separate I-phrases cannot be inserted between a NP-initial classifier and the verb, because these elements will prevent the NP-initial classifier from staying within the same I-phrase as the verb.⁵ In (12), the

³ There are some exceptions but they need not concern us here.

⁴ For a similar prosodic condition, see Sener (2006), who proposes a prosodic condition regarding focused *wh*/focused phrases and the verb in Turkish.

⁵ Note that I focus on NP-initial classifiers in this section. A potential analysis for classifier that are not NP-initial is that they are also phonologically deficient and phonologically depend on the word that immediately precedes them within the nominal phrase. Under this analysis, Num-CI-N

appositive, which has to be followed by a pause, forms a separate I-phrase, and thus the classifier in the direct object is not parsed in the same I-phrase as the verb. Therefore, without *yi* ‘one’, the sentence violates the VPC, since the NP-initial classifier (i.e., *-ben*) does not stay with the same I-phrase as the verb.

Also, when a pause is inserted after the indirect object in (10) and (11), *yi* ‘one’ must surface. In (14), a pause, indicated by the double hash mark, is inserted between the indirect object and the direct object. In this case, *yi* ‘one’ cannot be null. Following the VPC, the unacceptability of a CI-N phrase in (14a) and (14b) is expected. The NP-initial classifier needs to stay within the same I-phrase as the verb, but the inserted pause disrupts the prosodic phrasing (since it introduces an additional I-phrase). Therefore, with an inserted pause, *yi* ‘one’ has to surface in (14).

- (14). a. Yuehan song-le Zhangsan ## *(yi)-ben shu.
 John give-PAST Zhangsan one-CI book
 ‘John gave Zhangsan a/one book.’
 b. Yuehan song-le biaoXian zuihao de xuesheng ## *(yi)-ben shu.
 John give-PAST perform best DE student one-CI book
 ‘John gave the student who performed the best a/one book.’

Recall now that CI-N phrases cannot occur in subject or topic positions, as in (15). This can also follow from the Verb Proximity Condition, given that subjects and topics are generally assumed to form separate I-phrases, which means that a NP-initial classifier within a topic or a subject could not be parsed in the same I-phrase as the verb.

- (15). *ge nanhai chi-le dangao.
 CI boy eat-PAST cake
 Intended: ‘A boy ate the cake.’

phrases, Dem-CI-N phrases, and *mei* ‘every’-CI-N phrases are allowed because the phonologically deficient classifiers within them have a word preceding them within the same nominal phrase. However, a classifier cannot directly follow a possessor or an adjective, as in (i) and (ii).

- | | | | |
|----|---|-----|--|
| i. | Zhangsan de *(yi)-ben shu
Zhangsan DE one-CI book
‘Zhangsan’s book’ | ii. | hongse de *(yi)-ben shu
red DE one-CI book
‘a/one book which is red’ |
|----|---|-----|--|

The issue here could be that the element immediately preceding the classifier in (i) and (ii) is *de*. It is possible that *de* cannot support phonologically deficient classifiers within nominal phrases. I will leave this issue open for future research.

However, such cases may also be ruled out independently, given that subject and topic positions in Mandarin disallow non-specific expressions (cf. Chao 1968; Li & Thompson 1981), and that numeral expressions in Mandarin are generally interpreted as non-specific (cf. Huang et al. 2009). In (16), a non-specific numeral expression occurs in the subject position, so the sentence is degraded.

- (16). *??san-ge xuesheng chi-le dangao.*
 three-CI student eat-PAST cake
 ‘Three students ate the cake.’ (Huang et al. 2009)

Importantly, note that (15), with a CI-N phrase as the subject, is even worse than (16), with a non-specific numeral expression as the subject. This contrast can be explained under the current analysis. The example in (16) violates the ‘specificity’ requirement on the subject position, while (15) violates both the ‘specificity’ requirement on the subject position and the Verb Proximity Condition on NP-initial classifiers. According to Wang (2019), a CI-N phrase, which involves a covert numeral *yi* ‘one’, is interpreted as non-specific. The Verb Proximity Condition requires the NP-initial classifier in a CI-N phrase to be parsed within the same I-phrase as the verb. However, as noted above, a subject forms a separate I-phrase. Then, the NP-initial classifier in (15), which is in the subject position, cannot be parsed in the same I-phrase as the verb. Therefore, (15), which has a non-specific CI-N phrase as the subject, involves a double violation and is worse than (16), which involves only one violation.

4. Conclusion

To sum up, this paper has discussed the distribution of Mandarin classifiers. I have proposed the Verb Proximity Condition (VPC), which requires NP-initial classifiers in Mandarin to stay within the same intonational phrase as the verb. That is why Mandarin CI-N phrases are restricted in terms of their distribution. Regarding the distribution of CI-N phrases, the Verb Proximity Condition (VPC) displays advantages, compared with the government condition (Cheng & Sybesma 1999; Li & Bisang 2012; Li & Feng 2015), the semantic analysis by Zhang (2019), and the clitic analysis by Yang (2001). Finally, the VPC, together with the observations that CI-N phrases lack specific readings, explains why CI-N phrases are banned from the subject/topic positions in Mandarin. Mandarin subject/topic positions generally disallow non-specific expressions, so that non-specific CI-N phrases cannot appear in these positions. Additionally, elements in subject/topic positions generally form separate I-phrases by themselves, so that in these positions, a CI-N phrase with a NP-initial classifier cannot stay within the same I-phrase with the verb, violating the VPC. This also explains why CI-N phrases as subjects are even worse than numeral expressions with overt numerals other than *yi* ‘one’. The former involves a double violation (both the specificity requirement on subjects and the

VPC), while the latter only violates one requirement (i.e., the specificity requirement on subjects).

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On the Mandarin Distributive Marker *Gezi*

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This paper focuses on the distributive/one-on-one ambiguity phenomenon of Chinese *gezi* and tries to explain it by showing two different LFs with the same denotation of *gezi*. Following Champollion's (2016) reformulation of D operators in Neo-Davidsonian algebraic event semantics, I claim that *gezi* applies to different event predicates and make the sum event available for further modification by arguments and adjuncts.

0. Introduction

In the literature, the Mandarin adverbial *gezi* has been seen as a distributive marker (Yang 2012). For instance, (1) says that each of the children in the relevant group left, and (2) says that each member in the relevant group ate an apple.

- (1) Naxie xiaohai gezi likai le. (Yang 2012; p 30)
those children GEZI leave ASP
'Those kids left separately.'
- (2) Tamen gezi chi-le yi-ge pingguo.
They GEZI eat-ASP one-CL apple
'They each ate an apple.'

Nevertheless, it has not been noted that *gezi* may bring up an ambiguity when it occurs with a transitive verb. Consider (3). Just like (1) and (2), (3) carries a reading which says that each of the tuners repaired 9 pianos; hence, in a situation in which (3) is true on such a reading, there are 81 pianos in total that were repaired. On the other hand, (3) may be true as well in a situation in which each tuner repaired one (and only one) piano, and there are only 9 pianos that were repaired. Throughout this paper, I call the reading that makes (3) true in such a situation a **one-on-one branching** reading.

- (3) Zhe jiu-wei tiaoyinshi gezi xiuli jiu-bu gangqin.
This nine-CL tuners GEZI repair nine-CL pianos
Reading 1: 'These nine tuners each repaired nine pianos.' (distributive)
Reading 2: 'There are nine pianos and each of these nine tuners repaired one piano.'
(one-on-one branching)

The one-on-one branch reading, which says that each of the four people sat in one corner of a house, is even more salient in (4); in fact, it is the only sensible reading, given that under normal circumstance, one individual cannot appear in more than one corner.

- (4) Zhe si-ge ren gezi zuo-zai wuzi-de si-ge jiaoluo.
 this four-CL people GEZI sit-at house-MOD 4-CL corners
 ‘Each of these four people sat in one of the four corners of the house.’

The existence of the one-on-one reading of *gezi* is further evidenced by the following examples acquired through Google. (5)-(7) make the same point as (4) does. In (8) the continuation of the sentence where *gezi* occurs clearly indicates that each of these composers composed one piece, not three.

- (5) Wushilan tichu yi-ge jianyi, na jiushi si-ge ren gezi zuo-zai
 p.n. purpose one-CL advice that is four-CL people GEZI sit-at
 wuzi-de di-ge jiaoluo.
 house-MOD 4-CL corners
 ‘Wushilan purposed that four people sit at four corners in the house respectively.’

- (6) Fumu keyi gezi zhan-zai liangtou.
 parents can GEZI stand-at two-sides
 ‘The parents can stand at two sides respectively.’

- (7) Ma Long he Xu Xin liang-wei zhongguo xuanshou, gezi zhenshou
 p.n. and p.n. 2-CL Chinese player GEZI defend
 shang xia ban qu.
 upper lower half zone
 ‘Two Chinese players Ma Long and Xu Xin defended upper and lower half zone respectively.’

- (8) Tamen san-ge ren gezi chuangzuo san-shou qumu, Guo Minqin-de
 they 3-CL people GEZI create 3-CL song p.n.-POSS
 Mai...,... zuopin Jinmo..., Ren Zhong-de xin-zuo Che...
Mai song *Jinmo* p.n.-POSS new-song *Che*
 ‘These three people composed three songs respectively, Guo Minqin's *Mai*...Pan Yitong's song *Jinmo*...Ren Zhong's new song *Che*...’

As will be shown below, while the distributive reading of *gezi* is expected from the previous analysis, the one-on-one branch reading is not. Note that *gezi* with a transitive verb does not always give to a one-on-one branching reading. Consider the modalized sentences in (9)-(10). In (9), *gezi* occurs after the modals *must/should*, the

sentence is ambiguous between a distributive reading and a one-on-one branching reading. Nevertheless, such ambiguity disappears in (10), where *gezi* precedes the modal *must/should*. The result is that the only available interpretation of the sentence is the distributive reading.

- (9) Zhe san-ge ren bixu/yinggai gezi wancheng san-ge renwu.
 this 3-CL people must/should GEZI complete 3-CL missions
 ✓Reading 1: ‘The 3 people must/should each complete 3 missions.’ (distributive)
 ✓Reading 2: ‘Each of the 3 people must/should complete 1 mission, and there must/should be 3 missions completed.’ (one-on-one branching)
- (10) Zhe san-ge ren gezi bixu/yinggai wancheng san-ge renwu.
 this 3-CL people GEZI must/should complete 3-CL missions
 ✓Reading 1: ‘The 3 people each must/should complete 3 missions.’ (distributive)
 *Reading 2: ‘Each of these 3 people must/should complete 1 mission, and there must/should be three missions completed.’ (one-on-one branching)

The contrast between (9) and (10) suggests that the presence of the one-on-one branching reading of *gezi* is syntactically constrained. The lack of this reading when *gezi* occurs before the modal is further evidenced by the oddity of (11); given that (11), according to our world knowledge, only makes sense on the one-on-one branching reading, the oddity observed suggests that such reading is not available.

- (11) #Na si-ge ren gezi bixu/yinggai zuo-zai si-ge jiaoluo.
 that 4-CL people GEZI must/should sit-at 4-CL corners
 ‘The 4 people each must/should each sit at 4 corners.’

The focus of this paper is on the one-on-one branch reading of *gezi* observed in the examples above; the goal is to (i) have a uniform analysis for the distributive and the one-on-one reading of *gezi*, and (ii) account for the syntactic restriction on the presence of the one-on-one reading shown in (9)-(11). The analysis I suggest is couched on the Neo-Davidsonian event semantics along the lines of Champollion (2016).

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 1 I reviewed some of the previous analysis of *gezi* and *ge*. As we know, *ge* is another distributive marker in Mandarin that might bear some morphological relevance with *gezi*. In Section 2, following the theoretical assumption of Champollion (2016), I propose the denotation of *gezi* and two different LF that *gezi* may involve to cause the ambiguity, which can be proved by the prediction with modals in some sentences. Section 3 concludes the paper.

1. Literature Review

In this section I review Yang's (2012) analysis of *gezi*, which to my knowledge is the only discussion of this distributive marker to be found in the literature. Morphologically, the distributive marker *gezi* can be divided into two morphemes; *ge* may be seen as the Mandarin counterpart of English adverbial *each* (e.g., *John and Mary each* ate an apple), and *zi* may be seen a reflexivizer. Given the morphological relevance, some analyses of the syntax and semantics of *ge*, namely Lin (1998) and Soh (2005), will be reviewed as well.

In Lin's (1998) analysis, *ge* must be associated with a distributable argument (e.g., in (12), *yi-dong fangzi* (one house)) and quantifies over a plural NP, crucially, the NP that *ge* quantifies over should be originated from the same clause.

- (12) Laowang he Laoli ge mai-le yi-dong fangzi
 p.n and p.n GE buy-ASP one-CL house
 'Laowang and Laoli each bought a house.'

Lin (1998) observes that *ge* cannot adjoin to a site higher than vP, since *ge* can only appear after a sentence-level element, including modals, sentential adverbs, negation markers, and aspect markers (see (13)).

- (13) a. Mei-ge xuesheng hui ge jiao yi-pian zuowen gei wo.
 every-CL student will GE hand one-CL composition give me
 'Each of the students will hand a composition to me.'
 (Lin 1998; p 9)
- b. *Mei-ge xuesheng ge hui jiao yi-pian zuowen gei wo.
 every-CL student GE will hand one-CL composition give me
 (Lin 1998; p 9)

Building on Lin's (1998) observation, Soh (2005) proposes that *ge* may adjoin to a vP or a VP. The fact that *ge* occurs before a manner/instrumental adverb (see (14)) and a goal/source phrase (see (15)) suggests that its adjunction site may be at least as high as vP.

- (14) a. Gongren-men ge henhen-de zou-le Lisi yi-dun.
 worker-PL GE fiercely beat-ASP Lisi one-CL
 'Each of the workers gave Lisi a fierce blow.'
- b. ??Gongren-men henhen-de ge zou-le Lisi yi-dun.
 worker-PL fiercely GE beat-PERF Lisi one-CL
 'Each of the workers gave Lisi a fierce blow.' (Lin 1998; p 12-13)

- (15) a. Mei-ge guojia ge cong Riben-ren nar xuedao-le yi-dian dongxi.
 every-CL country GE from Japanese there learn-PERF one-CL thing
 ‘Each of the countries learns something from the Japanese.’
- b. Mei-ge guojia cong Riben-ren nar ge xuedao-le yi-dian dongxi.
 every-CL country from Japanese there GE learn-PERF one-CL thing
 ‘Each of the countries learns something from the Japanese.’ (Lin 1998; p 13)

The fact that *ge* may occur after the verb in a double-object sentence (see (16a)) suggests that *ge* may adjoin to VP.

- (16) a. Tamen ge yao-le na-ge pingguo yi kou.
 they GE bite-ASP that-CL apple one mouth
 ‘They each took a bite of the apple.’
- b. Ta yao-le na san-ge pingguo ge yi kou.
 he bite-ASP that three-CL apple GE one mouth
 ‘He took a bite of each of the three apples.’

Yang (2012) has several observations on *gezi*. Related to the issue under investigation in this paper, she claims that *gezi*, unlike *ge*, can only be associated with the subject that refers to a sentient individual.

- (17) a. Naxie ren ge/gezi chi-le yi-ge hanbao.
 those man GEZI eat-ASP one-CL hamburger
 ‘Those people ate a hamburger separately.’
- b. Na ji mian qiang ge/*gezi tie-le yi-zhang haibao.
 those several surface wall GEZI paste-ASP one-CL poster
 ‘Those walls each got one poster stuck on.’

Yang (2012) also claims that semantically *gezi* only operates on events, while *ge* may operate on events or individuals. Furthermore, in her analysis, the adjunction site of *gezi* is higher than VP.

None of the analyses reviewed above provides an account for the ambiguity observed in (3). As noted above, (3), in addition to having a distributive reading, may carry an one-on-one branch reading. Hence, simply extending to *gezi* the analysis of *ge* according to which *ge* adjoins to a predicate, be it a VP or *vP*, and functions as a

distributive operator semantically, we would expect that (3) carries only a distributive reading.

2. Proposal for *gezi*

In this section I take the Neo-Davidsonian event semantics along the lines of Champollion (2016) as the theoretical assumption. Based on that I will try to propose a uniform analysis for the distributive and the one-on-one reading of *gezi*.

2.1 Theoretical Assumption

Champollion (2016a) assumes that singular count nouns involve reference to atoms, thematic roles are cumulative partial functions and verbs are cumulative event predicates. He uses the following typing conventions: t for truth values, e for ordinary objects, v for events. The symbols x, y, z, x', y', z' and so on stand for variables that range over ordinary objects, and the symbols e, e', e'' , for events. He uses P for (variables that range over) predicates of type $\langle e, t \rangle$, V for predicates of type $\langle v, t \rangle$, and θ as well as Θ for functions of type $\langle v, e \rangle$.

Champollion (2016) proposes to redefine the distributive operator as follows:

(18) Definition: Event-based D operator

$$\llbracket D_{\theta} \rrbracket = \lambda V \lambda e [e \in * \lambda e' (V(e') \wedge \text{Atom}(\theta(e')))]$$

This operator applies to an event predicate V , such as a verb phrase. It returns another event predicate, one which holds of any event e as long as it consists of one or more events that are in V and which are each mapped by the function θ to an atom. He assumes that θ is a free variable that is resolved to a thematic role — formally, a function that maps events to their agents, themes, and so on.

The examples in (19) and (20) illustrate how the D operator in (18) works. (19) gives a baseline, scopeless reading that does not use the D operator. Sentence (20) shows the D operator in action to model a distributive reading.

(19) a. The boys saw a monkey.

b. $\exists e [* \text{agent}(e) = \text{boy} \wedge * \text{see}(e) \wedge \text{monkey}(\text{theme}(e))]$

‘There is a potentially plural seeing event whose agents sum up to the boys, and whose theme is one monkey. That is, only one monkey is seen.’

(20) a. The boys $[D_{\text{agent}} [\text{saw a monkey}]]$.

b. $\exists e [* \text{agent}(e) = \text{boy} \wedge e \in * \lambda e' (* \text{see}(e') \wedge \text{monkey}(\text{theme}(e')) \wedge \text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')))]$

‘There is an event whose agents sum up to the boys, and this event consists of seeing events for each of which the agent is an atom and the theme is a monkey.’

Following Pylkkänen (2008), Champollion (2016) assumes that thematic roles are introduced into the compositional derivation by θ -role heads, and distance-distributive items (e.g. *each*) in certain languages including English must be coindexed with a θ -role head in their clause. Accordingly, he refers to this coindexation as θ -indexing. In assuming that θ -indexing is binding-theoretic in nature, he follows previous semantic analyses that interpret adnominal *each* without any movement, such as Zimmermann (2002b).

2.2 The Semantics of *gezi*

Here I follow Champollion (2016)'s reformulation of D operators in Neo-Davidsonian algebraic event semantics, and propose that *gezi* has the following denotation:

$$(21) \llbracket \text{gezi} \rrbracket = \lambda P_{\langle v, t \rangle}. \lambda e_v. e \in *[\lambda e'. P(e') \text{ and } \text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')) \text{ and } \neg \exists e'' [e'' \sqsubseteq e' \text{ and } P(e'')]]$$

I suggest that this denotation gives rise to both the distributive reading and the one-on-one branch reading. Nevertheless, these two cases differ in the scope of *gezi*.

Along with the denotation of *gezi* in (21) and the assumptions above, I suggest that the distributive reading of (22), according to which each of these 9 tuners fixed 9 pianos, is derived through the LF in (23). Note that just as Champollion (2016) assumes, the thematic roles are introduced into the compositional derivation by θ -role heads. In this LF, *gezi* adjoins to the predicate *repair 9 pianos*. The detailed semantic composition is given in (24). Here, following Heim (1982) and others, I assume that a numeral indefinite such as *9 pianos* denotes a property.

- (22) Zhe jiu-wei tiaoyinshi gezi xiuli jiu-tai gangqin.
 this 9-CL tuners GEZI repair 9-CL pianos
 'These 9 tuners each repair 9 pianos.'

(23) DISTRIBUTIVE READING

LF1:

(24)

$\llbracket \text{gezi} \rrbracket = \lambda P_{\langle v, t \rangle}. \lambda e_v. e \in *[\lambda e'. P(e') \text{ and } \text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')) \text{ and } \neg \exists e'' [e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } P(e'')]]$

$\llbracket 9 \text{ piano} \rrbracket = \lambda x. |x|=9 \text{ and } *piano(x)$

$\llbracket \text{Theme} \rrbracket = \lambda P_{\langle e, t \rangle}. \lambda e_v. P(\text{Theme}(e))$

$\llbracket \text{repair} \rrbracket = \lambda e. \text{repair}(e)$

$\llbracket \text{the 9 tuners} \rrbracket = \text{the unique } x \text{ such that } |x|=9 \text{ and } x \text{ are tuners}$

$\llbracket \text{Agent} \rrbracket = \lambda x. \lambda e. \text{agent}(e) = x$

$\llbracket \text{Theme } [9 \text{ piano}] \rrbracket = \lambda e.. |*\text{Theme}(e)|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e))$

(Functional Application)

$\llbracket \text{Agent}[\text{the 9 tuners}] \rrbracket = \lambda e. *\text{Agent}(e) = \text{the unique } x \text{ such that } |x|=9 \text{ and } x \text{ are tuners}$

(Functional Application)

$\llbracket \textcircled{3} \rrbracket = \llbracket \text{repair} \rrbracket \ \& \ \llbracket \textcircled{4} \rrbracket$

$= \lambda e.. \text{repair}(e) \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e)|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e))$

(Predicate Modification)

$\llbracket \textcircled{2} \rrbracket = \llbracket \text{GEZI} \rrbracket (\llbracket \textcircled{3} \rrbracket)$

$= \lambda P_{\langle v, t \rangle}. \lambda e_v. e \in *[\lambda e'. P(e') \text{ and } \text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')) \text{ and } \neg \exists e'' [e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } P(e'')]]$

$(\lambda e.. \text{repair}(e) \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e)|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e)))$

$= \lambda e.. e \in *[\lambda e'. \text{repair}(e') \ \& \ |*\text{Theme}(e')|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e')) \text{ and}$

$\text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')) \text{ and } \neg \exists e'' [e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } \text{repair}(e'') \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e'')|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e''))]]$

(Functional Application)

$\llbracket S \rrbracket = \llbracket \textcircled{1} \rrbracket \ \& \ \llbracket \textcircled{2} \rrbracket$

$= \lambda e. \text{agent}(e) = \text{the unique } x \text{ such that } |x|=9 \text{ and } x \text{ are tuners and } e \in *[\lambda e'.$

$\text{repair}(e') \ \& \ |*\text{Theme}(e')|=9 \text{ and } *piano(\text{Theme}(e')) \text{ and } \text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')) \text{ and}$

$\neg \exists e'' [e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } \text{repair}(e'') \ \& \ |*\text{Theme}(e'')|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e''))]]$

(Predicate Modification)

Here, $\llbracket S \rrbracket$ means that there is an event e whose agent is 9 tuners and which consists entirely of repairing events whose agents are individual tuners and whose themes are sums of 9 pianos, and there doesn't exist any sub-event of those events whose themes are sums of 9 pianos. From this and from the assumption that the agent role is a sum homomorphism, we can conclude that every tuner repaired nine pianos.

One the other hand, the one-on-one branch reading of (22), according to which each of these 9 tuners fixed 1 piano, is derived through the LF in (25).

(25) BRANCHING READING

LF2:

(25) means that V-adjoined *gezi* takes scope over its complement but — unlike VP-adjoined *gezi* — not over the whole verbal projection. The detailed semantic composition is given in (26):

(26)

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \textcircled{3} \rrbracket &= \llbracket \text{GEZI} \rrbracket (\llbracket \text{repair} \rrbracket) \\ &= \lambda e_v. e \in *[\lambda e'. \text{repair}(e') \text{ and } \text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')) \text{ and } \neg \exists e''[e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } \text{repair}(e'')]] \end{aligned}$$

(Functional Application)

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \textcircled{2} \rrbracket &= \llbracket \textcircled{3} \rrbracket \& \llbracket \textcircled{4} \rrbracket \\ &= \lambda e_v. e \in *[\lambda e'. \text{repair}(e') \text{ and } \text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')) \text{ and } \neg \exists e''[e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } \text{repair}(e'')]] \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e)|=9 \text{ and } *\text{piano}(*\text{Theme}(e)) \end{aligned}$$

(Predicate Modification)

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket S \rrbracket &= \llbracket \textcircled{1} \rrbracket \& \llbracket \textcircled{2} \rrbracket \\ &= \lambda e. \text{agent}(e) = \text{the unique } x \text{ such that } |x|=9 \text{ and } x \text{ are tuners and } e \in *[\lambda e'. \text{repair}(e') \text{ and } \text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')) \text{ and } \neg \exists e''[e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } \text{repair}(e'')]] \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e)|=9 \text{ and } *\text{piano}(*\text{Theme}(e)) \end{aligned}$$

(Predicate Modification)

Here, $\llbracket S \rrbracket$ means that there is an event e whose agent is 9 tuners and theme is 9 pianos which consists entirely of repairing events whose agents are individual tuners, and there doesn't exist any sub-event of those events. Thus we get the one-on-one branch reading, in which each of these 9 tuners repaired his one (and only one) piano, respectively.

In sum, I have proposed a single denotation of *gezi*, which may result in the availability of both distributive and one-on-one branching readings. This behavior is captured by two distinct LF structures, differentiated by the adjunction site of *gezi* either above or below the theme.

2.3 The Prediction

We can see in (27)-(29) that when modals like *bixu/yinggai* (must/should) are higher than *gezi*, we can get both distributive and one-on-one readings. On the other hand, when these modals are between *gezi* and V, we will only get the distributive reading:

(27) a. Na sigeren bixu/yinggai gezi zuo-zai si-ge jiaoluo.
 that 4 people must/should GEZI sit-at 4-CL corners
 'Those four people must/should each take a seat at one of the four corners.'
 (one-on-one branching reading)

b. #Na si-ge ren gezi bixu/yinggai zuo-zai si-ge jiaoluo.
 that 4-CL people GEZI must/should sit-at 4-CL corners
 'Those four people must/should each sit at four corners.'
 (distributive reading)

(28) Zhe jiu-wei tiaoyinshi bixu/yinggai gezi xiuli jiu-tai gangqin
 this 9-CL tuners must/should GEZI fix 9-CL pianos
 ✓ Distributive reading: 'The 9 tuners must/should each fix 9 pianos.'
 ✓ One-on-one branching reading: 'The 9 tuners must/should fix 9 pianos separately.'

(29) Zhe jiu-wei tiaoyinshi gezi bixu/yinggai xiuli jiu-tai gangqin
 this 9-CL tuners GEZI must/should fix 9-CL pianos
 ✓ Distributive reading: 'The 9 tuners must/should each fix 9 pianos.'
 ✗ One-on-one branching reading: 'The 9 tuners must/should fix 9 pianos separately.'

Following Hacquard (2009), we assume the deontic modal *must* to be as follows in (30):

(30) $\llbracket \text{must} \rrbracket = \lambda w_s \lambda P_{\langle v, t \rangle} \lambda e_v. \forall w' \text{ compatible with circumstances in } w: P(w')(e)$

When *gezi* precedes *must*, the only possible LF is (31), which leads to the distributive reading. This is consistent with native speaker intuitions for sentence (29).

(31)

(32)

$\llbracket \textcircled{4} \rrbracket = \llbracket \text{must} \rrbracket (\llbracket w \rrbracket)$
 $= \lambda P_{\langle v, t \rangle} \lambda e_v. \forall w' \text{ compatible with circumstances in } w: P(w')(e)$
 (Functional Application)

$\llbracket \textcircled{2} \rrbracket = \llbracket \textcircled{4} \rrbracket (\llbracket \textcircled{3} \rrbracket)$
 $= \lambda e_v. \forall w' \text{ compatible with circumstances in } w: \text{repair}(e) \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e)|=9$
 and $*\text{piano}(*\text{Theme}(e))$ in w'
 (Functional Application)

$\llbracket \textcircled{1} \rrbracket = \llbracket \text{GEZI} \rrbracket (\llbracket \textcircled{2} \rrbracket)$
 $= \lambda e_v. e \in *[\lambda e'. \forall w' \text{ compatible with circumstances in } w: \text{repair}(e') \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e')|=9$
 and $*\text{piano}(*\text{Theme}(e'))$ in w' and $\text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e'))$ and $\neg \exists e'' [e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } \forall w' \text{ compatible with circumstances in } w: \text{repair}(e'') \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e'')|=9$
 and $*\text{piano}(*\text{Theme}(e''))$ in $w']$
 (Functional Application)

On the other hand, when *gezi* follows *must*, there will be two possible LFs, see (33)(35). In (33), *gezi* adjoins to the whole VP (e.g. *repair 9 pianos*), while in (35), *gezi* only adjoins to the verb (e.g. *repair*), which leads to the ambiguous reading in (28).

(33)

(34)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \llbracket \textcircled{2} \rrbracket &= \llbracket \text{GEZI} \rrbracket (\llbracket \textcircled{3} \rrbracket) \\
 &= \lambda P_{\langle v, t \rangle}. \lambda e_v. e \in *[\lambda e'. P(e') \text{ and } \text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')) \text{ and } \neg \exists e'' [e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } P(e'')]] (\lambda e_v. \text{repair}(e) \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e)|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e))) \\
 &= \lambda e_v. e \in *[\lambda e'. \text{repair}(e') \ \& \ |*\text{Theme}(e')|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e')) \text{ and } \text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')) \text{ and } \neg \exists e'' [e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } \text{repair}(e'') \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e'')|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e''))]]
 \end{aligned}$$

(Functional Application)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \llbracket \textcircled{4} \rrbracket &= \llbracket \text{must} \rrbracket (\llbracket w \rrbracket) \\
 &= \lambda P_{\langle v, t \rangle}. \lambda e_v. \forall w' \text{ compatible with circumstances in } w: P(w')(e)
 \end{aligned}$$

(Functional Application)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \llbracket \textcircled{1} \rrbracket &= \llbracket \textcircled{4} \rrbracket (\llbracket \textcircled{2} \rrbracket) \\
 &= \lambda e_v. \forall w' \text{ compatible with circumstances in } w: \lambda e_v. e \in *[\lambda e'. \text{repair}(e') \ \& \ |*\text{Theme}(e')|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e')) \text{ and } \text{Atom}(\text{agent}(e')) \text{ in } w' \text{ and } \neg \exists e'' [e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } \text{repair}(e'') \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e'')|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e''))]]
 \end{aligned}$$

(Functional Application)

(35)

‘9 pianos’

(36)

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \textcircled{4} \rrbracket &= \llbracket \text{must} \rrbracket (\llbracket w \rrbracket) \\ &= \lambda P_{\langle v, t \rangle} \lambda e_v. \forall w' \text{ compatible with circumstances in } w: P(w')(e) \end{aligned}$$

(Functional Application)

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \textcircled{1} \rrbracket &= \llbracket \textcircled{4} \rrbracket (\llbracket \textcircled{2} \rrbracket) \\ &= \lambda e_v. \forall w' \text{ compatible with circumstances in } w: e \in *[\lambda e'. \text{repair}(e')] \text{ and} \end{aligned}$$

Atom(agent(e')) in w' and $\neg \exists e'' [e'' \subseteq e' \text{ and } \text{repair}(e'')] \text{ and } |*\text{Theme}(e)|=9 \text{ and } *piano(*\text{Theme}(e))$

(Functional Application)

To sum up, based on the proposed LF structures, when modals get in between *gezi* and V, the modals will obligatorily modify the sub-events as schematized in the LF in (31). When modals are higher than *gezi*, both LFs are acceptable, and thus the aforementioned distributive/one-on-one ambiguity is generated.

3. Conclusion

When the Mandarin distributive marker *gezi* occurs together with a transitive verb, it may bring up an ambiguity in which one reading is distributive, and the other is what I have called one-on-one branching reading.

This paper has presented a possible denotation of Chinese *gezi*, combining ideas from algebraic semantics Link (1983) and Neo-Davidsonian event semantics, which exposes thematic roles to the compositional process. The phenomenon of distributive/one-on-one interpretational ambiguity for such sentences has been explained by two distinct LFs, in which *gezi* combines with particular thematic roles at distinct points in the derivation.

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Generalized Scope Economy

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Scope Economy (SE) dictates that scope-shifting operations must have semantic effects, i.e. they are licensed by crossing a quantificational element. Little has been said on whether focus can be a licenser. Meanwhile, ‘quantificational elements’ are often conflated with focused/focusing elements in the discussion of Intervention Effects (IE). This paper motivates a generalized version of SE where focused elements are also proper licensors for scope-shifting operations, unifying the range of licensors in SE and interveners in IE. We present empirical evidence from the distribution of root modals in Mandarin Chinese.

1. Introduction

Chinese root modals are generally disallowed in sentence-initial positions (i.e. they follow the subject), as in (1) (taken from T.-H. J. Lin 2011:69).

- (1) ***neng** / ***hui** / ***keyi** Zhangsan zhunbei wancan
can will can Zhangsan prepare dinner
Int.: ‘Zhangsan can/ will/ may prepare the dinner.’

However, it has been observed that root modals like *neng* ‘can’, *hui* ‘will’, *keyi* ‘can/may’ or *yinggai* ‘should’ (in deontic use), if they are in A-not-A form, can appear sentence-initially (J.-W. Lin & Tang 1995, Huang, Li & Li 2009), as in (2) (taken from T.-H. J. Lin 2011:69):

- (2) **neng-bu-neng** / **hui-bu-hui** / **ke-bu-keyi** Zhangsan zhunbei wancan?¹
can-NEG-can will-NEG-will can-NEG-can Zhangsan prepare dinner
‘Can/ will/ may Zhangsan prepare the dinner?’

The contrast constitutes a long-standing puzzle in the literature of Chinese modals and has not been received a principled explanation yet.

¹ Abbreviations used in this paper: 1 = First Person; 2 = Second Person; 3 = Third Person; CL = Classifier; FOC = Focus marker; NEG = Negation; PERF = Perfect Aspect Marker; PL = Plural; Q = Question; SG = Singular; SFP = Sentence-final Particle.

This paper argues that sentence-initial *root* modals (SIMs) are indeed a more general phenomenon which interacts with focus.² To be specific, we propose that SIMs could be derived by moving a root modal across a focused element. SIMs are not licensed by the A-not-A form *per se*, but the (subject) focus triggered by A-not-A questions. It is further argued that the movement is regulated by Scope Economy (SE) which dictates that scope-shifting operations must have semantic effects (Fox 2000). That is, the movement must alter the scopal relation of a root modal and another quantificational/focused element. While little has been said on focus in Fox (2000), the interaction of SIMs and focus provides crucial evidence for a generalized version of Scope Economy that includes the alternation of focus scope as a semantic effect. Consequently, the licensors in SE and the interveners in Intervention Effects (IE) in Rizzi's (2001, 2004) are unified, which include both quantificational and focused elements.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 generalizes the licensing conditions of SIMs as immediate precedence of a focused element. Section 3 proposes a movement account for SIMs where the movement is licit only when crossing a focus, and argues against alternative base-generation approaches. Section 4 motivates a generalized version of Scope Economy with the scopal relation of SIMs and focus as well as quantifiers. Section 5 concludes by pointing to the 'mirroring' roles of a unified set of licensors in SE and interveners in IE.

2. Sentence-initial root modals and focus

Modals may be dichotomized into epistemic modals and root modals (Ross 1969, Perlmutter 1971, Jackendoff 1972).³ The well-received epistemic/root distinction is manifested in Chinese as a difference in syntactic positions, where the epistemic ones may precede canonical subjects and the root ones may not (T.-H. J. Lin 2011, Tsai 2015):

(3) Root modals may not precede the subject

(*keyi) Zhangsan (keyi) zhunbei wancan
 can Zhangsan can prepare dinner
 'Zhangsan may prepare the dinner.'

² The term "sentence-initial (root) modal" is adopted from Hsu (2016) for pre-subject root modals. It should be noted that it is just a convenient label instead of description. With the presence of sentential adverbials or topics, the pre-subject position of SIMs might not be necessarily sentence-initial.

³ The latter is a heterogeneous class which could (at least) be further divided as deontic modals and dynamic modals (Palmer 1986; see Portner 2009 for a finer classification). This paper focuses on deontic modals which have a raising structure instead of a control one (Wurmbrand 1999; see J.-W. Lin & Tang 1995 for Chinese modals).

(4) Epistemic modals may precede the subject

(**keneng**) Zhangsan (**keneng**) zhunbei-le wancan
 be.possible Zhangsan be.possible prepare-PERF dinner
 ‘Zhangsan is possible to have prepared the dinner.’

(T.-H. J. Lin 2011:50-51)

It is however observed that root modals could occur sentence-initially (i.e. preceding subjects), but only in certain occasions. The favorable contexts for SIMs are provided below which are generalized to be related to focus.

First, J.-W. Lin & Tang (1995:62, ft7) observed that insertion of narrow focus marker *shi* after the root modal would improve sentences like (3), as in (5). Importantly, *shi* must be associated with the subject. Association with the VP or object would yield a degradation of the sentence, as in (6).

(5) Shi-focus construction (subject)

Keyi shi **Zhangsan**_F qu Beijing
 can FOC Zhangsan go Beijing
 ‘It can be the case that it is Zhangsan who goes to Beijing.’

(6) Shi-focus construction (VP/ object)

*Keyi Zhangsan shi [**qu Beijing**]_F
 can Zhangsan FOC go Beijing
 Int.: ‘It can be the case that Zhangsan go to Beijing (but not do something else).’

The same contrast is also found in alternative questions with *haishi* which contains the focus marker *shi*, where only *subject* alternative questions are allowed:

(7) Disjunction questions with haishi (subjects)

Keyi **Zhangsan**_F haishi **Lisi**_F qu?
 can Zhangsan or.Q Lisi go
 ‘Zhangsan or Lisi, who may go?’

(8) Disjunction questions with haishi (objects)

*Keyi Zhangsan qu **Beijing**_F haishi **Taipei**_F?
 can Zhangsan go Beijing or.Q Taipei?
 Int.: ‘Beijing or Taipei, which one may Zhangsan go to?’

Similar can be said to contrastive focus by continuation in (9). The sentence is allowed only if the focus immediately follows the SIM.

(9) Contrastive continuation (subjects)

Keyi **ni_F** qu, ye keji **ta_F** qu
 can 2SG go also can 3SG go

‘It can be the case that you go or it also can be the case that he goes.’

(10) Contrastive continuation (verbs)

*Keyi ni **liuxia_F**, ye keyi ni **zou_F**
 can 2SG stay also can 2SG leave

Int.: ‘It can be the case that you stay or it also can be the case that you leave.’

This asymmetry may be achieved by stressing either the subject or the object in Northern Mandarin which gives rise to a contrastive reading.

(11) Accented subject

Keyi **ZHANGSAN_F** qu Beijing
 can Zhangsan go Beijing

‘It can be the case that it is Zhangsan (but not someone else) who goes to Beijing.’

(12) Accented object

*Keyi Zhangsan qu **BEIJING_F**
 can Zhangsan go Beijing

Int.: ‘It can be the case that Zhangsan go to Beijing (but not somewhere else).’

Second, *wh*-questions may also license SIMs. An SIM is licensed if it is immediately followed by a *wh*-phrase (as the subject in (13)), but it is disallowed if the *wh*-phrase is not immediately following the SIM, as the object in (14). Note that *wh*-phrases bear inherent focus interpretation (Rochemont 1986) and may thus form a natural class with the contrastive focus above.

(13) Wh-subject

Name, keyi [**shei**]_F mianfei qu Beijing?
 so can who free.of.charge go Beijing

‘Who may go to Beijing for free then?’

(14) Wh-object

*Name, keyi Zhangsan mianfei qu [**nali**]_F?
 so can Zhangsan free.of.charge go where

Int.: ‘Where may Zhangsan go for free then?’

Third, we observe polarity questions with the presence of a question intonation or a question particle may also license SIMs:

(15) Polarity question

Keyi Zhangsan qu Beijing {↗/ ma}? (↗ = rising question intonation)
 can Zhangsan go Beijing Q SFP.Q
 ‘May Zhangsan go to Beijing?’

It may be difficult to see how a question intonation/particle could be grouped with contrastive focus and *wh*-phrases at the first glance. We suggest that SIMs are however not licensed by the intonation or particles *per se*, but the focus triggered by them. The subject in polarity questions with SIMs receives focus, as indicated by the pre-subject position of the focus marker *shi* in (16). The incompatibility with VP focus in (16) also indicates that the question intonation/particle is not the true licenser, otherwise the SIMs should be licensed regardless of the focus position.

(16) Keyi (shi) **Zhangsan** (*shi) **qu Beijing** {↗/ ma}?

can FOC Zhangsan FOC go Beijing Q SFP.Q

a. ‘Can it be the case that Zhangsan but not someone else go to Beijing?’/

b. *‘Can it be the case that Zhangsan go to Beijing but not do something else?’

Following this line of reasoning, SIMs in A-not-A questions are indeed not licensed by the A-not-A form, but the subject focus being triggered. We observe that A-not-A form does not *always* license SIM:

(17) A-not-A questions

Lisi’s Mainland Travel Permit had expired, so that he cannot go to Beijing...

a. Ke-bu-keyi **Zhangsan_F** qu Beijing?

can-NEG-can Zhangsan go Beijing

‘May Zhangsan go to Beijing?’

b. *Ke-bu-keyi Lisi **qu Taipei_F**?

can-NEG-can Lisi go Taipei

Int.: ‘May Lisi go to Taipei?’

While an SIM is allowed in (a), it is disallowed in (b). The difference between (a) and (b) is that the subject is focused in the former but not the latter, again pointing to focus being a crucial licensing condition but not the A-not-A form.

Some may wonder why a A-not-A question could trigger focus. A plain A-not-A question formed by verbs (V-not-V) is a non-biased (neutral) question where the speakers presumes no polarity on the answer as in (18). It could be understood as the sentence bearing a broad focus instead of a narrow one.

(18) [Context: The speaker knows nothing about Zhangsan:]

Zhangsan qu-bu-qu Beijing?

Zhangsan go-NEG-go Beijing

‘Does Zhangsan go to Beijing?’

We suggest that this question could be answered by adopting a more fine-grained typology of A-not-A questions. A-not-A questions, as proposed by Schaffar and Chen (2001) and Tsai and Yang (2015), may be divided into two types. The first type, called inner A-not-A in Tsai & Yang’s terminology, is often formed by verbs and contribute to a neutral/broad focus interpretation. The second type (outer A-not-A) is often formed by copular *shi* (or epistemic modals) and contribute to a narrow focus interpretation. (19) exemplifies different focus possibilities in the outer A-not-A questions.

(19) a. [Context: The speaker knows that Zhangsan likes only Beijing:]

Zhangsan shi-bu-shi qu **Beijing**_F? (object focus)

Zhangsan be-NEG-be go Beijing

‘Does Zhangsan go to Beijing (but not somewhere else)?’

b. [Context: The speaker knows that only Zhangsan likes Beijing:]

shi-bu-shi **Zhangsan**_F qu Beijing? (subject focus)

be-NEG-be Zhangsan go Beijing

‘Does Zhangsan (but not someone else) go to Beijing?’

These two types of A-not-A questions are also distinguished in structural terms. Inner A-not-A questions are formed by a lower functional head located within the TP domain, while outer A-not-A questions involve a higher functional head in the CP domain (head of Pol2P in Schaffar & Chen 2001, or head of AstP in Tsai & Yang 2015). Verbs, however, are too low to move into the outer A-not-A head:

(20) *Qu-bu-qu Zhangsan_F Beijing?

go-NEG-go Zhangsan Beijing

‘Does Zhangsan (but not someone else) go to Beijing?’

We suggest that A-not-A questions formed by SIMs (= (2) & (17)) are outer A-not-A questions carrying a higher functional head in CP domain. The outer A-not-A head is responsible for the narrow focus interpretation.

Building on the distribution of focus in (#1) contrastive contexts, (#2) *wh*-questions and (#3) polarity questions (including A-not-A questions), we generalize the licensing condition of SIMs as (21):

(21) SIMs are licensed if the element immediately following them receives focus interpretation.

3. Towards a movement approach

3.1. Proposal

Following Tsai (2015), we retain the classic treatment that root modals (e.g. *keyi* ‘can/may’, deontic *yinggai* ‘should’) are base-generated below Spec TP (i.e. they are lower than the subject), and propose that SIMs can undergo head movement only when it crosses a focus, diagrammed in (22):

(22) SIM movement (*preliminary version*)

This movement is not allowed if the element immediately following the root modal does not receive a focus interpretation, hence capturing the generalization in (21). Thus, the contrast in (1) and (2) (reproduced below) can be attributed to whether the SIM moves across a focus.

(23) ***neng** / ***hui** / ***keyi** Zhangsan zhunbei wancan
 can will can Zhangsan prepare dinner
 Int.: ‘Zhangsan can/ will/ may prepare the dinner.’

(24) **neng-bu-neng** / **hui-bu-hui** / **ke-bu-keyi** Zhangsan_F zhunbei wancan?
 can-NEG-can will-NEG-will can-NEG-can Zhangsan prepare dinner
 ‘Can/ will/ may Zhangsan prepare the dinner?’

(23) is a plain declarative clause with no context triggering subject focus. *Keyi* ‘can’ thus cannot move from the TP-internal position across the non-focused subject to the sentence-initial position. (24) is an outer A-not-A question with a higher functional head in the CP domain to trigger a subject narrow focus. The movement of *keyi* is made licit by crossing the focused subject. *Keyi* further fuses with the A-not-A head to form *ke-bu-keyi*.⁴ The relevant derivations for this pair are given in (25) and (26) respectively.

(25) ***[keyi** [TP Zhangsan_{-Focus}] [_ [VP prepare dinner]]]

(26) [A-not-A [**keyi** [TP Zhangsan_{Focus}] [_ [VP prepare dinner]]]]

⁴ Note that it is *not* obligatory for the SIM to fuse with the A-not-A head, as shown below:

(i) [Shi-bu-shi [keyi Zhangsan_{Focus}] _ [zhunbei wancan]] ?
 be-NEG-be can Zhangsan prepare dinner
 ‘Is it the case that it is Zhangsan that may prepare dinner?’

This strongly supports that A-not-A form *per se* is *not* the licenser for SIMs.

It should be clarified that the proposed movement is not a focus-triggering operation, rather, it is licensed by crossing a focus. The exact mechanism of licensing will be introduced in Section 4. The movement of root modals does not trigger any focus nor create any focus position and should be carefully distinguished with clefting or other focus movement (e.g. *lian* ‘even’ focus and object shift in Mandarin Chinese), which may involve movement of the focused element itself.

Our movement account in (22) derives a subject-object asymmetry where a focused subject can license SIMs while a (in-situ) focused object cannot. Moreover, (22) predicts that an object undergone focus movement may license an SIM if the object is immediately following the SIM. The prediction is borne out:

(27) Object focus movement with SIMs

- a. Jingran keyi **lian** **GB** na-ge-laoshi dou bu-jiao, zhen lipu!
 unexpectedly can even GB that-CL-teacher also NEG-teach really unacceptable
 ‘How could that teacher not teach GB (Government & Binding theory)! That’s insane!’
- b. *Jingran keyi na-ge-laoshi **lian** **GB** dou bu-jiao, zhen lipu!
 unexpectedly can that-CL-teacher even GB also NEG-teach really unacceptable
- c. *Jingran **lian** **GB** keyi na-ge-laoshi dou bu-jiao, zhen lipu!
 unexpectedly even GB can that-CL-teacher also NEG-teach really unacceptable

3.2. *Variable landing sites*

The landing site of SIMs is variable. An SIM may move to a position right above Spec TP yet below the topic (presumably below TopicP on a cartographic clausal spine):

(28) SIMs follow the topic

- a. [Zhe-jian-dangao]_t, Zhangsan_F **yinggai** chi *t* (, bu shi ni_F)
 this-CL-cake Zhangsan should eat NEG be 2SG
- b. [Zhe-jian-dangao]_t, **yinggai** Zhangsan_F chi *t* (, bu shi ni_F) (SIM)
 this-CL-cake should Zhangsan eat NEG be 2SG
- (a)-(b): ‘This cake, it is Zhangsan that should eat (but not you).’

An SIM may also move to a pre-topic position. We have already seen that SIMs may precede a pre-subject *lian* ‘even’ focus in (27)a. (29) with a *wh*-object topic illustrates the same.

(29) SIMs precede the topic

- a. Name, [na-ge-pinpai]_F_t women **yinggai** yao yongyuan bu mai *t* ?
 so which-CL-brand 1PL should should ever NEG buy
- b. Name, **yinggai** [na-ge-pinpai]_F_t women yao yongyuan bu mai *t* ? (SIM)
 so should which-CL-brand 1PL should ever NEG buy
- (a)-(b): ‘So, which brand should we never buy?’

It is noteworthy that however far SIMs can move, they cannot move across an epistemic modal such as *keneng* ‘be.possible’:

(30) SIMs follow epistemic modals

- a. Keneng **keyi** ni_F qu (, bu-yiding yao ta qu)
 be.possible can 2SG go NEG-must should 3SG go
 ‘It is possible that it is you (but not necessarily he) that may go.’
- b. ***Keyi** keneng ni_F qu (, bu-yiding yao ta qu)
 can be.possible 2SG go NEG-must should 3SG go
- c. ***Keyi** ni_F keneng qu (, bu-yiding yao ta qu)
 can 2SG be.possible go NEG-must should 3SG go

3.3. *Alternatives*

There have been attempts to account for SIMs without resort to movement, i.e. base-generation approach. The general ideas are to treat the pre-subject SIMs base-generated in syntax differently from their post-subject root modal use, as either epistemic modals (T.-H. J. Lin 2011) or focus operators (Hsu 2016). Let’s consider the first one. T.-H. J. Lin (2011) observes that SIMs (in A-not-A form) come with an epistemic-like reading which is otherwise absent in their low positions. This suggests that SIMs may pattern with epistemic modals in terms of positional flexibility. Note that Lin’s work concerns a broader issue of finiteness in Mandarin and he at best hints at a possible explanation to SIMs. For expository reasons, we take a stronger form of his suggestion, namely, “SIMs are epistemic modals”, and see how this approach is empirically challenged.

First, genuine epistemic modals like *keneng* ‘be.possible’ impose no restriction on the focus distribution. They may freely occur in a sentence-initial position with object focus as in (31). The sentence-initial position seems to be unmarked for canonical epistemic modals. It is then unclear that why SIMs have to be licensed by a focus immediately following them if they were epistemic modals.

- (31) *Keneng ta shi qu-le Beijing_F, bu shi Taipei_F*
 be.possible 3SG FOC go-PERF Beijing NEG FOC Taipei
 ‘It is possible that he went to Beijing instead of Taipei.’

Second, root modals *neng* ‘can’ and *keyi* ‘can/may’ carry weak modal force, just as the epistemic modal *keneng* ‘be.possible’. Assuming that they bear the same existential quantifier over possible worlds and are differentiated only in modal base (Kratzer 1991), these two root modals are predicted to be synonymous with *keneng* ‘may’ in their SIM uses. This prediction is however not borne out, as shown by the contrast between (32) and (33). In (32), it is preferred for *neng* to associate with inherent ability (e.g. arms) and *keyi* to associate with permission (e.g. kids are not allowed to enter kitchens) in (a) and

(b), but not the possibility to cook. Thus, the answer concerning the absence of kitchen in (c) is infelicitous. *Keneng*, however, is merely possibility and is compatible with all the answers (a), (b) and (c).

(32) Q: **neng-bu-neng/ ke-bu-keyi** Zhangsan zhunbei wancan?
 can-NEG-can can-NEG-can Zhangsan prepare dinner
 ‘Can/ may Zhangsan prepare the dinner?’

A: (a) No, his arm is broken. (preferred for *neng*)
 (b) No, he is just a kid. (preferred for *keyi*)
 (c) %No, there is no kitchen in the house at all.

(33) Q: **ke-bu-keneng** Zhangsan zhunbei wancan?
 be.possible-NEG-be.possible Zhangsan prepare dinner
 ‘Is it possible that Zhangsan prepares the dinner?’ ≠ (32)

A: (a) No, his arm is broken. (preferred for *neng*)
 (b) No, he is just a kid. (preferred for *keyi*)
 (c) No, there is no kitchen in the house at all.

The same problem arises with *yinggai* ‘should’, which has both epistemic and deontic uses. It is predicted to be disambiguated at sentence-initial position under T.-H. J. Lin’s proposal, contrary to the ambiguity shown in (34).

- (34) a. **Yinggai**^{Epistemic} Zhangsan bu lai (, ta shengbing le)
 should Zhangsan NEG come 3SG be.sick SFP
 ‘It should be the case that Zhangsan will not come. (He is sick.)’
 b. **Yinggai**^{Deontic} Zhangsan bu lai (, bu yinggai ni bu lai)
 should Zhangsan NEG come NEG should 2SG NEG come
 ‘It is Zhangsan that should not come (but not you).’

Another piece of evidence supporting the difference between SIM *yinggai* and epistemic *yinggai* comes from modal stacking. As observed by T.-H. J. Lin (2012:157) in (35), epistemic *yinggai* (necessity) precedes *keneng* (possibility), but not the other way round.

- (35) a. Zhangsan **yinggai**^{Epistemic} keneng lai
 Zhangsan should be.possible come
 ‘It should be the case that Zhangsan is possible to come.’
 b. *Zhangsan keneng **yinggai**^{Epistemic} lai le
 Zhangsan be.likely.to should come SFP

Yet, SIM *yinggai* may follow *keneng* as in (36). This suggests that the syntactic position of SIM *yinggai* is lower than epistemic modal *keneng* as well as epistemic *yinggai*.

- (36) a. Keneng **yinggai**^{Deontic} ta_F cai shi diren
 be.possible should 3SG really be enemy
 ‘It is possible that he (but not someone else) should be the enemy.’
- b. ***Yinggai**^{Deontic} keneng ta_F cai shi diren
 should be.possible 3SG really be enemy
- c. ***Yinggai**^{Deontic} ta_F keneng cai shi diren
 should 3SG be.possible really be enemy

To retain the epistemic/root interpretative differences, another way is to treat SIMs as *verum focus operators* base-generated in the CP domain (Hsu 2016). This also give rises to the narrow focus interpretation in SIM sentences. Hsu’s major argument comes from the intervention effect displayed by *wh*-phrases.

- (37) *Yinggai Zhangsan mai **shenme**_F ne? (Hsu 2016:263)
 Should Zhangsan buy what SFP.Q
 Int.: ‘What should Zhangsan buy?’

She suggests that (37) is disallowed because *yinggai* is intervening between the Q-operator (above SIM) and the *wh*-object (below SIM). Her proposal, however, wrongly predicts SIMs with *wh*-subjects ((13) above & (38) below) to be ungrammatical.

- (38) Yinggai **shei**_F qu?
 should who go
 ‘Who should go?’

Under our movement analysis, (37) is disallowed on the same ground as (1)/(23) and (14), where *Zhangsan* is not (and cannot be, in this case,) focused, while (13) and (38) are allowed since *wh*-phrases bear inherent focus. The subject-object asymmetry is a natural consequence of our proposal. Hence, Hsu’s proposal is untenable either.

In the next section, we will discuss why the movement of SIMs needs to be licensed by focus, i.e. what is the exact mechanism that regulates the licensing condition of SIM movement.

4. Generalized Scope Economy

4.1. Alternation of focus scope with modals

To answer why focus may license modal movement, we first note that movement of an SIM across a *focused* element has semantic effects. Consider the pair below:

- (39) #*Shi shangdi_F keyi zhengjiu ni, suiran wo bu xin shangdi cunzai*
 FOC God can help 2SG although 1SG NEG believe God exist
 Int.: ‘God (but not someone else) may help you, though I don’t believe God is here.’
- (40) *Keyi shi shangdi_F zhengjiu ni, suiran wo bu xin shangdi cunzai*
 can FOC God help 2SG although 1SG NEG believe God exist
 ‘God (but not someone else) may help you, though I don’t believe God is here.’

Before movement, (39) presupposes the existence of the focused subject ‘God’ and is infelicitous with a contradicting continuation, while this presupposition is removed after movement (=40). Adopting a quantificational analysis of focus (Chomsky 1971, Larson & Lefebvre 1991), focus contains an existential quantifier and the presuppositional difference may be explained by the alternation of scopal relation between the existential quantifier and the root modal.

4.2. Scope Economy

We argue that SIM movement is regulated by Scope Economy (SE) (Fox 2000). SE dictates that scope-shifting operation must have semantic effects. Put differently, the grammar prohibits any vacuous operations. For example, quantifier-raising (QR) can be applied only if the inverse scope and surface scope are semantically distinct (e.g. different in truth conditions).

While QR is covert in many languages, overt movement may also be constrained by SE. Take aspectual verbs in Cantonese (one of the major Chinese varieties) as an illustration. Aspectual verb *hoici* ‘begin’ may overtly move across a quantifier, e.g. the restrictive quantifier ‘only’ in (41), but not a definite expression in (42) (Lee 2019:1-2).

- (41) a. Dak Aaming hoici haau-dou hou singzik (only>begin / *begin>only)
 only Aaming begin get-able good result
 ‘Only Aaming is such that he begins to get good results.’
- b. **Hoici dak Aaming** haau-dou hou singzik (*only>begin / begin >only)
 begin only Aaming get-able good result
 ‘It begins to be that case that only Aaming is getting good results.’
- (42) a. Aaming hoici haau-dou hou singzik
 Aaming begin get-able good result
 ‘Aaming begins to get good results.’
- b. ***Hoici Aaming** haau-dou hou singzik
 begin Aaming get-able good result

Crucially, (a) and (b) in (41) differ in truth conditions. Since both the restrictive quantifier and *hoici* are quantificational elements and are scopally informative/uncommutative (i.e. inverse scope \neq surface scope) with each other, movement of *hoici* across ‘only Aaming’ has semantic effects and is thus possible. Definite expressions such as proper names, however, generally do not interact with other quantifiers to give different truth conditions and are scopally uninformative/ commutative with quantificational elements. *Hoici* thus fails to move across ‘Aaming’ (also see Szabolcsi 2009 for a similar use of ‘begin’ in Hungarian).

The same can be said to root modals, too. Modals are quantifiers over possible worlds (Kratzer 1991). The scopal interaction of them with other quantifiers may give rise to different interpretations. This explains why root modals may move across a restrictive quantifier (which also gives a restrictive focus interpretation at the same time) in (43) but not a proper name in (44).

- (43) a. Zhiyouxuesheng **keyi** lai (only>can / *can>only)
 only students can come
 ‘Only students may come.’ (i.e. non-students cannot come.)
 b. **Keyi** zhiyou xuesheng lai, (ye keyizhiyou laoshi lai) (*only>can / can>only)
 can only students come also can only teacher come
 ‘It can be the case that only students come (, or that only teachers come).’
 (i.e. non-students may also come) \neq (a)
- (44) a. Zhangsan **keyi** lai
 Zhangsan can come
 ‘Zhangsan may come.’
 b. ***Keyi** Zhangsan lai (without subject focus)
 can Zhangsan come

In (43), the truth conditions for (b) is different from (a) after the movement *keyi* across ‘only students’. While (a) prohibits non-students from coming, (b) simply allows for a situation that only students come. It is compatible with a scenario that only teachers come, as the continuation indicated. This could be explained if the movement alters the scope relation between the restrictive quantifier and the root modal.

It is now clear that why focus could be a major licensing condition for SIMs. Both SIMs and focus are scope-bearing elements and their scopal interaction licenses SIM movement. If the focus is not on the path of SIM movement (e.g. in-situ object focus), the inverse scope remains the same with the surface scope, leading the derivation to crash (SE not satisfied). This explains why there must be a focus immediately following SIMs.

The interaction of focus and root modals also motivates a focus-sensitive SE. The original formulation of SE in Fox (2000) has said little on the role of focus. With evidence from SIMs, we propose a generalized version of SE in (45), which recognizes interaction with focus scope as semantic effects.

(45) Generalized Scope Economy (GSE)

[X ... [... Y_[Quantificational/ Focus] ... [... <X> ...]]],

↑
 where X is a scope-bearing element and Y is a *quantificational* or *focused* element and X and Y are scopally informative/ uncommutative for licit X-movement.

Our proposal for SIM movement could thus be refined as (46) to accommodate quantificational elements (e.g. restrictive quantifiers) beside focus and incorporate GSE:

(46) SIM movement (final version)

[Mod^{root} [TP/ TopicP XP_[Quantificational/ Focus] ... [___ [VP ...]]] (regulated by GSE),

↑
 where the movement must have semantic effects.

5. Concluding remarks

This paper attempted to solve a long-standing puzzle for Chinese modals, that is, A-not-A questions may mysteriously license an otherwise ungrammatical sentence-initial root modals in pre-subject position. It is argued that A-not-A licensing is actually just the tip of the iceberg. SIMs represent a broader phenomenon related to focus and quantificational elements in general. Specifically, SIMs are licensed by a quantificational or focused element immediately following them. In the case of (outer) A-not-A questions, a higher A-not-A head in the CP domain triggers narrow focus which may license SIMs. Thus, it is not the A-not-A form *per se* that licenses SIMs, but the (subject) focus triggered.

We further proposed that root modals may undergo movement across a quantificational or focused element to a higher position, yielding a wide scope reading of modals that is otherwise absent. Following the spirit of Scope Economy (Fox 2000), we suggest that the movement is constrained by scopal informativity, i.e. only movement with semantic effects is licit. This provides a principled explanation to why there must be a focused (or quantificational) element on the movement path of SIMs. This also motivates a *generalized* version of Scope Economy, which dictates that movement must have semantic effects with alternation in focus scope recognized.

A broader consequence of incorporating focus into Scope Economy is that it points to different roles of the same set of elements in syntax. Quantificational and focused elements not only license syntactic dependencies, but they also interrupt them. Particularly, they may trigger Intervention Effects (IE), such as *wh*-movement (Rizzi 2001, 2004). In Rizzi's formulation of Relativized Minimality, both quantificational and focused elements belong to a bigger 'Qu(antificational)' class. They may intervene between a dependency formed by the same class of [Qu] elements. Notably, the set of [Qu] interveners in IE is the same as the set of licensors in the proposed version of SE.

They thus play entirely different roles in IE and SE: while they may *intervene* movement by IE, they may *license* movement by SE. An interesting issue for future research is why they may have such ‘mirroring’ roles, and furthermore, whether it would provide hints on the potentially distinct nature of the syntactic dependencies being licensed and being interrupted.

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Matrix *Shuo* in Mandarin *

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This paper investigates matrix occurrences of *shuo* in Mandarin. We show that, even though it has been known that *shuo* can function as a speech verb and as an unmarked/pure complementizer, matrix *shuo* in question is not an instance of either of them. Rather, we demonstrate that it shows similarities with evidential markers in other languages and argue that matrix *shuo* is in fact an evidential marker, which heads an Evidentiality Phrase, unlike the pure complementizer *shuo*, which heads ForceP. We also briefly discuss distributional differences between *shuo* and Spanish *que*, which provides support for Demonte and Fernández-Soriano's (2014) analysis of matrix *que* in Spanish.

1. Introduction

Evidentials are often described as functional morphemes which encode speaker's information source regarding the statement she is making. A reportative evidential indicates that the speaker's source of information is a person other than the speaker or the addressee. As Aikhenvald (2004) notes, all natural languages have their own "evidentiality strategies", i.e., the evidentiality can be expressed by other lexical items (usually by verbs equivalent to 'see', 'hear', and/or 'say') even in languages which do not have dedicated evidential morphemes. For instance, in Mandarin, the verb *shuo* 'say' can explicitly indicate the speaker's source of information (= John), as shown in (1).

- (1) Yuehan **shuo** [mingtian ting shui.]
John say tomorrow stop water
'John said that there will be water suspension tomorrow.'

Despite its lexical meaning as the verb 'say', Mandarin *shuo* can also be used as a complementizer when following a certain type of verbs such as *jiang* 'speak' and *juede* 'feel', as shown in (2).

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- (2) Wo zongshi juede **shuo** [shenghuo li que le dian shenme.]
 I always feel SHUO life in lack PERF little what
 ‘I always feel that there is something a little lacking in my life.’
 (From the Peking University corpus of spoken transcriptions, Fang 2006)

The non-verbal use of *shuo* in (2) has been standardly assumed to be a counterpart of English *that* (i.e. a regular complementizer) (Li and Thompson 1989, Huang 1982, Hwang 1998); this kind of grammaticalization of saying verbs is in fact not rare cross-linguistically (e.g. Taiwanese *kong* and Cantonese *wa* among Chinese dialects, see Simpson and Wu 2002 for discussion). What is of particular interest here is that the distribution of *shuo* is not limited to embedded clauses: non-verbal *shuo* can also occur in matrix clauses, as shown in (3).¹

- (3) **Shuo** Kongyiji yijing si le.
 SHUO Kongyiji already die PERF
 ‘(Someone said/I heard) Kongyiji has died.’

Shuo in (3) contributes an additional meaning that the sentence is a report of a declarative. In this way, the matrix *shuo* seems to have a different meaning from the pure complementizer *shuo* in embedded clauses, as the latter does not have this evidential use. We will argue that *shuo* in (3) is an evidential marker, not a verb or an unmarked/pure complementizer (like English *that*).

2. *Shuo* as an evidential marker

In this section, we will show that: (i) matrix *shuo* is not an unmarked/pure complementizer, and (ii) matrix *shuo* is not a speech verb. Rather, matrix *shuo* shows similarities to evidential markers found in other languages.

For the first point, our argument comes from the interpretational difference between matrix *shuo* and the pure complementizer *shuo*: as observed in (3) above, matrix *shuo*, like verbal *shuo*, encodes information of a speech event while the pure complementizer *shuo* does not. The latter is semantically bleached so that it no longer encodes such information (see (2) above, see also Li and Thompson 1989).

However, matrix *shuo* is not a speech verb either. While matrix *shuo* semantically encodes information of a speech event, it is not verbal: verbal *shuo* can be modified by adverbs while matrix *shuo* resists adverbial modification, as shown in (4).

¹ *Shuo* can also appear in the sentence-final position, but we will focus on sentence-initial *shuo* (3). See Simpson and Wu (2002) for the sentence-final usage of grammaticalized speech verbs in Taiwanese.

- (4) a. Yuehan dasheng-de **shuo** mingtian yao xiayu
 John loudly SHUO tomorrow will rain
 ‘John loudly said it will rain tomorrow.’
- b. * Dasheng-de **shuo** mingtian yao xiayu
 loudly SHUO tomorrow will rain
 Intended: ‘(Someone loudly said) it will rain tomorrow.’

The second argument comes from the test of challenging the information source of a proposition. As Lim (2010) describes it, one of the most important characteristics of evidentials is that “the meaning introduced by the narrow evidential marker is not truth conditional and the evidential marker does not contribute to the truth-conditional meaning” (see also Speas 2008 and references therein). Murray (2010) defines this characteristic of evidentials as “not-at-issueness”, i.e., evidentials contribute a not-at-issue proposition, which gives the source of evidence that the speaker has for the at-issue proposition. Given this, if matrix *shuo* is an evidential, then the addressee can only negate the at-issue proposition (the truth of the propositional content), but cannot negate the not-at-issue proposition (where the information comes from). On the other hand, if matrix *shuo* is not an evidential, i.e., it is part of the assertion, then the addressee should be able to challenge how the speaker got the information. The contrast found in (5) indicates that matrix *shuo* is in fact an evidential; the proposition the matrix *shuo* takes is deniable, as in (5B1), but challenging about the speech event expressed by matrix *shuo* yields in felicity, as in (5B2).

- (5) A: **Shuo** shuoxiang si le.
 SHUO prime.minister die PERF
 ‘The prime minister has died (someone said/I heard).’
- B1: Bu dui. Shouxiang mei si.
 NEG right prime.minister NEG die
 ‘That is not true. The prime minister has not died.’
- B2: #Bu dui. Shouxiang si le, dan yinggai meiren gaosu guo ni.
 NEG right prime minister die PERF but should nobody tell EXP you
 ‘That is not true. The prime minister has died, but nobody should have told you this.’

In contrast, with verbal *shuo*, unlike matrix *shuo*, the speech event expressed by *shuo* is the at-issue content of the utterance, and thus it can be challenged, as shown in (6).

- (6) A: Yuehan **shuo** mingtian ting shui.
 John say tomorrow stop water
 ‘John said that there will be water suspension tomorrow.’

B: Bu dui mingtian hui ting shui, dan Yuehan mei shuo guo.
 NEG right tomorrow will stop water but John NEG say EXP
 ‘No, that’s not true. There will be water suspension tomorrow, but John
 didn’t/doesn’t say that.’

There is a further similarity between matrix *shuo* and reportative/hearsay evidential markers in other languages. Matrix *shuo* cannot report the speaker’s or the addressee’s saying. For example, in (3) above, repeated in (7) below, it can only mean ‘Kongyiji has died according to someone different from the speaker and the addressee’. This is another common property of (hearsay) evidentials in other languages (see e.g. Demonte and Fernández-Soriano 2014 and references therein).

- (7) **Shuo** Kongyiji yijing si le. = (3)
 SHUO Kongyiji already die PERF
 ‘(Someone said/I heard) Kongyiji has died.’
 * ‘Kongyiji has died according to me/you.’

In sum, in this section we have shown that Matrix *shuo* is not a verb or an unmarked/pure complementizer. Rather, it has a number of similarities to evidential markers. In the next section, we will argue that matrix *shuo* under investigation is in fact an evidential marker, which is located in a syntactically different position from verbal *shuo* and the pure complementizer *shuo*.

3. Matrix *shuo* as an Evid head

In the previous section, we have observed that matrix *shuo* is not a mere counterpart of English *that* or a speech verb. Rather, it shows many similarities to reportative/hearsay evidential markers in other languages. In this section, we will argue that matrix *shuo* under investigation is an evidential marker, not a pure complementizer, which means that matrix *shuo* is located in a different syntactic position from the pure complementizer *shuo*.

On the basis of the observations from the previous section, we argue that matrix *shuo* under investigation is in fact a reportative/hearsay evidential marker. We suggest that it is located in a different syntactic position from the pure complementizer *shuo*, which is a counterpart of English complementizer *that* (see (2)). To be more specific, assuming a fine-grained split CP-domain (Cinque 1999, Speas and Tenny 2003 a.o.), we suggest that matrix *shuo* heads an Evidentiality Phrase (EvidP), as shown in (8) (see Demonte and Fernández-Soriano 2014 for Spanish and Saito 2019 for Japanese).

- (8) [EvidP *shuo* [...]]

In contrast, the pure complementizer *shuo* is, just like English *that*, the head of ForceP, which is selected by matrix predicates (e.g. ‘say’, ‘think’).

(9) ... V [_{ForceP} *shuo* [...]]

Note here that it is cross-linguistically common that elements of the same phonological form can function as an evidential marker as well as an unmarked complementizer. Thus, *tte* in Japanese (see (10)), and *kong* in Taiwanese can function as a (pure) complementizer and as an evidential marker (see Simpson and Wu 2002, Hsieh and Rint 2011, Saito 2019 and references therein). As discussed in more detail in the next section, *que* in Spanish has the same kind of multifunctionality.

(10) Japanese

- a. John-ga [asita kuru tte] itta.
 John-Nom tomorrow come TTE(C) said
 ‘John said that he would come tomorrow.’
- b. Gakubutyoo-ga yameta tte.
 dean-Nom resigned TTE(evidential)
 ‘The dean has resigned (someone said/I heard).’

In this section, we have argued that matrix *shuo* under investigation is an evidential marker, heading an Evidentiality Phrase, which contrasts with the unmarked complementizer *shuo*, which we suggest is the head of ForceP.

4. Consequences: Two matrix *que*'s vs. One matrix *shuo*

In the previous section, we have observed multifunctionality of *shuo*; it functions as an unmarked/pure complementizer (like English *that*) and as an evidential marker. As briefly mentioned above, this kind of multifunctionality is observed cross-linguistically. In this section, we will briefly compare the distribution of matrix *shuo* and *que* in Spanish. We will observe that despite their similarities, there are differences regarding *shuo* and *que* regarding the availability of a specific type of their matrix occurrences, which can be seen as support for Demonte and Fernández-Soriano's 2014 analysis of matrix *que*.

We have seen that *shuo* can function as an evidential marker and as a pure complementizer. This distribution of *shuo* is strikingly similar to *que* in Spanish. Just like *shuo*, *que* is usually assumed to be a counterpart of *that* in English, since it functions as a pure complementizer, as in (11). However, it can also occur in matrix clauses, as in (12) (e.g. Spitzer 1942, Etxepare 2007, Etxepare 2010, Demonte and Fernández-Soriano 2014).

- (11) John dijo que ha dimitido el decano.
 John said QUE(C) has resigned the dean
 ‘John said that the dean has resigned.’

- (12) Que ha dimitido el decano.
 QUE has resigned the dean
 ‘The dean has resigned (someone said/I heard).’
 ((12) is taken from Demonte and Fernández-Soriano 2014: 229)

Based on a number of similarities between *que* in (12) and evidential markers in other languages, Demonte and Fernández-Soriano (2014) (D&F, henceforth) argue that *que* in question is in fact an evidential marker, referring to this use as *evidential que*. Assuming a fine-grained split-CP domain, they suggest that evidential *que* heads an EvidP, as in (13), just like our matrix *shuo*.

- (13) Evidential *que*: [EvidP *que*_{Evid} [...]]

D&F further observe that this use of *que* is not the only instance of matrix occurrences of *que*. They show that matrix *que* has another usage: *echoic que*.

- (14) Echoic *que*

- A: No me he acordado de sacar las entradas.
 not Refl have remembered of get the tickets
 ‘I did not remember to get the tickets.’
 B: ¿Que no te has acordado?
 QUE not Refl have remembered
 ‘Are you saying you did not remember?’ (Porroche Ballesteros 2000: 104)

The core characteristic of echoic *que* is that “the source of the *que*-clause is inside the linguistic context, i.e. there is a particular portion of speech that is (partly) reproduced” (D&F: 238). Thus, in (14), the speaker reproduces a part of the addressee’s utterance (‘did not remember’).

D&F show that evidential *que* and echoic *que* behave differently in a number of syntactic and semantic respects, despite their apparent similarities. Based on such differences, they suggest that echoic *que* is located in a different syntactic position than evidential *que*. Specifically, they argue that echoic *que* is in fact the regular complementizer *que*, located in Force⁰. This Force(P) is selected by a silent verb of communication, e.g. ‘say’, as illustrated in (15).

- (15) Echoic *que*: ... V_(null) [ForceP *que* [...]]

What is important for us here is that, while there is a similarity between Mandarin *shuo* and Spanish *que* in that both can function as a complementizer and as an evidential marker, *shuo* lacks the echoic use, as shown in (16).

- (16) A: Wo wang le mai piao.
 I forget Perf buy ticket
 ‘I forgot to buy tickets.’
 B:* Shuo ni wang le mai piao?
 SHUO you forget Perf buy ticket
 Intended: ‘Are you saying that you forgot to buy tickets?’

As shown above, *shuo* has an evidential use but lacks an echoic use. In other words, *shuo* has only one of the two usages of “matrix complementizers” identified by D&F. There then need to be (at least) two distinct types of “matrix complementizers” (i.e. evidential and echoic) to capture the difference between Mandarin *shuo* and Spanish *que*. Hence, the distribution of matrix *shuo* provides support for D&F’s dual treatment of matrix *que*. It should also be noted that, if D&F’s and our analyses of *que/shuo* are on the right track, the fact that Mandarin lacks the echoic use of *shuo* implies that Mandarin, unlike Spanish, does not have a phonologically null communication verb.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we have investigated matrix *shuo* in Mandarin. We have shown that matrix *shuo* is not a speech verb or an unmarked/pure complementizer. We have argued that it is an evidential marker, heading an EvidP, unlike the pure complementizer *shuo*, which heads ForceP. We have also discussed the distributional differences between *shuo* and Spanish *que*, demonstrating that matrix *shuo* lacks one of the two usages of matrix *que* identified by Demonte and Fernández-Soriano (2014), which we have suggested can be seen as support for Demonte and Fernández-Soriano’s (2014) analysis of matrix *que*.

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The Origins of Sino-Khmer Numerals: A historical-Linguistic Analysis

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This paper offers a new explanation of the origin of Khmer numerals through examination of historical evidence, primarily via Willmott's framework of Sino-Cambodian contact, and phonological evidence, via analysis of Sinitic, Thai, and Khmer numerals. Previous literature has described Khmer numerals as Thai or Cantonese in origin yet offers insufficient detail. I argue that modern Khmer's numerals are a hybrid system of Sinitic words that reflect two strata of selective borrowing from Thai and Chinese. Shared phonologically rare changes in Thai and Khmer numerals suggest that Khmer adopted most Sinitic numerals indirectly through Thai. Thai's intermediary role is further supported by the presence of such patterns in Khmer as the partial adoption of Sinitic numerals. Additionally, the presence of Sinitic [dɔp] in Old and Modern Khmer reflects a two-stage adoption of Chinese numerals whereby some words were directly adopted from Chinese prior to broader adoption through Thai.

0. Introduction

The linguistic relationship between Sinitic and its many neighboring languages has long been a subject of study, used as a point of reference in research on Chinese historical linguistics. Examples of such research includes Sagart 1994, which argues that morphological similarities between the languages of the Austronesian, Austroasiatic, and Sino-Tibetan language families potentially reflect an expansive Sino-Austic language family; and Mei & Norman 1976, which examines lexical similarities between Austroasiatic languages and Chinese. Indeed, Southeast Asia's rich linguistic diversity has been the source of a great wealth of scholarship in Chinese linguistics studies, particularly in the Austroasiatic, Tai-Kadai (Kra-Dai), and Miao-Yao (Hmong-Mien) language families. Lacking in this research, however, is sufficient examination of the relationship between Khmer and Chinese. This deficiency can perhaps be explained by a scarcity of linguists well-versed enough in the two languages to conduct research thereof. Still, the lack of research in this area should surprise those familiar with the two languages, as some basic similarities are almost immediately apparent. This is especially true of Khmer numerals, which exhibit a clear similarity to the numerals of more conservative varieties of Chinese (eg. Cantonese, Hokkien), while also maintaining use of native Khmer numerals in a hybridized system. Thirty in Khmer, for example is [sa:m sɔp] (compare with Hokkien

[sam⁴⁴ sip⁴⁴]), whereas thirty-one is [sa:m səp muəj], using the native Khmer [muəj] for “one”. This peculiar system’s origins are insufficiently explained in existing literature. In *Notes on the numerals and numeral coefficients in old, middle and modern Khmer*, Judith Jacob briefly refers to Khmer’s “Thai loan words” for thirty through one hundred but does not elaborate upon this claim (Jacob 1965:143-162). Similarly, in *The Chinese in Cambodia*, William Willmott uses “the Khmer adoption of Cantonese numbers” as evidence to support the early arrival of Cantonese-speaking migrants in Cambodia (Willmott 1967:7). These analyses appear to be based upon surface level observations about the phonological similarities between these languages’ numerals. In this paper, I provide a more detailed explanation for the origins of Khmer’s peculiar numeral system through an examination of phonological evidence and the available history of contact between Sinitic and Khmer speakers. I conclude firstly that Sino-Khmer numerals were, more precisely, borrowed from some variety of Chinese similar to Hokkien through Thai as an intermediary; and secondly that the presence of Sino-Khmer [dɔp] “ten” in Old Khmer suggests a second stratum of borrowing from Chinese. To understand this complex network of loaning, let us first examine the history of Chinese-Cambodian contact.

1. Historical Background of Chinese-Cambodian Contact

The history of Sino-Khmer contact is long and inconsistent, with intermittent periods of direct and indirect contact. A full periodization of this contact and various stages of Chinese and Khmer are provided in this section, as shown in Table 1. The primary periods of interest are those in which new Sinitic numeral loanwords appeared in Khmer, namely the 6th and 17th centuries CE. Following the first known period of direct contact between the Chinese and Khmer during the Kingdom of Funan (or Nokor Phnom, 1st to 6th century CE), there was a more than two-century lapse in contact between Cambodia and China during the period of Zhen-la (6th to 9th century). Contact was not renewed until the beginning of the Angkorian period in the 10th century (Willmott 1966:15-38).

ALLARD: SINO-KHMER NUMERALS

Before Common Era	Late Old Chinese	Proto-Austroasiatic	Indirect contact?	
1st Century CE				
2nd CE				
3rd CE		??*		
4th CE	Early Middle Chinese	Proto-Khmer	Some contact	
5th CE				
6th CE				
7th CE		Pre-Angkorian Old Khmer	Indirect contact	
8th CE				
9th CE				
10th CE	Late Middle Chinese	Angkorian Old Khmer	Some contact	
11th CE				
12th CE				
13th CE	Early Modern Chinese and Dialects	Middle Khmer	Chinese migration to Cambodia	
14th CE				
15th CE				
16th CE				
17th CE				
18th CE	Modern Chinese	Modern Khmer		
19th CE				
20th CE				
Present				

TABLE 1. Periodization of Khmer, Chinese, and historical communications. “Historical communications” are based on the historical framework established in this section. The exact timeline of transition between Proto-Austroasiatic and Proto-Khmer is unclear. The source used for the timeline of Khmer language lists Proto-Khmer as its earliest stage, which is described as “before 600 CE” (Sidewell 2009:107).

Gradually, contact and trade led to permanent Chinese settlement in Cambodia in as early as the 13th century. By the 15th century, large-scale Chinese migration began, mostly concentrated in Cambodia’s newly found capital of Phnom Penh.¹ Historical records of Cambodian demographics are sparse, but Willmott cites an early 17th century Portuguese traveler’s account, saying that, “Phnom-Penh had a population of twenty thousand, of which three thousand were Chinese,” or comprising roughly 15%. Among the Chinese migrants to first install themselves in Cambodia were the natives of Guangdong and Fujian provinces, where the spoken varieties of Chinese are primarily the Yue and Min, respectively. Unsurprisingly, Yue and Min appear to exert the most influence in lexical transfers to Khmer.

¹ It has been theorized that the relocation of the Khmer capital from Angkor to Phnom Penh following the fall of the Khmer Empire, led to an increase in trade because of Phnom Penh’s position on the Mekong, giving it greater maritime accessibility.

The demographic composition of the Chinese-Cambodian diaspora seems to support Willmott's proposed Cantonese origin for Khmer numerals. Willmott uses "the Khmer adoption of Cantonese numbers" as evidence of early Cantonese migration to Cambodia. Upon first consideration this theory seems highly probably. Indeed, the first recorded use of Sino-Khmer numerals (with the exception of Old Khmer /tap/) is in Middle Khmer, corresponding with the beginning of large-scale Chinese migration to Cambodia. Additionally, many loan words in Khmer appear to be a result of the social position of early Cantonese-speaking migrants in Cambodia, who were often merchants or financiers and generally associated with commerce (Willmott 1967:60). It is plausible that the prevalence of Cantonese-speaking merchants contributed to the adoption of their numerals in Khmer.

Still, while historical evidence strongly supports Willmott's theory of adoption from Cantonese, it does not preclude adoption from Thai. On the contrary, it is well-established that the Thai and Khmer people, especially in the period when Sinitic numerals first appeared in Khmer, had frequent contact due to their proximity, leading to extensive lexical borrowing in both languages (Huffman 1986:199-210). Additionally, a network of contact appears to have existed between the Chinese, Khmer, and Thai at various points throughout their history. Ferlus (2012:10-19), for example, cites Chinese texts and linguistic evidence that support the existence of trans-peninsular trade connecting China, Thailand, Vietnam, and Cambodia in the 3rd to 8th centuries. Additionally, Suthiwan and Tadmor (2009:601) write that the Tai² people, like the Austroasiatics, lived for centuries in Southern China, only migrating south-westwards one thousand years ago. They were thus in prolonged and regular contact with the Chinese, unlike the Khmer who left southern China much earlier, around 2000 BCE, and subsequently had limited, periodic contact with China (Higham 2002, Lockard 2009:13). Unsurprisingly, the Tai people's long-term geographic proximity to China led to extensive borrowing, including, evidently, in their number system. Based upon this evidence alone, both Willmott's and Jacob's theories of Khmer numeral adoption appear plausible. Thus, this section has established that historical evidence offers avenues of adoption of Sino-Khmer numerals both directly from Cantonese or indirectly through Thai. However, as I will establish in the next section, only a two-stage adoption theory from Chinese, to Thai, to Khmer is supported by both historical and phonological evidence.

2. Overview of Khmer Numerals

Let us now turn to Khmer numerals themselves. Table 2 demonstrates similarities between Thai and Khmer numerals, while also showing the greater degree of adoption from Chinese in Thai. Note that while Khmer maintains a hybrid numeral system, nearly all Thai numerals are of Chinese origin. Khmer numerals one through nine use native base-5 terms, with other loaned numerals from Sanskrit, Chinese, and Thai. For example, the Old Khmer word for "hundred," /sat/ or /sata/ is likely borrowed from the Sanskrit *śatá*. On the other

² Note the distinction between Tai and Thai: Tai refers to the group which spoke Proto-Tai, to which Thai is a modern successor.

hand, the Middle Khmer word for “ten,” [dáp] appears at first to have been borrowed from Middle Chinese [dziip] (ten), though I will examine this in more detail later.

Old/Middle Khmer	Khmer	Middle Chinese	Hokkien	Thai	Value
/mvay/	[muəj]	[ʔit]	[it ³²]	[nùŋ]	1
/vyar/	[pi:]	[ŋi ^H]	[ji ²²]	[sǝ:ŋ]	2
/pi/	[bəj]	[sam]	[sam ⁴⁴]	[sǎ:m]	3
/pvan/	[buən]	[si ^H]	[si ²¹]*	[si:]	4
/pram/	[pram]	[ŋuo ^X]	[ŋo ⁵³] or [go ²²]*	[hâ:]	5
/pram mvay/	[pram muəj]	[liuk]	[liok ⁴]	[hòk]	6
/pram vyar/	[pram pi:]	[ts ^h it]	[tɕ ^h it ³²]	[tɕè:t]	7
/pram pi/	[pram bəj]	[p ^v et]	[pat ³²] or [pe ^ʔ 32]*	[pè:t]	8
/pram pvan/	[pram buən]	[kiu ^X]	[kao ⁵³]*	[kâ:w]	9
/tap/ [dáp] ^M	[dáp]	[dziip]	[sip ⁴] or [tsap ⁴]*	[sip]	10
	[dáp muəj]	[dziip ʔit]	[sip ⁴ it ³²]	[sip ʔèt]	11
/bhai/	[mp ^h ej]	[ŋi ^H dziip]	[ji ²² sip ⁴]	[jî: sip]	20
	[sa:m səp]	[sam dziip]	[sam ⁴⁴ sip ⁴]	[sǎ:m sip]	30
	[sa:m səp muəj]	[sam dziip ʔit]	[sam ⁴⁴ sip ⁴ it ³²]	[sǎ:m sip ʔèt]	31
	[sa:m səp pi:]	[sam dziip ŋi ^H]	[sam ⁴⁴ sip ⁴ ji ²²]	[sǎ:m sip sǝ:ŋ]	32
/plon/	[sæ səp]	[si ^H dziip]	[su ²¹ sip ⁴]	[si: sip]	40
	[ha: səp]	[ŋuo ^X dziip]	[ŋo ⁵³ sip ⁴]	[hâ: sip]	50
	[hok səp]	[liuk dziip]	[liok ⁴ sip ⁴]	[hòk sip]	60
	[cət səp]	[ts ^h it dziip]	[tɕ ^h it ³² sip ⁴]	[tɕè:t sip]	70
/bhai pvan/	[pæ:t səp]	[p ^v et dziip]	[pat ³² sip ⁴]	[pè:t sip]	80
	[kaw səp]	[kiu ^X dziip]	[kiu ⁵³ sip ⁴]	[kâ:w sip]	90
/sat/ or /sata/	[rɔ:j]	[p ^v æk]	[pek ³²]	[ró:j]	100
[ban] ^M	[poan]	[ts ^h en]	[tɕ ^h ian ⁴⁴]	[p ^h ān]	1,000
[mu:n] ^M	[məin]	[mæŋ ^H]	[ban ²²]	[mù:n]	10,000

TABLE 2. Comparison of Khmer numbers with other languages. The bordered section contains key similarities between Modern Khmer, Chinese, and Thai (the words for 100 and 1,000, are only similar for Khmer and Thai). A note about the use of Hokkien: The transcriptions marked with an asterisk are used colloquially. All others are literary pronunciations. Thus, not all Hokkien data reflect common speech. For the purposes of this chart, multiple varieties of Chinese were examined, and the Hokkien selections were made based on closeness to Thai and Khmer. See further discussion and explanation below. Entries in the ‘Old/Middle Khmer’ column marked with a superscript M are Middle Khmer (ie. only attested after the 16th century) All others are standard Old Khmer transcriptions.

3. Phonological Evidence for Primary Adoption of Sinitic Numerals in Thai

The presence of loanwords from a variety of languages used from Old to Modern Khmer reflects strata of borrowing in the Khmer numeral system. While these strata complicate the investigation of Khmer words and their origin, they also provide clues that assist in creating a timeline of borrowing. One such example that will help to establish that Sino-Khmer numerals were adopted through Thai is the Middle Khmer word for ten thousand [mu:n]. Similarity between the Thai and Middle Khmer words for “ten thousand” (Thai: [mù:n]) is clear. With the exception of tonality, the Middle Khmer word is identical, even in vowel length. Compare with the original Middle Chinese word for ten thousand [mæ̃nH]. Both nuclei of the Thai and Khmer words have raised and monophthongized, resulting in [uə] > [u:]. For Khmer and Thai to independently adopt this word and develop the same vowel change is unlikely, and so it can be concluded that the word was initially adopted by either Thai or Khmer from Chinese, and subsequently transferred from one to the other after having undergone this change. The low tone in the Thai word resembles the low tone of the modern Cantonese [ma:n²²]. Because Khmer has never had phonemic tonality, in order for tonality to have been preserved in the Thai loanword, Thai would have to have been the first adopter. Some consistency in tone borrowing is also apparent for the Hokkien lower entering tones (yang-ru [4]) and upper rising (yin-shang [53]), which, for this data set, all correspond to low (J) and falling (V) tones, respectively in Thai.³ If borrowing had first occurred in Khmer, the tones would not have been retained, as Khmer has no phonemic analogue, meaning that the presence of such a correlation between the Thai and Chinese tones is most likely a reflection of Thai being the first adopter.

Further evidence for the two-stage adoption theory is found in the unusual phonological difference between the original Chinese and the loaned Khmer and Thai pronunciations of “five” and “six” (as in Khmer “fifty” and “sixty”). While the Middle Chinese word “five” [ŋuo^X] has a rounded diphthong as its nucleus, the Thai and Khmer ([hâ:] and [ha:]) nuclei are both an unrounded /a/. Haspelmath and Tadmor explain that the difference in pronunciation is likely derived from the Old Chinese pronunciation [*ŋa:ʔ]. Given the scarcity of contact between Khmer and Old Chinese as established in historical evidence, whereas Thai is known to have had extensive contact with China since its antiquity, it seems unlikely that Khmer was the original adopter. It is unclear how /ŋ/ would have become /h/, but that this phonologically rare change is present in both the Khmer and Thai pronunciations further points to a two-stage adoption. For Khmer and Thai to have both independently adopted from Chinese and developed identical, rare changes is exceedingly unlikely. Similarly, the /l/ in Middle Chinese “six” [liuk] has also become /h/ in both Khmer [hok] and Thai [hòk]. Interestingly, this means that all the sonorants in the Chinese portion of the dataset, /l/ and /ŋ/ became /h/ in Thai and Khmer. One possibility, then, is that the sonorants devoiced to /l̥/ and /ŋ̥/ before becoming /h/, though further data would be needed to substantiate such a claim. The case of /ŋ/ > /h/ could be an example of

³ Given that it is difficult to determine the precise value of Chinese and Thai tones at the time of borrowing and the changes that have occurred since then, it is more important that there is consistent correspondence than that the tones’ contours match.

rhinoglottophilia, though this too requires further evidence. Still another possibility exists; note that if the colloquial Hokkien pronunciation for “five” [gɔ²²] were adopted in Thai, /g/ would have become /k^h/ between the 14th and 17th century, when Thai voiced stops became voiceless aspirated stops (Diller 2008:49-55). For /k^h/ to become /h/ is a much less rare sound change compared to /ŋ/ to /h/. As for the /l/, note Hokkien [lɔk⁴] contains /l/ followed by a front vowel. There are examples of /l/, when followed by a front vowel or when palatalized, becoming /x/ eg. in Spanish.⁴ Thus it is possible that such a change occurred in Thai, with /x/ subsequently becoming /h/. This is simply speculation but could provide an avenue for this rare shift in pronunciation. Nevertheless, the important fact remains that it is highly unlikely that Thai and Khmer independently adopted Chinese numerals, given their pronunciations changed in nearly identically rare ways. For these phonological adaptations to take place in both Khmer and Thai, Thai numerals must have had a long period of independent evolution after their adoption from Chinese. If it is true that the devoicing that occurred between the 14th and 17th centuries is the cause of the unexpected pronunciation of Thai “five,” it follows that for this trait to be shared, adoption of Thai numerals in Khmer must have happened subsequent to this phonological change, ie. no earlier than the 14th century. This is congruent with the first known use of Sino-Khmer fifty and sixty in the 17th century. The similarity between Thai and Khmer words for “hundred” and “thousand,” independent of borrowing from Chinese, also suggests a two-stage borrowing of Thai’s hybrid numeral system. Interestingly, these loanwords also appear in Khmer in the 16th and 17th centuries.

That Thai was the earlier adopter of Chinese numerals is further supported by its greater extent of adoption. Thai numerals from 2 to 99 are borrowed from Chinese in their entirety (Thai “two” is borrowed from a separate Middle Chinese word 雙 [ʃ^vʌŋ], meaning two, dual, both). Modern Khmer numerals, however, use a system of selective borrowing that is markedly different. Observe that the Khmer single digit numbers are entirely unlike their Thai and Chinese counterparts. Khmer numbers six through nine are formed by adding the numbers one through four to the number five (eg. seven is lit. “five two”). Twenty [mp^hej] is also a native Khmer word, being formed from a contraction between the Old Khmer “one” /mvay/ and “twenty” /bhai/. Chinese loanwords are not used in Khmer numerals until after thirty, but even so, the digits one through nine which follow multiples of ten are still in their native Khmer form. For example, in “thirty-three” [sə:m səp bəj], the first two syllables resemble the Sino-Thai word for thirty [sə:m sɨp], but the native Khmer word [bəj] is used for three. If there was a two-stage adoption of Chinese numerals for Thai and Khmer, which phonological and historical evidence supports, then it is very unlikely that Khmer was the first adopter, as this partial adoption is not in any way reflected in Thai’s numerals. Note that for Khmer numerals thirty through ninety, the Sino-Thai word for ten [sɨp] is borrowed, following the Chinese format of “three ten” to mean thirty,

⁴ Compare Latin *filius* [ˈfi.li.ʊs] to Spanish *hijo* [ˈixo]; *allium* [ˈal.li.ũ] to *ajo* [ˈaxo]; *folia* [fɔ.li.a] and *hoja* [ˈoxa], etc.

“four ten” to mean forty, and so forth. However, for the Khmer number ten, itself [dɔp], the Thai [sɨp] is evidently not the source, and yet the two words are both Chinese in origin.⁵

4. Strata of Borrowing in Khmer

The Khmer word for ten [dɔp] (or [dɔp] in some speech) complicates the two-stage adoption theory through its apparent direct borrowing of the word from Middle Chinese. Indeed, [dɔp] is certainly not thought of as a loanword to the same degree as the numbers thirty through ninety. Because of its adoption in Khmer since as early as the 6th century, it has been assimilated to a degree where it appears almost native. Phonologically, Khmer [dɔp] bears some resemblance to Middle Chinese [dzɨp]; they share a voiced initial and /p/ as their coda. Indeed, Khmer adoption of [dɔp] in the 6th century would correspond with Early Middle Chinese, clearly predating the earliest possible borrowing of Sino-Thai numerals. While it may appear that the presence of voiced alveolar implosive /d/ in the Khmer word’s onset precludes loaning from Middle Chinese, this difference can be explained by phonological changes.⁶ From Proto-Austroasiatic to Old Khmer, implosives were lost, merging with plain voiced stops. Implosives did not reappear until possibly Middle Khmer when, “prevocalic labial and apical voiceless stops became implosives,” Sidwell (2014:688) explains. Since Middle Chinese [dzɨp] appears to have been loaned to Khmer in the 6th century, the word’s introduction predates the return of implosives in Khmer. Thus, the implosive /d/ in Middle and Modern Khmer is the result of later phonological changes. The word [dɔp] therefore indicates a second stratum of borrowing in Khmer numerals. It is evident that prior to the broad adoption of Sino-Thai numerals in Middle Khmer, another Chinese origin word was introduced. While it is not impossible that [dɔp] was also adopted indirectly through Thai, there is no available evidence of a similar word in earlier stages of Thai. Additionally the established historical framework would allow for contact to have occurred between the Chinese and the Khmer in the 6th century CE, making direct loaning possible. Still, it is not clear that Middle Chinese [dzɨp] is the most accurate etymological candidate. Interestingly, some modern varieties of Chinese have more similar pronunciations of the word “ten”, eg. Hainanese [tap] or Xiamen Hokkien and Teochew [tsap]. Note that the Hainanese initial is a stop rather than an affricate, and that both words have the vowel /a/, somewhat closer to the /a/ of Modern Khmer [dɔp]. The Vietnamese reading of the Chinese character for “ten” is [tʰəpʔ], which

⁵ Note that the words for thirty through ninety are analyzed as single morphemes in Khmer, and not as the combination of two morphemes “three” and “ten” as in Chinese. This can be demonstrated by the abbreviation often used in colloquial Khmer where one simply says [sa:m bəj], dropping the word “ten,” to mean 33. This is easily accomplished in Khmer due to the hybridity of their numerals; a distinct foreign word for “three” is used to mean thirty, while a native word for “three” is used for three. A similar abbreviation sometimes occurs in Chinese, ie. san-san to mean 33, but only in successive counting where one’s meaning is clearer.

⁶ Note that all instances of Modern Khmer implosives /d/ and /b/ are free allophones with their plain voiced counterparts /d/ and /b/, varying from speaker to speaker.

may suggest yet another alternative path for Khmer adoption of the Sinitic word “ten.” While the exact language from which the word originates remains undetermined, to be certain, the word is ultimately Sinitic and represents an earlier stratum of borrowing than the Sino-Thai numerals of Middle and Modern Khmer.

Lastly, the timing of the broad adoption of Sino-Thai numerals in Khmer is important to determining the precise variety of Chinese which Thai and Khmer borrowed from. Records from SEALang indicate that Sino-Thai words for 1-9 were present in Khmer at least by the 17th century, corresponding to Middle Khmer. Phonological evidence confirms this timeline. In addition to the devoicing of Thai stops discussed above, a vocalic change from Middle to Modern Khmer provides further evidence. Ferlus (1992:64) describes a shift whereby Middle Khmer /e:/ and /ɛ:/ became /ae/ in Modern Khmer, diverging with pronunciations borrowed from Thai. Compare “four,” Thai [sì:], Middle Khmer [se:], and Modern Khmer [sae:]; and “eight” Thai [pè:t] and Khmer [paet]. It is clear that Sino-Thai numerals were in use by the time of Middle Khmer (15th to 18th centuries). This would mean that the adoption of Sino-Thai numerals would have coincided roughly with the beginning of Early Modern Chinese. However, despite examining several varieties of Chinese, including Middle Chinese and several southern varieties of Chinese, no single one clearly corresponds to Thai and Khmer pronunciations. While Hokkien bears the greatest overall resemblance, some differences between the two remain, even when a mixture of literary and colloquial pronunciations are used to better draw comparison. Thus, Thai numerals must have either been influenced by multiple varieties of Chinese, or some variety of Chinese lacking developed phonological history. Further research is necessary to determine the precise timing and variety of Chinese adopted by Thai and Khmer.

5. Conclusions

This paper has principally concluded that (1) Modern Khmer did not adopt its numerals directly from Chinese; (2) instead Khmer numerals reflect a two-stage adoption, from some variety of Chinese to Thai, and subsequently from Thai to Middle Khmer; and (3) the Khmer word [dɔp] “ten” represents a second stratum, or wave of borrowing of Sinitic numerals in Old Khmer, the immediate loaner of which is unclear. This paper thus clarifies inconsistencies in previous literature that had claimed adoption from either Thai or Cantonese. Further examination of interactions between Sinitic and Khmer speakers should be pursued for the potential benefits it has to understanding the Southeast Asian *sprachbund* and the historical phonology of southern Chinese languages.

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Chinese Concessive Mechanism in a Semantic-Diachronic Perspective: Case of 哪怕 *Nǎ Pà*

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In a concessive phrase, the assertion or the hypothesis introduced in the subordinate clause q should prevent the consequence of the main clause p in the “universe of belief” (U) (Martin 1987: 36): (if q , $\neg p$), while it does not in the “anti-universe of belief” (\bar{U}) (Martin 1987: 38): \neg (if q , $\neg p$). The concessive clause q can therefore be considered as an “ineffective cause” (Soutet 1990: 11). This paper, from a semantic-logical, syntactic-discursive, and diachronic point of view, aims at exploring the concessive mechanism in Mandarin via studying the concessive connector 哪怕 *nǎ pà* “even if” “even though”. By analyzing its grammaticalization process, our research deepens into the problems of rhetorical question, psychological operations, subjectivity, hypothesis, and modalities based on various corpuses from archaic Chinese to modern Chinese.

0. Introduction

Since the dawn of the first systematic work on the Mandarin’s grammar *Ma Shi Wen Tong* (The grammar of Ma) in 1898, the conjunction, as one of the most important functional categories (also named “empty categories” by the author), was first introduced in an independent chapter. One of its sub-classifications, concessive conjunctions, is the most problematic category. According to Chinese linguists (Li: 1924, Wang: 1943, Lü: 1956 & 1980, Ding: 1980, etc.), the concessive sentence belongs to the complex sentence field whose subordinate has a position opposite to that of the principal. In a concessive phrase, the enunciator provisionally “allows” or “admits” the assertion or hypothesis of the subordinate by using it as a concession in the discourse (Li: 1924). The so-called “concession” is thus a temporary admission (Lü: 1956). This is the reason why some Chinese linguists also called concessive conjunctions “permissive” or “admissive” conjunctions.

Chinese researchers have considerably been deepening the properties, constraints, and subdivisions of concessive conjunctions since the embryonic stage of the modern Chinese grammar system. Li (1924) distinguishes two types of concessional conjunctions. For the first one, represented by 虽然 *suī rán* “despite”, and its various derivatives (such as 虽是 *suī shì* and 虽说 *suī shuō*, whose first morpheme means “despite” and the second morphemes mean respectively “to be” and “to say”), it introduces an assertion from a

certain fact. For the second, represented by 即使 *jǐ shǐ*, 就是 *jiù shì*, 纵然 *zòng rán* and its derivatives, as well as 哪怕 *nǎ pà*, they all mean “although” or “even if” according to the linguistic context. In contrast to “allowing” a certain assertion, this second type of concessive conjunctions is often used as a basis for psychological “presupposition”. Wang (1943), who has a similar point of view, considers that 虽然 *suī rán* “despite” and its derivatives belong to the concessive conjunctions of “real permission”, while the other expressions mentioned above are concessive markers of “hypothetical permission”. According to Lü (1956), the clause introduced by 虽然 *suī rán* “despite”, as well as that introduced by 即使 *jǐ shǐ* “although” or “even if”, are all concessive clauses. For the author, there is a logic in relation to the concessive subordinate: in a sentence in the form of “[Concessive connector] + *q*, *p*” either “the cause of *q* does not produce the consequence of *p*” or “the consequence of *p* nevertheless occurs despite the cause of *q*”. Xing (2001) added the third concessive type in Mandarin: the unconditional concessive, represented by the concessive marker 无论 *wú lùn* “regardless” “no matter what/how/when/where/who”.

However, the concessive link is not restricted to a simple logical relation but is a complex operation. On a logico-causal level, the concession is a cause that should have acted but did not act. In this article, based on previous research (Wu: 2006, Zhang: 2008, Zhou: 2009, Li: 2014, Che & Zhang: 2011, Feng: 2012, etc.), we deepen these two different uses of 哪怕 *nǎ pà*, which still coexist in modern Chinese but have both undergone a grammaticalization process during centuries. We also reveal how various linguistic notions (subjectivity, rhetoric, hypothesis, etc.) function together to form this concessive conjunction 哪怕 *nǎ pà*.

1. Semantic-logical links in concessive sentences

The French linguist Martin (1987) reveals the intrinsic link of a concessive phrase from the semantical-logical angle. According to the author, whatever the language studied, the concession involves an “underlying implication” (Martin: 1987): something is expected to arise from the given situation (proposition). For instance:

- (1) 虽然 外面 下 大 雨，
 suīrán *wàimiàn* *xià* *dà* *yǔ*
 although outside go down heavy rain
 我 也 要 出门。
wǒ *yě* *yào* *chūmén*
 P1SgPron:I also will go out
 “Although it rains heavily outside, I will go out.”

The above statement leads us to believe that the heavy rain should have prevented the enunciator from going out. The statement thus refers to an interpretation as follows: if it rains (q), then the enunciator does not go out ($\neg p$). Yet this interpretation (if q , $\neg p$), although it is “underlying” and “considered” valid by the enunciator, is not verified in reality: the rain does not prevent the enunciator from going out. This ineffectiveness of the cause is translated by Soutet (1990: 11): $(q \wedge p)$ and $\neg(\text{if } q, \neg p)$, i.e., two incompatible propositions come together in a concessive sentence, and the second is used to “destroy”, even to “restrict” the first.

Martin (1987: 36 & 38) also proposes the universes involved in a concessive relation: the “universe of belief” (U) and the “anti-universe” (\bar{U}), by defining them as follows:

We shall name *universe of belief* or *universe* (U) the whole of indefinite propositions that the speaker, as he is speaking, holds to be true or wants to assert as such. We shall name *anti-universe* (\bar{U}) the whole of propositions that, although false in t_0 , could have been true or we imagine as such, which means that there are counterfactual worlds where they are true.

If we refer to these two notions (*universe* and *anti-universe*) proposed by Martin (1987: 83) and to the schema established by Soutet (1990: 15) on French concessive links, we propose below a table of the underlying implications of the three key concessive links in Mandarin as well as their universe and anti-universe involved:

Semantic-logical summary of key concessive links in Mandarin			
Concessional typologies	Typical concessive markers and examples	Underlying implications	Universe of belief (U) et anti-universe (\bar{U}) involved
“Permissive” or “Admissive” concession	虽然下雨了, 尼古拉还是要出门。 “Although it is raining, Nicolas will go out.”	If it rains, normally we do not go out.	U: $(q \wedge p)$ \bar{U} : $(\text{if } q, \neg p)$
Hypothetical concession	即使下雨了, 尼古莱还是要出门。 “Even if it is raining, Nicolas will go out.”	In probability, the rain prevents going out.	Q = q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n U: $(\forall q(\in Q) \wedge p)$ ($\forall q$: low probabilities) \bar{U} : $(\text{if } \forall q(\in Q), \neg p)$
Unconditional concessive	无论什么天气, 尼古拉都会出门。 “Whatever the weather, Nicolas will go out.”	There are times when going out is less possible.	Q = q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n , U: $(q \wedge p)$ \bar{U} : $(\text{if } q(\in Q), \neg p)$

2. The concessive conjunction 哪怕 *nǎ pà*

The study of the concessive marker 哪怕 *nǎ pà* is recent in modern Chinese. Several important studies relating to its diachronic evolution have been carried out since the 2000s (Zhang: 2008, Zhou: 2009, Li: 2014, Che & Zhang: 2011, Feng: 2012, etc.). Taken separately, the two morphemes 哪 *nǎ* and 怕 *pà* are from different natures.

哪 *nǎ* can act as an adverb in rhetorical question to reinforce the negative tone of the speaker. For instance:

(2) 六 四 年 若 不 是 他 们 治 好 了
liùsì nián ruò bù shì tāmen zhì hǎo le
 1964 year if Neg Cop PronP3Pl:they heal CplmResul:well AccplAspPtcl
 我的 大肚子病, 哪 能 有 今日?
wǒde dàdùzibìng nǎ néng yǒu jīnrì
 Gen:my bilharzia **RheQueAdv:how** to be able to have today
 “If they had not cured my bilharzia in 1964, how could I have lived until today?”

(Literature of Shan Dong, Li: 1984)¹

In this statement, despite the English translation of the adverb 哪 *nǎ* “how”, the speaker obviously does not expect the interlocutor to answer the question “how could I have lived until today?” but expects a dichotomous response, even an affirmative one to reinforce the speaker’s negative tone on the impossibility of living until today. This rhetorical use of 哪 *nǎ*, a component morpheme of the concessional conjunction 哪怕 *nǎ pà* “even if” “although”, is remarkably interesting.

怕 *pà* is essentially a verb meaning “to be afraid” “to fear”. For example:

(3) 社 员 们 真 是 有 点 怕 吃 亏
shèyuán men zhēn shì yǒu diǎn pà chīkuī
 members PlMk really Cop have a bit **afraid** suffer damage

上当。

shàngdàng

to be duped

“Members are really afraid of being harmed and duped.”

(Hebei Daily)²

¹ Institute of Applied Linguistics Ministry of Education of China, “Na,” *Yu liao ku zai xian* (website), accessed October 19, 2015, <https://bit.ly/2VcBfKp>.

² Institute of Applied Linguistics Ministry of Education of China, “Pa,” *Yu liao ku zai xian* (website), accessed October 19, 2015, <https://bit.ly/3qiziUS>.

怕 *pà* is also a tone particle used in front of the predicate or at the beginning of a sentence to express an estimation, a presumption or a doubt about a situation. It is the equivalent of the adverbs of possibility like “probably” and “perhaps”, but to which is added a nuance of worry. For instance:

(4) 我	悲哀地	意识	到:	这
<i>wǒ</i>	<i>bēiāide</i>	<i>yìshì</i>	<i>dào</i>	<i>zhè</i>
P1SgPron:I	sadly	become aware	CplmRslt:succeed	AdjDem
—	夜,	怕	是 再 也 逃	
<i>yí</i>	<i>yè</i>	<i>pà</i>	<i>shì zài yě táo</i>	
Num:one	night	TonPtcl:probably	Cop either also	flee
不 脱		鬼门关	了!	
<i>bù tuō</i>		<i>guǐménguān</i>	<i>le</i>	
Neg	CplmRslt:get out of	Hell’s gate	ModPtcl:Ø	

“I sadly realize that I might not be able to escape Hell’s Gate.”

(*Lonely journey to the end of the world*, Xi: 1984)³

Whatever the definition of 怕 *pà*, verb or particle, it always involves the speaker’s psychology: to be afraid, to fear, to doubt, to assume, to estimate, etc.

In the *Xin Hua Dictionary*⁴, 哪怕 *nǎ pà* is defined as a (hypothetical) concessive conjunction. Without any verbal inflections to mark the grammatical mood in Mandarin, 哪怕 *nǎ pà* can be used either to express realis (indicative) or irrealis (subjunctive) moods. It is the equivalent of 即使 *jí shǐ* “even if” “although” and of 就算 *jiù suàn* “even if” “although”. Compare these two examples below:

(5) 哪怕	葬身	海底	喂	鲨鱼,
<i>nǎpà</i>	<i>zàngshēn</i>	<i>hǎidǐ</i>	<i>wèi</i>	<i>shāyú</i>
even if	being buried	at the bottom of the sea	feed	shark
也 是 一 种 解脱。				
<i>yě shì yì zhǒng jiětuō</i>				
also Cop	Num:one	CI	relief	

“(Ellipsis: If we look at her sad experiences, understandably for her,) even if she was buried at the bottom of the sea to serve as a meal for sharks, that might be some kind of a relief.”

(*Register of a refugee girl*, Cheng: 1992)⁵

³ *Id.*

⁴ Dictionary Editing Office, Institute of Linguistics, Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, “Na pa,” *Xin Hua Dictionary* (website), accessed April 12, 2015, <https://bit.ly/3mgSMGZ>.

⁵ Institute of Applied Linguistics Ministry of Education of China, “Na pa,” *Yu liao ku zai xian* (website), accessed October 19, 2015, <https://bit.ly/3fZm6F>.

In this example, 哪怕 *nǎ pà* is the equivalent of “even if” in English, since “being buried at the bottom of the sea to serve as a meal for sharks” is obviously a hypothesis that seems the least likely solution to get someone out of misery (q_m in U). However, this probability is actualized in the universe \bar{U} . This is the logic of the second type of concession in Mandarin: the hypothetical one.

(6) 这 时 他 哪怕 是 一 个
zhè shí tā nǎpà shì yí gè
 AdjDem moment P3SgMascPron:he **although** Cop Num:one Cl
 高 层 管 理 者 ， 讲 话 也 不 会 有 人 听。
gāo céng guǎnlǐzhě jiǎnghuà yě bú huì yǒu rén tīng
 high level director speak also Neg will have people listen
 “In the meantime, despite the fact that he is a high-level manager, no one would listen to him if he spoke up.”

(*Talent Management Study*, Shuo: 1987)⁶

The statement above is taken from a description paragraph of a senior manager. It is an assertion instead of a hypothesis. 哪怕 *nǎ pà* in this case is the equivalent of “although”. Moreover, the logical link between protasis and apodosis is that of the “permissive” concessive one here: normally, when a high-level manager speaks (q), everyone listens (p), but here this cause-consequence relation does not take place (if q , $\neg p$).

Apart from the concessive conjunctive definition, 哪怕 *nǎ pà* in modern Chinese is also commonly used as a syntactic construction: “adverb of the rhetorical question 哪 *nǎ* ‘how is it (possible) that’ + verb 怕 *pà* ‘to be afraid’ ‘to fear’ ‘to worry’” (Li 2014: 1). For example:

(7) 硬 汉 子 哪 怕 别 人 嘲 笑。
yìng hànzi nǎ pà biérén cháoxiào
 brave man **RheQueAdv:how to fear** others to make fun of
 “How is it that a brave man is afraid that others will laugh at him?”

(Li 2014: 1)

In this example, the syntactic form “the rhetorical question adverb 哪 *nǎ* ‘how is it that’ + the verb 怕 *pà* ‘to fear’” is used as a transitive verb followed by a subject-predicate subordinate clause. The form “rhetorical question adverb 哪 *nǎ* ‘how come’ + a verb” is quite common in modern Chinese. The example (2) above illustrates this point where the rhetorical question adverb 哪 *nǎ* is combined with the verb 能 *néng* “to be able”.

⁶ Institute of Applied Linguistics Ministry of Education of China, “Na,” *Yu liao ku zai xian* (website), accessed April 19, 2015, <https://bit.ly/2VcBFKp>.

3. A brief introduction of the grammaticalization process of 哪怕 *nǎ pà*

In archaic Chinese until the end of the Han Dynasty (202 BC–220 AD), no statement is found neither corresponds to the syntactic form 哪怕 *nǎ pà* nor includes the morpheme 哪 *nǎ* according to the search results shown on our corpus website. Only three statements including the verb 怕 *pà* “to fear” “to be afraid” are found towards the end of the Han Dynasty (202 BC–220 AD). No other use of 怕 *pà* is attested during this very archaic period.

The first statement with 哪 *nǎ* is found in the “Six Dynasties” period (220–581). At this time, however, 哪 *nǎ* is used as an interrogative adverb “where” without being followed by any noun or quantifier. For example:

(8) 余 因 此 问 山 中
 yú *yīn* *cǐ* *wèn* *shān* *zhōng*
 P1SgPron:I due to DemPron request mountain Prep:in
 那⁷ 得 酒?
nǎ *dé* *jiǔ*
where to get alcohol
 “I ask you where I can get alcohol in this mountain?”

(*Bao Pu Zi*: 17–420)⁸

In terms of the verb 怕 *pà*, it continues to be used to express the meanings “to fear”, “to be afraid” during this millennium.

According to our research results, we note that 怕 *pà* starts to convey the meaning “to worry” since the Tang Dynasty (618–907). Zhang (2008)⁹ draws the same conclusion: “怕 *pà* begins to express the meaning of ‘worrying because of fear’ since the Tang Dynasty (618–907)”. Here are two examples from the Tang Dynasty (618–907) in which 怕 *pà* respectively means “to be afraid” and “to worry”:

(9) 工部¹⁰ 员外¹¹ 汝南¹² 周愿 独 云:
 gōngbù *yuánwài* *rǔnán* *zhōuyuàn* *dú* *yún*
 work ministry officer PprN PprN only say
 “爱宣 州¹³ 观察使¹⁴, 怕 大虫。”

⁷ In the writings of the “Six Dynasties” period (220–581), 哪 *nǎ* is written as 那 *nǎ*.

⁸ Sturgeon, Donald, “Bao pu zi,” *Chinese Text Project* (website), accessed February 5, 2015, <https://bit.ly/33tcd86>.

⁹ Cited in Li (2014: 27).

¹⁰ The Ministry of Labor is one of the six ministries of Imperial China.

¹¹ Name of a civil servant position in Imperial China.

¹² County name in Henan province.

¹³ An administrative department of the Antiquity.

¹⁴ Name of a civil servant position in Imperial China.

àixuān zhōu guāncháshǐ pà dàchóng
 PprN department mediator **be afraid of** tigers
 “Only Zhou Yuan, an officer of the Ministry of Labor in Runan, said: ‘The mediator of the Aixuan department is afraid of tigers.’”

(*Da Tang Chuan Zai*, 618–907)¹⁵

(10) 不 愁 世 上 无 人 识,
 bù chóu shì shàng wú rén shí
 Neg care world Prep:above Neg people know
 唯 怕 村 中 没 酒 沽。
 wéi pà cūn zhōng méi jiǔ gū
 only **worry** village Prep:in Neg alcohol sell
 “I do not care that nobody knows me in the whole world, I worry that there is no alcohol for sale in the village¹⁶ (ellipsis: where I am settling).”

(*Quan Tang Shi*, 618–907)¹⁷

The very first statement including the combination of the two morphemes 哪 *nǎ* and 怕 *pà* is found in *Zhuzi Yulei* (Collection of the speeches between the prominent neo-Confucian scholar Zhu Xi and his students) during the Song Dynasty (960–1279). At the time, 哪怕 *nǎ pà* was a syntactic construction of the rhetorical question adverb 哪 *nǎ* “how is it that” and of the verb 怕 *pà* “to be afraid” “to fear”. It essentially expresses the meaning of “how is it that we fear” “how could it be possible that we fear”, which implies a negation: we do not fear. Here is the only example of 哪怕 *nǎ pà* found during this period:

(11) 天 下 只 有 一 个 道 理,
 tiān xià zhǐ yǒu yí gè dào lǐ
 sky Prep:under only have Num:one Cl rule
 紧 包 在 那 下, 撕 破
 jǐn bāo zài nà xià sī pò
 tightly wrap Loc:in DemPron Prep:under tear CplmRslt:broken
 便 光 明, 那¹⁸ 怕 不 通!
 biàn guāngmíng nǎ pà bù tōng
 then clarity **RheQueAdv:how to fear** Neg unhindered

¹⁵ Wikimedia Foundation, “Da Tang Chuan Zai,” *Wikisource* (website), accessed May 30, 2015, <https://bit.ly/3kRmtNj>.

¹⁶ In Chinese culture, alcohol consumption is often associated with poetry and scholars. The great poets during the Tang Dynasty (618–907) were notorious drunks (Li Bai, Du Fu, etc.), known to have often found inspiration and written extensively while drinking.

¹⁷ Wikimedia Foundation, “Quan tang shi,” *Wikisource* (website), accessed May 17, 2015, <https://urlzs.com/goPBJ>.

¹⁸ In the writings of the Song Dynasty (960–1279), 哪怕 *nǎ pà* is written as 那怕 *nǎ pà*.

“All the people under heaven are tightly controlled by the emperor’s governance. We cannot come out of darkness to go towards clarity without freeing ourselves from this domination. (Ellipse: Since it is so), how is it that we fear difficulties?”

(*Zhuzi yulei*, 1270)¹⁹

The syntactic form “哪 *nǎ* ‘how is it that’ + 怕 *pà* ‘to be afraid’ ‘to fear’” underwent an important process of grammaticalization towards the concessive conjunction during the Ming Dynasty (1368–1644). According to the search results, 哪怕 *nǎ pà* is widely used during this period compared to previous eras: 45 statements are found. This generalization shows that 哪怕 *nǎ pà* is no longer a punctual syntactic combination. It functions as a fixed construction (example (12)), or even as an independent concessive marker (example (13)). Let us now analyze two examples found in different literary works during this dynasty:

(12) 景先 道：“儿子 媳妇， 多 是 青年，
jǐngxiān dào érzi xífu duō shì qīngnián
 PprN say sons stepdaughters most Cop young people

只要 儿子 调理 身体 好 了，
zhǐyào érzi tiáolǐ shēntǐ hǎo le
 provided that son take care of health well PtlState:Ø

那 怕 少 孙子。”
nǎ pà shǎo sūnzi

RheQueAdv:how to fear lack grandchildren

“Jing Xian said: ‘Most of your sons and daughters-in-law are young. How come you worry about not having grandsons?’”

(*Er Ke Pai An Jing Qi*, 1632)²⁰

(13) 那怕 他 八万 里
nǎpà tā bāwàn lǐ
even if P3SgMascPron:he Num:eighty thousand Cl:0.5 kilometer

火焰， 可 一 扇 而 消 也。
huǒyàn kě yí shàn ér xiāo yě
 flame can Num:one Cl:fan PtlStru:Ø extinguish PtlTn:Ø

“Even if the flame spreads over 40,000 kilometers (very far), I can extinguish it by waving this fan.”

(*Xi You Ji*, End of the 16th century)²¹

¹⁹ Sturgeon, Donald. “Zhuzi Yu Lei,” *Chinese Text Project* (website), accessed January 19, 2015, <https://bit.ly/2Va0h6F>. Example illustrated in the article of Li (2014: 27).

²⁰ Wikimedia Foundation, “Er Ke Pai An Jing Qi,” *Wikisource* (website), accessed April 25, 2015, <https://urlzs.com/ZQV2E>.

²¹ Wikimedia Foundation, “Xi You Ji,” *Wikisource* (website), accessed April 25, 2015, <https://bit.ly/2VbWxk>.

On the one hand, 哪怕 *nǎ pà* functions always as the syntactic structure of the rhetorical question adverb 哪 *nǎ* “how is it (possible) that” and the psychological verb 怕 *pà* “to be afraid” “to fear” in the example (12), whose underlying meaning is still a negation: “you do not need to worry about not having grandsons”. On the other hand, as for the example (13), 哪怕 *nǎ pà* can be interpreted as the hypothetical concessional marker “even if”. The intrinsic logical links between these two propositions are obvious: the flame spreading over 40,000 kilometers is a hypothesis whose probability to be extinguished by waving a fan is the least plausible (q_m in U). However, the probability is actualized in the universe \bar{U} .

Li (2014: 4) indicates the following syntactic characteristic evolution of 哪怕 *nǎ pà*: from the Ming Dynasty (1368–1644), 哪怕 *nǎ pà* starts to introduce a protasis in which it takes the head position. The introduced protasis is often an extremely particular hypothetical situation. It is the subordinate of a complex sentence and it maintains a concessional relationship with the main clause that follows it. According to the author (2014: 4), the syntactic evolution during this dynasty plays a crucial role towards a hypothetical concessive conjunction.

There is still a controversy among linguists on the date on which the syntactic construction 哪怕 *nǎ pà* ends its grammaticalization by becoming a concessive conjunction. On the semantic-logical level, as we analyzed above and according to the studied corpora, the link of the hypothetical concession between the subordinate introduced by 哪怕 *nǎ pà* and the main clause was well established during the Ming Dynasty (1368–1644). This would be the reason why certain linguists like Che & Zhang (2011) and Liu (2010)²² consider that as soon as 哪怕 *nǎ pà* introduced a hypothetical concessive subordinate, it has finished its evolution from a syntactic construction towards a conjunction. On the other hand, some others like Lü (1980), Feng (2000) and Li (2014) consider that during this period, 哪怕 *nǎ pà* has not yet become a concessive hypothetical conjunction. These authors state that the Ming Dynasty (1368–1644) is a period of transition from the syntactic structure “哪 *nǎ* + 怕 *pà*” to the concessive conjunction 哪怕 *nǎ pà*. We support such a conclusion. If we take again the example (13) in considering 哪怕 *nǎ pà* as a syntactic form “how is it that one fears/is afraid” “one does not fear”, we have the following interpretation:

(13') 那	怕	他	八万			
<i>nǎ</i>	<i>pà</i>	<i>tā</i>	<i>bāwàn</i>			
RheQueAdv:how	to fear	P3SgMascPron:he	Num:eighty thousand			
里	火焰,	可	一	扇	而	消
<i>lǐ</i>	<i>huǒyàn</i>	<i>kě</i>	<i>yí</i>	<i>shàn</i>	<i>ér</i>	<i>xiāo</i>
Cl:0.5 kilometer	flame	can	Num:one	Cl:fan	PtclStru:∅	extinguish
						PtclTn:∅

²² Cited in Li (2014: 29).

“How is it that I fear this flame which spreads over 40,000 kilometers, I can extinguish it by waving this fan.”

(*Xi You Ji*, End of the 16th century)²³

The translation of the syntactic construction “哪 *nǎ* ‘how is it (possible) that’ + 怕 *pà* ‘to be afraid’ ‘to fear’” is possible in this example. Thus, in this statement, 哪怕 *nǎ pà* has two natures (hypothetical concessive conjunction and syntactic form) according to different segmentations²⁴. The meaning of the verb “to be afraid” “to fear” is not fully grammaticalized.

These two uses of 哪怕 *nǎ pà* coexisted during the Qing Dynasty (1644–1912), a period where the frequency of the concessive conjunction 哪怕 *nǎ pà* was remarkably increased, and the process of grammaticalization of 哪怕 *nǎ pà* tended to end: 26 statements (out of 38 in total) integrated with the concessive conjunction 哪怕 *nǎ pà* “even if” are found according to the results shown. The remaining 12 are integrated with the syntactic construction “哪 *nǎ* ‘how is it that’ + 怕 *pà* ‘to be afraid’ ‘to fear’”.

As mentioned above, the two natures of 哪怕 *nǎ pà*: concessive conjunction and rhetorical syntactic construction, still coexist in modern Chinese. According to Lü’s *Xiandai Hanyu Babai Ci* (Eight hundred words in modern Chinese) (1980: 395), one of the syntactic factors showing the grammaticalization termination is that the concessive marker correlates with the adverbs 也 *yě* “also”/都 *dōu* “all”/还 *hái* “still” in the apodosis in a significant frequency: [Concessive connector] + *q*, 也 *yě* ‘also’/都 *dōu* ‘all’/还 *hái* ‘again’ + *p*. According to our research, among the 88 statements integrated with the concessive meaning of 哪怕 *nǎ pà*, 41 statements (out of 88) correspond to the structure “哪怕 *nǎ pà* ‘even if’ ‘although’+ *q*, 也 *yě* ‘also’ + *p*”; 7 statements (out of 88) correspond to the structure “哪怕 *nǎ pà* ‘even if’ ‘although’+ *q*, 都 *dōu*/总 *zǒng* ‘all’+ *p*”. Therefore, we consider 哪怕 *nǎ pà* terminated its grammaticalization process in modern Chinese (since the Republic of China till today (1911–now)).

4. Concession and rhetorical question

According to the previous subchapter on the grammaticalization process, it is already clear how the concessive conjunction 哪怕 *nǎ pà* grammaticalized from the syntactic construction nourished by the rhetorical question adverb 哪 *nǎ*.

The rhetorical question, also known by its various names as “oratory question” “disguised assertion” “fake interrogation”, is an important rhetorical figure. The French rhetorician Fontanier (1827) calls it “figurative interrogation” in his book *Des Figures du*

²³ Wikimedia Foundation, “Xi You Ji,” *Wikisource* (website), accessed April 25, 2015, <https://bit.ly/2VbwHxk>. Example illustrated in the article of Li (2014: 27).

²⁴ Li (2014: 29) draws the same conclusion.

discours (Figures of the discourse). According to the author, the rhetorical question is a speaker's discursive manipulation: he puts his interlocutor in a situation where he feigns an objection or a negative response from the interlocutor but leads him/her to reinforce the speaker's implied statement. This definition is specified by Anscombe & Ducrot (1981: 14):

The speaker of the interrogative utterance acts as if the answer to the question is self-evident, both for himself and for the interlocutor. The question is there only to remind this answer. It plays roughly the role of the latter's assertion, presented as an accepted truth.

In a question form, this rhetorical figure serves to make the statement admitted as obvious by presenting an affirmative value.

As a matter of fact, the emergence of the rhetorical question use dates from antiquity even before the first Chinese imperial dynasty: the Qin Dynasty (221 BC – 207 BC). According to Chen (2000)²⁵, in the *Analects of Confucius*, the most influential work of Confucianism written during the Spring and Autumn period up to the Warring States period (from approximately 479 BC until 221 AD): there are 326 interrogative sentences, including 183 rhetorical questions representing 56.1% of the total number of questions. Ancient and commonly used in both archaic and modern Chinese, the rhetorical question has also been well studied by Chinese linguists, especially on a pragmatic level.

Since the establishment of the Mandarin Chinese language system in 1898 with the publication of the book *Ma Shi Wen Tong* (The grammar of Ma), a great number of sinologists have contributed to the subject: Li (1924), Wang (1943: 169–170), Lü (1956), Shao (1996: 163–164), Zhang (1997), etc. Despite the convergences of these linguists, the oratorical question creates a speech effect which expresses the underlying meaning of the speaker. As a figure of speech, the rhetorical question is used predominantly in writing to reinforce the author's emotion. It is a pragmatic tool frequently used by politicians in their speeches and negotiations.

In general, the rhetorical question has the following three characteristics in Chinese linguistics (Shi 2009: 116):

- a) the rhetorical question is in the same structural form as the direct interrogative sentence but does not require an answer;
- b) the speaker always expects an “opposing” response from the interlocutor: if the rhetorical question is asked in an affirmative way, the speaker expects a negative response, and *vice versa*;
- c) the rhetorical question reinforces the speaker's assertion: it is more convincing than a statement or a direct questioning.

It is not a coincidence that a rhetorical figure can be found in a concessionary marker. For example, in French, the concession is at the beginning a rhetorical figure that finds its first definition in a rhetoric treatise: *De institutione oratoria* of Quintilien (around

²⁵ Cited in Shi (2009: 116).

year 95 CE)²⁶. In Mandarin, although the concession is not included as a rhetorical tool, we still find its rhetorical origin in very archaic times, the rhetorical adverb 哪 *nǎ* for example. This proves that concessive mechanism shares common origins despite different typological features of different language families.

5. Concession and subjectivity, hypothesis, and modality

According to Xing (2001: 499 & 517), the semantic link between the principal and the subordinate(s) in a complex sentence has a double character: it expresses both an objective assertion and a subjective opinion of the speaker. The objective assertion serves as the sentence's basis providing materials to constitute the semantic link. The subjective opinion reflects the speaker's decision to choose the semantic link between protasis and apodosis. Xing (2001: 499 & 517) specifies that to form a complex sentence, subjective opinion is empirical, while objective basis is secondary. Therefore, the enunciator's subjectivity is the decisive factor in choosing the semantic-logical link, as well as the syntactic structure of the complex sentence.

Subjectivity is closely related with the hypothesis. Using a hypothetical concessive phrase, the statement exhibits a strong subjectivity as well as an intensity of the speaker's emotion. For example:

- (14) [...] 没 有 人 冤 枉 人, 没 有 人
méi yǒu rén yuānwàng rén méi yǒu rén
 Neg have people unjustly accuse people Neg have people
 暗 害 人, 活 的 放 心, [...] 像 这 样,
àn hài rén huó de fàngxīn xiàng zhèyàng
 secretly harm in secret people live PtcIStu in insurance like DemPron
 哪 怕 活 一 天 俺 都 觉 得 舒 坦。
nǎpà huó yì tiān ǎn dōu juéde shūtan
 even if live Num:one Cl:day P1SgPron:I all feel comfortable
 "There is no unfair accusation or secret nuisance. (Ellipse: Everyone) lives without worry. Even if I ever experienced this life for one day, I would feel reassured."
 (Acquired, Bai: 1979)²⁷

In a hypothetical concessional logic, 哪怕 *nǎ pà* "even if" reinforces the speaker's strong desire: I have such an eager to live a life like this, even for a single day.

Moreover, many sinologists have been devoted to analyzing the reasons of the grammaticalization of 哪怕 *nǎ pà* since the 2000s. For example, both Zhou (2009) and Liu (2010) think that the subjective emotion of 怕 *pà* "to fear" has a major influence on

²⁶ Cited in Morel (1980) and Soutet (1990).

²⁷ Institute of Applied Linguistics Ministry of Education of China, "Na pa," *Yu liao ku zai xian* (website), accessed October 19, 2015, <https://bit.ly/3fZm6F>.

the evolution of 哪怕 *nǎ pà* towards a (hypothetical) concessional conjunction. Li (2014: 11) elaborates this point by stating that since the verb 怕 *pà* “to fear” is followed by a fact about which one is worried, and which is an adversarial situation in the main proposition, this conformity favors the gradual transformation of 哪怕 *nǎ pà* into a concession (hypothetical) conjunction. Regardless of the divergence of the authors’ opinions, the psychological verb 怕 *pà* “to fear” is always at the heart of the grammaticalization process of 哪怕 *nǎ pà*. We precise this point with a concrete example:

- (15) 哪怕 外面 下 雨 了,
 nǎpà *wàimiàn xià* *yǔ le*
 even if/although outside go down rain PtcIFnl:Ø
 我 也 要 出门。
wǒ *yě yào chūmén*
 P1SgPron:I also will go out
 “Even if/Although it rains outside, I will go out.”

The concessive link is clear here: the rain often prevents people from going out, yet the speaker will go out all the same. Nevertheless, in addition to this semantic-logic concessive link, the statement also implies a psychological subjective operation: the rain leads to a worry. The worry of the rain then leads to an expected behavior: be aware of the rain or not to go outside. The semantic importance of the psychological verb 怕 *pà* in 哪怕 *nǎ pà* may explain why until today, the syntactic construction 哪怕 *nǎ pà* still coexists with the concessive conjunction 哪怕 *nǎ pà*.

In semantics, it is believed that there are both a real world (W) with “real” things and individuals, and at least one unreal world (W₁) with counterfactual things and individuals. This theory of possible “worlds” universe was developed by Leibniz in modality studies in the 20th century thanks to an abundant presence of works on modal logic. According to Palmer (1986: 16), modality is the grammaticalized product of the speaker’s attitude and opinion. Subjectivity is thus an essential standard of modality. For instance:

- (16) 他 一定 来。
 tā *yídìng lái*
 P3SgMascPron:he for sure to come
 “He will come for sure.”

In this statement, 他来 *tā lái* “he will come” is an objective proposition; 一定 *yídìng* “for sure” is a subjective attitude of the speaker: the speaker is certain that he will come.

Palmer (2001: 22) again draws up, from a typological point of view, a list of basic modality categories in his book *Mood and Modality*:

Propositional modality: 1) Epistemic: Speculative, Deductive, Assumptive. 2)

Evidential: Reported, Sensory.

Event modality: 1) Deontic: Permissive, Mandatory, Commissive. 2) Dynamic:

Abilitive, Volitive.

We see that in a hypothetical concessional sentence, we often find both propositional and event modalities proposed by Palmer (2001). For example:

(17) 只要 同志 们 愿意 跟 他
zhǐyào tóngzhì men yuànyì gēn tā
 provided that comrades P1Mk be willing to to follow P3MascPron
 革命, 哪怕 几十 个人, 他 也
gémìng nǎpà jǐshí gè rén tā yě
 revolute even if Num:dozens Cl people P3MascPron:he also
 要把 这 只 剩余 部队 带 出 去。
yào bǎ zhè zhī shèngyú bùduì dài chū qù
 will BA DemAdj Cl remaining troop guide out CplmRslt:go

“Provided that the comrades (ellipsis: in the remaining troop) kindly follow him to revolute, even if they are only a few dozens, he will guide them out (ellipse: from this trench).”

(*Commander in Chief in the Mountain*, Wu & Qiu: 1992)²⁸

In this example, 哪怕 *nǎ pà* “even if” marks the hypothetical concessional link: a troop of only a few dozens of soldiers is the least probable hypothesis to survive (q_m in U) since it is considered as a very weak force. However, this probability is actualized in the universe \bar{U} : the troop will survive if he guides it. According to the categories of Palmer (2001), the subordinate introduced by 哪怕 *nǎ pà* “even if” shows here an epistemic value: the enunciator considers, personally, that the chance of saving a troop of few soldiers is minimal. This is a completely subjective evaluation from the enunciator since for others, dozens of soldiers might be a large number and they would have a good chance of being saved. In addition, the modality verb 要 *yào* in the main clause expresses a dynamic value (Zhu : 2005, Peng : 2007): I have the firm willing to save this remaining troop of dozens of soldiers who wish to make a revolution with me. As a result, we consider that subjectivity, hypothesis, and modalities are closely related and inseparable notions, which “nourish” together the notion of concession.

6. Conclusion

²⁸ Institute of Applied Linguistics Ministry of Education of China, “Na pa,” *Yu liao ku zai xian* (website), accessed October 19, 2015, <https://bit.ly/3fZm6F>.

In this paper, we have explored the concessive mechanism from formal semantic perspectives at first, then shed light on the grammaticalization process of 哪怕 *nǎ pà* as well as relevant linguistic concepts. The two constituent morphemes 哪 *nǎ* and 怕 *pà* are of different natures and have respectively several different meanings. Yet, they still share some semantic features: both 哪 *nǎ* and 怕 *pà* relate to psychological operations and the subjectivity reinforcement. During the Ming Dynasty (1368–1644), the syntactic form “哪 *nǎ* ‘how is it that’ + 怕 *pà* ‘to be afraid’ ‘to fear’” became a fixed construction and then began, little by little, to grammaticalize towards a concessive conjunction. It should be noted that the syntactic construction 哪怕 *nǎ pà* “how is it that” does not disappear. It coexists with the concessive meaning of 哪怕 *nǎ pà* in modern Chinese.

The concession is a complex logical relationship nourished by an aggregation of basic notions, which are already complex. The study of 哪怕 *nǎ pà* led us to analyze several relevant topics: rhetorical question, psychological operations, subjectivity, hypothesis, and modalities. It will be heuristic to continue deepening other pertinent notions (causality, negation, etc.) in our forthcoming research.

Abbreviations					
∅	Meaningless	Gen	Genitive	Ppr	Proper
Accp	Accomplished	Loc	Locative	Prep	Preposition
Adj	Adjectif	Masc	Masculine	Pron	Pronoun
Adv	Adverb	Mod	Modal	Ptcl	Particle
Asp	Aspect	Mk	Marker	Que	Question
BA	把 <i>bǎ</i>	N	Noun	Resul	Resultative
Cl	Classifier	Neg	Negation	Rhe	Rhetoric
Cplm	Complementizer	Num	Numeral	Sg	Singular
Cop	Copula	P1	First Person	Stru	Structure
Dem	Demonstrative	P3	Third person	Ton	Tone
Fnl	Final	Pl	Plural		

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Why *Er* is not the Ancestral Form of *Ne*¹

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Finding the ancestral form of *ne* and imitating the grammaticalisation process has been the subject of much debate in Chinese linguistics. Previous studies claim that there is a strong relationship between *er* and *ne* due to phonological reasons, however, a large-scale corpus study makes it possible to refute this argument. Results find out that *er* is not the previous form of *ne* because *er* is not frequently found as an interrogative marker in archaic Chinese. Besides, there is a timing overlap between *er* and *ne* in Ming and Qing Dynasty. Therefore, the ancestral form and the grammaticalisation process of *ne* still needs to be studied.

1. Introduction

Ne is multifunctional in Mandarin Chinese. There are several positions of *ne* in the sentence: as a topic marker, this particle is found in the sentence-initial position behind the topic component; as a sentence final particle in declarative sentences, this *ne* is used as a mood particle (Jiang, 1986; Shao, 1989). In interrogative sentences, *ne* is also found, and it has multiple functions: According to Qi (2002), *ne* represents interrogative force. This function cannot be used in *yes-no* questions but is applicable in *wh*-questions and A-not-A questions. Besides, *ne* can introduce rhetorical questions but expressing positive information (Qi, 2002).

Finding out the previous form of *ne* is appealing because when finding out the previous form, we can then find out the grammaticalisation process of *ne* and find out which features are retained and which features are abandoned through the process of change. Previous studies argue that *er* is the ancestral form of *ne* due to phonological reasons (Yang, 1928; Wang, 2004). A large-scale corpus study makes it possible to refute this argument.

This paper is divided into the following parts: The second section discusses the functions of *er* and *ne*, previous studies on these two words, and the hypothesis. Following a methodology section including the data collection and visualisation methods, the results section includes graphs and tables. The fourth section is a discussion, proposing that *er* is not the previous form of *ne*. The final section is the conclusion and summary.

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2. Previous Study of *Er* and *Ne* and Hypothesis

As mentioned in the previous section, there are functional relations between *er*, which can only be found in archaic Chinese, and *ne*. In this part, there are three subsections: in the first part, the functions of *ne* and *er* are introduced. In the second part, previous studies on the relationships between *er* and *ne* are discussed. Last but not least, the hypothesis and testing method are brought out.

1) Functions of *er* and *ne* in interrogative sentences

Er has the following functions: first of all, it is a second-person pronoun:

(1) 以尔车来, 以我贿迁。

yǐ ěr chē lái, yǐ wǒ huì qiān.

Use you car come, use my property move.

“(You) come with your car, in order to move my properties.”

“*The Book of Songs: Wei Style*”

In (1), *er* means ‘you’ and it is a second-person pronoun.

The second function of *er* is that *er* can be a demonstrative pronoun:

(2) 尔夜风恬月朗。

ěr yè fēng tián yuè lǎng.

This night wind calm moon light.

“This night has a calm wind and a bright moon.”

“*A New Account of the Tales of the World*”

In sentence (2), *er* represents the proximal demonstrative ‘this’. It can also represent the distal demonstrative ‘that’. Whether it is translated into *this* or *that* depends on the distance between the time of the event and the speaker wants to mention. In sentence (2), because the night has a close distance to the speaker, the *er* is translated to ‘this’.

The third function of *er* is that it can represent “near”:

(3) 其说甚尔。

qí shuō shèn ěr.

Its statement quite near.

“The statement is quite near (to what I expect).”

“*Xun Zi*”

In (3), the *er* is translated as *near*, and this character can also be written as *er* “迹”, which has the same meaning as 尔.

The fourth meaning of *er* is that it is a derivational suffix forming either an adjective or an adverb:

(4) 夫子莞尔而笑。

fūzǐ wǎn ěr ér xiào.

Confucius soft ER and smile.

“Confucius gave a soft smile.”

“*Analects of Confucius*”

Lastly, *er* can be a modal particle and it is often put at the sentence-final position:

(5) 定 楚 国, 如 反 手 尔。

dìng chǔ guó, rú fǎn shǒu ěr.

Conquer Chu Country, like flip hand ER.

“Conquer Chu Country is as easy as snapping your fingers.”

The *er* in this sentence represents the meaning of confirmation and certainty.

“Xun Zi”

As for the functions of *ne*, Constant (2011) observes that *ne* marker can be found in two positions: either in the middle or at the end of the sentence. When found in the middle of the sentence, according to Constant’s theory (2011), the function of *ne* is to introduce contrastive topics, and this type of *ne* is marked as *nect* (Constant, 2011). This *ne* always immediately follows an NP, indicating a contrast to the constituent mentioned before. This marker can be omitted but does not change the meaning of the sentence, as example shown in (6).

(6) 我 会 弹 钢琴, 她 (呢), 会 拉 小提琴。

Wǒ huì tán gāngqín, tā ne, huì lā xiǎotíqín.

I can play piano, she (NE), can play violin.

“I can play the piano; as for her, she can play the violin.”

Another type of *ne* can be regarded as *ne_{ASP}* (Constant, 2011); in this function, “*ne* serves to intercept a situation between its inception and termination, without focusing on any particular part of the situation’s actualisation” (Constant, 2011: 21).

As for *ne* appearing in interrogative sentences, the *ne* marker is always found at the end of the sentence, as in example shown in (7):

(7) 你 干 什 么 呢?

nǐ gàn shénme ne?

you do what ne?

“What are you doing?”

From the functions of *er* and *ne*, we can see there are substantial differences between these two characters. So why do linguists argue that there are connections between *ne* and *er*?

2) Previous Studies on the connections between *er* and *ne*

The first linguist who proposed a relationship between *er* and *ne* was Li Wang in 1956. He believes that it is very hard to find out the ancestral form of *ne*. In *Han You Shi Gao* (2004), Wang argues that *er* is able to be used as an interrogative marker, and that the sound of *er* [njelʔ] is very similar to the pronunciation of present-day *ne*. Therefore it is reasonable to say that there are connections between these two

characters. However, there is nearly a 1000-year gap between the appearance of *er* and *ne*; therefore, there is little chance to build up a connection between these two characters (Wang, 2004).

In order to find out the further connections between *er* and *ne*, by conducting a corpus study, Jiang (1986) proposed a possible model of the development of *ne*. He points out that *er* is used in Wei and Jin Dynasty, and he found some examples to fill in the 1000-year gap. He also points out that in Song dynasty, *ni* (你) and *na* (那) appear and gradually develop into *ni* (甞), *ni* (尼) and *li* (裏). Finally, in Qing Dynasty, *ne* (呢) is frequently used and becomes the function word still used in Chinese today.

These two studies are the most influential studies on the origin of *ne*, and all other studies discussing the origin of *ne* are based on these two studies.

3) Hypothesis

Since there is a massive gap of around 1000 years between the attestations of *er* and *ni*, it is reasonable to doubt that *er* is the ancestral form of *ne*. Language can change a lot in a thousand years. The hypothesis that *er* is not the ancestral form of *ne* is made.

3. Methodology

1) Data Collection

In order to test this hypothesis, a two-phase corpus study was conducted. Corpus studies are the most suitable method for analysing historical change because the chosen texts can be assumed to reflect the language behaviour used at a certain period of time and it is relatively reliable to use these language examples to create the model and show the changing pathway of a certain language phenomenon in fine-grained detail. The CCL corpus from the Centre for Chinese Linguistics at Peking University and the BCC corpus from Beijing Language and Culture University were used. The reason for choosing these two corpora is because these corpora are the largest existing Chinese corpora at the moment. In cases where punctuation marks were missing in one of the corpora, the version in the other corpus was used instead. However, the disadvantage of these two corpora is that they are not tagged. Therefore, all the examples from these corpora were analysed and sifted through manually for a second time. In the first phase, 44 books were chosen from these two corpora (shown below):

Table 1. Books chosen for analysis

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The reason for choosing these books is that they share similar genres: they all belong to story-telling style. In these books, there exist many records of direct discourse and these discourses are reflections of how people communicate over that period of time. In the second phase, all the examples with *er* at the end of interrogative sentences in the CCL corpus were analysed.

2) Variables and visualisation

Book	Year	Book	Year	Book	Year
Zhou Yi	1046BC	Xian Di Chun Qiu	160AD	Meng Xi Bi Tan	1090AD
Jin Wen Shang Shu	475BC	Fei Yan Wai Zhuan	170AD	Da Song Xuan he Yi Shi	1280AD
Chun Qiu Gong Yang Zhuan	470BC	Qian Han Ji	200AD	Quan Yuan San Qu	1290AD
Lun Yu	465BC	Sou Shen Ji	325AD	Xi Xiang Ji	1300AD
Yi Zhou Shu	440BC	Hua Yang Guo Zhi	350AD	Liao Shi	1344AD
Guo Yu	425BC	Hou Han Shu	440AD	Yuan Shi	1370AD
Yan Zi Chun Qiu	370BC	Wen Xin Diao Long	501AD	Shui Hu Zhuan	1380AD
Zuo Zhuan	350BC	Shui Jing Zhu	520AD	Mu Dan Ting	1597AD
Meng Zi	325BC	Qi Min Yao Shu	540AD	Tian Gong Kai Wu	1637AD
Zhong Yong	300BC	Tang Guo Shi Bu	823AD	Yin Shui Ci	1670AD
Mo zi	200BC	Zu Tang Ji	952AD	Ming Shi	1739AD
Zhan Guo Ce	200BC	Jiu Tang Shu	945AD	Hong Lou Meng	1773AD
Huai Nan Zi	150BC	Tai Ping Guang Ji	988AD	Wen Shi Tong Yi	1801AD
Shi Ji	95BC	Xin Tang Shu	1050AD	Zeng Guo Fan Jia Shu	1850AD
Lun Heng	86AD	Zi Zhi Tong Jian	1084AD		

In order to find out the percentages of interrogative marker *er* in different dynasties, the following variables are analysed: the numbers of interrogative marker *er* in the 44 books; a total number of interrogative marker *er* in 44 books; the numbers of interrogative marker *er* in the archaic Chinese section (1060BC-1907AD); a total number of interrogative marker *er* in the archaic Chinese section. R is used to visualise the data. The *ggplot2* package is used for plotting the smoothed conditional means of the graphs. All

the null data (with 0%) are cleared. The character size of each book is also shown in the graph.

4. Results

1) Phase 1 results

Graph 1 shows the percentages of using *er* in sentence-final position in interrogative sentences in the 44 books, as in examples shown in (8):

(8) 痴 汉 何 敢 尔 ？

chī hàn hé gǎn ěr?

fool people how dare this?

“You moron, how you dare to do this?”

“*Gu Jin Xiao Tan*”

The size of the black dots represents the total number of characters that the books contain, and the blue line is the smoothed conditional mean of the usage of *er* in interrogative sentences. The average percentage of *er* is between 0% and 8%. For the first 1000 years, there appears to be a gradual decrease in usage, and from around 50 years onwards, the average percentage of *er* is around 0%.

Graph 1: The trend of using *er* as an in sentence-final position in interrogative sentences in the history (44 books)

It is worth noticing that there is an outlier at 470BC and this book is called *Gongyang Commentary on Spring and Autumn Annals*. In this book, *er* is

mostly used as a sentence-final interrogative particle, and this usage takes up 51% of all the sentences (N = 112) containing *er*. When getting rid of this outlier, the trend of using *er* as an interrogative particle in sentence-final position is shown in graph 2:

Graph 2: The trend of using *er* as a sentence-final interrogative particle (43 books)

When getting rid of this outlier, from this graph, we can see that the percentage of using *er* averages from 0% to 1%. There is a rise-and-fall trend: from 1000BC to 400AD, the usage of *er* as a sentence-final interrogative particle rises from 0% to 0.7%. Then the usage has a gradual fall from 0.75% to 0% after 400AD, which means that *er* is not frequently used in sentence-final position in interrogative sentences.

2) Phase 2 Results

In phase 2, a large-scale analysis of *er* is undertaken. The results are shown in table 2 below:

Dynasty	Examples	Percentage of <i>er</i> in interrogative sentences
The Warring State	3	0, 248 %
West Han	35	2, 970 %
East Han	3	0, 250 %
The Three Kingdoms	3	0, 232 %
West Jin	3	0, 248 %
East Jin	17	1, 485 %
The Sixteen Kingdoms	9	0, 743 %
North and South Dynasty	23	1, 980 %
Sui	6	0, 495 %
Tang	87	7, 426 %
Five Dynasties and Ten Countries	9	0, 743 %
Song	114	9, 653 %
Jin	9	0, 743 %
Yuan	41	3, 465 %
Ming	218	18, 564 %
Qing	518	44, 059 %
People' s Republic of China	79	6, 683 %

Table 2: Usage of *er* in different dynasties

The total number of these examples are 1176, which is the total number of interrogative sentences which contain *er* as the sentence-final marker. From the table we can see that the usage of *er* in interrogative sentences is only between 0% to 10% of all the interrogative sentences with *er* from the Warring State until Yuan Dynasty. Then it comes to a peak in Qing Dynasty, and has a sharp decrease in the Republic of China period. Therefore, *er* is not a popular sentence-final interrogative particle in archaic Chinese period.

5. Discussion and Questioning points

In this part, why it is not possible that *er* is the ancestor of *ne* is discussed from the following perspectives: from the function perspective and from the timing perspective.

Firstly, from the function perspective. Although *er* can be found in interrogative sentences, this does not necessarily mean that *er* contains the interrogative function. In all the sentences I found in the BCC corpus, the function of *er* always stays in the five functions we mentioned in the second section, as in examples shown in (9):

(9) a. 痴 汉 何 敢 尔 ?

chī hàn hé gǎn ěr?

fool people how dare this?

“You moron, how you dare to do this?”

“Gu Jin Xiao Tan”

b. 赠 黄 子 也, 何 赠 尔 ?

zèng huáng zǐ yě, hé zèng ěr?

give Huang son YE, why give you?

“Quan Weng Da Quan Ji”

In (9a), this *er* represents “this”, and in (9b), the *er* represents you. In all the 1176 examples found in the BCC corpus, *er* is either combined with *he* (何, why) in order to present the interrogative mood, or used alone in a non-interrogative function. Therefore, *er* itself does not contain any interrogative mood. This feature is different from *ne* because *ne* does not have any of the functions *er* has. Although we can make a hypothesis that the development procedure went through a semantic bleaching procedure, there is no functional overlap between these two words, so it is very hard to build up the connection between them.

Secondly, from the timing perspective. From Graph 2, we can see that the frequent usage of *er* appears in Ming and Qing Dynasty. If *er* is the ancestral form of *ne*, then we expect it to appear before late Tang and Song Dynasty because in late Tang and Song Dynasty, other question particles like *ni* and *li* appear and become popular in people’s daily communication. It is not realistic, if *er* is largely appearing in Ming and Qing Dynasty, to also argue that *er* is the ancestral form of *ne*.

However, there still remains one possibility: In Song Dynasty, *ni* (你) is used to introduce interrogative questions. Since *ni* also has the second-personal pronoun property, is it the case that *er* develops into *ni* and then *ni* develops into *ne* later in the history of Chinese? I also looked into the existence of *ni* in interrogative sentences and found out that *ni* is found in Buddhist quotes, and there are not very many examples with *ni*, as shown below:

(10) a. 僧 曰 : “ 作 何 你 ? ”

sēng yuē: “ zuò hé ni?”
Monk say do what NI?
“The monk says ‘What does (it) want to do?’”

“Zu Tang Ji”

b. 师 问：“ 什 摩 处 你？”
shī wèn: “shénmó chù ni?”
Teacher ask: “ what place NI?”
“The teacher asks ‘where is it?’”

“Zu Tang Ji”

c. 老 宿 怪 讶， 遂 问 童 子 曰：“ 阿 谁 教 你？”
lǎo xiǔ guài yà, suì wèn tóng zǐ yuē: “ ā shuí jiāo ni?”
old man wonder surprise, so ask young kid say: “ A-who teach NI?”
“The old man was very surprised and asked the young kid: ‘Who taught (you) this?’”

“Wu Deng Hui Yuan”

This phenomenon shows that firstly, *ni* is mainly found in translated Buddhist texts. The existence of *ni* might be an error in writing the character, . Secondly, this use of *ni* only appears for a short period in Song Dynasty and disappears soon afterwards. If *ni* is the connection point between *er* and *ne*, *ne* should also contain the feature of being a second-person pronoun. Therefore, I would draw the conclusion that *ni* is not the connection point between *er* and *ne*.

6. Conclusion

This paper argues that *er* is not the previous form of *ne*. This is for the following reasons: First, the usage of *er* being an interrogative marker is rare in the archaic Chinese period. Secondly, there is no overlap between *ne* and *er* in function. Last but not least, there is a timing overlap in Ming and Qing Dynasty: Although in Song Dynasty, *ni* appears for a short time, it is still not possible to draw the conclusion that there is a process of change from *er* to *ni* and finally to *ne*. Therefore, there is no relationship between *er* and *ne*.

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Appendix: All the interrogative sentences containing *er* in 44 books

	Dynasty	Book	year	examples	QP	percentage	characters
1	Zhou	Jin Wen Shang Shu	-475	232	0	0%	33444
2		Zhou Yi	-1046	5	0	0%	30970
3		Chun Qiu Gong Yang Zhuan	-470	165	84	51%	67359
4	Chun Qiu	Guo Yu	-425	23	0	0%	88738
5		Mo zi	-200	6	0	0%	92344
6		Zuo Zhuan	-350	76	0	0%	252534
7		Lun Yu	-465	28	0	0%	21746
8	Zhan Guo	Zhong Yong	-300	4	0	0%	4465
9		Meng Zi	-325	31	0	0%	45069
10		Yan Zi Chun Qiu	-370	13	0	0%	56698
11		Yi Zhou Shu	-440	45	0	0%	44402
12	Xi Han	Zhan Guo Ce	-200	4	0	0%	156698
13		Shi Ji	-95	66	0	0%	592368
14		Huai Nan Zi	-150	7	0	0%	158669
15	Dong Han	Xian Di Chun Qiu	160	1	0	0%	531
16		Fei Yan Wai Zhuan	170	1	0	0%	3655
17		Qian Han Ji	200	22	0	0%	212086
18		Lun Heng	86	26	0	0%	246956
19	Liu Chao	Hou Han Shu	440	146	1	1%	910107
20		Sou Shen Ji	325	48	1	2%	71313

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21		Hua Yang Guo Zhi	350	44	1	2%	452286
22		Wen Xin Diao Long	501	9	0	0%	50000
23	Bei Chao	Qi Min Yao Shu	540	117	0	0%	141567
24		Shui Jing Zhu	520	53	0	0%	319750
25	Tang	Tang Guo Shi Bu	823	5	0	0%	23829
26		Zu Tang Ji	952	106	0	0%	249664
27	Song	Jiu Tang Shu	945	367	2	1%	2389053
28		Xin Tang Shu	1050	468	7	1%	1999737
29		Zi Zhi Tong Jian	1084	744	8	1%	3127070
30		Tai Ping Guang Ji	988	1132	6	1%	1942897
31		Meng Xi Bi Tan	1090	28	0	0%	126459
32	Yuan	Xi Xiang Ji	1300	8	0	0%	45523
33		Quan Yuan San Qu	1290	35	0	0%	479063
34		Da Song Xuan he Yi Shi	1280	11	0	0%	66401
35		Liao Shi	1344	68	0	0%	425341
36	Ming	Tian Gong Kai Wu	1637	0	0	0%	57462
37		Shui Hu Zhuan	1380	23	0	0%	922837
38		Yuan Shi	1370	476	0	0%	1869407
39		Mu Dan Ting	1597	7	0	0%	90159
40	Qing	Ming Shi	1739	569	2	0%	3303829
41		Zeng Guo Fan Jia Shu	1850	34	0	0%	102698
42		Hong Lou Meng	1773	24	0	0%	861081
43		Yin Shui Ci	1670	0	0	0%	8706

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44		Wen Shi Tong Yi	1801	114	0	0%	205548
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汉语个体量词认知功能的研究

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本研究从认知心理学角度对中文量词展开实验研究，来探讨量词除语义功能以外的其它功能。实验 1 结果表明，量词形象性影响人对名词的认知加工，高视觉表象清晰度的人从量词形象性中获益更多。实验 2 结果发现，定配性高的量词对名词的启动发生最快，即量词对名词有预测作用和反制约作用。

0. 概述

量词作为汉语中极富特色的一种词类，使用范围广，使用频率高，它不仅是名词的计量单位，更重要的是它反映着人们对名词的认识。

量词不但是个数量相对较多的词类，同时，使用频率较高。这与量词的功能密切相关。量词除了计数外，还有很强的形象特征。生活中我们无时无刻不在与各种大小不一，长短不齐，形状各异的事物打交道。当我们在计量这些事物时，如果不去细究他们的这些区别，而一概用同一个量词来限定，无疑将使语言的表达显得单一模糊，缺少一份应有的灵动活泼与明晰有效。而现代汉语无比丰富的词汇，则为我们提供了大量的可供选择以区别事物特点的量词，使我们能够得心应手地通过不同的量词达到区别事物大小、长短、形状、功用、效果等目的。汉语的“数词+量词+名词”句法结构反映了“数目+形状+事物”的语义结构，体现了汉民族在认知客观事物时凸现形状的特点。量词的定配性、地域性是与人人们的交际语言的约定俗成有密切关系。量词的模糊性、形象性、表敬性、表贬性是人们对事物的认识深入、细致、深化的结果，是思维越来越严密，语言越来越丰富，分工越来越细致的必然结晶。量词的这些特点，是汉语这一分析性语言语汇丰富又一体现，是使用这一语言人们的思维发达的又一体现，是语言严密、科学的证明。量词是汉语表情达意不可或缺的一个部分。

但在量词的研究发展中，也产生了许多不同的看法。戴婉莹（1984）论道：自从 50 年代起，就有人提出汉语量词的“个化”问题。60 年代中期，有人看到现代汉语中“个”字的广泛应用，就得出结论说：汉语量词正在消亡，汉语量词是没有前途的，将来发展，它将会完全被消灭，一切量词都将归于“个化”。70 年代后期，有人预言：“各色各样的量词都会渐渐

走向简化”，如个体量词渐有“个化”趋势，但形象化的说法如“一缕烟”之类就不会代以“一个烟”。80年代中期，又有人提出“表量的物量词可以而且应该‘个化’，修饰的个体量词则不可能也不必‘个化’”。随着讨论的不断深入，量词“个化”所涉及的范围越来越小，但什么是“个化”？迄今为止，尚未见过“个化”的定义，能看到的只是类似定义的界说：“量词‘个’因量词简化的趋势而产生巨大的同化能力，使许多量词失去了固有的地位而让位于它。”根据这样的界说来断定，量词的“个化”是指其它量词失去固有的地位而让位于“个”。

除了在量词理论上存在分歧外，量词也成了对外汉语教学及少数民族地区双语教学的难点，量词是跨文化交际产生歧异最多的词类。如量词“条”，我们可以说一条线，一条鱼，一条裤子等。这是习惯呢还是有理据的呢？这类问题，本族人往往“知其然，不知其所以然”，留学生更是困惑不解，工具书、教科书又往往语焉不详。

针对量词理论和实践中存在的问题，传统的语义分析帮不上什么忙，结构主义和转换生成语法也没什么用武之地。语言不仅是人类重要的交际工具和信息载体，还是人类重要的知识编码体系。不同的语言编码体现着不同民族对世界的经验和认识。而量词相关问题都与汉民族对外部世界的经验和认识有关。认知语言学从人与外部世界的互动经验出发，探讨语言结构的成因和用法的理据，因而常能在其他理论无所作为之处独显魅力。从认知心理学角度来探讨量词的认知功能将为量词的发展提供佐证。

1. 相关研究

Shi Zhang, Bernd Schmitt (1998) 把汉语和英语进行比较，认为汉语者更倾向以量词为基础来认知和归类事物。他们的研究表明，量词来源于真实世界中物体的特点和相关性，因此会影响人们对物体特点的认知；共用一个量词的物体通常在汉语者的心理词典中被归为一类；与物体匹配的量词的概念特点会影响人们对该物体的评价。

Ahrens (1994) 提出原型模型，认为每一量词都有一定的语义内容，如果量词与它后面名词语义相似，那么量词被“个”替代的可能性很小。也就是说，如果名词只包含前面量词的一个语义特征，那么这个量词更容易被“个”替代。如：沙发前面的量词“张”与卡片前面的“张”相比，前者的“张”更容易被“个”替代。因为“卡片”是一个平而宽的物体，和“张”的语义非常接近，而沙发的“平”和“宽”的特征都不非常突出，所以，更容易被“个”取代。Ahrens 认为量词的选择主要是受名词特征的典型性的影响。根据原型模型：当一个量词与目标名词有密切的关系时，这个量词较难被其他中性量词替代。当名词与量词的意义特征完全匹配，那么这个量词将很难被其他量词替代。

Chou, Huang, Lee, and Lee (2014) 基于量词和名词定配性前提观察被试对三种定配性量词（高，低， 和 不适合）以及相应名词的大脑反应，其结果显示当量词和名词的定配性高时，被试的 N400 显著减弱。这一结果说明汉语中的某些量词具有独特性，只能和特定的名词配搭，若用其它量词取代这些特殊量词，则会造成理解困难。

2. 本研究基本假设

根据上述量词演化的历史过程和现在量词使用的一些规律，我们认为量词具有认知功能，并做出如下假设：

- (1) 量词会影响人们对其所修饰名词的表象认知，如形状、方向、大小等；
- (2) 量词与名词的组合具有定配性，所以量词的出现对与其结合的名词的认知有预测作用。

拟以两个实验从不同角度展开探讨。

实验 1 主要考察量词对物体表象认知的影响，通过对不同视觉表象清晰度的被试进行对比，来说明量词能否合并。

实验 3 主要考察量词对名词的启动，通过反应时实验，来验证量词的定配性和对名词的预测作用。

3. 实验 1--汉语量词对物体表象认知的影响

研究目的

考察量词对物体表象认知的影响。陈望道先生(1973)再《论现代汉语中单位和单位词》中，指出量词具有形体特征，并把量词称为“形体单位的量词”。此后，语言学界又提出汉语量词的形象色彩。显然人们是在通过量词“形”的特点来揭示量词的表达功能。因为汉语是以理据性为编码基础的语言，所以汉语量词就反映了这种编码特征。量词的形成理据大多来源于名词，特别是个体量词绝大多数由名词转化而来。这些量词的表形方式有鲜明特点，主要是运用了相似性、相关性、相联性的理据，来实现编码以突出量词形象特征。一些学者，如陈平、王珏与刘顺等，都认为“名词+数量词或量词”表示名词的空间义或空间量。并且，汉语的绝大多数个体量词有直接表事物空间形状的意义（邵敬敏，1993）。个体量词与所搭配的名词具有原型性关联中的名词所表达的语义，所以同一个名词与不同量词的搭配，可以帮助确定名词的语义范畴。但也有人认为，某些量词，如头、匹、口、条、只等，在表量功能上没有任何差异，在修辞功能上也没有什么不同，所以，他们建议把这些形异、音异的“同义量词”加以合并。但却没有充分的实验数据来支持他们的这一想法。本研究通过问卷方式来论证，同一物体，使用

不同的量词, 会影响人们对物体的形象特点的判断, 影响方面包括物体的方位、体积、物体部件的清晰度等。

方法

被试

选取仲恺农业技术学院不同专业(英语、计算机、农经、市营)的大一和大二大学生 409 名, 其中男生 220 名, 女生 189 名。

测验材料

材料 1: 视觉表象清晰度问卷(VVIQ)。视觉表象是人的视觉化的能力, 即形成视觉表象的能力或在脑海中再现物体或图画的能力。视觉表象的口头报告表明, 视觉表象在强度和清晰度上存在个人差异, 这种个别差异具有心理学价值。该问卷一共有 16 个题目。被试唤起的表象的清晰度评定有“极其清晰, 就像和真正看到一样逼真”、“清晰, 比较生动逼真”、“一般清晰”、“模糊不清晰, 暗淡无光”、“根本没有表象, 你觉得你想到的不过是个物体名称”5 个等级。被试根据每个题目在个人脑海里唤起表象的清晰度进行评定。具体实验材料见附录 1。

材料 2: 自编的纸笔测验, 共 48 道题目。分为两部分, 一部分是选择题, 例如, “请想象一朵云, 云是什么形状? a. 圆形 b. 长条形”; 另一部分是 7 级评定题目, 例如: “请想象一顶花轿, 有顶吗? 1 2 3 4 5 6 7。”所有题目都是量词与名词的组合, 其中名词共有 35 个, 分别与两个不同的量词搭配, 这些搭配都合乎汉语的习惯。其中一个量词具有明显的形象性, 另一个量词的形象性较低。量词的形象性首先通过词典来分类, 然后再由 30 个被试对这些量词进行 7 点评定来进一步确定其分类, 其中形象性高的量词平均分为 6.27, 形象性低的量词平均分为 2.65。具体实验材料见附录 2。

为了减少对判断的干扰, 两个相同名词出现的顺序有一定间隔。被试思考后, 对名词的某些特点, 如方向、大小、特点等进行判断。

研究设计

2(视觉表象清晰度: 高/低) × 2(量词形象性: 明晰/模糊) 双因素混合设计。其中视觉表象清晰度为被试间变量, 量词形象性为被试内变量; 因变量为对同一名词特征判断。

测验程序

本测验分为两部分: 第一部分是视觉表象清晰度测验; 第二部分为量词形象性对物体表象认知影响的测验。所有测验任务都是纸笔测验, 由被试独立完成。

(1) 视觉表象清晰度测验: 让被试根据所看到的描述语句想象相应的事物, 唤起被试的视觉表象, 然后要求被试判断表象的清晰度, 并将结果填写到相应的题号处。分 4 组事物共 16 题, 第一次要求被试睁开眼睛想象判定

清晰等级，第二次要求被试闭上眼睛想象判定。在开始测验前，要求被试充分熟悉 5 个清晰等级。计分标准为极其清晰记 1 分，根本没有表象记 5 分，其它等级则按顺序由低到高计分。最终分数越低的被试，视觉表象清晰度越高，反之，则视觉表象清晰度越差。根据视觉表象清晰度测验的得分，从中选出低分的 82 个学生，组成高表象清晰组；选出高分的 79 个学生，组成低表象清晰组。

(2)量词对物体表象认知的影响：分别让两组被试根据他们所看到的句子想象相应的事物，唤起被试的视觉表象，然后要求被试判断事物的特点。分 2 部分共 48 题，第一部分有 22 题，第二部分有 26 题。大学生第二部分要求做 7 级评定，因此在开始测验前，要求被试充分熟悉所有的 7 个等级。数据处理由 Spss13.0 统计软件包完成。

结果与分析

选择题的结果与分析

选择题的结果见表 1 和表 2。

表 1 不同视觉表象清晰度的被试符合量词特点的正确选择比率和标准差

被试	量词形象清晰	量词形象模糊
高视觉表象清晰度组	0.608(0.169)	0.353(0.161)
低视觉表象清晰度组	0.552(0.158)	0.478(0.135)

图 1 不同视觉表象清晰度的被试符合量词特点的正确选择比率

2 (视觉表象清晰度：高/低) × 2 (量词形象性：清晰/模糊) 两因素混合方差分析表明，量词形象性的主效应极显著， $F(1, 16) = 21.06$ ， $p = 0.000$ ，被试对量词形象清晰的名词的正确选择比率明显高于对量词形象模糊的名词的正确选择比率，表明量词的形象性对名词形状和特点的判断产生了重要影响，形象性强的量词对名词所代表的事物的形象加工产生了积极

作用。视觉表象清晰度的主效应不显著, $F(1, 16) = 0.28, p > 0.05$ 。不论是高视觉表象清晰度的被试还是低视觉表象清晰度的被试, 当量词特点明晰时, 正确选择的比率都远高于量词特点模糊时正确选择的比率。量词形象性与视觉表象清晰度的交互作用显著, $F(1, 16) = 6.40, p < 0.05$ 。简单效应分析表明, 在量词形象清晰时, 高视觉表象清晰度组和低视觉表象清晰度组差异小, 但在量词形象模糊时, 高视觉表象清晰度组和低视觉表象清晰度组差异大。这表明, 被试视觉表象清晰度对形象模糊的量词认知起作用更大。

评定题的结果与分析

评定题的结果见表 2。

表 2 不同视觉表象清晰度的被试名词形象性的平均评定和标准差

	量词形象明晰	量词形象模糊
高视觉表象清晰度	5.16(0.67)	4.87(0.84)
低视觉表象清晰度	4.80(0.89)	4.78(0.89)

图 2 不同视觉表象清晰度的被试名词形象性的平均评定

2 (视觉表象清晰度: 高/低) \times 2 (量词的形象性: 清晰/模糊) 两因素混合方差分析表明, 量词形象性的主效应显著, $F(1, 159) = 10.14, p < 0.01$ 。从表 2 可见, 量词形象清晰时平均评定高于量词形象模糊时。被试的视觉表象清晰度的主效应不显著, $F(1, 159) = 3.50, p > 0.05$ 。量词形象性与被试的视觉表象清晰度交互作用显著, $F(1, 159) = 7.03, p < 0.05$ 。简单效应分析表明, 量词形象清晰时, 高视觉表象清晰度的被试和低视觉表象清晰度的被试的平均评定差异显著, $p < 0.01$; 当量词形象模糊时, 高视觉表象清晰度的被试和低视觉表象清晰度的被试的平均评定差异不

显著, $p > 0.05$ 。这表明, 当量词形象清晰时, 高视觉表象清晰度的被试对名词形象特点的判断更能从量词加工中获益。

讨论

本研究表明, 同一名词与两种形象性不同的量词搭配时, 被试对名词所代表的事物的形象认知有区别。不论是哪种题目, 量词形象性的主效应都显著, 表明量词形象性在判断名词特点的过程中产生了显著影响。表达中选择的量词形象越清晰, 人们对它所修饰的名词形成的表象也越准确。这一结果说明了那些试图将“同义量词”合并的想法的不合理性。“同义量词合并”虽然能使汉语的学习和表达变得简单, 但却影响汉语表达的质量。

本研究还表明, 被试的视觉表象清晰度与量词的形象性之间具有显著的交互作用。这说明, 在量词形象程度相同的情况下, 不同视觉表象清晰度的人对量词修饰的名词形象有差异。当量词形象清晰时, 高视觉表象清晰度的人对量词修饰的名词的特点判断更准确, 而当量词形象模糊时, 高视觉表象清晰度的人和低视觉表象清晰度的人的认知操作无差异或差异不大。这表明, 量词的形象性对人的认知加工的影响因人而异。在认知事物的形象特征时, 高视觉表象清晰度的人更能从量词的形象性中获益, 而这种影响对低视觉表象清晰度的人而言就要小许多。不过, 在本研究的两部分测试中, 被试视觉表象清晰度的主效应都不显著。这表明不论是视觉表象清晰度高的人还是视觉表象清晰度低的人, 在量词形象性不同的时候, 对所修饰的名词都产生了不同的表象, 说明量词本身的形象性对所有对名词表征的物体形象的认知都有影响, 不过是影响大小不同而已。

4. 实验 2--量词对名词的启动

研究目的

在以往汉语量词研究中, 学者已经发现量词的一些特点, 如量词的定配性, 即量词与名词的组合是有条件的, 有一定限制。量词对名词有制约作用。汉语量词研究的这些结论, 是通过对各种实例的观察、总结得出的, 尚未经过实验证实。本研究主要考察量词的定配性对认知的影响。我们的假设是: 由于量词和名词的组合具有定配性, 所以量词的出现对与其结合的名词的认知有预测作用。在现有的汉语量词中, 有的量词可以与许多名词结合, 如“个”、“只”, 而另一些量词则只能与少量名词结合, 如量词“匹”只能与“马”和“布”结合。认知心理学家 Anderson(1974)曾提出 Fan 效应理论。这一理论认为, Fan 指被试学习过的、与某一概念有关的事件或单词的数量。与某一特定概念有关的事件或单词的数量越多, 被试辨认其中某一事件或单词的时间就越长, 错误率也越高。从 Fan 效应的观点来看汉语量词的定配性, 一个量词可能结合的名词越多, 它的定配性就越差, 它对紧随其后的名词的预测作用就越差。本研究就是考察这种可能性的。

方法

被试

大学一年级学生 70 人。视力正常或矫正视力正常。

实验设计

3 (量词的定配性: 高/中/低) × 3 (SOA: 无启动条件/100ms/200ms) 两因素混合设计。量词定配性和启动条件均为被试内变量; 因变量为被试对名词命名的反应时和错误率。

实验材料

首先根据词典, 选出能引导名词多的、中等、少的量词各 11 个, 由 60 名大学生对这些量词进行 7 级评定, 看这些量词归类是否与词典一致, 评定结果与词典相同。再分别从每组量词中选出 6 个, 由 60 名被试写出这些量词后最常出现的名词。最后选出每个量词后出现频率高的 2 个名词, 并且每组中名词词频与笔划数保持平衡, 再与这些量词共同作为实验材料。由于定配性强的量词一般熟悉性都较低, 定配性低的量词一般熟悉性都较高, 所以三组量词的熟悉性并不相等。实验材料见附录 4。

实验仪器

采用 E-prime 编写程序。实验仪器包括 PET-SRBOX 反应盒, 麦克风和计算机。图片都呈现在计算机屏幕中央, 被试的反应通过 PET-SRBOX 连接的麦克风记录, 计算机自动记录被试反应时, 计时单位为 ms, 误差为 ± 1ms。主试在旁边记录被试反应是否正确。

实验程序

实验分学习阶段和正式实验两个部分。在学习阶段, 被试要熟悉所有需要用到的量词和名词。在正式实验阶段, 被试被告知不需要注意量词, 尽量又快又准地对名词进行命名。实验程序是, 先呈现注视点 500ms, 接着按照不同启动条件, 呈现量词和名词, 被试命名时, 名词消失。在正式实验前, 有一个练习阶段, 让被试充分熟悉实验过程。正式实验阶段的刺激呈现顺序由电脑随机决定。所有数据处理均用 Spss13.0 统计软件包完成。

结果与分析

被试反应时的结果见表 5 和图 4。

表 3 被试对名词命名的平均反应时和标准差 (ms)

量词定配性	无启动条件	启动条件	
		SOA=100ms	SOA=200ms
定配性高	533(63)	513(61)	499(62)
定配性中	492(55)	493(57)	462(56)
定配性低	501(57)	491(62)	481(65)

图 3 被试对名词命名的平均反应时 (ms)

反应时的重复测量方差分析表明, 量词定配性的主效应显著, $F(2, 138) = 69.65$, $p < 0.001$ 。启动类型的主效应显著, $F(2, 138) = 42.37$, $p < 0.001$ 。量词定配性与启动类型交互作用也显著, $F(4, 276) = 5.73$, $p < 0.001$ 。简单效应分析表明, 对于定配性高的量词而言, 无启动条件下与 SOA=100ms 时的反应时差异显著, $p < 0.001$; 无启动条件下与 SOA=200ms 时的反应时差异也显著, $p < 0.001$; SOA=100ms 与 SOA=200ms 时的反应时差异也显著, $p < 0.05$ 。这表明, 定配性高的量词对所修饰的名词命名有显著的促进作用。对定配性中等的量词而言, 无启动条件下与 SOA=100ms 时反应时差异不显著, $p > 0.05$, 无启动条件下和 SOA=100ms 时的反应时与 SOA=200ms 时差异显著, $p < 0.001$ 。这表明, 定配性中等的量词对名词的启动作用发生得晚。对定配性低的量词而言, 反应时的趋势与定配性中等的量词类似, 只是启动量小一些。虽然三种量词的熟悉性不同, 笔画数不同, 量词修饰的名词也不完全同质, 但对三种定配性量词修饰的名词的命名反应时的比较时, 发现定配性高的量词修饰的名词命名反应时长, 是由于量词和名词熟悉性都低些的缘故。

讨论

本研究考察了定配性不同的量词在不同启动条件下对名词命名的影响。结果表明, 量词的定配性的主效应极显著, 说明量词对其所修饰的名词有显著限制作用。在 SOA=100ms 时, 定配性高的量词就显著出对所修饰的名词的显著的启动作用。但在此时, 定配性中等和定配性低的量词对所修饰的名词的命名却没有显著的影响。但是, 随着 SOA 的延长, 量词的语义被激活的更充分, 从而与量词有关的名词语义也被激活, 当 SOA=200ms 时, 对相应名词命名的反应时也缩短了。这表明, SOA=100ms 时, 定配性中等和定配性低的量词的语义激活还很低, 因而与之相关的名词不能被启动, 但

在 200ms 时, 量词的语义激活达到较高水平, 从而激活相关名词的语义, 所以命名名词的反应时就缩短了。

5. 综合讨论

实验一根据表象理论和双重编码理论来设计, 考察量词对名词表象认知的影响。量词的形成理据大多来源于名词, 特别是个体量词绝大多数由名词转化而来。这些量词的表形方式有鲜明的特点, 主要是运用了相似性、相关性、相联性的理据, 来实现编码以突出量词形象特征。与之相对应的则是形象性模糊的量词。根据双重编码理论, 量词本身是言语编码, 当人们看到量词的时候, 头脑中与量词形象相关的表象被激活, 这种表象自然会影响人们对与之组合的名词的特点的认识。但由表象理论, 我们得知人的视觉表象清晰度是不同的, 所以, 在看到量词的时候, 头脑中被激活的表象清晰度也不同, 因而, 对名词的认识程度的影响也不同。总的来说, 不论是形象性清晰还是形象性模糊的量词, 对视觉表象清晰度高的人认识名词的影响更大。另外, 从实验一的结果中, 我们看到不论视觉表象清晰度高或低, 当量词形象性清晰时, 他们对名词的认识均比量词形象性模糊时准确。这表明, 不同量词虽然主要是用来标量的, 但其表达效果确实不同, 直接影响人们对与之组合的名词的认识。这无疑是对“同义量词合并”的想法的有力驳斥。如果把同义量词合并, 不但使汉语表达逊色, 同时也掩盖了汉民族认识事物的方式和思维特点。

实验二进一步探讨量词对名词的定配性。扩散激活理论认为当激活从概念扩散到词汇水平时, 进入词汇激活和选择阶段, 有一些词产生语义激活, 包括目标项的语义激活和语义相关项的语义激活。当语义特征相应于一个刺激在语义水平上被激活时, 每一语义特征反过来激活与其联系的词条节点。例如, 量词“匹”在词汇水平被激活, 同时“马”、“布”也会有一定程度的激活。词汇水平上激活的节点将激活与其相连的所有节点。一般来说, 非目标词语的激活程度要弱于目标词语。经历一系列的步骤以后, 在词汇水平上激活最高的节点被选择。因此, 在本实验中, 我们看到随着 SOA 时间的延长, 被试命名的反应时在缩短, 这说明量词能激活与之相关的名词, 即量词具有定配性。在本实验的结果中, 我们发现定配性高的量词在各种条件下命名反应时都最长, 而定配性中等和低的则较短, 这符合 Forster & Chambers (1973) 的发现, 即高频词的命名要比罕见词的要快, 因为定配性高的量词和与之组合的名词笔划复杂、熟悉性低, 故属于低频词, 反应时长。本实验的另一个重要结果是定配性高的量词在 SOA 为 100ms 时就产生明显的激活作用, 而定配性中等和低的量词在 SOA 为 100ms 时这种激活不明显, 因为 Fan 效应理论认为一个概念与越多的事实相关联, 那么提取其中一个事实的时间也越长, 与定配性高的量词组合的名词很有限, 所以, 在 SOA 很短的情况下, 名词能被提取出来, 而定配性低的量词所能组合的名

词甚多, 故需要较长的 SOA 来提取名词。实验三的各种结果充分反应了量词具有定配性。

6. 结论

本研究通过两个实验考察了量词的一些特点, 主要结论归纳如下:

(1) 个体物量词按照其形象性程度可分为形象明晰的和形象模糊的, 量词的形象性对人的认知加工的影响因人而异。在认知事物的形象特征时, 高视觉表象清晰度的人更能从量词的形象性中获益, 而这种影响对低视觉表象清晰度的人而言就要小许多。但不论怎样, 量词本身形象性对所有人对名词表征的物体形象的认知都有影响, 不过是影响大小不同而已。因此, 汉语中的个体物量词具有不同的形象色彩, 不能随意的进行简化和合并。

(2) 个体物量词具有可预测性, 即量词的定配性和量词对名词的反制约。量词的定配性分为高、中、低三种情况, 定配性高的量词被激活的时间最短, 对名词的限制最强, 而定配性中等和低的量词被激活的时间相对长些, 所以, 它们对名词的制约弱些。

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Offline Processing of *Ba-* and *Bei-*Constructions in Mandarin Chinese

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This study investigated how Chinese speakers use different types of linguistic cues in offline processing and interpretation of *Ba-* and *Bei-*constructions. Two untimed acceptability/naturalness judgement tests were conducted. Both experiments showed that Chinese generally tends to prefer animate NP1s and inanimate NP2s. Thus, Chinese seems to combine animacy and word order cues for interpretation. This tendency is modulated by morphosyntactic cues reflected in speakers' favoring of inanimate NP1s with *Bei-*constructions and animate NP1s with *Ba-*constructions in Experiment 1. We also found a facilitative role for animacy contrast in sentence comprehension from Experiment 1, in which sentences with inanimate and animate NPs were accepted with higher scores. Experiment 2 revealed somewhat different patterns from those obtained in Experiment 1. The critical finding was that *Bei-*constructions favored inanimate NP2s, which was not predicted based on the animacy-based thematic cues. The addition of manner adverbs following NP1s to prepare for online studies provides a possible account for this finding. Agent-oriented manner adverbs could have invoked an interpretation of NP1 as agent, so a patient/theme reading of NP2 was favored. This result may also be explained by specific properties of the *Bei-*construction. Overall, the findings of this study support the view that on-line sentence comprehension is probabilistically constrained by different sources of information in the manner of competition and convergence.

0. Introduction

One of the fundamental aspects of language use and learning is to determine *who-did-what-to-whom* in the events denoted by transitive clauses. For example, given the sentence, *the dog chased the coyote*, an English speaker should have the knowledge that *the dog* is the initiator of this chasing event and *the coyote* is the receiver the action is performed upon. To build up this event representation during sentence comprehension, language users must semantically interpret *the dog* in the subject position as the agent and *the coyote* in the object position the patient. Several models have been proposed to explain how the thematic role each NP is assigned in this process and the semantic relationships between the thematic roles different NPs bear is computed (Ferreira & Henderson, 1990; MacWhinney, 2007; MacDonald, 2013; Trueswell & Tanenhaus, 1994). Garden-path and constraint-based models among others as the two most prominent approaches to sentence processing both hold that thematic role assignment is highly incremental as sentence proceeds and multiple kinds of linguistic information can be used for the assignment (see

Ferreira & Çokal (2016) for review). What differs between them relates to the time-course of the activation and application of different sources of information during this process (Van Gompel et al., 2001). For example, mixed results exist regarding the role of semantic information, e.g., animacy, in the initial parsing stage of sentence processing. In two eye-tracking experiments, Trueswell et al (1994) revealed that, when presented with temporarily ambiguous sentence strings such as (1) the defendant examined by... vs. (2) the evidence examined by..., readers experienced more processing difficulties with (1) than with (2). This is because an animate NP better fits the interpretation of it as an Agent as opposed to a Patient to which an inanimate NP is usually assigned. When (1) was initially encountered, its interpretation was skewed towards the main clause rather than the reduced relative clause. Thus, processing difficulty arose when disambiguating information in the *by*-phrase, became available. Ferreira and Clifton (1986) demonstrated, however, that NP1 animacy information was not consulted until the reanalysis stage. According to the constraint-based model, linguistic information of various kinds is parallelly activated to probabilistically trigger all analyses that are consistent with the grammar in a given language (MacDonald et al., 1994; Van Gompel et al., 2001). Therefore, in the case of (1) and (2), the verb form which is morphologically ambiguous between a past tense and a passive participle form also statistically provides cues in conjunction with NP1 animacy to constrain sentence interpretation.

Decades of psycholinguistic research have primarily focused on syntactically complex clause structures involving local ambiguity or long-distance dependency (e.g., subject/object relative clauses, *wh*-questions). Little attention has been paid to people's comprehension of basic and unambiguous sentences (Ferreira, 2003). Ferreira (2003) further pointed out that existing models are inadequate to account for difficulties associated with the processing of syntactically unambiguous sentences especially when the correct thematic role assignment is challenged by apparent world knowledge (e.g., the dog was bitten by the man). The Competition Model (Bates & MacWhinney, 1982, 1989) and Noun-Verb-Noun (NVN) heuristics (Bever, 1970; Townsend & Bever, 2001) are two widely adopted approaches to the processing of simple transitive sentences either in active or passive voice. The NVN heuristic approach assigns ranked strength to NPs based on animacy, case-marking, and word order, which are weighted differently crosslinguistically. The Competition Model proposes that such cues compete and converge for an interpretation during processing (MacWhinney, 2008). For example, in the English sentence *the brick hits the cat*, the word order cue wins over the animacy cue in their competition favoring *the brick* as an Agent. Thus, English treats word order as a stronger cue than animacy in that preverbal NPs in English are strongly associated with an agent interpretation. The situation is reversed in Japanese where animacy cues are weighted heavier than word order cues to determine the agent role in an event (Harrington, 1987). Therefore, the strength of word order cues is much higher for English speakers than that for Japanese speakers. The empirical findings from Chinese, which serves as the target language for the current study, are divergent (e.g., Li et al., 1993; Philipp et al., 2008).

Relevant research will be reviewed in detail in Section 2. The NVN heuristic-based approach argued that, instead of using fine-grained syntactic and semantic information, comprehenders basically employ an NVN processing strategy to produce a ‘shallow’ sentence interpretation whereby any NP appearing in the grammatical subject and object position in a sentence is parsed as the agent and patient respectively (Carlson & Tanenhaus, 1988; Ferreira, 2003; Townsend & Bever, 2001). The use of this strategy may provide an alternative explanation to the processing difficulties associated with English passives which are often misinterpreted as actives (Ferreira, 2003, Messenger et al., 2012). It is an empirical question as to whether the application of the NVN strategy is a language-specific cognitive process or a universal perceptual strategy that language users would employ during sentence processing. Given that English primarily relies on word order cues (SVO) to achieve thematic role assignment, it would be not easy to disentangle the potential effects of NVN heuristics and linguistically driven cues in English. Therefore, it is desirable to investigate languages such as Mandarin Chinese (henceforth, ‘Chinese’), whose linguistic properties are distinct from many Indo-European languages. The current study provides experimental evidence to further examine the roles that animacy, word order and morphosyntactic markers play in building up semantic interpretation in Chinese. Before delving into the experiments, we briefly present some linguistic facts about the target structure *ba/bei* constructions and also relevant empirical research that has been done regarding the influences of different cues on the representation and processing of Chinese *ba/bei* constructions.

1. The structure and processing of *Ba-* and *Bei-* constructions

Like English, Chinese heavily uses word order to encode grammatical and thematic relations among constituents in a syntactic structure (Chao, 1968; Li & Thompson, 1981). The dominant word order in Chinese is SVO (Sun & Givon, 1985). Given such word orders, the thematic role each NP in a transitive clause receives depends on their relative positioning with respect to the main verb, namely the NP preceding the verb is interpreted as the agent and the NP following the verb is parsed as the patient. In this case, the effects of word order and animacy would be hard to tease apart especially when the NP1 were animate, which is the also the case in English. To separate those effects, we take advantage of two types of verb-final constructions in Chinese to investigate how preverbal morphosyntactic markers (*Ba/Bei*) and the NP animacy are coordinated for interpretation. *Ba* and *Bei* are free morphemes and often treated as morphosyntactic markers which are distinguished from the case markers typically seen in most Indo-European languages (Huang et al., 2013). Structurally, in both *Ba-* and *Bei-* constructions exemplified in (1), the sentence-initial NP serves as the grammatical subject, and the grammatical object is preceded by the marker *Ba* or *Bei*. Although the syntactic status of *Ba* and *Bei* remains to be settled (see Hui (2012) for review),¹ they are thematically associated with adjacent NPs.

¹ They are treated either as co-verbs or prepositions.

The NP appearing before the marker *Ba* receives the agent role and the NP following the marker receives the patient role. In *Ba*- constructions shown in (1a), word order, morphosyntactic markers and animacy would point to the same thematic role assignment. When the *Bei* marker is used, the thematic role of NP1 is Patient and NP2 is Agent. Thus, in the *Bei* construction, if the word order and morphosyntactic markers are both applied during sentence interpretation, conflicting thematic role assignment arises. But if animacy interacts with both cues in this case, the interpretation of NP1 would be towards Agent. Therefore, Chinese offers an ideal window into the investigation of how those cues are weighted and interact to influence Chinese sentence processing and interpretation. In addition, the fact that the verb appears sentence-finally in the *Ba*- and *Bei*-constructions leaves out the potential influence from verb forms on sentence processing.

- (1) a. Xiaonanhai ba pingguo chi-le.
 Little boy BA apple eat-PERF²
 AGENT PATIENT ACTION
 ‘The little boy ate an apple.’
- b. Pingguo bei xiaonanhai chi-le.
 Apple BEI little boy eat-PERF
 PATIENT AGENT ACTION
 ‘‘The apple was eaten by the little boy’’

Previous studies on these constructions have adopted various methods and have led to mixed results. The first systematic study of sentence processing in Chinese within the framework of Competition Model was carried out by Li, Bates and MacWhinney (1993). In this study, they constructed various types of sentence strings each containing two nouns and a verb by manipulating different cue combinations involved in those sentences. Participants were instructed to identify the picture that corresponds to the agent in the sentence they auditorily received. The results reflected a complex interaction among different cues during sentence interpretation. They proposed the hierarchy of cue strengths in Chinese: passive marker *bei* > animacy > word order > object marker *ba* > indefinite marker *yi*. Despite of the informativeness regarding how different cues compete and converge for Chinese sentence interpretation, several methodologically related issues in their study were identified and addressed in the current study. First, the inanimate NP1 – inanimate NP2 configuration both for *Ba*- and *Bei*-constructions, which is completely acceptable in Chinese, was absent. Second, the inclusion of ungrammatical stimuli, which is a common practice by proponents of Competition Model, could have had an unnatural effect on sentence interpretation (Bates, 1999). Third, participants were asked to decide only the agent, but not both agent and patient roles, of each sentence. In response to these

² PERF is the abbreviation for perfective marker indicating the completion of an event.

issues raised in Li et al. (1993), the following improvements are made in our study. First, the test sentences are created with NP1 and NP1 animacy fully crossed in either *Ba*- or *Bei*-constructions. Second, all the test sentences used for experimentation are naturally occurring in daily speech thus completely grammatical. Third, we adopted acceptability judgement tests (AJTs) to tap into reader's comprehension of each sentence in its entirety. Regarding the correlation between cue strength and offline sentence processing, it is predicted that competing cues inhibit interpretation resulting in lower acceptability, whereas converging cues facilitate interpretation leading to higher acceptability. Philipp et al. (2008) conducted an ERP research investigating how animacy of NPs influence the processing of Chinese *Ba*- and *Bei*-constructions reflected in different event-related brain potentials. Their results revealed no interaction between *Ba* and NP animacy and also no main effect of animacy at the position of NP1. In addition, they also found an N400 effect for the *Bei*-construction with an inanimate NP1. This is because Chinese *Bei*-constructions are argued to be associated with adversative readings (Li & Thompson, 1989), and only animate entities appearing in the NP1 position can experience this psychological state. The inanimate NP1 causes a semantic conflict and leads to the N400 effect. Zhou & Ma (2018) controlled the animacy of NPs and found that Chinese adults could use morphosyntactic information encoded in *Ba* and *Bei* to equally effectively build up event structure representation during sentence processing in a visual world eye-tracking experiment.

To provide further evidence for how different kinds of linguistic cues can be used and coordinated during sentence processing, we conducted two untimed acceptability/naturalness judgement task (AJT) experiments. Specifically, experiment 1 was carried out to examine how animacy, morphosyntactic information, and word order cues constrain offline sentence interpretation by Chinese speakers. However, untimed AJTs cannot tell us when these cues are utilized as sentences unfold in real time. We therefore plan to conduct a self-paced reading (SPR) experiment in future to closely look at the timing of the constraints applied during sentence processing. Experiment 2 was set up to serve as the baseline for the preplanned SPR experiment in which the test sentences are the same as those used in the current study except when modification is necessary.

2. The current study

2.1. Experiment 1

2.1.1. Participants

149 native speakers of Mandarin Chinese (70 males and 79 females, mean age=18.7) voluntarily participated in this experiment. All the participants were college students from mainland China and naïve to the theoretical purposes of this study.

2.1.2. Design & Materials

We manipulated three factors, namely the animacy³ of NP1 (animate vs. inanimate), NP2 (animate vs. inanimate) and the morphosyntactic markers (Ba vs. Bei). The test sentences thus were created out of a 2x2x2 fully crossed factorial design. We constructed 64 critical sentences for eight conditions each with 8 items. Each sentence is formatted as NP1+Ba/Bei+NP2+RVCs+PERF exemplified in (2a). RVC refers to resultative verb compounds, which are often used in conjunction with *Ba*- and *Bei*-constructions. This is because both constructions signal disposability of some kind in that they describe events where an entity or person (NP2 in *Ba*-constructions and NP1 in *Bei*-constructions) is affected in some way (Li & Thompson, 1989). A RVC consists of two adjacent verbs (V1V2) with V1 denoting the action and V2 the result. In addition, disposability usually implies the completeness of an event (telicity), which is why both sentence types end with the perfective maker (*le*). The 64 critical items were distributed among eight lists using a Latin Square procedure such that participants will never read experimental items from each condition more than once.⁴ This method means that each participant will receive only one item per condition plus 36 fillers (half of them are ungrammatical), for a total of 44 items. Items of each list were randomized for distribution. An example sentence is shown in (2).

- (2) Xiaonanhai ba shengzi jianduan-le.
 Little boy BA rope cut-broken PERF.
 ‘The little boy cut through the rope.’

2.1.3. Procedure

The task was an untimed acceptability judgment test (AJT) in written format. The experiment began with 6 practice items for participants to familiarize themselves with the task (2 each of low, medium and high acceptability). Including the practice items, each participant was assigned 50 items in the experimental session. The task was implemented via Qualtrics. Surveys were sent to the target participants for them to do on their own laptop or tablet. Participants rated sentences for acceptability along a 7-point Likert scale with 1 indicating completely unacceptable and 7 completely acceptable. After AJT session, participants answered questions about their language background. The experimental session lasted approximately 15 minutes.

2.1.4. Data analysis

For individual participants, the difference between the average rating of the two completely ungrammatical and completely grammatical practice items was computed.

³ Animacy is deemed gradient ranging from the most animate (e.g., humans) to the least animate (e.g., abstract concepts) (Aissen, 2003). The current study follows (Paczynski & Kuperberg, 2011), however, adopting a binary distinction grouping humans and animals to ANIMATE and other inanimate entities to INANIMATE.

⁴ With only one item per condition per participant, the AJTs can still be well-powered (Sprouse & Almeida, 2017).

Seven participants each of whom has a difference lower than zero, indicating a failure to understand the task, were excluded for statistical analysis. Another 2 participants who took time beyond 2.5 standard deviations from the mean to complete the experiment were further removed. To reduce skewedness and mitigate scale bias, z-score transformation was applied to all ratings (fillers included⁵) collected from individual participants.

Linear mixed-effects (LME) regression was used to model the variation of z-scores as a function of the three factors under investigation. The model includes NP1 animacy, NP2 animacy, morphosyntactic marker and their interactions as the fixed effects. To facilitate the interpretation of main effects and interactions, all fixed effects were sum coded (-0.5 = NP1 animate or NP2 animate or *Ba*, +0.5 = NP1 inanimate, NP2 inanimate or *Bei*). Participants and items were treated as random effects. Following Barr et al. (2013), we maintained a maximal random effect structure allowed by the design, adding by-participant random slopes for within-subject factors. The random effect structure was simplified whenever the model failed to converge. The model eventually converged when the by-item intercept was removed⁶ and only by-participant random slopes for NP1 was kept. Residuals of LME models were always checked revealing no obvious deviations from normality and homoscedasticity, thus meeting assumptions required by the LME modelling. All statistical analyses were conducted with R version 3.6.2 (R Core Team, 2019). *P*-values were obtained using lmer Test package (Kuznetsova, Brockhoff & Christensen, 2017).

2.1.5. Results

The distribution of the z-scored ratings from different conditions is illustrated in Figure 1. The estimated coefficients of the LME models are displayed in Table 1. Of theoretical interest are the findings of interaction between NP1 animacy and morphosyntactic markers and the three-way interaction among NP1 animacy, morphosyntactic marker and NP2 animacy. Post-hoc multiple comparison with Tukey *p*-value adjustments for the two-way interaction indicated that *Ba*-constructions significantly prefer animate NP1s ($\beta=0.329$, $t=4.297$, $p<.0001$). When NP1 was inanimate, *Bei*-constructions were accepted significantly higher than *Ba*-constructions ($\beta=-0.349$, $t=0.072$, $p<.001$). Critical results from post-hoc comparison for the three-way interaction are summarized as follows. First, *Ba*-constructions with animate NP2s prefer inanimate NP1s to animate NP1s ($\beta=0.303$, $t=2.45$, $p<.05$). Second, *Bei*-constructions with animate NP1s tend to have inanimate NP2s rather than animate NP2s ($\beta=0.445$, $t=4.194$, $p<.001$). Third, when NP1 was inanimate and NP2 was animate, *Bei*-constructions were more acceptable than *Ba*-constructions ($\beta=0.571$, $t=5.04$, $p<.001$). As also can be seen in the table, the main

⁵ The practice of including critical items and fillers for z-score transformation was suggested by Jon Sprouse (email communication, Oct. 10, 2019). By doing so, we can avoid running the risk of confounding the target effect and scale bias.

⁶ It is theoretically reasonable to not include random intercepts for items because the number of critical items per condition per participant ($n=1$) is small and the inclusion of by-item random intercept would overshadow the amount of variance that fixed effects could have explained.

effects of NP1 and NP2 indicate a preference for animate NP1s and inanimate NP2s regardless of *Ba*- and *Bei*-constructions. The main effect of morphosyntactic marker indicates that *Bei*-constructions were generally preferred than *Ba*-constructions in Mandarin Chinese.

Figure 1. Interaction of NP animacy and ba/bei in normalized acceptability

Table 1. Model outputs for normalized acceptability

Effects of NP1 animacy, NP2 animacy and morphosyntactic markers on ZAJs					
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>std. Error</i>	<i>Conf. Int (95%)</i>	<i>Statistic</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
(Intercept)	0.00	0.05	-0.09 – 0.09	0.00	1.000
NP1	-0.13	0.06	-0.24 – -0.02	-2.25	0.025
NP2	0.29	0.05	0.19 – 0.39	5.80	<0.001
ConsType	0.15	0.05	0.05 – 0.25	2.95	0.003
NP1:NP2	-0.18	0.10	-0.38 – 0.02	-1.80	0.072
NP1:ConsType	0.40	0.10	0.20 – 0.60	3.95	<0.001
NP2:ConsType	-0.16	0.10	-0.36 – 0.04	-1.60	0.110
NP1*NP2*ConsType	-0.57	0.20	-0.96 – -0.17	-2.80	0.005
Random Effects					
σ^2	0.72				
τ_{00} subject	0.21				
τ_{11} subject.NP11	0.10				
ρ_{01} subject	0.98				
ICC	0.25				
N _{subject}	141				
Observations	1128				
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.050 / 0.283				

AJTs that ask participants to provide a rating to a given sentence can only measure the end-product of comprehension, not the moment-by-moment process itself. Future investigation will use self-paced reading (SPR) or eye-tracking to tap into the dynamic process where linguistic information of different sources is used and integrated as sentence unfolds over time. Experiment 2 which used naturalness judgment test (NJT) on one hand aims to set up the baseline for online performance by Chinese speakers as to how they offline interpret *Ba*- and *Bei*-constructions with different NP1-NP2 animacy configurations. On the other hand, the materials used in NJTs will be ready for SPR or eye-tracking reading research in future.

2.2. Experiment 2

The methods of Experiment 2 including design, material, procedure and data analysis were the same as Experiment 1, except as described here.

2.2.1. Participants

112 native speakers of Chinese (54 males and 58 females, mean age=19) who had not participated in experiment 1 recruited from mainland China took part in the current experiment. All the participants again were naïve to the purpose of this study.

2.2.2. Materials

The materials adopted from experiment 1 were modified as follows. First, a sentence-initial time adverbial was added to create a discourse context for each sentence to be presented. Second, a demonstrative determiner modifying NP1 was added to explicitly mark the definiteness of NP1. Third, between NP1 and morphosyntactic markers was a manner adverbial inserted to create a region for the potential effect of NP1 animacy to be located. Fourth, to handle the wrap-up effects during sentence processing, every sentence ended with a comment. An example sentence is illustrated in (3).

- (3) Zuotian zaoshang, nage nanhai henhende ba zuqiu tifeile, zhen lihai!
 Yesterday morning, that boy strongly Ba football kick fly into air-PERF, so great!
 ‘Yesterday morning, that boy strongly kicked the football into air, so great.’

2.2.3. Procedure

The task was again implemented via Qualtrics. Surveys were sent to the target participants for them to do on their own laptop or tablet. Participants rated sentences for naturalness along a 7-point Likert scale with 1 indicating very unnatural and 7 very natural. After the judgement test session, participants answered questions about their language background. The experimental session lasted approximately 15 minutes.

2.2.4. Data analysis

Following the same steps for screening participants, 97 participants remained for statistical analyses.

2.2.5. Results

The distribution of the z-scored ratings from different conditions is illustrated in Figure 2. The estimated coefficients of the LME models are displayed in Table 2. As can be seen from the table, there is an interaction between NP2 and morphosyntactic marker. Post-hoc multiple comparison with Tukey p-value adjustments for this interaction indicated that *Bei*-constructions prefer NP2s to be inanimate ($\beta=-0.558$, $t=-5.863$, $p<.001$). When NP2s were animate, *Ba*-constructions were preferred than *Bei*-constructions ($\beta=0.671$, $t=7.047$, $p<.001$). Regarding the main effects of NP1 and NP2, animate NP1s and inanimate NP2s were generally preferred irrespective of morphosyntactic markers. Chinese speakers showed a preference for *Ba*-constructions than *Bei*-constructions in this experiment.

Figure 2. Interaction of NP animacy and ba/bei in normalized acceptability

Table 2. Model outputs for normalized acceptability

Effects of NP1 animacy, NP2 animacy and morphosyntactic markers on ZAJs					
Predictors	Estimates	std. Error	Conf. Int (95%)	Statistic	P-Value
(Intercept)	-0.02	0.04	-0.10 – 0.06	-0.41	0.683
NP1	-0.15	0.07	-0.28 – -0.02	-2.21	0.027
NP2	0.29	0.07	0.16 – 0.42	4.29	<0.001
ConsType	-0.40	0.07	-0.53 – -0.27	-5.97	<0.001
NP1:NP2	0.12	0.13	-0.14 – 0.38	0.89	0.372
NP1:ConsType	0.05	0.13	-0.21 – 0.32	0.39	0.696
NP2:ConsType	0.54	0.13	0.27 – 0.80	4.00	<0.001
NP1*NP2*ConsType	-0.13	0.27	-0.65 – 0.40	-0.47	0.639
Random Effects					
σ^2	0.89				
τ_{00} subject	0.05				
ICC	0.05				
N _{subject}	98				
Observations	784				
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.084 / 0.130				

3. Discussion

The purpose of this study was to examine how and to what extent different linguistic cues would affect Chinese speakers' offline processing and interpretation of *Ba*- and *Bei*-constructions. Different cues are weighted differently such that those cues may play differential roles in this process. Moreover, given that sentence interpretation may be probabilistically constrained by various kinds of linguistic information in the manner of competition or convergence, there should be some interplay among different linguistic cues in constraining Chinese speakers' sentence comprehension. Without considering the effects of morphosyntactic markers, both experiments seem to suggest that Chinese sentence tends to prefer an animate NP1 and an inanimate NP2. This finding is inconsistent with Philipp et al. (2008), who found no animacy effect at NP1. In this case, the results indicate that Chinese patterns with languages such as English treating whatever appears in the NP1 position as the agent, which is closely related to animate entities. It might also be the case that Chinese speakers simply adopt a Noun-Verb-Noun processing strategy when interpreting transitive clauses either in active or passive voice. This pattern is consistent with an isolating language in which basic word order is the dominant cue for interpretation of thematic roles and grammatical functions.

Despite the main effect of morphosyntactic markers obtained in either experiment, the directionality of the difference between *Ba*- and *Bei*-constructions differs. According to constraint-based models, structures of higher frequency should be easier to process than those of relatively low frequency (MacDonald et al., 1994). *Bei*-constructions, which are far less frequent than *Ba*-constructions, should incur more processing difficulties. The result of experiment 2 where *Ba*-constructions were more acceptable than *Bei*-constructions supported such a prediction. The case was the opposite in experiment 1 where *Bei*-constructions were accepted more than *Ba*-constructions. We provide no satisfactory explanation to this asymmetry based on the current study.

Taking into account all relevant factors, we indeed found a complex interplay among different cues during Chinese sentence processing and interpretation in both experiments. In experiment 1, the results showed that *Ba*-constructions prefer animate NP1s and *Bei*-constructions prefer inanimate NP1s. This is a clear interaction between the animacy of NP1 and morphosyntactic markers. This pattern can be well explained by the Competition Model (Bates & MacWhinney, 1987). Animate NP1 is correlated to the assignment of the agent role, and *Ba* marker cues the assignment of NP1 in the grammatical subject position as the agent. Likewise, inanimate NP1 is correlated to the assignment of the patient/theme role, and *Bei* marker confirms the assignment of NP1 as the patient/theme role. Both cues converge to promote the interpretation of NP1 in *Ba*-constructions as the agent and NP1 in *Bei*-constructions as the patient/theme. Incremental processing models can also provide some insights as to how such interpretation was accomplished. The parser treated the first encountered NP in the subject position, especially when the NP1 was

animate, as the agent. The interpretation was confirmed when the parser encountered *Ba* marker but revised when *Bei* marker was integrated to the ongoing representation.

Another important finding from experiment 1 is that either *Ba*- or *Bei*-constructions were more acceptable when NP1 and NP2 are contrastive in animacy compared to when they are not. The facilitative effect of animacy contrast was also observed in eye-tracking and ERP studies of non-canonical sentence comprehension among aphasia patients (Caramazza & Zurif, 1976) and samples from unimpaired populations (Traxler, Morris & Seely, 2002). One explanation to this robust effect is that animacy contrasts allow comprehenders to more easily activate animacy cues to assign thematic roles of NPs during sentence processing (Ferreira, 2003).

In experiment 2, morphosyntactic markers interacted with NP2 animacy but not with NP1 animacy. Critically, regardless of the animacy of NP1, *Bei*-constructions were more acceptable when NP2 was inanimate compared to when NP2 was animate. It seems that NP1 animacy does not play a role in initially assigning a thematic role to NP1 in the subject position before any further information was encountered by comprehenders. We speculate that the manner adverb following NP1s and the construction-specific properties related to *Bei*-constructions may play some role in this process. First, the adverb *cleverly* in sentences such as *John cleverly dropped his cup of coffee* was deemed subject-oriented (Jackendoff, 1972 : 49) or agent-oriented (Piñón, 2010). Accordingly, one reading we can get from the sentence *John cleverly dropped his cup of coffee* is *It was clever of John to drop his cup of coffee*. We argued that the manner adverbs (e.g., *toutoude*, ‘secretly’; *buxiaoxin*, ‘carelessly’) added after NP1s may be semantically associated with the interpretation of NP1 as agent. The process could be that NP1 was not assigned with any thematic roles until the encounter of the manner adverb which leads the interpretation of NP1 towards agent, and the parser anticipates a patient/theme until it receives an inanimate NP2, which is an ideal patient/theme. The effect of *Bei* marker seems not strong enough to modulate this process. The higher acceptance of *Bei*-constructions containing inanimate NP2s can also be attributed to the adversative reading with which *Bei*-construction is typically associated. The adversely affected argument in *Bei*-constructions is NP1, which is the experiencer of this affectedness, and an animate NP1 is an ideal experiencer even though it is thematically interpreted as a patient/theme. The animacy contrast may operate in this case such that inanimate NP2s were expected and thus preferred.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we investigated how different linguistic cues operate in Chinese speakers’ processing and interpretation of *Ba*- and *Bei*-constructions. Not considering morphosyntactic markers, Mandarin Chinese seems to pattern like English resorting to animacy-linked word order cues to establish interpretation. The interpretation constructed by NP animacy and word order cues is subject to modulation when morphosyntactic information is integrated and used during this process. NP1-NP2 animacy contrasts seem to play an important role in sentence interpretation, especially when the sentences used for

the experiments are simple in structure (NP1 Ba/Bei NP2 V). When more complex clause structures were constructed (temporal adverbial, NP1 manner adverb Ba/Bei NP2 V, comment), the main interaction was found to be morphosyntactic marker*NP2 animacy rather than NP1*morphosyntactic marker(*NP2). The properties related to manner adverb and sentence construction could account for the favor of inanimate NP2s in *Bei*-constructions. As the current study only looked into the offline processing of Chinese sentences, future research should consider using reaction time measures such as SPR and eye-tracking to analyze the time course of activation and use of different kinds of linguistic information during sentence processing.

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CFL Learners' Mandarin Syllable-Tone Word Production: Effects of Task and Prior Phonological and Lexical Learning

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This study examined the learning outcome of a 3-day Mandarin Chinese word learning experiment in terms of word production. Fifteen beginner-level L1-English Chinese as a Foreign Language (CFL) learners learned ten tonal monosyllabic minimal pairs (e.g., *ku1* 'to cry' vs. *ku4* 'warehouse') in a sound-image word learning experiment in three consecutive days. Half of the words were homophonous with previously learned words (e.g., *ku4* 'pants'), and the other half did not have any previously learned homophones (e.g., *ku1*). Within the homophonous and non-homophonous words, half had high syllable token frequency (e.g., *ta*) while the other half had low syllable token frequency (e.g., *ku*). After the word learning sessions, participants performed an image naming task followed by a pinyin-reading task. Ten native Mandarin speakers transcribed the recorded tokens as an assessment of the production accuracy. The results showed that overall word production in the pinyin-reading task was more accurate than naming. We also found homophone status and phonological syllable token frequency also interacted with task type. The results suggest that learners' word production is affected by pinyin orthography, prior phonological and lexical knowledge.

0. Introduction

Adult Chinese as a Foreign Language (CFL) learners typically started with Pinyin instruction. For example, in the United States, commonly used Chinese textbook series for college learners, such as Integrated Chinese (Liu and Yao 2009) and Chinese Link (Wu et al. 2010), all begin with familiarizing learners with the pinyin system. Pinyin has been shown to facilitate word learning in adult CFL learners (Everson, 1998; Jiang, 2003). A very strong correlation was found between CFL learners' ability to pronounce or write pinyin for given words and their knowledge of word meanings. More recently, in a study of the impact of pinyin on vocabulary assessment, Zhang et al. (2019) asked CFL learners to take a computer-based test in which they had first to select a picture that represented the meaning of a target word presented in characters only, and then answer the same item presented in both characters and pinyin. The provision of pinyin

substantially increased test reliability and learners' test scores. Among those test items that were initially given wrong responses when only characters were provided, almost all were corrected the second time when pinyin was presented together with the characters.

It is widely known that lexical tone is very challenging for CFL learners if their L1 is a non-tonal language such as English (Hao, 2012; Pelzl, 2019). In the research of CFL learners' tone learning, study has found that pinyin accompanied with either the visual drawing of the pitch contour or tone diacritic (e.g., ā á ǎ à) is more effective than pinyin accompanied with tone number (e.g., a1, a2, a3, a4) in terms of tone identification (Liu et al., 2011; Chung, 2002; 2003). A similar facilitative effect of tonal diacritics has been found in tone production as well (Wiener et al., 2020). In addition to the research on the use of different formats of pinyin on tone perception and production, Chang (2018) further studied how tone format in pinyin affected word learning in L2 Chinese. Three visual-prompt conditions were used in her word learning sessions for a group of intermediate L1-English CFL learners to learn a set of new Chinese words written in Chinese characters: (1) tone diacritics + pinyin + English translation; (2) tone number + pinyin + English translation; and (3) English translation only. The audio file for each word was played to the participants together with one of the three visual prompts during the word learning session. After the learners passed a criterion test with 90% correct, they were asked to complete a tone perception and production task. The result showed that participants in the tone diacritics + pinyin condition outperformed participants in the other two conditions. This study shows that even though the participants in all three conditions learned the meaning associated with the words very well (above 90% accuracy), the tonal representation they finally attained is still largely affected by the format of tone representation. It also showed that presenting tone numbers to learners did no better job than without any tone information (English translation only condition).

In the current study, we further study L1-English CFL learners' word learning, particularly to examine how learners' pinyin knowledge and previously learned homophones may affect the word production at the end of a spoken word learning experiment. One interesting result in Chang (2018) is that in the character-only condition without any pinyin input, the participants simply exposed to the audio files still reached a reasonable accuracy rate in tone production (62%). It suggests that with a certain amount of formal Chinese instruction or input, learners seem to be able to use established phonological representation of syllables + tones to learn new words without any pinyin orthography. Liu and Wiener (2020) found that beginner-level CFL learners can use previously learned homophones to better learn a set of new words in terms of spoken word recognition. The participants learned the new words with tonal contrasts in a 'natural' sound-to-image spoken word learning paradigm. Here 'natural' means no orthography input at all. Thus, it simulates a child's acquisition of new vocabulary. The current study serves as an extension of Liu and Wiener's (2020) study. We examine a subset of the participants from their study and have them perform two oral production tasks after the image-to-sound learning. Understanding that providing pinyin with tone

diacritics is highly effective for L2 Chinese word learning, we examined to what extent the naming of new words through a direct meaning-to-sound mapping task is comparable to the reading of the same new words written in pinyin. To do this, we asked the participants to produce the newly learned words by viewing either their picture only or their pinyin only. In this way, we examine whether the two production tasks differ in how they make use of learners' prior lexical and phonological knowledge.

1. Research questions

1. After learning a set of new words, do CFL learners' production of the newly learned words differ in the picture-naming and pinyin-reading tasks in terms of accuracy?
2. After learning a set of new words, do learners produce newly learned words that have homophones more accurately than words without any homophones in the picture-naming and pinyin-reading tasks? Does syllable token frequency interact with this learning?

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

Fifteen beginner level CFL learners (7 male; 8 female) who had learned Chinese for just over one semester (about 19 weeks) at a public U.S. university took part in the study. All participants were native English speakers, no participant was a heritage Chinese speaker, and no participant self-reported speaking another foreign language. No participant self-reported a hearing or vision impairment. All participants received class credit and a small payment for their participation. To measure the participants' pronunciation accuracy, 10 native adult Chinese speakers in China with minimal exposure to CFL learners transcribed the word tokens produced by the learners in pinyin.

2.2 Stimuli

We first built a small corpus of words that the participants have already learned in the textbook (*Integrated Chinese, level 1, part 1*; Liu & Yao, 2009). It shows that the participants had been exposed to 115 unique syllable types in formal class instruction. For example, the syllable-tone combination *ku4* occurred in words such as 裤子 *ku4-zi* 'pants', 短裤 *duan3-ku4* 'shorts', etc. Thus, we considered *ku* a learned syllable and identified one unlearned tonal homophone 库 *ku4* 'warehouse' as well as one unlearned tonal non-homophone 哭 *ku1* 'to cry.' This design resulted in a total of 20 words with two homophone status conditions: homophone (10 words) and non-homophone (10 words) (see the word list in the Appendix).

Following Ziegler et al. (2000) and Wang et al. (2012), we categorized our stimuli into high syllable token frequency if its token count was ≥ 8 and low syllable token frequency if its token count was < 8 . Thus, homophone status and syllable token frequency were crossed, resulting in 4 conditions (Homophone-High, Homophone-Low, Non-homophone-High, Non-homophone-Low) with 5 items per condition for a total of 20 target monosyllabic words or 10 minimal pairs differing in tone.

Prior to the experiment, all participants were screened to ensure that they did not know the 20 new words but did know the presumed 10 homophones. None of the 20 new words were correctly identified by the participants. All participants correctly identified the 10 previously learned words' pinyin and English translation.

The 20 target words were recorded by a female native Mandarin speaker from Beijing. Recordings were saved at 44k Hz/16 bits using Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2018). Each word was paired with a hand-drawn color image designed to establish the sound--meaning connection. Figure 1 shows the *ku4*-*ku1* minimal pair.

Figure 1. Images used for *ku4* 'warehouse' (left, homophone-low frequency condition) and *ku1* 'to cry' (right, non-homophone-low frequency condition).

2.3 Procedure

Participants came to the language lab for three consecutive days. They sat in front of a computer screen with headphones on. When the experiment started, the audio file of a target word was played to the participant meanwhile the image of the target word was shown on the screen. Participants were instructed to memorize the sound-image pair and to mouse-click at their own pace to advance to the next trial. After the learning trials, participants were tested using a 4-alternative-force-choice task in which four images were presented on the screen while one of the image's audio was played over headphones. Participants were asked to mouse-click on the perceived target as accurately and quickly as possible.

On the third day, all participants reached an accuracy rate of 80% or above in the spoken word recognition. Participants were asked to do a naming task and a pinyin reading task, which measured the participants' tone production. In the naming task, the 20 images were pseudo-randomly presented on screen. Participants were instructed to

produce the audio label associated with the images as accurately as possible. In the pinyin reading task, the 20 words written in pinyin with tone diacritics along with their English translation were presented to participants. Participants were instructed to read the words aloud as accurately as possible. Because we worried that the pinyin reading might bias participants, it was always presented second after the picture naming task.

Then ten native Chinese speakers listened to the recorded tokens and transcribed them in pinyin with tone category. We coded a token with value ‘1’ when everything (i.e., initial, final and tone) was correct and a value ‘0’ otherwise. The accuracy measurement was highly consistent among the 10 L1 raters indicated by Cronbach’s α (0.95 for the naming task; 0.94 for the pinyin reading task). Any item with disagreement among L1 raters was manually checked by the first author, who is a trained phonetician and experienced Chinese instructor.

3. Results

3.1 Word production accuracy analysis

To test whether task type (naming vs. pinyin-reading), homophone status (words with homophone vs. words without homophone) and syllable token frequency (high vs. low) affected word production accuracy, a mixed-effects logistic regression model was built with the *lme4* package in R (version 3.5.1; R Core Team, 2017) with task type, homophone status and syllable token frequency as sum coded variables (1, -1). Model fit, including the selection of predictors and their interactions, the random effect structure, and reported p -values were derived from the χ^2 -test of the change in deviance between the models with and without the effect of interest. Table 1 reports the final model output and R code.

Table 1. Summary of fixed-effects coefficient estimates and significance values for outcomes on production accuracy. R code:

```
glmer(CorrectWord~Task+Task:Homophone+Task:Homophone:Syllable+(1|image)+(1|Subject),family="binomial")
```

	β	SE	z value	p
(Intercept)	0.7615	0.4142	1.839	0.07
Task	-0.4322	0.1097	-3.941	< .001
Task:Homophone	-0.3273	0.1192	-2.746	.006
Task: Homophone:Syllable	-0.4235	0.1195	-3.544	< .001

A main effect of Task was found, indicating that the production accuracy in the pinyin-reading task (mean: 0.71, 95% Confidence Interval (CI): [0.67, 0.73]) was significantly higher than that in Naming task (mean: 0.58, 95% CI: [0.55, 0.61]). A significant two-way interaction between Task and Homophone and a significant three-way Task, Homophone and Syllable token frequency interaction were found.

To identify the locus of the two-way and three-way interactions, we subset the data into high and low syllable token frequency groups respectively. For words with high token frequency syllables, pinyin-reading had a significantly higher accuracy rate than the naming task in the Homophone condition ($\beta = 2.35$, $SE = 0.53$, $z = 4.36$, $p < .001$) whereas accuracy rates in the naming and pinyin-reading tasks did not differ in the Non-Homophone condition ($\beta = 0.68$, $SE = 0.46$, $z = 1.47$, $p = 0.14$). For words with low token frequency syllables, the pinyin-reading task had a marginal higher accuracy rate than the naming task in the Homophone condition, ($\beta = 0.72$, $SE = 0.41$, $z = 1.74$, $p = 0.08$) whereas pinyin-reading had a significantly higher accuracy rate than the naming task in the Non-Homophone condition, ($\beta = 1.12$, $SE = 0.42$, $z = 2.65$, $p < .01$). The three-way interaction is summarized in Figure 2.

To summarize the results of the correct syllable-tone analysis, participants were overall more accurate at reading the pinyin than naming the target, though neither task resulted in mean accuracy above 71 percent. A two-way and three-way interaction indicated that this difference was primarily driven by two particular conditions. Participants were more accurate at reading the pinyin compared to naming for new words with homophones that consisted of high token frequency syllables and for new words without homophones that consisted of low token frequency syllables.

Figure 2. Mean production accuracy results by Homophone mate status, Syllable token frequency and Task. Error bars indicate standard error of the mean.

3.2 Tone error analysis

As the majority of errors were tonal errors, we next examine the participants' tone error pattern. The tone error rate is summarized in Figure 3. Overall, the error rate of pinyin-reading was lower than that of naming task (Pinyin-reading task: mean, .14, 95% CI, [.12, .14] vs. Naming task: mean .24, 95% CI, [.22, .26]). To test whether task type, homophone status and syllable token frequency affected tone error rate, a mixed-effects logistic regression model was built according to the same criterion mentioned earlier. A main effect of task was found, indicating that the pinyin-reading had a significantly lower tone error rate than the naming task. A significant 3-way interaction between task, homophone status and syllable token frequency was found.

Table 2. Summary of fixed-effects coefficient estimates and significance values for outcomes on tone errors. Final model output, R code:

```
glmer(ToneError~Task+Homophone:Syllable:Task+(1|image)+(1|Subject),
family="binomial")
```

	β	SE	z-value	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	-2.0843	0.3810	-5.470	< .001
Task	0.4632	0.1284	3.607	< .001
Task:Homophone:Syllable	0.4990	0.1348	3.701	< .001

Figure 3. Tone error rates by Homophone mate status, Syllable token frequency (High vs. Low) and Task. Error bars indicate standard error of the mean.

To identify the locus of the three-way interaction, we subset the data into high (and low syllable token frequency words respectively. For words with high syllable token frequency, the pinyin-reading's tone error rate was significantly lower than the naming task's tone error rate in the Homophone condition ($\beta = -2.57$, $SE = 0.68$, $z = -3.78$, $p < .001$) whereas the pinyin-reading and naming tasks did not differ in terms of tone error rate in the Non-Homophone condition ($\beta = 0.63$, $SE = 0.55$, $z = 1.14$, $p = 0.25$). For words with low syllable token frequency, the pinyin-reading and naming tasks did not differ in terms of tone error rate in the Homophone condition ($\beta = -0.32$, $SE = 0.45$, $z = -0.72$, $p = 0.47$) whereas the pinyin-reading's tone error rate was significantly lower than the naming task's tone error rate in the Non-Homophone condition, ($\beta = -1.47$, $SE = 0.52$, $z = -2.82$, $p < .01$). The result indicated that the pinyin-reading advantage over naming task in terms tone error rate was conditioned by both homophone mate status and syllable token frequency in line with the results from the word accuracy analysis in section 3.1.

4. Discussion

In the current study, we examined how previously learned homophones, syllable token frequency and pinyin orthography affected beginner-level CFL learners' word production. First, we found that pinyin reading task overall lead to a significantly higher word production accuracy rate than the naming task (pinyin: 71% vs. naming: 58%). It indicates that CFL learners after just about one semester formal Chinese instruction had become able to use pinyin+tone diacritics to guide their word production, particularly the tone production. This finding is consistent with previous research demonstrating that the visual presentation of tone diacritics or pitch contour shape can facilitate tone learning (Liu et al. 2011; Chang 2018). However, it is not clear whether the pinyin advantage came from the pinyin orthography alone or it is also partially attributed to the participants' 3-day exposure to the audio input. Because if without the audio model speech, the pinyin reading advantage may not be as strong as the one found in the current study. But nevertheless the pinyin orthography provided some form of guideline, which is useful for learners to produce the words.

In addition to the main effect of Task, we found that participants were statistically more accurate at reading the pinyin compared to naming only for new words with homophones that consisted of high token frequency syllables and for new words without homophones that consisted of low token frequency syllables. Second, the source of the word production errors almost exclusively came from tone errors. In the tone error analysis, we found a very similar pattern to the word production accuracy result, namely, the pinyin-reading task had a lower tone error rate than the naming task in two conditions. The first condition was when the words had homophones and the syllable token frequency was high and the second condition was when the words did not have homophones and the syllable token frequency was low. The results indicate that, in either meaning-to-sound or formal classroom word learning settings, learners' tone learning is not separated from word learning. It is not the case that once a tone category is perceived

and produced well in one syllable or rime then it can be easily generalized to another syllable or rime for CFL learners. Without pinyin orthography guidance, the more ‘natural’ spoken word learning consisting of a range of familiar, unfamiliar, frequent, and infrequent phonological forms set up in the present study revealed that certain combination of homophonous status and syllable token frequency of the newly learned words caused more tone production errors than other combinations of the two factors. Our finding further corroborates recent research that showed CFL learners’ sensitivity to syllable+tone distribution patterns in spoken word learning (Wiener et al., 2018; Wiener et al., 2019).

To put our findings in a learning context, consider a word such as 塔 *ta3* ‘pagoda’ whose syllable frequently occurs in the textbook but always occurs with Tone 1 (e.g., 他/她 *ta1* ‘he/she’). This item caused problems for participants in the naming task. This is presumably because learners had so often produced *ta* with a high-level Tone 1 that producing it with a new, unfamiliar tone caused problems during the pinyin reading. In contrast, a word such as 哭 *kul* ‘to cry’ carries a relatively infrequent syllable, so learners may not have as much experience with producing the syllable and learners may have no other *kul* form in the lexicon to cause naming production problems.

To compare the word production accuracy result in the current study with other two research that examined CFL learners’ word production in the context of word learning, we found that the average accuracy rates in the naming task of our current study (mean: .76 in the naming task) is higher than the average accuracy rate reported in Chang’s (2018) study (mean: .62 without any pinyin orthography). This accuracy rate difference may be a result of different tasks given to the participants. The current study only involved meaning-to-sound learning without orthography learning while in Chang’s (2018) study, it included meaning, Chinese character, and sound learning. Thus, the learning task in Chang’s study was more cognitively demanding for the participants. We argue that the lower accuracy rate in Chang’s study may come from the limited cognitive resource that can be allocated to the tone learning for beginner level CFL learners (see Barcroft, 2015). It seems that the amount of lexical information sometimes may overwhelm the learners, thus, causing the less successful tone learning for CFL learners during the vocabulary learning.

In terms of the pedagogical implications, based on the current finding that showed learners took advantage of previously learned homophones when producing the newly learned words with pinyin orthography prompt, instructors may consider using learners’ previously learned homophones as an anchor point to learn new words. Such a way may not only help to learn new words but also enhance the long-term memory of the previously learned vocabulary. It may build a more robust representation of the tone bearing unit, thus, facilitating tone perception and production. Also, if the instruction goal is to improve CFL learners’ tone learning in the context of word learning, then maybe building the association between sound and meaning can go before the learning of the orthography (Zhao, 2011).

Appendix

Experiment stimuli:

Homophone		Non-homophone	
High Syllable Token Frequency	Low Syllable Token Frequency	High Syllable Token Frequency	Low Syllable Token Frequency
ta1 塌 ‘to collapse’	shu1 叔 ‘uncle’	ta3 塔 ‘pagoda’	shu3 鼠 ‘mouse’
ren2 仁 ‘nuts’	chen4 称 ‘scale’	ren3 忍 ‘to tolerate’	chen2 沉 ‘to sink’
wan3 碗 ‘bowl’	jie3 解 ‘to untie’	wan2 丸 ‘(meat) ball’	jie1 接 ‘to pick up’
hai2 骸 ‘skeleton’	ku4 库 ‘warehouse’	hai3 海 ‘ocean’	ku1 哭 ‘to cry’
shi4 柿 ‘persimmon’	hong2 虹 ‘rainbow’	shi1 湿 ‘wetness’	hong1 烘 ‘to bake’

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Are Pants Clothes or Long Objects: Exploring the L2 Acquisition of Chinese Classifiers

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The current study employed a self-paced reading task, a lexical decision task, a classifier knowledge test, and a proficiency test, aiming to investigate the process by which English-speaking learners of Chinese acquire the new functional category, Mandarin classifiers, with a focus on the source of the challenges L2 learners face in the process. The results suggest that establishing the new functional category, classifiers, in L2 syntax is not unattainable for English-speaking learners of Chinese. The real constraint may lie at the lexical level. Sufficient lexical knowledge can contribute to native-like performance regarding Chinese classifiers. L2 learners of Chinese differ from native speakers in ability to access co-occurrence information between classifiers and nouns in mental lexicon organization with regard to classifiers. The role of L2 proficiency in classifier acquisition is also discussed.

1. Introduction

A number of studies on adult second language (L2) acquisition have demonstrated the existence of variability in production and non-nativeness in processing when morphological marking (e.g. gender, tense, number) is involved (e.g. Franceschina, 2001; Prévost & White, 2000; VanPatten, Keating, & Leiser, 2012; White, Valenzuela, Kozłowska-Macgregor, & Leung, 2004). However, no consensus has been reached regarding the source of such variability.

There are several possibilities. According to the syntactic account, the problem is centered on new functional categories and features, which may not be acquirable by L2 learners after the critical period if the first language lacks them, because adult learners are not able to instantiate the new categories or features in their grammar and thus they have difficulty in both production and comprehension of the new structure (e.g. the representational deficit hypothesis of Hawkins & Chan, 1997). The missing surface inflection hypothesis (MSIH, Prévost & White, 2000), however, attributes persistent L2 difficulty to, rather than problems in the syntactic level, lexical retrieval difficulties in production. Importantly, this hypothesis predicts that new functional categories and features are ultimately acquirable, and the morphological issue is due to morphological failure under processing pressure. The lexical learning account extends MSIH to

comprehension, and attributes the difficulty more specifically to weak lexical representation due to inadequate learning of individual items (the lexical gender learning hypothesis of Grüter, Lew-Williams, & Fernald, 2012; Hopp, 2013). The discussion is drawing growing attention because it helps us to understand the nature of learners' difficulties, and ultimately possibly how to address them through pedagogical interventions.

Along this line, the current study aims to further explore the source of L2 difficulty by investigating L2 online comprehension of a new functional category for English-speaking learners, the Chinese classifier.

A classifier is an independent morpheme that “denotes some salient perceived or imputed characteristic of the entity to which the associated noun refers” (Allan 1977, p. 285). In Chinese, a classifier is obligatory between a noun and a numeral (e.g. *yi* ‘one’, *er* ‘two’), or between a noun and a demonstrative determiner (e.g. *zhe* ‘this’, *na* ‘that’), or some quantifiers (e.g. *mei* ‘every’). It is relevant in the current study that classifiers have rich semantic information, and they are not attached to nouns and thus are subject to omission.

Several studies have investigated how adult L2 learners use classifiers in oral or written production. Offline comprehension of classifiers has also been investigated. However, very few studies have focused on the online comprehension of Chinese classifiers.

Lau and Grüter (2015) investigated whether English-speaking learners of Chinese could use classifiers as facilitative cues to predict upcoming nouns. They found that English-speaking learners showed a trend towards a facilitative effect; learners who were more proficient based on their performance on a cloze test showed a pattern more similar to the native group. In comparison with previous studies on Spanish gender, in which the facilitative effect was absent, the authors attributed the facilitative effect they observed to semantic information available in classifiers and the limited number of nouns associated with each classifier. That is, rich lexical information encoded in classifiers might facilitate acquisition, particularly in cases where an encounter with a particular classifier narrows down the possible selection of nouns to a very small number.

Despite the findings that it is possible for adult L2 learners to use classifiers to predict upcoming nouns, it remains unclear what type of information was utilized by learners in online comprehension: the syntactic information, the semantic information, or other lexical information. Grüter, Lau, and Ling (2018) tried to determine what information is available to learners by including three different competitor conditions in the visual world eye-tracking experiment: competitors from the same classifier class as the target noun, matching the semantic features of the class (for instance, when the target was ‘dog’, which could take the long shape classifier *tiao*, the competitor was ‘rope’); competitors from another classifier class as the target but semantically matched with the class (for instance, when the target was ‘dog,’ the competitor was ‘wrist watch’, which has a long shape but takes a different classifier than *tiao*); competitors from another

classifier class, not consistent with the semantic features of the target (e.g., when the target was ‘dog,’ the competitor was ‘apple’). It was found that for native speakers of Chinese, the class-consistent competitors were more distracting than the class-inconsistent but semantics-consistent ones. As for L2 learners of Chinese, semantics-consistent competitors were equally distractive no matter whether they were from the same classifier class as the targets. When both the target and the competitor appear to be semantically inconsistent with the classifier (e.g., ‘dog’ with the long shape classifier *tiao*, with ‘apple’ as the competitor. Note that actually there is no semantic conflict between ‘dog’ and *tiao*, but in learners’ perception ‘dog’ is not related to long objects.), the classifier-class information could also serve as a facilitative cue to predict the upcoming nouns. The authors argued that L2 learners primarily rely on semantic information for online comprehension of classifier-noun combinations, because the competitors that were consistent with the semantic features of the classifier were distractive to learners, even though they were not from the classifier category. When semantic information is not informative in learners’ perception, co-occurrence relationship between classifiers and nouns could also be utilized. The findings indicate that semantic features of classifier were easier for learners to acquire, and meanwhile co-occurrence information between classifiers and nouns was also accessible to learners.

In the previous studies targeting online comprehension of Mandarin classifiers, the role of learners’ lexical knowledge has been investigated by using an offline task to test whether participants could connect classifiers with nouns. However, a lexical test targeting lexical retrieval speed could provide further information on the quality of lexical representation (Hopp, 2017). To this end, the present study also includes a lexical decision task modeled on LexTALE, in which all the target nouns in the production and comprehension tasks were included in the stimuli list; participants’ accuracy as well as reaction time in deciding whether the words they saw were real words were recorded. More information on the lexical test is introduced in the methodology section.

To summarize, classifiers are understudied in the field of L2 acquisition. The only conclusive finding seems to be that classifiers are challenging to adult learners. However, more evidence is needed to locate the source of the observed difficulty in the L2 acquisition of classifiers.

The current study will investigate the online comprehension of classifiers via error detection, which provides different information than predictive processing. Different from predictive processing, which explores whether learners can use a specific type of information to predict upcoming elements, grammatical sensitivity to errors reflects what learners do not accept. Manipulation of violation types could help to track the root of variability in use of classifiers.

Syntactic violations with the classifier can be created by omitting the classifier between the numeral/determiner and the noun. Violations on the lexical level can be created by using an inconsistent classifier with the noun. Lexical information includes semantic features of classifier class, and also co-occurrence relationships between

classifiers and nouns. The co-occurrence information is needed to know which semantic feature is picked to determine the classifier membership. For example, pants are clothes and they are long, their shape rather than function is picked by the classifier system, therefore a shape classifier rather than a taxonomy classifier is required. Semantic feature is not sufficient to determine which classifier is the correct one, whether a shape classifier or a taxonomy classifier is required. For example, ‘book’ has a flat surface, but it takes the taxonomy classifier *ben* (for bound items) rather than a shape classifier.

According to previous studies that have included L2 proficiency as a factor, it seems that the classifier system develops as proficiency grows, which is similar to the L2 acquisition of grammatical genders. It has also been argued that gender develops with proficiency; lower-level learners have difficulty with both agreement and assignment with gender, while upper level learners primarily have difficulty with assignment (Alarcón, 2011; Grüter et al., 2012; Kupisch, Akpınar, & Stöhr, 2013). The majority of previous studies focused on how the classifier system develops in L2 grammar in production (typically offline production) and offline comprehension. However, there has been little investigation regarding the ways in which the L2 classifier system develops with proficiency in online comprehension and production.

In the self-paced reading task, I examined whether learners of Chinese show sensitivity to classifier omissions and uses of incongruent classifier. In searching for more information regarding the nature of difficulty in classifier acquisition, an elicited production task was also included to investigate the relationship between learners’ performance on production and online comprehension.

2. The current study

The current study employs a self-paced reading task, a lexical decision task targeting lexical retrieval, as well as an offline cloze test for classifiers, to investigate the source of difficulty for classifier acquisition. The research questions are as follows: (1) What is the source of non-native like performance in L2 classifier online comprehension? Whether the syntactic account or the lexical account better account for the difficulty L2ers encounter? (2) Whether and how different types of lexical information affect online processing of classifiers? The lexical information examined in this study includes participants’ lexical knowledge of classifiers, familiarity with nouns, and Cl-noun co-occurrent information.

2.1. Experiments

Participants. Thirty-two English speaking learners of Chinese and 33 native speakers of Chinese took part in the study. The L2 learners were students who had enrolled in at least three semesters’ Chinese classes in a large Midwestern university in the United States. Their ages ranged from 18 to 36 ($M=20.82$, $SD=3.17$), and they started learning Chinese between the age of nine and 25 ($M=14.12$, $SD=4.21$). Among all the learners, seven of them went to a 10-week study abroad program before the data collection, and another ten of them lived in China for one to four years ($M=2.25$,

$SD=1.27$). The learner participants were asked to self-report their proficiency on a 5-point scale with 1 being “poor” and 5 being “superior” on listening, reading, speaking and writing. The self-report scores were as follows: Reading ($M=3.18$, $SD=0.80$); Speaking ($M=2.94$, $SD=0.70$); Writing ($M=2.76$, $SD=1.00$); Listening ($M=3.03$, $SD=0.87$).

The native participants were recruited from the same large Midwestern university as well as a Midwestern liberal arts college. The majority of the native speakers recruited were full time students or visiting scholars in the university and the college. The native participants’ ages ranged from 19 to 40 ($M=24.88$, $SD=5.62$), and their length of stay in the United States ranged from 2 months to 12 years ($M=3.29$ years, $SD=2.62$). All of them spoke Mandarin, and 23 of them spoke one or two dialects in addition to Mandarin.

Procedure and materials. Participants went through the consent form, then filled out a background questionnaire (Appendix A) on paper. After filling out the background questionnaire, participants took part in the lexical decision task, which was followed by the proficiency test. After the proficiency test it was the self-paced reading task. The cloze task was given last.

The proficiency test was a reading test adapted from the mock HSK (Chinese Proficiency Test) tests available on the official website of the HSK. The test used in the study consists of three parts (adapted from Level 3-5 tests), 15 items in all.

The lexical decision task was modeled on *LexTALE*, and administered on a computer via Praat 6.0.30 (Boersma & Weenink, 2017), in a quiet lab. In the test, participants saw three practice items and 60 words on a computer screen. The words appeared in the middle of the screen, one word each time. Participants were instructed to decide whether the word they saw was a real Chinese word or not. If they thought the word is an existing Chinese word, they hit ‘Y’ on the key board, if not, they hit ‘N’. They hit ‘Y’ if they thought the word is a real word, even though they could not recall the meaning of the word; if they were not sure whether the word exists, they were asked to hit ‘N’. After hitting one of the two keys, the next word appeared. There was no time limit to this task, but participants were instructed to respond as quickly as possible. All participants completed the task in no more than three minutes. The test score based on accuracy was calculated automatically. Reaction times were also recorded. The test includes three practice items and 60 words, all of which were nouns. The word list consisted of 40 real words and 20 non-words. In the 40 real words, 32 were the target words investigated in self-paced reading tasks.

The word-by-word non-cumulative moving window self-paced reading aims to investigate participants’ processing of classifier-noun combinations. The task was administered on a computer via *SuperLab* in a quiet laboratory room. Participants were instructed to read at a natural speed, and not to take breaks in the middle of reading sentences. Five practice items were presented to familiarize participants with the task. The task took approximately 15 minutes for native speakers of Chinese to complete and around 30 minutes for L2 learners.

In this task, the seven classifiers and 32 nouns were included (Table 1).

Table 1
Classifiers and nouns used in the self-paced reading task

Semantic domain	Classifier	Noun
Animacy	<i>zhi</i> (small animals)	<i>mao</i> ('cat'), <i>xiaoniao</i> ('bird'), <i>ji</i> ('chicken'), <i>yazi</i> ('duck'), <i>yang</i> ('sheep/goat')
Shape	<i>tiao</i> (long and slender objects) <i>zhang</i> (flat surfaced objects)	<i>kuzi</i> ('pants'), <i>qunzi</i> ('skirt'), <i>chuan</i> ('boat') <i>xiaolu</i> ('road'), <i>tanzi</i> ('blanket'), <i>yu</i> ('fish') <i>zhuozi</i> ('table'), <i>zhaopian</i> ('photo'), <i>ditu</i> ('map'), <i>xinyongka</i> ('credit card'), <i>zhi</i> ('paper'), <i>chuang</i> ('bed')
Function	<i>jian</i> (clothes) <i>liang</i> (vehicles) <i>ben</i> (bounded items) <i>tai</i> (machine)	<i>chenshan</i> ('shirt'), <i>maoyi</i> ('sweater'), <i>waitao</i> ('overcoat'), <i>jiake</i> ('jacket'), <i>yundongfu</i> ('sweatshirt'), T-xushan ('T-shirt') <i>chuzuche</i> ('taxi'), <i>zixingche</i> ('bicycle'), <i>motuoche</i> ('motorcycle') <i>zidian</i> ('dictionary'), <i>keben</i> ('textbook'), <i>shu</i> ('book') <i>diannao</i> ('computer'), <i>dianshi</i> ('television'), <i>bingxiang</i> ('refrigerator')

There were four conditions for each sentence, which were the grammatical condition, the classifier omission condition, the incongruent condition in which there was no semantic clash between the classifier and the noun, as well as another incongruent condition in which there was semantic clash. The sentences were divided into four lists using a Latin-square design. Each participant was presented with one of the four lists composed of 32 target sentences (eight items in each condition), along with 64 fillers. All of the target sentences and half of the fillers were followed by a true/false comprehension question to ensure participants processed the sentences. A sample set of stimuli is shown below in (1) (displaying regions are divided by '/').

(1) Grammatical/classifier omission/no semantic clash/ semantic clash condition.

小王/看到/那条/裤子/在/柜子/里/放着。

*那

*那件

*那张

Xiaowang/see/that-(CI)/pants/in/closet/inside/put
 'Xiaowang saw that pants in the closet.'

Comprehension question:

Ture or false: 裤子在床上。 ('The pants are on the bed')

The critical region was the noun after the classifier. The classifiers appeared after a numeral in 16 sentences, and after a demonstrative in 16 sentences; both of these two types of context are very familiar to learners. In all sentences, the critical region was followed by a preposition (*zai* 'on/in/at', *cong* 'from', or *gei* 'to') and a noun (two characters) to ensure consistent spill-over regions. Reading time on the following two regions (preposition + noun) was analyzed for spill-over effects.

An offline paper-and-pencil cloze task was carried out after self-paced reading task. Materials were the 32 nouns used in previous tasks, appearing in numeral phrases. Participants were instructed to fill in a classifier to complete the phrase, and they were instructed to not to use the general classifier *ge*.

2.1. Results

In the self-paced reading task, thirty-two sets of sentences were included as stimuli, and each participant read 32 target sentences (and also 64 fillers), therefore contributing 32 observations to the overall data set, eight observations in each condition.

Reading times beyond 2.5 SD of the participant mean at each region were removed (Jegerski, 2014), which affected 3.6% of the learners' data, and 3.7% of the native speakers' data. In addition, for the learner group, if their response for a noun in the lexical decision task was incorrect, the corresponding item in the self-paced reading task was removed; this further affected 17.2% of the learner data.

Figure 1 shows the mean reading time for each region for the native group after data trimming; Figure 2 shows the meaning reading time for the learner group. Region 4 was the critical region, the noun; Region 5 and 6 were the two spill-over regions. It can be seen from the two figures that, for both native speakers and learners, the reading time for the classifier omission condition on Region 3 was shorter than the other three conditions. This pattern is not surprising because Region 3 was shorter in the classifier omission condition, which was a one-character numeral or demonstrative, while in the other three conditions, Region 3 was composed of a numeral or a demonstrative with a classifier.

The following Generalized linear mixed-effect model with an Inverse Gaussian distribution and inverse link was used for further analyses on the native group and learner group's reading time:

$$\text{Reading Time (RT)} \sim \text{Condition} + (1 \mid \text{Subject}) + (1 \mid \text{Item})$$

Analyses revealed significant reading time slowdown for native speakers in the classifier omission condition on the critical region ($t=-3.84$, $p<.001$); natives' reading time slowdown for the incongruent condition without semantic clash (e.g., 一件裤子) reached significant level in the first spill over region ($t=-3.13$, $p=.002$); so as the incongruent condition with semantic clash (e.g., 一张裤子) ($t=-4.66$, $p<.001$). As for learners, only the reading time slowdown for the incongruent classifier with semantic clash condition reached significant level ($t=-3.25$, $p=.001$), on the critical region, such

slowdown for the other two ungrammatical conditions was not significant in any analyzed region.

Figure 1.
Reading time for each region: the native group

Figure 2.
Reading for each region: the learner group

To summarize, English-speaking learners of Chinese showed sensitivity to specific types of violations in classifier use, which was reflected by the elevated reading time. However, when the classifier was omitted, or an incongruent classifier without semantic clash with the noun was used, the learners did not show significantly longer reading times, which suggested a lack of sensitivity to the violations. Therefore, the

learner group showed different patterns in online processing of sentences containing classifiers compared to native speakers of Chinese.

To investigate whether learners of different Chinese proficiency levels perform differently or not in their online comprehension of classifiers, we included learners' Z score of the proficiency test in the analyses, using the following model:

$$\text{Reading Time (RT)} \sim \text{Condition} * \text{Proficiency Z score} + (1 | \text{Subject}) + (1 | \text{Item})$$

The analyses revealed significant interaction between the classifier omission condition and the Z score ($t=2.23$, $p=.03$), which suggested that learners of different L2 proficiency levels performed differently on the classifier omission condition. To further explore the significant interaction, the reading time of the critical noun was plotted over the proficiency Z score (Figure 3). It can be seen from the regression lines in the figure that for participants who got a lower score in the proficiency test, they were more sensitive to classifier omission as it was suggested by the elevated reading time compared to the grammatical condition. However, with the growth in proficiency score, their sensitivity to classifier omission decreased, and the reading time for the classifier omission condition was even shorter than the grammatical condition. This is a somewhat counter-intuitive result.

Figure 3.

Learner reading time over proficiency Z score on the critical region

To investigate whether knowledge of individual classifier and noun pairs affects online comprehension, we divided all the observations from the 32 English-speaking learners of Chinese in the self-paced reading task into two sets based on whether a correct classifier was provided in the offline classifier knowledge task. After the grouping, 55.25% of the observations fell into the classifier-consistent group, for which participants showed knowledge of the classifier in the offline task; 44.75% of the observations fell into the classifier-inconsistent group, for which participants failed to provide correct

classifiers in the offline task, or the classifier provided was not the one used in the self-paced reading task.

The two sets of data were analyzed separately using the same generalized linear regression models in previous analyses. For the items for which participants were able to provide a consistent classifier for the noun in the offline cloze task, on the critical region, when an incongruent classifier with semantic clash with the noun was used, the learners read the critical noun significantly more slowly compared to the grammatical condition ($t=-3.48$, $p<.001$). In addition, learners also showed a trend to being sensitive to incongruent without semantic clash with the noun, which was suggested by the marginally significant longer reading time for Condition c ($t=-1.47$, $p=.08$). When learners failed to provide a consistent classifier in the offline cloze task, they failed to show any significant sensitivity to any of the ungrammatical classifier use in any analyzed regions.

In the lexical decision task modeled on *LexTALE*, reaction times to make decisions about each word, which indicates lexical retrieval speed, were recorded. To investigate the role of lexical retrieval speed in online comprehension of classifier-noun pairs, the following generalized linear mixed models were used for data analysis:

Reading Time ~ Condition * Retrieval time + (1 | Subject) + (1 | Item)

A significant interaction between the classifier omission condition and lexical retrieval time was detected ($t=1.98$, $p=.05$). In addition, a marginally significant interaction between the incongruent classifier with semantic clash condition and Lexical retrieval time was also present. Figure 4 showed the relationship between the reading time on this spill-over region and the lexical retrieval time of the noun in the lexical decision task. The regression lines in the figure show the source of the interaction, which is that when participants retrieved the noun faster in the lexical decision task, they tended to be able to detect the ungrammaticality when the classifier was omitted (Condition *b*), or when an incongruent classifier without semantic clash with the noun was used (Condition *d*), as they tended to read these two conditions more slowly than the grammatical condition; however, when it took them longer to retrieve the noun, their sensitivity to those two types of ungrammaticality tended to decrease and even disappear. The results suggested that higher quality noun representations helped with detection of specific types of ungrammaticality with regard to classifiers.

Figure 4.

Learner reading time over lexical retrieval time on the second spill-over region

3. Discussion and conclusion

The current study aims to investigate the process by which English-speaking learners of Chinese acquire Mandarin classifiers, with a focus on the source of the challenges L2 learners face in the process. A self-paced reading task, a proficiency test, a classifier knowledge cloze task, and a word decision task were employed.

In the online comprehension task, when read sentences with classifier-noun combinations, native speakers of Chinese were sensitive to all types of ungrammatical use of classifiers. As for the L2 group, they were not sensitive to classifier omission, and they only showed sensitivity to inconsistent classifiers with semantic clash with the nouns (e.g., 一张裤子), not to inconsistent classifiers without semantic clash (e.g., 一件裤子).

The results of the current study suggested that L2 proficiency played a role in the online comprehension of Chinese classifiers, in that learners with lower L2 proficiency tended to be sensitive to classifier omission, while the higher proficiency learners did not.

L2 learners' knowledge of classifiers seemed to be an important contributing factor to their behavior pattern online comprehension. The learner group behaved differently on items that they were able to provide the correct classifier for in the offline task than on those for which they failed to do so. When L2 learners managed to provide the correct classifier for the noun in the offline classifier knowledge task, they were sensitive to incongruent classifiers with semantic clash with the nouns, and they showed a trend toward being able to be sensitive to classifiers without semantic clash. When L2 learners were not able to provide the correct classifier for the noun in the offline task, they were not sensitive to any type of ungrammaticality with regard to classifiers.

Lexical retrieval speed was also found to be an influential factor in L2 learners' online comprehension of classifiers. Learners' faster retrieval of the noun predicted more sensitivity to classifier omission and incongruent classifiers with semantic clash with the

nouns, and this sensitivity decreased and even disappeared with longer reaction time to the noun in the word decision task measuring lexical retrieval speed.

Generally speaking, the results lend support to the lexical account rather than the syntactic account in terms of the source of difficulty in classifier acquisition. Though as a whole group, the learners failed to show sensitive to classifier omission, which may suggest they failed to establish the new functional category in their L2 Chinese; however, when taking into consideration L2 proficiency, we found that lower proficiency learners tended to be sensitive to classifier omission, while the trend towards sensitivity did not appear in higher proficiency learners' performance. If English-speaking learners of Chinese have difficulty establishing the functional category of CI in their L2 Chinese syntax, why did lower proficiency learner group show a tendency of being sensitive to classifier omission in online comprehension? But a problem we have is, there is no reason to speculate that the new functional category was established in L2 syntax in the early stage of acquisition, and then disappeared with higher L2 proficiency.

It might be possible that L2 learners of Chinese firstly regard the classifiers as bounded to the numeral/determiner (Polio, 1994), and the combination might have been used as a chunk before the noun. The closer connection between the classifier and numeral/determiner than between the classifier and the noun might be enhanced by the input, as in Chinese, the classifier and the noun can be separated by elements such as adjectives. For instance, 'a large cat' in Chinese is *one-CI big cat*. If this is the case, lower-proficiency learners' sensitivity to classifier omission in online comprehension might be due to their sensitivity to missing elements in chunks, rather than the syntactic violation. Spinner (2013) also argued that English-speaking learners of Swahili had difficulty segmenting the gender marker (which is realized as prefix) from the noun root at least at early stages of the acquisition. Therefore, their use of gender prefix in production and perception did not necessarily reflect the representation in their L2 syntax.

Being treated as a chunk, the numeral-classifier association could also be unpacked in later stages of acquisition (Myles, Mitchell, & Hooper, 1999). The transition from connecting the classifier with the numeral to connecting it with the noun is not beyond the realms of possibility, because it was found that faster retrieval speed of the noun in the lexical decision task entailed sensitivity of classifier omission in learners' online comprehension, and the sensitivity decreased or even disappeared with slower retrieval speed. The results might be able to provide evidence that with sufficient lexical knowledge of the noun, the classifier could be associated with the noun under the syntactic projection of CI in the L2 grammar.

The higher proficiency learner group's lack of sensitivity to classifier omission in online comprehension might because even the higher proficiency group in the current study were not proficient enough to show native-like performance. The most of the L2 participants had no or limited experience living in the L2 environment, and most of their exposure to Chinese was in formal classroom setting. There is a possibility that the higher

proficiency L2 group in the current study had not passed the transition stage from associating the classifier with the numeral to associating it with the noun. When the chunk was decomposed, and new connection had not been built, the sensitivity to missing element in the chunk would not be present anymore, and the sensitivity to syntactic violation had not fully developed. Further investigation with higher proficiency learners of Chinese is needed.

The current study also revealed L2 limitations in terms of access to lexical co-occurrence information. It was found that in online comprehension, the L2 participants were not able to detect the classifier error when semantic information was not useful. For instance, learners did not detect errors when the clothes classifier *jian* was used for ‘pants’, where a long shape classifier *tiao* was required. The incorrect classifier *jian* does not contradict with the semantic feature of the noun, as ‘pants’ falls in the category of clothes. In this case, familiarity with the semantic features of the classifier and the noun could not help to detect the error as no semantic conflict was involved. Co-occurrence relationships between the classifier and the noun was the only hint of whether a taxonomy classifier or a shape classifier is required. Only with extensive knowledge of the co-occurrence relationship could learners know whether a taxonomy or a shape classifier was required. It was also found that even with faster retrieval speed of the noun, there is no trend that the co-occurrence information could become more accessible to L2 learners in online comprehension, which further suggests that it is difficult for L2 learners to access the co-occurrence information.

To conclude, the results presented generally support the lexical account of variability in L2 acquisition of new features and functional categories. Sufficient lexical knowledge, which includes access to different types of lexical information, and fast lexical retrieval can contribute to native-like performance regarding Chinese classifiers.

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An Analysis of the Errors and Teaching Strategies in the Acquisition of Chinese Diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ by Thai Students

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The acquisition of second language (L2) sound system takes time and often displays developmental patterns at different stages. This chapter examines the acquisition of two back diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ of Chinese by Thai L2 learners. Productions of /uo/ and /ua/ by Thai L2 learners at different stages are compared acoustically in order to reveal their developmental patterns of in the process of acquiring these two diphthongs in Mandarin Chinese. Linguistic explanations and pedagogical suggestions are also provided.

1. Introduction

Both Chinese and Thai belong to the Sino-Tibetan language family. They have similarities in pronunciation, vocabulary and grammar, as well as many differences. These differences and similarities may form both positive transfer and negative transfer, thus affecting Thai students' Chinese.

In the process of second language phonetic learning, when the phonetic features and pronunciation positions of the mother tongue and the second language are relatively close, the second language pronunciation is treated as the mother tongue and assimilated by the mother tongue, which hinders the construction of new phonetic categories. This mechanism is called phonetic category assimilation. If the phonetic features of the mother tongue and the second language are quite different, the brain's disassimilation processing mechanism will try to distinguish the phonetic categories of the mother tongue and the second language, so as to maintain the opposition between the two and help to construct a new phonetic category. This process is called phonetic category disassimilation (Flege,2002,2005,2009).

In fact, in addition to the differences in phonetic features, the construction of phonetic system and the transfer of mother tongue, the factors such as learning time, phonetic environment and learners' attitude will all have an impact on second language pronunciation acquisition.

The final consonants /uo/ and /ua/ in Chinese belong to a pair of vowels with the same rhyme but different endings. The phonetic category is likely to be assimilated, so it may be a difficulty for Thai students. Some Thai students at the initial and intermediate stages are confused with /uo/ and /ua/ in pronunciation, which affects their second language acquisition. Why is it a difficult problem for Thai students to understand the two diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ in Mandarin? Are they the fourth level of the new transfer theory

of speech learning model proposed by Flege(1992), "new speech not found in mother tongue" or two variants of the same phoneme proposed by Li (1995)?

2. Previous research

Previous studies have examined the acquisition of /uo/ and /ua/ by Thai L2 learners. Rao (1991) analyzed the difficulties that Thai students have in learning Mandarin and pointed out that the absence of /uo/ vowel in Thai made it easy for Thai students to use /ua/ instead of /uo/. However, Li (1995) believes that there is an equivalent to /uo/ in Thai pronunciation. Otherwise, it is difficult to explain the phenomenon that students use /ua/ to replace /uo/ and /uo/ to replace /ua/ at the same time. Li(1995) found that there are two actual pronunciations in Thai, namely [u:a] and [uo]. These two actual pronunciation do not play a role in distinguishing meaning, and there is no perceptual difference for Thai people, so it can be regarded as two variants of uo . The instability of vowel pronunciation uo affects Thai students' correct perception of Chinese /uo/ and /ua/ diphthongs, thus confusing their pronunciation. Cai and Cao (2002) found that Thai students often have a follow-up sound when they pronounce /uo/, which sounds like [uA], while the actual /ua/ is sometimes pronounced as [uo]; there is no [uo] in Thai, which is similar to [u:a]. /u/ in [u:a] is long, which students often use to replace /uo/[2]. Chen and Li (2007) pointed out that there are 14 diphthongs in Thai, but not the Chinese diphthong uo [uo], while there are two ua [ua] and ua [u:a] in Thai, but not the Chinese diphthong ua [uA][3]. In this paper, we will not go deep into whether there are two vowels, uo [uo] and ua [uA] in Thai. We will analyze and discuss the errors of Thai students' acquisition of Chinese vowels /uo/ and /ua/. We will compare and analyze the productions of Thai Students' /uo/, /ua/ in different stages based on phonetic experiments, in hopes of revealing the underlying mechanisms leading to such errors and coming up with some effective pedagogical suggestions and measures.

Diphthongs are widely investigated. Yang and Cao (1984) pointed out that the ending period of diphthongs is longer than the beginning period (onset), especially in the ending portions of /ia/ and /ua/, and the ending portion is about six times longer than the beginning portion. The ending portions of nine diphthongs in Mandarin are longer than the beginning portions, especially for back vowels. Wu and Lin (1989) think that in terms of formants, diphthongs are in sliding state, generally there are few stable segments, and only the later portion of the back diphthongs may have stable segments. Shi (2002) pointed out that the vowels /a/ in Beijing dialect can be formed into /ia/ and /ua/; the vowels /ə/ can be formed into /uo/, /ie/ or /ye/. When the vowel o[o] has a labial initial in front, the actual pronunciation is [uɤ] with a vowel u due to labialization. It can be seen from the spectrograms that the distribution of /ɤ/ vowels is a narrow band from top to bottom, with an obvious movement. The pronunciation of vowel /ɤ/ is generally from [u] to [ʌ]. Zhu (2013) thinks that [uə] and [uɤ] belong to special pronuclear disyllabic sounds, because the latter part of [uə] [uɤ] is lower, but the former part is the main part of compound vowels.

While diphthongs are widely investigated, but there are very limited experimental studies on the acquisition of Mandarin diphthongs by Thai L2 learners. Chen, Xu and Gao (2012) found that the central vowel [ə] of the female students in Thailand was consistent with that of the Chinese students, and had a strong migration. Its distribution was a narrow band from top to bottom, with an obvious movement. However, the vowels [ə] of male students are scattered and unstable. We believe that this probably makes it difficult for Thai students to pronounce Mandarin /uo/.

3. Research questions

In the process of teaching, we found that Thai students in different stages have different characteristics in the process of acquiring Mandarin Chinese. Thai students in the initial and intermediate stages tend to confuse between diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/, due to negative transfer of their native language and the interference of the target language. More specifically when /uo/ is located in the second syllable of the word or at the word-final position, Thai students tend to confuse between diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/. Meanwhile, pronunciation of /ua/ is easy to slide to /uo/ when it is in the first syllable. Thai students in intermediate stage can distinguish /uo/ and /ua/ through adequate phonetic trainings, but it is not stable, which easily leads to the fossilization of the so-called "Thai accent"; the pronunciation of Thai students in advanced stage is relatively stable and the two diphthongs can be produced correctly most of the time, but for some learners, the production of these diphthongs have fossilized, which makes it difficult to change the "Thai accent".

In this study we attempt to explore the following issues:

- 3.1 Can Thai L2 learners correctly distinguish the back diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/? Why is it easier for /uo/ to slide to /ua/ when it is in the second syllable or at the end of the word? And why is /ua/ easy to slide to /uo/ when it is in the first syllable?
- 3.2 Can Thai L2 learners produce Mandarin back diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ in Mandarin Chinese?
- 3.3 How can we explain the Thai L2 learners' confusion of the two back diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ in Mandarin Chinese?

4. Phonetic experiment

4.1 Participants

We recruited six Thai L2 learners (three male and three female) from the Thai learner population at Southwest Forestry university in China. They are from the Royal University of Bibury and Royal University of Foton in Thailand, with an average age of 21. They are the third year students majoring in Chinese. Some of them have passed the HSK (Chinese Proficiency Test) 3 and 4. The six participants were divided into three groups: group A (low level), group B (middle level) and group C (high level), according to their actual Chinese proficiency. Each group has two participants (one male and one

female). Although the sample size is small in this study, they can still represent the linguistic repertoires of Thai L2 learners to a certain extent.

Two Chinese students (one male and one female) were also recruited, as the control group at the same university. They are both 21 years old and speaks standard southwest Mandarin (Level 2A or above in the National *Putonghua* Proficiency Test).

4.2 Experimental stimuli

To elicit native speakers and Thai L2 learners' diphthong productions, we prepared a list of words containing the four cardinal vowels /a/, /i/, /u/, /o/ and the two back vowels /uo/ and /ua/. For the two diphthongs, both monosyllabic and polysyllabic words were used. Altogether there are 17 monosyllabic words and 28 polysyllabic words (refer to the Appendix for the whole word list).

4.3 Procedure

In this paper, the voice collected from the recording is used as the experimental corpus. Praat software developed by Paul Boersma & David weinink (2020) and modified by Bei Xianming and Xiang Ning (2020) is used to extract the formant data of vowels, calculate and analyze the recorded data, and draw the acoustic vowel diagram according to the common vibration peak frequency measured by acoustic experiment. It's a speech analysis program, was used in the study to collect participants' recording of the participants. The participants were instructed to read aloud the words on the list at their normal speed twice. After recording, acoustic measurements were conducted on the target vowels. For the cardinal vowels, the means of formant 1 (F1) and formant 2 (F2) were measured with the help of Praat. Then the vowel charts of each speaker, with both F1 and F2 averaged over the all words, were plotted with Praat. According to M. Joos (1948), although the frequency of the same vowel formant varies from person to person, the relative position of each vowel on the acoustic vowel diagram is basically stable. Therefore, we try our best to select the single character with zero initial and Yin flat tone from the experimental corpus, and divide the formant curve of the vowel part of the speech sample into 10 parts, so as to obtain the formant data of 11 measurement points, and the acoustic unit is Hertz (Hz). Then, the data of 11 measurement points (each measuring point includes three dimensions of F1, F2 and F3) are obtained for the posterior consonant /uo/ and /ua/, and the data of 2 backward consonant disyllables of 8 speakers is $11 * 8 * 3 = 264$ measurement points.

The formant patterns and acoustic vowels of Chinese Putonghua from six Thai students and two Chinese students were obtained by means of cut tone analysis and statistical mapping.

4.4 The formant patterns of /uo/ and /ua/

We inputed the data from acoustic analysis into Excel to draw scatter plot, and carried out according to the actual performance of formant trajectory the average values of male and female in each vowel category were calculated. Then, with time (T) as the horizontal axis and frequency (Hz) as the vertical axis, the formant pattern of each retroactive diphthong was drawn.

Figure 1 The formant pattern of Thai learner A (male)

Figure 2 The formant pattern of Thai learner A (female)

Figure 3 The formant pattern of Thai learner B (male)

Figure 4 The formant pattern of Thai learner B (female)

Figure 5 The formant pattern of Thai learner C (male)

Figure 6 The formant pattern of Thai learner C (female)

Figure 7 The formant pattern of Chinese speaker (male)

Figure 8 The formant pattern of Chinese speaker (female)

Through the comparative analysis, we can clearly see that similarities and differences of Thai students and Chinese students pronouncing the the two vowels /uo / and /ua/.

4.4.1 Similarities

Both male and female students can clearly see the dynamic changes of the tongue position of the backward consonant vowels /uo / and /ua/ from the ventral /u/ to the final /o/ and /a/ of the Chinese Putonghua students from Thailand and China. Relatively speaking, the formant trend of /ua/ is relatively stable, while the change range of /uo/ is larger, especially for males, and Chinese males are no exception.

4.4.2 Dissimilarities

Compared with male students, the formants of /uo/ and /ua/ in Mandarin Chinese of Thai female students and Chinese female students are more stable. Because Thai learner B is easy to slide to /ua/ when she pronounced /uo/, her F2 and F3 movements are obvious, especially when F3 is the same as Thai boy B, the change range is larger. However, the F2 movement of /uo/ of the four boys is obvious. Is it because the actual pronunciation of /uo / is [uɤ], the vowel of /uo/ is relatively stable, and the distribution of /ɤ/ vowels is a narrow band from top to bottom. It can be seen from the diagram that there is an obvious dynamic process.

4.5 Comparative analysis of acoustic vowels in Mandarin Chinese by Thai and Chinese students

In order to show the difference between /uo / and /ua/ more intuitively, we put /uo/ and /ua/ in the same acoustic vowel diagram to see their comparative performance. At the same time, we also put the average values of the three vertex vowels of /a/, /i/, /u/ and /o/ in the diagram as the reference point of the acoustic degree. As shown in Figure 9-16:

Figure 9 Vowe chart by Thai learner A (male)

Figure 10 Vowel chart of Thai learner A (female)

Figure 11 Vowel chart by Thai learner B (male)

Figure 12 Vowel chart of Thai learner B (female)

Figure 13 Vowel chart by Thai learner C (male)

Figure 14 Vowel chart by Thai learner C (female)

Figure 15 Vowel chart by Chinese speaker (male)

Figure 16 Vowel chart by Chinese speaker (female)

In the above eight figures, the red mark is /uo/, and the black mark is /ua/.

Through comparative analysis, we can clearly see the similarities and differences of the backward diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ between Thai students and Chinese students in Mandarin Chinese.

4. 5.1 The similarities

On the whole, Thai students and Chinese students have concentrated, fixed, and not very dispersed pronunciation positions of the backward diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ in Mandarin Chinese. The pronunciation position of /uo/ is basically above /ua/, except for some Thai students whose pronunciation positions of /uo/ and /ua/ overlap, most Thai students and Chinese students have obvious differences in the pronunciation position of the backward consonant /uo/ and /ua/, and the position of /uo/ is significantly higher than that of /ua/.

4. 5.2 The differences

As shown in Fig.9-14, the backward diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ of Thai students in Mandarin Chinese are very close to each other. Although the distance between the two articulation regions is not large, it can still be distinguished. The F1 values of /uo/ are mostly between 800-1000hz, some are lower than 800Hz or higher than 1000Hz; F2 values are mostly between 1000-1500hz and some are between 1500-2000hz. The F1 values of /ua/ are mostly between 800-1200hz, and F2 values are mostly around 1500hz. In addition to Thai male students C and Thai girls B and C, the pronunciation positions of /uo/ and /ua/ in the other three Thai students were significantly close to the lower lip vowels /a/. However, Thai boy c and Thai girl b and C have been able to distinguish

/uo/ and /ua/ correctly due to their high level of Chinese. Therefore, some of the pronunciation positions of /uo/ are close to those of Round Lip vowels /o/.

As shown in Fig.15-16, the positions of the backward diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ are significantly different among Chinese students. The positions of /uo/ was significantly higher than that of /ua/ and was close to the back half of the tongue near the back half -raised rounded vowels /o/ of the tongue, The positions of /ua/ was significantly lower than that of /uo/ and was close to the front half of the tongue near the front low-spread vowels /a/ of the tongue. The F1 values of Chinese boys are mostly around 600Hz, while those of Chinese girls are mostly around 800Hz; the F2 values of two Chinese students are mostly around 1500Hz.

5. An analysis of the transfer of backward diphthongs /uo /, /ua/ by Thai students in Mandarin Chinese acquisition

To sum up, the biggest problem of Thai students in acquiring Mandarin is the location and duration of the backward diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/. Zhu (2013) pointed out that the diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ in Mandarin Chinese are all post core compound vowels, and the rhyme part is longer. Because the latter part is the main and stable vowel, the former part /u/ is only a slip, and the rhyme o/a together constitute the vowel, so the stable vowel section of the vowel in the back ring is longer. Wang Ping (2008) proved that the duration /a/ of /ua/ is more than twice that of /au/, and the ratio of the critical point duration of /ua/ to the total syllable duration is more than twice that of /au/ pass through experimental confirmation. So, are Thai students affected by the Thai long vowel ua[uɹ:a] to extend the ending of /uo/ and send it to /ua/? Shi (2002) pointed out that the last vowel of the back diphthongs, that is, the vowel stable segment is longer. Because the actual pronunciation of the backward diphthongs /uo/ in Mandarin is [uɥ], the pronunciation of [ɥ] vowel is generally sliding from [u] to [ʌ]. Compared with vertex vowels, the middle vowel is often unstable and has the nature of wandering. This should be paid special attention to in teaching and Research.

Due to the negative transfer of their mother tongue and the interference of the target language, Thai students at the initial and intermediate stages are easily confused with the backward diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ in Mandarin Chinese. To a large extent, the instability /ɥ/ of /uo/ vowels leads to the slip of /uo/ to /ua/. When /uo/ is in the second syllable or at the end of the word, it is easy to slide to /ua/, while it is relatively stable when it is in the first syllable. This may be because the first syllable does not take long, and the speaker does not need or have time to slide to the position of the first low vowel /a/. Similarly, when /ua/ is in the first syllable, it is easy to slide to /uo/, but it is relatively stable when it is in the second syllable. Thai students in the intermediate stage can distinguish between /uo/ and /ua/ after a certain period of normal training. For example, the Thai students in group C will not have the previous phonetic errors when they pronounce /uo/ and /ua/ respectively. But sometimes it is not very stable, especially in the use of words, which is difficult to correct without scientific training.

Although most Thai students can pronounce the backward diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ in Mandarin Chinese, but it's easy for Thai students in the primary and intermediate stages to confuse and even mispronounced. Thai students in advanced stage usually do not have these phonetic errors, because they can correctly distinguish these easily confused sounds.

In view of the above analysis, we have the following findings:

(1) Thai students can correctly distinguish the backward diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/, but it is easier to /uo/ slide to /ua/ when it is in the second syllable or at the end of the word. When /ua/ is in the first syllable, it is easy to slide to /uo/.

(2) Thai students confusing the backward diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ in Mandarin Chinese because of the negative transfer of their mother tongue. We also found that /ie/ is easy to slide to /ia/. Is it possible that Thai students to have a tendency for the instability /y/ tend to slide to /a/? We will discuss this in another article.

(3) There may be other reasons, such as the level of Chinese proficiency of Thai students, learning time, phonetic environment and learners' attitude will all affect second language speech acquisition.

6. Teaching strategies

In view of the phonetic errors of the the backward diphthongs /uo/ and /ua/ in Mandarin Chinese of Thai students, we can help them correctly distinguish the pronunciation positions of /o/ and /a/ according to the phonetic characteristics of Mandarin Chinese. We can find that /o/ is a round lip vowel at the back of the tongue and /a/ is a low spreading lip vowel in front of the tongue dissimilarity. Both inside and outside the classroom, it is necessary to practice repeatedly according to the pronunciation position and mouth type, and classify the words with the final consonant of /uo/ and /ua/, such as teaching the Chinese characters with /uo/ and /o/ together to tell the students that their finals are actually the same; the Chinese characters with /ua/ and /a/ are taught together. In addition, we can help Thai students acquire the backward diphthongs of Mandarin Chinese by repeatedly practicing the pronunciation and discrimination of "gua" and "guo", "hua" and "huo", "shua" and "shuo".

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Appendix:
 Mandarin Chinese pronunciation list of Thai Students
 Monophonic: i/u/o/a

Vowels	uo	ua
Monosyllabic words	Guo/duo/luo/suo/huo Shuo/ruo/zhuo/zuo/cuo	Gua/hua/kua/zhua/shua Gua/kua
Polysyllabic words	Zhongguo/henduo/qiaoluo chusuo/huoze/woshuo Ruguo/huozhuo/jizuo Zuoyou/xiecuo/cuowu Shenghuo/satuo/shuzuo Luotuo/chengnuo/nuoyan	Xigua/xiaohua/huahua Xiehua/wanshua/guahua Hengkua/kuayikua Zhuayizhua/shuayishua

Processing Phonetic Radicals of Chinese Characters in a Sentence: Data from Mandarin Native Speakers

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A self-paced reading task, and semantic violation paradigm were involved to test for the phonetic radicals of processing Chinese character in the different context sentences. The results demonstrate that: (1) In the high-constraints context, the orthography makes a significant effect in the early stage when processing a Chinese character, while the phonological cue was emerged gradually in the late stage. In the low-constraints context, neither the orthography nor the phonological cue was activated when native speakers processed the Chinese characters. (2) The present study also indicates that the processing model of phonetic radical is similar to the model of whole characters in the high-constraint context and supports the dual-route hypothesis.

1. Introduction

More than 80 percent of Chinese characters are phonograms. A phonogram consists of two parts, the semantic radical, which offers the semantic information for the whole character, and the phonetic radical, which provides the phonological cue for the character. Besides, a phonetic radical can always be used as a single character. There are three character-processing models: dual-route access model, direct access route, and phonologically mediated access route. Direct access route suggests that the phonological cue does not take part in the processing, and access the meaning of lexical words directly (Aronson & Ferres, 1983; Yin, 1990; Ziegler et.al, 1999; Chen, 2001). The phonological mediated route suggests that the phonological cue as the mediation, and the semantic meaning of lexical is accessed by both the phonological cue and the orthographical cue (Perfetti & Zhang, 1995). The dual-route access hypothesis suggests there are two routes when we access the meaning of a lexical word. The first one is direct access to the meaning through the orthographical information, and the second route is through both orthographical information and phonological information (Aronson, D.et al. 1983; Coltheart, M.et al. 1993.).

A lot of the previous studies were involved into researching the phonetic radicals and semantic radicals in sub-lexical level. Zhou (2013) concludes that whatever the function of the phonetic radicals and semantic radicals were, they all had their own representation, and were processed independently. Yeh (2017) used Stroop task to prove

the semantic activation of phonetic radicals, and to conclude that the phonological cue was not necessary when processing a Chinese character.

What were said above is the previous study about processing in a whole character level or a sub-lexical level. Based on it, how a character is processed in a sentence context is a hot topic for many researchers. In sentences, the character can be constrained by different factors of sentence (i.e. sentence context, sentence structure, sentence semantic, etc.). Wu (1998) used the moving window paradigm to find both the phonological cue and orthographical cue were activated in the early stage of the reading. Wong (1999) used semantic violation paradigm with the eye-tracking skill to conclude that the orthographic information was found in the early stage of character processing and the phonological information was found in the late stage when processing the character. Besides, in different sentence context, the ways to process the character were also different. The sentence contexts can be divided into two parts, the high-constrains context and the low-constrains context. The way of processing character will depend on different sentence context. The target character was constrained highly in the high-constraint sentence context, because the sentence context can let the readers to have a highly prediction in target character. however, the target character was constrained lower in the low-constraint sentence context than the high one, because the sentence context can make the readers have a low prediction in target character. Ren (2012) researched the character processing model in different context, and suggested the orthographical information emerged in the early stage, and the interaction effect of orthography and the phonology emerged in the later stage when processing the character in the high-constraint sentence context. However, in the low-constraint sentence context, the orthographical information was found in the early stage, while the phonological information was found in the later stage.

For the topic about the radicals (sub-lexical level) processed in sentences. Pan (2019) adopted different research paradigm of eye tracking, and researched how participants processed the phonetic radicals in different reading models (silent reading and reading aloud). The result showed that, whatever the research paradigm was, the phonological information in the sub-lexical character level was not activated in silent reading, and in the reading tasks aloud, the Pan. et, al found that the phonological information was not activated in the early stage when processing a whole character, and for the sub-lexical level, the phonological information was not activated in both the early and the late stage. However, Luo (2018) adopted the same paradigm as that Pan (2019) used in the experiment two, and researched for how the phonetic radical was processed in a sentence. The result supported the dual-route hypothesis, but found that the phonological information of phonetic radical emerged in the early stage when processing the whole character and the orthographical information emerged in the end of the sentence, and integrated the meaning of whole sentences.

But, the reading model of phonetic radicals remains controversial. Whether the different sentence context can influence the orthographical information and the phonological information also needs to be studied. In the present paper, we will use the

self-paced reading task and the semantic violation paradigm to explore how the phonetic radicals are processed in the different sentence context.

2. Method

2.1. Participants

45 Chinese native speakers were from Xinxiang University in Henan. The average age of participants was 20. They had normal or corrected-to-normal vision. They were all right-handed. Before conducting the experiment, the participants need to sign the consent form and they were paid for their attendance after the experiment.

2.2. Material and Design

The material consisted of three parts, the formal experimental material, the fillers and the practice part. For the formal material, the present experiment consisted of 15 groups sentences, and every group had ten conditions, so we adopted the 2 (high/low constraints) × 5 (the target type: the consistent condition, s_C+R+P, s_C-R+P+, s_C-R-P+, unrelated condition) design. For the consistent condition: the target character was the right character which was fit for the sentence; For the s_C+R+P+: the target character was a wrong character, while the pronunciation of whole character was similar to the pronunciation of character of consistent condition, and the phonetic radical of the character was similar to the character of consistent condition; For the s_C-R+P+: the target character was a wrong character, while the pronunciation of whole character was not similar to the pronunciation of character of consistent condition, but the phonetic radical was similar to the consistent condition; For the s_C-R-P+: the target character was a wrong character, and only the pronunciation of phonetic radical was similar to the character of consistent condition. For the unrelated condition: the target character was completely unrelated to the consistent condition. There were also 60 filler sentences, and 10 practice sentences. In order to ensure that the participants read every sentence carefully, we put some yes or no questions after every sentence. The experiment material was showed as shown as Table 1:

Condition	Critical Character	High-constraint 1	High-constraint 2	Low-constraint 1	Low-constraint 2
consistent	风 wind	她们雷厉风行地抓捕凶手 They arrested the murderer vigorously	阵阵的冷风让人捂紧胸口 The bursts of cold wind made people hold their chest tightly.	她们沦落风尘后依旧善良 They are still kind after falling into the dust	萧瑟的寒风将树叶吹落了 The bleak wind blows the leaves off
s_C+R+P	枫 maple	她们雷厉枫行地抓捕凶手	阵阵的冷枫让人捂紧胸口	她们沦落枫尘后依旧善良	萧瑟的寒枫将树叶吹落了
s_C-R+P+	飒 handsome	她们雷厉飒行地抓捕凶手	阵阵的冷飒让人捂紧胸口	她们沦落飒尘后依旧善良	萧瑟的寒飒将树叶吹落了
s_C-R-P+	蚌 shell	她们雷厉蚌行地抓捕凶手	阵阵的冷蚌让人捂紧胸口	她们沦落蚌尘后依旧善良	萧瑟的寒蚌将树叶吹落了
unrelated	骏 horse	她们雷厉骏行地抓捕凶手	阵阵的冷骏让人捂紧胸口	她们沦落骏尘后依旧善良	萧瑟的寒骏将树叶吹落了

Table 1

Before making the experiment material, we made some high/low-constraints sentences material which were according to every consistent character. In order to ensure all the formal experiment material were the reliable high/low-constraint sentences, we used another 40 students who would not take part in the self-paced reading experiment to finish a constraint condition survey of sentence context. The questionnaire was made by some gap-fillings, and there were 4 characters before every blank as sentence context (such as, 他们雷厉___, “ They are fast__ ”). We asked the participants to fill the fifth character in the blank according to the meaning of the first 4 characters. If the rate that the fifth character of a sentence filled by participants was in accord with the fifth character in the original sentences we made before was more than 93%, we would decide to use them as the high-constraint sentence context, and if the coincidence rate was less than 7%, it would be chosen as the low-constraint sentence context. The experiment material was divided into 5 groups by Latin square design, and every condition was presented to a participant six times. Therefore, in this experiment, there are 120 experiment sentences (60 formal experiment sentence, 60 fillers). The self-paced reading task and semantic violation paradigm were involved in present study.

2.3 Apparatus:

The material of experiment was presented in a MacBook Pro desktop, and we programmed the material in the “ibex farm”, which is a psycholinguistics research platform. In order to avoid the mistake bought by the unstable internet environment, all the participants were invited to a quiet classroom to conducted the experiment.

2.4 Procedure:

The participants sat before the desktop, and the distance between the desktop and the participants is around 60cm. The participant needed to fill out a consent form. After that, the participants themselves must fill some basic information consent form after the researcher opened the experiment link. Before practicing, the participants must read the instruction and begin the practice after clicking the “continue”. After the practice, the participants needed to make out the task clearly before they began the formal experiment. If they had some questions about the task, they can ask the researcher before the formal experiment. At beginning of the experiment, a red cross was showed in the center of the screen for 1000ms, so as to let the participants concentrate on the experiment. When the cross disappeared, a dashed line would be presented on the center of the screen. The participants were asked to press the space bar according to their reading speed. Every time, the participants pressed the space bar, a character disappeared, while the next character appeared. The time clock recorded the time of every interval between two contiguous pressing bar. The participants needed to do a yes/no question after reading every formal experiment sentence.

3. Results and Analysis

The reaction time (RT) as the data entered the statistics analysis. We deleted the result that the accuracy rate was lower than 80%. We logged the RT data firstly, and deleted the data outside plus or minus 2.5 standard deviations, so as to ensure the data was satisfied with the normal distribution. We used the one-way ANOVA statistic method. The target types were regarded as the independent variable. We used the “lme4” package to build up the Linear Mixed Effect Model. The Table 2 below is the RT data of every character in every sentence under every condition. When we analyzed the data, the consistence condition would be the reference condition. The difference between the s_C-R-P+ and s_C-R+P+ represents the activation of the orthographic information of phonetic radical. The difference between the unrelated condition and s_C-R-P- represents the activation of the phonological information of phonetic radical; Besides, due to the consistency rules, the difference between s_C+R+P+ and s_C-R+P+ also represents the activation of the phonological information of phonetic radical.

constraints	condition	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
high	Control	452(225)	439(186)	419(185)	410(163)	402(158)	413(187)	409(180)	392(176)
	s_C+R+P+	456(217)	535(302)	510(267)	450(210)	420(168)	417(200)	394(143)	364(125)
	s_C-R+P+	448(217)	549(318)	560(283)	470(244)	428(192)	409(163)	381(152)	374(136)
	s_C-R-P+	456(230)	575(356)	635(326)	488(255)	419(174)	407(158)	388(163)	361(130)
low	Unrelated	452(239)	584(361)	641(359)	540(291)	462(197)	419(210)	397(168)	382(150)
	Control	455(205)	478(221)	501(267)	454(198)	460(225)	433(192)	404(138)	399(162)
	s_C+R+P+	438(200)	560(330)	608(319)	513(242)	459(187)	429(174)	411(188)	386(154)
	s_C-R+P+	435(220)	522(326)	642(344)	522(273)	455(196)	457(239)	392(150)	384(153)
	s_C-R-P+	444(212)	551(329)	643(362)	514(245)	454(192)	440(203)	410(169)	400(185)
	Unrelated	436(185)	540(310)	633(353)	558(291)	479(228)	432(174)	418(177)	396(146)

Table 2

In the following, we will analyze the difference between different conditions:

3.1 high-constraint context:

According to the Table 2 above, the data of “constraint-high”, we analyzed it character by character, and made a conclusion as follows:

For the fourth character position, which was the character before the critical character. The main effect of character condition was not found ($p=0.9416$), which meant that when participants did not read the critical character, the five condition had no different effect on the RT of the fourth condition.

For the fifth character position, the critical character, the main effect of character condition was found ($X^2= 37.953, df=4, p<0.001$). Through the analysis of post-hoc test, the results showed that, the RT of s_C+R+P+ ($b=0.06, SE=0.015, t=3.839, p<0.001$), s_C-R+P+ ($b=0.07, SE=0.015, t=4.567, p<0.001$), s_C-R-P+ ($b=0.08, SE=0.016, t=4.919, p<0.001$), and the unrelated condition ($b=0.09, SE=0.016, t=5.477, p<0.001$) were significantly higher than the RT of consistent condition ($ps.<0.05$). However, there is no significant difference between any two of character conditions. This result meant that the substitute character of s_C+R+P+, s_C-R+P+, s_C-R-P+, and unrelated condition led to

increasing of RT, but the phonological cue and the orthographical cue of the phonetic radical were not activated during the character processing. Therefore, in the present study on the critical character position, the phonological cue and the orthographical cue were not activated.

For the sixth character position, the character behind the critical character, the main effect of character condition was found ($X^2=149.74$, $df=4$, $p<0.001$). The analysis of the post-hoc test showed that the RT of condition of s_C+R+P+ ($b=0.076$, $SE=0.015$, $t=5.042$, $p<0.001$), s_C-R+P+ ($b=0.114$, $SE=0.015$, $t=7.554$, $p<0.001$), s_C-R-P+ ($b=0.16$, $SE=0.015$, $t=10.651$, $p<0.001$), and unrelated condition ($b=0.162$, $SE=0.015$, $t=10.621$, $p<0.001$) were significantly higher than that of the consistent condition (s_C+R+P+ > consistent condition, $p<0.001$; s_C-R+P+ > consistent condition, $p<0.001$; s_C-R-P+ > consistent condition, $p<0.001$; unrelated condition > consistent condition, $p<0.001$). This result indicated that the substitute character of s_C+R+P+, s_C-R+P+, s_C-R-P+, and unrelated condition led to increasing of reaction time. Besides, there was a significant difference between s_C+R+P+ and s_C-R-P+ ($p<0.001$), and s_C-R+P+ and s_C-R-P+ ($p<0.05$), which showed that the orthographical cue of phonetic radical affected the character processing. The difference between s_C-R+P+ and s_C+R+P+ was marginally significant ($p=0.0977$), and the difference between s_C-R-P+ and unrelated condition was not significant ($p=1$), which both indicated that the phonological cue of phonetic radical was not activated, but the phonology cue of whole character may be activated.

For the seventh character position, which was the second character after the critical character, the main effect of character condition was found ($X^2= 59.288$, $df=4$, $p=0.07$). The results of the post-hoc test showed that there was marginally significant difference between the condition of s_C+R+P+ ($b=0.03$, $SE=0.013$, $t=2.563$, $p<0.01$) and consistent condition ($p=0.077$), and the RT in s_C-R+P+ condition ($b=0.05$, $SE=0.013$, $t=3.657$, $p<0.001$), s_C-R-P+ condition ($b=0.06$, $SE=0.013$, $t=4.403$, $p<0.001$) and unrelated condition ($b=0.1$, $SE=0.013$, $t=7.562$, $p<0.001$) were significantly higher than that of consistent condition ($ps.<0.001$). The above results indicated that on the seventh character position, the reaction time was increased by replacing character when the sentence of s_C+R+P+ condition, s_C-R+P+ condition, s_C-R-P+ condition and unrelated condition were processed. There was no significant difference between the s_C-R+P+ condition and s_C-R-P+ ($p=0.91$), which meant that the orthographical cue of phonetic radical did not merge individually on the seventh position. However, the RT of unrelated condition was significantly higher than that of s_C-R-P+ condition ($p=0.012$), which meant the phonological cue of phonetic radical was activated individually on the seventh character position. Moreover, that the RT of unrelated condition was significantly higher than that of s_C-R+P+ condition ($p<0.001$) and s_C+R+P+ condition ($p<0.001$) meant that the orthographical cue and phonological cue had interaction effect on the second character position after the critical character.

For the eighth character, that is the third character after the critical character, the main effect of character condition was found ($X^2= 20.8$, $df=4$, $p<0.001$). The post-hoc test

indicated that, there were no significant difference ($ps.>0.1$) between consistent condition and s_C+R+P+ condition ($b=0.009$, $SE=0.012$, $t=0.792$, $p=0.4$), between consistent condition and s_C-R+P+ condition ($b=0.011$, $SE=0.015$, $t=0.976$, $p=0.329$), between consistent condition and s_C-R-P+ condition ($b=0.008$, $SE=0.012$, $t=0.732$, $p=0.464$), which indicated that on the seventh character position, the reaction time was not increased by replacing characters of s_C+R+P+ condition, s_C-R+P+ condition, and s_C-R-P+ conditions. Moreover, the RT of s_C-R-P+ conditions were significantly higher than that of the s_C-R+P+ condition and s_C+R+P+ condition collectively ($p=1$), and this results above indicated that the orthographical cue of phonetic radical of critical character was not activated when participants processed the eighth character position. However, the RT of unrelated condition ($b=0.05$, $SE=0.01$, $t=4.505$, $p<0.001$) was still significantly higher than that of s_C+R+P+ condition, s_C-R+P+ condition and s_C-R-P+ condition ($ps.<0.05$), which indicated the phonological cue of phonetic radical was also activated individually. However, in Luo (2018), they only found that the regular phonogram (s_C+R+P+ at present study) was significantly different from unrelated condition (unrelated condition at present study), but did not find the irregular (s_C-R+P+ condition in the present study) and homophone were significantly different from the unrelated condition respectively. Therefore, Luo (2018) concluded only when the phonetic radical had the same pronunciation with the whole character, the phonological cue of phonetic radical could make the positive activation, which could not apply to explain the result in the present study.

For the ninth character and the tenth character, which were the fourth and the fifth character after the critical character, the main effect of character condition was not found ($ps.>0.05$). However, the main effect of character condition showed significance on the eleventh character ($p=0.0314$), which was the sixth character after the critical character. The post-hoc test suggested the RT of s_C-R-P+ ($b=-0.025$, $SE=0.009$, $t=-2.746$, $p=0.006$) was significantly shorter than that of consistent condition, and the RT of s_C+R+P+ ($b=-0.024$, $SE=0.009$, $t=-2.482$, $p=0.013$) was significantly shorter than consistent condition. However, this result cannot suggest anything, since they have shorter RT than the consistent condition.

3.2 low-constraint context:

According to the data of “low constraints”, we analyzed it character by character, and made a conclusion as shown:

For the fourth character, that is the last character before the critical character. The main effect of character condition was not found ($p=0.24$), which meant when participants did not read the critical character, the five conditions had no different effect on the reaction time of the fourth character.

For the fifth character, that is the critical character. The main effect of character condition was found ($X^2=13.557$, $df=4$, $p=0.009$), The post-hoc test showed that the RT of s_C+R+P+ condition and s_C-R+P+ condition were significantly higher than the

consistent condition ($p=0.0349$ and $p=0.0138$ respectively), which meant when the participants read the critical character, replacing the character in the condition of s_C+R+P+ and s_C-R-P+ led to the significant difference of reaction time between the consistent condition and s_C+R+P+ condition and s_C-R-P+ condition.

For the sixth character, that is the first character after the critical character. The main effect of character condition was found ($X^2=62.671$, $df=4$, $p<0.001$). The post-hoc test showed that the last four conditions (s_C+R+P+ , s_C-R+P+ , s_C-R-P+ , unrelated condition) were significantly different from the consistent condition ($s_C+R+P+ >$ consistent condition, $p<0.001$; $s_C-R+P+ >$ consistent condition, $p<0.001$; $s_C-R-P+ >$ consistent condition, $p<0.001$; unrelated condition $>$ consistent condition, $p<0.001$). However, there was no difference between the two of last four conditions (s_C+R+P+ , s_C-R+P+ , s_C-R-P+ , unrelated condition), which meant that whatever the destroy of orthographical cue of phonetic radical, or the destroy of phonological cue of phonetic radical was, the reaction time did not show significant difference between these four conditions, and whatever the condition was, they were all regarded as the unrelated condition was for the participants.

For the seventh character, that is the second character after the critical character. The main effect of character condition was found ($X^2=32.771$, $df=4$, $p<0.001$), through the post-hoc test, we found that RT of s_C+R+P+ condition ($b=0.048$, $SE=0.013$, $t=3.674$, $p<0.001$), s_C-R+P+ condition ($b=0.054$, $SE=0.013$, $t=4.091$, $p<0.001$), s_C-R-P+ condition ($b=0.055$, $SE=0.013$, $t=4.161$, $p<0.001$), and the unrelated condition ($b=0.078$, $SE=0.013$, $t=5.998$, $p<0.001$) were significantly higher than that of the consistent condition ($p<0.06$) ($s_C+R+P+ >$ consistent condition, $p<0.01$; $s_C-R+P+ >$ consistent condition, $p<0.001$; $s_C-R-P+ >$ consistent condition, $p<0.001$; unrelated condition $>$ consistent condition, $p<0.001$). The results showed that on the seventh position, the substitution of critical character led to the increase in reaction time. However, there was not any significant difference among these four conditions, which meant the orthographical cue and phonological cue were not activated, and whatever the condition was, they were all regarded as the unrelated condition was for the participants.

From the eighth character position to the eleventh character position in a sentence, that is to say, the third position to the last character position after the critical character, the main effect of character condition was not significant ($ps. > 0.1$). The results showed that in the low-constraint context, from the third character position to the last character position after the critical character, the processing difficulty triggered by substitution of critical character was gradually recovered, and disappeared.

Overall, through the statistical analysis of reaction time, the phonological cue of phonetic radical was activated in the high constraints context. In the early period of character processing, the phonological cue of phonetic radical was activated, and then the interaction effect of phonological cue and the orthographical cue of phonetic radical were activated. Finally, the phonological cue of phonetic radical was activated with the interaction effect of phonological cue and the orthographical cue of phonetic radical. In the

low-constraint context, the phonological cue of phonetic radical was not activated statistically. However, seen from the reaction time, there existed time difference between the two character conditions, and the detailed analysis will be shown as the following.

4. Discussion

4.1 The discussion of the result in high-constraint context

In the high constraint context, the orthographical cue was activated firstly, and the phonological cue of phonetic radical was activated gradually. This result indicated that the orthographical cue of phonetic radical was early activated when the participants processed the character, but the phonological cue of phonetic radical was activated in the later time. The conclusion above meant that processing model of phonetic radical in a sentence context could be the direct access route, which was access to the meaning of lexical words through the orthographical information directly, and could also be the dual-route access modal, which was access to the meaning through the orthographical information, or through both orthographical information and phonological information. Therefore, this result proved the dual-route hypothesis when native speakers processed the phonetic radicals in the high-constraint context. This conclusion is consistent with the previous studies, like the conclusion in Pan (2019) and Luo (2018). However, even the processing pattern was similar between the Luo (2018) and present study, there was a big difference between them. Through the first fixation duration (FFD) of eye movement. Luo (2019) found there were significant differences between the regular condition (i.e. “qing” “清” “clean”, this condition like s_C+R+P+ in present study.) and the irregular condition (i.e. “cai” “猜” “guess”, this condition like s_C-R+P+ in present study), and the regular condition and unrelated condition. Luo (2018) thought the results may due to the activation of phonological cue of phonetic radical. So they made a conclusion: only when the pronunciation of phonetic radical was consistent with the whole character’s pronunciation, the phonological cue of phonetic radical could be positively activated, then the fixation time of regular condition would be shorter than the irregular condition, and the orthographical cue of phonetic radical was activated in the later stage. So the result of Luo (2018) was inconsistent with the result in present study. The reason resulting in the different result may be due to the experimental material. We replaced the homophone condition (i.e. “qing” “轻” “light”) of Luo (2018) study with s_C-R-P+ condition of present study (only the pronunciation of phonetic radical was the same with the right critical character.), and this s_C-R-P+ condition can be directly distinguished whether the phonological cue of phonetic radical activated at present study, which was the same with the second condition of Pan (2019). At present self-paced reading study, in the eighth character position of high-constraint context sentences, we found the significant difference between the s_C-R-P+ condition and the unrelated condition, which directly suggested that the phonological cue of phonetic radical was activated. However, according to the conclusion of Luo (2018), we might also see the significant difference between s_C-R+P+ and s_C+R+P+, but we did not. In my deduction, the material in Luo’s (2018) study could

not be made the result directly that the phonological cue of phonetic radical was activated in the early stage, and I suppose that, in Luo (2018) result, they did not get the significant difference between the homophone condition and unrelated condition, which indicated that phonological cue of whole character was not activated individually, and the FFD of regular condition was significantly shorter than the FFD of irregular condition due to the interaction effect of the same phonological cue of whole character and phonetic radical, but not the phonological cue of whole character or phonetic radical individually. Therefore, we may not easily to conclude that the phonological cue of phonetic radical was activated individually in the early stage of processing character.

4.2 The discussion of the result in low-constraint context

In the low-constraint context, From the critical character position to the second character position after the critical character, the main effect of character condition was found, but did not find that the orthographical or phonological cue of phonetic radicals affected the reaction time. So, in the low-constraint context, the orthographical or phonological cue of phonetic radicals was not activated, and the character processing may be presented in the whole character level. Pan (2019) studied the the pattern of phonetic radicals and the whole characters in silent reading condition through two experiments (experiment 1&2), and whatever paradigm (the parafoveal preview paradigm and the semantic violation paradigm) they used, they still did not find the activation in sub-lexical level (phonetic radicals). This result was consistent with the present study in low-constraint context. What's more, seen from the sentence example of semantic violation experiment in Pan (2019), the sentence constraint was similar to the constraint in low-constraint context in present study (e.g. “她的这幅油画意在描绘夕阳下事物的祥和美好。” “Her oil painting is intended to project the peace and beauty of things in the sunset). Although Pan (2019) used the eye movement skill, maybe the material was some reason that the result was similar to the result of low-constraint context in the present study. This result was caused by the reason that the participants could not attain the predictive information from low-constraint context, and could not judge the meaning of the right critical character from the context.

4.3 The influence of context on character processing

Rayner (1998) studied the phonological code of English word in different context, and found that in the high-constraint context, the processing mechanism was top-down, and the context information made more contribution in understanding the information. So we can easily get the critical word meaning from the previous context in a sentence, and could quickly process this critical character. However, according to the study of Rayner (1998), we were difficult to get the meaning of the critical word from the low-constraint context, since the processing mechanism was bottom-up, which the information from the context was limited. So at present study, readers need to integrate the meaning of a sentence character by character, and it is slow for readers to get the meaning of the critical word.

We could easily find from Table2 that the reaction time of high-constraint context were shorter than the reaction times of low-constraint context, which the critical character in high-constraint context could give a quick cue of critical word with the whole lexical level and sub-lexical level to prime the target character in different conditions, and to make some significant difference between two of last four conditions (s_C+R+P+, s_C-R+P+, s_C-R-P+, unrelated condition). However, as it difficult provide an accurate information of lexical level and sub-lexical level of critical character in low-constraint context, it still did not show any significant difference between the two of the last four conditions (s_C+R+P+, s_C-R+P+, s_C-R-P+, unrelated condition), even up to the end of the sentence in low-constraint context. Therefore, according to the above, Chinese character might have different processing pattern in different sentence context, which also supports the result in present study. Besides, according to Rayner (1998)' study, "the top-down processes might defeat spelling check stages and reveal the involvement of phonological processing in lexical access if there were more contextual support for a target word, which means that the phonological code in English was activated automatically and quickly. However, the material of Rayner (1998) was the English words. As Wong (1999) said, the character system of Chinese word was different from the word system of English. English is the alphabetic script writing system, which a syllable represents a phoneme, so the relationship between the pronunciation and the syllable was close. However, Chinese character was a logographic script system, and a pronunciation can represent many different characters, so there is not too close relationship between one pronunciation and one character. In the high-constraint context, the orthographical cue was activated and accessed the semantic radical directly and automatically in the early stage of processing, but the phonological cue was not, which also indicated the phonetic radical did not always provide the phonological cue when a whole character was processed.

5. Conclusion

We have summarized four conclusions in the present study. First, In the high-constraint context, the orthographical cue of phonetic radical was found in the early stage, at the same time, the interaction effect of phonological cue and the orthographical cue of phonetic radical was in the later stage when native speakers processed a character. Second, the phonetic radical was not activated in the low-constraint context. Third, processing the phonetic radical in high-constraint context is similar to processing the whole characters, and the present study also proves the statement in Zhou (2013): the sub-lexical representation exists independently when people processes the words. Finally, not only can the phonetic radical provide the phonological cue, but also provide the orthographical cue, and the result supports the phonetic processing modal was dual-route modal.

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How Mandarin Bidialectal Listeners Recognize Words when Their Two Tonal Systems Are Diametrically Opposed?

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In this eyetracking study, we investigate the online process of spoken word recognition among Putonghua/Lanzhou Mandarin listeners because half tones in these two dialects have opposed tonal properties. Specifically, the pitch contours of Putonghua tone 2 and tone 4 are systematically reversed in Lanzhou Mandarin. We are interested in finding out: i) whether this conflict of tonal properties causes interference for the Putonghua/Lanzhou bidialectal listeners in word recognition of both dialects; and ii) whether the bidialectal listeners behave any differently from the monodialectal Beijing listeners in word recognition of Putonghua. Despite word recognition in Mandarin is relatively well researched, our paper fills the gap in literature, providing the evidence to how two tonal systems interact and compete within a Mandarin bidialectal listener's brain.

1. Introduction

Bilinguals are capable of understanding and speaking two languages. A unique challenge to a bilingual speaker/listener is that their two linguistic systems may contain conflicting rules. A long-standing simplification in linguistics is to treat Mandarin Chinese speakers as a homogenous monolingual group, ignoring the complex reality in which a vast majority of them are in fact bidialectal/bilingual. Taking people living in Lanzhou City (Gansu province) for instance, they grow up speaking the local dialect, *Lanzhouhua* (Lanzhou Mandarin, a regional dialect of Mandarin), in the community but have learned to become proficient second-dialect speakers of *Putonghua* (standard Mandarin based on the Beijing Mandarin dialect) in the education system. Interestingly, the tonal systems of the two dialects are not identical. In particular, the pitch contours of Putonghua tone 2 words and tone 4 words are reversed in Lanzhou Mandarin, see the illustration in Figure 1. For example, the word 轴 *zhou2* 'axis' is pronounced with a rising contour in Putonghua/Beijing Mandarin, and a falling contour in Lanzhou, while the word 咒 *zhou4* 'to curse' is pronounced with a falling contour in Beijing and a rising contour in Lanzhou. Then the imminent question is, what are the consequences for those Lanzhou bidialectal speakers since the two dialects have diametrically opposed tonal properties for roughly half of the vocabulary?

Figure 1. Pitch contours for Tones 1–4 in Putonghua/Beijing Mandarin and Lanzhou

Throughout this paper, tones 2 and 4 are referred to as *disagreeing tones* (i.e., tones whose pitch contours move in the opposite direction in the two dialects) and tones 1 and 3 are referred to as *agreeing tones* (i.e., tones whose pitch contours move in roughly the same direction in both dialects.)

In this paper, three questions are explored using the visual world paradigm (VWP), the standard methodology investigating the question of online word recognition: first, do words with disagreeing tones interfere in word recognition of the Lanzhou/Putonghua bidialectal listeners? Second, if so, is the interference one-way or two-way? Last, since Mandarin speakers are inevitably bidialectal/bilingual, can we safely ignore their linguistic experience? In other words, during identifying Putonghua words with a disagreeing tone, will Lanzhou/Putonghua bidialectal listeners behave the same as the monodialectal Beijing listeners?

Before delving into searching for the answers, it is necessary to present the relevant background about Lanzhou Mandarin and previous research on bilingual word recognition.

1.1 Lanzhou Mandarin

Mandarin is the largest family within Chinese language. The term Mandarin is confusing because it is used to refer to the family as well as the standard dialect. To avoid confusion, I use *Putonghua* throughout the paper to refer to the standard dialect¹. Within the family, eight subgroups are identified: Beijing, Northeast, Ji Lu, Jiao Liao, Zhongyuan, Lan Yin, Jianghuai, and Southwest (Wurm et al. 1987). Several of the dialects use different pitch contours for the four tones, and some dialects in the Lan Yin subgroup have fewer than four contrastive tones.

The Lan Yin subgroup includes the local varieties of Mandarin spoken in Lanzhou (population 3.6 million), the capital city of Gansu province. Among the scarce amount of existing research on Lanzhou Mandarin, the findings about tones disagree on details. For example, Norman (1988) and Zhang (2009) agree it to be a four-tone system

¹ The term “dialect” is used in this paper to refer to any particular variety of language used by a group of people rather than its restrictive sense associating the language variety to its geographical regions. Beijing Mandarin is perceived more “accented” than Putonghua, but we primarily concern the tonal properties, which are identical between the two varieties. Hence, we use Beijing Mandarin and Putonghua interchangeably in this paper.

but differ in the nuance of pitch contours, see Table 1. In the survey of tonal systems in Gansu province by Xu (2015: 67-68), the counties of Yongdeng, Gaolan, and Yuzhong are classified as three-tone dialect regions; while the districts of Honggu and Xigu (only in the Majiashan area) are classified as two-tone dialect regions. At least for Yuzhong, tone reduction seems to be a recent innovation — Zhang (1990) reports it having four tones and the later fieldwork by Zhang (2009) reports it as having only three tones. To our knowledge, there has been no research at all into the ramifications for the dialects' tonal systems of the fact that so many of their speakers are bidialectal in Beijing-based Putonghua.

Table 1 Reported tone values of Lanzhou Mandarin

	Norman (1988)	Zhang (2009)
Tone 1	31	31
Tone 2	53	53
Tone 3	33	442
Tone 4	24	13

The tonal system of Lanzhou Mandarin investigated in this paper is from Chengguan district, which is very similar to the three-tone system that Norman (1988) gives for Yinchuan, another member of the Lan Yin subgroup. Its contours are illustrated in Figure 2 which shows the normalized pitch-tracks of the word productions of one of the participants in this experiment (using Stanford's 2008 tonetic method). It is worth pointing out that tone 3 (yellow) and tone 4 (green) are extremely similar, though perhaps not completely neutralized. Since all our Lanzhou participants come from the same district, we will refer to this tonal system as simply “Lanzhou Mandarin”.

Figure 2. Normalized pitch tracks for Lanzhou tones: Tone 1 (red), Tone 2 (blue), Tone 3 (yellow), Tone 4 (green)

1.2 Previous research on Mandarin word recognition

Allopena et al. (1998) has shown that word recognition is an incremental process, that is, listeners do not wait for the speaker to complete the last sound of the utterance,

instead, they start analyzing and integrating the acoustic signals as soon as the acoustic input unfolds. The methodology called *visual world paradigm* (VWP) is best suited for studying online word recognition because it provides time-sensitive measurements manifesting the dynamic process about lexical activation and lexical competition. In this paradigm, a device called an eye-tracker records participants' eye gazes and eye movements during the entire course of the experiment. The logic of eyetracking in revealing participant's decision-making process is, if the auditory input activates the lexical representations associated with the picture, participants are expected to spend time fixating on the picture during the unfolding of the auditory input. According to this design, the extent of lexical activation and competition can be assessed by quantifying the probability of fixation to each of these pictures.

Researchers studying Chinese word recognition have used the VWP to show that listeners take tonal information into account as soon as they can. For example, Malins and Joanisse (2010) showed that tonally-divergent *hua4* 'painting' starts losing ground in its competition against the target word *hua1* 'flower' just as early as segmentally-divergent *hui1* 'grey' does.

In the study of bilingualism, VWP has allowed researchers to show how words in one of the listener's languages can interfere with word recognition in their other language. For example, Weber and Cutler (2004) showed that words from their L1 act as serious competitors while the listener is trying to recognize words in their L2, e.g., Dutch *deksel* 'lid' acts as a competitor for a Dutch/English bilingual trying to recognize English *desk*. Ju and Luce (2004) showed that if the phonetic realizations are anomalous enough, even words of an L2 can be competitors in L1 word recognition. In addition, phonological features that are only relevant in listeners' L1 can also affect word recognition of those words' L2 translation equivalents. For example, Shook and Marian (2016) found that Mandarin/English bilinguals performing a translation task would look toward the translation 树 on the screen more quickly if they heard the English word *tree* spoken with a falling pitch (matching *shu4*) than if it was spoken with a different pitch contour. Similarly, Wang et al. (2017) found that the English word *rain* acted as a strong competitor for Mandarin/English bilinguals trying to recognize the English word *feather*, since both are translated as *yu3* in Mandarin, but neither English *fish* (translated to Mandarin *yu2*) nor *wheat* (translated as *gu3*) acted as competitors — once again showing that tonal information is just as effective at eliminating competitors as segmental information is. Above all, even if such tonal information is completely irrelevant to the L2 words, L1's phonological properties can transfer and affect the word processing of L2.

1.3 This study

Based on earlier research, listeners are expected to be able to use tonal information quickly to eliminate competitors during word recognition. They would also be able to use tonal information that exists in words of their first dialect to eliminate

competitors while recognizing words in their second dialect. But for Lanzhou/Putonghua bidialectal listeners, that tonal information is conflicting in the two dialects. This conflict will be the key of this paper in testing what kind of interference there is between the two dialects during word recognition. Concretely, when a Beijing Mandarin listener hears *zhóu* with a rising pitch, they will be able to use tonal information to quickly recognize it as 轴 ‘axis’ *zhou2* and efficiently rule out the word 咒 ‘to curse’ *zhou4* as a serious competitor. But a Lanzhou/Putonghua bidialectal listener may experience interference between their two dialects. When they hear Beijing Mandarin *zhóu* with the rising-pitch, it may activate Lanzhou word 咒 ‘to curse’ *zhou4* as a serious competitor. If there is also interference from “L2” to “L1”², accordingly, hearing Lanzhou Mandarin *zhóu* may also activate the rising-pitch Beijing word 轴 ‘axis’ *zhou2* as a serious competitor. In the VWP, the competition effects can be captured via the relative proportion of eyegaze toward the target relative to its opposite-tone competitor, and perhaps also in slower response times and lower accuracy. The specific hypotheses are laid out as follows.

Hypothesis 1: If Putonghua acts like the “L2” of Lanzhou Mandarin speakers, then their knowledge of Lanzhou Mandarin may interfere with their comprehension of Putonghua. We would predict that Lanzhou speakers listening to Putonghua words will be slower and less accurate on words with disagreeing tones (2 and 4) than on words with agreeing tones (1 and 3). In the eyetracking data, the target word will be more slowly and weakly activated (as reflected in eyegaze toward the target character) if it has a disagreeing tone than if it has an agreeing tone.

Hypothesis 2: If there is the bidirectional interference – Putonghua also interferes in word recognition of Lanzhou Mandarin. Lanzhou participants listening to Lanzhou Mandarin words with disagreeing tones would respond more slowly, less accurately, and show weak and slow activation in their eyegaze than listening to Lanzhou Mandarin words with agreeing tones.

Hypothesis 3: If hypothesis 1 and 2 are both attested, then Beijing participants are expected not to experience the competition from the opposite-tone competitor character since they lack the interference from an additional dialect. Specifically, their response time and accuracy should show no difference regardless of tone disagreement, and their eyetracking data should also display no difference regarding which tone they hear.

2. Method

2.1 Participants

Twenty adult native Mandarin Chinese speakers living in Manitoba were recruited for this experiment. Ten were speakers of the Lanzhou dialect and ten were speakers of the Beijing (or a similar) dialect. The Lanzhou speakers were all from Chengguan

² In this paper, L1 is used in a parallel sense to the dominant dialect that the speaker shows a native level competence, not necessarily the dialect that the speaker has acquired first.

district, Lanzhou City, a district which is reported to have reversed tones (2 and 4) but without having tone 3 and tone 4 neutralized. The speakers in the “Beijing” group were from Beijing or from neighboring northern cities whose dialects fall in the Northeast or Ji Lu subgroup, closely resembling the tonal properties of Putonghua.

Prior to the experiment, participants were asked to self-rate their proficiency in both dialects as well as the frequency in use of each dialect. The proficiency question asked how familiar they were with Putonghua and with Lanzhou dialect, on a scale from 0, meaning “no knowledge of”, to 10, meaning “perfectly fluent in”. The frequency question asked how often they had used each dialect in the previous month, with the score of 0 representing “never”, 0.5 “occasionally”, and 1 “daily”. The results are seen in Table 2, in which both groups were highly proficient in Putonghua and used it daily. Against our expectation, our Lanzhou group showed higher score of proficiency and frequency in Putonghua rather than in Lanzhou Mandarin. But in interpreting the results that follow, it would be accurate to say that the participants in our Lanzhou group are indeed bidialectal, but their dominant dialect is Putonghua and non-dominant dialect is Lanzhou Mandarin.

Table 2 Mean proficiency and frequency of participants

Participants	in Putonghua	in Lanzhou dialect
Proficiency of Lanzhou group	9.7	7.5
Proficiency of Beijing group	10	0.5
Frequency of Lanzhou group	0.95	0.25
Frequency of Beijing group	1	0

2.2. Materials

In this pilot study, written Chinese characters instead of pictures were used in the VWP. Several studies that used written words on the computer screen have shown comparable results, such as McQueen & Viebahn (2007) and Mitterer & Russell (2013) on Dutch, Shook and Marian (2016) on Chinese.

In our eyetracking experiment, each target or distractor characters was drawn from a pool of monosyllabic words. In the stimuli pool, there were 94 pairs of words with the same segmental syllable but with *disagreeing* tones 2 and 4, e.g., 轴 *zhou2*, 咒 *zhou4*. There were 119 pairs of words with the same syllable and *agreeing* tones 1 and 3, e.g., 舟 *zhou1*, 肘 *zhou3*. There were another 340 characters, representing 206 other syllables, that were used only as distractors, e.g., 工 *gong1*, 共 *gong4*. Every character in the pool meets the following three criteria: first, it did not represent an ambiguous syllable (thus excluding, for example, 行 = *xing2/hang2*); second, it did not represent an ambiguous tone (excluding, for example, 空 = *kong1/kong4*); third, it had at least moderately high frequency — the least frequent stimulus ranks 3195th in the list of character frequencies of Da (2005).

To minimize priming effects, the same syllable was never used more than once as a target in the 128 trials of the experiment, and no distractor ever used the same syllable as any of the targets. Every participant was given a different randomized set of targets, competitors, and distractors. Every randomized set of stimuli of the experiment was manipulated into two conditions: 64 target words were first drawn from the pool of “*disagreeing*” pairs (32 with tone 2 and 32 with tone 4). Then 64 target words were drawn from the pool of “*agreeing*” pairs (32 with tone 1 and 32 with tone 3). None of the “agreeing” syllables had already been chosen as a “disagreeing” target.

The target word is further divided into two conditions: half in a *competitive* condition, where the opposite-tone competitor was one of the three other non-target characters appearing on the screen; half were used in a *non-competitive* condition, where the target character appeared with three unrelated distractors. The non-competitive trials were essentially fillers. Such design is for two reasons: first it prevents the participants from finding a pattern where two characters on the screen always shared the same syllable and that the right answer was always one of those two; second, it can reveal whether disagreeing tones are genuinely difficult to process for participants even when a competitor is not on the screen, in parallel to many eyetracking studies with regards to effect of higher cohort competition (more competitor words that share the same initial phonemes), regardless of whether one of those competitors is actually shown on the screen.

The auditory stimuli that the participants heard were recorded by two female speakers, who did not participate in the experiment. Each word was read in the carrier phrase *wo xianzai yao nian ___ zhe ge zi* (我现在要念 ___ 这个字) ‘I now am going to read ___ this word’. The recordings were made using Praat in the sociolinguistics lab at the University of Manitoba and saved as WAV files at a sample rate of 44.1 K and a 16-bit resolution. Later the 432 potential target words were segmented out of the carrier phrase and saved as individual WAV files.

2.3 Procedure

The experiment was run using the experiment software OpenSesame (Mathôt & Theeuwes 2012), using PyGaze to interface with the eyetracker (Dalmaijer et al. 2014). The participants were tested individually. To minimize the influence of being exposed to Putonghua just before the experiment, the instructions of how the experiment proceeds were given in Putonghua to the Beijing group and in Lanzhou Mandarin to the Lanzhou group, since many of the Lanzhou participants may strongly associate written Chinese with Putonghua, which might prime them to be more influenced by Beijing Mandarin tonal patterns. In addition, to minimize the participants’ exposure to written Chinese during the experiment, in the eye-tracking task, which necessarily involved written characters, all participants listened to the block of Lanzhou stimuli before the block of Beijing stimuli.

During the eye-tracking task, participants wore closed-back headphones and sat about 60 cm away from an ASUS laptop with a 14-inch-screen. An Eye Tribe eyetracker was mounted on a short table-top tripod immediately in front of the laptop about 50 cm from the participants' eyes. Since the Eye Tribe was pre-tested to be easily confused by head movement, participants were asked to place their chins on a chin-rest attached to a table-top tripod that was adjusted to a comfortable height. Before any trials began, the Eye Tribe's nine-point calibration procedure was conducted. The sampling rate of the eyetracker was 30 Hz.

Each experiment consists of two blocks, the first half is in Lanzhou Mandarin and the second half is in Putonghua. The first three trials of the eyetracking experiment were practice trials, meaning to familiarize the participants with the task.

In each trial, participants looked at the fixation dot in the centre of an otherwise blank screen. Then four characters appeared in the corners of the screen, as illustrated in Figure 3. One second later, the sound recording of the target word began playing over the headphones, and participants used the mouse to click on the character that matched the word they heard as quickly as possible. Once they clicked, the experiment advanced to the next trial. If participants did not click on any character within four seconds, the trial timed out and the experiment advanced to the next trial.

Figure 3 Example of a computer screen in one trial of the experiment. The four characters (clockwise from the top-left) are *men2*, *zhou4*, *qie4*, *zhou2*. In this example, *zhou4* is the target character that the participant should click on, *zhou2* is the competitor, and *men2* and *qie4* are the unrelated distractors. In non-competitive trials, the competitor *zhou2* would be replaced with a third unrelated distractor.

3. Results

Two types of results were collected: the standard behavioral measurements of accuracy and response times (RTs) out of participant's mouse clicks as well as the eyetracking data. The eyetracker captured the location of participant's eyegaze on the computer screen every 30 ms. All statistical analyses were performed in version 4.0.0 of R (R Core Team 2020). The implicational statistics were constructed based on mixed-effect models using the lme4 package (Bates et al. 2015), and the lmerTest package

provided estimated p-values using the Satterthwaite approximation for degrees of freedom (Kuznetsova et al. 2017).

3.1 Behavioral results

Two kinds of mouse click results were excluded from our analysis. First, the response time was faster than 600 ms after word-onset (0.8% of the data) were eliminated because those clicks happened before the auditory stimulus even began. Second, the responses counted as incorrect when no response was recorded within four seconds when the trial timed out (1.5% of the data).

Table 3 shows the mean accuracy of participants' mouse clicks by tone condition, disagreeing tones (2, 4) and agreeing tones (1, 3), and by auditory stimuli, Beijing stimuli and Lanzhou stimuli. As shown below, Beijing listeners performed almost perfect on their own dialect and Lanzhou listeners were almost as good as Beijing listeners on Beijing stimuli, but Lanzhou listeners' accuracy became worse when they listened to their own dialect, especially even worse on disagreeing tones.

Table 3 Mean accuracy (%) for the mouse click

	Lanzhou stimuli		Beijing stimuli	
	agreeing	disagreeing	agreeing	disagreeing
Lanzhou listeners	90.25	84.81	98.71	94.48
Beijing listeners	81.59	59.37	99.37	98.75

Then the logistic mixed-effects model was constructed to predict the accuracy of Lanzhou listeners' mouse-clicks. In this model, participant and target word were treated as random effects. The fixed effects of dialect, tone disagreement, and competition were added. The statistics predicted that Lanzhou listeners would make an error about 5 times greater if they are responding to a Lanzhou stimulus rather than a Beijing stimulus (i.e., increased log-odds of 1.6, SE = 0.2629, $p < 0.001$); about 2.2 times greater if the tones are disagreeing than if the tones are agreeing (i.e., increased log-odds of 0.8, SE = 0.2390, $p < 0.001$); and about 21 times greater if the opposite-tone competitor is on-screen (i.e., increased log-odds of 3.04, SE = 0.3997, $p < 0.001$). All effects are significant.

To attest if Lanzhou listeners would perform worse accuracy at a Beijing stimulus than Beijing listeners, a logistic mixed-effects model was constructed, predicting the accuracy of the mouse-clicks when participants listens to Beijing stimuli, with participant and target word as random effects. The statistics shows that the odds of a listener making an error are about 10 times greater if the participant is a Lanzhou listener rather than a Beijing listener (i.e., increased log-odds of 2.38, SE = 0.05598, $p < 0.001$), about 6 times greater if the opposite-tone competitor is on-screen (i.e., increased log-odds of 1.84, SE = 0.05512, $p < 0.001$), and about 5 times greater if the tones are disagreeing than if the

tones are agreeing (i.e., increased log-odds of 1.63, SE = 0.04718, $p < 0.001$). Again, all effects are significant.

In terms of RT results, to investigate if Lanzhou listeners experience interference when listening to disagreeing tones, longer RTs serve as the crucial evidence. Table 4 summarizes the mean RTs of all participants' mouse clicks. In hearing Lanzhou stimuli, it seems that Lanzhou listeners' RTs were slower in trials with a disagreeing tone than in trials without. But the mixed-effects model with participant as a random effect predicted that the effect of tone disagreement is non-significant (effect size = 56.82 ms, $df \approx 535.97$, $p = 0.16$).

Table 4 Mean RTs (ms) for the mouse clicks

	Lanzhou stimuli		Beijing stimuli	
	agreeing	disagreeing	agreeing	disagreeing
Lanzhou listeners	1970.02	2027.98	1671.98	1713.27
Beijing listeners	2134.90	2425.71	1847.93	1882.86

However, during post-hoc exploration of the data, a different story surfaced when the effect of proficiency was added. As shown in Table 5, the lowest-proficiency Lanzhou listeners still show no significant effect of tone disagreement on RT (at least in their accurate responses), but the more proficient the listener is, the more their responses are slowed down by a tone disagreement.

Table 5 Coefficients of a mixed-effects model predicting RT, including an interaction between tone disagreement and the listener's self-rated Lanzhou dialect proficiency. (The Lanzhou participants all rated themselves between 6 and 10 out of 10. The "proficiency" variable in this model is their rating minus 6, so that the model intercept corresponds to the lowest-proficiency Lanzhou participants.)

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr ($> t $)
(Intercept)	2005.038	121.364	9.638	16.521	2.16e-08 ***
disagreement	-50.485	63.432	535.658	-0.796	0.426454
proficiency	-55.339	60.655	9.147	-0.912	0.384993
disagreement: proficiency	68.854	31.305	535.019	2.199	0.028270 *

Returning to Table 4, in hearing Beijing stimuli, the RTs of Lanzhou listeners were also slower in trials with a disagreeing tone than in trials without. The estimated effect size for tone disagreement is about the same as it was for Lanzhou stimuli (effect size = 55.14 ms, $df \approx 298.34$), now with a marginal p -value of .069. (This model is not

improved by adding either proficiency in either the Lanzhou dialect or Putonghua as predictors.)

Lastly, to test if there is a difference between two groups in processing a Beijing stimulus, the corresponding model of coefficients predicting Beijing listener's RTs are constructed, with the same predictors as the Lanzhou-listener model. Unlike the model for Lanzhou listeners, the estimated effect size for tone disagreement is smaller (31.38 ms, $df \approx 293.86$) and it has a non-significant p-value (0.79). (This model is not improved by adding either proficiency in or the Lanzhou listener as predictors.)

3.2 Eyetracking results

In typical eyetracking studies, the incorrect behavioral responses were excluded because they were treated as evidence that the participant was not paying attention during that trial, but in this study, due to the conflicting tone information between the two dialects, the choice clicking to the wrong character is much expected. Moreover, the whole point of eyetracking is to examine which candidates the listener is seriously considering before they have completely made up their mind, so it is largely irrelevant which word they eventually choose and whether that choice is correct or not. Therefore, the incorrect trials were not excluded from our eyetracking analysis. The eyetracking analysis excluded one Lanzhou participant due to equipment failure.³

Figure 4 illustrates the eyetracking results showing that Lanzhou listeners' fixation proportion toward the target, the competitor, and each of the two distractors evolves in the time immediately following the onset of the auditory word. The vertical dotted line in each panel indicates the median behavioural response time for that condition.

The top two panels of Figure 4 show bidialectal participants' fixation when they listen to Beijing stimuli in real time. Their performance is much as expected as a monodialectal Beijing listener, that is, their eyegaze toward the target character peaks early and strongly for both agreeing and disagreeing tones (though slightly later and less strongly for the disagreeing tones); their eyegaze toward the opposite-tone competitor is barely dramatically more than that of the unrelated distractor characters. But in the small minority of very slow responses (i.e. past the point of the dotted line), especially to disagreeing tones, a considering amount of increase occurs in their eyegaze toward the competitor character, indicating the Lanzhou listeners are having a second-guess about their earlier word identification.

In contrast, in the bottom two panels of Figure 4, the situation is different when Lanzhou participants are listening to Lanzhou stimuli. In terms of the tracks indicating their eyegaze toward the target, the participants are less decisive than they are in listening

³ The equipment failure was not due to the eyetracker, but to something on the laptop that caused random long delays between some trials, which allowed the eyetracker to drift out of calibration in fewer trials than for other participants.

Beijing stimuli, reflected by lower fixation proportion and later peaks. As for their eyegaze toward the competitor character, the opposite-toned competitor shows serious competition against the target character regardless in agreeing tones or disagreeing tones. Crucially for this paper, if we look closely at the trials where they listen to a disagreeing tone (bottom-right), the competition is much stronger.

Figure 4 Gazes for Lanzhou listeners in competitive trials. The dotted line indicates the median response time for mouse clicks in each condition

Figure 5 shows the corresponding evolution in eyegaze for Beijing listeners. When they are listening to their own dialect, the activation to the target character is quickly and strongly; the low and dying track of the competitor reveals that they are not affected by the opposite-toned competitor as expected since they do not have such tone conflict. Their eyegaze behavior when listening to Lanzhou stimuli, unsurprisingly, also confirms with hypothesis 3 laid out in the beginning of this paper. With the fact that tone 1 and tone 3 are comparable in the two dialects, they are able to correctly activate the target character, but due to their unfamiliarity to Lanzhou Mandarin, the activation to the target is slow and weak and they do not completely rule out considering the opposite-toned competitor as a candidate. As for disagreeing conditions, because of the inversion of tone 2 and tone 4 in their pitch contours between the two dialects, they treat the competitor as the target settling on the “incorrect” one.

Figure 5 Gazes for Beijing listeners in competitive trials. The dotted line indicates the median response time for mouse clicks in each condition

These informal observations about the time-courses of the word recognition competition can be confirmed statistically. For eyetracking analysis, the variable of *target proportion* was computed for each trial, which denotes between 500 ms and 1900 ms what proportion of the eyegazes are directed toward the target character.

Table 6 gives the coefficients of the best mixed-effects model predicting the proportion of gazes toward the target for Lanzhou listeners responding to Lanzhou stimuli, with participant as a random effect. The coefficients tell us that listeners spend 5% less of the window looking toward the target when an opposite-tone competitor with an agreeing tone (1 or 3) is on the screen, and that listeners also spend 6% less of the window looking toward the target when it has a disagreeing tone (2 or 4) than when it has an agreeing tone, even when the opposite-tone competitor is absent from the screen. Adding an interaction between on-screen competition and tone disagreement does not result in a better model. (The approximated *p*-value of the interaction is 0.47 and both the Akaike Information Criterion and the Bayesian Information Criterion prefer the model without the interaction.) Thus, beyond the sum of 5% and 6%, there seems to be no additional disadvantage for trials that use *both* a “disagreeing” tone target *and* an on-screen opposite-tone competitor.

Table 6 Coefficients of a mixed-effects model for target proportion, Lanzhou listeners hearing Lanzhou stimuli

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr (> t)
(Intercept)	0.40121	0.02611	15.365	5.83e-09 ***
disagreeing	-0.05951	0.01482	-4.015	6.75e-05 ***
competing	-0.04971	0.01482	-3.354	0.000851 ***

Consistent with the post-hoc analysis for RTs considering the effect of listener's proficiency, the mixed effect model of Lanzhou listeners' eyegazes also shows a significant interaction between tone disagreement and proficiency. The coefficient of the interaction is -0.2880 ($t = -2.597$, $df \approx 562.02$, $p = 0.00965$), which means, the more proficient the listener is, the less they look at the target when it's in a disagreeing tone.

As for the prediction to the target proportion of Lanzhou participants listening to Beijing stimuli, there is no significant effect of on-screen competitor or of tone disagreement. The coefficients of the interaction model where the interaction between the tone disagreement and on-screen competition has a marginal significance (effect size = -0.056, $SD = 0.033345$, $t = 564.00$, $p = 0.09$), indicating they might look 5% less toward the target word if it is in tone 2 or tone 4 and the opposite-tone competitor is on screen.

As for the last question if the bidialectal listeners significantly differ from the monodialectal listeners when processing Putonghua words, unsurprisingly, Beijing participants listening to Beijing stimuli are not affected by tone disagreement. But they are still confused a little when there is an on-screen competitor (maybe a little less confused than Lanzhou listeners are). Adding an interaction between on-screen competition and tone disagreement does not result in a better model. (The approximated p -value of the interaction is 0.25 and both the Akaike Information Criterion and the Bayesian Information Criterion prefer the model without the interaction.)

4. Discussion

Tying the results to the questions addressed at the beginning of this paper, here below is the brief discussion.

Question 1: do words with conflicting tones interfere word recognition of the Lanzhou/Putonghua bidialectal listeners?

Yes, however, not entirely or ubiquitously.

In terms of handling Lanzhou words, the bidialectal listeners are apparently affected by their knowledge for knowing two dialects in which two tones are diametrically opposed. Behaviorally, a significant effect of disagreeing tone is found in their accuracy to Lanzhou stimuli. In other words, they make more mistakes when they hear a word that is in a disagreeing tone (2 and 4), although they make even more mistakes when the opposite-tone competitor is also present on the computer screen. Even though there is no significant effect of disagreeing tone in the planned analysis of RTs, the post-hoc analysis reveals a significant interaction effect between tone condition and

listener's proficiency – the more proficient the listener is in Lanzhou Mandarin, the more likely they are slowed by words with disagreeing tones. The eyetracking results also strongly support the interference of tone disagreement on Lanzhou word-recognition. Firstly, the activation levels of the target words are weaker and slower to grow. Secondly, Lanzhou listeners are worse at activating the target word when an opposite-tone competitor is on the screen. More importantly, they are worse at activating words that have disagreeing tones even when the opposite-tone competitor is not present.

However, our bidialectal listeners are unaffected by such conflicting tone properties when hearing Putonghua words. Behaviorally, they were pretty much alike Beijing monodialectal listeners when hearing Putonghua words – demonstrating high accuracy and fast response times regardless of tone. Some Lanzhou participants are somewhat less accurate than the typical Beijing listener, again regardless of tone. But all of the Lanzhou participants are faster and at least as accurate when listening to Putonghua words as they are when listening to Lanzhou words.⁴ Their eyetracking results also confirm that there is no effect of tone disagreement.

Above all, the conflicting tones interfere the bidialectal listeners only when they listen to Lanzhou stimuli but not to Putonghua stimuli. The plausible conclusion from this is that the bidialectal participants in this study were actually dominant in Lanzhou Mandarin. Despite a few of them may be considered as almost balanced bilinguals (equally competent in both dialects), most are dominant in Putonghua and treat Lanzhou Mandarin as their “L2”. This imbalance is also reflected in their own self-ratings of proficiency in the two dialects. Even though the Lanzhou participants are less proficient in Lanzhou Mandarin and demonstrated worse performance on recognizing Lanzhou words, this does not negate their eligibility of being real bidialectal – unlike Beijing monodialectal listeners, they usually are able to eventually choose the correct target.

Question 2: Is this interference unidirectional or bidirectional?

This study has not found strong evidence for the bidirectional interference. Instead, the interference is unidirectional and it is Putonghua that interferes with their Lanzhou Mandarin rather than the other way around. This result is consistent with a model where phonological information from the bidialectal listener's dominant dialect (here Putonghua) can interfere with word recognition in their non-dominant dialect (here, Lanzhou Mandarin). As manifested by non-significant or marginally significant effects of tone disagreement during word recognition, a bidialectal listener's word recognition in

⁴ The Lanzhou participants were also faster overall than our Beijing participants, even when listening to Beijing stimuli. This may just be an irrelevant difference due to a small sample size — perhaps the Lanzhou participants in our sample happened to be somewhat more biased toward speed in the speed-accuracy tradeoff than the Beijing participants were (which, if true, could also explain why their accuracy is also somewhat lower than that of the Beijing participants). Or it might be that the Beijing listeners got so confused by the unfamiliar stimuli in the initial Lanzhou block that they remained uncharacteristically cautious throughout the second block of Beijing stimuli.

their dominant dialect seems not strongly affected by phonological properties of their non-dominant dialect.

However, the post-doc RT analysis seems to suggest a possible bidirectional interference – the bidialectal listener’s sensitivity toward tone disagreement is stronger if they are more proficient in Lanzhou Mandarin. In this study, the sampled participants inevitably turned out to be Putonghua-dominant for three reasons. Firstly, many of them were university students, which means they have been strongly influenced by Putonghua over several years of education. Secondly, they have lived in Winnipeg for years where the Chinese community is predominantly speaking Putonghua and Cantonese. Lastly, some participants had always had Lanzhou Mandarin as their second dialect. Due to higher social prestige associated with use of Putonghua, for example, some participants were asked to exclusively speak Putonghua with their family at home but began learning Lanzhou Mandarin only later at school as a form of covert prestige getting along better with other students. For future research, the participants whose dominant dialect is Lanzhou Mandarin should be recruited. Preferably, if the repeating study could be conducted in Lanzhou City, it would allow us to see a wider range of proficiencies in Lanzhou Mandarin, and I assume that the most proficient of those Lanzhou Mandarin speakers would reveal the bidirectional interference in accordance with the original hypothesis.

Question 3: Are Mandarin native speakers really a homogeneous group?

Probably no. If we only compare the behavioral results and the overall eyetracking activation patterns, both groups seem to be considerably alike when hearing Putonghua words – showing no significant difference to words regardless it is in a disagreeing tone or not. However, if we examine their gaze proportion closer, even though there is no significant effect of tone disagreement found from either group of the participants, the fine-grained details on the activation toward the target and the competitor show the subtle difference in their online processing. Unlike Beijing participants, Lanzhou listeners apparently demonstrated sensitivity to disagreeing tones when hearing Putonghua/Beijing Mandarin stimuli (cf. the top two panels of Figure 4 and 5). Especially in the condition of disagreeing tones in those trials that took longer than the median RTs (i.e. past the dotted lines), Beijing listeners do not show the competition effect where the activation toward the competitor soon dies out since the median RT and never rises again. On the contrary, Lanzhou listeners obviously experience a *late lexical competition* indicated by the late gradual growth in gaze proportion toward the competitor around 1500 ms and this growth continues till the end and never dies down.

Although the Lanzhou listeners’ offline behavioral performance is quite comparable with that of Beijing listeners, their eyetracking results reveal the subtle effect of disagreeing tones. The Putonghua-dominant bidialectal participants in this study show the subtle interference from tone disagreement, suggesting that even the highly proficient Putonghua speakers may demonstrate inter-speaker variations in their online performance according to their other language experience. This supports the concern raised in the

beginning of this paper, that is, we should at least be moderately cautious in terms of participant recruitment and not ruthlessly lump Mandarin speakers as a homogenous group without considering their language experience.

5. Conclusion

This paper uses the visual world paradigm to investigate if the Putonghua/Lanzhou bidialectal speakers would experience interference during word recognition resulting from the fact that tone 2 and tone 4 have reversed pitch contours between the two dialects. Despite of the fact that Lanzhou participants were not dominant in the dialect we expected, the compelling evidence from eyetracking and behavioural accuracy, as well as a post-hoc effect on response time among the more proficient Lanzhou speakers, all point to the conclusion that their dominant dialect (Putonghua) interferes with word recognition in their non-dominant dialect (Lanzhou Mandarin).

As a novel study looking into bilingual/bidialectal speakers whose both languages are tonal, this paper adds supporting empirical evidence to the account of language coactivation illustrating how lexical competition unfolds in two tonal dialects. In addition, as a representative group, Lanzhou/Putonghua participants have demonstrated the often simplified (if not ignored) fact that the overwhelming number of Mandarin L1 speakers are bidialectal in nature. Lastly, this paper points out the correlation between bidialectal speaker's proficiency in each dialect and their susceptibility to the interference from the mismatching phonological properties across two dialects. All in all, future linguistics research should be cautious and need to consider the potential interference that may come from a bilingual's L2 phonological properties.

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汉语第三人称显性代词加工实证研究

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本文报告母语者消解汉语第三人称显性和零形代词的两个实验。实验一采用离线的句子判断任务，考察在回指和逆回指加工中显性代词和零代词的共指，结果发现，在回指加工中显性代词有很大的灵活性：既可与同一句中的名词短语共指，也可不与其共指；在逆回指加工中显性代词不与同一句中的名词共指。实验二为自定步速阅读实验，考察显性代词在线回指和逆回指加工中的时间进程。结果在两种加工模式中都没有发现性别不一致效应，但是性别不一致效应的消失是由不同的原因造成的。

1. 引言

在语篇理解过程中准确快速地识解指代成分，无论对母语者还是二语学习者都是至关重要的能力，因此代词的研究一直是语言学家和心理学家研究的热点问题。代词的理解依赖于对语篇中代词和先行词之间共指关系的准确理解，这就等于说代词必须从其先行词得到指称认同。因此，代词的加工就是指加工者遇到代词时，从语境中的先行词获取意义的过程(Rigalleau et al. 2004)。代词的加工分为回指加工和逆回指加工。回指加工是指代词从前面提到的先行词获取意义，这类代词被称为前照应代词(Quirk & Greenbaum 1978)。与此相反，逆回指加工指的是代词从后面的先行词获取意义，这类代词称为后照应代词(Quirk & Greenbaum 1978; Carden 1982)。

以往对代词的研究大部分关注英语代词(详述参见 Garnham 2001)，对汉语代词的研究相对较少(Chen et al. 2000, Yang et al. 1999、2003、2001, 李榕 2014, 李榕等 2016)。鉴于汉语中零代词的广泛使用，这些关于汉语代词的研究大都聚焦汉语第三人称零代词相对于显性代词的回指理解和加工，探讨汉语代词逆回指加工的研究屈指可数(Zhao 2014, Sun & Kennison 2015)。本文将研究较少的逆回指加工列入考察范围，探讨汉语母语者对汉语第三人称显性代词的回指加工和逆回指加工。

语言学家发现(王宗炎 1994, 王灿龙 2000、2006, 许余龙 2007) 英语代词即可以回指同一句中的名词，如句(1)，也可以后指同一句中的名词，见句

(2)，该名词被称为先行词。而汉语代词只能指代前面提到的名词，如句(3)，不能后指同一句中的名词，如句(4)。相同下标表示共指。

- (1) a. Mike_i scold his_i brother.
b. When Tom_i watched TV, he_i ate a big apple.
- (2) a. His_i brother scold Mike_i.
b. When he_i watched TV, Tom_i ate a big apple.
- (3) a. 迈克_i批评了他_i的哥哥。
b. 迈克_i看电视的时候，他_i吃了一个大苹果。
- (4) a. *他_i的哥哥批评了迈克_i。
b. *他_i看电视的时候，汤姆_j吃了一个大苹果。

Huang (1982) 认为汉语代词不能后指同一句中的名词是因为汉语代词遵循严格的结构制约，见句(5)。

- (5) 代词不可以循环 c-统领 (cyclic c-command) 它的先行词
循环 c-统领: A 循环 c-统领 B 当且仅当:
a. A c-统领 B; 或者
b. C 是统领 A 的最小的分支节点 (NP 或者 CP), 但不立即受另一个分支节点统领, 那么 C c-统领 B。

(Huang 1982: 394)

然而针对这一问题的心理学实证研究结果一直存在争议。Zhao (2014) 使用图片判断任务，让汉语母语者和二语者根据所见图片给相应的句子评分（如句(6)和句(7)）。结果显示回指加工中，显性代词共指的评分大于非共指，逆回指加工中显性代词的共指评分明显小于非共指评分，汉语母语者和二语者允许显性代词在回指加工中的共指理解和逆回指加工中的不共指理解，而对于回指加工中的非共指理解表现出一定程度的不确定性。

- (6) 老鲁看电视的时候，Ø/他抱着一个球。
(7) Ø/他看电视的时候，老鲁抱着一个球。

可是 Sun and Kennison (2015) 使用句子判断任务所做的实证研究得出截然不同的结果，超过 70% 的受试认为无论回指还是逆回指，代词都可以和同一句中的名词共指。在这项研究中，受试阅读完句子(8)之后，判断句子中的加粗体的两个动作是否是同一个人做的，然后从句(9)中的两个选项中做出选择。

- (8) 男学生**认出疑犯**之后，在/他/她**挥动双手**示意警察
在Ø/他/她**认出疑犯**之后，男学生**挥动双手**示意警察
- (9) 这两件事是同一个人做的么？ 是 不是

造成此实验结果一个原因可能是，选项为“是（共指）”或“不是（非共指）”的二元对立选择，受试不得不从中做出选择，即使他们认为共指的可能性不是很大，因而无法准确反映被试做出选择时的确定性程度。另一个原因可能是因为受试的注意力完全集中在加粗的两个动作上，而一个人完全可以接连完成句子中的两个动作，因此受试很可能在阅读句子的过程中，根本没有考虑代词和名词是否共指的问题。为了澄清这一问题，本文将采用更直接的代词指代判断任务的离线研究和自定步速阅读的在线研究相结合的方法，考察汉语第三人称显性代词在回指加工和逆回指加工中的共指现象及其背后的隐含原因。

综上所述，本文讨论汉语显性代词在回指加工和逆回指加工模式下两个方面的问题：

- 1) 不同加工模式下代词是否可以和同一句中的名词共指？
- 2) 不同加工模式下是否存在性别不一致效应？

2. 研究方法

2.1. 实验一：离线句子判断，确定代词先行词

2.1.1. 被试

一所中国大学的 28 名非外语专业学生（女生 20 人）参加本实验。他们均在中国出生长大，没有出国经历，作为实验报酬他们将获得相应的教分。

2.1.2. 实验材料

24 组实验测试材料由一个复杂句构成，如（10），在回指加工的实验材料中，从句的主语是典型的中文人名（男性人名和女性人名各占一半），主句的主语是第三人称零代词或者显性代词。我们包含零代词的条件是为了保证这项研究选择的受试允许零代词出现在从句的主语位置和主句的主语位置。如果被试根本不接受零代词出现在上述的位置，那么正确理解实验材料是不可能的。在逆回指加工的材料中，从句的主语是第三人称零代词或者显性代词，主句的主语是典型的中文人名（男性人名和女性人名各占一半）。句中的代词始终与人名性别一致。为了保证实验材料中的中文人名具有典型的性别特征，排除性别典型性不同带来的干扰因素，我们从选取了 10 名未参加其它实验的大学本科被试对 90 个中文人名的性别典型性按照李克特 5 点量表来判断，1 代表非常典型的男性人名，5 代表典型的女性人名。最后确定一份包含 44 个男性人名和 44 个女性人名的名

2.1.4. 数据分析

如果被试判断代词指代同一句子中的名词，我们计为共指，反之计为非共指，共指百分比数据是两分 (binary) 数据 (“共指” 和 “非共指”)，因此采用 lme4 包中的 glmer 函数的混合效应模型来拟合数据 (见 Baayen et al. 2008)，优先使用具有最大的随机效应的模型，只有在未拟合的情况下，模型才会被简化 (Barr et al. 2013)，拟合后的回归模型如下：

Mixedmodel: glmer(Percentage ~ (Con1+1|Subj) + (1|Item) + Con1*Con2, data=dat, family=binomial)

其中 Percentage 是被试的共指百分比，为因变量。自变量是实验的条件即代词加工模式 (回指/逆回指) 和代词类型 (零代词/显性代词) 也是混合效应模型的固定因素。被试和测试材料是混合效应模型的随机因素。

表3中列出了估计值、标准误差和固定效应的z值，我们用蒙特卡罗马尔科夫链计算了p值(pvals.fnc function, Bates & Maechler, 2010)。此外，我们使用 lme4 R 软件包 (Bates et al. 2015, version 1.1-8) 对选项评分进行了混合效应回归模型 (LMER) (Baayen 2008, Baayen et al. 2008, Jaeger 2008) 分析。我们对零代词和显性代词条件下的选项评分分别进行了分析。实验条件代词加工模式 (回指/逆回指) 和选项 (共指/不共指) 以及两者之间的交互为固定因素，被试与测试材料以及两种效应之间的随机斜率为随机因素。分析得到了每种固定效应和相互作用的系数、标准误差和 t 值。对于线性模型而言，如果t的绝对值超过2，则该系数在0.05处被认为是显著的 (Baayen 2008)。

2.1.5. 实验结果和分析

图1 实验一 平均共指百分比 (标准误)

表 1 实验一混合效应回归模型分析结果

	估计值	标准误差	z值	p值
截距	0.903	0.237	3.815	0.000136***
加工模式	0.822	0.147	5.582	2.38e-08***
代词类型	1.828	0.154	11.865	<2e-16***
加工模式x代词类型	-0.189	0.145	-1.304	0.192

图 1 列出每种条件下的共指百分比。表 1 列出了共指百分比的统计分析的结果，混合效应的模型拟合结果显示加工模式主效应显著 ($p < 0.001$)，表明代词回指的共指百分比显著高于逆回指 (73.51 > 50.89)。并且代词类型主效应显著 ($p < 0.001$)，表明零代词的共指百分比显著高于显性代词 (89.88 > 34.53)。

表 2 确定性评分 (标准差)

	共指	非共指
前指-零代词	4.58 (0.65)	3.88 (0.83)
前指-显性代词	4.22 (0.86)	3.96 (0.11)
后指-零代词	4.56 (0.65)	4 (1.02)
后指-显性代词	3.86 (0.99)	4.31 (0.83)

表 2 列出了各种条件下共指的确信性评分和非共指的确信性评分，表 3 和表 4 分别列出零代词和显性代词条件下的选项评分的统计分析结果。

表 3 零代词条件下的混合效应回归模型分析结果

	估计值	标准误差	t值
截距	4.30	0.098	43.685
加工模式	0.009	0.061	0.148
选项	-0.262	0.063	-4.14*
加工模式x选项	-0.001	0.061	-0.032

零代词条件下，选项主效应显著 ($t = -4.14$)，共指的评分高于非共指的评分，表明无论回指还是逆回指加工，对于零代词而言，共指选项的确信性大于非共指选项 ($p < 0.001$)。

表4 显性代词条件下基于线性混合效应分析结果

	估计值	标准误差	t值
截距	4.80	0.100	40.627
加工模式	0.010	0.050	0.194
选项	0.048	0.053	0.899
加工模式x选项	-0.199	0.052	-3.843*

显性代词条件下，尽管没有发现显著的主效应，我们在 R (r core team 2018) 中使用 tukey 测试 (multcomp 软件包的 glht 功能: Hothorn et al. 2008; version 1.4-1) 进行了配对比较。分析结果显示在逆回指-显性代词的条件下共指选项的确定性明显小于非共指选项 (3.86 < 4.31)。而回指-显性代词条件下共指和非共指的确定程度差别不大 (4.22 vs. 3.96)。

离线句子判断实验表明零代词的共指百分比明显高于显性代词。这说明无论在回指加工还是逆回指加工中，同一句中的名词都是零代词默认先行语。零代词条件下，共指的评分明显高于非共指评分也证实了这一点。显性代词的共指百分比在回指加工中高于逆回指加工，汉语显性代词在回指加工中具有很大的灵活性，共指百分比略高于随机水平 51.79%，共指和非共指的确定性差别很小，说明显性代词在回指加工中既可以指代同一句的名词也可以指代句子之外的名词。而显性代词在逆回指加工中的共指百分比仅为 17.26%，这说明逆回指加工中，显性代词通常不与同一句子中的名词共指，并且共指选项的确定性明显小于非共指选项，表明显性代词的逆回指加工受循环 c-统领的制约，支持 Zhao (2014) 的研究结果，不支持 Sun and Kennison (2015) 的研究结果。

2.2. 实验二：自定步速阅读任务

2.2.1. 受试

我们从一所本科院校招募了 30 名非英语专业学生（女生 15 人）参加本实验，这些被试都没有参加过实验一。他们获得相应的教分作为报酬。

2.2.2. 实验材料和设计

40 组在线实验材料均由两个句子构成，第一个句子大部分来源于实验一中包含显性代词的复杂句，从句和主句中的主语和代词性别匹配或不匹配，第二个句子是一个简单句，句子的主语为中文人名。实验材料中包含第二个句子的目的是当第一个句子中的代词和名词性别不匹配时，给代词提供一个潜在的合法先行词。

本实验为 2（加工模式）x 2（性别一致性）实验。一半的实验材料里的代词为男性代词“他”，另一半实验材料里的代词为女性代词“她”。性别匹配和不匹配

的句子唯一的区别在于句中人名的性别不同，并且人名字数相同。为了避免产生任何影响代词和句中主语共指解释的语义偏见，第一个句子中的两个分句经过精心挑选，保证两个分句中的事件可以由同一个施事者完成，也可以由两个不同的施事者完成。同时，为了保证每个句子中的代词都有唯一的合法先行词，在逆回指加工条件下，第二句的主语总是与代词的性别相匹配，并充当语法先行词。在回指加工，性别匹配的条件下，第二句主语的性别与代词的性别不匹配，因为代词和主句主语之间可能存在共指关系，而在回指加工性别不匹配的条件下，第二句的主语的性别在与代词的性别相同。

12 (a) 回指-性别一致

张丽丽/写作业/的时候，她/吃光了/桌上/所有的/零食。李海军/并没/生气。

(b) 回指-性别不一致

王志勇/写作业/的时候，她/吃光了/桌上/所有的/零食。王雪梅/并不/满足。

(c) 逆回指指-性别一致

她/写作业/的时候，张丽丽/吃光了/桌上/所有的/零食。王雪梅/并没/生气。

(d) 逆回指-性别不一致

她/写作业/的时候，王志勇/吃光了/桌上/所有的/零食。王雪梅/并没/生气。

2.2.3. 实验步骤

本实验我们采用的是移动窗口逐词掩蔽范式，40个实验句和100个干扰句由Linger程序随机呈现。实验在不受打扰的安静环境中进行。被试使用一台运行Linger软件(麻省理工学院 Doug Rohde 开发)的 windows 电脑进行测试。句子以标准的非累积性逐字移动窗口模式呈现(Just et al. 1982)。首先被试会看到一行或者两行破折号，这些破折号会覆盖句子里所有的词语和标点符号，但在词语之间留下空格。当被试按下空格键，第一个词语就会出现。之后每按一次空格键，一个新的词语就会出现并且之前的词语又被破折号覆盖。每个句子之后都会出现一个是非问答理解问题。回答这个问题需按“F”来代表是或者“J”来代表否。

为了掩盖研究的主要目的和减少有意识阅读策略的风险，是非问答理解问题从未针对代词的指称问题。被试根据要求以自然的速度阅读句子，并尽可能准确地回答理解问题。为了让被试熟悉实验操作，所有的指导语都是汉语的，并且实验正式开始之前设置了6个练习句。

2.2.4. 数据分析

我们使用lme4 R软件包(Bates et al. 2015, version 1.1-8)对阅读时间进行了混合效应回归模型(LMER)(Baayen 2008, Baayen et al. 2008, Jaeger 2008)分析。实验条件代词加工模式(回指/逆回指)和性别(一致/不一致)以及两者之间的交互

为固定因素，被试与测试材料的截距以及两种因素之间的随机斜率为随机因素。分析得到了每种固定效应和相互作用的系数、标准误差和t值。对于线性模型而言，如果t的绝对值超过2，则该系数在0.05处被认为是显著的 (Baayen 2008)。

2.2.5. 实验结果和分析

表 5 列出了每种实验条件下平均阅读理解准确率。是非问答题的平均准确率为 86.17%。各条件下准确率之间没有显著差异。表 6 和图 2、图 3 为反应时的实验结果。表 7 为关键第二分句各区域的统计分析结果。

表 5 每种条件下的平均阅读理解准确率

条件	准确率	
	平均值	标准误
回指		
性别一致	84.0	2.1
性别不一致	84.7	2.1
逆回指		
性别一致	87.3	1.9
性别不一致	88.7	1.8

表 6 11 个区域的平均阅读时间（毫秒）

区域	回指加工		逆回指加工	
	性别一致	性别不一致	性别一致	性别不一致
1	590.1 (21.5)	596.7 (26.5)	442.1 (8.6)	456.0 (11.2)
2	506.1 (17.60)	501.2 (14.4)	438.6 (12.7)	427.6 (10.8)
3	481.7 (16.3)	457.4 (13.3)	463.5 (14.2)	441.8 (13.0)
4	454.4 (14.1)	436.0 (11.2)	508.6 (17.2)	510.4 (18.0)
5	391.2 (8.3)	406.7 (8.1)	465.6 (11.0)	445.3 (10.3)
6	386.4 (8.2)	396.5 (8.2)	421.3 (9.7)	402.6 (8.5)
7	396.3 (8.5)	414.1 (19.3)	429.9 (10.2)	409.3 (8.6)
8	445.9 (12.5)	443.3 (11.8)	443.6 (11.8)	432.2 (11.3)
9	503.6 (14.1)	491.5 (14.1)	473.7 (11.0)	470.2 (11.7)
10	434.2 (8.6)	422.4 (7.0)	433.0 (7.8)	421.0 (7.7)
11	510.5 (13.4)	512.6 (13.6)	501.1 (12.9)	463.0 (9.8)

回指加工的条件

如图 2 和表 6 所示，回指加工中各区域的平均阅读时间差异不显著。即使在关键第二个分句各区域，有没有发现任何性别主效应和由此引起的交互作用（见表 7）。

表 7 主句（R4 到 R8）的混合效应模型拟合结果

区域	估计值	标准误差	t值
4			
截距	6.055	0.051	118.38
加工模式	-0.040	0.011	-3.749*
性别	-0.007	0.011	-0.629
加工模式 x 性别	-0.004	0.011	-0.362
5			
截距	5.990	0.039	155.375
加工模式	-0.058	0.009	-6.692*
性别	0.000	0.009	0.042
加工模式 x 性别	0.023	0.009	1.630
6			
截距	5.933	0.039	151.108
加工模式	-0.022	0.009	-2.688*
性别	-0.002	0.009	-0.219
加工模式 x 性别	0.013	0.009	1.616
7			
截距	5.958	0.043	137.974
加工模式	-0.018	0.012	-1.557
性别	0.002	0.008	0.282
加工模式 x 性别	0.020	0.008	2.450
8			
截距	6.008	0.045	134.768
加工模式	0.006	0.010	0.638
性别	0.006	0.010	-0.592
加工模式 x 性别	0.007	0.010	0.695

逆回指加工条件

第一个分句各区域（1-3）的阅读时间没有显著差异，从关键的第二个主语（区域 4）之后一个词语（区域 5）的位置开始，性别一致条件下的平均阅读时间

比性别不一致条件下的阅读时间长（区域 5：性别一致，465.6ms；性别不一致，445.3ms，区域 6：性别一致，421.3ms；性别不一致，402.6ms，区域 7：性别一致，429.9ms；性别不一致，409.3ms），但是这些差异没有达到任何显著的主效应。其余的区域的阅读时间也没有任何显著效应和交互作用。从区域 4 开始出现的加工模式主效应显著是由于第二分句主语位置上的词语数量的不同造成的（回指：代词为一个字；逆回指：人名为三个字），见图 3 和表 6。

张丽丽/王志勇₁ 写作业₂的时候₃，她₄吃光了₅桌上₆所有的₇零食₈。
李海军/王雪梅₉ 并没/不₁₀ 生气/满足₁₁。

图 2 实验二回指加工条件下的平均阅读时间（毫秒）

她₁写作业₂的时候₃，张丽丽/王志勇₄吃光了₅桌上₆所有的₇零食₈。
王雪梅₉ 并没₁₀ 生气₁₁。

图 3 实验二逆回指加工条件下的平均阅读时间（毫秒）

3. 讨论

本研究主要考察了汉语第三人称显性代词在回指加工和逆回指加工中是否可以和同一句中的名词共指的问题。离线加工中, 显性代词在回指加工的共指百分比为 51.79%, 表明显性代词非常灵活, 既可以指代同一句中的名词, 也可以指代句子之外语境中的其他人。在逆回指加工中, 显性代词的共指百分比仅为 17.26%, 表明显性代词通常不能用来共指同一句中的名词。无论是在回指加工中和逆回指加工中, 零代词都是句中名词的默认先行词, 共指百分比分别为 95.23%和 84.52%。这一点支持 Zhao (2014) 中汉语母语者的研究结果, 不支持 Sun and Shelia (2015) 的实验结果。

在线加工的实验结果基本上与离线加工的实验结果是一致的。无论在回指加工中和还是逆回指加工中阅读时间在性别一致和性别不一致的条件下没有显著差异, 也就是说在回指加工和逆回指加工中都没有发现显著的性别不一致效应。但是造成这一结果的原因却各不相同, 下面我们从代词加工过程的角度来分析缺少性别不一致效应的原因。

代词回指加工中没有发现性别不一致效应是因为汉语是空主语语言, 其代词体系中既有显性代词又有零代词, 从句的主语名词是零代词的默认先行语词。显性代词具有很大的灵活性, 共指百分比仅为 51.79%。也就是说显性代词既可以指代同一句中的先行语, 也可以指代语境中的先行语, 在指代的倾向性上没有太大差异。

代词的共指消解一般分为链接和诊断两个阶段 (Garrod 1994, Garrod & Sanford 1982, Sturt 2003)。当被试读到 (13) 句中主句主语位置的代词“她”时, 迅速从记忆中提取或激活从句中主语名词, 并建立两者之间链接; 在诊断阶段, 如果激活的从句的主语名词 (张丽丽) 与代词性别一致时, 确定共指关系, 代词消解结束。如果提取或激活的主语名词 (王志勇) 与代词性别不一致时, 共指立即被排除, 代词消解也随之结束, 因为汉语中句中的主语名词是零代词的默认先行语, 显性代词有接近 50%的几率可以指代句子之外语境中的先行语。因此无论性别匹配与否, 在阅读时间上不存在差异。同为空主语语言的意大利语种的显性代词也具有一定的灵活性和不稳定性 (Carminati 2002)。

英语代词回指加工中发现显著的性别不一致效应, 也就是说性别不一致时, 阅读时间长, (Kennison 2003, Kennison et al. 2009) 可能是因为英语中只有显性代词 (Haegeman & Ihsane, 2001), 句中的主语名词就是显性代词的默认先行语, 因此在诊断阶段, 当激活的主语名词和代词性别不一致时, 需要更多的阅读时间重新整合句子。

(13) 张丽丽/王志勇写作业的时候, 她吃光了桌上所有的零食。李海军并不生气/王雪梅还不高兴。

在逆回指加工中，没有发现性别不一致效应，是因为受到句法约束（循环 c-统领）的制约，显性代词不可以与主句的主语名词共指，因此处在这个位置上的先行语根本不在考虑范围之内。也就是说当被试读到（14）句从句的主语“她”时，由于受句法的限制，根本不会在代词和位于主句的主语位置上的名词之间建立链接，因此无论是性别匹配（张丽丽）还是性别不匹配（王志勇）都不会影响加工难度，因而不存在性别不一致效应。

（14）她写作业的时候，张丽丽/王志勇吃光了桌上所有的零食。王雪梅并不生气。

同样，约束理论 C 原则规定名词短语不能与统领它的代词共指（Chomsky 1981），因此（15）中的代词“she”不能指代从句中的名词“Sue/Ben”。

（15）Although every Sunday she_i ate breakfast while Sue/Ben_j worked on the crossword, Jessicai never offered to help.

很多研究得出一致性结论，即 C 原则在线加工中发挥强大的作用，以致于在受 C 原则约束的逆回指加工中，性别不一致效应会消失（Kazanina et al. 2007, Kazanina & Phillips 2010）。汉语代词逆回指加工中性别不一致效应的消失同样说明了循环 c-统领在搜索过程的早期阶段发挥着强大的作用。代词逆回指加工是受句法约束的积极搜索方式，因此，被试在逆回指加工的过程中根本不考虑主句主语位置的非法先行词。

那么为什么 Sun and Shelia(2015)的逆回指加工在线实验中会发现性别不一致效应，也就是说性别不一致条件下的阅读时间要长于性别一致的条件呢？仔细研究他们的实验材料不难发现，在 48 套实验材料中，有 28 套是用“...之前”和“...之后”引导的时间状语从句，虽然汉语中还有待进一步研究，但是俄语逆回指加工中由“...之前”和“...之后”引导的从时间状语从句中的代词可以和主句中的主语共指，而“...的时候”引导的表示“同时性”的时间状语从句中的代词不可以与主句的主语共指（Kazanina & Phillips 2010）。另一个原因可能是由于在他们的实验材料中名词短语不是中文人名，而是一些职业名词（如法官，演员，编辑等）。在相当一部分句子中职业名词和代词“他”或“她”后面的动词有直接的联系，如（16）中“歌手演唱”，（17）中“演员表演”以及（18）中“学生写论文”，被试在这种直接关系的指引下会认为从句的动作是主句的主语发出的，因此当主句主语的性别与代词不一致时，会导致加工困难，产生性别不一致效应。

（16）在他演唱/歌曲/的时候，/男歌手(女歌手)舞动/手中/紧握的/旗帜。

（17）在/她表演了/舞蹈/之后，/女演员(男演员)缺席了/后面的/几次/彩排。

(18) 在/他写完/论文/之后, /男学生(女学生)卖掉了/所有/课程的/教材。

Zhao(2014) 和本研究中的实验材料中的名词都是没有身份特征的中文人名, 有效的避免了类似问题的发生。

4. 结论

汉语作为话题凸显的语言, 准允空主语, 在指代系统中不仅包含显性代词, 也包含零代词。对于零代词, 无论在回指加工还是逆回指加工中, 同一句中的名词短语都可以与其共指, 是其默认先行语; 而对于显性代词, 在回指和逆回指加工中与同一句中名词短语的共指程度差别较大: 回指加工中共指百分比为 52%, 机会概率, 说明显性代词既可与同一句中的名词短语共指, 也可不与其共指, 指代语境中的其他人; 而在逆回指加工中, 显性代词一般不与同一句中的名词共指 (17%), 更倾向于指代语境中的其他人。这种共指倾向制约了显性代词的在线加工。无论在回指加工还是逆回指加工中都没有发现性别不一致效应, 但是原因却各不相同。具体来说, 回指加工中的性别不一致效应是由显性代词的灵活性和不稳定性造成的。逆回指加工中性别不一致效应的消失是由句法约束造成的。本研究在逆回指在线加工中缺少不受制约的控制条件, 如果在不受制约的控制条件下, 发现性别不一致效应, 而在句法制约条件下没有发现性别不一致性效应, 更能说明循环 c-统领这一句法刚性制约作用, 有待于进一步研究。

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Attitudes toward L2 Mandarin Speakers of Chinese and Non-Chinese Ethnicity

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Perceived ethnicity is known to bias perception of accentedness of non-native speakers, but most existing research demonstrating this has been done on majority languages of North American and European countries. In the present study, a group of L1 Mandarin listeners were asked to rate the personalities and language abilities of highly proficient L2 Mandarin speakers of Chinese and non-Chinese ethnicity after listening to short statements by each speaker. Results show an effect of ethnic ingroup favoritism on several personality traits but no difference in perceived language proficiency. In the same way that ethnic biases against L2 speakers of European languages have been confirmed by research, this study confirms that ethnic biases can be present in an East Asian context. The study also provides evidence that achieving nativelylike pronunciation in a second language does not eliminate discrimination against members of an outgroup.

0. Introduction

Studies of perceived comprehensibility, intelligibility and accentedness¹ of second language (L2) speakers are often done on English in the US, where multilingualism isn't the norm and ethnic diversity is comparatively common. However, in much of the world, such as in many Chinese-speaking communities, multilingualism is the norm, yet ethnic diversity is not. Mandarin is spoken as a second language in greater China by many first language (L1) speakers of other Chinese languages, so exposure to accented Mandarin is not unusual. However, mutually unintelligible Chinese languages are popularly considered to be dialects of the same language, at least in mainland China, which results in a distinction between L2 Mandarin speakers of L1 Chinese languages and those of other L1s. While there are probably fewer proficient Mandarin speakers of non-Chinese L1s, many Mandarin speakers encounter these speakers through media, such as in unscripted television programs or internet videos, and some encounter these speakers in daily life. This exposure is likely to increase in the future with the growth in interest in Mandarin language

¹ *Intelligibility*, *comprehensibility*, and *accentedness* are used here as defined by Munro, Derwing, & Morton (2006). *Intelligibility*: Actual understanding of the meaning of a word or utterance, i.e. more understanding on the part of the listener is equivalent to more intelligibility of a part of a word or utterance. *Comprehensibility*: Ease with which a word or utterance can be understood, i.e. less effort on the part of the listener is equivalent to more comprehensibility on of a word or utterance. *Accentedness*: The degree to which the pronunciation of an utterance sounds different from an expected production pattern.

programs. In the United States, Mandarin is the 4th most popular foreign language by enrollment in K-12 education (American Councils for International Education 2017) and 7th most popular in higher education (Looney & Lusin 2018).

L2 speakers face specific consequences in society, such as negative treatment in the media, courts, housing, and employment (Lippi-Green 2012). While comprehensibility of L2 speech is influenced by morphosyntactic and lexical features, the factor most associated with L2 accentedness is pronunciation (Saito, Trofimovich, & Isaacs 2016). Both L2 speakers and their listeners often believe that it is possible to eliminate an L2 accent and may even believe that it is laziness on the part of the L2 speaker that prevents elimination of their accent (Gluszek & Dovidio 2010). There are conflicting opinions as to whether it is possible for adult L2 language learners to achieve nativelike pronunciation, but there is evidence that comprehensibility is improved if pronunciation instruction is more explicitly included in language classroom activities (Derwing & Munro 2015, Yang 2016). There is also evidence, outlined below, that perceived characteristics of a speaker's identity influence processing of the language input received by listeners. Some scholars argue that L2 speakers should not be responsible for "improvement" of their pronunciation to improve communication between themselves and L1 (or other L2) speakers, and that listeners should make an effort to better comprehend accented speech (Gluszek & Dovidio 2010, Kang, Rubin, & Lindemann 2015). Indeed, there is evidence that practice in listening to multiple accented L2 speakers of a language can improve speaker-independent intelligibility of accented speech (Baese-Berk, Bradlow, & Wright 2013). Regardless, students of second languages can make better-informed decisions about how much time and effort to spend on pronunciation with accurate information on how their accented speech is perceived.

1. Literature Review

Perceived speaker ethnicity is known to influence processing of and opinions about speakers and their speech. In a well-known study (Rubin 1992), college-student subjects listened to identical speech samples presented by a university instructor, but some subjects were presented with a photograph of a Caucasian woman while others were presented with a photograph of an Asian woman. Participants shown the photograph of the Asian woman performed worse on an intelligibility test and reported hearing a stronger accent. In a verbal guise study, Yook & Lindemann (2013) demonstrated that knowing a speaker's ethnicity can impact opinions about a speaker's character by surveying Korean college students who listened to speakers of five varieties of English. One group of participants were informed of the speakers' nationalities and ethnicities while the other group was not. In comparison to uninformed listeners, informed listeners tended to rate European-American and Korean English speakers higher than the others on status/competence traits, and they rated British Australian and African American Vernacular English speakers lower on social attractiveness traits than did uninformed listeners.

SOCIAL COGNITION AND DUAL PROCESSING. The Dual Processing theory of social cognition, which developed over many decades and is not credited to one particular individual (but see Fiske & Neuberg 1990 for one major Dual Processing model and Fiske & Taylor 2017 for a general overview), can be used to better understand evaluative reactions to language input. The dual modes of reacting to and processing stimuli are 1) automatic and 2) conscious, and the model allows for investigation of the interface between the two. This section discusses relevant psychology literature along with its application to language attitudes research.

Macrae & Bodenhausen's (2000) explanation of categorical thinking illustrates many of the details of automatic processing. The categorical thinking process is divided into the three potential steps of activation, application, and inhibition. Automatic category activation refers to the initial, subconscious process that occurs when first encountering a stimulus, like the auditory stimulus of L2-accented speech, or being told that the ethnicity of the person who produced that speech matches the ethnicity of the listener. Automatic category activation may or may not take place; for the purpose of efficiency, the encountered person is associated with a relevant social category if and only if the social meaning of the encountered person is perceived as relevant to current information processing concerns. For the example of speaker ethnicity and L2-accented speech, the speaker will be categorized according to the listener's beliefs about L2 speakers and/or people of the L2 speaker's ethnicity. This categorization then triggers other representations of the category as well as stored information about members of such a social group. Category application is the next step in the categorical thinking process. Once a recognized individual is categorized into a social group, as long as the information perceived is consistent with the stereotypes held by the perceiver, the stereotype category is applied (Fiske & Taylor 2017). This application affects the subsequent interaction between individuals in the same way that any other prime would (Macrae & Bodenhausen 2000).

Categorical thinking, however, is not always applied; certainly, a perceiver could process a speaker as an individual person instead of a representative of a social category. According to a great deal of work cited by Macrae & Bodenhausen (2000), categorical stereotypes are most likely used when a perceiver lacks motivation or is burdened with a shortage of time or a high cognitive load (e.g. due to increased effort required to process accented speech). In such a situation, categorical thinking allows for efficiency and less expended effort in the processing of input. The perceiver can shift focus and free up mental resources for parsing of potential unexpected information. If the automatic perception, however, is inconsistent with the held stereotype, or if multiple social stereotypes are simultaneously activated, the perceiver may either attempt to classify the perceived in terms of a subtype that contains unique categories differentiating the perceived from the stereotype(s), or the perceiver may instead try to access exemplars of members of the stereotype category (Fiske & Taylor 2017). The last possibility, which could happen after either form of category application, is that the perceiver proceeds with conscious processing as executive function takes over (Macrae & Bodenhausen 2000).

According to Fiske & Taylor (2017), conscious processing can inhibit and control the associations made during the category activation above. Fiske & Taylor outline several potential motives for determining whether processing rises to the level of conscious or not; two of these, self-enhancement and trusting ingroup, encourage use of automatic processes. People usually expect good things from their ingroup members, and negativity stands out, cognitively speaking, much more quickly than positivity. An L2 speaker may be more likely to be considered to be an outgroup member by an L1 speaker, as would a person of a different ethnicity. Macrae & Bodenhausen (2000) argue that people are not always successful at inhibiting stereotypical thoughts; a person may fail to do so out of a lack of awareness that the thoughts occurring in the mind are stereotypical. If a person is, in fact, aware, they must employ a cognitively demanding process to identify and replace the stereotypical thoughts. Should a person be unable to cope with such demands, the person has now created a situation in which the stereotypical thoughts are highly accessible yet not inhibited, resulting in more stereotypical thoughts. Given that cognitive load is increased when processing accented speech (Derwing & Munro 2015), inhibitory failure in this situation may be expected.

THE POTENTIATED RECRUITMENT FRAMEWORK FOR IMPLICIT AND EXPLICIT ATTITUDES. Bassili & Brown's (2005) *potentiated recruitment* framework has been used successfully to model language attitudes in terms of input, processing and response (Preston 2017). In the context of the dual processing model, potentiated recruitment is appealing as it allows components of attitude creation and activation to be accessed both consciously and auto-matically. Bassili & Brown (2005) argue that "connectionist networks" of stored experiences, evaluations, attitudes and exemplars are a good fit for the parts that underlie implicit and explicit attitudes. Rosenberg's (1968) *attitudinal cognitorium* is used as a means of understanding the structure of these networks in relation to stimulus processing and attitudinal response. The *cognitorium* is described as a connectionist network of *microconcepts*, each of which represents information sensitive to the context at the time it was stored in memory. A microconcept, a node in this network, is retrieved from memory in a new context each time it is accessed. It is then associated with other microconcepts, meaning that each implicit or explicit attitude a person holds can change in context depending on which microconcepts have been activated. This is why context is key to understanding attitudes, according to Bassili & Brown. These authors go as far as to say that "features of the context are just as involved in the potentiation features of the attitude object" (Bassili & Brown 2005, p. 555-556). Bassili & Brown's model is uniquely effective in accounting for attitude malleability, as no node is likely to be recalled in the exact same way as when it was originally stored. Potentiation, or level of activation, of micro-concepts is influenced by a perceiver's recent information processing experiences, currently perceived information about the attitude object, activation between linked concepts in the cognitorium, and, for explicit attitudes, cognitive activity in working memory. The influence from currently perceived information "exert[s] powerful

potentiating influences on the attitudinal cognitorium” (Bassili & Brown 2005, p. 553) and appears to be easiest to manipulate by a researcher in an experiment in the form of a prime.

SOCIAL COGNITION IN THE CHINESE CONTEXT. To apply a social cognition framework to perception of second-language Mandarin speakers by contemporary Chinese, certain concepts must be modified, or at least qualified, to fit the Chinese context. The concept of membership in an East Asian (typically Chinese, Japanese, or Korean) “collectivist” culture can be misinterpreted as loyalty to or identification with one’s ingroup from the point of view of a western, “individualistic” culture. Yuki (2003) found that for small social groups of students in the US and Japan, Americans identified more with and were more loyal to their ingroups than their Japanese counterparts, according to psychological measures of ingroup loyalty and identity. Yuki also found that while knowledge of role relations within a group, as measured by a scale of subjective sociometric knowledge, was correlated with ingroup loyalty and identity for both Japanese and American respondents, perceived ingroup homogeneity was only correlated with ingroup identity for Americans. Yuki’s experiment was set up from the viewpoint of traditional Confucian notions of social harmony as resulting from fulfillment of one’s particular role in the family and not from loyalty to or identification with one’s country, community, or society. In fact, according to Liu, Li, & Yue (2010), the idea of asserting one’s identity with a broader social group, at least in China’s Confucian culture, did not present itself until the forced establishment of European treaty ports in China. Ingroup favoritism with respect to membership in a social group broader than the family first became relevant and widespread in China via the adoption of western nationalism, done as a defense mechanism against Europeans and their stratified society, and eventually as “benevolent paternalism” towards outgroup members perceived as inferior (Liu et al. 2010). Western-style nationalism in modern China, however, is not necessarily a direct reaction to Western nations, given, for example, the widespread knowledge of the atrocities committed by Japan in China in the early twentieth century. Ethnicity, then, in China, has not historically been divorced from nationality in terms of ingroup/outgroup categorization, and can serve as a source of discrimination in contemporary Chinese society. It has yet to be demonstrated, though, that ethnicity can interact with language in such categorization and subsequent discrimination.

LANGUAGE STEREOTYPES. Existing research on language stereotypes predicts that listeners evaluate speakers along dimensions of *status*, *solidarity*, and *dynamism*. These three affective dimensions are related to the types of affective meaning in social psychology that can be applied to evaluation of any object: *potency*, *evaluation*, and *activity* (Osgood, May, & Miron 1975). According to Zahn & Hopper (1985) and Fiske, Taylor, Cuddy, & Xu (2002) (the latter for *status* and *solidarity* only), individuals rated highly on *status* are thought to be of high competence, high social class, and high language fluency, people rated highly on *solidarity* are thought to be warmer and more socially and aesthetically attractive, and those rated highly on *dynamism* are thought to have higher levels of activity and social power. While Osgood et al. (1975) found that there is some

cultural variation in dimensions of affective meaning, they also found that evaluation, potency, and activity were significant for Cantonese speaker-listeners. Wible & Hui (1985) and White & Li (1991) found that evaluation, potency, and activity were significant for L1 Mandarin speakers listening to L2 Mandarin speech.

The Matched Guise Technique (Lambert, Hodgson, Gardner, & Fillenbaum 1960) traditionally presents a group of listeners with several recordings of the same text, each ostensibly produced by a different speaker. In actuality, some of the recordings are sets of two with each set produced by the same speaker using a different language or language variety. After listening to each recording, respondents are asked to rate each speaker's voice on semantic differential scales of personality traits and language impressions that are expected to represent listeners' attitudes of the groups thought to use these different language varieties. Use of the same speaker removes the possibility of ratings based on idiosyncratic variation naturally found between speakers. In contrast to traditional matched guise studies, the language samples presented to respondents are not varied in the present study (respondents rated the exact same language samples twice); rather, different information about the speaker's ethnicity is presented to respondents for each "guise." A similar technique been used with speaker nationality in previous matched guise studies (Hay, Nolan, & Drager 2006; Niedzielski 1999).

2. Research Questions

This research study aims to answer the following questions: Do ethnically Chinese native Mandarin-speaking listeners find ethnic Chinese L2 speakers to be more socially attractive and/or less accented due to simple ingroup bias, i.e. ethnic solidarity? Conversely, do these listeners find highly proficient ethnic outgroup members to be more socially attractive and/or less accented due to listener ideologies that ethnic ingroup members should know how to speak the language? Or, is the effect of ethnicity more nuanced than this?

3. Methods

STIMULI. L1 Mandarin stimuli were used to test the hypothetical situation in which an L2 speaker has acquired a nativelike pronunciation of Mandarin. Stimuli were selected from the Mandarin Affective Speech Corpus (Yang, Li, & Wu 2007), which contains recordings of 68 students (males: 45, mean age = 21.7) at Zhejiang University, all of whom had lived in Mainland China since birth and the "majority [of which] were trained to speak in standard Mandarin from early childhood" (p. 3). This corpus was chosen because it contains a large number of speakers reading the same sentences and is controlled for emotional state. The present study used 20 "neutral" recorded utterances from 20 different speakers (males: 10), chosen by the author to be relatively consistent in terms of prosody (length of utterance) and recording quality (presence of clipping, signal-to-noise ratio). In addition to the author, two L1 speakers of Mandarin from two different regions of China and one other highly proficient L2 Mandarin speaker screened the stimuli for regionally

marked speech features (such as merger of alveolar and retroflex fricatives, vowel diphthongization, etc.). Four speakers were presented as matched guises, while the remaining sixteen utterances were included as distractors. The example speakers and sentences for the matched guises are shown in Table 1. Different target sentences were used to make the task more engaging and better maintain rater attention. Half of the recordings were (falsely) presented to respondents as having been produced by ethnically Chinese L2 speakers and the other half of the recordings were (falsely) presented to respondents as produced by ethnically non-Chinese L2 speakers, but there were no actual linguistic differences between the distractor sentences in each group presented to listeners, and there were no differences at all between the target (matched guise) sentences.

Speaker ID	Sex	Sentence - Chinese	Sentence – English Translation
F1	Female	今天晚上会下雨。	It's going to rain tonight.
M1	Male		
F2	Female	我们室友总是把寝室弄得很脏。	Our roommates always make the dorm room very messy.
M2	Male		

Table 1: Target sentences and speakers

RESPONDENTS. Respondents were required to have been raised in Mainland China, of self-reported native or near-native Mandarin proficiency, at least 18 years of age, and with no known speech or hearing disorders. Because the web survey was administered using Google Cloud Platform, which is often inaccessible in China, respondents were recruited in Seattle through emails disseminated to Chinese student groups and students in introductory linguistics classes, flyers posted on the University of Washington campus, and through researcher contacts, though trained sociolinguists and first-order researcher contacts were asked to refrain from taking the survey. The survey was distributed from 9/27/2019 – 11/06/2019. 30 of the 58 respondents evaluated all 24 audio stimuli, and 28 of the 30 respondents provided their demographic information. Analyses include the 30 respondents who evaluated all 24 audio stimuli, and the completion rate is calculated to be 52%. An additional four respondents completed enough of the survey to evaluate both guises of at least one speaker; these observations were also included in the analyses. Respondents ranged in from 18-36 years of age, with a mean of 22.9 years, a variance of 22.5, and a standard deviation of 4.7. 13 of the respondents were women, 15 were men, and none were of other genders. Reported ethnicities were Han (n=24), Manchu (n=2), Hui (n=1), and no response (n=1). 11 respondents reported being an L1 speaker of at least one language or dialect in addition to Mandarin. Respondents were raised in a mixture of hometowns from different geographic areas of China (see Online Supplemental Materials).

PRESENTATION. Respondents were told (in Mandarin) that researchers were interested in getting their impressions on how second language Chinese speech sounds. Prior to beginning the study, respondents were asked for informed consent. Respondents

were then told that they would be listening to 24 different speech samples, each recorded by a different, highly proficient, L2 Mandarin speaker. As to not give the impression that some stimuli were produced by heritage speakers, respondents were told that none of these speakers were raised in a Chinese-speaking country, none began studying Chinese before the age of 14, and none learned Chinese from their families. Respondents were told that half of the speakers were ethnically Chinese (华裔 *huáyì*), and half were of non-Chinese ethnicity (非华裔 *fēi huáyì*). Respondents were accurately told that they would randomly be assigned to first hear the group of twelve ethnic Chinese speakers (n=21) or the group of twelve non-ethnic Chinese speakers (n=13). After rating each block, respondents were advised to take a break of a few minutes before being presented with the remaining twelve speech samples. Respondents were told that they could listen to each sample as many times as they wanted but were asked to quickly respond to each question according to their first impression of each speaker. Respondents were asked to wear earphones for the study and to adjust the volume to a suitable level before beginning.

Respondents were told that they would be asked to answer several questions about each speech sample. In order to familiarize respondents with the task, they were provided with an example question containing 7 radio buttons on a scale of 1 to 7, with two example adjectives that would later be included in the actual rating task: 冷淡的 *lěngdàn de* “cold (personality)” written to the left of the scale and 热情的 *rèqíng de* “warm (personality)” to the right of the scale. They were told the colder their impression of a speaker, the closer to “cold” they should click, whereas the warmer their impression of a speaker, the closer to “warm” they should click. They were told that if they were unsure or had no impression of the speaker that they should select the radio button in the center, labeled as 没什么印象 *méi shénme yìnxiàng* “no impression.” At the top of the next page, the speaker number and ethnicity of the speakers in the current block were displayed. For the first recording, respondents clicked a “play” button to listen to each recording. Below the media player, they were presented with twelve semantic differential scales corresponding to nine personality traits and three language measures, described in the following section of this paper. Respondents rated the speaker on each trait and then clicked the “next” button, which submitted their response, cleared the form, and played the next recording. After listening to and rating all stimuli, respondents were asked for demographic information and thanked for their participation.

Participants rated each guise on nine personality traits and three impressions of language proficiency along seven-step semantic differential scales, in keeping with Osgood et al. (1975). The speaker traits included on the questionnaire were chosen after consulting language attitudes work for L2 speakers of English (Yook & Lindemann 2013) and L1 speakers of Mandarin (Liao 2008, Lin 2018, Peng 2016, Tan 2016, Yang 2014). Raters were also asked to rate each speaker’s standardness, fluency, and foreign-accentedness on seven-level scales. Four rating scales of speaker traits and language proficiency were selected for each evaluative dimension to which they were predicted to correspond: *status*: competent-incompetent, smart-stupid, standard-not standard, and fluent-not fluent,

solidarity: deep-shallow, warm-cold, likeable-unlikeable, and accented-not accented, and *dynamism*: strong-weak, polite-rude, modern-conservative, and kind-arrogant. All seven values of the semantic differential scales were used by one respondent in a pilot study, so the seven options were left in. All semantic differential scales were arranged by placing the trait with negative valence on the left and positive valence on the right, except for the accented/not accented scale, which was reversed in order to detect straightlining, a strategy in which respondents simply select the same answer to all questions in order to finish the survey faster. No straightlining was observed, and accented/not accented scores were transformed to match the other scales, i.e. a score of 1 was converted to 7, a score of 2 was converted to 6, and a score of 3 was converted to 5.

4. Results

Table 2 shows summary statistics in the form of medians and interquartile ranges (IQRs) by semantic differential scale, pooling ratings from all respondents on all target speakers (distractor recordings were excluded). These descriptive statistics establish that ratings differed in terms of perceived speaker personality and perceived speaker language proficiency, as found by Wible & Hui (1985). While the median ratings for personality trait scales were either 5 (for arrogant/kind, rude/polite and unlikeable/likeable) or 4 (for the other seven personality traits), the median ratings for each of the language proficiency scales (accented/not accented, fluent/not fluent, standard/not standard) was 7. The IQRs for conservative/modern and weak/strong show that a very high proportion of respondents were unwilling or unable to evaluate the speakers on those scales. Visual distributions of ratings are presented in Figure 1. An exploratory factor analysis was conducted via principal components analysis with varimax rotation and Kaiser normalization. As expected, this analysis yielded three factors with eigenvalues above 1, accounting for 65.89% of the variance. The factor loadings are shown in Table 3. Rotated component 2 clearly consists of the three scales on which language proficiency was rated. As has been observed in previous studies on social stereotyping, it may be the case that *dynamism* is not a dimension at play here. If so, it is likely that the scales intended to measure dynamism actually measured *status* (strong-weak) and *solidarity* (the remaining three), and that rotated component 1 represents *solidarity* and rotated component 3 represents *status*. The principal components analysis and the vastly different distributions in ratings indicate that it would be illogical to group the twelve scales into the original three indices of *status*, *solidarity* and *dynamism*, in which ratings of language proficiency and personality traits were combined. Further, the non-normal distribution of the ratings as shown in Figure 1 indicates that non-parametric statistical procedures should be used, and that combining scales into indices representing dimensions of affective meaning may obscure individual differences among respondents in their interpretation of the points on each semantic differential scale. The ratings in this study, then, are conceptualized as follows: each respondent k generates score x_{ijk} by rating speaker i on bipolar scale j . Raters evaluated

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the same speaker on the same bipolar scales twice, one in each ethnicity condition, so their scores were compared as:

$$H_0: \text{Chinese}_{ijk} = \text{Non-Chinese}_{ijk}.$$

Scale (English)	Scale (Mandarin)	Median	IQR (25%-75%)
Not Accented / Accented	没/有洋腔洋调	7*	6-7*
Arrogant / Kind	高傲的/和爱的	5	4-5
Cold / Warm	冷淡的/热情的	4	4-5
Conservative / Modern	保守的/前卫的	4	4-4
Not Fluent / Fluent	不/流利的	7	6-7
Incompetent / Competent	没/有才干的	4	4-5
Rude / Polite	没/有礼貌的	5	4-6
Shallow / Deep	肤浅的/有深度的	4	4-5
Not Standard / Standard	不/标准	7	6-7
Stupid / Smart	愚蠢的/聪明的	4	4-5
Unlikeable / Likeable	不/招人喜欢的	5	4-6
Weak / Strong	不/坚强的	4	4-4

Table 2: Medians and interquartile ranges for target stimuli ratings, across raters and speakers.* indicates a transformed rating

Scale / Component	Predicted dimension of affective meaning	Rotated Comp 1	Rotated Comp 3	Rotated Comp 2
Rude / Polite	Dynamism	.73	.32	
Stupid / Smart	Status	.47	.63	
Shallow / Deep	Solidarity		.87	
Cold / Warm	Solidarity	.79		
Incompetent / Competent	Status		.78	
Weak / Strong	Dynamism		.69	
Conservative / Modern	Dynamism	.53		
Arrogant / Kind	Dynamism	.88		
Unlikeable / Likeable	Solidarity	.77	.34	
Not Standard / Standard	Status			.86
Not Fluent / Fluent	Status			.88
Accented / Not Accented	Solidarity			.74

Table 3: Principal component analysis with varimax rotation and Kaiser normalization

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Figure 1 Counts of scores for target stimuli by rating scale, across raters and speakers. The columns, from right to left, represent status, solidarity, and dynamism measures.

Scale / Speaker	F1	M1	F2	M2
Not Accented / Accented	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Arrogant / Kind	0.0094**	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Cold / Warm	0.0178*	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Conservative / Modern	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Not Fluent / Fluent	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Incompetent / Competent	0.0397*	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Rude / Polite	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Shallow / Deep	0.0057**	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Not Standard / Standard	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Stupid / Smart	0.0210**	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Unlikeable / Likeable	0.0013**	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Weak / Strong	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

Table 4: *p* values for each scale, by speaker. **p* < .05, ***p* < .01

Scale	Pseudo- median	95% CI	Scale	Pseudo- median	95% CI
Arrogant / Kind	1.00	0.5-1.5	Shallow / Deep	1.00	0.00-2.00
Cold / Warm	1.00	0.00-2.00	Stupid / Smart	1.00	0.00-2.00
Incompetent / Competent	1.00	0.00-2.00	Unlikeable / Likeable	1.50	0.50-2.00

Table 5: Estimated location for the median of the difference from a sample of Chinese v. non-Chinese guises (pseudomedian) for speaker F1, all significant scales

To test whether these paired ratings were significantly different, a two-tailed Wilcoxon signed rank test was conducted, as in Bender (2004). This test has the advantage of not assuming that ratings on the semantic differential scales are continuous (interval or ratio) nor that the ratings are distributed normally in any of dimensions i , j , or k . In other words, it compares individual differences across conditions, so there is no potential for bias introduced by individual differences between raters' uses of the different scales on the different speakers. Results are shown in Table 4.

The p value of each two-tailed Wilcoxon signed rank test does not indicate directionality; it only indicates that there is a significant difference between rankings of each guise. To calculate directionality, an estimated location for the median of the difference between a sample from each guise is calculated based on a confidence interval, represented in Table 5. The sign of the estimated location indicates the direction in which rankings are higher; a positive value indicates that rankings in the first group (Chinese) are higher whereas a negative value indicates that the rankings in the second group (non-Chinese) are higher. All estimated location values for significant scale/speaker combinations were positive, indicating that the Chinese guise was rated more favorably for all statistically significant differences.²

3. Discussion

This study has provided strong evidence that L1 Mandarin-speaking listeners find ethnic Chinese L2 Mandarin speakers to be of higher status and more socially attractive than non-Chinese L2 Mandarin speakers due to ethnic ingroup implicit bias. In contrast to the results for character traits, no strong evidence is found for an effect of ethnicity on fluency, accentedness, or standardness. All observed differences in ratings for personality traits, statistically significant or not, are in the direction of favoring those who are ethnically Chinese. These findings confirm that ethnic biases present against L2 speakers of European languages can be extended to an East Asian context, despite claims by Liu et al. (2010) that such favoritism is only displayed by the Chinese as a defensive reaction to an outside threat or as a benevolent paternalism. While neither the presence of an outside

² Wilcoxon signed rank tests were also run to investigate ordering effects; no significant ordering effects were found. For more information, see the online supplemental materials.

threat nor the supposed inferiority of outgroup members was directly manipulated in the present experiment, no evidence for either is found in respondents' qualitative comments (see supplementary materials), and the semantic differential scales did not converge in a way comparable to paternalistic prejudice as previously demonstrated (Fiske et al. 2002).

The results, while robust, were only observed for the first of the four target speakers in this experiment that respondents heard. While interactions between demographic variables such as speaker sex and ethnicity, or interactions between sentence length and demographic variables were suspected, it was not the case that an effect was shown for speakers of one sex or reading one sentence – it was shown only for a single speaker. One possible interpretation of this is that it reflects that social biases are not consistently applied; Fiske & Taylor (2017) write that categorical thinking does not happen consistently; rather, categorical thinking tends to occur in times of high cognitive load or low motivation (Macrae & Bodenhausen 2000). Higher cognitive load at the beginning of the survey due to unfamiliarity with the survey task is one possible explanation for why speaker F1 was the only speaker that was rated differently across guises.

The difference in distributions of personality and language proficiency ratings is also of interest to a theory of language attitudes; there is a high proportion of “no impression” responses found in all nine of the personality trait scales but a high proportion of “not accented,” “not fluent,” and “not standard” scores for language proficiency traits. Particularly high rates of half or more of the judgements being “no impression/don't know” were found for six of the nine personality trait scales: conservative/modern (169 of 246 ratings), weak/strong (161), shallow/deep (158), incompetent/competent (152), cold/warm (135), and stupid/smart (122). While the most common rating was “no impression/don't know” for the remaining three personality trait judgments, the median rating for rude/polite and unlikeable/likeable were “somewhat polite” and “somewhat likeable,” whereas the median rating was still “no impression/don't know” for the arrogant/kind scale. The most common rating and median rating on the language proficiency scales, in contrast, were the maximum ratings of “very fluent,” “very standard,” and “very unaccented.” This means that respondents were not hesitant in judging a speaker's ability in the same way that they were hesitant about judging character. There are several possible interpretations for this difference. One interpretation is that social desirability bias prevents categorical thinking from applying to ratings of ability, i.e. it may be considered fair, legally or morally, to judge language proficiency, as opposed to character. Alternatively, since most of the respondents are L2 learners of English who live in an English-speaking cultural context, they may be demonstrating empathy towards L2 learners of Chinese. Another possible interpretation, supported by the qualitative comments, is that this population believes that language proficiency, unlike personality, can be judged by hearing a single sentence, such as those respondents heard in this study; this in itself is potentially relevant for future studies on ratings of L2 speakers. This is the opposite result, though, of what Wible & Hui (1985) found when L2 speakers of six different proficiency levels were judged, which is that linguistic areas were less salient than personality traits. It may be the case, then, that

language proficiency is seen as something that can be controlled (Gluszek & Dovidio 2010), unlike personality traits, which may be perceived as innate. This would indicate that any preferential treatment of ingroup members is based on biased perceptions of character rather than biased perceptions of ability, at least for highly proficient second-language speakers. The fact that language proficiency ratings did not differ by ethnicity is of interest; while an effect was present for ethnic ingroup bias in rating speaker characteristics, no such effect was present for ratings of language proficiency for these highly proficient speakers in this study. This is particularly relevant for second language learners of Mandarin; it should be known that while speaking with a nativelike accent may result in being perceived as very fluent, standard, and unaccented, regardless of ethnicity, there may be still be negative treatment if a speaker is a member of the ethnic outgroup. Researchers investigating attitudes towards L2 speakers of any language should therefore be cautious about directly comparing ratings of language proficiency to those of personality. Chinese language teachers should also keep in mind that stereotypes against speakers may influence their proficiency. An L2 speaker may worry about how an outgroup member may stereotype them or may believe that an outgroup member may feign inability to understand the speaker. This stress may cause them to avoid communicating in the accented language, leading to less practice and less fluency, and arouse feelings of frustration or insecurity (Gluszek & Dovidio 2010).

The present study's methodology demonstrates a stricter adherence to the assumptions made by statistical procedures as compared to most existing research on language and social psychology. Responses along the semantic differential scales were treated as ordinal, resulting in reporting of median ratings and use of the Wilcoxon signed rank test. Treatment of data as ordinal eliminates the possibility of calculating mean ratings of speakers along the dimensions of affective meaning probed in this study, as well as the use of certain inferential statistical techniques, such as linear regression and ANOVA. Some researchers have argued that it is appropriate under certain circumstances to treat semantic differential scales as interval data (Carfino & Perla 2007); they are often considered to be special, separate from Likert scales or other opinion continua not validated for cross-cultural meaning. This view is contested, however, due to the potential for individual differences in use of the scales; such variation can be conceptualized as a three-dimensional space: variation between respondents in interpretation of the different anchor points on a scale, variation in interpretations of the distance between the seven points of different seven-point scales (scale variation), and variation in applying different scales to different stimuli (stimulus variation) (Murakami & Kroonenberg 2003). This individual variation can have the effect of obscuring, exaggerating, or overgeneralizing results when left unanalyzed. The present study's results should be interpreted with the understanding that individual differences in the ratings of different objects are often left uninvestigated. It may be the case that the result of the present study, in which only one of the four matched guise speakers is rated differently across guises, is not at all unusual; rather, it may be a result that is commonly obscured in other research by the pooling of ratings of different

stimulus speakers. More research in statistics and psychometrics would clarify best practices in quantitative analysis for research in language and social psychology; if semantic differential data can be safely treated as interval, it simplifies the analysis and increases inferential power. Nevertheless, if those who argue that it is only safe to treat these kinds of data as ordinal are correct, social psychologists and sociolinguists would do well to employ available statistical techniques for ordinal data, at least for within-subject study designs. The Wilcoxon signed rank test is an example of a powerful statistical procedure that allows for better understanding of individual distances while offering generalizable results.

While efforts were made to limit sampling bias, it is possible that some bias was introduced by the method by which respondents were recruited. The population sampled is one that lives in a multi-ethnic society, which is not the case for most Mandarin speakers, and is a young and educated population. Bias may also have been introduced by the dropout rate of 48%; reducing the length of the survey and using the semantic differential scales with fewer “no impression” ratings could assist in reducing this bias (Dillman, Smyth, & Christian 2014).

In addition to the short length of the utterances presented, it is possible that giving no information about each speaker other than ethnicity to respondents is too abstract to relate to a real-world situation and may not actually activate social categories or exemplars similar to the speaker being judged. Indeed, it has been shown that perceptions of L2 speech can vary even down to personae within a group (D’Onofrio 2019, Zhang 2008). It may be ideal to provide speaker demographic information in addition to ethnicity, even if kept constant across guises, such as the nationality of the respondents. Giving information about nationality was avoided, though, in order to avoid possible interactions between ethnicity and nationality. Another option, as suggested by one of the respondent’s comments, is to tell respondents the context in which the example sentences were spoken; for instance, for the stimulus sentence about the weather, was this sentence produced in casual conversation, or was it produced by a meteorologist?

Future work measuring implicit, rather than explicit, attitudes or differences in processing of L2 Mandarin speech from speakers of different ethnicities may also help get to the root of the bias the population of L1 speakers from China. Such work would help determine whether social desirability bias is present, for example, by looking at differences in processing time when respondents believed they were listening to speech by ethnic Chinese and non-Chinese speakers.

4. Conclusion

The present work has demonstrated the potential for Chinese raters to express ingroup favoritism based only on knowledge of an outgroup member’s ethnicity. For this population of raters, ingroup favoritism does not apply to an L2 speaker’s language ability; rather, it applies to the speaker’s personality. Chinese language students and teachers should be aware of the existence of this ingroup favoritism when considering how much

time and energy to devote to pronunciation. L2 Mandarin speakers of any ethnicity should know that positive or negative bias may very well occur based on their outward appearance or their interlocutors' understanding of their background, even if nativelike pronunciation is achieved, just as in the Western societies in which much research at the intersection of linguistics and social psychology is carried out. This is not to say that ethnic non-Chinese never experience preferential treatment in Chinese society; however, motivations for this treatment are probably not feelings of envy or admiration towards an outgroup (Fiske et al. 2002), nor are they an illustration of the Chinese concept of *chóng yáng mèi wài* (崇洋媚外), which refers to blind worship of foreign things. A detailed discussion of the source of the ethnic ingroup bias presently observed is beyond the scope of this investigation, though the nationalist ideology promoted by contemporary Chinese state media, as part of the global resurgence of nationalism also observed in the United States, Europe, and the Middle East, would not be expected to curtail ingroup favoritism nor outgroup derogation. Whatever the source of this bias, social scientists aiming to produce research which helps improve intergroup relations would benefit from a greater focus on the behavior of populations outside of the Western societies which are overrepresented in our disciplines.

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS. Supplemental material is available at <https://zeos.ling.washington.edu/publications/supplemental/squizzero/NACCLsupplemental.html>. This material includes respondent demographic information, block-order analysis, and qualitative comments.

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Mandarin Self-Referential Expressions: A Sociolinguistic Study

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Mandarin speakers may use expressions other than the first-person singular pronoun *wo* 'I' to refer to themselves. This study explores the social meaning of those expressions with surveys and interviews. Based on 1135 questionnaires from all age groups and 29 provinces in China, the quantitative analyses support the hypothesis that social variables statistically significantly correlate with the usage of self-referential expressions tested in this study (*benren* 'this person', *baobao* 'baby', *baba* 'dad', *renjia* 'that person', and *laozi* 'old man'). By interviewing 21 Mandarin speakers with various demographic backgrounds, social meanings of each expression are analyzed. This study contributes to the literature in that: it explores the relationship between social variables and self-referential usages by large-sample-size quantitative analysis; it incorporates Mandarin self-reference users' subjective interactional aims and comments into scholars' analysis; it studies some unconventional usages of Mandarin referential expressions not mentioned in the previous literature.

1. Introduction

1.1 Self-references

Pronouns like *I* or *you* can be classified as deictics (Hanks 1992). Deixis plays a central role in the use and understanding of language (Hanks 1992). They can also be viewed as *shifters*, as the reference shifts in different speech situations (Silverstein 1976). Expressions other than pronouns can also serve as deictic expressions. In the field of philosophy, self-reference denotes a statement that refers to itself or its own referent, as in *this sentence is not true* (Bolander 2008). In this article, self-reference means what people call themselves.

In Chinese, there are various ways of referring to oneself. First-person singular pronouns such as *wu* and *yu* are self-references in Old Chinese, while *an* and *ou* are self-references in modern Chinese dialects (Xue and Zhang 2019). In modern Mandarin, the first-person singular pronoun *wo* is the canonical self-reference. There are also non-canonical usages of self-reference such as *nainai* 'grandma' in (1)¹. This study focuses on the lexical variants that function as self-references in modern Mandarin.

¹ This example is from Xue and Zhang 2019.

(1) 来，小朋友，奶奶带你买好吃的去！

Lai, xiaopengyou, nainai dai ni mai haochi de qu!

Come here, kiddo. Grandma will take you to buy something tasty!

1.2 Previous Research on Mandarin Self-referential Expressions

Previously, scholars (Zhang 1993, Xiao & Shen 2004, Chen 2009) have summarized the forms, categorizations, and pragmatic contexts of Mandarin self-references. Scholars categorized self-referential expressions in distinctive ways, but certain categories such as kinship terms, occupation terms, or pronouns are generally discernable. For instance, *baba* ‘dad’ and *laozi* ‘old man’ belong to the category of kinship referral pronoun, while *renjia* ‘that person’ can be used as a third-person referral pronoun. Zhang (2002) claimed that social identity could be related to self-reference by commenting that “In martial arts fictions, Chinese knights usually call themselves ‘I+ nickname’, and this phenomenon may correlate with some personality traits of the characters. In some novels, the particular kind of self-reference becomes the tag and even part of the identity of the person [author’s translation].”

Researchers have paid attention to the categorization of self-referential expressions and summarized their different communicative purposes. They have analyzed self-reference on a macro level, ignoring the impact of social factors on speakers’ choice and frequency of self-referential expressions. Liu (2015) accurately pointed out the lack of quantitative analysis and the absence of sociolinguistic perspective. Another limitation of previous research is that little attention has been given to speakers’ subjective purposes of using self-references. It is unclear whether the communicative purposes suggested by scholars reflect the opinions of the expressive subjects themselves. Previous speculations about the social meaning of self-references have not been supported by empirical evidence.

2. The Present Study

The purpose of this study is to advance the understanding of Mandarin self-reference by viewing it from a sociolinguistic perspective and by conducting both quantitative and qualitative analysis, which is unprecedented in the literature. An online survey is conducted to collect data for quantitative analyses. The study also compares interviewees’ responses and scholars’ interpretations on why or why not a certain expression is used. This compensates for the limitations of previous studies that only theoretically deduced the intentions of expressive subjects from a third-person perspective and that why a term is not used has been underexplored.

The dependent variable in question is the function of self-reference in Mandarin. The five lexical variants of the variable explored in the study are *benren* ‘this person’, *baobao* ‘baby’, *baba* ‘dad’, *renjia* ‘that person’, and *laozi* ‘old man’. These five expressions are chosen in this study because they could represent different categories. They are chosen also for their potential in sociolinguistic variation. These reasons will be discussed below from section 2.1 to section 2.5.

2.1 This Person *Benren*

Benren ‘this person’ is a first-person referral pronoun as in (2). It can also be translated as ‘I myself’ in English². When used as self-reference, *benren* ‘this person’ contains humor (Xu 1992). Compared with *wo* ‘I’, it is more subjective and is usually used in formal occasions (Yao 2008). Furthermore, *benren* ‘this person’ is often used in legal documents. Though its usage has expanded to daily conversation, it is worthwhile to know whether the industry the person works in correlates with the frequency of referring to oneself with *benren* ‘this person’.

(2) 本人对外面的待遇不是很了解。

Benren dui waimian de daiyu bushi hen liaojie.

This person does not know much about the salary of other companies.

2.2 Baby *Baobao*

Baobao ‘baby’ belongs to the category of nickname referral pronouns (Liu 2015), and it has been utilized as an increasingly popular term in Chinese. It is conventionally used by preschoolers or other non-adults. However, currently some adults also use *baobao* ‘baby’ to refer to themselves. Scholars (Zhao 2016, Hu 2016) claimed that it is used by an adult to create a childlike image and to narrow the distance between the interlocutors. It can be used to indicate various emotions or purposes including affection, aloofness, relaxation, and a demand for attention or protection (Xiao 2016).

Baobao ‘baby’ has drawn scholarly attention since it was listed as one of the top ten online buzzwords in 2015 by the National Center for Language Resources in China. There is no agreement on how this buzzword has gained popularity; however, it is widely acknowledged that this self-referential expression is so productive that people can use it in various circumstances. Example (3) is one of the most popular usages of the expression, and it is believed by Qin (2016) to be the origin of this buzzword.

(3) 吓死宝宝了!

Xiasi baobao le!

It scared baby to death!

Some scholars have speculated about which speakers are more likely to call themselves *baobao* ‘baby’. Feng and Li (2016) believed that people of any age or gender refer to themselves with it, though it had been used by young people, mostly female speakers, before this current popularity. Zhang (2016) believed that using *baobao* ‘baby’

² *Benren* is translated as ‘this person’, while *renjia* is translated as ‘that person’ in this paper. These two English translations have ‘person’ in common, which could suggest that there is the same relationship between the two Chinese expressions. However, it is not true. The two English expressions are close but not “perfect” translations.

is common among young female adults but not male speakers. Similarly, Zhao (2016) argued that female speakers can use it in many situations. Wan and Li (2016) argued that *baobao* ‘baby’ is widespread as a self-reference among young people, though it is used in all age groups. It is agreed that to some extent, young female adults may be more likely to refer to themselves with *baobao* ‘baby’ than other people. Therefore, special attention should be paid to see whether using *baobao* ‘baby’ as self-reference is correlated with age and gender.

2.3 Dad *Baba*

One kinship referral pronoun is *baba* ‘dad or daddy’ (Liu 2015). As a self-reference, it can be used by a father when talking to his children as in (4).

(4) 来, 爸爸给你讲个故事。

Lai, baba gei ni jiang ge gushi.

Come here, let dad tell you a story.

Interestingly, it is observed that both male and female speakers can also refer to themselves by *baba* ‘dad’ when talking with peers as in (5)³. Little scholarly attention has been paid to this novel usage. This unconventional usage and its difference from the conventional usage are examined in this study. In the survey, respondents who indicated that they refer to themselves with *baba* ‘dad’ had an additional question about to which interlocutor they refer to themselves with *baba* ‘dad’. Based on observations, it is hypothesized that young people are more likely to turn to this novel use and that male speakers are more likely to use *baba* ‘dad’ conventionally than female speakers.

(5) 爸爸要去吃饭了, 儿子要不要一起来?

Baba yao qu chifan le, erzi yaobuyao yiqilai?

Daddy is going to have lunch. Will my son have lunch with me or not?

2.4 That Person *Renjia*

Renjia ‘that person’ can be used as a third-person referral pronoun as in (6) (Lao 1982). In addition to its use as a self-reference, *renjia* ‘that person’ can also be used as a second- or third-person singular pronoun. Its first-person singular pronominal usage evolves from the third-person one (Wan 2006). Scholars (Wang 2016, Wan 2006) believed that speakers use the expression as self-reference in order to change perspective: the speaker adopts the perspective of the listeners, so that a third-person pronoun is used to refer to oneself.

(6) 你说话呀! 成心逗人家的火是怎么着?

³ This is an example provided by an interviewee.

Ni shuohua ya! Chengxin dou renjia de huo shi zenmezhao?
 Say something! Why must you always try to make that person mad?

It is hypothesized that women are more likely to use *renjia* ‘that person’ based on previous literature. Liu (2015) claimed that *renjia* ‘that person’ is commonly used by women. Zhai (2004) assumed that *renjia* ‘that person’ is a euphemistic first-person singular pronoun that occurs in dialogues of people with close relationships and that its users are mostly young female adults. Other scholars (Wan 2006, Cao 2018) also believed it is mostly used by women. Cao (2018) claimed that women tend to centralize the status of male speakers, and they desire to express unsatisfactory and other emotions euphemistically. To sum up, the hypothesis is that age and gender are correlated with the frequency of using *renjia* ‘that person’ as self-reference.

2.5 Old Man *Laozi*

Laozi ‘old man’ can be seen as a kinship referral pronoun because it has a meaning similar to *baba* ‘dad’. It can also be categorized as a communicative referral pronoun, and some people use *laozi* ‘old man’ to sound more powerful (Liu 2015). *Laozi* ‘old man’ is typically considered as a vulgar expression. (7) is an utterance by a guard of a gate, a job of relatively low social status. It is hypothesized that people with lower income, less education, and lower social status would be more likely to refer to themselves with *laozi* ‘old man’.

(7) 郑大人有郑大人的事，你们别找他瞎嚷嚷！

Zheng daren you zheng daren de shi, nimen bie zhao ta xia rangrang!
 Captain Zheng has his own business. You shouldn’t go to bother him!

这东门的事，是老子负责！

zhe dongmen de shi, shi laozi fuzu!

Issues of the East Gate are the old man’s responsibilities!

3. Methodology

3.1 The Quantitative Study

Following Kiesling (2004), who conducted self-report survey, I distributed anonymous online surveys that were created by Wenjuanxing in Mandarin Chinese. They were forwarded and shared through Wechat, Wechat groups, and QQ groups. Altogether 1171 survey responses were collected. The respondents were asked to select the answer choices most closely described their identities and their habits of using each self-referential expression. On the survey, respondents need to choose whether they *always*, *sometimes*, or *never* use each lexical variant of self-reference in question. There is a follow-up question about the circumstances of using *baba* ‘dad’ as self-reference to explore its unconventional

usage. There is one question for each social independent variable, and the reason for adopting each social independent variable will be discussed in section 3.1.1.

3.1.1 Independent Variables and Hypotheses

The social independent variables in question are gender, sexual orientation, age, geographical area, educational background, industry, income, and occupation. The independent variables of gender, age, educational background, and social status could be motivated by the previous analysis of the five expressions. The variables of gender and age are motivated by *baobao* ‘baby’, while the variables of educational background and social status are motivated by *laozi* ‘old man’. Taking the context of Chinese society into account, the variables of occupation, industry, and income were used to estimate social status. *Baba* ‘dad’ and *laozi* ‘old man’ are conventionally masculine self-references, but they have been observed to be used by females. Zimman (2017) argued that gender should be understood as elements of sociolinguistic style and it is complex. The independent variable of sexual orientation is used to try to decode the expression of gender. Online platforms allowed me to access questionnaires from all over China, and geographical area has been identified as a major determinant in sociolinguistic variations. Therefore, the independent variable of geographical area is identified.

To answer the question of whether Mandarin self-references are socially related, it is hypothesized that for each self-referential expression in question, there is a significant difference in usage among the demographic groups classified by each criterion. Specifically, the frequencies and/or usages of expressions exhibit discrepancy for people of different regions, genders, occupations, sexual orientations, and industry groups. Furthermore, as an individual’s age, education, and income increase, the frequencies of using several self-referential expressions either consistently increase or consistently decrease. To test previous claims and to explore the specific social meanings of each expression in question, other hypotheses, which are those observed or claimed relationships between using a self-referential expression and a social variable, are also evaluated.

3.1.2 Statistical Analysis

The 1171 questionnaires collected had undergone a screening process that excludes contradictory and inconsistent responses from further investigation⁴. Altogether there are 1135 effective questionnaires from all age groups and 29 out of 34 provinces in China. There are 525 respondents who declared themselves as male, and there are 610 people who reported that they are females.

The survey data are analyzed qualitatively and then quantitatively. The aggregated data frame for each possible correlation is visualized as a graph with the frequency of self-referential expressions at the y-axis and demographic categories at the x-axis. For correlations regarding categorical social variables (i.e., region, gender, occupation, and

⁴ The criteria to consider a questionnaire invalid include choosing *housewife* and *male* at the same time and selecting both *below 18* and *Doctor’s degree*.

sexual orientation), if there is an observed frequency discrepancy, I further use the chi-squared test to decide whether the difference is of statistical significance. As for other combinations concerning age, educational background, and income, if the visualized graph does not exhibit consistent patterns, it is concluded that there is no correlation between the social factor in question and the usage of this self-reference. If the graph shows that the frequency of using a term consistently increase or decrease from left to right, the chi-squared test is employed to determine whether the observed correlation is of statistical significance.

3.2 Sociolinguistic Interviews

Interviews are conducted to elicit speakers' opinions or linguistic ideologies on using self-reference. Interviews are essential in knowing why some speakers do not use some expressions, an issue that has not been discussed in previous literature. Twenty-one people from different demographic backgrounds were interviewed in this study. Nine interviewees were male and twelve were female. People who are in their early adulthood, middle-aged individuals, and people in their fifties or sixties were interviewed in this study. The highest level of education the interviewees received ranged from secondary school diploma to doctoral degree. Some interviewees were unknown to the researcher before the interview. Other interviewees were friends or family members of the researcher, so the effect of the observer's paradox could be reduced.

Interviews may start with self-introduction, if necessary, followed by questions about opinions on using self-references other than *wo* 'I' in general and on specific lexical items in this study. Interview questions included the following. Do you use *benren* 'this person' to refer to yourself? When or with whom do you call yourself *benren* 'this person'? Could you give me an example? Why do you use or not use this term? Who do you think would use this term to refer to themselves? What do you think of those people who refer to themselves with *benren* 'this person'? Similar questions were asked about each term for each interviewee.

4. Results

4.1 General Descriptions

The descriptive and analytical statistics results of the study are demonstrated in Table 1. Each cell in this table represents a combination of one social independent variable and one self-referential expression. The grey cells without numbers are the combinations that have no observed correlation, while the grey cells with numbers are the observed correlations without statistical significance ($p > .05$ or $p = .05$). All the white cells indicate statistically significant ($p < .05$) correlations between the demographic features and self-referential expressions. 73% of all the combinations of self-referential usages and social variables have confirmed to be statistically significant correlations. The study has found that for each social variable, there is at least one expression that is statistically relevant.

Furthermore, all the self-referential expressions are connected with more than four out of eight tested social variables.

Table 1. Descriptive and Analytical Statistics Results of Chi-squared Test

Expressions Social variable	<i>Benren</i> 'This Person'	<i>Baobao</i> 'Baby'	<i>Renjia</i> 'That person'	<i>Baba</i> 'Dad'	Non- Kinship <i>Baba</i>	<i>Laozi</i> 'Old Man'
Age		P<0.001			P<0.001	P<0.001
Region	0.007	P<0.001	0.170	0.315	0.762	P<0.001
Gender	0.005	P<0.001	0.003	P<0.001	P<0.001	P<0.001
Occupation	P<0.001	P<0.001	P<0.001	P<0.001	P<0.001	P<0.001
Sexual Orientation	0.028	0.014	P<0.001	P<0.001	0.012	P<0.001
Industry	P<0.001	P<0.001	0.001	P<0.001	0.152	P<0.001
Education				0.158	0.018	0.152
Income	P<0.001		0.035	P<0.001	P<0.001	0.002

As indicated in the table, the social factor of gender, sexual orientation, and occupation are related to the frequency of referring to oneself by all the five Mandarin expressions in question. Other social variables-- namely age, geographical area, industry, and income-- also correspond to most self-references. These support the general hypothesis that Mandarin self-references are socially-related.

4.2 This Person *Benren*: Objectively Formal and Subjectively Humorous

The hypothesis that *benren* 'this person' is correlated with industry is confirmed. Among the 102 respondents who work in law firms, accounting firms, or other consulting companies, 75 (74%) of them sometimes or always use this self-referential expression. Some interviews confirmed the observations of researchers. The response of one interviewee confirmed the claim of Yao (2008) that *benren* 'this person' is used in formal or official occasions. This respondent further elaborated on this viewpoint by saying that he uses it to keep the distance between unfamiliar audiences and himself. He pointed out that he uses *benren* 'this person' to show modesty as in (8). Another respondent's claim that *benren* 'this person' is adopted to joke with friends confirms the observation of Xu (1992) that the expression contains humor. Another interviewee asserted that because *benren* 'this person' is a formal expression, using it as self-reference makes the everyday conversation interesting.

(8) 本人没那么强的能力，本人讲得不好。

Benren mei name qiang de nengli, *benren* jiangde buhao.

This person's ability isn't that strong. This person did not lecture that well.

Not all observations of scholars have been supported by subjective communicative purposes of the interviewees. One respondent said that sometimes, instead of using *wo* ‘I’, a subjective term, to refer to himself, he would use *benren* ‘this person’ because there is no bias and it sounds objective. This comment is in line with the previously referenced response that *benren* ‘this person’ is employed to create distance. However, this comment directly contradicts the statement by Yao (2008) that *benren* ‘this person’ is subjective. This contradiction indicates that the speculative analysis of researchers is not sufficient.

During the interviews, some people claimed that *benren* ‘this person’ is too formal to be used in spoken language. Some people would never use *benren* ‘this person’ as self-reference because they think the expression “sounds self-centered,” “egoistic,” or “weird.” One respondent claimed that people in her mother’s generation use *benren* ‘this person’, and thus she does not use it.

4.3 Baby *Baobao*: Sentimentality of Young Female Adults

The statistical analysis verified some scholars’ speculation that young people and female speakers are more likely to use *baobao* ‘baby’. For adult speakers, the frequency of using *baobao* ‘baby’ as self-reference decreases with age, which suggests that even though it is an expression occurring in the idiolects of Chinese people from all age groups, it is still more prevalent among young adults. In addition, the study shows that significantly more female speakers use *baobao* ‘baby’ as self-reference.

Some comments made by the interviewees confirmed the assertions of scholars. A speaker claimed that he uses the expression to look cute when talking with close friends. One respondent described that when she is disappointed, she says (9) to talk to her close friends in jest. (9) can be viewed as an attention-seeking purpose as proposed by previous scholars.

(9) 宝宝比较心塞。

Baobao bijiao xinsai.

Baby is upset.

Some interviewees commented that they have never used *baobao* ‘baby’ since they think they are not the kind of person who would behave like a spoiled naïve child. Another respondent stated that she does not use the self-referential expression because it is too young for her. Another comment is that the expression is too sentimental and emotional, and thus does not fit the personality of the speaker. The female speaker who made this comment further described that she may use *baobao* ‘baby’ as self-reference to joke on rare occasions. Those comments support the claim of Xiao (2016) that people use *baobao* ‘baby’ to indicate emotion and to demand attention or protection. Other respondents do not use *baobao* ‘baby’ as self-reference because they think it is “of poor taste” or “lowly.”

4.4 Dad *Baba*: Kinship and Non-Kinship Self-reference

The conventional and unconventional usages of *baba* ‘dad’ exhibit different correlations with age. While people’s usage of *baba* ‘dad’ when talking with children increases with age, referring to oneself as *baba* ‘dad’ when having conversations with peers decreases with age. In other words, young people are more likely to use the kinship expression unconventionally, which confirms the observation mentioned before.

Among the interviewees who have children, some would use *baba* ‘dad’ as self-reference when talking with children while some would not. One respondent believed that children should be treated equally, and therefore, *baba* ‘dad’ is not used in the family as self-reference because it indicates inequality. This comment suggested that similar to *laozi* ‘old man’, *baba* ‘dad’ is correlated with power.

Several young female and male adults gave reasons for why they use *baba* ‘dad’ to refer to themselves when talking amongst peers. Two female speakers in their early twenties pointed out that using the expression makes them look tougher and more powerful. Both of them use it when talking to female and male peers. One of them uses the expression more often when talking to male than female friends because she thinks that male speakers adopt this unconventional usage of kinship term as a joke between each other more often. She suggested that, based on her experience, the usage is usually reciprocal. The other female speaker believed that she uses it more often in conversations via the social media application Wechat than in regular face-to-face talk. A male speaker who uses the kinship term unconventionally explained that he uses it when talking to close friends. He said that it is an expression that can narrow the distance between speakers and he believes that his peers use the term also for this reason.

Many interviewees were aware of the unconventional usage of *baba* ‘dad’, even though some of them do not use it themselves. One interviewee who has children stated her confusion about the novel usage. Most young adults, regardless of whether they use it or not, claimed that they think people who are using *baba* ‘dad’ among peers are joking. Young interviewees with peers who use the term respond differently. One interviewee adopts this unconventional usage occasionally because she thinks it is popular among peers. There is a young male adult who does not use the term and maintained that people who use *baba* ‘dad’ as a self-reference among peers are crossing the line. He believed that he is a gentle person who knows the proper boundaries. He also explained that in order to be polite, he does respond to others who use this term when talking to him.

4.5 That Person *Renjia*: Seeking a Sweet Perspective

The finding that *renjia* ‘that person’ is irrelevant to age contradicts some speculations of scholars. However, the result that significantly more female speakers use *renjia* ‘that person’ as self-reference confirms the proposition that this expression is associated with gender. Many interviewees also expressed their impression that *renjia* ‘that person’ is associated with the female gender.

People use this self-reference for various reasons. Some examples provided by interviewees support the view of Cao (2018) that *renjia* ‘that person’ is used to express dissatisfaction and other emotions euphemistically. One interviewee stated that she uses *renjia* ‘that person’ when talking to family members or close friends. For instance, she may use it when talking to her husband in order to *sajiao* ‘act like a spoiled child’. An unmarried female in her early twenties also commented that she uses it to *sajiao*. She said, “I am a girl, and it is normal to use it.” A middle-aged female interviewee said that she uses the expression when she is arguing with others as in (10). A male interviewee in his sixties claimed that he uses *renjia* ‘that person’ as self-reference in informal situations such as at home and that he uses it when talking to family members or friends. Another male interviewee in his fifties mentioned that he uses the expression when he feels that he has been misunderstood. He uses it when talking to his wife as in (11).

(10) 你光考虑你自己了，你怎么不考虑考虑人家啊？

Ni guangkaolv ni ziji le, ni zenme bu kaolvkaolv renjia a?

You only think of yourself, but why don't you consider that person?

人家也有不高兴的时候啊。

Renjia ye you bu gaoxing de shihou a.

That person also has unhappy moments.

(11) 人家都说了不吃了，你干嘛还要给我盛啊？

Renjia dou shuole buchi le, ni ganma haiyao geiwo cheng a?

That person has already said that he doesn't want anymore, so why do you still offer me more to eat?

One interactional aim brought up by an interviewee but not mentioned in previous literature is that *renjia* ‘that person’ can be used to express personal opinions objectively. The interviewee uses it to express her opinion in a way that the listener can understand the situation and idea without noticing that it is her opinion.

Mandarin speakers who never use *renjia* ‘that person’ provided several reasons. Interviewees indicated that s/he does not use *renjia* ‘that person’ to call herself or himself because s/he is conventional or straightforward. Other interviewees stated that young girls are associated with *renjia* ‘that person’ and that since s/he is not in that age or gender group, s/he does not use it. One female speaker in her early twenties claimed that she does not use *renjia* ‘that person’ as self-reference because she thinks it is too affectedly sweet.

4.6 Old Man *Laozi*: Rough, but Powerful

The stereotypically vulgar expression *laozi* ‘old man’ is not correlated to educational background, which is somewhat different from the previous prediction. The frequency of using *laozi* ‘old man’ decreases with the advancement of degree levels, but

chi-squared test shows that it is not a statistically significant correlation. The frequency of referring to oneself with *laozi* ‘old man’ decreases with age and increases with income. The result shows that it is likely that some people use it, even though their identity contradicts the stereotypical association of the self-referential expression.

Even though *baba* ‘dad’ and *laozi* ‘old man’ could both mean *dad*, some people do not use them interchangeably as self-reference. The young female speaker who calls herself *baba* ‘dad’ to joke does not use the term *laozi* ‘old man’ because it is “too serious to be used for teasing or joking.” She claimed that it crosses the line and it is not as mild and acceptable as *baba* ‘dad’. She thinks it is weird that others call themselves *laozi* ‘old man’. Similarly, another young female adult held that even though she sometimes calls herself *baba* ‘dad’, she never calls herself *laozi* ‘old man’ because she thinks the latter is too masculine.

Some people declared that they use *laozi* ‘old man’ as self-reference. A young female adult who calls herself *baba* ‘dad’ also uses *laozi* ‘old man’ as self-reference. She commented that she used *laozi* ‘old man’ more often in the past and now she always uses the self-reference *baba* ‘dad’. She said that to her *laozi* ‘old man’ and *baba* ‘dad’ are interchangeable, despite her change of habit. A young male adult claimed that he uses *laozi* ‘old man’ when he is outraged or when he is quarreling with others. A middle-aged male speaker claimed that he uses *laozi* ‘old man’ as self-reference at home or with people he is familiar with in casual occasions. He said that it is normal for him to call himself *laozi* ‘old man’ because he is the head of the family. He is a white-collar worker and is not of low income.

During interviews, most interviewees verified the negative connotation of the expression. Most of them claimed that they do not use it because it is impolite, rude, disrespectful, vulgar, or insulting. A female speaker explained that it is an expression used by male speakers, and since she is aware of the boundary of gender, *laozi* ‘old man’ is not in her idiolect. One female speaker claimed that she does not have the occasion to use it as self-reference. A father claimed that he does not use *laozi* ‘old man’ in his conversations with his son, since he thinks that it is only used in fierce occasions and that his conversations are not fierce.

5. Using or Not Using Self-References

The interviews provide insights into understanding Mandarin self-reference. Some people claimed that they do not use any self-referential expressions other than *wo* ‘I’ at all, while there are people who use one term or several terms according to their specific communicative purposes. This section summarizes interview results generally.

There are several common reasons for not using a given self-referential expression. Some interviewees claimed that they do not use certain self-referential expressions not because of any negative opinions toward the expression but because they simply do not have the habit or the personality to say it. People who do not use a term for these reasons usually do not judge others who use the term.

Other people do not use an expression for the reason that they think the expression has a negative connotation. They claimed that using the expression as a self-reference is weird. Speakers assume that there is a certain connotation associated with calling oneself by this expression and that they do not use it because they do not want to have that personality association. It is worth noting that this assumed linkage with the expression sometimes is the exact reason why some people use the expression as self-reference. For instance, some people use *baobao* ‘baby’ for its connotation of young age, and some people do not use it because they think it is too childish.

Another reason for not using a particular self-referential expression is the lack of an appropriate situation or interlocutor. For instance, some speakers may think it is a written expression that is too formal to be spoken in daily conversations. In general, people do not use a certain self-reference because of their personality, their perception of the term, or because of the lack of the appropriate situation.

6. Discussion

This study contributes to our understanding of self-reference and confirms the general hypothesis that Mandarin Chinese speakers’ self-referential habits correlate with their social backgrounds. Using the five expressions as self-reference is an expansion of the semantic meaning and pragmatic usages of them. In general, whether and to what degree an individual accepts the expansion varies according to the demographic background of the Mandarin speaker. Specifically, the research sheds new light on the five Mandarin self-referential expressions *benren* ‘this person’, *baobao* ‘baby’, *baba* ‘dad’, *renjia* ‘that person’, and *laozi* ‘old man’. The five expressions in this study are more or less stereotypes, since there existed metalinguistic commentary. Note that speakers tend to have their own specific interpretation of the stereotypical meaning. The meanings of variants are not precise or fixed but they constitute an indexical field which is fluid (Eckert 2008). One understudied self-referential topic explored in this research is the unconventional usage of *baba* ‘dad’ and *laozi* ‘old man’. The novel usage challenges, exploits, and expands the dictionary-defined semantic domain that contains masculine and parent, in order to fulfill various functions such as teasing or sounding powerful.

Regarding the research method, this study extends the scope of self-referential studies to a testable level and discovers that some speaking habits are relevant to objective external factors as well as subjective internal considerations. Previous explorations of self-reference, for instance, the ones on communicative purposes, are by and large context-specific analyses. Generalizations have been made about the reasons certain self-referential expressions exist and when those expressions are used. This research has ventured beyond speculative analysis by combining the methods of quantitative analysis and interviews. It not only verifies or denies some speculative conclusions with statistical evidence, but also offers novel perspectives for understanding the phenomenon. The contradiction between speculation and empirical evidence suggests that referential studies should not be limited to speculative analysis.

In languages other than Chinese, people may refer to themselves by using expressions other than the canonical first-person singular pronoun. A study on English self-references has suggested the possible correlation between social identity and referring to oneself. Based on speeches by Abraham Lincoln, Field (2011) has found that Lincoln preferred to refer to himself with “we” instead of “I.” Field (2011) indicated that this kind of preference is relevant to Lincoln’s status of leadership, which implies that self-reference may relate to social status or representation of collectivity in English. In the present study, young female speakers use the masculine expressions *baba* ‘dad’ and *laozi* ‘old man’ to refer to themselves in order to sound powerful. Similarly, *dude*, an address term mostly used by men to address another man in English, has pragmatically expanded to be used by and to women (Kiesling 2004). Women adopting linguistic usages symbolizing masculinity could indicate women’s hope of gaining power cross-culturally. It would be interesting to view self-reference from a typological point of view. A cross-linguistic analysis of self-reference may provide insights on human cognition, psychology, culture, and society.

Using self-report survey and interviews are efficient and practical ways given the available resources of this study. However, on surveys, respondents sometimes may provide answers that they regard as socially acceptable and deny using forms that are associated with lower social status or with other negative perceptions. Interviewees might not admit that they use some self-reference because they feel there is a negative connotation, even though they provided information on linguistic behavior and linguistic ideology. Observations of actual language use are necessary to compensate for the limitation of self-report data. These observations could also provide insights about gender identity and role in Chinese society. Moreover, using *baba* ‘dad’ and *laozi* ‘old man’ among peers can be analyzed within the paradigm of peer socialization. With more evidence from observation, it could be argued that in a peer group, a group member who calls himself or herself by those expressions is more likely to be the peer member of “higher social status.” Also, besides analyzing Mandarin self-reference synchronically, it would be interesting to explore the longitudinal variation of using a given self-reference in the idiolect of a person.

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“這麼一 V”與“這麼 V 來”篇章表現差異及成因分析

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本文以關聯理論及語法化理論作為理論框架，著眼於構形相似的漢語構式“這麼一 V”與“這麼 V 來”，從 BCC 語料庫中選取動詞數量佔有絕對優勢的“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”作為主要研究對象，從語篇層面對兩種構式的篇章表現共性與差異進行比較分析。結合“語法化”發生條件及篇章標記語特征，本文將兩種構式劃分為“已語法化”及“未完全語法化”兩個類別。以關聯語境為視角對已語法化“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”語料的描寫對比，發現它們作為篇章標記語時具備回指及話輪轉換功能，故篇章表現一致且在篇章中可互換使用，繼而將“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”在篇章中不可互換使用情況，即篇章表現差異，歸因於兩種構式的語法化程度差異。通過對未完全語法化“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”的描寫與統計，發現“這麼一說/看”中動詞“說/看”保有實詞語義情況更多，且可與更為豐富的詞類及句法形式並置，說明“這麼一說/看”的語法化程度低於“這麼說/看來”。這一差異進而揭示出“這麼一 V”與“這麼 V 來”的篇章表現差異及成因，即“這麼一 V”的語法化程度低於“這麼 V 來”，因此“這麼一 V”中動詞保有實詞語義的情況更多，篇章表現更為豐富。基於對語料的描寫與分析，本文較為詳盡地揭示了“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”的篇章表現共性、差異及差異成因，在一定程度上填補了“這麼一 V”與“這麼 V 來”對比研究的空白，為關聯理論及語法化理論在語篇層面的研究發展提供了些許參考，並希望能夠對日後相似構式的對比研究有所啟示。

0. 引言

學界目前多從句法、語義角度，對單個構式所顯現的構式特點展開較為深入的分析研究。但已有研究存在些許缺陷，一是未對單個構式與相關構式展開比較分析；二是多關注於構式自身特點，從而忽視了實際用法及使用條件（周莉、曹玉瑤，2018）。尤其從語篇層面對相似構式的研究少之又少。為嘗試在一定程度上豐富構式研究，本文選取相似漢語構式“這麼一 V”與“這麼 V 來”作為研究對象，從語篇層面對二者的篇章表現進行比較分析。整合前人相關研究資料發現，目前暫無針對構式“這麼一 V”與“這麼 V 來”的比較研究，故本文可借鑒的研究成果多為前人對“這麼一 V”或“這麼 V 來”單個構式的研究，但針對二者的分析也不盡完善。就我們所搜索到的資料來看，“這麼 V 來”的相關研究極少，僅

儲韻（2016）從話語標記角度對“這麼說來”進行分析，而“這麼一V”的相關研究散見於“這麼”及其組配形式分析或形近構式“這樣一來”等研究中（參考：王穎穎，2013；武辰霞，2014；殷志平，2015等）。如王鳳蘭、方清明（2015）指出“這樣/麼一來”的句法位置只能是句首或句中，不能是句尾。且處在句首位置時，有一些可與連詞成分並置，說明它們有著各自的功能，也表明了前後邏輯關係，如“但這樣一來”，“因為這樣一來”。但其研究中並未明確定義“有一些可與連詞成分並置”中“有一些”的限定範圍，且未對可並置的連詞成分有所歸類介紹。本文將在“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”篇章表現之異部分，就二者可並置連詞成分進行比對、分析，進而尋找差異，分析差異成因。總言之，雖“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”構形相似，且兩種構式作為篇章標記語時，篇章表現相一致，但二者並非完全相同。而“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”的篇章表現差異從何體現？差異成因為何？本文將逐一解決這些問題。通過比較分析“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”的篇章表現，本文以期在一定程度上填補“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”比較研究的空白，並嘗試對相似構式的分析研究有所啟示。

為達持之以據，本文選取關聯理論及語法化理論作為理論框架。首先，我們先簡言介紹關聯理論。

關聯理論（Relevance Theory）由 Sperber and Wilson（1986）首次提出。沈家煊（1988）首次將關聯理論引入漢語研究。關聯理論認為交際是一種動態的認知活動，即“明示—推理”。交際中的信息一部分是明示的（指言者運用大量信息向聽者傳達其意圖），一部分則需要聽者推理得出（指聽者通過言者言語中傳達的信息去推斷言者的真實意圖）（Sperber and Wilson, 1986）。聽者除了要接收言者已明示的信息外，還要付出努力依靠語境假設去推理言者暗含的信息。如，言者說“約翰的警服被脫了”，明示信息為“約翰的警服（衣服）被別人脫下來了”，可推理得出的信息為“約翰失去了警員工作（職位）”。聽者除了要接收到“脫警服”的明示含義，還要付出努力接收到“脫警服”意味著“被開除、解雇”的暗含信息，其語境假設也就是“約翰因為失職或某些不當原因，導致自己被開除，所以他的“警服”被脫了”。也就是說，在關聯理論視角下，推理是語言交際的核心，即結合語境對話語進行解碼。

關聯理論與語用領域已結合得非常緊密，運用關聯理論分析篇章標記語的研究已日趨豐富。前人研究多肯定了應用關聯理論對話語標記語研究的重要性（參考：Blakemore, 1987、2002；Jucker, 1993；陳開舉，2002；馬蕭，2003；唐斌，2007；Schourup, 2011等）。莫愛屏（2004）提出關聯理論能夠為現有的話語理解理論作出補充，並證明應用關聯理論分析篇章標記語具有較強的解釋力。其依據在於關聯理論中語境是可變的，但關聯關係並不會隨其變動而完全消失，篇章標記語被視為尋找關聯關係的重要標記。莫文指出，在關聯理論框架下研究話語標記語，話語本身不一定需要某種連接手段取得連貫效果，連貫可以在尋找到某種語境關聯，獲得語境假設的情況下實現，且篇章標記語不僅具有連貫功能，其多功能性

需在不同語境中得以體現。由此，本文將結合前人經驗，在關聯理論框架下，以關聯語境為視角，在“這麼一 V”與“這麼 V 來”的篇章表現之同處，運用“明示—推理”方法展開分析研究。接下來，我們來看語法化理論。

“語法化”(Grammaticalization)這一概念首先由法國學者 Meillet 于 1912 年提出，“語法化”也被定義為在一個原來自自主的詞上附加語法屬性(趙學德、王晴, 2009)。沈家煊(1994)首次將語法化理論引入中國。他歸納了 Hopper (1991)“語法化”的五條原則，即 1) 並存原則。一種語法功能可具有多種語法表現形式，新舊表現形式可共存；2) 歧變原則。一個實詞可以往不同方向變為不同的語法成分；3) 擇一原則。在並存原則下，一個語法功能可有多種語法形式，但經過篩選後僅有一、二種形式被留下；4) 保持原則。實詞經歷虛化，成為一個語法成分後依然保持少量實詞特點；5) 降類原則。實詞從名詞、動詞經歷虛化後降類為助詞、介詞等。在此基礎上，沈文參考其他文獻又補充了四條原則，即 6) 滯後原則。語義變化先於語形變化，這也就是一詞多義存在的原因；7) 頻率原則。使用頻率越高越容易虛化，虛化後又增加了使用頻率；8) 漸變原則。一個 A 義的詞在虛化為 B 義的過程中，一定經歷 A-AB-B 的過程，虛化過程不是一蹴而就的；9) 單項循環原則。一個實詞在經歷極限的虛化後最終演變為一個跟實詞融合在一起的“零形式”。由此，“語法化”原則從五條擴展至九條。

在語法化理論框架下分析話語標記語的形成研究已較為廣泛。吳福祥(2005)指出話語標記語的產生就是一種典型的語法化現象。馮光武(2005)指出語法化理論能給話語標記語和語用/語義介面的研究帶來啟示，我們要對語用標記語展開語法化的考察。馮文指出語用標記語是語法化過程的產物，它們是一個連續體，並經歷了從實義向語用功能義的單向轉變。Brinton(1996)對中古英語話語標記語的個案研究證明了話語標記語的演化遵循語法化的三個趨勢，實現從命題功能向語篇功能再到人際功能的轉變(轉引自楊國萍、向明友、許碩, 2017)。這三個趨勢也就是“語法化”發生的三個條件：1) 語義空泛。以“來”為例，在經歷語法化前，“來”就是語義泛化的動詞，遵守歧變原則虛化出多種用法；2) 高頻使用。遵守頻率原則，實詞使用頻率越高，越容易虛化；3) 句法和語義條件。指結構式中的語法化，語法化不僅指詞彙在特定情境中的虛化，還涉及它所在的結構式，如短語或構式等更大語段的變化(穀峰, 2008)。本文將借鑒前人研究經驗，結合“語法化”發生的三個條件及 Hölker 指出的篇章標記語的四個特徵：1) 不對話語真值條件產生影響；2) 不增加話語命題內容；3) 篇章標記語與話語發生時的情形有關，與話語內容中涉及的情形無關；4) 篇章標記語具有連貫功能，但不具有認知、指稱等功能(Jucker and Ziv, 1998; 轉引自殷樹林, 2012)。從而判斷本文研究對象“這麼一 V”與“這麼 V 來”是否完全語法化為篇章標記語，若並未完全語法化為篇章標記語，本文將對其保留的詞彙義和句法義現象進行分析。

最後，本文分為以下五個部分：1) 引言。簡要介紹本文研究對象、研究現狀及理論框架；2) 數據構成。主要介紹本文數據來源及數據篩選準則；3) “這麼

一V”與“這麼V來”篇章表現之同。主要介紹“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”篇章表現相一致部分；4）“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”篇章表現之異。主要介紹“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”篇章表現相異之處及差異成因；5）結論。本文將“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”篇章表現之同及之異部分所得小結加以整合得出全文結論。

1. 數據構成

本文以北京語言大學現代漢語語料庫（BCC）作為數據來源，以真實的自然語料為分析對象，比較分析“這麼一V”（如例1所示）與“這麼V來”（如例2所示）的篇章表現差異。

（1）“…如今老師已有充分理由憎恨我了。”這麼一想，我心頭驀地湧起了一股稀奇古怪的喜悅。（三島由紀夫/金閣寺）

（2）克萊德一聽到這個扯兒，心中不由得暗自思忖起來。這麼說來，晚宴以後，他們個個吃飽喝足了，就要去一個所謂“窩兒”的地方——准是一個下流場所。（希歐多爾·德萊塞/美國的悲劇）

以例（1）、（2）中“這麼一想”及“這麼說來”為例，本文研究對象“這麼一V”指“這麼+一+動詞”，“這麼V來”指“這麼+動詞+來”。

通過資料統計發現，在“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”中，動詞“V”種類豐富且數量龐大，如單音節動詞（想、劃、讓、寫、辦、勸、弄等）、雙音節動詞（發表、轉念、琢磨安排、提醒、拾掇等）、動詞短語（豎起來、定下來、早起來等）。我們發現指示代詞“這麼”與動詞短語搭配形式中的“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”均未完全語法化。依據在於，結合“語法化”發生的三個條件及篇章標記語的四個特徵來看，“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”並非整體粘著構式，且動詞“V”謂詞義明確，構式自身具備指稱功能、影響話語命題內容及真值條件，故不可刪除。在我們搜索到的語料中，我們發現這些搭配形式使用頻率極少。因此，這些“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”均未完全語法化為篇章標記語，不具備篇章功能，故篩除與“這麼一V”及“這麼V來”篇章功能無關的形式，並不在文內做詳細討論，具體包括：

1. 指示代詞“這麼”與豐富的動詞短語搭配。如：否定+這麼+形容詞+動詞，“不這麼早起來”；這麼+V來V去，“這麼奔來跑去”；這麼+動詞短語+了，“這麼定下來了”等。以上形式中的“這麼V來”均非整體黏著並獨立於前後句的結構，且“V”為表義實在的動詞或動詞短語。“這麼V來”整體具有詞彙義，增加話語命題內容，若刪除，話語真值條件即被改變，不符合篇章標記語特徵。因此，“這麼”與保有動詞義的動詞或動詞短語搭配的形式均不可作篇章標記語。

2. 當動詞“說”進入“這麼一V”構式，有一類特殊情況，即“說”作名詞，指“說法”。如“有這麼一說沒有？”與“有你這麼一說！”。這兩個小句中數詞“一”均未虛化，修飾作名詞的“說”，指“一種說法”。此類“這麼一說”亦不可做篇章標記語，故不作為本文的考察對象。

此外，本文共搜索到“這麼一V”數據 1360 條，“這麼V來”數據 368 條。將能夠進入“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”中的全部動詞“V”進行窮盡式搜索及分析是本文篇幅所無法承載的，因此，通過統計動詞種類及數量，我們發現動詞“說”與“看”在“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”中佔有絕對數量優勢，具有典型性，具體表現為動詞“說/看”進入“這麼一V”中共有 638 條數據，佔比 46.91%，進入“這麼V來”中共有 358 條數據，佔比 97.28%。除“說/看”外，其他動詞進入“這麼一V”中共有 722 條數據，佔比 53.09%，進入“這麼V來”中共有 10 條數據，佔比 2.72%。因此，“說/看”在“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”中是佔有絕對數量優勢的動詞，故本文選取“說/看”作為主要研究動詞，進而分別對“這麼一說”、“這麼一看”、“這麼說來”、“這麼看來”四個具體構式進行檢索、比對及分析。

2. “這麼一V”與“這麼V來”的篇章表現之同

從結構出發，“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”均緊密黏著成一個整體並獨立於前後句，有明顯標點符號將“這麼一說/看”及“這麼說/看來”與前後句隔開（如例 3、4 所示）。因“這麼一說/看”及“這麼說/看來”獨立於前後句格式一致，均由標點隔開，故僅選取“這麼一說”及“這麼說來”例句以示格式。

(3) “…我想是這樣吧，問這個幹嗎？”“因為，這麼一說，我幹了坑人的事啦！”接著她說了事情經過。（湯瑪斯·哈代/無名的裘德）

(4) 沈老說，專業幅度相差很大，既有文學、哲學、宗教，也有數學、工程、化學，記不太清了。這麼說來，他其實是在人類的知能天域中漂泊了，但他哪兒也不想駐足，像穿了那雙紅鞋子，一路跳下去。（餘秋雨/漂泊者們）

在“這麼一說/看”中，“說”與“看”經說話人主觀化表達後演變出認知義，在“這麼說/看來”中，“說來”及“看來”的語法化主要表現為“說”及“看”的主觀化及“來”的隱喻化（李治平，2014）。由此，已語法化的“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”在篇章中僅作標記話題的篇章標記語。本文這一部分主要關注二者作為篇章標記語時，篇章表現相同之處。

總體看來，“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”作為篇章標記語時，均可置於敘述及對話兩類語段中。置於敘述中時，“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”具有回指功能，並具有連貫前後小句及句群，達到語義邏輯連貫，從而進一步推進語篇進程的作用（如例 5 所示）；置於對話中時，“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看

來”具有話輪轉換功能：1) 承接話題，推動原話題的進一步延續（如例 6 所示）；2) 轉換話題，聽話人承接話輪後轉換為說話人，繼而轉換當前話題並引出與話題相關的新信息。且“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”體現不出說話人明顯的前後句語義邏輯關係，聽話人須依託關聯原則及話語理解原則進行信息解碼，從而達到前後句間邏輯關係連貫的功能（如例 7 所示）。下面我們結合例句逐一分析：

(5) “聽聽，這丫頭多不知道客臊？哪兒有小姑子當媒人的？我們請了正經的‘古瓦西’！”韓太太也笑了。女賓們卻說新月去合適，模樣兒又體面，又是新郎的親妹妹，再好不過了。這麼一說，似乎顯得韓太太的資格倒差了點兒似的。（霍達/穆斯林的葬禮）

例(5)中，為達簡潔，我們將“這麼一說”前的小句稱之為前句，“這麼一說”後的小句稱之為後句。“這麼一說”作為篇章標記語連貫前後句，並回指“女賓們說新月去合適”的“話”。“這麼一說”前句中的新信息“又是新郎的親妹妹”與現時語境“哪兒有小姑子當媒人的？”相矛盾，符合何自然(1995)提出的新信息足以影響現時語境假設時需要聽話人付出努力才能獲得語境假設。

根據關聯理論中“明示—推理”，需要聽話人付出努力推理得出信息為：顯得“韓太太資格差”的原因並不是把她和“模樣兒體面的新月”進行模樣上的對比，而是把“新郎的妹妹新月”與“有資格請正經“古瓦西”的韓太太”進行地位上的對比。“這麼一說”制約著理解話語時的直接聯想（莫愛屏，2004）。同時，“這麼一說”也體現出說話人主觀判斷的因果關係，即因為“女賓們說新月去合適”，所以“倒顯得韓太太資格倒差了點兒”。此外，作為篇章標記語的“這麼一說”並不為原語段增加語義，刪除也無妨。若將“這麼一說”替換為“這麼說來”，“這麼說來”連貫前後句，並回指“女賓們”說的“話”。後句中的“似乎”體現說話人主觀上的推斷，即“女賓們說新月去合適”的話使得“韓太太資格倒顯得差了點兒”。若刪去“這麼說來”，前後句語義邏輯不受到影響，話語真值條件不受到改變。因此，“這麼一說”與“這麼說來”在這一情境下可互換使用。接下來看例句(6)。

(6) A: “你那可愛的未婚妻呀。有一些女士就是討厭人家闖進她們的廚房。” B: “瑪茜在這方面倒是挺隨便的，”我說。瑪茜早已開心得歡蹦亂跳了。 A: “那太好了。這麼一看，沒說的，她准是個挺可愛的姑娘。她叫瑪茜，是不是？嗨，奧利弗……你看她會喜歡我嗎？”（埃裡奇·西格爾/奧利弗的故事）

例(6)中，說話人 B 指出“瑪茜在這方面挺隨便的”的明示信息為“瑪茜不像其他女士一樣討厭別人闖進廚房”，需要說話人 A 推理得出的暗含信息為

“瑪茜允許別人進她的廚房”。A 承接當前話題，引出“她准是個可愛的姑娘”，進而延續話題。“這麼一看”體現出說話人主觀推測的因果邏輯關係。因為“瑪茜不像其他女士，她不討厭別人進她的廚房”，所以說話人得出“她與其他女士不同，她准是個可愛的姑娘”的推論。若將“這麼一看”替換為“這麼看來”，“這麼看來”承接話題，連貫前後句且不增加話語命題內容。若將“這麼看來”刪去也不影響話語真值條件，因此，“這麼一看”與“這麼看來”可互換使用。最後再來看例句（7）。

（7）A：“你穿著白大褂，凝視著試管裡的鮮血，這樣的身影一定很美吧。”B：“我一看見血，就會想像著獻血或需要輸血的人，有時心裡覺得很奇怪。”A：“你說奇怪……”B：“想到人因為那些鮮紅的液體或生或死……”A：“嗯。”圭次點點頭，端起酒杯。“這麼看來，我的工作很平凡啊。”（渡邊淳一/野蒿園）

“這麼看來”前句說話人 B 明示信息為“看見血心裡覺得奇怪的原因是會有人因為這鮮紅的液體或生或死”，說話人 A 需要推導得出的信息為“穿著白大褂，作為醫生（或護士）要面對生死，也不是一件容易的事情”，根據關聯原則及話語理解原則，說話人 A 依靠語境假設充分理解信息後得出主觀推論“與要面對生死的工作比起來，自己的工作很平凡”。“這麼看來”前後句間無明顯邏輯關係，僅聽話人身份轉換後轉換話題，從而在後句中引入主觀結論（新信息）。若將“這麼看來”替換為“這麼一看”，“這麼一看”前後句無明顯邏輯關係，“這麼一看”不為前後句增加命題內容，刪除“這麼一看”也無妨。由此，“這麼一看”與“這麼看來”都遵從關聯原則與話語理解原則。聽話人需要從若干語義中選擇一個付出最小努力且獲得足夠語境效果的表達，作為對說話人話語意圖的推論。

綜合上述分析，已語法化的“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”在篇章中表現為緊密粘著的整體，且作為篇章標記語時，二者均可置於敘述及對話語段，並分別具有回指功能及話輪轉換功能。已語法化的“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”均表達了說話人的主觀推測，這符合篇章標記語具備主觀性的特點，即篇章標記語反應出說話人與話語單位間的關係或話語單位與語境間關係的主觀認識（董秀芳，2007）。若將“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”刪除，原句話語真值條件及話語命題內容均不受到影響，由此說明“說/看”的謂詞語義虛化，不具備實詞含義，也說明“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”具備篇章標記語特徵。已語法化的“這麼一說”、“這麼一看”、“這麼說來”、“這麼看來”篇章表現相同，均可互換使用。而與之對應的“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”功能相異時，兩種構式的篇章表現有何差異？差異成因為何？這是本文在明晰已語法化“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”篇章表現之同的基礎上，進一步要探究解決的問題。

3. “這麼一V”與“這麼V來”的篇章表現之異

3.1 未完全語法化“這麼一說/看”的篇章表現

“這麼一說/看”未完全語法化的表現為不具有篇章標記語的身份及功能，即 1) 若刪除“這麼一說/看”，影響話語真值條件；2) “這麼一說/看”增加話語命題內容；3) “這麼一說/看”具有認知功能；4) “這麼一說/看”與話語內容中的語境有關。結合例(8)具體來看：

(8) “假設，我們的遊行示威成為扳機，引發了諸如發生在墨西哥城的三元文化廣場上的大屠殺，那該怎麼辦呢？與六十年代和七十年代在東京實際發生的事件相比……不，那種慘狀根本就無法比較。”這麼一說呀，他們就會說出這樣的話來：“可是，即便如此，在日本不是什麼也沒有得到改變嗎？！就像墨西哥沒有發生任何變化一樣。（大江健三郎/愁容童子）

“這麼一說呀”中“這麼”指前句的“話”，即“…那種慘狀根本就無法比較”，“這麼一說呀”是“他們就會說出這樣的話來”的原因，即後句“這樣的話來”中“話”的內容（“可是，…”），是根據前句話語內容做出的回應。“說”具有言說義，若刪除“這麼一說”，話語真值條件被改變，前後句話語內容無因果邏輯關係，前後句語義不連貫。

由此，“這麼一說/看”均並未完全語法化為一緊密粘著整體，在篇章中不可作為篇章標記語。“說/看”的動詞義未完全虛化，如“說”具有言說義、“看”具有行為義。在我們的語料中，具有詞彙義的“這麼一說/看”可分別與連詞、副詞、名詞性成分/名詞短語、動詞短語、趨向補語、及被動結構並置。

3.1.1 與連詞並置

“這麼一說/看”可與三類連詞並置：表轉折類連詞（如“但是”、“然而”）、表順承類連詞（如“因為”）、表假設類連詞（如“要是”），並通過連詞表達篇章內邏輯關係。因篇章內邏輯關係主要由三類連詞表達，故限於篇幅，僅以轉折類連詞“但是”（如例9所示）及“然而”示例（如例10所示）。

(9) 吾來說怎麼樣深繪裡都是一個實體。但是這麼一說，確實也有那樣的可能性。（村上春樹/1Q84BOOK3）

“這麼一說”是連詞“但是”所連接後句中的動詞成分，“這麼”指“吾來”說的“怎麼樣深繪裡都是一個實體”這句話。連詞連接兩個動詞性成分時，前一個動詞性成分往往表示後一個動詞性成分的原因或方式（李譜英，1977）。“但

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是”連接的前句中“吾來說”是後句中“這麼一說”言說的方式，“這麼一說”中“說”作謂語動詞，言說義未虛化。

(10) 一剎那間，我還穿透那雙眼睛，窺探了一下她的靈魂深處，我腦子裡一亮：莫非這就是“她”的女兒……然而這麼一看以後，要她收我的錢是不行了。（普裡什文/大自然的日曆）

“這麼一看”前的“然而”是表轉折義的連詞。“這麼一看”中“這麼”指“我窺探她靈魂深處”的方式是“穿透那雙眼睛窺探的”，“看”與“窺探”對應；且“這麼一看”後置時間副詞“以後”，副詞前要有動詞進行修飾，故“看”具有動詞義。

3.1.2 與副詞並置

“這麼一說/看”可與四類副詞並置：時間副詞（如例 11 所示）、範圍副詞（如例 12 所示）、方向副詞（如例 13 所示）、方式副詞（如例 14 所示）。

(11) 便開口說道：“那可真是不可思議的音樂！我剛這麼一說，阿紗就笑了起來。（大江健三郎/愁容童子）

“我剛這麼一說”中，“我”是主語，時間副詞“剛”作狀語修飾動詞，“這麼”指前句中說的“話”，即“那可真是不可思議的音樂”。“說”作謂語動詞，言說義未虛化。

(12) 其實也沒有什麼傷口，但總要這麼一說來表示關心。所以她就用麻紗手絹蘸了樹葉上的露水，揩去了手腕上的綠印。（王小波/青銅時代）

“但總要這麼一說來表示關心”中，“總要”是範圍副詞，“來表示關心”是後置的目的狀語，都用來修飾動詞“說”，“這麼”指“說”的話，“說”作謂語動詞，言說義未虛化。

(13) 倖存者上片之下半耳。左右這麼一看，何《臨江仙》之有哉，直《如夢令》耳。（俞平伯/古槐夢遇）

“左右這麼一看”中，“左右”為方向副詞，修飾動詞“看”，且“看”具有空間上的動詞義，即從左看到右。

(14) 我父親到學校裡去查問成績的時候，先生老實地這麼一說，父親氣的要叫我停學，站櫃臺學徒去。（冰心/冰心全集第二卷）

“先生老實地這麼一說”中，“先生”是主語，“老實地”是方式副詞作情態狀語，修飾動詞“說”，“這麼”指說的“話”，“說”作謂語動詞，言說義未虛化。

3.1.3 與名詞性成分/名詞短語並置

(15) “我的錢不夠買兩張的。”我這麼一說，良子就說還是爬鐵絲網進去算了，便叫上一樣沒錢買票的和夫朝後面走去。（村上龍/無限近似于透明的藍）

(16) “沒事沒事。”碧雲這麼一說，心裡覺得十分窩囊（格非/江南三部曲）

“我這麼一說”及“碧雲這麼一說”中，“我”及“碧雲”分別是名詞性成分及專有名詞，均作主語。“這麼”指前句中說的“話”，即“我的錢不夠買兩張的”及“沒事沒事”。“說”作謂語動詞，言說義未虛化。

3.1.4 與動詞短語並置

(17) “哎呀，你看襪子都掛破了。”聽人這麼一說，直美才發現黑色連褲襪的膝蓋被掛破了一個洞，…”（川端康成/花的日記）

(18) “…這問題之難於解決，就像是那三隻戒指一樣叫人無從下個判斷。”薩拉丁聽他這麼一說，就知道那個猶太人十分機智，已躲避了他設下的圈套。（薄伽丘/十日談）

“聽人這麼一說”及“聽他這麼一說”是動賓結構，謂語動詞“聽”與賓語兼主語的“人”及“他”分別組成動詞短語，“這麼”分別指前句中說的“話”，即“哎呀，你看襪子都掛破了”與“…這問題之難於解決，…”。“說”作謂語動詞，言說義未虛化。

3.1.5 與趨向補語並置

“這麼一說/看”與趨向補語並置時，因數據中無“這麼一說”與“這麼一看”的例句，故選取與“看”有相交叉含義的“瞧”（瞧：解釋作“看”）進行論述。

(19) 一會兒他回來，腋下挾著個竹籃。他把竹籃隨手擱在爐旁。我往裡這麼一瞧，哇，有貨！那些長長的傢伙，大概是太冷，扭成一堆，滾成一團啣！（夏目漱石/我是貓）

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“我往裡這麼一瞧”中，“我”是主語，“往裡”是“瞧”的趨向補語，作狀語修飾動詞“瞧”，狀語“往裡”位於主語“我”與謂語“瞧”之間，“這麼”指“瞧”的方式是“往裡”，“瞧”作謂語動詞，表示“看”的動詞義未虛化。

3.1.6 與被動結構並置

(20) “素不相識的人突然跑來，說些這樣荒誕無稽的話，你聽了肯定非常困惑。”被他這麼一說，密擠出僵硬的笑容。（岩井俊二/華萊士人魚）

“被他這麼一說”是表示被動的主謂句，“他”作為施事，“這麼”指前句說的“話”，即“素不相識的人突然跑來…”。“說”作謂語動詞被狀語成分修飾，言說義未虛化。

(21) 安朱利厄利聽他居然說出這種話來，簡直氣昏了，尤其是當著這許多旁觀者，給他這麼一說，人家果真猜疑地打量起他來了，仿佛福塔利戈並沒輸去了他的錢，倒像是他安朱利厄利扣住了他的錢一般。（薄伽丘/十日談）

“給他這麼一說”是表示被動的主謂句，介詞“給”與“被”同義，“他”作為施事，“這麼”指說的“話”，“說”作謂語動詞被狀語成分修飾，言說義未虛化。

綜上所述，未完全語法化的“這麼一說/看”在篇章中不作篇章標記語、無回指及話輪轉換功能，但可與連詞、副詞、名詞性成分/名詞短語、動詞短語、趨向補語、被動結構等詞類及句法形式並置表達實詞語義。

3.2 未完全語法化“這麼說/看來”的篇章表現

“未完全語法化”表現為“這麼說/看來”不作篇章標記語，即“這麼說/看來”不是緊密黏著的整體，無回指及話輪轉換功能。“這麼說/看來”中的“說/看”動詞義明顯，“說”具有言說義，“看”具有行為義。由此，未完全語法化的“這麼說/看來”可分別與助詞（如例 22 所示）、介詞（方式介詞，如例 23 所示）、副詞（如例 24 所示）、動詞短語（如例 25 所示）並置表達實詞含義。

3.2.1 與助詞並置

(22) “也許你應當這麼說來的。”亞當站起身，在房裡走著，…（亞瑟·黑利/汽車城）

“也許你應當這麼說來的”中，“也許”是插入語，“你”是主語，“應當”是助動詞，表“應該”，“這麼”指說的“話”，“來”虛化后可省略，且省

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略後不影響句子的話語真值條件，即“也許你應當這麼說的”，其中“你應當這麼說的”是主謂結構，“的”作句末助詞，“說”作謂語動詞，言說義未虛化。

3.2.2 與介詞並置

(23) 有了這一大堆情況，事情就好理解了。一個非常有錢、非常漂亮的女人愛上了他。沃爾特爵士似乎承認，照這麼說來完全可以諒解。（簡·奧斯丁/勸導）

“照這麼說來完全可以諒解”中，“照”作介詞，指“按照”，“照這麼”作方式狀語修飾言說義動詞“說”，“這麼”指說的“話”，“來”虛化后可省略，且省略後不影響句子的話語真值條件，即“照這麼說完全可以諒解”。“說”作謂語動詞，言說義未虛化。

3.2.3 與副詞並置

(24) 方老三瞧一眼老伴熱切期待的眼睛，慢慢解開黃帆布挎包兒的系帶兒，把那三樣東西取了出來，擱在老伴面前：“就這麼說來！”老伴睜著發癡的眼睛，張著脫落了牙齒的嘴，一下怔住了。（陳忠實/心事重重）

“就這麼說來”中，副詞“就”修飾動詞“說”，“這麼”指說的“話”，“來”虛化后可省略，且省略後不影響句子的話語真值條件，即“就這麼說”。“說”作謂語動詞，言說義未虛化。

3.2.4 與動詞短語並置

(25) 卡格裡奧斯特羅說，“腦袋上挨一斧頭，就一了百了嘍。”餐廳裡響起了一片恐怖的尖叫聲。黎塞留和塔韋爾奈先生哀求卡格裡奧斯特羅別走得太遠了，但最終，他還是屈服在女性的好奇心下。“聽您這麼說來，說真的，伯爵，…”（大仲馬/王后的項鍊）

動賓結構“聽您這麼說來”中，謂語動詞“聽”與主語兼賓語“您”組成動詞短語，“這麼”指“說”的話，“來”虛化后表達所說“話”的來源，“來”可省略，且省略後不影響句子的話語真值條件，即“聽您這麼說”。“說”作謂語動詞，言說義未虛化。

綜上所述，未完全語法化的“這麼說/看來”在篇章中不可作篇章標記語、無回指及話輪轉換功能，但可分別與助詞、介詞、副詞、動詞短語並置表達實詞含義，“說/看”保有謂詞語義。

3.3 “這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”篇章表現差異成因

綜合上述分析發現，“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”的篇章表現存在諸多差異，即二者不可互換之處。究其原因，我們發現，篇章表現差異源於語法化程度差異，語法化程度差異正是通過它們分別可與不同詞類及句法形式並置得以體現。

未完全語法化的“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”均未完全符合“語法化”發生條件及篇章標記語特徵。依據在於，“說/看”動詞義未虛化，二者均保有明顯謂詞語義，且“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”均影響話語命題內容及真值條件，故不可刪除。未完全語法化的“這麼一說/看”可與連詞、介詞、副詞、名詞短語/名詞性成分、動詞短語、趨向補語、及被動結構並置；未完全語法化的“這麼說/看來”可與助詞、介詞、副詞、動詞短語並置。故表義實在的“這麼一說/看”可並置的詞類及句法形式比“這麼說/看來”更為豐富，說明“這麼一說/看”保有謂詞語義的情況更多。因此，“這麼一說/看”的語法化程度更低。

同時，就我們所搜索到的數據來看，“這麼一說/看”的 638 條數據中，“這麼一說”有 627 條，“這麼一看”有 11 條，其中，未完全語法化的“這麼一說”有 572 條，佔比 91.23%，未完全語法化的“這麼一看”有 8 條，佔比 72.73%；“這麼說/看來”的 358 條數據中，“這麼說來”有 310 條，“這麼看來”有 48 條，其中，未完全語法化的“這麼說來”有 51 條，佔比 16.45%，未完全語法化的“這麼看來”有 1 條，佔比 2.1%。因此，“這麼一說”與“這麼一看”未完全語法化數量占比遠高於“這麼說來”與“這麼看來”，故“這麼一說/看”的語法化程度低於“這麼說/看來”。因此，“這麼一說/看”可與更為豐富的詞類及句法形式並置。我們還發現，未完全語法化的“這麼說來”與“這麼看來”數量占比小，說明使用頻率少，也就說明已語法化的“這麼說來”與“這麼看來”數量占比大，使用頻率高；同理，未完全語法化的“這麼一說”與“這麼一看”數量占比大，使用頻率高，說明已語法化的“這麼一說”與“這麼一看”數量占比小，使用頻率小。由此，我們判斷“這麼說/看來”與“這麼一說/看”遵守語法化“頻率原則”，語法化程度越高，使用頻率越大，二者呈正相關關係。

4. 結論

綜合上述分析，得到結論如下：首先，已語法化的“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”均符合篇章標記語特徵，整體粘著為獨立整體且刪除無妨，既不影響話語真值條件，也不影響話語命題內容。與此同時，說明二者均具備“語法化”發生條件，即“說/看”語義泛化不具備謂詞語義，且已語法化的“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”遵守“頻率原則”，使用頻率與語法化程度呈正相關關係。由此，已語法化的“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”均可作為篇章標記語使用，同時二者篇章表現一致，均可互換使用。

其次，除“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”篇章表現一致可互換使用外，“這麼說/看來”與“這麼一說/看”的語法化程度差異致使它們存在不可互換的情

況。未完全語法化的“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”表現為“說/看”具有明顯謂詞語義，且“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”可與不同詞類及句法形式並置表達實義，若刪除會影響話語命題及話語真值條件。“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”的語法化程度差異體現為“這麼一說/看”可並置的詞類及句法形式比“這麼說/看來”更為豐富，說明“這麼一說/看”保有實詞含義的情況更多，“這麼一說/看”的語法化程度更低。由此，未完全語法化“這麼一說/看”的篇章表現更為豐富。

最後，我們從“這麼說/看來”與“這麼一說/看”的分析結果反觀“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”得到以下結論：“這麼說/看來”與“這麼一說/看”的篇章表現差異及差異成因，在一定程度上說明了“這麼V來”與“這麼一V”的篇章表現差異及語法化程度差異，即“這麼一V”的篇章表現比“這麼V來”豐富，“這麼一V”的語法化程度低於“這麼V來”。同時，除動詞“說/看”外，其他動詞進入“這麼一V”及“這麼V來”中的數量及佔比說明了“這麼一V”中“V”的種類數量較“這麼V來”而言更為豐富，因此“這麼一V”的篇章表現更為豐富。綜上所述，“這麼一說/看”與“這麼說/看來”的篇章表現差異及差異成因進一步證明了“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”的篇章表現差異及差異成因。本文從“語法化”角度對“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”的篇章表現差異及成因進行了分析研究，但“這麼一V”與“這麼V來”的篇章表現差異是否僅源於語法化程度差異，我們還可考慮從生成差異切入分析。總言之，本文以期有更為深入且多方面的分析，從而進一步推進相似構式的篇章功能研究。

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Research Trends in Chinese Linguistics from 2000 to 2020: Combining Bibliometric Analysis and Expert Opinions

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Chinese linguistics has a long tradition and gained international recognition. Against this backdrop, the current paper investigates the research trend in Chinese linguistics by analyzing the bibliometric data in both Chinese publications and English publications between 2000 and 2020. It is found that Chinese publications place more emphasis on morphology and syntax. The interactive construction grammar will be a trendy topic. On the other hand, the English publications deal more with psycholinguistic and quantitative issues. Bilingualism and neurolinguistics will gain popularity. Implications of this difference are also discussed.

1. Introduction

Linguistic research in China sprouted in the first prime of Chinese intellectual history. Rudimentary research can be found in the works of pre-qin scholars such as Xunzi, dating back to more than two thousand years ago (Wang 1989). Since then, a native tradition in Chinese linguistics began to take root. Drawing on the documents collected uninterruptedly, this tradition has made tremendous discoveries and contributions in philology, phonology, and grammatology (Wang 1981).

At the same time, such an indigenous tradition is not without limitations. As Wang (2006b) pointed out, in the second millennium, linguistic research in China greatly fell behind, as compared to the counterpart in the West. In the late 1800s, the native Chinese linguistics finally encountered linguistics from the West under the background of the drastic decline of Chinese's position in the world. In a hundred years that followed, Chinese linguistics was thoroughly influenced by the Western linguistics and the progress in Chinese linguistics was primarily achieved under the guidance of the theories in general linguistics (Wang 1981, p. 173; Chen 2018).

In the interaction of the two traditions in linguistics, Chinese linguistics has acquired a dual identity: one as the linguistics and philology passed on by Chinese scholars and another as the introduction of the methods in general linguistics to the languages found in China (Wang 1993). In 1973 and 1992 respectively, Chinese linguistics started to find its own voice and found its own association at the international level (Wang 1973, 1993).

Coming into the 21st century, Chinese linguistics is aiming to establish an international presence and contribute to the global academia (Ma 2004; Liu 2018). For example, between 2014 and 2016, in as little as three years of time, Chinese linguistics has witnessed four major volumes including two handbooks and two encyclopedias printed by major publishing houses (Jiao 2018).

2. The debate

As Chinese linguistics is on the way to the international arena at the turn of the 21st century, scholars in the field expressed their concerns by raising two intertwined questions: where Chinese linguistics should move forward and how Chinese linguistics should interact with general linguistics or so-call Western linguistics (Guo 1996; Pan 2008).

In particular, the interaction between the indigenous research tradition and modern linguistic theories often causes tension, as seen clearly in a debate between Pan (2000) and Han and Yan (2002) in the same journal. In the worst case, it may end up with one group of scholars ignoring the native scholarship while another group of linguists abandoning linguistic theory entirely (Lee 2000).

Making an either-or choice of academic tradition will not be wise. As the prominent Chinese linguist Wang Li once remarked: the scholars of Chinese grammar should have two types of training: one in Chinese philology and the other in general linguistics. Neither is dispensable. The work produced by a scholar with the mere command of Chinese philology will at best be a new dictionary. On the other hand, merely mastering general linguistics may commit the errors of fitting facts to theories in an arbitrary way (Wang 1985, p. 19).

3. The current study

Although the debate has been going on for some time, empirical data for the development of Chinese linguistics based on bibliometric data remain scarce. For example, Song (2012) examined the publications on Chinese linguistics in nine Chinese journals. The author found articles on grammar take up the majority. In addition, publications on general linguistics are lacking and cross-disciplinary research is only at the periphery. Another study by Wang and Xu (2014) analyzed the publications on linguistics in Chinese Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) between 2000 and 2011. They found the Chinese academia focused on the topics of grammar, language teaching, cognitive linguistics, systemic functional linguistics, and dialect.

Motivated by the previous discussion on the future of Chinese linguistics, the current study aims to provide some insight into two crucial questions regarding the future of Chinese linguistics: where Chinese linguistics should move forward and how indigenous Chinese linguistics interacts with West linguistics.

First, the study conducts a bibliometric analysis of the publications on Chinese linguistics to identify the research trend. The study focuses exclusively on research topics

and research trend, unlike previous studies which also considered researchers, institutions, and journals (Song 2012; Wang and Xu 2014; Li and Xu 2018). In addition, the research trend is analyzed from a comparative perspective. The publications in Chinese journals and English journals are used as proxies for the two different linguistic traditions. Finally, the study incorporates both quantitative data and experts' intuition. While many well-versed scholars have voiced their opinions and expectations about the future of Chinese linguistics, few studies provided empirical basis (Chen and Ma 2015).

The study intends to contribute to Chinese linguistics by identifying important articles, topics, and trend. It also hopes to find out how the Chinese tradition and Western tradition interact. It is hoped that this study will serve as reference for students of Chinese linguistics to make them aware and think about the two linguistic traditions as their research agenda is taking shape.

The study answers four research questions: 1. what are the important works in Chinese linguistics? 2. what are the hot topics in Chinese linguistics? 3. what is the research trend in Chinese linguistics? 4. how do the indigenous Chinese tradition differ from the Western tradition as seen in the publications?

4. Method

4.1 Data

To make the results comparable, the Chinese publications and English publications on Chinese linguistics were taken from linguistic journals in the Chinese Social Sciences Citation Index (CSSCI) and Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) respectively. The two databases included high-quality works in social sciences and provided detailed bibliometric data.

Ten Chinese journals, which are listed in CSSCI in 2020, were selected as the source. These include 世界汉语教学 (*Chinese Teaching in the World*), 中国语文 (*Studies of the Chinese Language*), 古汉语研究 (*Research in Ancient Chinese Language*), 方言 (*Dialect*), 语文研究 (*Linguistic Research*), 语言教学与研究 (*Language Teaching and Linguistic Studies*), 语言文字应用 (*Applied Linguistics*), 语言研究 (*Studies in Language and Linguistics*), 语言科学 (*Linguistic Sciences*), and 汉语学报 (*Chinese Linguistics*).

Bibliometric data of Chinese publications were retrieved from the CSSCI online database. The data of all the articles between 2000 and 2018 in the above journals were downloaded. The only exception is 语言研究 (*Studies in Language and Linguistics*) in which the data in 2010 and 2011 were missing in the database. The last access date was September 14, 2020 and a total of 9513 articles were obtained.

Bibliometric data of English publications were obtained from the Web of Science (WoS) database. Articles were searched by the several criteria: listed in SSCI, published between 2000 to 202-, fall into the category of "Linguistics" or "Language linguistics",

and contain the topic of “Chinese” or “Mandarin”. The last access date was September 14, 2020 and a total of 4574 articles were obtained.

4.2 Tool

To achieve the best analysis results possible, the study used a powerful tool in bibliometric studies, called CiteSpace II (Chen 2006).

CiteSpace II is a Java application that has been used widely for bibliometric analysis in academia. It boasts three powerful features. First, it can reveal both the intellectual base and research fronts in a field, producing results that are consistent with the opinions of domain experts. Second, it provides simplistic and elegant visualization with the purpose of changing how the users view the world. Third, it is compatible with various sources of data in different languages, including Web of Science and the CSSCI online database.

5. Results

5.1 Important works

CiteSpace II uses a measure called “between-centrality” to find pivotal points in the network of academic papers. In the software’s algorithm, nodes with high between-centrality often appear at the intersection of different clusters, indicting their crucial role in connecting the studies (Chen 2006).

In the current study, the bibliometric data of the publications were imported into CiteSpace II and the between-centrality scores were automatically calculated. The papers were then ranked by between-centrality scores and the top ten were selected as the intellectual base. The original data contained the between-centrality score, year of publication and references of the papers. For clarity of presentation, the between-centrality scores were replaced by the rank and the references were reduced to the title of the works. In addition, the author classified the works into related fields of inquiry.

As can be seen in Table 1, the Chinese publications are mostly concerned with word and sentence constructions, falling into the field of syntax and morphology. There are also works in linguistics theories about subjectification and register. The average year of publication is 2005. Another thing worth mentioning is that among the ten papers selected, there are four papers written by one scholar and another two written by a second scholar.

Table 1.

Important works in Chinese publications

Rank	Year of publication	Title	Related field
1	2001	语言的“主观性”和“主观化” [The "subjectivity" and "subjectivization" of language]	cognitive grammar

2	2000	论“把”字句的句式语义 [On the Syntactic Meaning of "Ba" Sentence]	syntax
3	1995	有界”与“无界 [On "Bounded" and "unbounded"]	syntax
4	2009	我看汉语的词类 [My view on Chinese parts of speech]	syntax
5	1999	现代汉语的双及物结构式 [The double transitive structure of modern Chinese]	syntax
6	2010	论语体的机制及其语法属性 [On the mechanism and grammatical attributes of registers]	other
7	2012	“零句”和“流水句” ["Zero sentences" and "flow sentences"]	syntax
8	2011	语言库藏类型学构想 [Conception of Inventory Typology]	language typology
9	2009	“了2”的行，知，言三域 [The three domains of behavior, knowledge and speech of le2]	syntax
10	2007	词汇化与话语标记的形成 [Lexicalization and the formation of discourse markers]	morphology-syntax

In Table 2, the topics of English publications cover syntax, Chinese words and characters as well as relative clauses. Some papers do not even bear any linguistic content in their title. Statistics and psycholinguistics are strongly involved. In addition, the average year of publication is about 2008. Moreover, there was one scholar who contributed two papers.

Table 2.
Important works in English publications

Rank	Year of publication	Title	Related fields
1	2009	The Syntax of Chinese	syntax
2	2008	Analyzing linguistic data. A practical introduction to statistics	statistics
3	2008	Mixed-effects modeling with crossed random effects for subjects and items	statistics
4	2003	Essays on the representational and derivational nature of grammar: The diversity of wh-constructions	syntax

5	2005	Neuroanatomical correlates of phonological processing of Chinese characters and alphabetic words: A meta-analysis	psycholinguistics
6	2013	Random effects structure for confirmatory hypothesis testing: Keep it maximal	statistics
7	2011	Thirty Years and Counting: Finding Meaning in the N400 Component of the Event-Related Brain Potential (ERP)	psycholinguistics
8	2008	Perceptual adaptation to non-native speech	psycholinguistics
9	2002	Processing Subject and Object Relative Clauses: Evidence from Eye Movements	psycholinguistics
10	2010	SUBTLEX-CH: Chinese Word and Character Frequencies Based on Film Subtitles	corpus linguistics

5.2 Hot topics

Hot topics are identified with cluster analysis. After the bibliometric data were imported, CiteSpace II analyzed the co-citation relation. If two papers cite the same paper, it suggests that these two papers are relevant in research topics. Based on the co-citation analysis, CiteSpace II created a co-citation network in which each paper is represented as a node in the space. Based on the cosine distance, the nodes can be grouped with neighbors and form a cluster. Thus, the cluster analysis can inform us of the bigger picture.

For simplicity, the number of clusters was reduced to ten. The labels of the clusters were set to be the keywords that each author provided for his or her article. As we can see from Figure 1, the clusters in Chinese publications tend to revolve around morphology and syntax (#0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6), with other topics interspersed such as typology (#2), dialect (#7), lexicography (#8), and phonology-morphology (#9). The topics in English publication is more scattered, covering phonetics (#0), morphology-syntax (#1), neurolinguistics (#4, 6), bilingualism and language contact (#3, 8), words and morphology (#5, 7), pragmatics (#9), and Other (#2).

5.3 Research trend

The research trend was extracted by the timeline visualization on top of the cluster analysis. The visualization shows the ebb and flow of each topic in the course of time.

Speaking of the Chinese publications, grammar is always a high priority. However, conventional research on grammar seems to give way to interactive construction grammar (#4). This topic, though newly appeared, contained a dense co-

citation network. It is predicted that interactive construction grammar will be an important topic in Chinese publications subsequently. Studies on mighty category (#2) are also on the rise. It is worth noting that both the mighty category and interactive construction grammar are theoretical constructs done by Chinese scholars. Another advance is the compilation and proofreading of dictionary and databases (#8). It may also play a role in Chinese publications.

In the English publications, attention to language impairment (#6), kanji (#7), and pidgin (#8) was diverted to lexical tone (#0), classifier (#1), politeness (#9), and identity (#2). More recently, there are a high volume of publications on bilingual education (#3), neurolinguistics (#4), and morphological awareness (#5). The citation of the R programming language is also present in the co-citation network, suggesting a heavy reliance on statistics by scholars. It can be expected that the English publications on Chinese linguistics will attach more importance to bilingualism, neurolinguistics experiments, and statistical analysis.

Figure 1.
Timeline analysis

6. Discussion

Based on the findings in the previous section, we can now turn to the research questions raised in the beginning of the paper.

Regarding the important works in Chinese linguistics, ten pivotal papers in Chinese publications and English publications were identified, with the help of the betweenness centrality measure in CiteSpace II. The important works in Chinese publications discuss fundamental morphological and syntactic phenomena in Chinese such as parts of speech, *ba* construction, and *le*. This is consistent with Zhou (2009) who found most influential works on linguistics written in Chinese are related to grammar. There are also two new theoretical constructs, namely, inventory typology and the mechanism of register. The English publications, however, are highly influenced by works on methodological issues such as statistics and psychological experiments.

The topics in Chinese linguistics are correlated with the important works. In the Chinese publications, a great emphasis is placed on grammar issues. In comparison, the topics in English publications are quite diverse, encompassing different disciplines.

In terms of research trend, the attention in the Chinese publications is shifted to a new theory: interactive construction grammar. It is predicted that more works will be published under the guidance of this theory. The English publications will get closer to bilingualism and neurolinguistics in the future.

Finally, a comparison between the Chinese publications and English publications shows a divergence in the research agenda. Despite the common interest in Chinese linguistics, there was little overlap in research topics and research trend between Chinese publications and English publications in general. While the Chinese publications focus on grammar, the English publications are more interested in cross-disciplinary research. This need not to be a bad thing as there is always more than one way to do linguistics. However, the divergence may be at risk of being an insulation, as Lee (2000) worried. In any case, it will be beneficial for the two traditions to compare notes and learn from each other.

It is obvious from the bibliometric study that the Chinese publications discuss very little about multilingualism and cross-disciplinary studies involving psychology, computer science, etc. This is exactly what Wang (2006) attributed as the reasons for the stagnance in traditional Chinese linguistics. Liu (2018) also advocated employing more scientific methods in linguistic research to gain international recognition of Chinese linguistics.

In this bibliometric study, we can still see some optimistic signs. Construction grammar is now a popular topic in Chinese publications, suggesting that the Chinese linguists are embracing the up-to-dated theory. Moreover, we find that the original or modified theoretical works began to appear in Chinese publications, such as the prosody grammar and interactive construction grammar. This is encouraging because it is widely acknowledged that the indigenous tradition in Chinese linguistics is not good at developing theories (Lu 1999; Ma 2004; Mai 2006). We may end with a positive note here and hope there will be more Chinese linguists who bridge the two traditions, just as the prominent linguist Wang Li himself had done and envisioned.

7. Conclusion

The current paper investigated important articles, hot topics, and research trend in Chinese linguistics using bibliometric analysis of both Chinese publications and English publications. It is found that Chinese publications tend to focus on morphology and syntax. In the future, the interactive construction grammar will be popular. On the other hand, the English publications are more interested in psycholinguistic and quantitative issues. It is expected that bilingualism and psycholinguistics will be in a favorable position. The empirical evidence shows that the Chinese publications and Western publications can be quite divergent, which is consistent with the opinions of the domain

experts. It is hoped that more cross-disciplinary and cross-linguistic studies can be seen in the Chinese publications.

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Estimating Cue Strengths in Child Chinese Input and Output: A Competition Model Approach to Corpus Data

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This study investigates how three devices that signal simple transitive actions—word order, animacy, and grammatical morphology—are used in child language, including both input (child-directed speech) and output (children’s utterances). By analyzing Chinese corpus data of naturalistic speech and using Bates and MacWhinney’s (1989) competition model as a framework, we find animacy to be the most important information in both input and output, followed by word order, and then by grammatical morphology. Considering the interaction of multiple cues (coalition and competition) confirms the importance of the animacy cue, but also shows that animacy and word order redundantly cue transitive relations.

1. Introduction

This study investigates how three devices that express transitive relations—word order, animacy, and grammatical morphology—are used in the input children receive and the output they produce. We analyzed (Mandarin) Chinese corpus data of child-directed speech and children’s utterances, adopting the framework of Bates and MacWhinney’s (1989) competition model. In the following subsections, we will briefly explain the competition model and review previous literature on Chinese within this framework before we present our data, analysis, and findings.

1.1. The competition model

The competition model proposed by Bates and MacWhinney (1989) is a framework that offers a functional and comprehensive approach to language learning and processing. In this model, language acquisition is defined as a process of acquiring the mappings between surface forms, called cues, and their functions and meanings. Examples of cues for simple transitive sentences (involving two NPs) are word order, grammatical morphology (e.g., case marking, subject-verb agreement), and animacy. Language learning is driven by the information values, or strengths, of these cues. The order of importance of cues, however, differs depending on languages; language learning therefore requires learning what cues are most useful in that language. For example, in a language with rigid word order like English, word order provides crucial information about transitive relations and has proved to be the most important cue for both adults and children (Bates et al. 1982, 1984). In a language with rich grammatical morphology such

as Italian, grammatical morphology tends to be the most important cue for adults (Bates et al. 1982). For Italian-acquiring children under 7, however, animacy is the most important cue, suggesting that the importance of cues likely differs across populations (Bates et al. 1984). Animacy serves as important semantic information denoting transitivity because transitive actions typically involve an animate agent and an inanimate patient. The major predictor of cue strengths in language acquisition is (overall) cue validity, which is calculated as the product of cue availability—how often the cue is present in a context that requires it—and cue reliability—how often the cue leads to the correct interpretation when one relies on it (Kempe & MacWhinney 1998; Sasaki 2006). Cues do not always act alone. Another important notion in this framework is conflict validity, which measures how often a certain cue wins in a context in which multiple cues conflict. It is also very common for cues and functions to have one-to-many mappings. Cue coalition evaluates such overlapping contexts.

1.2. Cues in Chinese

Establishing transitive relations in Chinese can be challenging. While the canonical word order is SVO, Chinese allows null arguments as shown in (1) as well as relatively free word order, as shown in (2) through (5).

- (1) — kàn-dào — le.
 see-reach PFV¹
 ‘(Someone) saw (something).’ (Huang et al. 2014, gloss modified)
- (2) Zhāngsān mài le yì běn shū. (SVO)
 Zhangsan sell PFV one CLF book
 ‘Zhangsan sold a book.’ (Li et al. 1992:212, (1), gloss added)
- (3) Shū Zhāngsān mài le. (OSV)
 book Zhangsan sell PFV (Li et al. 1992:212, (2), gloss added)
- (4) Zhāngsān shū mài le. (SOV)
 Zhangsan book sell PFV (Li et al. 1992:212, (3), gloss added)
- (5) Mài le shū Zhāngsān. (VOS)
 sell PFV book Zhangsan (Li et al. 1992:212, (4), gloss added)

¹ List of abbreviations: BA = object marker *ba*; BEI = passive marker *bei*; MOD = modality marker; SFP = sentence final particle. Other abbreviations follow the Leipzig Glossing Rules: <https://www.eva.mpg.de/lingua/pdf/Glossing-Rules.pdf>.

In addition, Chinese does not have a large inventory of inflectional affixes or a rich verbal morphology, although there are some markers that indicate transitive relations in sentences following a noncanonical word order. In some SOV sentences, the preverbal object is preceded by the object marker *ba*, as shown in (6).

- (6) Zhāngsān bǎ shū mài le.
Zhangsan BA book sell PFV (Li et al. 1992:212, (3), gloss added)

The passive marker *bei* is another important signal of verb transitivity. As shown in the example in (7), BEI-constructions also display noncanonical word order, in which both the sentential subject and the BEI-preceded agent occur preverbally.

- (7) Tā bèi jiějiě mà le.
he BEI elder.sister scold PFV
'He was scolded by his older sister.' (Li & Thompson 1989:492)

Miao (1981) and Liu et al. (1992) compared animacy and word order in Chinese, and reported that animacy is more important than word order in adult native speakers' sentence interpretation. Li et al. (1992, 1993) took BA and BEI into consideration as well, and found that the cue strength hierarchy was BEI > animacy > word order > BA.

To date, however, studies that investigate child Chinese are scarce, and it is not clear how the cue strengths are ordered. In one study on Cantonese, Chan et al. (2009) conducted an act-out experiment and showed that children aged 2;6, 3;6, and 4;6 understood transitive sentences best when word order and animacy redundantly mark transitivity, and children at 3;6 and older relied more on word order than animacy when the two cues are in conflict.

In addition, while the competition model encompasses both comprehension and production, previous studies on Chinese have focused on cue ordering only in sentence interpretation. In fact, many of the competition model studies use comprehension experiments to measure cue strengths, and only a handful have focused on production. Among these, Kempe and MacWhinney's (1998) study proposed a way to predict cue strengths in child-directed speech based on corpus data. Their method was adapted to Japanese by Tanaka and Shirai (2014), who used corpus data to estimate cue strengths in both child-directed speech and children's utterances.

This study therefore investigates the order of cue importance in child Chinese. We estimated the strengths of word order, animacy, BA, and BEI in both input (child-directed speech) and output (children's utterances) extracted from a corpus.

2. Data

The spoken data analyzed in this study were retrieved from the Taiwan Corpus of Child Mandarin (TCCM; Cheung et al. 2011) in CHILDES (MacWhinney 2000), which contains files from 10 children. We extracted utterances from seven of them: CHENG, CHOU, CHW, WANG, WU, WUYS, and XU. We coded and analyzed 2,298 utterances produced by adult speakers and 1,221 utterances by children, with the results reported below.

3. Results

We adapted the coding method used by Kempe and MacWhinney (1998) and Tanaka and Shirai (2014) to fit the structure of Chinese, which we explain in the following subsections using actual data from the TCCM.

3.1. Word order

We considered the word order cue to be available when two NPs were present in a sentence, as shown in (8).

- (8) Word order cue available
 Wǒ bú huì dǎ nǐ.
 I NEG MOD hit you
 ‘I am not going to hit you.’ (CHW, CHILD 3;6)

This is because it is not possible to determine word order in a sentence featuring only one argument NP or with both argument NPs omitted. In such a context, as shown in (9), the word order cue was coded as unavailable.

- (9) Word order cue unavailable
 Wán zhè ge!
 play this CLF
 ‘Play with this!’ (CHENG, CHILD 3;10)

The availability of the word order cue was therefore calculated as the number of sentences with two argument NPs divided by the total number of analyzed sentences.

Among the sentences in which the word order cue was available, we considered it to be reliable only in those displaying the canonical SVO word order, as in (10).

- (10) Word order cue available and reliable (=8)
 Wǒ bú huì dǎ nǐ.
 I NEG MOD hit you
 ‘I am not going to hit you.’ (CHW, CHILD 3;6)

The cue was available but unreliable when the word order was noncanonical, as in (11), which follows SOV word order.

- (11) Word order cue available but unreliable
 Nǐ zěnmē bǎ chēzǐ nòng-dào le?
 you how BA car make-fall PFV
 ‘Why did you drop the car?’ (CHW, ADULT)

The reliability of the word order cue was calculated as the number of SVO sentences divided by the number of sentences with two NPs.

The overall validity of the word order cue was then calculated as the product of availability and reliability. Table 1 presents the word order cue’s availability, reliability, and validity in the input and in the output.

	Input (child-directed speech)		Output (children’s production)	
Cue availability	1,172	.509	522	.428
Cue reliability	1,125	.960	500	.958
Cue validity		.488		.410

TABLE 1. Availability, reliability, and validity of word order as a cue in input and output.

As shown in Table 1, the word order cue’s availability in input and output was .509 and .428, respectively. This means that about half of the sentences did not feature two arguments. Children tended to omit either subject or object, or both, in their production. Note that when sentences had two overt NPs, they typically followed the canonical SVO word order. Thus, word order was highly reliable in both input (.960) and output (.958). Due to its low availability, however, the validity of the word order cue was relatively low (input: .488, output: .410). The results for input and output are very similar, with only minor differences with respect to cue availability and validity, which were slightly lower in output than in input.

3.2. Animacy

The animacy cue was estimated based on an animacy contrast between the two NPs. We considered the cue to be available when one of the NPs was animate and the other was inanimate, as shown in (12). In the following examples, inanimate NPs are underlined.

- (12) Animacy cue available
 Āpó yě huì tī qiúqiú
 grandma too MOD kick ball
 ‘Grandma can kick the ball too.’ (WANG, CHILD 2;6)

The animacy cue was coded as unavailable when both NPs were equal with respect to animacy, that is, both animate or both inanimate. This is because the lack of contrast does not offer an opportunity to establish transitive relations based on animacy alone. In example (13), both NPs are animate.

- (13) Animacy cue unavailable
 Ránhòu nǐ kàn tā ó!
 then you look him SFP
 ‘Then, (you) look at him!’ (CHENG, ADULT)

When there was a contrast in animacy, the animacy cue was reliable only if the subject was animate and the object inanimate, as in (12), repeated here as (14), as these are the typical animacy values assigned to these two arguments.

- (14) Animacy cue available and reliable (=12)
 Āpó yě huì tī qiúqiú.
 grandma too MOD kick ball
 ‘Grandma can kick the ball too.’ (WANG, CHILD 2;6)

In sentences like (15), the animacy cue was coded as unreliable because they involve an inanimate subject and an animate object, hence interpreting the sentence based on animacy information alone would lead to the wrong interpretation.

- (15) Animacy cue available but unreliable
 Dùzi zhǎng le chóng.
 belly grow PFV bug
 ‘The belly grew bugs.’ (WU, CHILD 1;7)

Overall cue validity was again calculated as the product of availability and reliability. Table 2 shows the availability, reliability, and validity of the animacy cue.

	Input (child-directed speech)		Output (children’s production)	
Cue availability	1764	.774	923	.756
Cue reliability	1741	.987	911	.987
Cue validity		.764		.746

TABLE 2. Availability, reliability, and validity of animacy as a cue in input and output.

Most sentences displayed an animacy contrast between the two argument NPs, thus leading to relatively high cue availability (input: .774, output: .756). Moreover, in both

input and output, subjects were usually animate and objects inanimate, which means that this cue was highly reliable (input: .987, output: .987). Due to the widespread availability and the very high reliability, the animacy contrast proved to be a very strong cue with high validity (input: .764, output: .746). As for word order, the results for output and input are very similar.

3.3. BA and BEI

The object marker BA was considered available when present in a sentence and reliable when followed by an overt object (i.e., patient), as in (16).

- (16) BA cue available and reliable (=11)
 Nǐ zěnmē bǎ chēzǐ nòng-dào le?
 you how BA car make-fall PFV
 ‘Why did you drop the car?’ (CHW, ADULT)

BA was not considered a reliable cue when it was not followed by an overt object or when the sentence was ill-formed, which was the case in some of the children’s utterances. In example (17), the child intended to say ‘kill him’ but used two objects in the same sentence.

- (17) Cue available but unreliable
 Yào bǎ tā dǎ-sǐ yí gè rén.
 make BA him hit-dead one CLF person
 ‘Kill him.’ (CHW, CHILD 3;6)

Similarly, the passive marker BEI, as a cue, was considered available when present in a sentence, and reliable when followed by an overt NP representing the agent, as shown in (18).

- (18) Cue available and reliable
 Nǐ nǎ ge péngyǒu bèi nǐ dǎ?
 you which CLF friend BEI you hit
 ‘Which friend of yours has been beaten by you?’ (CHW, ADULT)

While the same criteria as those for BA would have applied, no sentences were coded as unreliable because all BEI sentences were well-formed and always featured an overt agent NP following BEI.

The results for BA and BEI markers are summarized in Table 3.

	Input (child-directed speech)				Output (children's production)			
	BA		BEI		BA		BEI	
Cue availability	94	.041	31	.014	33	.027	10	.008
Cue reliability	94	1.000	31	1.000	29	.879	10	1.000
Cue validity	.041		.014		.024		.008	

TABLE 3. Availability, reliability, and validity of BA and BEI as cues in input and output.

Table 3 shows that, despite being highly reliable, both BA and BEI were by far the least available cues in both input and output, which obviously influenced their overall validity. Again, the output seems to closely mirror the input.

3.4. Cue coalitions and conflicts

So far, we have only looked at cues individually. As mentioned in §1.1, however, multiple cues interact with each other, and one-to-many mappings between cues and functions are common. In example (19), which again repeats the example in (12) and (14), animacy and word order both support the interpretation that grandma is the subject, and the ball is the object—there is an animate subject and inanimate object and the word order is SVO. This is an example of cue coalition.

- (19) Coalition of animacy and word order cues
 Āpó yě huì tī qiúqiú. (=12, 14)
 grandma too MOD kick ball
 ‘Grandma can kick the ball too.’ (WANG, CHILD 2;6)

In example (20), on the other hand, the animacy and word order cues conflict with each other.

- (20) Conflict between animacy and word order cues
Qiúqiú péi nǐ.
 ball accompany you
 ‘The balloon keeps you company.’ (CHENG, CHILD 3;1)

The correct interpretation in (20) is ‘the balloon keeps (or will keep) you company’ as indicated in the translation. Based on this interpretation, the word order cue is available and reliable, as indicated by the SVO word order. The animacy cue is available as well because there is an animacy contrast; however, crucially, the subject *qiúqiú* ‘balloon’ is inanimate and the object *nǐ* ‘you,’ referring to the child’s caretaker, is animate, thus making the cue unreliable. That is, an interpretation of the sentence based solely on animacy leads to the opposite interpretation. These two cues disagree with each other, and, in this case, word order wins out.

These two examples show clearly that word order is available and reliable in both utterances, but in two very different contexts, highlighting the importance of looking at how multiple cues interact with each other. We therefore evaluated whether each sentence contained multiple (available and) reliable cues or only a single reliable cue. Table 4 shows the breakdown of sentences into those in which animacy and word order were both reliable, those in which animacy was the only reliable cue, and those in which word order was the only reliable cue. We excluded BA and BEI cues because their validity was extremely low, therefore negligible.

	Input		Output	
Animacy and word order both reliable	669	.291	334	.274
Animacy only reliable	1,072	.467	577	.473
Word order only reliable	374	.163	149	.122

TABLE 4. Cue reliability: Only animacy, only word order, or both animacy and word order.

Table 4 reveals that in about one third of the sentences, animacy and word order redundantly mark transitive actions. Animacy was, however, the sole reliable cue in nearly half of the sentences. This indicates that speakers were inclined to encode transitive events mostly by means of animacy contrast, which, again, hints at the importance of this cue in Chinese.

4. Discussion

Based on the results of the overall validity of word order, animacy, and BA and BEI cues, we postulate, for both the input and the output, the following cue strength hierarchy: animacy > word order > BA/BEI. The results of the cue coalition calculations also suggest that animacy is a very important cue in Chinese. This finding supports the findings of Miao (1981) and Liu et al. (1992), who placed animacy in a higher position than word order in their cue hierarchy.

That said, animacy as a cue was also used quite frequently in combination with word order, redundantly marking the same interpretation. This is reminiscent of Chan et al.'s (2009) act-out results in Cantonese and Tanaka and Shirai's (2014) corpus results in Japanese.

BA and BEI were both very reliable but also used very sparingly, as also noted by Li et al. (1992), making their overall validity extremely low. Out of the two, children occasionally used BA incorrectly, but never made a mistake with BEI. The two forms have the same reliability in the input, while the overall validity is slightly higher for BA; therefore, it is unclear why children showed better accuracy with BEI. The lower accuracy in the use of BA observed in the output, however, is not necessarily a sign of

late(r) acquisition; on the contrary, BA was used slightly more frequently, which could mean that the children were more familiar with BA than with BEI. Research on the acquisition of these two structures has in fact observed that BA appears in children's speech earlier (around age 2) than BEI (around age 3), but neither form is fully acquired by age 5 (Erbaugh 1982; Yang 2015). This observation finds some support in our data too, as the few instances of BEI were all produced by the two oldest children of the seven. Lastly, our data show that BA and BEI are infrequently used in input too, and this, along with the objective structural complexity they entail, may be a factor contributing to their generally late acquisition.

Our findings are based on naturalistic speech, and while the TCCM provided us with a unique opportunity to investigate both children's input and output, this methodology also has limitations. For example, the striking similarity between cue validity patterns found in input and output suggests that children's use of the three cues mirrors what they hear in the input. This observation, however, does not explain children's developmental process—that is, how they learn to use the cues this way in their output based on the input they hear. An experimental investigation of comprehension and (real-time) production is a necessary step to be taken in the future in order to address such questions and build further understanding of children's acquisition of transitive sentences in Chinese.

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